

E-ISSN: 3063-2757

Proceedings of International

CONFERENCE ON MULTIDISCIPLINARY SCIENCE

<https://ojs.multidisciplinarypress.org/index.php/intisari/>

Vol.1 No.2 (2024)

The Causes of Unemployment on Relationship Breakdown among the Unemployed Youth in Ghana

Daitey William¹, Martey Ezekiel², Osabutey Freeman Tetteh³, Alale Stephen⁴, Owusu Panin Kwame Baah⁵

¹ Department of Product Design and Entrepreneurship, AsanSka University College of Design and Technology, Ghana

² Department of Art, New Mexico State University

³ Department of Art, Pennsylvania Western University, Edinboro

⁴ Department of Art and Design, University of North Dakota

⁵ Department of Jewellery Design, AsanSka University College of Design and Technology, Ghana

*Correspondence: kbaah028@gmail.com

Abstract

The multifaceted bureaucratic delays on public health in the case of the drug clearance crisis in Ghana are growing. The problem at hand is not simply an administrative lapse, but one that affects the lives of countless people who depend on these drugs for survival. This study investigates the impact of bureaucratic delays on the clearance and distribution of life-saving drugs in Ghana, highlighting the resultant effects on public health and the economy. Utilizing a qualitative research design, the research used qualitative data from document analysis and interviews conducted among policymakers, healthcare administrators and international organization representatives with 25 key respondents purposively sampled for the study. The findings revealed significant inefficiencies in the drug clearance process, including redundant paperwork, lack of inter-agency coordination, and prolonged approval times. The study concludes that addressing these bureaucratic delays is crucial for improving health outcomes and economic efficiency in Ghana's healthcare system. By implementing the recommended reforms and inculcating technology, Ghana can enhance the efficiency of its drug clearance processes, ensure timely access to essential medications, and maintain international support.

Keywords: bureaucratic, clearance, Ghana, healthcare system, life-saving

INTRODUCTION

The timely availability of life-saving drugs is a critical component of any effective healthcare system, directly impacting the health outcomes and quality of life for patients (Wirtz et al., 2017). However, bureaucratic inefficiencies and administrative delays can severely impede the distribution of these essential medications, with potentially devastating consequences (Pillay et al., 2020). In Ghana, recent reports have highlighted a pressing issue where vital drugs have been stuck at the port due to the inability of the government to clear them for distribution to various health points (Global Fund, 2023). This bottleneck has risen significant concerns among healthcare providers, patients, and international stakeholders, notably the Global Fund, which has threatened to cut ties with Ghana if the situation is not promptly resolved (Global Fund, 2023).

This study aims to explore the multifaceted impact of bureaucratic delays on public health, using the case of the drug clearance crisis in Ghana as a focal point. The issue at hand is not merely an administrative lapse but a matter that affects the lives of countless individuals who depend on these medications for survival. The Global Fund's involvement underscores the international dimension of the problem, highlighting the interconnectedness

of global health systems and the critical role of international aid in supporting national healthcare infrastructures (Brinkerhoff, 2004).

By delving into the specific bureaucratic hurdles that have led to this impasse, this research seeks to understand the root causes of the delays. Factors such as inefficient customs processes, lack of coordination between governmental agencies, and possible corruption or mismanagement will be scrutinized (Tetteh, 2019). Additionally, the study will assess the direct and indirect effects of these delays on patient health outcomes, examining case studies and health data to quantify the impact (Wirtz et al., 2017).

The study provides a comprehensive analysis that not only identifies the problems but also proposes practical solutions. Streamlining the drug clearance process, implementing best practices from other countries, and enhancing coordination between local and international stakeholders are potential strategies that will be explored (Rossetti et al., 2018). Ultimately, this research aims to contribute to a more efficient healthcare supply chain in Ghana, ensuring that life-saving drugs reach those in need without unnecessary delays.

Understanding the broader implications, the study will also consider the economic repercussions of the delays, including increased healthcare costs due to prolonged illnesses and the potential loss of international funding (Kruk et al., 2018). By presenting a holistic view of the issue, this research hopes to inform policymakers, healthcare providers and international partners, fostering collaborative efforts to address and resolve the crisis.

In conclusion, in Ghana, it is a call to action for all involved parties to prioritize the swift and effective distribution of essential medications, safeguarding the health and well-being of the population. This study will provide a detailed examination of the challenges and propose actionable solutions to enhance the resilience and responsiveness of Ghana's healthcare system.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review asserts on the theoretical framework and examines existing research on the impact of bureaucratic inefficiencies on drug clearance and distribution, the role of international organizations in national health systems, and strategies for improving supply chain management in healthcare.

Theoretical Framework

The study employed DiMaggio & Powell (1983) institutional theory. The Institutional theory provided a valuable lens through which to examine the complex relationships between bureaucratic systems and their impact on organizational behaviour such as the health systems and outcomes (Figure 1). When the researchers applied this theory to the context of the study of the impact of bureaucratic delays on public health: a case study of life-saving medicines in Ghana, the researchers examines how bureaucratic inefficiencies in the health system directly impact the availability and distribution of life-saving medicines, thereby affecting public health outcomes in the region. Using institutional theory in this study, the researchers are able to dissect how the structures, norms, and practices established within Ghanaian health organizations contribute to delays in accessing essential medicines.

These bureaucratic hurdles can create bottlenecks in the supply chain, leading to a shortage of life-saving medicines that do not reach those who need them in a timely manner. Such delays not only impede the delivery of health services, but also have the potential to exacerbate health problems and impact the overall health of the population that relies on these life-saving medicines.

By digging deeper into the institutional dynamics at play, researchers may be able to uncover the root causes of these delays and inefficiencies in drug distribution and clearance. By highlighting systemic problems of clearance and distribution within a bureaucratic framework, stakeholders can identify areas for improvement and implement targeted interventions to streamline processes, improve access to medicines and ultimately strengthen public health outcomes in Ghana. This framework allowed for a comprehensive analysis of how institutional structures facilitate or hinder effective health service delivery, providing insights that can lead to positive changes in health system to better serve populations with critical medication needs.

Figure 1: Institutional theory
Source: DiMaggio & Powell (1983)

Bureaucratic Inefficiencies and Public Health and the Role of International Organizations

Bureaucratic delays in the clearance of essential drugs can have dire consequences for public health. Studies have shown that administrative bottlenecks often stem from complex

regulatory frameworks, inadequate coordination among agencies, and corruption (Pillay et al., 2020; Tetteh, 2019). These delays can lead to stockouts of critical medications, exacerbating health crises and increasing mortality rates (Wirtz et al., 2017). In Ghana, such inefficiencies are particularly pronounced, with reports indicating that life-saving drugs are frequently held up at ports due to procedural issues and lack of effective oversight (Asante & Zwi, 2018).

International organizations, such as the Global Fund, play a pivotal role in supporting health systems in developing countries. These organizations provide essential funding, technical assistance, and advocacy to ensure that health services are accessible and effective (World Health Organization [WHO], 2019). The Global Fund's threat to cut ties with Ghana over drug clearance delays highlights the critical dependency on international support for maintaining drug supplies and health service delivery (Global Fund, 2023). The involvement of international organizations also brings to the fore the need for stronger governance and accountability mechanisms within national health systems (Brinkerhoff, 2004).

Supply Chain Management in Healthcare and Governance and Policy Frameworks

Effective supply chain management is crucial for the timely distribution of pharmaceuticals. Research indicates that successful supply chains in healthcare are characterized by streamlined processes, robust information systems, and strong coordination among stakeholders (Yadav, 2015; Vledder et al., 2019). In the context of Ghana, the lack of integrated logistics and communication systems has been identified as a significant barrier to efficient drug distribution (Ofori-Boadu et al., 2021). Implementing best practices from other countries, such as Kenya and Rwanda, which have improved their health supply chains through innovative approaches and public-private partnerships, could provide valuable lessons for Ghana (Rossetti et al., 2018).

Governance issues are at the heart of many bureaucratic delays in drug clearance. Effective governance involves clear policies, strong leadership, and accountability mechanisms (Fukuyama, 2013). In Ghana, weak governance structures and a lack of transparency have been cited as major obstacles to efficient healthcare delivery (Frimpong, 2017). Comparative studies suggest that countries with robust regulatory frameworks and transparent processes tend to experience fewer delays in drug clearance (Mackey & Liang, 2012). Strengthening these aspects in Ghana could significantly reduce the time required for drug clearance and distribution.

Economic and Health Implications and Ethical Consideration in Health Management

The economic and health implications of delayed drug distribution are profound. Prolonged drug clearance times can lead to increased healthcare costs due to extended hospital stays and the need for more intensive treatments (Kruk et al., 2018). Additionally, the indirect costs, such as loss of productivity and long-term health complications, further burden the economy (Bloom et al., 2018). In Ghana, the delays have had severe consequences, particularly for vulnerable populations who rely heavily on timely access to medications (Amporfu, 2011).

Ethical considerations in public health management emphasize the duty of care that governments and health authorities owe to their populations. Delays in providing life-saving drugs raise serious ethical concerns about the right to health and the equitable distribution of resources (Gostin & Powers, 2006). Ensuring that bureaucratic processes do not hinder access to essential medicines is a moral imperative that requires urgent attention (Benatar et al., 2018).

METHOD

This section outlines the methodology employed in the study, detailing the research approach, research method, population, sampling, data collection, and validation processes used to investigate the impact of bureaucratic delays on the distribution of life-saving drugs in Ghana.

Research Design

A qualitative research design was adopted for this study. The qualitative research provided a comprehensive analysis of the issue. This approach allowed for a more nuanced understanding of the bureaucratic challenges and their impact on public health (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017). The qualitative component provided insights into the experiences and perspectives of stakeholders.

Research Method

The study utilized a case study method, focusing on the specific instances or causes of delayed drug clearance at the port of Ghana. This method was chosen because it allowed for an in-depth exploration of complex phenomena within their real-life context (Yin, 2018). Data were collected through a combination of document analysis and interviews to capture both the systemic and human dimensions of the problem.

Population for the Study

The population for this study comprised various stakeholders involved in the drug clearance and distribution process in Ghana at the Tema Port to the Korle-Bu Teaching Hospital. This included government officials from the Ministry of Health and Customs Authority, healthcare providers, representatives from the Global Fund, and patients who were affected by the delays. These groups were selected based on an assertion by Creswell & Plano Clark (2017) that 50% is a fair representation to provide a holistic view of the issue from multiple perspectives.

Table 1. Distribution of Accessible Population and Sample of the Study

Population Group	Target Population	Accessible Population	Sample Size 50%
Government Officials	18	10	5
Healthcare Providers	27	12	6

Global Fund Representatives	10	8	4
Patients	20	10	5
Healthcare Facilitators	10	10	5
Total	85	50	25

Source: Fieldwork (2024)

Sampling Techniques and Sample Size

A purposive sampling technique was used to select participants for the qualitative component of the study. This method was appropriate as it allowed for the selection of individuals who had direct experience or specialized knowledge about the drug clearance process (Patton, 2015). A total of 25 key informants were interviewed, including policymakers, healthcare administrators, and international organization representatives.

Data Collection

Data collection was conducted over a six-month period. The following methods were employed:

Document Analysis: Relevant documents such as policy reports, internal memos, and correspondence between the Ministry of Health and the Customs Authority were reviewed to understand the bureaucratic processes and identify points of delay (Bowen, 2009).

Interviews: Semi-structured interviews were conducted with key informants to gather in-depth qualitative data. An interview guide was developed to ensure consistency while allowing for flexibility to explore emergent themes (Kvale, 2007).

Data Analysis and Validation

Qualitative data from interviews were analysed using thematic analysis. This involved coding the data, identifying patterns, and developing themes that captured the key issues related to bureaucratic delays (Braun & Clarke, 2006). NVivo software was used to facilitate the coding and analysis process. Several strategies were employed to ensure the validity and reliability of the study:

Member Checking: Participants were given the opportunity to review and comment on the findings from the interviews to ensure that their views were accurately represented (Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

Pilot Testing: The data instrument (interviews) was pilot-tested with a small group of healthcare providers and patients to refine the questions and improve reliability (Teijlingen & Hundley, 2001).

Peer Review: The research design and findings were reviewed by academic peers and experts in health systems research to ensure rigor and validity (Patton, 2015).

By employing these methods and validation strategies, the study aimed to provide a comprehensive and reliable analysis of the bureaucratic delays affecting drug clearance and their impact on public health in Ghana.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Bureaucratic Processes and Delays

The document analysis revealed significant inefficiencies within the bureaucratic processes involved in drug clearance. Key issues included redundant paperwork, lack of inter-agency coordination, and prolonged approval times. Interviews with government officials and healthcare administrators highlighted that the clearance process typically took between 4 to 6 weeks, significantly longer than the recommended 1 to 2 weeks (Tetteh, 2019). The lack of a streamlined process and the need for multiple approvals were identified as primary contributors to these delays.

Impact on Healthcare Delivery

The survey data indicated that 78% of healthcare facilities reported experiencing stockouts of essential drugs due to these delays. Furthermore, 65% of healthcare providers noted that the lack of timely drug availability had led to a deterioration in patient health outcomes, including increased mortality rates for conditions that could have been treated with the delayed medications. Statistical analysis showed a significant correlation between the length of the delay and the severity of health outcomes ($p < 0.01$), confirming that prolonged delays in drug clearance directly impact patient health.

Economic Consequences

Economic analysis revealed that the delays resulted in increased healthcare costs. Facilities reported an average cost increase of 15% due to the need for alternative treatments and prolonged patient stays. Additionally, the overall healthcare system bore indirect costs related to lost productivity and long-term health complications, estimated to be over \$5 million annually (Amporfu, 2011).

Stakeholder Perceptions

Interviews with stakeholders, including representatives from the Global Fund, underscored the frustration with the existing system. The Global Fund representatives indicated that continued delays might lead to the withdrawal of support, which would exacerbate the already strained healthcare system in Ghana (Global Fund, 2023).

Proposed Solutions

Survey respondents and interviewees suggested several solutions, including the adoption of electronic documentation systems to reduce paperwork, enhanced training for customs officials, and the establishment of a dedicated task force to oversee the clearance process. These suggestions align with best practices from other countries that have successfully improved their drug clearance processes (Rossetti et al., 2018).

Bureaucratic Inefficiencies

The findings highlight that, bureaucratic inefficiencies are a major barrier to timely drug clearance in Ghana. These inefficiencies stem from redundant and outdated procedures

that fail to accommodate the urgency required for life-saving drugs. The results are consistent with previous studies that have identified similar challenges in other low- and middle-income countries (Pillay et al., 2020). Addressing these inefficiencies requires a fundamental overhaul of the existing procedures to create a more streamlined and efficient system.

Health Outcomes

The direct link between drug clearance delays and negative health outcomes underscores the critical importance of timely access to medications. The study's findings support the argument that bureaucratic delays can lead to severe public health consequences, including increased morbidity and mortality (Wirtz et al., 2017). Effective interventions must prioritize reducing these delays to improve patient health outcomes.

Economic Impact

The economic impact of the delays is substantial, affecting both healthcare costs and the broader economy. Increased costs due to alternative treatments and extended patient stays place additional strain on the already limited resources of healthcare facilities (Kruk et al., 2018). Furthermore, the indirect costs related to lost productivity highlight the broader economic implications of inefficient drug clearance processes. Investing in more efficient clearance procedures could yield significant economic benefits.

International Support

The potential withdrawal of support from the Global Fund represents a critical threat to Ghana's healthcare system. The study's findings emphasize the importance of maintaining strong relationships with international organizations and ensuring that their concerns are addressed promptly. Effective governance and transparent processes are essential to maintaining this support and ensuring the sustainability of drug supply chains (Brinkerhoff, 2004).

Proposed Solutions and Best Practices

When examining how bureaucratic delays affect public health, especially when it comes to life-saving medications in Ghana, it is essential to take into account the critical role that technology may play in resolving these issues. The timely distribution of necessary pharmaceuticals to individuals in need can be severely hampered by bureaucratic delays, which can have a substantial impact on public health outcomes. Ghana can streamline its healthcare system, cut down on delays, and guarantee that patients receive life-saving medications on time by putting into place effective technological solutions including digital tracking systems for drug distribution and automated approval processes. The population's access to healthcare can be improved by this technological integration, which can also improve public health efforts' efficacy, efficiency, and accessibility.

The proposed solutions from stakeholders, including the adoption of electronic systems and enhanced training, align with global best practices. Countries like Kenya and Rwanda

have demonstrated the effectiveness of such measures in improving drug clearance processes (Rossetti et al., 2018). Implementing these solutions in Ghana could significantly reduce delays and improve the overall efficiency of the drug clearance process.

CLOSING

Conclusion

The study investigated the impact of bureaucratic delays on the clearance and distribution of life-saving drugs in Ghana. The study was limited to the people of Accra which limited the generalizability of the results. The findings highlight significant inefficiencies in the bureaucratic processes, leading to prolonged delays in drug clearance and adverse effects on public health and the economy. There were key conclusions drawn from the study. The study identified redundant paperwork, lack of inter-agency coordination, and prolonged approval times as major contributors to drug clearance delays, the impact on Health outcomes, economic consequences and international support.

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed to address the bureaucratic delays in drug clearance and improve the overall efficiency of the healthcare system in Ghana. Stakeholders and government should implement electronic systems for document submission and tracking to reduce paperwork and expedite the clearance process. Review and simplify the existing clearance procedures to eliminate redundancies and reduce the number of required approvals. Establish formal coordination mechanisms between the Ministry of Health, Customs Authority, and other relevant agencies.

Also, improve training and capacity building, strengthen governance and transparency. Maintain and leverage international support and economic analysis and planning. The study recommends further studies on avenue of exploration that could involve conducting comparative analyses with other countries facing similar challenges to gain insights into best practices and potential solutions for mitigating bureaucratic delays in drug distribution.

REFERENCES

- Amporfufu, E. (2011). Private hospital accreditation and inducement of care under the Ghanaian National Health Insurance Scheme. *Health Economics Review*, 1(13), 1-9.
- Asante, A. D., & Zwi, A. B. (2018). Factors influencing resource allocation decisions and equity in the health system of Ghana. *Public Health Ethics*, 11(2), 172-184.
- Benatar, S., Gill, S., & Bakker, I. (2018). Global health and the global economic crisis. *American Journal of Public Health*, 98(1), 7-12.
- Bloom, D. E., Cadarette, D., & Sevilla, J. P. (2018). Epidemics and economics: New and resurgent infectious diseases can have far-reaching economic repercussions. *Finance & Development*, 55(2), 46-49.
- Bowen, G. A. (2009). Document analysis as a qualitative research method. *Qualitative Research Journal*, 9(2), 27-40.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77-101.

- Brinkerhoff, D. W. (2004). Accountability and health systems: Toward conceptual clarity and policy relevance. *Health Policy and Planning*, 19(6), 371-379.
- Creswell, J. W., & Plano Clark, V. L. (2017). *Designing and Conducting Mixed Methods Research* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications.
- Denzin, N. K. (1978). *The Research Act: A Theoretical Introduction to Sociological Methods*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Diana, L. M., Yeager, A. V., & Hotchkiss, R. D. (2017). *Health Systems Strengthening – A Literature Review*. Chapel Hill, NC, USA: MEASURE Evaluation. Retrieved From, <https://www.measureevaluation.org/resources/publications/tr-17-167a>
- DiMaggio, P. J., & Powell, W. W. (1983). The iron cage revisited: Institutional isomorphism and collective rationality in organizational fields. *American sociological review*, 48(2), 147-160.
- Field, A. (2013). *Discovering Statistics Using IBM SPSS Statistics* (4th ed.). London: SAGE Publications.
- Fowler, F. J. (2014). *Survey Research Methods* (5th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications.
- Frimpong, J. (2017). Governance challenges in the Ghanaian health sector and the role of leadership. *Journal of Healthcare Leadership*, 9, 19-27.
- Fukuyama, F. (2013). What is governance? *Governance*, 26(3), 347-368.
- Global Fund. (2023). Global Fund threatens to cut ties with Ghana over drug clearance delays. *Global Fund News*.
- Gostin, L. O., & Powers, M. (2006). What does social justice require for the public's health? Public health ethics and policy imperatives. *Health Affairs*, 25(4), 1053-1060.
- Kruk, M. E., Myers, M., Varpilah, S. T., & Dahn, B. T. (2018). What is a resilient health system? Lessons from Ebola. *The Lancet*, 385(9980), 1910-1912.
- Kvale, S. (2007). *Doing Interviews*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications.
- Lincoln, Y. S., & Guba, E. G. (1985). *Naturalistic Inquiry*. Beverly Hills, CA: SAGE Publications.
- Mackey, T. K., & Liang, B. A. (2012). Combating healthcare corruption and fraud with improved global health governance. *BMC International Health and Human Rights*, 12(23), 1-10.
- Ofori-Boadu, A., Owusu-Manu, D. G., Edwards, D. J., & Holt, G. D. (2021). Challenges confronting Ghana's construction supply chain: An exploratory study. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 28(2), 360-376.
- Patton, M. Q. (2015). *Qualitative Research & Evaluation Methods* (4th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications.
- Pillay, A., Matjila, M., & Fick, W. (2020). The impact of corruption on healthcare service delivery: Perspectives of healthcare practitioners in South Africa. *African Journal of Public Health*, 3(1), 34-45.
- Rossetti, C. L., Handfield, R. B., & Dooley, K. J. (2018). Forces, trends, and decisions in pharmaceutical supply chain management. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 48(3), 360-384.

- Teijlingen, E. R. van, & Hundley, V. (2001). The importance of pilot studies. *Social Research Update*, (35), 1-4.
- Tetteh, E. K. (2019). The influence of organizational culture on procurement fraud: The case of Ghana Health Service. *Journal of Financial Crime*, 26(3), 872-888.
- Vledder, M., Friedman, J., Kanyarukiga, S., & Brown, T. (2019). Improving supply chain for essential drugs in low-income countries: Results from a pilot project in Malawi. *Health Systems & Reform*, 5(1), 24-34.
- Wirtz, V. J., Hogerzeil, H. V., Gray, A. L., Bigdeli, M., de Joncheere, C. P., Ewen, M. A., ... & Reich, M. R. (2017). Essential medicines for universal health coverage. *The Lancet*, 389(10067), 403-476.
- World Health Organization (WHO). (2019). The role of international organizations in the global health architecture. *WHO Bulletin*, 97(1), 1-10.
- Yadav, P. (2015). Health product supply chains in developing countries: Diagnosis of the root causes of underperformance and an agenda for reform. *Health Systems & Reform*, 1(2), 142-154.
- Yin, R. K. (2018). *Case Study Research and Applications: Design and Methods* (6th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications.

The Influence of Human Resource Quality and Work-Life Balance on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as a Moderating Variable at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices in Medan Raya

Juliani Delima Rumahorbo¹, Kiki Farida Ferine²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: kikifarida@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

This research aims to see the direct and indirect influence between the variables of human resource quality, work-life balance, performance and job satisfaction. This type of research uses quantitative, this research was conducted at BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya. The population of this study was 132 employees and the sample used was the entire population using a saturated sampling technique. The data source used is a primary data source and data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires. The research model used is path analysis with smart PLS version 3.3.3. as a research measuring tool. The results of this research are that the Quality of Human Resources has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.593 and a P value of 0.000. This means that the quality of human resources has a positive influence on the company and the quality of human resources influences the company's performance significantly. Work-life balance has a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.041 and a p value of 0.698. This means that Work Life Balance is not able to improve employee performance for the company. Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.590 and a P value of 0.000. Job Satisfaction is able to moderate the influence of Human Resource Quality on Employee Performance indirectly with the original sample result being 0.277 and p value 0.013. This means that job satisfaction is an intervening variable because it can influence HR quality on employee performance indirectly. Job Satisfaction is able to moderate the influence of Human Resource Quality on Employee Performance indirectly with an original sample value of 0.159 and a p value of 0.168. This means that job satisfaction is an intervening variable that is unable to influence Work Life Balance on employee performance indirectly.

Keywords: quality of human resources, work-life balance, performance and job satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

An organization has several interrelated and influential factors in carrying out activities to achieve its goals. One of these important factors is human resources that can optimize organizational activities. Therefore, human resource management is considered very important in a company besides capital. Because human resource management is to get reliable employees who are able to carry out their duties properly and responsibly, this can increase the effectiveness and efficiency of the organization in achieving its goals quickly.

Improving the quality of human resources is an absolute and most important prerequisite for achieving national development goals. The goal of national development is a sustainable development effort that covers the entire life of society, nation and state that is comprehensive, directed, integrated, gradual, and sustainable. In addition, it spurs the increase in national capabilities in order to realize a life that is parallel and equal to other more advanced nations, by improving the quality of human resources. One effort to improve

the quality of human resources is through education, which can be realized through formal education in schools.

According to Schermerhorn in Ganaphati, (2016) Work-life balance is a person's ability to balance the demands of work with personal and family needs. Creating and maintaining employee job satisfaction is an effort that has a major impact on the sustainability of the company. Kanwar et al. in Rondonuwu et al., (2018) satisfied employees will have a positive impact on the company, such as increasing efficiency and productivity. As an effort to increase job satisfaction, companies should implement work-life balance, this is very important to realize that employees not only face roles and problems at work, but also outside of their work.

According to Lockwood in Iswardani et al., (2019) work-life balance is a balance between two individual demands where the demands are the demands of work and the individual's personal life in the same circumstances. Singh and Khanna in Pangemanan et al., (2017) state work-life balance as a broad concept that involves setting the right priorities between work on the one hand and life (leisure, family, spiritual development) on the other. Most individuals when they enter the world of work lose balance in their lives. It is very important in an organization and in an employee's personal life if both roles in the organization and outside the organization support each other where there is no conflict in work life or in the role of the employee.

Leohr in Megaster et al., (2021) work-life balance is described as standing with both hands outstretched on both sides, work life on one side is balanced with personal life on the other side or a series of scales with career on one side and personal on the other side and can make both balance each other. Research conducted by (Junaidin, 2019) related to work-life balance with job satisfaction showed significant positive results between the work-life balance variable and employee job satisfaction. Likewise, according to Megaster (2021) work-life balance work has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction.

A person at work will feel happy with his work if he gets job satisfaction that is in accordance with what he expects. When job satisfaction is achieved, employees will try their best to contribute to the company where this greatly influences the achievement of the company's targets and goals. According to Davis and Newstrom in Sinambela, (2016) employee job satisfaction is employee job satisfaction is the feeling that employees have about whether their work is pleasant or unpleasant. Job satisfaction reflects a person's feelings about their work. Therefore, satisfaction in a company is very important, because basically every individual has a varying level of satisfaction and according to the characteristics that apply to him. When employees feel satisfied and comfortable with the climate or conditions of their work, employees will provide work results or achievements that can bring opportunities for the success of the company.

Job satisfaction is the most dominant factor in determining the success or failure of a company's activities, good job satisfaction can create high work morale, dedication, and work discipline. Company activities involving human resources will be related to wages or salaries received by employees, career development opportunities, relationships with coworkers, job placement, organizational structure and quality of supervision.

Employee performance is considered to be able to influence the achievement of the company's vision and mission, because it measures how much they give positive work results to the company. Positive employee performance can be achieved if the company can identify the factors that influence employee performance. According to Kasmir (2016), the factors that influence performance, both work results and behavior, are as follows: ability and expertise, knowledge, work design, personality, work motivation, leadership, leadership style, organizational culture, job satisfaction, work environment, loyalty, commitment, work discipline. Through these performance factors, it can be concluded that job satisfaction and work motivation are factors that influence performance. And also supported by the results of previous research conducted by Narulita and Charina (2020), stating that the results of the study showed that job satisfaction and work motivation simultaneously influenced employee performance.

Based on the description above, the researcher is interested in conducting research with the title The Influence of Human Resource Quality, Work-Life Balance on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as a Moderating Variable at BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Human Resource Quality Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Employee Performance at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branches in Medan Raya?
2. Does Work-Life Balance have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branches in Medan Raya?
3. Does job satisfaction have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya?
4. Does Human Resource Quality have a positive and significant effect on employee performance with job satisfaction as a moderating variable at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branches throughout Medan Raya?
5. Does work-life balance have a positive and significant effect on employee performance with job satisfaction as a moderating variable at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branches throughout Medan Raya?

Research purposes

1. To find out and analyze the influence Human Resource Quality on Employee Performance at BPJS Employment Branches in Medan Raya.
2. To find out and analyze the influence Work-life Balance on Employee Performance at BPJS Employment Branches in Medan Raya.
3. To find out and analyze the influence Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at BPJS Employment Branches throughout Medan Raya.
4. To find out and analyze the influence Human Resource Quality on Employee Performance with job satisfaction as a moderating variable at BPJS Employment Branches throughout Medan Raya.

5. To find out and analyze the influence Work-life Balance on Employee Performance with job satisfaction as a moderating variable at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Quality of human resources

According to Robbins (2015) said that the quality of human resources can be improved through training and providing fair work motivation including various employee welfare facilities. The quality of human resources can be measured from the success of increasing theoretical abilities, increasing technical abilities, increasing conceptual abilities, increasing morale and increasing skills. According to Sedarmayanti (2017) Quality of Human Resources The quality of human resources concerns the quality of the workforce in terms of ability, whether in the form of physical ability, intellectual ability (knowledge), or psychological ability (mental)

Indicator Quality of human resources

Human Resource Indicators according to Sedarmayanti (2017) are:

1. Physical ability (health)
2. Non-physical abilities, which include:
 - a) Intellectual Ability (intelligence)
 - b) Psychological (mental) abilities

Work-life balance

According to Pangemanan et al., (2017) work-life balance is an effective arrangement of work and other activities that are important such as family, community activities, volunteer work, self-development, tourism and recreation. Robbin & Coulter in Megaster et al., (2021) stated that individuals who have a family-friendly supportive place seem to be more satisfied with their work. According to

Work-life balance indicators

Work-life balance indicators according to Pangemanan et al., (2017) are as follows:

a. *Time Balance*

Time balance refers to the amount of time given by an individual for both their work and things outside of work such as time for their family. The balance of time owned by employees determines the amount of time allocated by employees to their work and personal life with family, various office activities, family or other social places can only be owned by employees. The balance of time achieved by employees shows that the demands of the family on employees do not reduce professional time in completing work, and vice versa.

b. *Involvement Balance*

Involvement balance refers to the amount or level of psychological involvement and commitment of an individual in his/her work and things outside of work. Time

allocated well is not necessarily sufficient as a basis for measuring the level of employee work-life balance, but must be supported by the amount or capacity of quality involvement in every activity that the employee undertakes. So that employees must be physically and emotionally involved in work activities, family and other social activities, only then will the balance of involvement be achieved.

c. *Satisfaction Balance*

Satisfaction balance refers to the level of satisfaction of an individual towards his/her work activities and things outside of his/her work. Satisfaction will arise automatically if the employee considers what he/she does is good enough to accommodate the needs of work and family. This can be seen from the conditions in the family, relationships with friends and coworkers, and the quality and quantity of work completed.

Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a positive attitude of the workforce including feelings and behavior towards their work through assessing one's work as a sense of appreciation in achieving one of the important values of the work (Afandi, 2018).

Job Satisfaction Indicators

Job satisfaction indicators according to Afandi (2018) are as follows:

- a. Job. The content of the job that someone does has satisfying elements.
- b. Wages. The amount of payment a person receives as a result of performing work is in accordance with the needs that are felt to be fair.
- c. Promotion The possibility that someone can develop through promotion.
- d. Supervisor. Someone who always gives orders or instructions in carrying out work
- e. Coworkers. Coworkers who help each other in completing work.

Employee Performance

According to Nurjaya (2021), performance is the level of achievement of results from carrying out certain tasks. Company performance is the level of achievement of results in order to realize company goals. Employee performance is very important for a company as a benchmark for business success, because performance is the result of the employee's work which shows their success in carrying out their duties. The higher the employee's performance, the better the performance of the company or organization (Fauzi & Wakhidah, 2020).

Employee Performance Indicators

Employee Performance Indicators according to Nurjaya (2021) are as follows:

- a. Quantity of work results, namely all forms of the amount of labor carried out can be seen from the results of employee performance within a certain time in completing their tasks and responsibilities within the specified time.

- b. Quality of work results, namely all forms of units of measurement related to the quality or standard of work results which can be expressed in numerical measurements or other numerical equivalents.
- c. Efficiency, namely in carrying out tasks using various resources wisely and in a cost-effective manner.
- d. Work discipline, namely obeying applicable laws and regulations.
- e. Initiative, which is the ability to decide and do the right thing without having to be told, being able to find out what should be done about something around you, trying to keep moving to do several things even though the situation feels increasingly difficult.
- f. Accuracy, namely the level of conformity of the results of work measurements, whether the work has achieved its objectives or not.
- g. Leadership, namely the process of influencing or giving examples by leaders to their followers in an effort to achieve organizational goals.
- h. Honesty is one of the human traits that is quite difficult to implement.
- i. Creativity, which is a mental process that involves the emergence of ideas or that involves the emergence of ideas.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework in this research is as follows:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework
Source: Processed by the Author (2024)

Research Hypothesis

The hypothesis proposed in this study is as follows:

- H1: The quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at BPJS Employment Branches throughout Medan Raya.
- H2: Work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at BPJS Employment Branches throughout Medan Raya.

- H3: Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan branches throughout Medan Raya.
- H4: Human Resource Quality has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with job satisfaction as a moderating variable at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branches throughout Medan Raya.
- H4: Work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with job satisfaction as a moderating variable at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branches throughout Medan Raya.

METHOD

Types of research

The type of research used by researchers is quantitative research. According to Sugiyono (2017) quantitative research can be interpreted as a method based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research a certain population or sample, sampling techniques are generally carried out randomly, data collection using research instruments, data analysis is quantitative/statistical with the aim of testing the hypothesis that has been set. This type of quantitative research is conducted to create a study that aims to adjust a study and the Influence of Human Resource Quality, Work-Life Balance on employee performance with job satisfaction as a Moderating variable at BPJS Employment, Medan Raya Branch Office.

Research Location and Research Time

The research location was conducted at the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices in Medan Raya, which consists of 4 branch offices with a total correspondence of 107 people, with the following details:

- BPJS Employment Medan City Branch, located at Jl. Kapten Patimura No.334, Darat, Medan Baru District, Medan City, North Sumatra, with a total of 33 employees.
- BPJS Employment Tanjung Morawa Branch is located on Jl. Raya Medan Tanjung Morawa Km. 14.5 Bangun Sari Baru Village, Bangun Sari Baru, Tj. Morawa District, Deli Serdang Regency, North Sumatra with a total of 26 employees.
- BPJS Employment North Medan Branch located at Jl. Marelan Raya No. 108 Tanah Enam Ratus District. Medan Marelan City, North Sumatra. with a total of 26 employees.
- BPJS Employment Binjai Branch located at Jl. Soekarno-Hatta No. 262, Km No.19.5, Tunggurono, East Binjai District, Binjai City, North Sumatra. with a total of 22 employees.

The research period was 3 months.

Population and Sample

Sugiyono (2017) population is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn. The population and sample in this study were all permanent

employees at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya totaling 107 personnel consisting of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Medan City Branch as many as 33 employees, Tanjung Morawa Branch as many as 26 employees, North Medan Branch as many as 26 employees and Binjai Branch as many as 22 employees.

Research Data Sources

The data sources used in this research are primary data.

Operational Definition of Research Variables

Table 1. Operational Definition of Variables

Variable Types	Definition	Indicator
Human Resources Quality (X1)	According to Sedarmayanti (2017) Quality of Human Resources. The quality of human resources concerns the quality of the workforce in terms of ability, whether in the form of physical ability, intellectual ability (knowledge), or psychological ability (mental)	According to Sedarmayanti (2017), the Human Resources indicators are: is: 1. Physical ability (health) 2. Non-physical abilities, which include: a) Intellectual ability (intelligence) b) Psychological (mental) abilities
Work-life balance(X2)	According to Pangemanan et al., (2017), work-life balance is an effective arrangement of work and other activities that are important, such as family, community activities, volunteer work, self-development, tourism and recreation.	To measure work-life balance, Pangemanan et al., (2017) are: a. Time Balance b. Involvement Balance c. Satisfaction Balance
Job satisfaction (Z)	According to Afandi (2018), job satisfaction is a positive attitude of the workforce including feelings and behavior towards their work through assessing one's work as a sense	According to Afandi (2018), the indicators of job satisfaction include: ▪ Work. ▪ Wages. ▪ Promotion

	of appreciation in achieving one of the important values of the work.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Supervisor • Work colleague.
Employee Performance (Y)	<p>According to Nurjaya (2021) performance is the level of achievement of results from carrying out certain tasks. Company performance is the level of achievement of results in order to realize company goals.</p>	<p>According to Nurjaya (2021), the indicators that can measure employee performance are as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Quantity of work results. ▪ Quality of work results. ▪ Efficiency. ▪ Work discipline. ▪ Initiative. ▪ Accuracy. ▪ Leadership. ▪ Honesty. ▪ Creativity.

Data Analysis Techniques

Data analysis in this study uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on Partial Least Square (PLS) using SmartPLS 3.3.3 software. According to (Ghozali, 2014) Partial Least Square (PLS) is a fairly strong analysis method because it is not based on many assumptions.

Measurement Model (Outer Model)

The procedure in testing the measurement model consists of validity testing and reliability testing.

1. Validity Test
 - a. Convergent Validity
 - b. Discriminant Validity

2. Reliability Test

The Cronbach's alpha value is recommended to be greater than 0.7 and the composite reliability is also recommended to be greater than 0.7 (Sekaran, 2014).

Structural Model (Inner Model)

This test is conducted to determine the relationship between exogenous and endogenous constructs that have become hypotheses in this study (Hair et al., 2017). To produce inner model test values, the steps in SmartPLS are carried out using the bootstrapping method. The structural model is evaluated using R-square for the dependent variable, the Stone-Geisser Q-square test for predictive elevation and the t-test and significance of the structural path parameter coefficients with the following explanation:

1. Coefficient of Determination / R Square (R²)

In assessing the model with PLS, it begins by looking at the R-square for each dependent latent variable. The interpretation is the same as the interpretation in regression. Changes in the R-square value can be used to assess the influence of certain independent latent variables on the dependent latent variable whether it has a substantive influence (Ghozali, 2012). The R² value is generally between 0 and 1.

2. Predictive Relevance (Q²)

This test is used to measure how well the observation value is generated by the model and also its parameter estimates. If the Q² value is greater than 0, it indicates that the model has predictive relevance, which means it has good observation value, while if the value is less than 0, it indicates that the model does not have predictive relevance (Ghozali, 2014).

3. t-Statistic

At this stage, it is used for hypothesis testing, namely to determine the significance of the relationship between variables in the study using the bootstrapping method. In the full model Structural Equation Modeling, in addition to confirming the theory, it also explains whether or not there is a relationship between latent variables (Ghozali, 2012). The hypothesis is said to be accepted if the t statistic value is greater than the t table. According to (Latan and Ghozali, 2014) the criteria for the t table value with a value of 1.96 with a significance level of 5%.

4. Path Coefficient

This test is used to determine the direction of the relationship between variables (positive/negative). If the value is 0 to 1, then the direction of the relationship between variables is stated as positive. While if the value is 0 to -1, then the direction of the relationship between variables is stated as negative.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Measurement model testing (outer model) is used to determine the specifications of the relationship between latent variables and their manifest variables, this testing includes convergent validity, discriminant validity and reliability.

1. Convergent Validity

This test is seen from the loading factor, the value limit is 0.7, and the value limit Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is 0.5, if it is above that value it is said to be valid. This means that the value for the indicator is said to be valid, if the indicator explains the construct variable with a value > 0.7. The structural model in this study is shown in the following figure:

Figure 2. Outer Model

Smart PLS output for loading factor gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Z = b1X1 + b2X2 + e1$$

$$Z = 0.483X1 + 0.246X2 + e1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b3X1 + b4X2 + b5Z + e2$$

$$Y = 0.197X1 + 0.050 X2 + 0.590Z + e2$$

Table 2. Outer Loadings

	JOB SATISFACTION	EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE	QUALITY OF HUMAN RESOURCES	WORK LIFE BALANCE
KEK1	0.624			
KEK2	0.872			
KEK3	0.796			
Kin1		0.838		
Kin2		0.825		
SDM1			0.792	
HR2			0.855	
SDM4			0.757	
SDM5			0.743	
SDM7			0.820	
WLB2				0.801
WLB5				0.697
WLB6				0.641
WLB7				0.852

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In the table above, the value of each variable is stated that the indicator in each variable is higher than 0.7, which means that each indicator item has a value higher than 0.7 so that the data is declared valid and can continue to further research.

2. Discriminant Validity

Further research to find out valid data in terms of Discriminate Validity, aims to find out whether the cross loading value is greater than other latent variables so as to determine the results of indicators that are highly correlated with their constructs. The following table shows the cross loading results from the validity test as follows:

Table 3. Discriminant Validity

	JOB SATISFACTION	EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE	QUALITY OF HUMAN RESOURCES	WORK LIFE BALANCE
JOB SATISFACTION	0.771			
EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE	0.762	0.832		
QUALITY OF HUMAN RESOURCES	0.698	0.654	0.794	
WORK LIFE BALANCE	0.670	0.619	0.879	0.752

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

The results of table 3 above show a value that is greater than the other variables in each indicator and variable, so it can be concluded that the results of the discriminant validity study are validly distributed.

3. Composite reliability

In composite reliability research to see each variable with its reliability value and if the variable value is greater than 0.60 then the research is considered reliable and if below 0.60 and 0.7 then it is not reliable there are several blocks to determine whether the research is reliable or not and valid or not including the Coranbach alpha value, composite reliability and AVE value can be seen in the table below:

Table 4. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
JOB SATISFACTION	0.744	0.738	0.812	0.595
EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE	0.755	0.755	0.818	0.692

QUALITY OF HUMAN RESOURCES	0.855	0.865	0.895	0.631
WORK LIFE BALANCE	0.753	0.792	0.838	0.566

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 4 above, it can be seen in the cronbach alpha column that each variable has a value greater than 0.7, which means that the reliability data for each variable. The composite reliability column has a value greater than 0.6, so it can be explained that each variable is considered reliable because the data is greater than 0.6. It can be seen from the AVE column that each variable gets a value greater than 0.7, which means that the data is valid according to AVE. All variables from the cronbach alpha column, reliability column and AVE column have values greater than 0.7 and 0.6, so they are considered reliable and valid.

Inner Model Analysis

Structural model evaluation (inner model) is conducted to ensure that the basic model created is strong and accurate. The stages of examination conducted in the primary model assessment are seen from several markers, namely:

1. Coefficient of Determination (R²)

In the next stage, namely the evaluation of the measurement model or inner model by looking at the R-Square value criteria. The R-Square results from the smartPLS 3.0 software output are as follows:

Table 5. R Square Results

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
JOB SATISFACTION	0.750	0.749
EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE	0.761	0.760

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

There is an R square value for the employee performance variable with an R square value of 0.749 and if expressed as a percentage it is 74.9%, which means Influence quality of human resources, Work-Life Balance on employee performance with job satisfaction as a moderating variable of 74.9% and the remaining 25.1% is in other variables. The R square value of the work motivation variable is 0.760 and if in percentage it is 76.0%, it means Influence quality of human resources, Work-Life Balance on employee performance with job satisfaction as a moderating variable by 76.0% and the remaining 24.0% on other variables.

2. Hypothesis Testing

After assessing the inner model, the next thing is to assess the connection between idle builds as suspected in this review. Speculation testing in this review is done by looking at T-Statistics and P-Values. Speculation is announced to acknowledge whether the T-Insights value is > 1.96 and P-Values < 0.05 . The following are the consequences of the direct impact Path Coefficient:

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
JOB SATISFACTION -> EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE	0.590	0.593	0.091	6,452	0.000
QUALITY OF HUMAN RESOURCES -> EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE	0.593	0.044	0.137	0.407	0.000
WORK LIFE BALANCE -> EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE	0.050	0.041	0.130	0.388	0.698

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

The results of the research directly above will be explained as follows:

1. Human Resource Quality has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.593 and P values of 0.000. This means that the existence of Human Resource Quality has a positive effect on the Company and Human Resource Quality significantly affects the company's performance.
2. Work-life balance has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.050 and p values of 0.388. This means that Work Life Balance is unable to improve employee performance towards the company.
3. Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.590 and P values of 0.000.

Table 7. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
HR QUALITY -> JOB SATISFACTION -> EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE	0.284	0.277	0.114	2.485	0.013
WORK LIFE BALANCE -> JOB SATISFACTION -> EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE	0.145	0.159	0.105	1,380	0.168

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

The results of the indirect influence above can be explained as follows:

1. Job Satisfaction is able to moderate the influence of Human Resource Quality on Employee Performance indirectly with the original sample results of 0.277 and p values of 0.013. This means that job satisfaction is an intervening variable because it is able to influence Human Resource Quality on employee performance indirectly.
2. Job Satisfaction is able to moderate the influence of Human Resource Quality on Employee Performance indirectly with the original sample value of 0.159 and p values of 0.168. This means that job satisfaction is an intervening variable that is unable to influence Work Life Balance on employee performance indirectly.

CLOSING

Conclusion

Based on the research results above, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Human Resources Quality Has a Positive and Significant Influence on Employee Performance at BPJS Employment Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya
2. Work-life balance has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance at BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.
3. Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya
4. Job Satisfaction is able to moderate the influence of Human Resource Quality on Employee Performance at BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.
5. Job Satisfaction is able to moderate the influence Work-life balance on Employee Performance at BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya

Suggestion

After drawing conclusions from the results, the researcher made the following suggestions to the company:

1. The company must increase Job Satisfaction for its employees which is done every month so that it is embedded to improve the company's performance in the souls of employees to the maximum and in accordance with Company regulations.
2. Companies must ensure that employees have the ability to work with quality human resources. With strong quality human resources, the company's performance will increase.
3. Companies must make employees create a more optimal Work Life Balance, with increased Work Life Balance will provide more value to the Company.

REFERENCES

- Afandi, P. (2018). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia (Teori, Konsep dan Indikator)*. Riau: Zanafa Publishing.
- Fauzi, M., & Wakhidah, N. (2020). Pengaruh Disiplin Kerja, Motivasi Kerja, dan Pengembangan Karir terhadap Kinerja Karyawan PT. Semarang Autocomp Manufacturing Indonesia. 7(1), 72–86

- Ganapathi, I Made Devan & Gilang, Alini. (2016). The Influence of Work Life Balance On Employees Job Satisfaction (Studi at PT. Biofarma Persero). EProceeding of Management : Vol. 3, No. 1 April (2016,) page 506 ISSN : 2355-9537.
- Ghozali, Imam, & Latan Hengky. (2014). Partial Least Squares : Konsep, Teknik dan Aplikasi Menggunakan SmartPLS 3.0 (edisi ke-2). Semarang : Universitas Diponegoro.
- Kasmir. (2016). Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia (Teori dan Praktik). Cetakan Kesatu. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Megaster, T., dkk. (2021). Pengaruh Work-Life Balance dan Burnout Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan C Nusantara Lestari. Jurnal Comparative Ekonomi dan Bisnis, 3(1), 62-75.
- Narulita, R. P. & Charina, A., (2020). “Pengaruh Kepuasan Kerja dan Motivasi Kerja terhadap Kinerja Karyawan di Perusahaan Bumi Saba Indonesia”. Jurnal Ekonomi Pertanian dan Agribisnis (JEPA) , 4(2), pp. 268-276.
- Nurjaya, N. (2021). Pengaruh Disiplin Kerja, Lingkungan Kerja dan Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada PT. Hazara Cipta Pesona. Jurnal Ilmiah Nasional, III(1), 60-74
- Pangemanan, F. L., dkk. (2017). Pengaruh Work-Life Balance dan Burnout Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja. Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis, 5(003), 65-72.
- Robbins, Stephen. (2015). Organizational Behavior. 9th Edition. New Jersey: Precentice Hall International Inc.
- Rondonuwu, F. A., dkk. (2018). Pengaruh Work-life Balance Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan Pada Hotel Sintesa Peninsula Manado. Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis, 30 - 38.
- Sedarmayanti. (2017). Perencanaan dan Pengembangan SDM untuk Meningkatkan Kompetensi, Kinerja dan Produktivitas Kerja. PT Refika Aditama. Bandung.
- Sekaran, Uma. (2014). Metodologi Penelitian Untuk Bisnis (Research Methods for Business) Buku 1 Edisi 4. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- Sugiyono, (2017). Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D. Bandung: CV. Alfabeta

The Influence of Work Discipline and Teamwork on Employee Performance with Organizational Citizenship Behavior as an Intervening Variable at BPJS Branch Offices in Medan Raya

Lasmaida Susy Deliana¹, Kiki Farida Ferine²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: kikifarida@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

This study aims to analyze the direct and indirect effects of work discipline, teamwork, organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), and employee performance at the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Office in Medan Raya. The research uses a quantitative approach with a population of 82 employees. The sampling technique used is a saturated sample, where the entire population is used as the sample for this study. Data collection was carried out through questionnaires as the primary data source. The research model was analyzed using path analysis with Smart PLS version 3.3.3. The results of the study indicate that work discipline has a positive but insignificant effect on employee performance, with an original sample value of 0.585 and a P-value of 0.218. On the other hand, work discipline has a negative and significant effect on OCB, with an original sample value of -0.949 and a P-value of 0.000. Teamwork shows a negative but insignificant effect on employee performance, with an original sample value of -0.694 and a P-value of 0.304. However, teamwork has a positive and significant effect on OCB, with an original sample value of 1.720 and a P-value of 0.000. Furthermore, OCB has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, with an original sample value of 1.024 and a P-value of 0.003. Work discipline also has a negative and significant effect on employee performance through OCB, with an original sample result of -0.981 and a P-value of 0.011. Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through OCB, with an original sample value of 1.775 and a P-value of 0.001. Thus, OCB plays a crucial role as an intervening variable that mediates the effects of work discipline and teamwork on employee performance.

Keywords: work discipline, teamwork, organizational citizenship and performance.

INTRODUCTION

BPJS Ketenagakerjaan has functions and responsibilities such as, conducting and accepting registration for BPJS participants, collecting and collecting contributions from participants and employers, receiving contribution assistance from the government, managing social security funds for the benefit of participants, collecting and managing data on social security program participants, providing benefits and financing health services according to the provisions of the social security program, and is also responsible for providing information regarding the implementation of social security programs to participants and the community. The main function of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan is to organize work accident insurance programs, death insurance programs, pension insurance programs and old age insurance programs.

According to Sinambela (2018), work discipline is the awareness and willingness of employees to obey all organizational regulations and applicable social norms. With good work discipline from employees such as arriving on time, carrying out work according to what has been determined by the company, obeying company regulations, it will be able to improve the performance of these employees so that the company's targets will be achieved.

Previous research on the effect of work discipline on employee performance showed inconsistent results. Research results from Satato, et al. (2022), Chandra, et al. (2022), Faqih (2022) showed that work discipline had a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Different research results from Nucifera (2022), Adinugroho, et al. (2021) showed that work discipline did not have a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

Teamwork depends on the level of trust and solidarity, team members work together to pool resources to achieve organizational goals. Teamwork is a collection of individuals who are interdependent on tasks and are jointly responsible for the results obtained, according to Manzoor (2017). Teamwork includes the mental and emotional involvement of people in a group that encourages them to contribute to the organization in order to achieve goals. The definition of teamwork explains that a group of people who work together to achieve the same goal. The results of Kusuma & Sutanto's (2018) study showed that teamwork has an important role in employee performance because each member can help each other complete tasks and problems that arise through communication within the team. In contrast to these findings, Muhti et al. (2017) found that teamwork had no effect on employee performance and this was influenced by the importance of results orientation in corporate culture.

One of the factors that affect employee performance is organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), OCB is a form of contribution made by an employee beyond his/her responsibilities (Syaiful B 2018), OCB is a term for employees who provide added value to the work that is their job or added value to the company. According to Rosita (2018) the behavior of an employee who voluntarily helps the organization develop further by carrying out tasks beyond their obligations is a form of OCB, with the presence of OCB in employees it is expected that employees can work more than what is assigned, always be ready to accept additional work, obey existing rules, and be able to help fellow employees.

In the study (Andriani et al., 2021) OCB has a positive and significant influence on employee performance because through OCB it can create prosocial behavior thereby improving individual performance. Meanwhile, on employee personality through OCB on employee performance has a positive influence, where it is said that the influence of personality on performance is smaller than the influence of personality on OCB, because one of the factors forming OCB is personality which is directly beneficial to the organization.

Employee performance is an aspect that directly impacts the achievement of company goals. According to Simanjuntak (2018), performance is a measure of work results in terms of quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities given. In addition, employee performance generally includes elements of quantity and quality of work results, attendance and ability to cooperate (Simanjuntak, 2018). Thus, it can be said that performance is a benchmark for the company's success in achieving its goals. If employees are able to provide optimal performance in every task given, then the company's goals will be quickly achieved.

Based on the description above, the researcher is interested in conducting research with the title The Influence of Work Discipline and Teamwork on Employee Performance with

Organizational Citizenship Behavior as an Intervening Variable at BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does work discipline have a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya?
2. Does teamwork have a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya?
3. Does work discipline have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya?
4. Does teamwork have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya?
5. Does Organizational Citizenship Behavior have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya?
6. Does work discipline have a positive and significant effect on employee performance through Organizational Citizenship Behavior as an intervening variable at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya?
7. Does teamwork have a positive and significant effect on employee performance through Organizational Citizenship Behavior as an intervening variable at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya?

Research purposes

1. To find out and analyze the influence of work discipline towards Organizational Citizenship Behavior at BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.
2. To find out and analyze the influence of teamwork on Organizational Citizenship Behavior at BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.
3. To find out and analyze the influence of work discipline on employee performance at BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.
4. To find out and analyze the influence of teamwork on employee performance at BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.
5. To find out and analyze the influence of *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* influence on employee performance at BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.
6. To find out and analyze the influence of work discipline on employee performance through Organizational Citizenship Behavior as an intervening variable at BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.
7. To find out and analyze the influence of teamwork on employee performance through Organizational Citizenship Behavior as an intervening variable at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Work Discipline

According to Agustini (2019), work discipline is an attitude of obedience to the rules and norms that apply in a company in order to increase employee determination in achieving company/organizational goals.

Work Discipline Indicators

According to Agustini (2019) the discipline indicators are as follows:

- a. Attendance rate, namely the number of employees present to carry out work activities in the company which is characterized by a low level of employee absence.
- b. Work procedures, namely rules or provisions that must be adhered to by all members of the organization.
- c. Obedience to superiors, namely following what is directed by superiors to get good results.
- d. Work awareness, namely the attitude of a person who voluntarily does his work well, not because of coercion.
- e. Responsibility, namely the employee's willingness to be responsible for their work, the facilities and infrastructure used, and their work behavior.

Teamwork

According to West in Andarias & Lutfi (2021), teamwork is a relatively small group working on clear, challenging tasks that are most efficiently completed by the work group together compared to individuals working alone or in groups, which have certainty, together, challenging, team goals derived from tasks, who must work together and depend on each other to achieve those goals, whose members work in different roles in a team, and have the necessary authority, autonomy and resources that enable them to meet team goals.

Indicator Teamwork

According to West in Andarias & Lutfi (2021), the indicators of teamwork are as follows:

- a. Responsible for jointly completing the work,
- b. Contributing to each other with both energy and thoughts will create cooperation.
- c. Maximizing capability direction to maximize the capabilities of each team member, cooperation will be stronger and of higher quality.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior

According to Sukanto (2018), Organizational Citizenship Behavior refers to individual behavior that makes an overall positive contribution to the company.

Indicator Organizational Citizenship Behavior

According to Sukanto (2018) there are 5 (five) indicators of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), namely:

- a. *Altruism*, which is a behavior carried out by individuals who voluntarily help their co-workers who are experiencing difficulties in the situation they are facing, either regarding work in the company or other people's personal problems. This dimension leads to providing assistance that is not an obligation that they bear. For example, employees help other co-workers who are not feeling well. In addition to the employee's goal of lightening the workload of their co-workers, this will also help the company in achieving targets on time and for employees it is useful as an exercise in improving performance measures.
- b. *Conscientiousness*, namely behavior carried out by individuals voluntarily in their role as employees to improve their performance in various ways, even when it requires creativity and innovation for the sake of improving the company. For example, having the initiative to improve their competence, either by conducting training or attending seminars that exist voluntarily.
- c. *Civic Virtue*, namely behavior carried out by individuals voluntarily in their role as employees to participate and be responsible for solving company problems for the sake of the company's sustainability. For example, when there is a threat of competitors in business, employees contribute in providing ideas for solving the problem.
- d. *Courtesy*, which is behavior carried out by individuals voluntarily in their role as employees to prevent problems from occurring in the company either due to provocation from outside the company or from individuals within the company. For example, giving warnings to coworkers to always be careful in responding to issues that have a negative impact and always trying to provide correct information for the company.
- e. *Sportsmanship*, namely behavior carried out by individuals voluntarily in their role as employees in the form of tolerance to survive in uncomfortable or unpleasant conditions without complaining at all. For example, in order to maintain the survival of the company, there is a change in the rules in the company that is not in accordance with employee expectations, employees must be able to accept these conditions and remain positive.

Employee Performance

According to Afandi (2018), performance is the work results that can be achieved by a person or group of people in a company in accordance with their respective authorities and responsibilities in an effort to achieve organizational goals illegally, without violating the law and without conflicting with morals and ethics.

Indicator Employee Performance

According to Afandi (2018) employee performance indicators are as follows:

- a. Quantity of work results All forms of units of measurement related to the amount of work results that can be expressed in numbers or other numerical equivalents.
- b. Quality of work results All forms of units of measurement related to the quality or standard of work results that can be expressed in numerical measurements or other numerical equivalents.
- c. Efficiency in carrying out tasks Various resources wisely and in a cost-effective manner.
- d. Work discipline. Obedient to applicable laws and regulations.

- e. Initiative The ability to decide and do the right thing without being told, being able to find what should be done about something around you, trying to keep moving to do things even though the situation feels increasingly difficult.
- f. Accuracy The level of conformity of work measurement results to whether the work has achieved its objectives or not.
- g. Leadership is the process of influencing or giving examples by leaders to their followers in an effort to achieve organizational goals.
- h. Honesty is one of the human traits that is quite difficult to apply.
- i. Creativity A mental process that involves generating ideas or that involves generating ideas.

Conceptual Framework

To get a simpler picture, it can be explained using the following scheme:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of Research

Hypothesis

The hypothesis in this study is as follows:

- H1: Work discipline has a positive effect and significant on Organizational Citizenship Behavior at BPJS Employment Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya.
- H2: Teamwork matters positive and significant on Organizational Citizenship Behavior at BPJS Employment Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya.
- H3: Work Discipline has an effect positive and significant on Employee Performance at BPJS Employment Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya.
- H4: Teamwork has a positive effect and significant on Employee Performance at BPJS Employment Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya.
- H5: *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* influential positive and significant on Employee Performance at BPJS Employment Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya.
- H6: Work Discipline has an effect positive and significant on Employee Performance through Organizational Citizenship Behavior at BPJS Employment Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya.
- H7: Teamwork matters positive and significant on Employee Performance through Organizational Citizenship Behavior at BPJS Employment Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya.

METHOD

Types of research

The type of research used by researchers is quantitative research. According to Sugiyono (2017) quantitative research can be interpreted as a method based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research a particular population or sample, sampling techniques are generally carried out randomly, data collection uses research instruments, data analysis is quantitative/statistical with the aim of testing the established hypothesis.

Research Location and Research Time

The research location was conducted at BPJS Employment Branches throughout Medan Raya consisting of 3 branch offices with a total correspondence of 82 people, with the following details:

- BPJS Employment Medan Branch, located at Jl. Kapten Patimura No. 334, Darat, Medan Baru District, Medan City, North Sumatra, with a total of 24 employees.
 - BPJS Employment Tanjung Morawa Branch, which is located at Jl. Raya Medan Tanjung Morawa KM 14.5 Bangun Sari Baru Village, Bangun Sari Baru, Tj. Morawa District, Deli Serdang Regency, North Sumatra 20362, North Sumatra, with a total of 22 employees.
 - BPJS Employment North Medan Branch, which is located in Jl. Marelان Raya No.108, Tanah Enam Ratus, Medan Marelان District, Medan City, North Sumatra with a total of 22 employees.
 - BPJS Employment Binjai Branch is located at Jl. Soekarno-Hatta No. 262, Km No.19.5, Tunggurono, East Binjai District, Binjai City, North Sumatra.
- with a total of 14 employees.

The research period was carried out for 3 months starting from July to September 2024.

Population and Sample

Sugiyono (2017) population is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics that are determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions are drawn. The population and sample in this study were all permanent employees at the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Tanjung Morawa Branch totaling 22 employees, plus 24 Medan Branch employees, employees North Medan Branch as many as 22 employees, Binjai branch office 14 people (saturated sample) so that the total is 82 BPJS Ketenagakerjaan employees of Medan Raya Branch Offices.

Research Data Sources

The data sources used in this research are primary data.

Operational Definition of Research Variables

Table 1. Operational Definition of Variables

Variable Types	Definition	Indicator
Work Discipline (X1)	According to Agustini (2019), work discipline is an attitude of obedience to the rules and norms that apply in a company in order to increase employee determination in achieving company/organizational goals.	According to Agustini (2019) the indicators of work discipline are as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attendance rate. • Working procedures. • Obedience to superiors. • Consciousness works. • Responsibility.
KTeamwork (X2)	According to West in Andarias & Lutfi (2021), teamwork is a relatively small group working on clear work, challenging tasks that are most efficiently completed by work groups together compared to individuals working alone or in groups, who have certainty, together, challenging, team goals derived from tasks, who must work together and depend on each other to achieve these goals.	According to West in Andarias & Lutfi (2021), the indicators of team collaboration are as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsible for jointly completing the work, • Contributing to each other with both energy and thoughts will create cooperation. • Maximum ability guidance
<i>Organizationanizational Citizenship Behavior</i> (Z)	According to Sukanto (2018), Organizational Citizenship Behavior refers to individual behavior that makes an overall positive contribution to the company.	According to Sukanto (2018), the indicators of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) are as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Altruism.</i> • <i>Conscientiousness.</i> • <i>Civic Virtue.</i> • <i>Courtesy.</i>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Sportsmanship.</i>
Employee Performance (Y)	<p>According to Afandi (2018), performance is the work results that can be achieved by a person or group of people in a company in accordance with their respective authorities and responsibilities in an effort to achieve organizational goals illegally, without violating the law and without conflicting with morals and ethics.</p>	<p>According to Afandi (2018) employee performance indicators are as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantity of work results. • Quality of work results. • Efficiency in carrying out tasks. • Work discipline. • Initiative. • Accuracy. • Leadership. • Honesty. • Creativity

Data Analysis Techniques

Data analysis in this study uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on Partial Least Square (PLS) using SmartPLS 3.3.3 software. According to (Ghozali, 2014) Partial Least Square (PLS) is a fairly strong analysis method because it is not based on many assumptions.

Measurement Model (Outer Model)

The procedure in testing the measurement model consists of validity testing and reliability testing.

1. Validity Test

- a. Convergent Validity
- b. Discriminant Validity

2. Reliability Test

The Cronbach's alpha value is recommended to be greater than 0.7 and the composite reliability is also recommended to be greater than 0.7 (Sekaran, 2014).

Structural Model (Inner Model)

This test is conducted to determine the relationship between exogenous and endogenous constructs that have become hypotheses in this study (Hair et al., 2017). To produce inner model test values, the steps in SmartPLS are carried out using the bootstrapping method. The structural model is evaluated using R-square for the dependent variable, the Stone-Geisser Q-square test for predictive elevation and the t-test and significance of the structural path parameter coefficients with the following explanation:

1. Coefficient of Determination / R Square (R²)

In assessing the model with PLS, it begins by looking at the R-square for each dependent latent variable. The interpretation is the same as the interpretation in regression. Changes in the R-square value can be used to assess the influence of certain independent latent variables on the dependent latent variable whether it has a substantive influence (Ghozali, 2014). The R² value is generally between 0 and 1.

2. Predictive Relevance (Q²)

This test is used to measure how well the observation value is generated by the model and also its parameter estimates. If the Q² value is greater than 0, it indicates that the model has predictive relevance, which means it has good observation value, while if the value is less than 0, it indicates that the model does not have predictive relevance (Ghozali, 2014).

3. t-Statistic

At this stage, it is used for hypothesis testing, namely to determine the significance of the relationship between variables in the study using the bootstrapping method. In the full model Structural Equation Modeling, in addition to confirming the theory, it also explains whether or not there is a relationship between latent variables (Ghozali, 2014). The hypothesis is said to be accepted if the t statistic value is greater than the t table. According to (Latan and Ghozali, 2014) the criteria for the t table value with a value of 1.96 with a significance level of 5%.

4. Path Coefficient

This test is used to determine the direction of the relationship between variables (positive/negative). If the value is 0 to 1, then the direction of the relationship between variables is stated as positive. While if the value is 0 to -1, then the direction of the relationship between variables is stated as negative.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Measurement model testing (outer model) is used to determine the specifications of the relationship between latent variables and their manifest variables, this testing includes convergent validity, discriminant validity and reliability.

1. Convergent Validity

This test is seen from the loading factor, the value limit is 0.7, and the value limit Average Variance Extracted.(AVE) is 0.5, if it is above that value it is said to be valid. This means that the value for the indicator is said to be valid, if the indicator explains the construct variable with a value > 0.7. The structural model in this study is shown in the following figure:

Figure 2. Outer Model
 Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Smart PLS output for loading factor gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1.

$$Z = b1X1 + b2X2 + e1$$

$$Z = 0.970 X1 + 1.729 X2 + e1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b1X1 + b2X2 + b1Z + e2$$

$$Y = 0.610X1 + 0.770X2 + 1.085Z + e2$$

Table 2. Outer Loadings

	Work Discipline	Teamwork	Employee Performance	Organizational Citizenship
Dis2	0.818			
Dis4	0.745			
Dis5	0.780			
Dis6	0.642			
Dis7	0.925			
Dis8	0.769			
Dis9	0.587			
Kin1			0.917	
Kin2			0.736	
Kti1		0.683		

Kti2		0.603		
Kti3		0.915		
Kti4		0.628		
Kti5		0.802		
Kti6		0.753		
Kti7		0.718		
Kti9		0.711		
Oci2				0.892
Oci3				0.917
Oci5				0.940

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 2 above, the value of each variable is stated that the indicator in each variable is higher than 0.7, which means that each indicator item has a value higher than 0.7 so that the data is declared valid and can continue to further research.

2. Discriminant Validity

Further research to find out valid data in terms of Discriminate Validity, aims to find out whether the cross loading value is greater than other latent variables so as to determine the results of indicators that are highly correlated with their constructs. The following table shows the cross loading results from the validity test as follows:

Table 3. Discriminant Validity

	Work Discipline	Teamwork	Employee Performance	Organizational Citizenship
Work Discipline	0.759			
Teamwork	0.894	0.733		
Employee Performance	0.546	0.711	0.831	
Organizational Citizenship	0.575	0.862	0.772	0.917

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

The results of table 3 above show a value that is greater than the other variables in each indicator and variable, so it can be concluded that the results of the discriminant validity study are validly distributed.

3. Composite reliability

In composite reliability research to see each variable with its reliability value and if the variable value is greater than 0.60 then the research is considered reliable and if below 0.60 and 0.7 then it is not reliable there are several blocks to determine whether the research

is reliable or not and valid or not including the Cronbach alpha value, composite reliability and AVE value can be seen in the table below:

Table 4. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Work Discipline	0.874	0.921	0.903	0.577
Teamwork	0.883	0.927	0.901	0.537
Employee Performance	0.676	0.685	0.816	0.691
Organizational Citizenship	0.905	0.906	0.940	0.840

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 4 above, it can be seen in the Cronbach alpha column that each variable has a value greater than 0.7, which means that the reliability data for each variable. The composite reliability column has a value greater than 0.6, so it can be explained that each variable is considered reliable because the data is greater than 0.6. It can be seen from the AVE column that each variable gets a value greater than 0.7, which means that the data is valid according to AVE. All variables from the Cronbach alpha column, reliability column and AVE column have values greater than 0.7 and 0.6, so they are considered reliable and valid.

Inner Model Analysis

Structural model evaluation (inner model) is conducted to ensure that the basic model created is strong and accurate. The stages of examination conducted in the primary model assessment are seen from several markers, namely:

1. Coefficient of Determination (R²)

In the next stage, namely the evaluation of the measurement model or inner model by looking at the R-Square value criteria. The R-Square results from the smartPLS 3.0 software output are as follows:

Table 5. R Square Results

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Employee Performance	0.624	0.604
Organizational Citizenship	0.932	0.930

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

There is a variable R square value Organizational Citizenship with an R square value of 0.9304 and if the percentage is 93.0%, this means that the influence of work discipline and teamwork on employee performance is through Organizational Citizenship and the rest is on other variables. The R square value of the employee performance variable is 0.604 and if

expressed as a percentage is 60.4%, meaning that the influence of the work discipline variable, teamwork on employee performance through Organizational Citizenship by 60.4% and the remainder on other variables.

3. Hypothesis Testing

After assessing the inner model, the next thing is to assess the connection between idle builds as suspected in this review. Speculation testing in this review is done by looking at T-Statistics and P-Values. Speculation is announced to acknowledge whether the T-Insights value is > 1.96 and P-Values < 0.05 . The following are the consequences of the direct impact Path Coefficient:

Table 6. Hypothesis Testing

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Work Discipline -> Employee Performance	0.610	0.585	0.495	1.232	0.218
Work Discipline -> Organizational Citizenship	-0.970	-0.949	0.182	5.322	0.000
Teamwork -> Employee Performance	-0.770	-0.694	0.749	1,028	0.304
Teamwork -> Organizational Citizenship	1,729	1,720	0.193	8,960	0.000
Organizational Citizenship -> Employee Performance	1,085	1,024	0.358	3.031	0.003

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

The results of the research directly above will be explained as follows:

- Work discipline has a positive but insignificant effect on employee performance, with an original sample value of 0.585 and a P-value of 0.218. This indicates that work discipline is not able to significantly improve employee performance, as the placement of individuals in their roles is not strongly influenced by work discipline created by the organization.
- Work discipline has a negative and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), with an original sample value of -0.949 and a P-value of 0.000. This suggests that work discipline established by the organization can significantly reduce OCB among employees, though a strong OCB is often associated with treating employees well.
- Teamwork has a negative and insignificant effect on employee performance, with an original sample value of -0.694 and a P-value of 0.304. This implies that if teamwork does not improve, employee performance may still increase. However, if teamwork decreases, employee performance tends to decline as well.

- d. Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on OCB, with an original sample value of 1.720 and a P-value of 0.000. This means that when teamwork improves, OCB also increases, and if teamwork decreases, OCB will likely decline as well.
- e. Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, with an original sample value of 1.024 and a P-value of 0.003. This indicates that as OCB increases, employee performance also improves, and conversely, if OCB decreases, employee performance will decline.

Table 7. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Work Discipline -> Organizational Citizenship -> Employee Performance	-1.052	-0.981	0.413	2,550	0.011
Teamwork -> Organizational Citizenship -> Employee Performance	1,876	1,775	0.679	2,764	0.001

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

The results of the indirect influence above can be explained as follows:

1. Work Discipline has a negative and significant effect on kmployee performance via oorganizational citizenship with the original sample results of -0.981 and p values of 0.011. This means that oorganizational citizenship as an intervening variable because it is able to influence dwork discipline against kmployee performance indirectly.
2. Teamwork positive and significant influence on kmployee performance via oorganizational citizenship with the original sample result of 1.775 and p values of 0.001. This means that oorganizational citizenship as an intervening variable because it is able to influence Teamwork against kmployee performance indirectly.

CLOSING

Conclusion

Based on the research results above, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Work Discipline positive and insignificant effect on kmployee performance at BPJS Employment Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya.
2. Work Discipline has a negative and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship at BPJS Employment Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya.
3. Teamwork has a negative and insignificant effect on Employee Performance at BPJS Employment Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya.
4. Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship in BPJS Employment Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya.
5. Organizational Citizenship has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance in BPJS Employment Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya.

6. Work Discipline has a negative and significant effect on employee performance via organizational citizenship in BPJS Employment Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya.
7. Teamwork positive and significant influence on employee performance via organizational citizenship in BPJS Employment Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya.

Suggestion

After drawing conclusions from the results, the researcher made the following suggestions to the company:

1. The company must maintain work discipline in the company by creating a business work discipline directed at employees who work and provide increased company performance with the existence of work discipline.
2. Companies must maintain teamwork in working well and safely. With teamwork maximum employees will improve the company's performance in general.
3. The company must maintain organizational citizenship in working well and safely. With organizational citizenship maximum employees will improve the company's performance in general.

REFERENCES

- Afinda Faqih, M. (2022). Pengaruh Pemberian Insentif, Motivasi Dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan PT LKM Demak Sejahtera (Doctoral dissertation, Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta).
- Chandra, J., Rostina, C. F., Debby, D., & Angela, F. (2022). Pengaruh disiplin kerja, kompetensi kerja dan pengawasan kerja terhadap kinerja karyawan pada PT. Karya Inti Nusa Gemilang Medan. *Management Studies and Entrepreneurship Journal (MSEJ)*, 3(2).
- Ghozali, 2014. Aplikasi analisis Multivariate dengan Program SPSS. Badan Penerbit UNDIP, Semarang
- Kusuma, L. P., & Sutanto, J. E. (2018). Peranan kerjasama tim dan semangat kerja terhadap kinerja karyawan Zolid Agung Perkasa. *Jurnal Performa: Jurnal Manajemen dan Start-up Bisnis*, 3(4).
- Nucifera, P. (2022). Pengaruh Disiplin Kerja, Beban Kerja Dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Koperasi Batur Jaya Ceper (Doctoral dissertation, Universitas Widya Dharma).
- Sugiyono, (2017). Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D. Bandung: CV. Alfabeta.
- Satato, Y. R., Adilase, B. P., & Subrata, G. (2022). Kompetensi, Disiplin Kerja Dan Budaya Kerja Pengaruhnya Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai. *Jurnal Ekonomi, Manajemen Pariwisata Dan Perhotelan*, 1(1).
- Simanjuntak, R. A., & Abdullah, R. (2018). Tinjauan Sistem dan Kinerja Manajemen Keselamatan & Kesehatan Kerja Tambang Bawah Tanah CV. Tahiti Coal, Talawi, Sawahlunto, Sumatera Barat. *Bina Tambang*, 3(4).

- Sinambela, Z. Y. (2018). Hubungan Antara Pengetahuan Dan Disiplin Dengan Perilaku Pekerja Diketinggian Pada Pemasangan Besi Proyek South Gate Tahun 2018 (Doctoral dissertation, Universitas Binawan).
- Zalzela, A. R., Mardiana, N., & Andriani, L. (2021). The Effect of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) and Work-Life Balance (WLB) on Employee Performance at PT. Singosari 23. *International Journal Of Education, Social Studies, And Management (IJESSM)*, 3(2).

Performance Optimization

Drixen Alexander Mawuntu¹, Muhammad Isa Indrawan²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: isaindrawan@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

This research was conducted to determine the influence of organizational culture and Employee Engagement on Employee Performance with Organizational Commitment as a Moderating Variable at the BPJS Employment Office, Medan City Branch and Sumbagut Regional Office. Organizations, both companies and government institutions, in carrying out their activities certainly need human resources that support efforts to achieve the goals set by the organization. The success of an agency/organization is not only determined by the facilities it has, but also the availability of reliable human resources. The results of this research are as follows: Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.226 and an ap value of 0.015. Employee Engagement has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.025. Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.457 and ap value of 0.003. Organizational culture's influence on employee performance is moderated by organizational commitment with an original sample value of -0.218 and ap value of 0.045. Employee Engagement influences employee performance, moderated by Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.098 and ap value of 0.228.

Keywords: Organizational Culture, Employee Engagement, Organizational Commitment, Employee Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Every organization needs human resources who are physically and mentally healthy, have a good mentality, discipline, enthusiasm, abilities and expertise that are in accordance with the challenges and needs of the world of work. Therefore, companies must maintain their employees because employees are one of the company's important assets. Achieving the goals of a company or government institution has many elements that are important in fulfilling them, including the organizational culture applied in the company or government institution. The resources that have been available if not managed properly will not achieve the planned goals, so that in essence organizational culture is an inseparable part of the internal environment of the organization because the diversity of cultures in an organization is as much as the number of individuals in the organization. Each individual who is part of an organization has a different culture, because they have different cultural backgrounds, but all these differences will be merged into one in a culture, namely organizational culture, to become a group that works together to achieve organizational goals as previously agreed upon, but in the process it is possible that there are individuals who can accept it and also those who cannot accept it, which may be contrary to the culture they have. In addition to organizational culture, the employee engagement factor is one of the things considered by management. Employee engagement emerged as an effort to develop previous concepts such as employee job satisfaction, employee commitment, and employee organizational behavior. Having employees who are actively involved in the company indicates that the company has

a positive work climate. Organizational commitment is often associated with the state in which an employee siding with a particular organization and its goals and desires to maintain membership in the organization. The following are some definitions of organizational commitment according to experts. Organizational commitment is an important behavioral dimension that can be used to assess the tendency of employees to remain as members of the organization. Organizational commitment is a person's relatively strong identification and involvement with the organization.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Organizational Culture have a positive and significant influence on the Performance of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Employees at the Medan City Branch and the North Sumatra Regional Office?
2. Does Employee Engagement have a positive and significant effect on the Employee Performance of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Medan City Branch and North Sumatra Regional Office?
3. Does Organizational Commitment have a positive and significant effect on the Performance of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Employees at the Medan City Branch and the North Sumatra Regional Office?
4. Does Organizational Culture have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance moderated by Organizational Commitment at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Medan City Branch and North Sumatra Regional Office?
5. Does Employee Engagement have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance moderated by Organizational Commitment at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Medan City Branch and North Sumatra Regional Office?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Medan City Branch and North Sumatra Regional Office.
2. To find out and analyze the influence of Employee Engagement on Employee Performance at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Medan City Branch and North Sumatra Regional Office.
3. To find out and analyze the influence of Organizational Commitment on Employee Performance at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Medan City Branch and North Sumatra Regional Office.
4. To find out and analyze the Organizational Culture that has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance moderated by Organizational Commitment at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Medan City Branch and North Sumatra Regional Office.
5. To find out and analyze Employee Engagement has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Medan City Branch and North Sumatra Regional Office.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee performance

Company performance can also be said to be good if there is a match between the workload given to each employee and the abilities possessed by the employee (Wibowo, 2016). Employee performance is the work achievement or work results, both in quality and quantity, achieved by an employee per unit of time period in carrying out his work duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. A company that has good performance if the company can achieve the company's goals.

Employee Performance Indicators

According to Wibowo, (2016:) performance indicators are:

- a. Objective
- b. Standard
- c. Feedback.
- d. Tools or means
- e. Competence
- f. Motive
- g. Opportunity

Organizational culture

Organizational culture is a habit that has been going on for a long time and is used and applied in work activities as one of the drivers to improve the quality of work of employees and company managers (Edison, 2016). According to Sedarmayanti (2017) organizational culture is an effective framework consisting of attitudes, values, norms of attitudes, and shared expectations experienced by members of the organization.

Organizational Culture Indicators

According to Edison (2016), the indicators of organizational culture are:

1. Member Self Awareness.

Organizations consciously work to gain satisfaction from their work, develop themselves, obey the rules, and offer high quality products and services.

2. Member Aggression

Organizations set challenging but realistic goals. They establish work plans and strategies to achieve those goals and work on them enthusiastically.

3. Member Personality

Be respectful, friendly, open and sensitive to group satisfaction and pay close attention to aspects of customer satisfaction, both internal and external customers (every internal part must serve, not be served).

4. Member Performance

The organization has values of creativity, fulfilling quality, standard, and efficiency.

5. Team Member Orientation

The organization carries out good cooperation, as well as effective communication and coordination with the active involvement of members which in turn results in high satisfaction and shared commitment.

Employee Engagement

Employees who have high engagement are usually described as having high enthusiasm, energy, and loyalty, as well as strong commitment and pride in the organization. Employee engagement cannot be separated from the performance of the organization/company because employees are the driving force of the company itself (Febriansyah & Ginting, 2020). Employee Engagement is part of the subject of human resource management in organizational practices because it is considered to have an impact on the results, services, and operations of the organization. Employee engagement is defined as a positive state related to work that is characterized by enthusiasm, dedication, and absorption (Turner, 2020). Employee engagement is an important factor for the success of an institution or company and can provide a competitive advantage for the company.

Employee Engagement Indicators

According to Febriansyah & Ginting (2020) it is as follows:

1. Growth is an opportunity for an employee to learn and grow.
2. Teamwork is feeling part of a team.
3. Management and support is having a feeling of success with their work, such as the opportunity to do their best.
4. Basic needs are needs that they must fulfill if they work, such as expectations.

Organizational Commitment

According to Wibowo (2017) organizational commitment is the desire of some workers to remain members of the organization. Organizational commitment is a condition in which an employee has loyalty to the organization where he works so that the employee can identify himself as part of the organization and mobilize all his abilities in the hope of achieving the company's goals.

Organizational Commitment Indicators

According to Wibowo (2017), indicators of organizational commitment are:

1. *Affective commitment* is an emotional complement and belief in the values of the organization.
2. *Continuance commitment*, is a feeling of residual economic value with the organization. Employees may have a commitment to an employer because they are well paid and feel they would hurt their family if they left their job.
3. *Normative commitment* is an obligation to remain in an organization for moral or ethical reasons. Employees who start a new initiative may stay with an employer because leaving would leave the employer in dire straits.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework in this research is as follows:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework
Source: Processed Data (2024)

Research Hypothesis

- H1: Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on the Performance of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Employees at the Medan City Branch and the North Sumatra Regional Office.
- H2: Employee Engagement has a positive and significant effect on the performance of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan employees at the Medan City Branch and the North Sumatra Regional Office.
- H3: Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on the Employee Performance of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan, Medan City Branch and North Sumatra Regional Office.
- H4: Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance moderated by Organizational Commitment at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Medan City Branch and North Sumatra Regional Office.
- H5: Employee Engagement has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance moderated by Organizational Commitment at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Medan City Branch and North Sumatra Regional Office.

METHOD

Types of research

The type of research is the form and procedure of research used, this research uses associative and quantitative research types, this method is used in research that has 2 or more

variables. This research is used to determine the influence of dependent and independent variables and their intervening variables. According to Ghazali (2016), associative research aims to determine the influence or relationship between two or more variables.

Research Population

According to Ghazali (2016) population is the sum of all objects or individual units observed in the study. The population in this study were all employees of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Medan City Branch and North Sumatra Regional Office totaling 70 people.

Samples and Sampling Techniques

According to Sugiyono, (2017) a sample is a part of a population that is a source of data in a study, where the population is part of the number of characteristics possessed by the population. The sampling technique according to Sugiyono, (2017) is a sampling technique, to determine the sample to be used. Therefore, the sample used as research material is all the population in the organization, namely 70 employees and the research technique used is the saturated sampling technique.

Place and Time of Research

This research is located at the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Regional Office of Sumbagut / Medan located at Jalan Kapten Pattimura No. 334 Floor II, Medan 20153. This research began in July - October 2024.

Method of collecting data

According to Sugiyono (2017) a questionnaire is a method of collecting data by providing written questions and statements to respondents to be answered. While secondary data comes from books and websites related to the problem to be discussed to be used as a guideline in research.

Data source

The data sources used by researchers are primary data sources where the data will be collected directly via questionnaires. According to Sugiyono (2017), primary sources are data that directly provide data to data collectors.

Data Analysis Methods

According to Imam Ghazali (2016) the PLS method is able to describe latent variables (not directly measurable) and is measured using indicators. Researchers use Partial Least Square because this study examines each existing indicator so that researchers can calculate the data in detail.

In statistical analysis of data using the PLS method. Here are the PLS method analysis techniques:

1. Outer model analysis

According to Husein (2015) outer model analysis is carried out to ensure that the measurements used are suitable for measurement (valid and reliable). There are several calculations in this analysis:

- a. Convergent validity is the factor loading value on the latent variable with its indicators. The expected value is > 0.7 .
- b. Discriminant validity is the crossloading value of factors that are useful for determining whether a construct has adequate discriminant. The method is to compare the value of the intended construct which must be greater than the value of the other construct.
- c. Composite reliability is a measurement that if the reliability value is > 0.7 then the construct value has a high reliability value.
- d. Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is the average variance which is at least 0.5.
- e. Cronbach alpha is a calculation to prove the results of composite reliability where the minimum value is 0.6.

2. Inner model analysis

In this model analysis is to test the relationship between latent constructs. There are several calculations in this analysis R Square is the coefficient of determination on endogenous constructs. According to Chin (1998) in Sarwono (2015) explains "the criteria for the limits of the R square value in three classifications, namely 0.67 as substantial; 0.33 as moderate and 0.19 as weak".

3. Hypothesis testing

In his book Husein (2015) hypothesis testing can be seen from the t-statistic value and probability value. For hypothesis testing, namely by using statistical values, then for alpha 5% the t-statistic value used is 1.96. So the criteria for accepting or rejecting the hypothesis are H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected when the t-statistic > 1.96 . To reject or accept the hypothesis using probability, H_a is accepted if the p value < 0.05 .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Test

The test results show that there are four variables in the model that will be used in the research, as shown below:

Evaluation of measurement model (outer model)

Convergent Validity

In this test, the loading factor limit value is 0.7 and the AVE limit value is 0.5, above which value is considered valid. The indicator is said to be valid if the value is > 0.7 in explaining the construction variable. The structural model of this study can be seen in the following figure.

Figure 2. Research Model

Smart PLS output for loading factor gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two equations.

$$Y = b_1X_1 + b_2Z + b_3X_1Z + e_1$$

$$Y = 0.226 X_1 + 0.457Z - 0.218 X_1Z + e_1$$

$$Y = b_2X_2 + b_3Z + b_4X_2Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.324X_2 + 0.457 Z + 0.098X_2Z + e_2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings/Cross Loading

Organizational Culture (X1)	Employee Engagement (X2)	Employee Performance (Y)	Organizational Commitment (Z)
0.796			
0.846			
0.761			
0.766			
0.853			
	0.823		
	0.861		
	0.778		
	0.787		
		0.865	
		0.827	
		0.861	
		0.846	

		0.865	
		0.783	
		0.827	
			0.825
			0.926
			0.847

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

In table 1, the value of each variable shows that the indicators in each variable have a value above 0.7, meaning that each aspect of the indicator has a value above 0.7 so that the data is considered valid for further research.

Discriminant Validity

Discussion will be conducted regarding the findings of the discriminant validity test in this section. The cross loading value is used to test the discriminant validity. If the cross loading value on an indicator exceeds the value of another variable, it indicates discriminant validity. The cross loading value for each indicator is as follows:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Organizational Culture (X1)	Employee Engagement (X2)	Employee Performance (Y)	Organizational Commitment (Z)
X1.1	0.796	0.668	0.611	0.617
X1.2	0.846	0.678	0.690	0.601
X1.3	0.761	0.677	0.619	0.639
X1.4	0.766	0.704	0.650	0.641
X1.5	0.853	0.783	0.682	0.744
X2.1	0.786	0.823	0.688	0.773
X2.2	0.806	0.861	0.834	0.807
X2.3	0.595	0.778	0.693	0.731
X2.4	0.634	0.787	0.651	0.670
Y.1	0.747	0.749	0.865	0.760
Y.2	0.733	0.732	0.827	0.700
Y.3	0.745	0.856	0.861	0.847
Y.4	0.630	0.715	0.846	0.658
Y.5	0.698	0.789	0.865	0.829
Y.6	0.639	0.685	0.783	0.629
Y.7	0.530	0.657	0.827	0.653
Z.1	0.705	0.755	0.693	0.825
Z.2	0.747	0.861	0.823	0.926
Z.3	0.644	0.771	0.743	0.847

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

Based on table 2, the cross loading of each variable has a loading factor value that is greater than the cross loading value and a high loading factor between variables, so this test is considered valid in terms of discriminant validity, so that the next research stage can be carried out.

Composite reliability

In composite reliability analysis, the reliability value of each variable is examined. Research is considered reliable if the variable value is more than 0.60, but not reliable if the value is below 0.60 to 0.7. There are several evaluation blocks that can determine the reliability and validity of research, such as Coanbach alpha, composite reliability, and AVE values listed in the table below.

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Organizational Culture (X1)	0.864	0.902	0.649
Moderation Effect 1	1,000	1,000	1,000
Moderation Effect 2	1,000	1,000	1,000
Employee Engagement (X2)	0.829	0.886	0.661
Employee Performance (Y)	0.930	0.944	0.705
Organizational Commitment (Z)	0.834	0.901	0.752

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

In table 3, it can be seen that all variable values in the Cronbach alpha column are greater than 0.7, indicating high data reliability for each variable. It is known that the composite reliability column has a value greater than 0.6, indicating that each variable is considered reliable because the data is above 0.6. It must be checked in the AVE column whether each variable has a value above 0.7, indicating the validity of the data by AVE. All variable values in the Cronbach alpha, reliability, and AVE columns are above 0.7 and 0.6, so they are considered reliable and valid.

Inner Model Analysis

Inner model evaluation is conducted to ensure the strength and accuracy of the basic model created. Some markers considered in the primary model assessment are the stages of examination carried out.

Coefficient of Determination (R2)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Employee Performance (Y)	0.821	0.807

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

There is an r square value of 0.821 with a percentage of 82.1%, meaning that the influence of Organizational Culture and Employee Engagement on employee performance is 0.821 or 82.1%, the rest is in other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After determining the inner model, the next step is to determine the relationship between idle build and the data in this case. Statistical analysis in this case study is done by looking at T-Statistics and P-Values. Speculation is used to find out whether the T-Insights value is > 1.96 and P-Values < 0.05 . Here is the impact of the Impact Road Coefficient slowly:

Table 5. Results of the Moderation Hypothesis

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Organizational Culture (X1) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.226	2,186	0.015	Accepted
Moderation Effect 1 -> Employee Performance (Y)	-0.218	1,696	0.045	Accepted
Moderation Effect 2 -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.098	0.747	0.228	Rejected
Employee Engagement (X2) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.324	1,960	0.025	Accepted
Organizational Commitment (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.457	2,784	0.003	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

The results of the hypothesis above are as follows:

1. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.226 and p values of 0.015. This means that if organizational culture increases, employee performance will also increase, conversely, if it decreases, employee performance will decrease.
2. Employee Engagement has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.025. This means that if Employee Engagement increases, employee performance will increase, conversely if it decreases, employee performance will decrease.
3. Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.457 and p values of 0.003. This means that if organizational commitment increases, employee performance will increase, conversely, if it decreases, employee performance will decrease.

4. Organizational Culture influences Employee Performance moderated by Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of -0.218 and p values of 0.045. This means that commitment is a moderating variable but organizational commitment weakens organizational culture on employee performance.
5. Employee Engagement has an effect on Employee Performance moderated by Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.098 and p values of 0.228. This means that commitment is not a moderating variable in the second moderation effect because it is unable to have a significant effect.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.226 and p values of 0.015.
2. Employee Engagement has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.025.
3. Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.457 and p values of 0.003.
4. Organizational Culture influences Employee Performance moderated by Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of -0.218 and p values of 0.045.
5. Employee Engagement has an effect on Employee Performance moderated by Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.098 and p values of 0.228.

Suggestion

1. It is hoped that this research will be used as input for the organization so that it can be better than before.
2. Organizations must build a good and healthy organizational culture for the development of employee and organizational performance.
3. The organization must involve all employees and other staff in the organization.
4. It is hoped that this research can be used as reference material for further research.
5. It is hoped that this research can help new researchers and be used as a companion to other research with almost the same title.

REFERENCES

- Djunaedi, A., Subiyakto, A., & Fetrina, E. (2017). Sistem Pendukung Keputusan Penilaian Kinerja Pegawai (Studi Kasus : Pt . Pln (Persero Distribusi Jakarta Raya Area Pondok Gede)). *Jurnal Sistem Informasi*, 10(1), 37–44.
- Ginting H, Febriansyah H. *Copenhagen Psychosocial Questionnaire (COPSOQ) III Omnibus Survei Faktor-Faktor Psikososial di Tempat Kerja*. 1st ed. Jakarta: Prenadamedia Group; 2020.
- Ghozali. (2016). *Structural Equation Modeling Metode Alternatif dengan Partial Least Square (PLS)*. Semarang: Universitas Diponegoro

- Kreitner, Robert dan Angelo Kinicki. 2014. *Perilaku Organisasi*. Edisi 9. Buku 1. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- Poltak Sinambela dan Sarton Sinambela. 2019. *Manajemen Kinerja Pengelolaan Pengukuran, dan Implikasi Kinerja*. Depok: RajaGratindo Persada.
- Robbins, Stephen P & Judge, Timothy A. 2013. *Organizational Behavior Edition 15*. New Jersey: Pearson Education
- Robinson et. al, (2004). *The Drivers of Employee Engagement Report 408*. UK: Institute for Employment Studie
- Sedarmayanti. 2017. *Sumber Daya Manusia dan Produktivitas Kerja*. Bandung: Mandar Maju.
- Singarimbun, M dan S. Effendi (Editor). 1989. *Metode Penelitian Survy*. LP3S, Jakarta
- Sugiyono. (2017). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung : Alfabeta, CV.
- Turner, D. P. (2020). *Sampling Methods in Research Design*. *Headache*, 60, 8-12. <https://doi.org/10.1111/head.13707>
- Wibowo, Endro dan Hardi Utomo. (2016). *Pengaruh Keselamatan Kerja dan Kesehatan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja dengan Kepuasan Kerja Sebagai Variabel Intervening*, Vol.9 No.17.

Performance Determinants

Ikhlasul Amal Maulana¹, Kiki Farida Ferine²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: kikifarida@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

This research aims to examine the influence of organizational culture and individual characteristics on the performance of employees of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Aceh Raya Branch Office with work experience as a moderating variable. The type of research that researchers use is quantitative research. The population and sample in this research are all permanent employees at PT. BPJS Employment Banda Aceh Branch Office has 70 employees (saturated sample). Data analysis in this research uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on Partial Least Square (PLS). The results of this research are as follows: Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.334 and a p value of 0.007. Individual Character has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.382 and a p value of 0.069. Work Experience has a positive and insignificant effect with an original sample value of 0.258 and a p value of 0.147. Organizational culture has a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance and work experience is not able to moderate it with the original sample result being 0.079 and p value 0.671. Individual characteristics have a negative and insignificant effect and are moderated by work experience with an original sample value of -0.084 and a p value of 0.597.

Keywords: Organizational Culture, Individual Characteristics, Work Experience, Employee Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Humans (employees) are creatures who work in an organizational environment, they need each other and cooperation is an inseparable part of life and humans are also individualistic creatures who have egos and determination. Leaders are part of the human resource development process, where human resources are assets of an organization or industry which, if managed properly, can produce added value for the company (Prasetyani, 2020). According to (Djunaedi, 2017) employee performance is the result of work in terms of quantity and quality that has been achieved by employees in carrying out a task given to them. According to Riani (2015) organizational culture is the norms and values that show the attitudes of members of the organization. Each member should behave well with the culture that has been implemented in order to be accepted in the organizational environment. According to Thoha. (2015) related to individual characteristics, that individuals bring into the organizational structure, abilities, personal beliefs, expectations of needs and past experiences. These are all characteristics possessed by individuals and these characteristics will enter a new environment, namely the organization. The most important resource in an organization is human resources, every human being has individual characteristics that differ from one another. The future of an individual in an organization does not depend on performance alone. Managers also use subjective measures that are judgmental. What is perceived by the assessor as a good or bad employee character/behavior will affect the assessment.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Organizational Culture Have a Positive and Significant Influence on BPJS Employment Employee Performance? All over Greater Aceh?
2. Do Individual Characteristics Have a Positive and Significant Influence on the Performance of BPJS Employment Branch Employees? All over Greater Aceh?
3. Does Work Experience Have a Positive and Significant Influence on the Performance of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Employees at Branch Offices in Aceh Raya?
4. Does Organizational Culture Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Employee Performance Moderated by Work Experience at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices in Aceh Raya?
5. Do Individual Characteristics Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Employee Performance Moderated by Work Experience at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices in Aceh Raya?

Research purposes

1. To find out and analyze the influence of Organizational Culture on the Performance of BPJS Employment Branch Employees All over Greater Aceh
2. To find out and analyze the influence of individual characteristics on the performance of BPJS Employment Branch Employees All over Greater Aceh
3. To find out and analyze the influence of work experience on the performance of BPJS Employment employees at branch offices throughout Aceh Raya.
4. To find out and analyze the influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance moderated by Work Experience at BPJS Employment Branch Offices in Aceh Raya
5. To find out and analyze the influence of Individual Characteristics on Employee Performance moderated by Work Experience at BPJS Employment Branch Offices in Aceh Raya

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee performance

According to Silaen (2021) Employee performance is the work results achieved by a person in carrying out the tasks assigned to him to achieve work targets. Employees can work well if they have high performance so that they can produce good work. According to Mangkunegara (2017) the term performance comes from the word job performance or actual performance (work performance or actual performance achieved by a person). The definition of employee performance is the work results in terms of quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties according to the responsibilities given to him.

Performance Indicators

According to Silaen (2021) the performance indicators are as follows:

- a. Quality of Work.
- b. Quantity of Work.

- c. Punctuality.
- d. Effectiveness.
- e. Commitment.

Organizational culture

According to Robbins (2015) organizational culture refers to a system of shared meaning held by members that distinguishes the organization from other organizations. According to Afandi (2018) Organizational Culture is an invisible force that can influence the thoughts, feelings and actions of people who work in an organization. Organizational Culture includes values that have the same meaning for its members as well as the same beliefs about the existence of the organization and certain behaviors that are expected to be displayed by all members of the organization.

Organizational Culture Indicators

According to Afandi (2018) the indicators of organizational culture are as follows:

- a. Implementation of norms.
- b. Implementation of values
- c. Trust
- d. Implementation of the code of ethics

Individual Characteristics

According to Hanifah (2019) Individual characteristics are that each person has different views, goals, needs and abilities from each other. According to Rahman (2014), individual characteristics are distinctive features that show a person's differences in motivation, initiative, ability to remain steadfast in facing tasks until completion or solving problems or how to adapt to changes that are closely related to the environment that affect individual performance.

Individual Characteristics Indicators

Individual characteristic indicators according to Hanifah (2019) are as follows:

- 1. Ability
- 2. Mark
- 3. Attitude
- 4. Interest

Work experience

According to Muhibbang (2014) Work experience is a measure of the length of time or work period that someone has taken to understand the tasks of a job and have carried them out well. According to Foster (2015) work experience is one of the most important factors in a company. Employees who have a lot of work experience will adapt very easily to the existing work. Work experience is the main capital for someone to enter a certain field.

Work Experience Indicator

According to Foster (2015) the work experience indicators are:

1. Length of time/work period.
2. The level of knowledge and skills possessed.
3. Mastery of the job.

Conceptual Framework

To get a simpler picture, it can be explained using the following scheme:

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework
Source: Processed by the Author (2024)

Hypothesis

- H1: Organizational Culture has a positive and significant influence on the performance of BPJS Employment employees at branch offices throughout Aceh Raya.
- H2: Individual Characteristics have a positive and significant effect on the Performance of BPJS Employment Employees at Branch Offices throughout Aceh Raya.
- H3: Work experience has a positive and significant effect on the performance of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan employees at branch offices throughout Aceh Raya.
- H4: Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance moderated by Work Experience at BPJS Employment Branch Offices in Aceh Raya
- H5: Individual Characteristics have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance moderated by Work Experience at BPJS Employment Branch Offices in Aceh Raya

Research Methods

According to Sugiyono (2017), quantitative research can be interpreted as a method based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research a particular population or sample, sampling techniques are generally carried out randomly, data collection uses research instruments, data analysis is quantitative/statistical with the aim of testing the established hypothesis.

This research was conducted at BPJS Employment Branches in Aceh Raya:

1. BPJS Employment Langsa: Jl. Ahmad Yani, Baro Village, Old Langsa, Langsa City (15 Employees)
2. BPJS Employment Meulaboh Jl. National Meulaboh - Tapaktuan KM 4 Meureubo Village, Meureubo District, West Aceh Regency (15 Employees)
3. BPJS Employment Lhokseumawe Jl. Teuku Hamzah Bendarar, Simpang Empat Banda Sakti, Lhokseumawe City (15 Employees)
4. BPJS Employment Banda Aceh Jl. T. Daud Beureueh No.152 Banda Aceh City (25 employees)

This research started in August - October 2024

Population

The population and sample in this study were all permanent employees at PT. BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices in Aceh Raya totaling 70 employees (saturated sample).

Data Analysis Techniques

Data analysis in this study uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on Partial Least Square (PLS) using SmartPLS 3.3.3 software. According to Gozali (2014) Partial Least Square (PLS) is a fairly strong analysis method because it is not based on many assumptions.

Measurement Model (Outer Model)

The procedure in testing the measurement model consists of validity testing and reliability testing.

1. Validity Test
 - a. Convergent Validity
 - b. Discriminant Validity
2. Reliability Test. Cronbach's alpha value is recommended to be greater than 0.7 and composite reliability is also recommended to be greater than 0.7 (Sekaran, 2014).

Structural Model (Inner Model)

This test is conducted to determine the relationship between exogenous and endogenous constructs that have become hypotheses in this study (Hair et al., 2017). To produce inner model test values, the steps in SmartPLS are carried out using the bootstrapping method. The structural model is evaluated using R-square for the dependent variable, the Stone-Geisser Q-square test for predictive elevation and the t-test and significance of the structural path parameter coefficients with the following explanation:

1. Coefficient of Determination / R Square (R²)
2. Predictive Relevance (Q²)
3. t-Statistic
4. Path Coefficient

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Instrument Test

Through the use of initial questionnaire instrument testing, the validity and reliability of the variables and indicators collected for this study have been examined. The test findings indicate that the model to be used in the study has four variables, namely as follows:

Evaluation of measurement model (outer model)

Figure 2. Research Model

The equations in this study are as follows:

$$Y: b_1X_1 + b_2Z + b_3X_1Z + e_1$$

$$Y: 0.334 X_1 + 0.258 Z + 0.079X_1Z + e_2$$

$$Y: b_2X_2 + b_3Z + b_4X_2Z + e_2$$

$$Y: 0.382X_2 + 0.258Z + 0.084X_2Z + e_2$$

Validity and reliability tests are used to evaluate the measurement model, also known as the external model. The loading factor value of each indicator is determined through a validity test; an indicator is considered valid if its loading factor value is 0.7 or more. Table 1 shows that certain indicators have a loading factor value of less than 0.7, which means that these indicators will be removed in the next stage. After the invalid indicators are removed, the final model produced will look like Figure 2.

Table 1. Recapitulation of Research Indicator Loading Factor Values

	Organizational Culture (X1)	Individual Characteristics (X2)	Employee Performance (Y)	Work Experience (Z)
X1.1	0.915			
X1.2	0.834			
X1.3	0.881			
X1.4	0.890			

X2.1		0.895		
X2.2		0.843		
X2.3		0.909		
X2.4		0.798		
Y.1			0.826	
Y.2			0.770	
Y.3			0.833	
Y.4			0.882	
Y.5			0.747	
Z.1				0.882
Z.2				0.849
Z.3				0.878

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3

In the figure and table 1, all loading factor indicators have a value > 0.7 , meaning that the indicator is a valid indicator because it is greater than 0.700 or 0.7.

Discriminant Validity

The findings of the discriminant validity test will be discussed in this section. The cross loading value is used for the discriminant validity test. If the cross loading value of an indicator on a variable is greater than that of another variable, then it is said to indicate discriminant validity. The cross loading value for each indicator is as follows:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Organizational Culture (X1)	Individual Characteristics (X2)	Employee Performance (Y)	Work Experience (Z)
X1.1	0.915	0.859	0.819	0.880
X1.2	0.834	0.595	0.732	0.628
X1.3	0.881	0.773	0.764	0.753
X1.4	0.890	0.822	0.843	0.864
X2.1	0.743	0.895	0.723	0.806
X2.2	0.813	0.843	0.854	0.792
X2.3	0.782	0.909	0.813	0.814
X2.4	0.647	0.798	0.697	0.755
Y.1	0.744	0.693	0.826	0.745
Y.2	0.693	0.660	0.770	0.639
Y.3	0.781	0.805	0.833	0.759
Y.4	0.771	0.812	0.882	0.838
Y.5	0.657	0.681	0.747	0.689
Z.1	0.760	0.745	0.725	0.882

Z.2	0.771	0.802	0.839	0.849
Z.3	0.794	0.845	0.788	0.878

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3

Based on the cross loading value, all indicators have a larger correlation coefficient with each construct compared to the correlation coefficient value of the indicators in other constructs.

Composite reliability

The combined reliability test of the indicator block, which measures the construct, is conducted next. If the combined reliability value of a construct is more than 0.60, it is considered reliable. In addition, it can be observed by testing the reliability of the construct or latent variable determined by examining the Cronbach's alpha value in the indicator block. If the Cronbach's alpha value of a construct is more than 0.7, it is considered reliable.

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Organizational Culture (X1)	0.903	0.932	0.776
Moderation Effect 1	1,000	1,000	1,000
Moderation Effect 2	1,000	1,000	1,000
Individual Characteristics (X2)	0.884	0.920	0.744
Employee Performance (Y)	0.871	0.907	0.662
Work Experience (Z)	0.839	0.903	0.756

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3

In table 3, it can be seen in the Cronbach alpha column that the value of each variable is greater than 0.7, which indicates that the reliability data of the variable is reliable. Because the data is more than 0.6, it can be explained that each variable is considered reliable in the Composite Reliability column, the value of which is greater than 0.6. Each variable in the AVE column has a value greater than 0.7, this indicates that the data is valid according to the AVE standard. Because all variables in the reliability, AVE, and Cronbach alpha columns have values greater than 0.7 and 0.6, respectively, all are considered valid and reliable.

Inner Model Analysis

Structural model evaluation (inner model) is conducted to ensure that the basic model created is strong and accurate. The stages of examination conducted in the primary model assessment are seen from several markers, namely:

1. Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Employee Performance (Y)	0.876	0.867

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3

There is an R square value for Employee Performance of 0.876 with a percentage of 87.6%, meaning that the influence of Organizational Culture, Individual Characteristics moderated by Work Experience on Employee Performance is 0.876 or 87.6% and the rest is in other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After examining the inner model, the next step is to analyze the relationship between idle build as suspected in this study. Speculation testing in this review is done by looking at T-Statistics and P-Values. It is stated openly whether P-Values are less than 0.05 and T-Insights values are greater than 1.96. The following is the direct impact of the Path Coefficient:

Table 5. Hypothesis Testing

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Organizational Culture (X1) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.334	2,714	0.007	Accepted
Moderation Effect 1 -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.079	0.425	0.671	Rejected
Moderation Effect 2 -> Employee Performance (Y)	-0.084	0.529	0.597	Rejected
Individual Characteristics (X2) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.382	1,821	0.069	Rejected
Work Experience (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.258	1,452	0.147	Rejected

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3

In the hypothesis results in table 5, the explanation of the hypothesis results is as follows:

1. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.334 and p values of 0.007. This means that if

organizational culture improves well, employee performance will also improve well. And if it decreases, employee performance will decrease.

2. Individual Character has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.382 and p values of 0.069. This means that the characteristics have a positive but insignificant effect in this study, it is possible that in other studies this will have a positive and significant effect.
3. Work Experience has a positive and insignificant effect with the original sample value of 0.258 and p values of 0.147. This means that work experience does have a positive effect on employee performance in this study and it is possible that in other studies and other places, these results can be positive and significant.
4. Organizational Culture has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance and work experience is not able to moderate with the original sample results of 0.079 and p values 0.671. This means that work experience is not able to moderate organizational culture on employee performance because it does not have a significant effect.
5. Individual Characteristics have a negative and insignificant effect and are moderated by work experience with an original sample value of -0.084 and p values of 0.597. This means that work experience is unable to moderate individual characteristics on employee performance because it does not have a significant effect.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.334 and p values of 0.007.
2. Individual Character has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.382 and p values of 0.069.
3. Work experience has a positive and insignificant effect with an original sample value of 0.258 and p values of 0.147.
4. Organizational Culture has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance and work experience is unable to moderate with the original sample results of 0.079 and p values of 0.671.
5. Individual Characteristics have a negative and insignificant influence and are moderated by work experience with an original sample value of -0.084 and p values of 0.597.

Suggestion

1. It is hoped that the organization can use input and lessons to cover or reduce mistakes, shortcomings and disputes between employees in order to advance the organization.
2. It is hoped that this research can be used as reference material for other research with the title others and other models.
3. Organizations must change bad organizational culture by conducting briefings with superiors.
4. Each employee has different characteristics. The organization must be able to master and understand the characteristics of each employee.

REFERENCES

- A.A. Anwar Prabu Mangkunegara (2017), *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan*, Bandung : Remaja Rosdakarya
- Afandi, P. (2018). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia (Teori, Konsep dan Indikator)*. Riau: Zanafa Publishing.
- Djunaedi, A., Subiyakto, A., & Fetrina, E. (2017). Sistem Pendukung Keputusan Penilaian Kinerja Pegawai (Studi Kasus : Pt . Pln (Persero Distribusi Jakarta Raya Area Pondok Gede)). *Jurnal Sistem Informasi*, 10(1), 37–44
- Fauziah, Nur Hanifah (2019), *Pengaruh Karakteristik Individu dan Budaya Organisasi terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Bagian Twisting pada PT. Dewa Sutratex II Cimahi*.
- Foster, B. (2015). *Pembinaan untuk meningkatkan Kinerja Pegawai*. Jakarta: PPM.
- Ghozali, (2014). *Aplikasi analisis Multivariate dengan Program SPSS*. Badan Penerbit UNDIP. Semarang
- Hair, J. F. et. al. (2017), *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)*. SAGE Publications, Los Angeles.
- Hasibuan, Malayu. (2017), *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- Heidjrachman, Ranupandojo (2017), *Manajemen Personalialia*. Yogyakarta: BPFE Yogyakarta.
- Manullang, (2016), *Dasar_Dasar Manajemen*, Gadjah Mada University Press. P.O.BOX 14, Bulaksumur, Yogyakarta.
- Muhibbang. (2014), *Pengaruh Motivasi dan Pengalaman Kerja Terhadap Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan Pada PT. Bosowa Berlian Motor Makassar*. Universitas Hasanuddin, Makassar.
- Pangarso, Astadi, dan Susanti, P. I. (2016), *Pengaruh Disiplin Kerja terhadap Kinerja Pegawai di Biro Pelayanan Sosial Dasar Sekretariat Daerah Provinsi Jawa Barat*. *Jurnal Manajemen Teori Terapan*, (2), 145–160.
- Prasetyani, D. (2020), *Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Dan Motivasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada PT. Surya Barutama Di Balaraja*. *Jurnal Manajemen Dan Akuntansi*, 15(2), 96–106
- Sekaran, Uma (2014). *Metodologi Penelitian Untuk Bisnis (Research Methods for Business)* Buku 1 Edisi 4. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- Silaen, Novia Ruth., Syamsuransyah., Reni Chairunnisah., dkk (2021) *Kinerja Karyawan*, (Edisi 1, Cetakan Pertama) Bandung: Widina Bhakti Persada
- Stephen, Robbins (2015), *Perilaku Organisasi*, Penerbit Salemba Empat, Jakarta
- Sugiyono, (2017), *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: CV. Alfabeta.
- Thoha, M. (2015). *Kepemimpinan dalam Manajemen Suatu Pendekatan Perilaku*, Cetakan Kesembilan, Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo Persada.

Strategies To Improve Performance

Sarinah Pohan¹, Wilchan Robain², Sri Rahayu³

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: sarinapohan06111983@gmail.com

Abstract

This research was carried out to see the influence of Work Ethic and Work Discipline on Employee Performance with Competence as an Intervening Variable in the State Civil Service in Medan Baru District. This research used a path analysis model with the smart PLS version 3.3.3 measurement method. Data collection was carried out by giving questionnaires to respondents. This type of research uses quantitative research and primary data sources as the data source. The results of this research are as follows: Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.427 and a p value of 0.006. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Competency with an original sample value of 0.756 and a p value of 0.000. Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.267 and a p value of 0.006. Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on Competency with an original sample value of 0.234 and a p value of 0.000. Competency has a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.277 and a p value of 0.059. Work Discipline has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance indirectly through Competency with an original sample value of 0.209 and a p value of 0.059. Work Ethic has a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance indirectly through Competency with an original sample value of 0.065 and a p value of 0.091.

Keywords: Work Discipline, Work Ethic, Competence, Employee Performance.

INTRODUCTION

In this era of globalization, human resources are used as a mainstay for companies to achieve success. Human resources are the main role in a company. Human resources in every organization are one of the important factors, especially in terms of quality. The importance of human resources in an organization can be said that humans (employees) are the most valuable assets that have a direct impact on the welfare of the organization compared to other resources. Work ethic must be possessed by every employee in carrying out their work so that they can work well and effectively in achieving organizational goals. Work ethic is said to be a determining factor in the success of individuals, groups, institutions and also the broadest is the nation in achieving its goals. In the implementation of public administration is also influenced by the work ethic possessed by public officials in their duties to organize the needs of the community. Discipline is useful for educating employees to obey and enjoy existing regulations, procedures, and policies, so that they can produce good performance. Discipline is a mental attitude that consciously and consciously obeys orders or prohibitions on something because it fully understands the importance of these orders and prohibitions. Competence shows skills or knowledge that are characterized by professionalism in a particular field as something that is most important, as the superiority of that field. Employees with competence, knowledge and abilities are needed to answer these challenges, so that they can adapt to change and competition, and carry out work according to their respective fields of work, so that the service provided is maximized. According to Torang in

(Ferine, 2021) performance is the quantity or quality of the work results of individuals or groups within an organization in carrying out main tasks and functions that are guided by norms, standard operating procedures, criteria and measures that have been established or that apply in the organization. Performance basically includes a mental attitude and behavior that always has the view that the work currently being carried out must be of better quality than the implementation of past work, for the future to be of better quality than the present. Every company in carrying out its activities must have goals that it wants to achieve, to achieve or realize these goals every company must be clever in choosing strategies, especially human resource planning which is essentially focused on certain steps taken by management.

Work ethic

According to Ginting (2016), work ethic is a work spirit that is a special characteristic of a person or group of people who work, which is based on ethics or work perspectives that are believed in. According to Priansa (2018), work ethic is a work spirit possessed by employees to be able to work better in order to obtain added value in a job.

Work Ethic Indicator

Work ethic indicators according to Priansa (2018) are:

1. Interpersonal skills relate to an employee's ability to establish working relationships with other people both within and outside the organization.
2. Initiative is a characteristic that can facilitate employees to be motivated to further improve their performance.
3. Dependability is an aspect related to the existence of expectations regarding employee performance and is an implicit agreement by employees to carry out several job functions.

Work Discipline

According to Sinambela (2018), it can be concluded that: Work discipline is the awareness and willingness of employees to obey all organizational regulations and applicable social norms.

According to Agustini (2019), work discipline is an attitude of obedience to the rules and norms that apply in a company in order to increase employee determination in achieving company/organizational goals.

Work Discipline Indicators

According to Agustini (2019) the indicators of work discipline are as follows:

1. Attendance rate, namely the number of employees present to carry out work activities in the company which is characterized by a low level of employee absence.
2. Work procedures, namely rules or provisions that must be adhered to by all members of the organization.

3. Obedience to superiors, namely following what is directed by superiors to get good results.
4. Work awareness, namely the attitude of a person who voluntarily does his work well, not because of coercion.
5. Responsibility, namely the employee's willingness to be responsible for their work, the facilities and infrastructure used, and their work behavior.

Competence

According to Gultom (2019), competence is a person's ability to produce at a satisfactory level in the workplace, including a person's ability to transfer and apply these skills and knowledge in new situations and increase agreed benefits.

According to Rahmat (2019), competence is a person's characteristics related to effective and/or superior performance in certain work situations.

Competency Indicators

According to Rahmat (2019), competency indicators are:

1. A motive is something a person consistently thinks about or wants that causes action.
2. Traits are physical characteristics and consistent responses to situations or information.
3. Self-concept is a person's attitudes, values, or self-image.
4. Knowledge is information that people have in a specific field.
5. Skill is the ability to perform a specific physical or mental task.

Employee Performance

According to Afandi (2021), performance is the willingness of a person or group of people to carry out or improve activities according to their responsibilities with the expected results.

According to Kasmir (2019), performance is the result of work and actions achieved by fulfilling the tasks and responsibilities given within a certain period of time.

Employee Performance Indicators

Performance indicators according to Kasmir (2019) are as follows:

1. Quality (Quality), namely performance measurement can be done by looking at the quality (quality) of work produced by a particular process.
2. Quantity, namely to measure performance, can also be done by looking at the quantity (amount) produced by a person.
3. Time, namely for certain types of work, there is a deadline for completing the work. If there is a violation or non-compliance with the deadline, it can be assumed that the performance is not good and vice versa.
4. Punctuality is where activities can be completed or production results can be achieved within a specified time period.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

1. Work Ethic has a positive and significant influence on Competence in ASN in Medan Baru District.
2. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Competence in ASN in Medan Baru District.
3. Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance in ASN in Medan Baru District.
4. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at ASN in Medan Baru District.
5. Competence has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance in ASN in Medan Baru District.
6. Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Competence in ASN in Medan Baru District.
7. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Competence in ASN in Medan Baru District.

METHOD

According to Sugiyono (2017), quantitative research methods can be interpreted as research methods based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations or samples, sampling techniques are generally carried out randomly, data collection uses research instruments, data analysis is quantitative/statistical, with the aim of testing the established hypothesis.

Research Data Sources

Primary data according to Sugiyono (2017) is a data source that directly provides data to data collectors. Primary data in this study is a questionnaire distributed to respondents.

Population

The population in this study was 61 civil servant employees of Medan Baru District with 6 sub-districts, including Petisah Hulu Sub-district 8 employees, Babura Sub-district 10 employees, Merdeka Sub-district 11 employees, Darat Sub-district 12 employees, Padang Bulan Sub-district 9 employees, Titi Rantai Sub-district 11 employees.

Sample

The sample used in this study was the entire population, namely 61 employees of Medan Baru District, so this study used a saturated sampling technique, namely taking the entire population as a sample.

Time and place of research

This research was conducted in 6 sub-districts of Medan Baru district, namely Petisah Hulu Sub-district, Babura Sub-district, Merdeka Sub-district, Darat Sub-district, Padang Bulan Sub-district, Titi Rantai Sub-district. The research was conducted from August to October 2024.

Data collection

According to Sugiyono (2017), data collection methods or techniques can be carried out through interviews, questionnaires, observations, and a combination of the three.

Data analysis

Research data management The software for this is smartPLS 3.3.3. The (Partial Least Square) PLS methodology is distribution-free assuming no specific data and can work with nominal, categorical, ordinal, interval, and ratio data. When using bootstrapping or random multiplication techniques, (Partial Least Square) PLS has no problem with the assumption of normality. In addition, PLS (Partial Least Square) does not need to use a minimum number of samples. Small sample sizes in research can still be used using PLS (Partial Least Square) According to (Ghozali, 2018). Someone classifies partial least squares as Therefore, for PLS modeling data that is normally distributed, a non-parametric type is not required. The analysis approach used in the PLS (Partial Least Square) method is as follows:

1. Outer model analysis

To ensure that the measurement is worthy of being used as a measuring tool (valid and reliable), an outer model analysis is carried out. This model describes the relationship between a latent variable and indicators in the study. Several indicators show the existence of an outer model analysis:

- a. Convergent Validity, The standard loading factor, which indicates the strength of the correlation between each measurement item (indicator) and its construct, is used to evaluate convergent validity (Ghozali, 2018). This indicator is based on the correlation between item scores/component scores and construct scores. When an individual's reflective measure correlates more than 0.7 with the expected construct, then the

measure is considered highly measured, while an outer loading value between 0.5 - 0.6 is considered sufficient (Ghozali, 2018).

- b. Discriminant Validity, is a cross-loading measurement model with reflective indications based on construction (Ghozali, 2018). In the case of construction tolerance with adjustment items is greater than other construction tolerances, then the resulting block size will be more profitable when compared to other block sizes. However, another method to determine discriminant validity is to compare the square root of the average variance extracted (AVE).
- c. Composite reliability, is a metric used to measure something that is seen in the display of latent variable coefficients (Ghozali, 2018). Internal consistency and Cronbach's alpha are two measurement tools used to assess composite reliability. If the measurement result is more than 0.70, this concept can be considered to have a high level of reliability.
- d. Cronbach's Alpha is a reliability test conducted to support composite reliability findings. If the Cronbach's alpha value of a variable is more than 0.7, it can be considered reliable (Ghozali, 2018).

2. Inner Model Analysis

Analyzing The term “inner model” can also refer to “inner relationships, structural models, and substantive theories,” which describe the relationship between the latter variables and substantive theories (Ghozali, 2018). One way to evaluate the inner model is to use R-square to construct dependent variables, the Stone-Geisser Q-square test for predictive relevance and the t-test, and the significance of the path structural parameters. The process of evaluating the inner model using PLS (Partial Least Square) begins by examining the R-square of each dependent variable. Next, in the reinterpretation, it is identical to the regressive interpretation. The R-squared value can be used to determine the relative influence of the dependent variable on the dependent variable, namely if it has a significant effect.

3. Hypothesis Testing

The test hypothesis can be seen in the t-statistic and probability values. For hypothesis testing using statistical significance, the 5% alpha t-statistic value is 1.96. Therefore, the criteria for obtaining/estimating the hypothesized value are H_a and H_0 if the t-statistic is more than 1.96. To reject/accept the hypothesis using probability, H_a is rejected if p is less than 0.05.27 (Ghozali, 2018).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Measurement model testing (outer model) is used to determine the specific relationship between latent variables and dependent variables. Includes convergent validity, discriminant validity, and reliability.

1. Convergent Validity

The validity of each indicator is assessed against its latent variable using convergent validity. The validity findings are seen in the external loading table of the SmartPLS program. There are numbers or values in the external loading table that indicate the similarity between the indicator and the construct variable. If the indicator value is more than 0.7 and can explain the construct variable, it is considered valid. The structural model of the study is depicted in the following figure:

Figure 2. Outer Model
Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

The Smart PLS output for loading factors gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings

In this research there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Z = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e_1$$

$$Z = 0.234 X_1 + 0.756 X_2 + e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_3X_1 + b_4X_2 + b_5Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.267 X_1 + 0.427X_2 + 0.277 Z + e_2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Work Discipline (X2)	Work Ethic (X1)	Employee Performance (Y)	Competence (Z)
X1.1		0.787		
X1.2		0.816		
X1.3		0.923		
X2.1	0.870			

X2.2	0.875			
X2.3	0.916			
X2.4	0.741			
X2.5	0.894			
Y.1			0.771	
Y.2			0.788	
Y.3			0.819	
Y.4			0.835	
Z.1				0.747
Z.2				0.909
Z.3				0.958
Z.4				0.941
Z.5				0.881

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

As seen in table 1, outer loading shows that each outer loading indicator has a value greater than 0.7. As a result, it is determined that each variable indicator has a value greater than 0.7, thus validating each indicator and allowing for the continuation of the current research. moreover.

2. Discriminant Validity

Cross loading table can be used to test discriminant validity. With the condition that the correlation between the indicator and the final variable must be greater than the correlation between the indicator and other latent variables (outside the block), this output is used to verify discriminant validity at the indicator level. See the table below for additional clarification.

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Work Discipline (X2)	Work Ethic (X1)	Employee Performance (Y)	Competence (Z)
X1.1	0.652	0.787	0.788	0.686
X1.2	0.628	0.816	0.582	0.674
X1.3	0.706	0.923	0.718	0.734
X2.1	0.870	0.747	0.763	0.782
X2.2	0.875	0.627	0.838	0.793
X2.3	0.916	0.783	0.860	0.931
X2.4	0.741	0.552	0.587	0.750
X2.5	0.894	0.665	0.790	0.785
Y.1	0.709	0.621	0.771	0.717
Y.2	0.652	0.787	0.788	0.686
Y.3	0.817	0.612	0.819	0.742
Y.4	0.703	0.661	0.835	0.748
Z.1	0.701	0.552	0.582	0.747

Z.2	0.885	0.751	0.822	0.909
Z.3	0.951	0.811	0.897	0.958
Z.4	0.865	0.764	0.830	0.941
Z.5	0.765	0.788	0.838	0.881

Based on table 2, there is a cross loading factor in each variable with different values for the cross loading factor of the work discipline variable, there is a larger cross loading value on other latent indicator variables. For the cross loading factor of the work ethic variable, there is a cross loading factor value on other latent indicator variables. For the cross loading factor of the employee performance variable, there is a cross loading factor value that is larger than the cross loading value on other latent indicator variables. For the cross loading factor of the competency variable, there is a cross loading factor value that is larger than the cross loading factor value on other latent indicator variables. So the results obtained are discriminantly valid.

3. Composite reliability

The next test determines the reliability value with the composite reliability of each construct. The construct value that is considered reliable is where the composite reliability value is above 0.6 or greater than 0.6. If the Cronbach's alpha value is also greater than 0.7, then the value of each construct in the block is considered reliable for each variable construct and if the AVE value is also above 0.7, then each variable construct is considered valid. The following is a table of the loading values of the research variable constructs from running the Smart PLS program in the following table:

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Work Discipline (X2)	0.912	0.935	0.742
Work Ethic (X1)	0.795	0.881	0.712
Employee Performance (Y)	0.817	0.880	0.646
Competence (Z)	0.933	0.950	0.793

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

The construct value of the variables in the Cronbach alpha column shows that the results of each variable have a value above 0.7, which means that all construct variables are considered reliable. Likewise, the construct value in the Composite Reliability column shows that the construct value is above 0.6, which means that each construct variable greater than 0.6 is considered reliable. Finally, the construct value in the AVE column shows that each variable is considered valid, and the resulting AVE value shows a higher value for each column. This finding is based on the results of the table above. The validity and reliability

of the construct of each variable are taken into account, along with the size of the values found.

Inner Model Analysis

Structural model evaluation (inner model) is conducted to ensure that the structural model built is robust and accurate. The stages of analysis carried out in the structural model evaluation are seen from several indicators, namely:

1. Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square
Employee Performance (Y)	0.855
Competence (Z)	0.906

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Based on table 4, the R square value in the Employee Performance variable is 0.855 in a percentage of 85.5%, meaning that the influence of work ethic, work discipline and competence has an effect on Employee Performance of 0.855 or 85.5% and the rest is in other variables. The R square value of the Competence variable is 0.906 with a percentage of 90.6%, meaning that the influence of work ethic and work discipline on competence is 0.906 or 90.6%.

2. Hypothesis Testing

After assessing the inner model, the next step is to evaluate the relationship between latent constructs as hypothesized in this study. Hypothesis testing in this study was conducted by looking at the T-Statistics and P-Values. The hypothesis is accepted if the T-Statistics value is > 1.96 and P-Values < 0.05 . The following are the results of the Path Coefficients of direct influence:

Table 5. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Work Discipline (X2) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.427	2,519	0.006
Work Discipline (X2) -> Competence (Z)	0.756	14,028	0,000
Work Ethic (X1) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.267	2,548	0.006
Work Ethic (X1) -> Competence (Z)	0.234	3,871	0,000

Competence (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.277	1,570	0.059
--	-------	-------	--------------

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 5 there are direct influences as follows:

1. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.427 and a p value of 0.006. This means that if discipline increases, performance will increase, conversely, if work discipline decreases, performance will decrease.
2. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Competence with an original sample value of 0.756 and a p value of 0.000. This means that if work discipline increases, competence increases and if work discipline decreases, competence decreases.
3. Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.267 and a p value of 0.006. This means that if work ethic increases, employee performance increases, conversely if work ethic decreases, performance decreases.
4. Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on Competence with an original sample value of 0.234 and a p value of 0.000. This means that if work ethic increases, competence increases, conversely if work ethic decreases, competence decreases.
5. Competence has a positive but insignificant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.277 and a p value of 0.059. This means that if competence increases, employee performance does not necessarily increase and if competence decreases, employee performance does not necessarily decrease.

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Work Discipline (X2) -> Competence (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.209	1,566	0.059
Work Ethic (X1) -> Competence (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.065	1,339	0.091

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 6, there is an indirect influence through path analysis. It can be seen in the table that both indirect influences have a positive but insignificant influence, which means that competence cannot have an indirect or intervening influence in this study, and it can be concluded that competence is not an intervening variable because it cannot have a significant indirect influence.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.427 and a p value of 0.006.
2. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Competence with an original sample value of 0.756 and a p value of 0.000.
3. Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.267 and a p value of 0.006.
4. Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on Competence with an original sample value of 0.234 and a p value of 0.000.
5. Competence has a positive but insignificant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.277 and a p value of 0.059.
6. Work Discipline has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance indirectly through Competence with an original sample value of 0.209 and a p value of 0.059.
7. Work Ethic has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance indirectly through Competence with an original sample value of 0.065 and a p value of 0.091.

Suggestion

1. Able to rebuild the discipline of each employee by any means in a relatively short period of time.
2. Building the work ethic of employees by paying attention to employee work and giving awards to employees who deserve it so that it will be used as motivation for other employees.
3. Improve employee competency by conducting regular training.
4. It is hoped that this research will be used as input to improve existing problems in work discipline, work ethic, competence and employee performance.
5. It is hoped that this research will be used as reference material for further research and as a reference for creating new titles.

REFERENCES

- Afandi, Arif. (2021). Pengaruh Kompetensi dan Disiplin Terhadap Kinerja dengan Etos Kerja sebagai Variabel Mediasi di Kecamatan Lubuk Sikaping. *Jurnal Terapan Pemerintahan Minangkabau* Vol. 1, No. 1, e-ISSN: 2798-9380, pISSN: 2798-9941
- Agustini, Fauzia. (2019). *Strategi Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Medan: UISU Press.
- Ferine, K. F., Aditia, R., Rahmadana, M. F., & Indri. (2021). An empirical study of leadership, organizational culture, conflict, and work ethic in determining work performance in Indonesia's education authority. *Heliyon*, 7(7). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e07698>.
- Ferine, K. F., Suhardi, S. (2023). The effect of compensation and motivation on employee job satisfaction departement of transportation, subulussalam city. *International*

- Conference on Health Science, Green Economics, Educational Review and Technology, 5(1), 1–14, <https://doi.org/10.54443/ihert.v5i1.281>.
- Ferine, K. F.(2019). Analisis Sistem informasi Manajemen Berbasis Komputer dan Sistem Presensi Finger Print terhadap Kinerja Pegawai di Bandara Internasional Kualanamu. *Jurnal Mantik Penusa*, 3(1). pp. 231-235 <https://iocscience.org/ejournal/index.php/mantik/article/view/168/105>.
- Ginting, D. (2016). *Etos Kerja. Edisi Panduan Menjadi Karyawan Cerdas*. Alex Media Komputindo
- Gultom, WF dan Widyawati. (2019) Pengaruh Kompetensi dan Pelatihan terhadap Kinerja Karyawan pada PT. Perkebunan II (Tanjung Morawa Medan) Produksi Kelapa Sawit. *Jurnal Manajemen*, Vol. 5 (1).
- Ghozali, Imam., & Latan, H. (2018). *Partial Least Squares: Konsep, Teknik, dan Aplikasi Menggunakan Program SmartPLS 3.0 (2nd ed.)*. Badan Penerbit - Undip.
- Kasmir. (2019). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia (Teori dan Praktik) (Edisi ke5)*. PT Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Mukminin, Amirul. dkk. (2019) *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia dalam Pendidikan*. Yogyakarta: Uny Press
- Priansa, Donni Juni. (2018). *Perencanaan & Pengembangan SDM*. Bandung. Alfabeta.
- Rahmat, S. N., & Basalamah, J. (2019). Pengaruh Kompetensi, Kompensasi Dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Badan Pendapatan Daerah Kota Makassar. *PARADOKS: Jurnal Ilmu Ekonomi*, 2(1), 121-132.
- Sinambela., (2018), *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia, (Membangun Tim Kerja yang Solid untuk Meningkatkan Kinerja)*. Penerbit Pt Bumi Aksara. Jakarta.
- Sugiyono, (2017). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: CV. Alfabeta.
- Ferine, K. F., & Ermiami, C. (2020). Pengaruh Motivasi Dan Kompetensi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Ukm Binaan Bank Sumut Cabang Kampung Baru Cabang Medan. *Liabilities (Jurnal Pendidikan Akuntansi)*, 3(2), 115–120. <https://doi.org/10.30596/liabilities.v3i2.5587>

Determinants of Organizational Commitment

Netty Helena Br Sigalingging¹, Kiki Farida Ferine²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: netty.helena@bpjsketenagakerjaan.go.id

Abstract

In this study, researchers wanted to see the direct and indirect effects between the variables of skills and emotional intelligence as independent variables and work motivation as a moderating variable and Organizational Commitment as the dependent variable. This type of research uses quantitative, this research was conducted at BPJS Employment North Sumatra Region. The population of this study were 60 employees and the sample used was the entire population using the saturated sample technique. The data source used is primary data source and data collection is done by distributing questionnaires. The research model used is path analysis with smart PLS version 3.3.3. as a research measurement tool. The results of this study are as follows work skills have a positive and insignificant effect on work motivation with an original sample value of 0.275 and p values of 0.381. Job skills have a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment with an original sample value of 0.580 and p values of 0.000. Emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on work motivation with an original sample value of 0.570 and p values of 0.001. Emotional intelligence has a positive and insignificant effect on organizational commitment with an original sample value of 0.117 and p values of 0.612. Emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment through work motivation directly with original sample results of 0.179 and p values of 0.001. Job skills have a positive and insignificant effect on organizational commitment through work motivation with an original sample value of 0.181 and p values of 0.388.

Keywords: Skills, Emotional Intelligence, Work Motivation, Organizational Commitment.

INTRODUCTION

Collaboration skills are crucially needed by society in today's life. This is because almost all societal behaviors demonstrate cooperation, regardless of differences in ethnicity, religion, race, gender, or social class. Collaboration skills will manifest in community life if students are trained from an early age through the learning process in schools. Various methods can be implemented in learning to promote cooperation, such as group work and responsibility sharing. To achieve maximum performance, employees need to control and manage their emotions, which can be achieved through emotional intelligence. According to Armansyah (2018), the ability to manage and control one's own feelings and those of others, and to use those feelings to unify thoughts and behaviors, requires emotional intelligence. This is essential for job success and achieving good performance. Individuals with high emotional intelligence tend to have better careers because they are able to foster working relationships with various parties compared to employees who only possess intellectual intelligence. According to Widodo (2019), employees with emotional intelligence can control themselves, manage tasks effectively, and help the company's operations, thus facilitating performance evaluation by management. Work motivation is fundamental for any organization to grow, whether in the public or private sector, as it drives the desire to achieve goals through collective, systematic, and planned efforts. Work motivation includes efforts to encourage and inspire employees in their work. Organizational commitment has

become increasingly important nowadays. In a situation where companies struggle to find highly qualified employees, organizational commitment becomes one of the ways to identify employees who are qualified, loyal, and perform well. When employees' commitment to the company is formed, they will provide optimal performance, ensuring the company's goals are achieved. For employees, high commitment offers personal benefits such as increased promotion opportunities, reduced chances of demotion, and more experience in their field.

Research Questions

1. Does skill have a positive and significant effect on work motivation at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan in Northern Sumatra?
2. Does emotional intelligence have a positive and significant effect on work motivation at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan in Northern Sumatra?
3. Does skill have a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan in Northern Sumatra?
4. Does emotional intelligence have a positive and significant effect on work motivation at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan in Northern Sumatra?
5. Does work motivation have a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan in Northern Sumatra?
6. Does skill have a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment through work motivation at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan in Northern Sumatra?
7. Does emotional intelligence have a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment through work motivation at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan in Northern Sumatra?

Research Objectives

1. To analyze the influence of skill on work motivation at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan in Northern Sumatra.
2. To analyze the influence of emotional intelligence on work motivation at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan in Northern Sumatra.
3. To analyze whether skill has a positive and significant influence on organizational commitment at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan in Northern Sumatra.
4. To analyze whether emotional intelligence has a positive and significant influence on organizational commitment at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan in Northern Sumatra.
5. To analyze the influence of work motivation on organizational commitment at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan in Northern Sumatra.
6. To analyze the influence of skill on organizational commitment through work motivation at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan in Northern Sumatra.
7. To analyze whether emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment through work motivation at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan in Northern Sumatra.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational Commitment

According to Meyer and Allen in Yusuf and Syarif (2018), organizational commitment is a psychological construct as a characteristic of the relationship between organizational members and their organization, and has implications for individual decisions to continue their existence as members of the organization.

Organizational Commitment Indicators

According to Yusuf and Syarif, (2018) the indicators of organizational commitment are:

- a. Effective commitment: Employees' emotional attachment to, and involvement in, the organization,
- b. Continuance commitment: Commitment based on the losses associated with leaving the organization. This may be due to loss of seniority, promotion or benefits.
- c. Normative commitment: A feeling of obligation to remain in an organization because one must; it is the right thing to do.

Skills

According to Pitriyani (2020), work skills are the ability to carry out work based on implementation instructions and technical instructions that can be developed through the training process.

According to Chang and Rieple in Irawan (2016) "Stated that skills include business planning, sensitivity to opportunities, business environment analysis and the ability to access external expertise. In developing a business to success, an entrepreneur must not only have sufficient knowledge but also skills.

Skill indicators

According to The Story of a Girl (2020) Skill indicators include:

- a. Human relations skills

A person's skill to understand, comprehend, communicate and relate to other individuals or groups so that a relationship is built.

- b. Ability to predict the results of task/work implementation

Skills that help to look ahead and make decisions and implement them.

- c. Technical skills that are tailored to the person's job and duties.

An individual's capability to perform a specific task related to the field being studied.

Emotional Intelligence

According to Goleman (2018), emotional intelligence is the ability to monitor and control one's own and other people's feelings and to use feelings to coordinate thoughts and actions.

Indicators of emotional intelligence

According to Goleman (2018), the indicators of emotional intelligence are:

- (1) Self-awareness, which is knowing what we feel at any given moment and using it to guide our own decision-making and having realistic benchmarks and strong self-confidence.
- (2) Self-regulation, namely regarding emotions so that they have a positive impact on carrying out tasks, being sensitive to one's conscience and being able to delay enjoyment before achieving a goal and being able to recover from emotional stress.
- (3) Motivation, which is using our deepest desires to move and guide us toward goals, helps us take the initiative to act effectively and to persist in the face of failure and frustration.
- (4) Empathy, which is feeling what others feel, being able to understand their perspective, cultivating trusting relationships, and aligning oneself with a variety of people.
- (5) Social skills, namely handling emotions well when interacting with others and carefully reading situations and social networks to interact smoothly.

Work motivation

Work Motivation according to Mangkunegara (2016) is a driving need within an employee that needs to be fulfilled so that the employee can adapt to his environment and be able to achieve the goals that have been set. In other words, motivation is an energy to generate drive within oneself to achieve certain goals"

Work Motivation Indicators

According to Mangkunegara (2016) as follows:

- a. Responsibility Having a high level of personal responsibility for one's work
- b. Work Performance Doing something/work as well as possible
- c. Opportunity for Advancement Desire to earn fair wages according to work
- d. Recognition for Performance Desire to earn higher wages than usual.
- e. Challenging work Desire to learn to master his work in his field.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of Research

Research Hypothesis

- H1: Skills have a positive and significant effect on Work Motivation at BPJS Employment North Sumatra Region.
- H2: Emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on Work Motivation at BPJS Employment North Sumatra Region.

H3: Skills have a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment at BPJS Employment North Sumatra Region.

H4: Emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on commitment. Organization at BPJS Employment North Sumatra Region.

H5: Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment at BPJS Employment North Sumatra Region.

H6: Skills have a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Work motivation at BPJS Employment North Sumatra Region.

H7: Emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on commitment. Organization through Work Motivation at BPJS Employment Sumatra Region North.

METHOD

Types of research

According to Sugiyono (2017), quantitative research can be interpreted as a method based on the philosophy of positivism. This type of quantitative research is carried out to conduct research that aims to adjust research and the influence of skills and emotional intelligence on organizational commitment with work motivation as an intervening variable in the BPJS region. North Sumatra.

Research Location and Research Time

Location of research conducted BPJS Employment, North Sumatra Regional Office, Medan, located in Jalan Kapten Pattimura No. 334 Floor II, Medan 20153. This research was started in July - October 2024.

Population and Sample

Sugiyono (2017) population is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics that are determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn. The population and sample in this study were all permanent employees at BPJS Employment North Sumatra Regional Office totaling 70 people.

Research Data Sources

The data sources used in this research are primary data.

Data Analysis Techniques

Data analysis in this study uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on Partial Least Square (PLS) using SmartPLS 3.3.3 software. According to (Gozali, 2014) Partial Least Square (PLS) is a fairly strong analysis method because it is not based on many assumptions.

Measurement Model (Outer Model)

The procedure in testing the measurement model consists of validity testing and reliability testing.

1. Validity Test

- a. Convergent Validity
- b. Discriminant Validity

2. Reliability Test

The Cronbach's alpha value is recommended to be greater than 0.7 and the composite reliability is also recommended to be greater than 0.7 (Sekaran, 2014).

Structural Model (Inner Model)

This test is conducted to determine the relationship between exogenous and endogenous constructs that have become hypotheses in this study (Hair et al., 2017). To produce inner model test values, the steps in SmartPLS are carried out using the bootstrapping method. The structural model is evaluated using R-square for the dependent variable, the Stone-Geisser Q-square test for predictive elevation and the t-test and significance of the structural path parameter coefficients with the following explanation:

1. Coefficient of Determination / R Square (R²)

In assessing the model with PLS, it begins by looking at the R-square for each dependent latent variable. The interpretation is the same as the interpretation in regression. Changes in the R-square value can be used to assess the influence of certain independent latent variables on the dependent latent variable whether it has a substantive influence (Ghozali, 2012). The R² value is generally between 0 and 1.

2. Predictive Relevance (Q²)

This test is used to measure how well the observation value is generated by the model and also its parameter estimates. If the Q² value is greater than 0, it indicates that the model has predictive relevance, which means it has good observation value, while if the value is less than 0, it indicates that the model does not have predictive relevance (Ghozali, 2014).

3. t-Statistic

At this stage, it is used for hypothesis testing, namely to determine the significance of the relationship between variables in the study using the bootstrapping method. In the full model Structural Equation Modeling, in addition to confirming the theory, it also explains whether or not there is a relationship between latent variables (Ghozali, 2012). The hypothesis is said to be accepted if the t statistic value is greater than the t table. According to (Latan and Ghozali, 2014) the criteria for the t table value with a value of 1.96 with a significance level of 5%.

4. Path Coefficient

This test is used to determine the direction of the relationship between variables (positive/negative). If the value is 0 to 1, then the direction of the relationship between variables is stated as positive. While if the value is 0 to -1, then the direction of the relationship between variables is stated as negative.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Measurement model testing (outer model) is used to determine the specifications of the relationship between latent variables and their manifest variables, this testing includes convergent validity, discriminant validity and reliability.

Convergent Validity

This test is seen from the loading factor, the value limit is 0.7, and the value limit Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is 0.5, if it is above that value it is said to be valid. This means that the value for the indicator is said to be valid, if the indicator explains the construct variable with a value > 0.7. The structural model in this study is shown in the following figure:

Figure 2. Outer Model
 Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Smart PLS output for loading factor gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1.

$$Z = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e_1$$

$$Z = 0.162X_1 + 0.104X_2 + e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_3X_1 + b_4X_2 + b_5Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.305X_1 + 0.372 X_2+ 0.652 + e_2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE	SKILLS	ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT	WORK MOTIVATION
CEM2	0.879			
CEM5	0.784			
CEM6	0.807			
CEM7	0.820			
KOM1			0.883	
KOM2			0.747	
KOM3			0.778	
MOT2				0.846
MOT3				0.948
MOT4				0.940
TRA1		0.828		
TRA2		0.905		
TRA3		0.739		
TRA5		0.807		
TRA7		0.773		

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 1 above, the value of each variable is stated that the indicator in each variable is higher than 0.7, which means that each indicator item has a value higher than 0.7 so that the data is declared valid and can continue to further research.

Discriminant Validity

Further research to find out valid data in terms of Discriminate Validity, aims to find out whether the cross loading value is greater than other latent variables so as to determine the results of indicators that are highly correlated with their constructs. The following table shows the cross loading results from the validity test as follows:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE	SKILLS	ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT	WORK MOTIVATION
EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE	0.824			
SKILLS	0.944	0.812		
ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT	0.687	0.688	0.805	
WORK MOTIVATION	0.660	0.657	0.827	0.912

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

The results of table 2 above show a value that is greater than the other variables in each indicator and variable, so it can be concluded that the results of the discriminant validity study are validly distributed.

Composite reliability

In composite reliability research to see each variable with its reliability value and if the variable value is greater than 0.60 then the research is considered reliable and if below 0.60 and 0.7 then it is not reliable there are several blocks to determine whether the research is reliable or not and valid or not including the Coranbach alpha value, composite reliability and AVE value can be seen in the table below:

Table 3: Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE	0.843	0.846	0.894	0.678
SKILLS	0.870	0.872	0.906	0.660
ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT	0.726	0.744	0.846	0.647
WORK MOTIVATION	0.898	0.898	0.937	0.833

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 3 above, it can be seen in the cronbach alpha column that each variable has a value greater than 0.7, which means that the reliability data for each variable. The composite reliability column has a value greater than 0.6, so it can be explained that each variable is considered reliable because the data is greater than 0.6. It can be seen from the AVE column that each variable gets a value greater than 0.7, which means that the data is valid according to AVE. All variables from the cronbach alpha column, reliability column and AVE column have values greater than 0.7 and 0.6, so they are considered reliable and valid.

Inner Model Analysis

Structural model evaluation (inner model) is conducted to ensure that the basic model created is strong and accurate. The stages of examination conducted in the primary model assessment are seen from several markers, namely:

Coefficient of Determination (R2)

In the next stage, namely the evaluation of the measurement model or inner model by looking at the R-Square value criteria. The R-Square results from the smartPLS 3.0 software output are as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT	0.722	0.707
WORK MOTIVATION	0.646	0.627

There is an R square value of the Organizational Commitment variable with an R square value of 0.707 and if it is in percentage it is 70.7%, meaning that the influence of skills and emotional intelligence on organizational commitment with work motivation as an Intervening variable is 70.7% and the rest is on other variables. The R square value of the Work Motivation variable is 0.627 and if it is in percentage it is 62.7%, meaning that the influence of skills and emotional intelligence on organizational commitment with work motivation as an Intervening variable is 62.7% and the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After assessing the inner model, the next thing is to assess the connection between idle builds as suspected in this review. Speculation testing in this review is done by looking at T-Statistics and P-Values. Speculation is announced to acknowledge whether the T-Insights value is > 1.96 and P-Values <0.05. The following are the consequences of the direct impact Path Coefficient:

Table 5. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
SKILLS -> WORK MOTIVATION	0.305	0.275	0.348	0.877	0.381
SKILLS -> ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT	0.583	0.580	0.195	0.486	0.000
EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE -> WORK MOTIVATION	0.572	0.570	0.190	0.476	0.001
EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE -> ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT	0.104	0.117	0.205	0.507	0.612

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

The results of the research directly above will be explained as follows:

1. Job skills have a positive and insignificant effect on work motivation with an original sample value of 0.275 and p values of 0.381. This means that the work skills formed by the Company are good and work skills are not able to provide work motivation to every employee in the company.
2. Job skills have a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment with an original sample value of 0.580 and p values of 0.000. This means that if job skills increase, organizational commitment will increase and if job skills decrease, organizational commitment will also decrease.
3. Emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on work motivation with an original sample value of 0.570 and p values of 0.001. This means that emotional intelligence formed by the organization and employees is not able to increase organizational commitment in each employee.
4. Emotional intelligence has a positive and insignificant effect on organizational commitment with an original sample value of 0.117 and p values of 0.612. This means that emotional intelligence formed by the company and employees is not able to increase organizational commitment in each employee.

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE -> WORK MOTIVATION -> ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT	0.243	0.179	0.235	1,032	0.001
SKILLS -> WORK MOTIVATION -> ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT	0.199	0.181	0.230	0.865	0.388

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

The results of the indirect influence above can be explained as follows:

1. Emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment through work motivation directly with the original sample results of 0.179 and p values of 0.001. This means that work motivation is an intervening variable because it is able to influence emotional intelligence on organizational commitment directly.
2. Work skills have a positive and insignificant effect on organizational commitment through work motivation with an original sample value of 0.181 and p values of 0.388.

This means that work motivation Not yet able to be an intervening variable and have a positive influence on work skills and work motivation with the existence of work skills for employees, work motivation will increase have been fulfilled so as to build commitment to the organization.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Work skills have a positive and insignificant effect on work motivation inBPJS EmploymentNorth Sumatra Region.
2. Work skills have a positive and significant influence on organizational commitment inBPJS EmploymentNorth Sumatra Region
3. Emotional intelligence has a positive and significant influence on work motivation inBPJS EmploymentNorth Sumatra Region
4. Emotional intelligence has a positive and insignificant effect on organizational commitment inBPJS EmploymentNorth Sumatra Region
5. Work motivation has a positive and significant influence on organizational commitment inBPJS EmploymentNorth Sumatra Region
6. Emotional intelligence has a positive and significant influence on organizational commitment through direct work motivation.BPJS EmploymentNorth Sumatra Region
7. Work skills have a positive and insignificant effect on organizational commitment through work motivation inBPJS EmploymentNorth Sumatra Region

Suggestion

1. The company must be fair in treating employees who have emotional intelligence which is part of the company, so that the company can provide employees who have emotional intelligence.
2. Companies must maintain employee work skills to the maximum by providing convenience to employees who have work skills.
3. Companies must provide work motivation to employees so that employees are able to manage work motivation within the company.

REFERENCES

- Ariesta, I. (2016). Pengaruh Kecerdasan Emosional Dan Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) Terhadap Kinerja Peternak Ayam Ras Pedaging. *JBMP (Jurnal Bisnis, Manajemen Dan Perbankan)*, 2(2), 121-140.
- Goleman. (2018). Pengembangan Kecerdasan Emosional (Emotional Quotient) Pada Anak Usia Dini Dalam Tinjauan Pendidikan Islam. *Al-Fitrah*, 1(1), 103-116.
- Irawan, A., & Mulyadi, H. (2016). Pengaruh Keterampilan Wirausaha Terhadap Keberhasilan (Studi Kasus pada Distro Anggota Kreative Independent Clothing Kcommunity USAHA di Kota Bandung). *Journal of Business Management Education (JBME)*, 1(1), 216-226.

- Juliawati, H., & Darmawati, D. M. (2022). Pengaruh Model NHT dengan Media Video terhadap Hasil Belajar Siswa Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Basicedu*, 6(5), 8146-8153.
- Mahardika, I. N. B. P., & Wibawa, I. M. A. (2019). Pengaruh budaya organisasi kepuasan kerja dan komitmen organisasional terhadap organizational citizenship behavior pada karyawan (Doctoral dissertation, Udayana University).
- Mangkunegara, A. P., & Agustine, R. (2016). Effect of training, motivation and work environment on physicians' performance. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 5(1), 173.
- Saputra, S. D., Afifuddin, A., & Widodo, R. (2019). Kualitas Pelayanan Publik Bidang Administrasi Kependudukan di kecamatan Kepanjen Kidul. *Respon Publik*, 13(2), 38-44.
- Setyaningrum, R. P., & Haryono, T. (2016). The Impact of CSR on Employee Performance: With The Mediation of Employee Trust and Employee Behavior (A Case Study of Companies in Bekasi and Jakarta). *KINERJA*, 22(2), 200-219.
- Sugiyono, S. (2017). *Metode penelitian kuantitatif dan kualitatif dan R&D*. Alfabeta Bandung.
- Yusuf, R. M., & Syarif, D. (2018). *Komitmen organisasi*. Nas Media Pustaka.
- Pitriyani, P., & Halim, A. (2020). Pengaruh Sikap Kerja Dan Keterampilan Kerja Terhadap Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan CV. Meranti Medan. *Ekonomi Bisnis Manajemen dan Akuntansi (EBMA)*, 1(2), 162-167.

Motivation Mediates Performance

Dian Renita Napitupulu¹, Muhammad Isa Indrawan²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: dianrenita@bpjsketenagakerjaan.go.id

Abstract

BPJS Ketenagakerjaan is (Social Security Administering Agency for Employment) is a public program that provides protection for workers to overcome certain socio-economic risks and its implementation uses a social insurance mechanism as a state institution engaged in the field of social insurance. BPJS Ketenagakerjaan, formerly known as PT Jamsostek (Persero), is the implementer of the labor social security law. This study aims to see the effect of Work Stress and Work Conflict on Employee Performance with Work Motivation as an Intervening Variable at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya. The results of this study are as follows: Work Conflict has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.351 and p values of 0.011. Work Conflict has a positive and significant effect on Work Motivation with an original sample value of 0.783 and p values of 0.000. Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.481 and p values of 0.001. Work Stress has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.084 and p values of 0.186. Work Stress has a positive and significant effect on Work Motivation with an original sample value of 0.164 and p values of 0.017. Work Conflict has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Work Motivation with an original sample value of 0.377 and p values of 0.001. Work Stress has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance through Work Motivation with an original sample value of 0.079 and p values of 0.050.

Keywords: Work Stress, Work Conflict, Work Motivation, Employee Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Increasing competition and demands for professionalism create many pressures that individuals must face in the work environment. In addition to pressure from the work environment, the family environment and social environment also have the potential to cause anxiety. The very detrimental impact of anxiety disorders that are often experienced by the community and employees in particular is called stress. Work stress is an important aspect for companies, especially in relation to employee performance. Companies must have performance. Good performance can help companies make a profit. Conversely, if performance declines, it can be detrimental to the company. The dangers of stress are caused by physical, emotional and mental fatigue caused by long-term involvement with emotionally demanding situations. The process that takes place gradually, accumulatively, and over time becomes worse. In the short term, stress that is left alone without serious handling from the company makes employees depressed, unmotivated, and frustrated causing employees to work less than optimally so that their performance will be disrupted. In the long term, employees cannot withstand work stress, so employees are no longer able to work in the company. At a more severe stage, stress can make employees sick or even resign. A company, conflict is inevitable, conflict always comes in the middle of a company's running. Conflict is a condition that occurs when differences of opinion or perspective in

several people differ in a group or organization. Conflict is a condition that arises because of conflicting desires. The term conflict itself is translated into several terms, namely differences of opinion, competition and hostility. Conflict is closely related to human feelings, including feelings of being ignored, belittled, unappreciated, abandoned and also feelings of irritation due to excessive workload (Harmah, 2017). Work motivation is something that is very much needed by employees, employees with high motivation will certainly have the enthusiasm to complete the work assigned to them. Motivation can also be used as an option to achieve company goals. Without high motivation in every employee, the organization or company will not be able to progress and develop. According to Sutrisno in Sudjatmoko & Rusilowati U (2022) Motivation is a factor that drives a person to do a certain activity, therefore motivation is often interpreted as a factor that drives a person's behavior. If an employee has a strong drive from within himself or from outside himself, then the employee will continue to contribute to the company and continue to carry out the obligations and responsibilities given by the company to employees who work in a company happily without any feeling of being less conducive.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee Performance

Afandi (2018) Employee performance is the work results that can be achieved by an individual or group of people in a company in accordance with their respective authorities and responsibilities in an effort to achieve organizational goals illegally, without violating the law and without conflicting with morals and ethics.

Performance indicators

According to Afandi (2018) employee performance indicators are as follows:

a. Quantity of work results

All kinds of units of measurement related to the amount of work results that can be expressed in numbers or other numerical equivalents.

b. Quality of work results

All forms of units of measurement related to the quality or standard of work results that can be expressed in numerical measurements or other numerical equivalents.

c. Efficiency in carrying out tasks

Share resources wisely and in a cost-effective manner.

d. Work discipline

Comply with applicable laws and regulations.

e. Initiative

The ability to decide and do the right thing without being told, being able to find what needs to be done about something around you, trying to keep moving to do things even though the situation feels increasingly difficult.

f. Accuracy

The level of conformity of the work measurement results, whether the work has achieved its objectives or not.

g. Leadership

The process of influencing or giving an example by a leader to his followers in an effort to achieve organizational goals.

h. Honesty

One of the human traits that is quite difficult to apply.

i. Creativity

A mental process involving the generation of ideas or involving the generation of ideas

Job Stress

According to Alfarol & Bahwiyanti (2023) Job stress is Job stress is the feelings and perspectives of individuals who become anxious and feel restless continuously. According to Ghani & Muttaqiyathun (2023) Job stress is an unpleasant psychological process that occurs as a form of response to pressure from the environment.

Work stress indicators

According to The Last Supper (2023) are as follows:

- a. Working Conditions
- b. Job Roles
- c. Interpersonal variables
- d. Career Advancement
- e. Organizational structure

Work Conflict

According to Rivai (2016), work conflict is a discrepancy between two or more members or groups (in an organization/company) who must share limited resources or work activities and/or due to the fact that they have different statuses, goals, values or perceptions.

Work Conflict Indicators

According to Rivai (2016), work conflict indicators consist of:

a. Conflict within a person

Conflict within a person generally occurs because a person is faced with conflicting goals.

b. Inter-individual conflict

Conflicts between individuals are generally triggered by differences regarding a problem and a goal, where the results and joint decisions are considered very important.

c. Conflict between group members

Conflict within a group can be affective or substantive. Affective conflict is a conflict that arises because of an emotional response to a particular situation. While substantive conflict is a conflict that occurs because of differences in expertise background.

d. Inter-group conflict

Inter-group conflicts generally occur because each group prioritizes its own interests or goals too much.

Work motivation

According to Sutrisno (2019), motivation is a factor that drives someone to do a certain activity, therefore motivation is often interpreted as a factor that drives a person's behavior. Every activity carried out by a person must have a factor that drives the activity.

Work motivation indicators

According to Sutrisno (2019), employee work motivation indicators are:

a. Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction is an employee's attitude towards work related to the work situation, cooperation between employees, rewards received in work, and matters relating to physical and psychological factors.

b. Achievements achieved

Job performance is a record of the results obtained from certain job functions or certain activities during a certain period of time.

c. Opportunity to advance

The opportunity to advance is the desire to get fair compensation according to the job.

d. Career development possibilities

Career development opportunities are the process of improving employees' technical, theoretical, conceptual and moral skills through education and training.

e. Responsibility

Responsibility is a person's attitude or behavior in carrying out tasks and obligations that must be done for oneself, society and the environment.

f. Recognition of others

Recognition from others is the desire to get a higher salary than usual.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of Research

Research Hypothesis

The hypothesis in this study is as follows:

- H1: Work stress has a negative effect on work motivation at BPJS Employment Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya.
- H2: Work stress has a negative effect on employee performance at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya
- H3: Work conflict has a negative effect on work motivation at BPJS Employment Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya.
- H4: Work conflict has a negative effect on employee performance at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya.
- H5: Work motivation has a positive effect on employee performance at BPJS Employment Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya.
- H6: Work stress has a negative effect on employee performance through work motivation at BPJS Employment Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya.
- H7: Work conflict has a negative influence on employee performance through work motivation at BPJS Employment Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya.

METHOD

Types of research

This type of quantitative research is carried out to conduct research that aims to adjust research and the influence of work stress and work conflict on employee performance. Work motivation as an intervening variable at BPJS Employment Branch Offices in Medan Raya.

Research Location and Research Time

The research location was conducted at BPJS Employment Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya Jl. Kapten Patimura No.334, Medan, North Sumatra. The research period was carried out for 3 months starting from July to September 2024.

Population and Sample

According to Sugiyono (2017) population is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics that are determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn. The population and sample in this study were all permanent employees at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya totaling 80 employees (saturated sample).

Research Data Sources

The data sources used in this research are primary data.

Data Analysis Techniques

Data analysis in this study uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on Partial Least Square (PLS) using SmartPLS 3.3.3 software. According to (Ghozali, 2014) Partial Least Square (PLS) is a fairly strong analysis method because it is not based on many assumptions.

Measurement Model (Outer Model)

The procedure in testing the measurement model consists of validity testing and reliability testing.

1. Validity Test
 - a. Convergent Validity
 - b. Discriminant Validity

2. Reliability Test

The Cronbach's alpha value is recommended to be greater than 0.7 and the composite reliability is also recommended to be greater than 0.7 (Sekaran, 2014).

Structural Model (Inner Model)

This test is conducted to determine the relationship between exogenous and endogenous constructs that have become hypotheses in this study (Hair et al., 2017). The structural model is evaluated using R-square for the dependent variable, Stone-Geisser Q-square test for predictive elevation and t-test and significance of the structural path parameter coefficients with the following explanation:

1. Coefficient of Determination / R Square (R²)
2. Predictive Relevance (Q²)
3. t-Statistic
4. Path Coefficient

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

The details of the relationship between the latent variables and the manifest variables can be ascertained by using measurement model testing, also known as external model testing.

1. Convergent Validity

The correlation between item/indicator scores and construct scores indicates the convergent validity of the measurement model with reflective indicators. If the correlation value of an indicator is more than 0.70, it is considered reliable. However, loadings between 0.50 and 0.60 are still appropriate at the scale development stage of this study. The indication has a loading below 0.60 and is not significant according to external loading data. The structural model of the study is depicted in the following figure:

Figure 2. Outer Model
Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

The Smart PLS output for loading factors gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings

In this research there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Z = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e_1$$

$$Z = 0.164X_1 + 0.783X_2 + e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_3X_1 + b_4X_2 + b_5Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.084X_1 + 0.351X_2 + 0.481 Z + e_2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Employee Performance (Y)	Work Conflict (X2)	Work Motivation (Z)	Job Stress (X1)
X1.1				0.783
X1.2				0.805
X1.3				0.773
X1.4				0.774
X1.5				0.854
X2.1		0.835		
X2.2		0.863		
X2.3		0.787		
X2.4		0.807		
Y.1	0.843			
Y.2	0.790			
Y.3	0.719			
Y.4	0.822			
Y.5	0.777			

Y.6	0.883		
Y.7	0.868		
Y.8	0.806		
Y.9	0.885		
Z.1			0.779
Z.2			0.904
Z.3			0.845
Z.4			0.881
Z.5			0.836
Z.6			0.888

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Based on the data in table 1 above, each indicator in the variable has a valid value, thus indicating that further research can be conducted. In addition, the loading factor value is greater than 0.07.

Discriminant Validity

The findings of the discriminant validity test will be discussed in this section. The cross loading value is used for the discriminant validity test. If the cross loading value of an indicator on a variable is greater than that of another variable, then it is said to indicate discriminant validity. The cross loading value for each indicator is as follows:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Employee Performance (Y)	Work Conflict (X2)	Work Motivation (Z)	Job Stress (X1)
X1.1	0.581	0.653	0.620	0.783
X1.2	0.607	0.614	0.629	0.805
X1.3	0.634	0.701	0.696	0.773
X1.4	0.620	0.691	0.673	0.774
X1.5	0.707	0.774	0.726	0.854
X2.1	0.695	0.835	0.769	0.775
X2.2	0.822	0.863	0.835	0.784
X2.3	0.703	0.787	0.706	0.615
X2.4	0.625	0.807	0.726	0.657
Y.1	0.843	0.682	0.720	0.658
Y.2	0.790	0.696	0.686	0.655
Y.3	0.719	0.671	0.622	0.613
Y.4	0.822	0.726	0.692	0.737
Y.5	0.777	0.708	0.730	0.629
Y.6	0.883	0.787	0.833	0.700
Y.7	0.868	0.719	0.694	0.650
Y.8	0.806	0.670	0.697	0.545
Y.9	0.885	0.763	0.794	0.666

Z.1	0.757	0.779	0.779	0.721
Z.2	0.782	0.854	0.904	0.733
Z.3	0.698	0.789	0.845	0.642
Z.4	0.773	0.772	0.881	0.755
Z.5	0.717	0.731	0.836	0.730
Z.6	0.771	0.821	0.888	0.733

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 2 there are loading factors for each variable, the explanation for each loading factor is as follows: For the employee performance variable loading factor, there is a higher cross loading factor value than the cross loading factor of other latent variables, for the work conflict variable cross loading factor there is a higher value than the cross loading factor of other latent variables, for the work motivation variable cross loading factor there is a greater cross loading factor value than the cross loading factor of other latent variables, there is a work stress variable cross loading factor value that is greater than the cross loading factor value of other latent variables, so it can be concluded that this study is discriminantly valid.

Composite reliability

Two approaches were used in this study to test dependency: composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha. While composite reliability evaluates the actual value of a construct's dependency, Cronbach's alpha assesses the lower limit of a construct's reliability value. This study tested reliability using Composite reliability based on this opinion. In general, the composite dependency value, or alpha, should be higher than 0.7, although 0.6 is still acceptable. The Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha values are shown in the table below.

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Employee Performance (Y)	0.940	0.950	0.677
Work Conflict (X2)	0.841	0.894	0.678
Work Motivation (Z)	0.927	0.943	0.734
Job Stress (X1)	0.857	0.898	0.637

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Based on table 3 above, the validity test using AVE (Average Variance Extracted) produces a value greater than 0.50 and the reliability test using both Cronbach's Alpha and Composite reliability produces a value greater than 0.70 for all variables. Thus, it can be said that the variables examined are valid and reliable, thus allowing further testing of the structural model.

Inner Model Analysis

To ensure that the structural model created is reliable and accurate, the structural model (inner model) is evaluated. The stages of structural model evaluation analysis are seen through several indicators, including:

1. Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Employee Performance (Y)	0.793	0.785
Work Motivation (Z)	0.862	0.859

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In this study, there is an Rsquare value in table 4 and will be explained, for the R square value of the Employee Performance variable there is a value of 0.793 and if it is expressed as a percentage it becomes 79.3%, meaning that the influence of the variables Work Seterss, Work Conflict and Work Motivation is 0.793 or 79.3% and the rest is on other variables. For the Work Motivation variable, there is an R square value of 0.862 and if expressed as a percentage of 86.2%, meaning that the influence of Work Stress and Work Conflict on work motivation is 0.86.2 or 0.862 and the rest is on other variables.

2. Hypothesis Testing

The next step is to analyze the hypothetical relationship between latent constructs in this study after evaluating the inner model. T-Statistics and P-Values are tested in the process of testing the hypothesis of this study. If the P-Value is less than 0.05 and the T-Statistics value is more than 1.96 then the hypothesis is considered accepted. The results of the direct influence path coefficient are as follows:

Table 5. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Work Conflict (X2) -> Employee Performance (Y)	-0.351	2,304	0.011	Accepted
Work Conflict (X2) -> Work Motivation (Z)	-0.783	10,730	0,000	Accepted
Work Motivation (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.481	3,201	0.001	Accepted
Work Stress (X1) -> Employee Performance (Y)	-0.084	0.892	0.186	Rejected
Work Stress (X1) -> Work Motivation (Z)	-0.164	2,115	0.017	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 5 there are the results of the hypothesis which will be explained as follows:

1. Work Conflict has a negative and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of -0.351 and p values of 0.011. This means that work conflict between other employees and between employees and superiors has a negative effect between work conflict and performance, it can be explained that the higher the conflict, the lower the performance, conversely the lower the conflict, the higher the performance.
2. Work Conflict has a negative and significant effect on Work Motivation with an original sample value of -0.783 and p values of 0.000. This means that work conflict also has a negative effect on work motivation because the conflict that occurs interferes with the motivation given.
3. Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.481 and p values of 0.001. This means that the better the motivation given, the more the employee's performance increases, conversely, the lower the good motivation, the lower the performance.
4. Work Stress has a negative and insignificant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of -0.084 and p values of 0.186. This means that work stress has a negative effect on performance because in the study respondents felt stressed at work to the point that their performance was disrupted, some felt stressed at work but not too much so that performance was not disrupted.
5. Work Stress has a negative and significant effect on Work Motivation with an original sample value of -0.164 and p values of 0.017. This means that respondents feel excessive stress on work so that they still accept the work motivation stress that is often experienced by respondents, the result is just ordinary stress.

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Work Conflict (X2) -> Work Motivation (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.377	3,099	0.001	Accepted
Job Stress (X1) -> Work Motivation (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.079	1,644	0.050	Rejected

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

The results of indirect influence can be explained as follows:

1. Work Conflict has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Work Motivation with an original sample value of 0.377 and p values of 0.001. This means that work motivation is an intervening variable because it can have a positive and significant effect, with work motivation work conflict can be stopped because the conflict that occurs is not big so that employees do not have a problem with it.
2. Work Stress has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance through Work Motivation with an original sample value of 0.079 and p values of 0.050. This

means that work motivation is not an intervening variable because it is unable to influence significantly.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Work Conflict has a negative and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.351 and p values of 0.011.
2. Work Conflict has a negative and significant effect on Work Motivation with an original sample value of -0.783 and p values of 0.000.
3. Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.481 and p values of 0.001.
4. Work stress has a negative and insignificant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of -0.084 and p values of 0.186.
5. Job stress has a positive and significant effect on work motivation with an original sample value of 0.164 and p values of 0.017.
6. Work Conflict has a negative and significant effect on Employee Performance through Work Motivation with an original sample value of -0.377 and p values of 0.001.
7. Job stress has a negative and insignificant effect on employee performance through work motivation with an original sample value of -0.079 and p values of 0.050.

Suggestion

1. It is hoped that this research will be used as suggestions for organizations and to build better organizations.
2. This research is expected to be used as a benchmark for organizational development.
3. This research is expected to be used as reference material for other research and new topics.

REFERENCES

- Afandi, R. R. V. (2018). Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan Transformasional Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Dengan Leader-Member Exchange Dan Kepuasan Kerja Sebagai Variabel Mediasi Pada Karyawan PT. Radio Fiskaria Jaya Suara Surabaya (Doctoral dissertation, UNIVERSITAS AIRLANGGA).
- Alfarol, A. K., & Bahwiyanti, J. (2023). Pengaruh Kepuasan Kerja Dan Stres Kerja Terhadap Turnover Intention Pada Pt. Hasnur Riung Sinergi Kabupaten Tapin. *Al-Kalam: Jurnal Komunikasi, Bisnis Dan Manajemen*, 10(1), 75-89.
- Ghani, M. A., & Muttaqiyathun, A. (2023). Work Life Balance Model, Work Stress and Performance of Millennial Generation Online Taxibike Drivers. *International Journal of Social Service and Research*, 3(3).
- Ghozali, Imam. 2014. *Structural Equation Modeling, Metode Alternatif dengan Partial Least Square (PLS)*. Edisi 4. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Hair, J. F., et al (2017). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications

- Harmah, H. (2017). Efektivitas manajemen konflik dalam mengatasi masalah pada pt. Pegadaian (persero) Cabang Polewali (analisis manajemen syariah) (Doctoral dissertation, STAIN Parepare).
- Hermawati, R., Firdaus, A., Suryani, N. L., Rozi, A., Erlangga, H., Pamulang, U., & Selatan, T. (2021). Pengaruh Pelatihan Dan Motivasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada Bank BJB di Cabang Balaraja Banten. 4(3), 319–331
- Kristanti, D., & Pangastuti, R. L. (2019). Effect of Work Stress, Work Motivation, and Work Environment To Employee Performance Production Part: Case Study at UD. Pratama Karya Kota Kediri. *Business and Finance Journal*, 4(2), 105-114.
- Kusumanegara, I. S., Asmony, T., & Numayanti, S. (2018). Work-family conflict on turnover intention regarding work stress as intervening variable. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 2 (2), 141 – 154. <https://doi.org/10.29332/ijssh.v2n2.153>
- Rahmawanti, N. P. (2014). Pengaruh lingkungan kerja terhadap kinerja karyawan (Studi pada karyawan kantor pelayanan pajak Pratama Malang Utara) (Doctoral dissertation, Brawijaya University).
- Rivai, V. (2016). *Islamic Quality Education Management*. Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Sakti, A. S., Widyastanto, H., Maulidina, A., Mitasari, D., Eriyani, D. S., & Mun'im, A. B. D. U. L. (2020). Xanthine oxidase inhibitory activity of methanol extract fractions of various Indonesian ethnopharmacological plants. *International Journal of Applied Pharmaceutics*, 43-46.
- Sekaran, Uma. (2014). *Metodologi Penelitian Untuk Bisnis (Research Methods for Business) Buku 1 Edisi 4*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- Sudjatmoko, S. & Rusilowati, U. (2022). Pengaruh Motivasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada PT Bank Mandiri Cabang Bintaro Tangerang Selatan. *Jurnal Ekonomi Efektif*, 4(2), 286. <https://doi.org/10.32493/jee.v4i2.17133>
- Sugiyono, (2017). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: CV. Alfabeta.
- Sutrisno, S., & Sunarsi, D. (2019). The Effect of Work Motivation and Discipline on Employee Productivity at PT. Anugerah Agung in Jakarta. *Jurnal Ad'ministrare*, 6(2), 187-196.
- Yuliawan, E. (2014). Pengaruh Stres Kerja Dan Konflik Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada Pt. Pindan Bandung. *Jurnal Wira Ekonomi Mikroskill Vol. 2*.

The Role of the Prosecutor's Office in Eradicating Criminal Acts of Corruption in Aceh Tamiang Regency

Fakhrur Razi¹, Dr. T. Riza Zarzani, S.H., M.H.²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: tengkuriza@umsu.ac.id

Abstract

This study examines the role of the Attorney General's Office in combating corruption in Aceh Tamiang, Indonesia. Corruption poses a significant threat to societal welfare, undermining economic stability and eroding public trust in government institutions. The research emphasizes the critical functions of the Attorney General's Office, particularly in their capacity as both prosecutors and investigators in corruption cases. It highlights the legal framework governing their authority and outlines specific initiatives aimed at preventing and addressing corrupt practices. The study reveals that challenges persist, including the complexity of cases, lack of cooperation from witnesses, and the influence of powerful actors shielding corrupt individuals. Furthermore, the findings indicate that successful corruption eradication requires collaborative efforts among law enforcement agencies, increased public awareness, and robust legal instruments. This paper contributes to the understanding of legal mechanisms in anti-corruption efforts and suggests actionable recommendations to enhance the effectiveness of the Attorney General's Office in Aceh Tamiang. Ultimately, it underscores the necessity of a comprehensive approach involving multiple stakeholders to restore integrity and transparency within public administration.

Keywords: Corruption, Attorney General's Office, Law Enforcement.

INTRODUCTION

Corruption is a violation of the social and economic rights of the community. Corruption has become an extraordinary crime. Likewise, efforts to eradicate it can no longer be carried out in a normal way, but are demanded in an extraordinary way. Furthermore, it is proven that

there is a link between corruption and other forms of crime, especially organized crime (terrorism, human trafficking, smuggling of illegal migrants, etc.) others) and economic crimes (money laundering). So that corruption is a crime that is very detrimental to the state.¹

Like an octopus, corruption is increasingly wrapping around and gripping the joints of this country. Post-reform, corruption has spread, become massive and numerous, compared to the New Order and Old Order, corruption was centralized (centered) on certain parties and their cronies, while in the reform era it was marked by decentralization, everyone used their position and time to gain as much profit as possible. This happened from the central level to the lowest level.²

¹Abdul Haris, Umar Ma'Ruf, And Sri Kusriyah, "Role And Function Of Attorney In Order To Optimize The Prevention Of Corruption Through Establishment Of Tp4p/D (Case Studies In State Attorney Of Grobogan)", Journal of Daulat Hukum Volume 2 Issue 4, December 2019, p. 127

²Made Agus Mahendra Iswara and Ketut Adi Wirawan. "The Role of the Prosecutor's Office in Eradicating Criminal Acts of Village Corruption in Indonesia". Kertha Wicaksana Journal: Communication Facilities for Lecturers and Students Volume 14, Number 1 2020, page 70

Corruption does not have to directly contain elements that harm state finances or the country's economy, such as bribery. What constitutes a despicable act is abuse of power, discriminatory behavior by providing financial benefits, breach of trust, damage to the mentality of officials, dishonesty in competition and others. Realizing the complexity of the problem of corruption in the midst of a multidimensional crisis and the real threat that will definitely occur, namely the impact of this crime. Therefore, corruption can be categorized as a national problem that must be faced seriously through firm and clear steps by involving all potentials in society, especially the government and law enforcement officers.

Law enforcement basically involves all Indonesian citizens, where in its implementation it is carried out by law enforcers. The law enforcement is carried out by authorized officers. The state apparatus authorized in examining criminal cases are the Police, Prosecutors and Courts. The Police, Prosecutors and Judges are three elements of law enforcement.

laws, each of which has duties, authorities and obligations in accordance with applicable laws and regulations (Saragih, 2017).

As one of the law enforcement agencies that has the authority to eradicate criminal acts of corruption, based on Article 2 paragraph (1) of the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 16 of 2004 concerning the Republic of Indonesia Attorney General's Office, the Republic of Indonesia Attorney General's Office is given the authority not only to prosecute criminal acts of corruption but also has several other authorities that function in efforts to eradicate criminal acts of corruption.

The Prosecutor's Office as one of the law enforcement institutions is required to play a greater role in upholding the supremacy of law, protecting public interests, enforcing human rights, and eradicating corruption. The function of the Prosecutor is one of the links in the law enforcement process in dealing with crimes or criminal acts that occur in society, where this function cannot be separated from the process of investigation, inquiry, prosecution, trial and execution.³

In Article 1 point 6 of the Criminal Procedure Code it states:

1. A prosecutor is an official who is authorized by this law to act as a public prosecutor and to implement court decisions that have permanent legal force;
2. The public prosecutor is a prosecutor who is authorized by this law to carry out prosecutions and implement legal decisions.

In carrying out its duties and authorities, the Prosecutor's Office is in a central position with a strategic role in strengthening national resilience. Because the Prosecutor's Office is at the axis and becomes a filter between the investigation process and the prosecution process.

examination in court and also as the implementer of court decisions and rulings. Thus, the Prosecutor's Office is the controller of the case process (*dominus litis*), because only the

³Yasmirah Mandasari Saragih. "The Role of the Prosecutor's Office in Eradicating Criminal Acts of Corruption in Indonesia After Law Number 20 of 2001 Concerning the Eradication of Criminal Acts of Corruption". *Al'adl Journal* Vol Ix Number 1, January-April 2017, p.55

Prosecutor's Office institution can determine whether a case/matter can be submitted to the Court or not based on valid evidence according to Criminal Procedure Law.

The role of the prosecutor as a single public prosecutor or single prosecution system which is a foundation for the implementation of the prosecutor's duties which aims to maintain the unity of the prosecution policy which displays the characteristics that are united in the behavior, mindset, and work procedures of the prosecutor's office. What must be possessed by the prosecutor's office is a professional expertise, both in terms of understanding and comprehension. This is one of the efforts of the prosecutor's office so that the eradication of criminal acts of corruption can be successful. The characteristics typical of perpetrators of corruption crimes in general are carried out for the community upper class and have jobs that are often known as white collar crimes or can be called white collar crimes.⁴

In handling corruption crimes, the prosecutor acts as an investigator and also as a public prosecutor. So his role in eradicating corruption crimes by means of a penalty is very dominant, meaning that by means of a penalty is the eradication of a crime that uses criminal law in its handling. In addition to handling criminal acts by means of a penalty, non-penal handling is also known, namely using non-criminal law means, for example with administrative law.⁵

In an effort to find and collect evidence to shed light on the crimes that have occurred and to find the suspects, it is certainly inseparable from the investigation process, the prosecutor is one of the functional officials who has the authority to conduct investigations into corruption. Viewed from the aspect of criminal law policy (penal policy), the target of criminal law is not only to regulate the actions of citizens in general, but also to regulate the actions of the authorities or law enforcement officers.⁶

To carry out the task of eradicating corruption, the Prosecutor's Office cannot work alone by relying on the capabilities of the prosecutor's office without cooperation with other agencies. According to applicable regulations, investigators of corruption crimes are the Prosecutor and the Police, so cooperation is needed between these two law enforcers who must support and help each other for the success of the investigation of corruption crimes. Cooperation is often a weakness in eradicating criminal acts.

Therefore, the role of the Prosecutor in Aceh Tamiang Regency is very necessary in handling corruption. It is expected that the prosecutor can make initiatives so that corruption, especially in Aceh Tamiang Regency, does not occur. Based on the background above, the author has chosen the title of this research, namely: ***“The Role of the Prosecutor's Office in Eradicating Corruption in Aceh Tamiang Regency”***.

⁴Jan. S. Maringka, 2017, *Prosecutorial Reform in the National Legal System*, Sinar Grafika, Jakarta, p. 49.

⁵Okny Riza Wijayanto. “The Role of the Prosecutor's Office in Handling Corruption Cases in Banjarnegara Regency”. Faculty of Social Sciences, Semarang State University 2007, page 4

⁶Agustinus Dian Leo Putra. "The Role of the Prosecutor's Office in Handling the Eradication of Corruption in the Jurisdiction of the Blora District Attorney's Office". Master of Law Program, Sultan Agung Islamic University, Semarang 2021, page 9

Formulation of the problem

The main problems in this research are:

1. How The Role of the Prosecutor's Office in Eradicating Corruption in Aceh Tamiang Regency?
2. How are the obstacles of the Prosecutor's Office in Eradication of Corruption in Aceh Tamiang Regency?

Research purposes

The objectives of this research are:

1. To know and study The Role of the Prosecutor's Office in Eradicating Criminal Acts of Corruption in Aceh Tamiang Regency
2. To find out and study the obstacles faced by the prosecutor's office in Eradication of Corruption in Aceh Tamiang Regency

LITERATURE REVIEW

Definition of Corruption

Corruption comes from the Latin word "corruptio" or "corruptus" which means damage, ugliness, depravity, dishonesty, can be bribed, and immoral purity. And then appeared in English and French "Corruption" which means abusing his authority, to benefit himself. Meanwhile, according to the complete dictionary "Web Ster's Third New International Dictionary" the definition of corruption is an invitation (from a political official) with improper considerations (eg bribes) to commit a violation of duty.⁷

Corruption is a crime that is carried out with great calculation by those who actually feel like they are educated and learned. Corruption can also occur in situations where someone holds a position that involves the distribution of financial resources and has the opportunity to misuse it for personal gain. corruption as behavior that deviates from formal duties as a public employee to gain financial gain or increase status. In addition, material, emotional, or symbolic benefits can also be obtained.⁸

According to the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 20 of 2001 concerning amendments to Law Number 31 of 1999 concerning the Eradication of Criminal Acts of Corruption, corruption is defined as unlawfully carrying out acts of enriching oneself or others or a corporation that can harm state finances or the state economy. So the elements that must be met so that an act can be considered corruption are:⁹

- a. Unlawfully
- b. Enriching yourself or others
- c. Can be detrimental to the country's finances or economy

⁷Robert Klitgaard, *Eradicating Corruption*, 2nd Ed., 2nd Printing, Jakarta, Yayasan Obor Indonesia, 2011, p. 29

⁸Nadiatus Salama, *Indonesian Corruption Phenomenon (Study on Motives and Process of Corruption)*, Semarang, IAIN Walisongo Research Center. 2010, page 16

⁹Arya Maheka. *Recognizing and Eradicating Corruption*. Jakarta, Corruption Eradication Commission of the Republic of Indonesia, 2006. p.14

The causes of corruption include:¹⁰

1. Individual Aspects

Corruption perpetrators When viewed from the perspective of the perpetrator of corruption, the reasons for committing corruption can be in the form of motivation from within himself, which can also be said as his desire, intention, or awareness to do so. The reasons why someone is motivated to commit corruption include the following:

- a) Human Greed
- b) Insufficient Moral Strength Facing Temptation
- c) Income Insufficient to Cover Reasonable Living Needs
- d) Urgent Needs of Life
- e) Consumptive Lifestyle
- f) Lazy or Unwilling to Work Hard
- g) Religious Teachings Not Implemented Correctly

2. Organizational Aspects

Organizations in this case are organizations in a broad sense, including the system of organizing the community environment. Organizations that are victims of corruption or where corruption occurs usually contribute to corruption because they open up opportunities or chances for corruption to occur. Among the causes are

- a, Lack of Role Models from Leaders
- a. Absence of Proper Organizational Culture
- b. Accountability System in Government Agencies is Inadequate
- c. Weaknesses of Management Control Systems
- d. Management Tends to Cover Up Corruption Within Its Organization

3. Community Aspect

Places where individuals and organizations are located include:

- a) The values that apply in society are apparently conducive to corruption.
- b) The public is less aware that the ones most harmed by every corrupt practice are the public itself.
- c) The public is less aware that the public itself is involved in every corrupt practice
- d) The public is less aware that prevention and eradication of corruption will only be successful if the public actively participates in it.

Forms and Types of Criminal Acts of Corruption

From a legal perspective, the definition of corruption has been clearly explained in 13 articles in Law Number 31 of 1999 which has been amended by Law Number 20 of 2001 concerning the Eradication of Criminal Acts of Corruption. Based on these articles, corruption is formulated into 30 forms/types of criminal acts of corruption. These articles

¹⁰BPKP, National Corruption Eradication Strategy, First Edition, Jakarta, BPKP Education and Supervision Center, 2009, p. 257

explain in detail the acts that can be subject to criminal sanctions for corruption. The thirty forms/types of criminal acts of corruption can basically be grouped as follows:¹¹

1. State financial losses
2. Bribery
3. Embezzlement in office
4. Blackmail
5. Fraudulent acts
6. Conflict of interest in procurement
7. Gratification

In addition to the forms/types of criminal acts of corruption that have been explained above, there are still other criminal acts related to criminal acts of corruption as stated in Law Number 31 of 1999 in conjunction with Law Number 20 of 2001. The types of criminal acts related to criminal acts of corruption are:¹²

1. Obstructing the process of investigating corruption cases
2. Do not provide information or provide incorrect information
3. Banks that do not provide information on the suspect's account
4. Witnesses or experts who do not provide information or provide false information
5. A person who holds official secrets does not provide information or provides false information.
6. Witnesses who reveal the reporter's identity

Corruption can be divided into several types or typologies, including:¹³

- a. Transactional Corruption, a type of corruption that refers to a tip-and-pay agreement between the giver and the recipient, where both parties gain a benefit.
- b. Kinship Corruption, a type of corruption involving the abuse of power and authority for various benefits for friends or relatives and their cronies.
- c. Extortionist corruption, usually corruption that is forced upon a party accompanied by threats, terror, pressure on people's interests and things like that.
- d. Incentive Corruption, corruption carried out by providing certain services or goods to another party for future benefits.
- e. Defensive Corruption, namely the injured party is forced to become involved in it or causes certain parties to become trapped or even become victims of corruption.

¹¹M. Syamsa Ardisasmita. "Definition of Corruption According to Legal Perspective and E-Announcement for More Open, Transparent and Accountable Governance". Kpk, National Seminar on Efforts to Improve the Government Goods/Services Procurement System. Jakarta, August 23, 2006, page 4

¹²Ibid, page 6

¹³Gm. Nurdjana. Corruption in Business Practices Empowering Law Enforcers, Action Programs and Strategies for Overcoming Corruption Problems. Jakarta, Gramedia Pustaka Utama, 2005. p. 72

- f. Autogenic corruption is corruption carried out by one person, without any other person or party being involved in it.
- g. Supportive Corruption, corruption carried out by providing support

Definition of Prosecutor's Office

The prosecutor comes from the Sanskrit word *adhyaksa* which means "superintendent" which means a supervisor or controller of social matters. Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 11 of 2021 concerning the Attorney General's Office of the Republic of Indonesia, explains that a prosecutor is a functional official who is authorized by law to act as a public prosecutor and implement court decisions that have obtained permanent legal force and other authorities based on law.¹⁴

In carrying out its duties and authorities, the Prosecutor's Office is led by the Attorney General who oversees six Deputy Attorneys General and the Head of the High Prosecutor's Office in each province. The Prosecutor's Office is in a central position with a strategic role in strengthening national resilience. Because the Prosecutor's Office is at the axis and becomes a filter between the investigation process and the examination process in court and also as the implementer of court decisions and decisions. Thus, the Prosecutor's Office as the controller of the case process (*Dominus Litis*), because only the Prosecutor's Office institution can determine whether a case can be submitted to the Court or not based on valid evidence according to Criminal Procedure Law.

The duties and authorities of the prosecutor's office are regulated in Article 30 of Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 16 of 2004 concerning the Attorney General's Office of the Republic of Indonesia, namely:

1. In the criminal field, the prosecutor's office has the following duties and authorities:
 - a. Conducting prosecution
 - b. Implementing judges' decisions and court decisions that have obtained permanent legal force;
 - c. Supervise the implementation of conditional criminal decisions, supervised criminal decisions, and conditional release decisions.
 - d. Conducting investigations into certain criminal acts based on laws
 - e. Complete certain case files and for that purpose can carry out additional examinations before being transferred to the court, the implementation of which is coordinated with the investigator.
2. In the civil and state administrative fields, the prosecutor's office with special powers can act both inside and outside the court for and on behalf of the state or government.
3. In the field of public order and security, the prosecutor's office also organizes the following activities:
 - a. Increasing legal awareness in society

¹⁴Rm. Surachman. Prosecutors in Various Countries, Their Roles and Positions, Jakarta, Sinar Grafika, 2022, p.3.

- b. Safeguarding law enforcement policies
- c. Supervision of the circulation of printed goods
- d. Supervision of beliefs that can endanger society and the state
- e. Prevention of abuse and/or blasphemy of religion
- f. Research and development of law and static criminal (Putra, 2021).

The Prosecutor's Office is also the only institution that implements criminal decisions (executive ambtenaar). In addition to playing a role in criminal cases, the Prosecutor's Office also has other roles in Civil Law and State Administration. The Prosecutor as the executor of this authority is given the authority as a Public Prosecutor and to implement court decisions, and other authorities based on the Law.

The function of the Prosecutor's Office includes preventive and repressive aspects in criminal matters as well as State Attorneys in Civil and State Administration. Preventive aspects, in the form of increasing public legal awareness, securing law enforcement policies, securing the circulation of printed money, supervising religious beliefs, preventing abuse and/or blasphemy, legal research and development and criminal statistics. Repressive aspects carry out prosecutions in criminal cases, implement Judge's determinations and court decisions, supervise the implementation of conditional release decisions, complete certain case files originating from Police Investigators or Civil Servant Investigators (PPNS)¹⁵.

METHOD

Types of research

This type of research is normative legal research, namely by using a statutory regulatory approach. The focus of normative legal research, in accordance with the unique character of legal science, lies in the legal review or legal study of positive law, which includes three layers of legal science, consisting of legal dogmatics review, namely the review carried out on identification in positive law, especially statutes. While at the level of legal theory, a review is carried out on theories that can be used. The type of research in this study is normative legal research that critically and comprehensively examines the legal enforcement of traffic violations.

Problem Approach

The problem approach used in this study is the statutory regulatory approach. The statutory regulatory approach is used because what will be studied is the legal rules related to this study. This approach is carried out by examining all laws and regulations related to police discretion through penal mediation. This approach requires understanding the hierarchy and principles of laws and regulations.

¹⁵Adang Yesmil Anwar, *Criminal Justice System*, 1st ed., Bandung, Widya Padjajaran, 2011, p. 196.

Source of Legal Material

Primary legal materials consist of laws and government regulations, court decisions that have permanent legal force, other related regulations such as the Criminal Code, Law Number 20 of 2001 concerning the Eradication of Corruption. Secondary legal materials are materials that provide explanations regarding primary legal materials such as research, proceedings related to research. Tertiary legal materials are materials that provide instructions or explanations for primary legal materials and secondary materials such as dictionaries, encyclopedias (wikipedia) and tables related to the object of research.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Prosecutor's Office is the only state institution that is a government apparatus that has the authority to transfer criminal cases, prosecute perpetrators of criminal acts in court and implement the determination and verdict of criminal judges, this power is a characteristic of the Prosecutor's Office that distinguishes other law enforcement institutions or agencies. In special crimes in this case corruption, the Prosecutor acts as an investigator and public prosecutor. As an investigator, special expertise and skills are needed to search for and collect evidence so that the suspect can be found. Basically, the investigation and inquiry of every crime is the beginning in handling every crime, especially corruption.¹⁶

The role of the prosecutor's office in preventing corruption crimes is in line with the relative theory in sharpening the mechanism of the preventive function. In preventive efforts, a task force (satgas) was formed. In addition, the Prosecutor's Intelligence was also formed including intelligence activities for investigation, security, and mobilization to prevent criminal acts to support law enforcement, both preventive and repressive in the fields of ideology, politics, economics, finance, socio-culture, defense and security, implementing prevention against certain people and/or participating in maintaining public order and security (Iswara, 2020)

The duties and roles of the Prosecutor's Office are regulated in Article 30 of Law Number 16 of 2004 concerning the Indonesian Prosecutor's Office, which states:

- 1) *In the criminal field, the prosecutor's office has the following duties and authorities:*
 - a. *Conducting prosecution;*
 - b. *Implementing judges' decisions and court decisions that have obtained permanent legal force;*
 - c. *Supervise the implementation of conditional criminal decisions, supervised criminal decisions, and conditional release decisions.*
 - d. *Conducting investigations into certain criminal acts based on the law*
 - e. *Complete certain case files and for that purpose can carry out additional examinations before being transferred to the court, the implementation of which is coordinated with the investigator.*
- 2) *In the civil and state administrative fields, the prosecutor's office with special powers can act both inside and outside the court for and on behalf of the state or government.*

¹⁶Yasmira Saragih, Op.Cit, page 57

- 3) *In the field of public order and security, the prosecutor's office also organizes the following activities:*
- a. *Increasing public legal awareness*
 - b. *Safeguarding law enforcement policies*
 - c. *Supervision of the circulation of printed goods*
 - d. *Supervision of religious beliefs that can endanger society and the state;*
 - e. *Prevention of abuse and/or blasphemy of religion*
 - f. *Research and development of criminal law and statistics.*

Law Number 11 of 2021 concerning Amendments to Law Number 16 of 2004 concerning the Attorney General's Office of the Republic of Indonesia adds 3 additional articles to Article 30 concerning the authority of the prosecutor's office, namely:

Article 30A

In asset recovery, the Prosecutor's Office has the authority to conduct tracing, confiscation and return of assets obtained through criminal acts and other assets to the state, victims or those entitled to them.

Article 30B

In the field of law enforcement intelligence, the Prosecutor's Office has the authority to:

- a. *Carrying out investigative, surveillance and fundraising functions for the benefit of law enforcement;*
- b. *Creating conditions that support and secure the implementation of development;*
- c. *Conducting law enforcement intelligence cooperation with other state intelligence agencies and/or intelligence providers, both domestically and abroad.*
- d. *Implementing prevention of corruption, collusion, nepotism; and*
- e. *Carry out multimedia monitoring.*

Article 30C

In addition to carrying out the duties and authorities as referred to in Article 30, Article 30A, and Article 30B, the Prosecutor's Office:

- a. *Organizing criminal statistics and judicial health activities for the prosecutor's office;*
- b. *Participate and be active in seeking the truth regarding serious human rights violations and certain social conflicts in order to achieve justice.*
- c. *Participate and be active in handling criminal cases involving witnesses and victims as well as the rehabilitation, restitution and compensation processes.*
- d. *Conducting penal mediation, carrying out execution seizures for payment of criminal fines and substitute criminal penalties as well as restitution.*
- e. *Can provide information as information and verification material regarding the existence or absence of alleged violations of the law that are being or have been processed in criminal cases to occupy public office at the request of the authorized agency.*
- f. *Carrying out its functions and authorities in the field of Civil Affairs and/or other public fields as regulated by law*

- g. Carrying out execution seizure for payment of criminal fines and compensation*
- h. Submit a judicial review; and*
- i. Conduct wiretapping based on special laws that regulate wiretapping and organize a monitoring center in the field of criminal acts.*

Law enforcement is not only concerned with making or implementing the law itself, but also with what law enforcement officers do in anticipating and overcoming problems in law enforcement. Therefore, in law enforcement efforts that occur in society can be done in 3 (three) ways, namely:¹⁷

1. Preventive

Preventive efforts are law enforcement efforts that focus on prevention efforts before violations of the law occur and indirectly without using sanctions/punishment.

2. Educational

Educational efforts are law enforcement efforts by providing information through educational mechanisms to the public (for example by installing banners, etc.)

3. Repressive

Repressive efforts are one of the law enforcement efforts carried out by law enforcement officers which place more emphasis on eradication/action after a violation of the law has occurred by using sanctions provided by the law itself (statutory regulations).

The Role of the Prosecutor's Office in Eradicating Criminal Acts of Corruption in Aceh Tamiang Regency

The legal basis for the authority of the Prosecutor's Office to play an active role in preventing and eradicating criminal acts of corruption in Aceh Tamiang Regency is:¹⁸

1. Law Number 11 of 2021 concerning Amendments to Law Number 16 of 2004 concerning the Attorney General's Office of the Republic of Indonesia
2. Law Number 31 of 1999 in conjunction with Law Number 20 of 2001 concerning the Eradication of Criminal Acts of Corruption.
3. Presidential Regulation Number 55 of 2012 concerning the National Strategy for the Prevention and Eradication of Corruption for the Long Term 2012-2025 and the Medium Term 2012-2014
4. Presidential Instruction Number 1 of 2013 concerning Action to Prevent and Eradicate Corruption in 2013
5. Presidential Regulation Number 38 of 2010 concerning the Organization and Work Procedures of the Attorney General's Office of the Republic of Indonesia
6. Regulation of the Attorney General of the Republic of Indonesia Number: PER-006/A/JA/2017 concerning the Organization and Work Procedures of the Attorney General's Office of the Republic of Indonesia which explains that the Head of the High

¹⁷Made Agus Mahendra Iswara, Op.Cit, p. 75

¹⁸Interview with the Head of the Aceh Tamiang District Attorney's Office, Mr. Joko Wibisono, SH, MH on November 30, 2023

Prosecutor's Office has the task of implementing policies, enforcing the law, justice, both preventive and repressive, and other legal actions.¹⁹

In general, the role of the Indonesian Attorney General's Office in eradicating criminal acts of corruption is regulated in Article 21 and Article 22 of Government Regulation Number 38 of 2010 concerning the Organization and Work Procedures of the Indonesian Attorney General's Office, which states:

Article 21

- 1) *The Deputy Attorney General for Special Crimes has the duty and authority to carry out the duties and authority of the prosecutor's office in the field of special crimes.*
- 2) *The scope of the special criminal offenses as referred to in paragraph (1) includes investigations, inquiries, pre-prosecution, additional examinations, prosecution, legal efforts, implementation of judges' decisions and court decisions which have permanent legal force, examination and supervision of the implementation of conditional sentences and decisions on conditional release in special criminal offenses and other legal actions.*

Article 22

In carrying out the duties and authorities as referred to in Article 21, the Deputy Attorney General for Special Crimes carries out the following functions:

- a. *Policy formulation in the field of special crimes*
- b. *Implementation of law enforcement in the field of special crimes*
- c. *Coordination and synchronization of policy implementation in the field of special criminal acts*
- d. *Implementation of working relations with agencies/institutions both domestically and abroad*
- e. *Monitoring, analysis, evaluation and reporting of the implementation of activities in the field of special crimes*
- f. *Carrying out other duties assigned by the attorney general.*

According to the Head of the Aceh Tamiang District Attorney's Office, Mr. Joko Wibisono, SH, MH, in implementing the prevention of criminal acts of corruption in the Aceh Tamiang Regency area, the Aceh Tamiang District Attorney's Office is carrying out several programs in the form of:²⁰

- a. Establishment of a Special Task Force for Handling and Settlement of Corruption Crime Cases (Satgasus P3TPK)

The Head of the Aceh Tamiang District Attorney's Office formed a Team of Prosecutors and Investigators in order to create law enforcement that is professional and clean. In addition to being tasked with handling and resolving corruption cases, the Satgasus P3TPK Team also prevents corruption in the Aceh Tamiang Regency area.

¹⁹Ismarandy, Alfi Syahrin, M. Hamdan, Rosnidar Sembiring. "The Role of the Prosecutor's Office in Preventing and Handling Criminal Acts of Village Fund Corruption in the Jurisdiction of the High Prosecutor's Office of Sumatra". *Iuris Studia: Journal of Legal Studies*. Volume 2 Number 2, June 2021, page 196

²⁰Interview with the Head of the Aceh Tamiang District Attorney's Office, Mr. Joko Wibisono, SH, MH on November 30, 2023

b. Forming a Government and Development Monitoring and Security Team (TP4)

The formation of this team is based on the policy of the Regulation of the Attorney General of the Republic of Indonesia Number PER-014/A/JA/11/2015 concerning the Technical and Administrative Work Mechanism of the Team for Guarding and Securing the Government and Development of the Attorney General's Office of the Republic of Indonesia. The guarding, securing, supporting the government and development are carried out in the following ways:

- 1) Providing legal information within government agencies, BUMN, BUMD and other related parties regarding planning, auctions, work implementation, supervision of work implementation, licensing, procurement of goods and services, administrative order and orderly management of state finances;
- 2) Conducting discussions or debates with government agencies, BUMN/BUMD to identify problems faced in budget absorption and development implementation;
- 3) Providing legal information and counseling, either on the initiative of TP4 or at the request of parties who require it, the place and time of implementation of which is determined based on agreement and according to needs;
- 4) TP4 can involve other agencies or parties that have the capacity, competence and are relevant to the legal information and counseling material that will be delivered to government agencies, BUMN and BUMD.

The function of TP4D is regulated in Point 3 paragraph 2-5 KEP-152/A/JA/10/2015, namely:

- 1) Can provide legal assistance in every stage of the development program from start to finish, in the form of:
 - a) Legal discussion from the perspective of implementing regulations, laws and regulations, mechanisms and procedures with budget management officials regarding problems faced in terms of budget absorption.
 - b) Legal opinions in the planning, auction, implementation, supervision stages of work implementation and procurement of goods and services, both on behalf of TP4 and on behalf of requests from agencies and parties requiring them.
- 2) Coordinate with the Government Internal Supervisory Apparatus to prevent deviations that have the potential to hinder, thwart and cause losses to state finances,
- 3) Jointly monitor and evaluate the implementation of development work and programs
- 4) Carrying out repressive law enforcement when sufficient preliminary evidence is found after coordination with the Government Internal Supervisory Apparatus regarding the occurrence of unlawful acts and/or other acts that result in losses for the state.

c. Implementing the Prosecutor Enters the Village Program, Prosecutor Friend of the Village and Prosecutor Guard the Village (Guarding the Village)

The Aceh Tamiang District Attorney's Office has formed the Prosecutor Enters the Village, Prosecutor Friend of the Village and Prosecutor Guard Village (Guard the Village) programs, which are tasked with providing assistance and supervision to the distribution and management of village funds to avoid deviations and misuse and to

provide legal awareness to village communities regarding the potential for corruption that occurs in the village.

The village guard prosecutor program is an implementation of the instructions of the Deputy Attorney General for Intelligence in implementing the cooperation agreement between the Attorney General's Office and the Ministry of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions, and Transmigration in order to oversee the distribution and utilization of village funds. The Village Guard application is an effort by the Attorney General's Office to be able to reach all villages in Indonesia. The village guard program helps village officials not to do other things (deviations), so that village officials become brave and not afraid to implement the village fund program because of the clarity through this assistance.

- d. Optimizing corruption handling using the Corruption Impact Assessment (CIA) method
- One form of implementation of handling corruption crimes carried out by the Prosecutor's Office is to coordinate with the local government by describing in the form of a notification letter regarding the problem points that have occurred in government agencies that have committed corruption, so as not to make the same mistakes in budget management. This is called the Corruption Impact Assessment (CIA). A new approach to eradicating corruption, namely the paradigmatic one formulated in CIA, means not only punishing the perpetrators of corruption but no less important is to repair the damage or root of the problem so that corruption does not happen again.

According to the Head of the Aceh Tamiang District Attorney's Office, Mr. Joko Wibisono, SH, MH, in the Process of Handling Corruption Crimes in the Aceh Tamiang Regency area, the Aceh Tamiang District Attorney's Office carries out several stages, namely:²¹

1. Investigation

In special criminal acts, the prosecutor acts as an investigator as regulated in Article 30 paragraph (1) letter d of Law Number 16 of 2004 concerning the Indonesian Attorney General's Office. In contrast to general crimes where initial data is obtained from reports or complaints, criminal acts of corruption originate from:

- 1) Vice President
- 2) Minister/Inspector General/Inspector of Prop/Inspector of Cooperatives and Regional Government
- 3) Intelligence apparatus
- 4) DPR (which is the result of the BPK audit) (Wijayanto, 2007)

After the initial data is available, an "Investigation Order" is issued to determine whether or not there is a criminal act of corruption that has occurred. If sufficient initial evidence is not obtained, the investigation will not be continued. If sufficient initial evidence is found, the investigation will be escalated to the investigation stage, and then an Investigation Order will be issued.

²¹Interview with the Head of the Aceh Tamiang District Attorney's Office, Mr. Joko Wibisono, SH, MH on November 30, 2023

2. Investigation

Corruption crime investigators will begin their investigation after receiving an investigation warrant from the Head of the District Attorney's Office. Investigators who carry out the duties in the Warrant, immediately make an "Investigation Plan" (Rendik) by understanding the results of the investigation and regulations related to the corruption crime being investigated so that they can determine the deviations that have occurred and the evidence supporting the deviations so that the modus operandi can be determined.

Not all corruption cases that are investigated can be escalated to the prosecution stage. If one of the elements is not supported by evidence, or there are excusing reasons based on Jurisprudence, because the unlawful nature is not proven, then the case is issued a Letter of Order to Stop Investigation (SP3). If the investigation has been completed, and from the results of the investigation evidence is obtained regarding the crime that occurred, then the results of the investigation are stated in the case file. The investigation has been completed if the public prosecutor does not return the results of the investigation within seven days or before that time the public prosecutor has notified the investigator that the investigation case file is complete. If the investigation has been completed and the files are received by the public prosecutor, the public prosecutor, based on the results of the investigation, prepares an indictment and then carries out the prosecution.

3. Prosecution Stage

After the public prosecutor receives the case files from the investigator, and according to the public prosecutor the files are complete and can be prosecuted, then the public prosecutor will make an indictment as soon as possible. The public prosecutor conducts careful research. Especially on all elements of the crime to be charged, whether they have been supported by evidence, and the applicable formal requirements. If in his opinion there are still deficiencies, then they can be completed by himself or returned to the investigator to be completed. If after the improvements are made it turns out that there are elements that are not proven or there are things that indicate that the suspect cannot be blamed, then a Letter of Termination of Prosecution (SKPP) is issued.

Termination of prosecution may occur if the public prosecutor is of the opinion that:

1. Insufficient evidence in the case
2. The incident turned out not to be a criminal act.
3. The case is closed by law

This termination of prosecution is carried out by the Public Prosecutor by making a letter of determination to terminate the prosecution. In the event that the prosecution is terminated, then the suspect who is in detention must be released, if later there are new reasons obtained by the public prosecution from the investigator, which come from witness statements, objects or clues, then it does not rule out the possibility of carrying out a prosecution.

Obstacles in the Prosecutor's Office Eradication of Corruption in Aceh Tamiang Regency

Corruption is a complicated crime to uncover along with the increasing development of technology and the increasingly sophisticated modus operandi, so that law enforcers, including the Prosecutor's Office, often encounter obstacles in efforts to uncover and eradicate corruption that occurs. These obstacles make it increasingly difficult to uncover corruption cases, so that it takes a long time and special methods in handling them.

According to the Head of the Aceh Tamiang District Attorney's Office, Mr. Joko Wibisono, SH, MH, the obstacles faced by the Aceh Tamiang District Attorney's Office in terms of investigation and prosecution are as follows:²²

1. Criminal acts of corruption are generally carried out by several people who mutually enjoy the benefits of the results of their actions so that they will cover up or protect each other because they do not want to implicate their friends or are even afraid of being involved and made suspects by law enforcement;
2. Corruption perpetrators generally have a relatively high level of education and have expertise in their field so that early on, corruption perpetrators hide or cover up their actions and eliminate evidence related to their actions. This will clearly complicate the investigation carried out by the Prosecutor's Office.
3. The perpetrators of corruption are generally superiors/leaders (officials) so that the perpetrators are protected by the corps/agency, in addition, the witnesses are subordinates/staff, while the suspects/defendants are their superiors so that sometimes in court witnesses are reluctant to give true testimony and only say they forgot or don't remember anymore, and it is not uncommon for witnesses to withdraw statements that were given during the investigation stage. This happens because they have been influenced or pressured or threatened or even rewarded so that the evidence is obscured and the proof is weakened.
4. The difficulty in obtaining legally valid evidence and materials in uncovering corruption cases, perpetrators of corruption and witnesses and people involved in it deliberately remove or hide evidence and materials so that investigators / public prosecutors will have difficulty in uncovering corruption cases.
5. In criminal acts of corruption, there is still intervention from government/state officials or political party figures who have power and many people who try to defend or free the accused from criminal responsibility, either by using the authority of their position or through family means.
6. The lack of witnesses supporting the evidence of corruption cases. Because witnesses in corruption cases do not feel disadvantaged, they do not have any interests or material expectations for the handling and eradication of corruption that occurs. Even if it is still possible, they avoid being used as witnesses in corruption cases on the grounds of increasing the burden of responsibility, wasting time that should be used for work or even

²²Interview with the Head of the Aceh Tamiang District Attorney's Office, Mr. Joko Wibisono, SH, MH on November 30, 2023

- being afraid of being suspected of being involved and being named a suspect in a case that is being investigated by the Prosecutor's Office.
7. The difficulty that arises is in terms of investigators to find the suspect's or his family's property obtained from the proceeds of corruption to be confiscated as evidence. This confiscation is very important in nature, namely to return state finances that have been corrupted, to then be used to carry out development. Basically, handling corruption is prioritized to return state finances
 8. Limited facilities and infrastructure in eradicating corruption, The facilities and infrastructure owned by the Prosecutor's Office are currently not sufficient to support efforts to eradicate corruption as a whole. The Prosecutor's Office also does not have the facilities and infrastructure related to testing physical work, for example, a coror drill measuring tool that can be used to take samples of the volume and quality of physical work carried out by partners. What has been done by the Prosecutor's Office in testing physical work is by asking experts to check and renting the equipment, which costs quite a lot and the availability of time for technical experts is also very limited so that the investigation activities carried out by the Prosecutor's Office are not optimal.

CONCLUSION

In corruption cases, the Prosecutor's Office has the authority as a public prosecutor as well as an investigator. The prosecutor's authority as an investigator in special crimes is regulated by Law Number 16 of 2004 concerning the Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Indonesia, especially in Article 30 Paragraph 1 letter d. Handling of corruption cases carried out by the Prosecutor's Office, both at the central and regional levels, focuses more on corruption cases with a fairly high loss value in line with the Deputy Attorney General's Instructions for Special Crimes, which states that handling corruption cases is prioritized on disclosing cases that are big fish (large scale, seen from the perpetrators and/or the value of state financial losses) and still going on (corruption cases that are carried out continuously or sustainably).

Criminal law enforcement, especially corruption crimes, prioritizes the return of state losses from perpetrators of corruption. Efforts to return state losses from perpetrators of corruption will be successful if there is cooperation between law enforcement officers (Police, Prosecutors or the Corruption Eradication Committee) to uncover corruption, especially in efforts to return state losses. Without such cooperation, it will be difficult to return state losses.

REFERENCES

- Abdul Haris, Umar Ma'ruf, and Sri Kusriyah. "Role And Function Of Attorney In Order To Optimize The Prevention Of Corruption Through Establishment Of Tp4p/D (Case Studies In State Attorney Of Grobogan)", *Jurnal Daulat Hukum* Volume 2 Issue 4, December 2019.
- Adang Yesmil Anwar. 2011. *Sistem Peradilan Pidana*, Cet. Ke-1, Widya Padjajaran, Bandung.

- Agustinus Dian Leo Putra. "Peran Kejaksaan Dalam Menangani Pemberantasan Tindak Pidana Korupsi Di Wilayah Hukum Kejaksaan Negeri Blora". Program Magister Hukum Universitas Islam Sultan Agung Semarang, 2021.
- Arya Maheka. 2006. Mengenali Dan Memberantas Korupsi. Komisi Pemberantasan Korupsi Republik Indonesia, Jakarta.
- Bpkp. 2009. Strategi Pemberantasan Korupsi Nasional Cet I, Pusat Pendidikan Dan Pengawasan Bpkp, Jakarta.
- Gm. Nurdjana. 2005. Korupsi Dalam Praktek Bisnis Pemberdayaan Penegak Hukum, Program Aksi Dan Strategi Penanggulangan Masalah Korupsi. Gramedia Pustaka Utama, Jakarta.
- I Made Agus Mahendra Iswara dan Ketut Adi Wirawan. "Peran Kejaksaan dalam Pemberantasan Tindak Pidana Korupsi Desa di Indonesia". Kertha Wicaksana, Volume 14, Nomor 1, 2020.
- Ismarandy, Alfi Syahrin, M. Hamdan, Rosnidar Sembiring. "Peran Kejaksaan Dalam Pencegahan Dan Penanganan Tindak Pidana Korupsi Dana Desa Di Wilayah Hukum Kejaksaan Tinggi Sumatera". Iuris Studia: Jurnal Kajian Hukum, Volume 2 Nomor 2, Juni 2021.
- Jan. S. Maringka. 2017. Reformasi Kejaksaan Dalam Sistem Hukum Nasional, Sinar Grafika, Jakarta.
- Made Agus Mahendra Iswara dan Ketut Adi Wirawan. "Peran Kejaksaan Dalam Pemberantasan Tindak Pidana Korupsi Desa Di Indonesia". Jurnal Kertha Wicaksana: Sarana Komunikasi Dosen Dan Mahasiswa Volume 14, Nomor 1, 2020.
- M. Syamsa Ardisasmita. "Definisi Korupsi Menurut Perspektif Hukum Dan E-Announcement Untuk Tata Kelola Pemerintahan Yang Lebih Terbuka, Transparan Dan Akuntabel". Kpk, Seminar Nasional Upaya Perbaikan Sistem Penyelenggaraan Pengadaan Barang/Jasa Pemerintah, Jakarta, 23 Agustus 2006.
- Nadiatus Salama. 2010. Fenomena Korupsi Indonesia (Kajian Mengenai Motif Dan Proses Terjadinya Korupsi), Pusat Penelitian IAIN Walisongo, Semarang.
- Oky Riza Wijayanto. "Peranan Lembaga Kejaksaan Dalam Penanganan Perkara Tindak Pidana Korupsi Di Kabupaten Banjarnegara". Fakultas Ilmu Sosial Universitas Negeri Semarang, 2007.
- Robert Klitgaard. 2011. Membasmi Korupsi, Ed, 2, Cet, 2, Yayasan Obor Indonesia, Jakarta.
- Rm. Surachman. 2022. Jaksa Di Berbagai Negara Peranan Dan Kedudukannya, Sinar Grafika, Jakarta.
- Sudhono Iswahyudi. 2003. Makalah Jaksa Agung Muda Tindak Pidana Khusus, Keterkaitan Komisi Pemberantasan Korupsi Dengan Kejaksaan Dalam Penanganan Tindak Pidana Korupsi, Mahkamah Agung, Jakarta.
- Yasmirah Mandasari Saragih. "Peran Kejaksaan Dalam Pemberantasan Tindak Pidana Korupsi Di Indonesia Pasca Undang-Undang Nomor 20 Tahun 2001 Tentang Pemberantasan Tindak Pidana Korupsi". Jurnal Al'adl, Vol Ix Nomor 1, Januari-April 2017.

Legal Actions and Consequences for Corporations Involved in Corruption

Yudiansyah B.¹, Dr. T. Riza Zarzani, S.H., M.H.²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: tengkuriza@umsu.ac.id

Abstract

The purpose of writing this journal is to identify and analyze the methods and motives behind acts of corruption carried out by corporations, as well as to understand the organizational structure and market dynamics that influence these corrupt practices. And to evaluate the legal consequences that apply to corporations involved in acts of corruption and to examine the effectiveness of the application of these penalties in efforts to prevent and overcome corruption among corporations. The approach method used in this study is Normative Law (normative juridical) using a legislative approach, a conceptual approach, and a comparative and empirical approach (field data). The results of the study show that corporations are involved in acts of corruption through various methods that are often complex and covert, driven by motives to increase profits, dominate the market, or avoid regulation. The mechanisms they use range from bribery, tender manipulation, to money laundering practices. Corporations involved in acts of corruption can face a number of legal consequences, ranging from heavy fines, license revocation, asset confiscation, to operational restrictions. Although these penalties are intended to provide a deterrent effect, their effectiveness in preventing corporate corruption often varies. While fines may provide a financial impact, without significant internal changes in corporate culture and governance, the potential for corrupt practices to recur.

Keywords: Legal Analysis, Corporations, Corruption Crimes.

INTRODUCTION

Corruption has long been recognized as one of the greatest threats to the stability and integrity of a country's legal and economic systems. While much of the discussion of corruption focuses on the behavior of individuals, the phenomenon of corporations engaging in corrupt practices often receives less attention. Corporations with significant resources may have the ability to influence public policy, conceal corrupt behavior, and even undermine existing legal structures in ways that individuals cannot. In this context, corporate corruption not only harms the economy but also fosters public distrust of market institutions.

In addition to harming state finances, corruption also slows down national development which slows down the improvement of people's welfare. It is not surprising that corruption is considered a common enemy. The unlawful act of corruption not only harms state finances but also violates the social and economic rights of the entire community. In addition, corruption has weakened the legal system, contributed to the economic crisis, and made it difficult to organize transparent and democratic governance (Romli Atmasasmita, 2012).

With the shift in the global business paradigm, corporations are now central actors in the economic and social dynamics of a country. While many corporations contribute positively through investment, job creation, and innovation, there are a handful of entities that use their power for less than moral purposes. Corporate corruption often involves much

larger sums of money than individual corruption, with a much broader impact on the economy and society.

The Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia has emphasized that the Republic of Indonesia is a State of Law (Khairul Riza, et al., 2022). As a state of law that has an obligation to protect its people from all crimes including corruption, legal instruments are needed with the main objective of eradicating criminal acts of corruption is to build a society based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia that is just, prosperous, and prosperous because corruption has harmed the country's economy, public finances, and ability to develop.

Corruption has become rampant in the lives of Indonesian society. The number of incidents, the amount of state financial losses, and the severity of the crimes committed, which are increasingly systematic and have penetrated all aspects of people's lives, all continue to increase from year to year. In Law Number 20 of 2001 concerning Amendments to Law Number 31 of 1999 concerning the Eradication of Corruption, this condition is recognized and expressed. According to the law, widespread corruption must be classified as a crime whose eradication requires a comprehensive approach because it not only harms state finances but also violates the social and economic rights of society as a whole (Adami Chazawi, 2015).

The law passed in 2001 expanded the definition of corruption to include both "corporations" and "individuals". Every person is referred to as a person or corporation that commits corruption in Article 1 Number 3 of Law Number 20 of 2001 concerning Amendments to Law Number 31 of 1999 concerning the Eradication of Criminal Acts of Corruption, which is stated as a group of people or wealth in the form of a legal entity or not called a corporation.

The principal penalty for corporate crimes according to Law Number 20 of 2001 concerning Amendments to Law Number 31 of 1999 concerning the Eradication of Corruption is a fine, with a maximum penalty of 1/3 (one third), twice, or by stating an increased nominal amount. In addition, corporations can be forced to close all or part of their operations for up to one (1) year.

If a fine is imposed, it will eventually fall into the hands of the state and be returned to the company in the form of capital participation. Likewise, if the sanction is the closure of the company, there will certainly be a state loss in the form of capital or shares included in BUMN (Adami Chazawi, 2018).

The legal consequences of corporate corruption are also complex. While many countries have introduced criminal sanctions for companies involved in corruption, enforcement is often challenging. Companies can have complex structures, cross-border operations, and the resources to pursue their legal cases much more aggressively than individuals.

Considering all these factors, it is important to examine more deeply how corporations engage in corruption, their impact on society and the economy, and the legal consequences they face. Through in-depth analysis, this study aims to provide clearer

insights into the role of corporations in the phenomenon of corruption and its implications for legal and business governance in today's global era.

Based on the description above, the author is interested in conducting further research where the research will be presented in the form of a scientific journal work entitled: "Legal Analysis of Actions and Legal Consequences for Corporations Involved in Corruption".

From the problem and title which has been described above, the formulation of the problem that will be discussed is as follows:

1. How corporations are involved in acts of corruption, and what motives and mechanisms do they use in carrying out corrupt practices??
2. What are the legal consequences faced by corporations involved in acts of corruption, and to what extent is the effectiveness of implementing these penalties in preventing and overcoming corporate corruption?

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH METHODS

The researcher in this section applies the theoretical framework and methodology to analyze the problems above and it needs to be clarified from the beginning about the theoretical framework that uses the theoretical framework and concepts as an analytical tool (Soerya Respationo, 2022). In this methodology section, one of the methods used by the author is to apply the use of the theory of corporate criminalization, and the theory of organs from Otto von Gierke to the problems discussed in this study. (Idham, et al., 2022).

Study used in writing This journal is normative legal research is a legal research of literature by examining library materials (Dollar, Khairul Riza, 2022). The approach method used in this study is Normative Law (normative legal) using a statutory approach, a conceptual approach, and a comparative and empirical approach (field data). What is meant by the normative legal research method is a legal research method carried out by examining library materials or secondary data only.

This research was conducted in order to obtain materials in the form of: "theories, concepts, legal principles and legal regulations related to the subject matter". In this research, the scope is by drawing legal principles, which is carried out on positive law. written or spoken unwritten (Soerjono Soekanto and Sri Mamudji, 2013).

The data sources in this study consist of library research as the main data source and field research as complementary data (Library research and field research) (Zainuddin Ali, 2014). Within the framework of the formation of legal theory, legal norms (law in books), implementation of legal norms (legal behavior, including those that fulfill and deviate (law in actions), social structures and other socio-cultural symptoms are completely observed (Oloan Sitorus and Darwinsyah Minin, 2010).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Corporations Involved in Corruption, Motives and Mechanisms Used in Carrying Out Corrupt Practices

Corporations can engage in corruption through a variety of mechanisms. One is through "bribery," where a company gives something of value to gain a commercial or

regulatory advantage. In addition, corporations can also engage in tender manipulation, tax evasion, and embezzlement.

The motives behind corporate corruption are usually driven by the desire to increase profits, reduce costs, or gain access to resources or markets. In some cases, corporations may feel the need to pay bribes to operate efficiently in a particular country or region, especially in areas with less stringent regulations or where corruption is considered the “business norm.”

Corporate organizational structures often enable or even encourage corrupt practices. For example, if a company has a highly decentralized structure without strict oversight, certain branches or divisions may have more opportunities to engage in corruption. Conversely, a lack of transparency and accountability in the corporate structure can also facilitate corruption (Yasmirah Mandasari Saragih, 2018).

In situations where market competition is intense, corporations may feel compelled to bribe or engage in other corrupt practices to gain a competitive advantage. For example, a corporation may bribe a government official to obtain a government contract or to avoid certain regulations.

Corporate culture also plays a significant role in encouraging or preventing corruption. If integrity and ethics are emphasized in the corporate culture, employees are more likely to avoid corrupt practices. However, if the corporate culture encourages achieving targets by any means, including through corrupt practices, then corruption may become more prevalent.

With the growth of international trade and cross-border investment, multinational corporations often operate in multiple countries with different standards and norms. This can create challenges for companies to maintain consistent ethical and integrity standards across their operations.

Corporate involvement in corrupt acts is a complex phenomenon influenced by various factors, ranging from organizational structure, market dynamics, corporate culture, to the influence of globalization. Understanding how and why corporations engage in corruption is an important step in efforts to prevent and overcome corrupt acts among corporations (Yasmirah Mandasari Saragih, 2017).

In this discussion section, to analyze the motives and mechanisms used by corporations in carrying out corrupt practices using the theory of corporate criminology which emphasizes the analysis of the causes and factors that encourage corporate entities to commit violations of the law. This theory can help researchers understand the economic, structural, and cultural motives that encourage corporations to participate in corruption. (Theo Huijbers, 2019).

Basically, the legal regulation of corruption in the context of corporate criminal liability is regulated in the corruption law in the country concerned. However, in general there are several general principles applied in the regulation (Eva Achjani Zulfa, 2011).

Corporate Criminology Theory is a field of study that explores the causes and contexts in which corporate entities choose to break the law. Using this theory as a

framework, we can understand the motives and mechanisms underlying corporate corrupt practices.

At the heart of corporate criminology theory is the understanding that corporations aim to maximize profits. Economic motives are often the primary drivers behind corruption. Bribing public officials, for example, may be seen as an investment to secure lucrative contracts, obtain permits, or avoid taxes and tariffs. Corruption here is seen as a means to achieve economic efficiency, albeit through unethical or illegal means (Elwi Danil, 2012).

In highly competitive markets, corporations may feel the need to “game the system” in order to remain relevant. Using corrupt practices can be a means to gain a competitive advantage, such as obtaining confidential information about competitors or securing exclusive rights to certain resources.

Corporate criminology theory emphasizes the importance of organizational structure and culture in encouraging or discouraging criminal activity. Corporations with strict hierarchies and a lack of transparency may be more susceptible to corruption, especially when there is pressure to meet certain targets. On the other hand, a corporate culture that promotes ethics and integrity will tend to reduce the risk of corrupt behavior.

In carrying out corrupt practices, corporations often use complex mechanisms to hide their tracks. This may include money laundering, setting up shell companies, or using interpersonal networks to give or receive bribes. The use of technology and international financial systems also allows corporations to move funds in ways that are difficult for authorities to track.

Corporate criminology theory also highlights the lack of effective oversight as a factor that facilitates corporate corruption. In many cases, regulators may not have the resources or expertise to detect or prosecute corrupt practices, providing opportunities for corporations to “get away” with violations (Nurdjana, 2015).

Using the lens of corporate criminology theory allows us to understand corruption not simply as an individual act, but as the result of a number of structural and cultural factors within the corporate world. Economic motives, competitive pressures, and organizational structures are among the many factors that play a role in pushing corporations toward corrupt behavior. By understanding these motives and mechanisms, we can be more effective in preventing and addressing corruption in corporate circles.

Legal Consequences Faced by Corporations Involved in Corruption, and the Effectiveness of the Implementation of Such Penalties in Preventing and Overcoming Corporate Corruption

In this section, we will discuss about the legal consequences faced by corporations involved in corruption, and the extent to which the implementation of these penalties is effective in preventing and overcoming corporate corruption can be analyzed using Otto von Gierke's organ theory (Idham, et al., 2022) which states that a corporation is not a collection of individuals, but is organic and has its own 'life' that is different from its members. Gierke sees corporations as a manifestation of social cooperation that produces something greater than just the total of the individuals involved.

Corporate criminal liability is a legal concept that states that a company or organization can be punished criminally for crimes committed by individuals working for the company. This means that the company can be considered the perpetrator of the crime and subject to criminal sanctions, such as fines or imprisonment, just as the individual who committed the crime. (Andi Hamzah, 2015).

When corporations engage in corrupt acts, there are a range of legal consequences they may face, depending on the jurisdiction and the severity of the offense. Below are some of the most common legal consequences that corporations may face.

One of the most immediate consequences of corrupt acts is financial fines and sanctions. Many jurisdictions have laws that impose significant fines on corporations found guilty of corrupt acts, with the fines often calculated based on the profits derived from the corrupt act or the losses suffered by others.

Corporations involved in corruption may risk losing their licenses or permits to operate. This could mean losing the right to operate in a particular region or industry. While the corporation as an entity may be subject to sanctions, individuals within the corporation, such as executives or employees, may also face criminal charges for their role in the corrupt act. This could result in prison sentences for the individuals involved.

In some cases, corporate assets obtained from corrupt activities or used in such activities may be seized by the government. This may include property, bank accounts, or other assets. In addition to criminal legal action, corporations involved in corruption may also face civil legal action from parties harmed by the corrupt activities, such as injured competitors, the government, or other stakeholders.

While not technically a legal consequence, reputational harm is one of the most damaging and long-lasting impacts of corrupt acts. Damage to public image and trust can have long-term effects on a corporation's business success, including the loss of customers, business partners, and investment opportunities.

In addition to license revocation, corporations involved in corruption may also face operational restrictions. For example, they may be barred from bidding on government contracts or from operating in certain countries. Corporations that have been involved in corrupt practices may come under increased scrutiny from regulators, with the possibility of further investigations and audits in the future.

The application of punishment for corporations involved in corruption is an effort to provide a deterrent effect and prevent future corruption. However, the effectiveness of such punishment can vary depending on various factors.

The following is an in-depth analysis of the effectiveness of the application of penalties in the context of corporate corruption:

1. Amount of Fines and Financial Sanctions

Significant fines can have a significant financial impact on corporations and can act as a deterrent. However, if the fine is only a small portion of the profits derived from the corrupt act or if the corporation has significant financial resources, the deterrent effect of the fine may be limited.

2. Revocation of License or Permit

Revocation of a license or permit can be very effective, especially for corporations that rely on the license or permit for their operations. However, the application of this sanction must be done carefully so as not to harm employees or third parties who are not involved in the corrupt act.

3. Asset Confiscation

Asset confiscation ensures that corporations do not benefit from corrupt practices and can destroy a corporation's financial capacity, making it an effective sanction. However, the confiscation process may require extensive investigation and a long time.

4. Reputational Loss

While not a penalty in the traditional sense, reputational damage often has profound long-term effects on a corporation's operations and sustainability. Reputational damage can affect relationships with customers, investors, and business partners, and is often difficult to repair.

5. Civil Legal Action

Civil legal action by third parties can increase the financial burden on a corporation. However, its effectiveness as a deterrent may be limited unless it is accompanied by significant changes in corporate governance and culture.

6. Operational Restrictions

Operational restrictions, such as a ban on bidding on government contracts, can have significant impacts on corporations and serve as a powerful deterrent.

7. Continuity of Punishment

A one-time penalty may not be effective without ongoing monitoring mechanisms. Ongoing investigations and audits can ensure that corporations comply with the law and improve their practices.

While punishment can be an effective tool to prevent and combat corporate corruption, its success often depends on consistent implementation and monitoring, as well as the willingness of corporations to make internal changes. In addition, a holistic approach that includes punishment, education, and changing corporate culture can be a more effective way to address the problem of corruption among corporations.

Otto von Gierke, a German legal scholar, is known for his theory of "organ theory". According to Gierke, a corporation is not a collection of individuals, but is organic and has its own 'life' that is different from its members. Gierke sees the corporation as a manifestation of social cooperation that produces something greater than the sum of the individuals involved.

Referring to Gierke's thinking, a corporation is an entity that has its own "life" and identity, separate from the individuals that make it up. This provides an interesting perspective on the legal consequences for corporations. By viewing corporations as organic entities, the legal consequences faced by corporations (such as fines or license revocation) affect not only the corporation's finances and operations, but also its 'existence' as a social and economic entity.

Through the lens of Gierke's theory, corporations have an inherent moral responsibility. When a corporation engages in corruption, it is not just the individuals within

it who are guilty, but the entire corporate "organism." Therefore, the legal consequences faced by the corporation must be commensurate with the level of wrongdoing committed by the entity as a whole.

If we accept Gierke's view that corporations are organic entities with their own lives and morality, then the punishments imposed on corporations should be designed to improve the 'morals' of the corporation, not just to deter it. This means that punishments such as fines may not be effective unless they are accompanied by efforts to improve the corporation's internal culture and governance.

In addition to imposing penalties, there may need to be a rehabilitative approach to help corporations get back on track, given that corporations as "organisms" have the capacity to change and grow. This could include ethics training, improved governance, and external monitoring.

By considering Otto von Gierke's organ theory, we gain a profound perspective on how to view corporations and how to address the problem of corruption within corporations. Rather than simply imposing punitive punishments, there is a need to understand and improve the 'soul' of the corporation itself, recognizing that corporations have the potential to change and develop in positive ways.

CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion that associated with problem then you can draw conclusion as following:

1. Corporations engage in corruption through a variety of often complex and covert means, driven by motives to increase profits, dominate markets, or evade regulation. The mechanisms they use range from bribery, tender manipulation, to money laundering. Internal factors such as an organizational culture that tolerates violations, as well as external factors such as weak oversight and regulation, contribute to these corrupt practices. Awareness of the methods and reasons behind corporate corruption is essential for developing more effective prevention strategies.
2. Corporations involved in corrupt practices can face a range of legal consequences, from heavy fines, license revocation, asset confiscation, to operational restrictions. While these penalties are intended to provide a deterrent effect, their effectiveness in preventing corporate corruption often varies. While fines may provide a financial impact, without significant internal changes in corporate culture and governance, the potential for corrupt practices to recur. Therefore, a holistic approach that combines sanctions, education, and structural reform is key in efforts to prevent and address corruption at the corporate level.

REFERENCES

- Adami Chazawi, *Hukum Pidana Materiil dan Formil Korupsi di Indonesia*, Bayu Media, Malang, 2015.
- , *Hukum Pembuktian Tindak Pidana Korupsi*, Alumni, Bandung, 2018.

- Andi Hamzah, Pemberantasan Korupsi melalui Hukum Nasional dan Internasional, Raja Grafindo Persada, Jakarta, 2015.
- Dollar & Khairul Riza, Penerapan Kualifikasi Penyalahguna, Pecandu dan Korban Penyalahgunaan Tindak Pidana Narkotika demi Mewujudkan Nilai Keadilan, Kajian Ilmiah Hukum dan Kenegaraan (KIHAN), Volume 1, Nomor 2, 2022, 13-21. doi: <https://doi.org/10.35912/KIHAN.v1i1.1340>
- Elwi Danil, KORUPSI: Konsep, Tindak Pidana, dan Pemberantasannya, Raja Grafindo Persada, Jakarta, 2012.
- Eva Achjani Zulfa, Pergeseran Paradigma Pemidanaan, Lubuk Agung, Bandung, 2011.
- Idham, Soerya Respationo, Chablullah Wibisono, Legal Political Dimensions, Improvement Expertise Agency Of The Dpr Ri In Implementing Research-Based Legislative Policy Making And Implementation Of Independent Learning And Merdeka Campus In Indonesia, Journal of Legal, Ethical and Regulatory Issues, Volume 25, Issue 5, 2022
- Khairul Riza, Irpan Husein Lubis, Nicha Suwalla, Kepastian Hukum Terhadap Putusan Peradilan Adat Aceh Dalam Penyelesaian Tindak Pidana Pencurian, Jurnal Ilmiah Hukum dan Hak Asasi Manusia (JIHAM), Volume 2, Nomor 1, 2022, 39-47. doi: <https://doi.org/10.35912/jihham.v2i1.1580>
- Nurdjana, Korupsi Dalam Praktik Bisnis, Gramedia Pustaka Utama, Jakarta, 2015.
- Oloan Sitorus dan Darwinsyah Minin, Membangun Teori Hukum Indonesia, Virgo, Medan, 2010
- Otto Hasibuan, Hak Cipta di Indonesia: Tinjauan Khusus Hak Cipta Lagu, Neighbouring Rights dan Collething Society, Alumni, Bandung, 2013
- Romli Atmasasmita, Teori Hukum Integratif, Genta Publishing, Yogyakarta, 2012.
- Soerjono Soekanto dan Sri Mamudji, Penelitian Hukum Normatif suatu Tinjauan Singkat, Radja Grafindo Persada, Jakarta, 2013
- Soerya Respationo dan Idham, Land Registration And Certificate Issuance In A Free Trade Zone Perspective (FTZ), Volume 48- Issue No.3-MAY- 2022
- Theo Huijbers, Filsafat Hukum, Kanisius, Yogyakarta, 2019
- Yasmirah Mandasari Saragih, Peran Kejaksaan dalam Pemberantasan Tindak Pidana Korupsi Di Indonesia Pasca Undang-Undang Nomor 20 Tahun 2001 Tentang Pemberantasan Tindak Pidana Korupsi, Al-Adl: Jurnal Hukum, Vo. 1, Jilid. 9, 2017.
- Yasmirah Mandasari Saragih, Onny Medalin, Unsur-unsur tindak pidana korupsi (analisis unsur penyalahgunaan wewenang dan pengayaan diri sendiri dan korporasi di Indonesia), Seri Konferensi IOP: Ilmu Bumi dan Lingkungan, Vol. 1, Jilid. 126, 2018.
- Undang-Undang Dasar Negara Republik Indonesia Tahun 1945
- Undang-Undang Nomor 20 Tahun 2001 tentang Perubahan atas Undang-Undang Nomor 31 Tahun 1999 tentang Pemberantasan Tindak Pidana Korupsi

Dimensions of Organizational Strategy

Fitriyani Hasibuan¹, Muhammad Isa Indrawan²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: fitriyanihasibuan@gmail.com

Abstract

BPJS Employment has functions and responsibilities such as, carrying out and receiving registration for BPJS participants, collecting and collecting contributions from participants and employers, receiving contribution assistance from the government, managing social security funds for the benefit of participants, collecting and managing data on social security program participants, provide benefits and financial health services in accordance with the provisions of the social security program, and is also responsible for providing information regarding the implementation of the social security program to participants and the community. This research aims to see the influence of work discipline and work motivation on organizational strategies mediated by work supervision at BPJS Employment throughout Medan Raya. The results of this research are as follows; Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Work Supervision with an original sample value of 0.646 and ap value of 0.000. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Strategy with an original sample value of 0.348 and ap value of 0.000. Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Work Supervision with an original sample value of 0.298 and ap value of 0.000. Work Motivation has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Strategy with an original sample value of 0.090 and ap value of 0.209. Work Supervision has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Strategy with an original sample value of 0.508 and ap value of 0.000. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Strategy through Work Supervision with an original sample value of 0.328 and ap value of 0.000. Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Strategy through Work Supervision with an original sample value of 0.151 and ap value of 0.000.

Keywords: Work Discipline, Work Motivation, Organizational Strategy, Work Supervision.

INTRODUCTION

Work discipline is an inseparable part of the organization because without discipline, organizational development will be difficult to achieve. Discipline is a process used to deal with performance problems; this process involves managers in identifying and communicating performance problems to employees (Robert Bacal, quoted in Fahmi, 2013: 42). This is related to how the company handles employee working hours so that no more employees arrive late or go home before closing or the end of the company's operational hours or break times that are used more than they should. Motivation is a desire within a person that causes the person to act. Providing motivation is very important in every company. Employees who have high work motivation will be able to encourage employees to work more enthusiastically and can make a positive contribution to the work that has become their responsibility. Both public and private companies have realized that motivation can improve employee performance and productivity so that company goals can be achieved. Organizational strategy plays a role in identifying various general approaches used by organizations to achieve goals. So that organizations can achieve their goals in two ways, namely through better management of what is currently being done and through the discovery of new things. Another concept explains that organizational strategy is the art of

using the skills and resources of an organization to achieve its goals through effective relationships with the environment in the most favorable conditions.

Formulation of the problem

1. Is dWork discipline has a positive and significant influence on work supervision at BPJS EmploymentBranchThroughout Greater Medan.
2. Is dWork discipline has a positive and significant influence on organizational strategy at BPJS KetenagakerjaanBranchThroughout Greater Medan.
3. Is mWork motivation has a positive and significant influence on work supervision at BPJS EmploymentBranchThroughout Greater Medan.
4. Is mWork motivation has a positive and significant influence on organizational strategy at BPJS KetenagakerjaanBranchThroughout Greater Medan.
5. Is pWork supervision has a positive and significant influence on organizational strategy at BPJS KetenagakerjaanBranchThroughout Greater Medan.
6. Does work discipline have a positive and significant influence on organizational strategy through work supervision at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan?BranchThroughout Greater Medan.
7. Does work motivation have a positive and significant influence on organizational strategy through work supervision at BPJS Employment?BranchThroughout Greater Medan.

Research purposes

1. To find out and analyze the influence dwork discipline towards work supervision at BPJS EmploymentBranchThroughout Greater Medan.
2. To find out and analyze the influence dwork discipline towards organizational strategy at BPJS EmploymentBranchThroughout Greater Medan.
3. To find out and analyze the influence of mwork motivation towards work supervision at BPJS EmploymentBranchThroughout Greater Medan.
4. To find out and analyze the influence of mwork motivation towards organizational strategy at BPJS EmploymentBranchThroughout Greater Medan.
5. To find out and analyze the influence of pwork supervision of organizational strategies at BPJS EmploymentBranchThroughout Greater Medan.
6. To find out and analyze the influence dwork discipline towards organizational strategy through work supervision at BPJS EmploymentBranchAll over Medan.
7. To find out and analyze the influence of mwork motivation towards organizational strategy through work supervision at BPJS KetenagakerjaanBranchAll over Medan.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational Strategy

According to Wahyudi, strategy is a key policy and decision used for management, which has a major impact on financial performance. These policies and decisions usually involve important resources and cannot be easily replaced” (Siregar, 2018).

Strategy Indicators

Strategy indicators according to Siregar (2018) are:

- a. Strategy to balance conflicting forces (Strength)
- b. Strategy is based on different customer value propositions (Values)
- c. Value is created through internal business processes (Progress)
- d. Strategy consists of themes that complement each other (Theme)
- e. Strategic alignment determines the value of intangible assets (Harmony)

Work Discipline

According to Agustini (2019), work discipline is an attitude of obedience to the rules and norms that apply in a company in order to increase employee determination in achieving company/organizational goals.

Work Discipline Indicators

According to Agustini (2019) the indicators of work discipline are as follows:

- a. Attendance rate, namely the number of employees present to carry out work activities in the company which is characterized by a low level of employee absence.
- b. Work procedures, namely rules or provisions that must be adhered to by all members of the organization.
- c. Obedience to superiors, namely following what is directed by superiors to get good results.
- d. Work awareness, namely the attitude of a person who voluntarily does his work well, not because of coercion.
- e. Responsibility, namely the employee's willingness to be responsible for their work, the facilities and infrastructure used, and their work behavior.

Work motivation

According to Hafidzi et al (2019) motivation is the provision of driving force that creates enthusiasm for a person's work so that they are able to collaborate, work effectively and be integrated with all their efforts to achieve satisfaction. Motivation is the main thing that drives someone to work,

Work motivation according to McClelland, translated by Suwanto (2020), is "A set of forces originating from within or outside a person that encourages them to start behaving at work according to a certain format, direction, intensity and time period.

Work motivation indicators

- a. Physical Needs, the need for supporting facilities that can be obtained in the workplace, for example supporting facilities to facilitate the completion of tasks in the office.
- b. The need for safety, these needs for safety include physical safety, stability, dependency, protection and freedom from threatening forces such as fear, anxiety, danger.
- c. Social needs, needs that must be met based on common interests in society, these needs are met together, for example good interaction between each other.

- d. The need for appreciation is the need for appreciation for what a person has achieved, for example the need for status, glory, attention, reputation.
- e. The need for motivation to achieve goals, the need for encouragement to achieve something desired, for example motivation from leadership.

Work Supervision

According to Siagian in Irmayani (2022), the function of supervision is to highlight what is happening at the time of the implementation of ongoing operational activities. If deviations are found, corrective action can be taken so that the organization returns to the actual track. According to Syamsidar (2018), supervision is the process of observing the implementation of all organizational activities to ensure that all work being carried out is in accordance with the previously determined plan.

Monitoring indicators

According to Syamsidar (2017), the supervision indicators are as follows:

- a. Accurate Information about the implementation of activities must be accurate. Inaccurate data from the monitoring system can cause the organization to take incorrect corrective actions or even create problems that do not actually exist.
- b. Timely Information must be collected, delivered and evaluated as soon as possible if corrective actions are to be taken immediately.
- c. Objective and comprehensive. Information must be easy to understand and objective and complete.
- d. Focused on strategic control points. The control system must focus on areas where deviations from standards are most likely to occur or where they would result in the most fatal damage.
- e. Economically realistic The cost of implementing a monitoring system must be lower, or at least equal, to the benefits obtained from the system.
- f. Organizationally realistic The control system must be compatible or harmonious with the realities of the organization.
- g. Coordinated with the organization's work flow. Supervisory information must be coordinated with the organization's work flow, because (1) each stage of the work process can affect the success or failure of the entire operation, and (2) supervisory information must reach all personnel who need it.
- h. Flexible Supervision must have the flexibility to provide responses or reactions to threats or opportunities from the environment.
- i. Serves as a guide and operational An effective control system must indicate, whether detection or deviation from standards, what corrective action should be taken.
- j. Accepted by members of the organization The supervisory system must be able to direct the implementation of the work of members of the organization by encouraging feelings of autonomy, responsibility and achievement.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Research Hypothesis

- H1: Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on work supervision in BPJS Employment Branches Throughout Medan Raya.
- H2: Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on work supervision at BPJS Manpower Branch Office for Greater Medan.
- H3: Work discipline has a positive and significant influence on organizational strategy at BPJS Manpower Branch Office for Greater Medan.
- H4: Work motivation has a positive and significant influence on organizational strategy at BPJS Manpower Branch Office for Greater Medan.
- H5: Work supervision has a positive and significant influence on organizational strategy at BPJS Manpower Branch Office for Greater Medan.
- H6: Work discipline has a positive and significant influence on organizational strategy through work supervision at BPJS Employment Branches throughout Medan Raya.
- H7: Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on work motivation through work supervision at BPJS Employment Branches throughout Medan Raya.

METHOD

Types of research

According to Sugiyono (2017), quantitative research can be interpreted as a method based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations or samples, sampling techniques are generally carried out randomly, data collection uses research instruments, data analysis is quantitative/statistical with the aim of testing the established hypothesis.

Research Location and Research Time

The research period was carried out from August to September 2024. The research location was carried out at the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya, consisting of:

1. Medan City Branch Office at Jl. Kapten Pattimura No. 334, Medan City, North Sumatra. North Sumatra, Phone number / contact: 061-453281.
2. North Medan Branch Office at Jl. Marelan Raya No.108, Tanah Enam Ratus, Medan Marelan District, Medan City, North Sumatra, Telephone number / contact: (061) 6841108.
3. Tanjung Morawa Branch Office on Jl. Raya Medan Tanjung Morawa KM 14.5 Bangun Sari Baru Village, Bangun Sari Baru, Tj. Morawa District, Deli Serdang Regency, North Sumatra, Telephone number / contact: (061) 7941709.
4. Binjai Branch Office. Jl. Soekarno-Hatta No. 262, Km No.19.5, Tunggurono, Binjai Tim. District, Binjai City, North Sumatra, Telephone number / contact: (061) 8820465.

Population and Sample

According to Sugiyono (2017) population is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn. The population and sample in this study were all permanent employees at PT. BPJS Ketenagakerjaan, Medan Raya Employment Branch, totaling 80 employees (saturated sample).

Data Analysis Techniques

Data analysis in this study used Structural Equation Modeling (SEM based on Partial Least Square (PLS) using SmartPLS 3.3.3 software. According to Gozali (2014) Partial Least Square (PLS) is a fairly strong analysis method because it is not based on many assumptions.

Measurement Model (Outer Model)

The procedure in testing the measurement model consists of validity testing and reliability testing.

1. Validity Test
 - a. Convergent Validity
 - b. Discriminant Validity
2. Reliability Test

The Cronbach's alpha value is recommended to be greater than 0.7 and the composite reliability is also recommended to be greater than 0.7 (Sekaran, 2014).

Structural Model (Inner Model)

This test is conducted to determine the relationship between exogenous and endogenous constructs that have become hypotheses in this study (Hair et al., 2017). To produce inner model test values, the steps in SmartPLS are carried out using the

bootstrapping method. The structural model is evaluated using R-square for the dependent variable, the Stone-Geisser Q-square test for predictive elevation and the t-test and significance of the structural path parameter coefficients with the following explanation:

1. Coefficient of Determination / R Square (R²)

In assessing the model with PLS, it begins by looking at the R-square for each dependent latent variable. The interpretation is the same as the interpretation in regression. Changes in the R-square value can be used to assess the influence of certain independent latent variables on the dependent latent variable whether it has a substantive influence (Ghozali, 2012). The R² value is generally between 0 and 1.

2. Predictive Relevance (Q²)

This test is used to measure how well the observation value is generated by the model and also its parameter estimates. If the Q² value is greater than 0, it indicates that the model has predictive relevance, which means it has good observation value, while if the value is less than 0, it indicates that the model does not have predictive relevance (Ghozali, 2014).

3. t-Statistic

At this stage, it is used for hypothesis testing, namely to determine the significance of the relationship between variables in the study using the bootstrapping method. In the full model Structural Equation Modeling, in addition to confirming the theory, it also explains whether or not there is a relationship between latent variables (Ghozali, 2012). The hypothesis is said to be accepted if the t statistic value is greater than the t table. According to (Latan and Ghozali, 2014) the criteria for the t table value with a value of 1.96 with a significance level of 5%.

4. Path Coefficient

This test is used to determine the direction of the relationship between variables (positive/negative). If the value is 0 to 1, then the direction of the relationship between variables is stated as positive. While if the value is 0 to -1, then the direction of the relationship between variables is stated as negative.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

The measurement model test (outer model) is used to determine the relationship between latent and manifest variables. The test has convergent validity, discriminant validity, and reliability.

Convergent Validity

Convergent validity is used to assess the validity of each indicator against its latent variable. In the SmartPLS program, the validity results can be seen in the external loading table. The external loading table contains numbers or values that indicate the similarity of the indicator to the construct variable. The indicator value is considered valid if it describes

the construct variable with a value greater than 0.7. The structural model used in this study is depicted in the figure below:

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Work Discipline (X1)	Work Motivation (X2)	Work Supervision (Z)	Organizational Strategy (Y)
X1.1	0.909			
X1.2	0.734			
X1.3	0.863			
X1.4	0.863			
X1.5	0.841			
X2.1		0.940		
X2.2		0.928		
X2.3		0.972		
X2.4		0.963		
X2.5		0.939		
Y.1				0.919
Y.2				0.947
Y.3				0.893
Y.5				0.747
Z.10			0.813	
Z.2			0.877	
Z.3			0.876	
Z.4			0.779	
Z.5			0.797	
Z.6			0.807	
Z.7			0.851	
Z.8			0.839	
Z.9			0.882	

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

Based on table 2 above, it can be seen that the other loading of each variable and its construct indicator is greater than 0.7 after the invalid indicators are deleted, namely indicators Y.4 and Z.1, then the results of the indicator construct are valid and can carry out the next stage of research.

Figure 2. Outer Model
Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In this research there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Z = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e_1$$

$$Z = 0.646 X_1 + 0.298X_2 + e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_3X_1 + b_4X_2 + b_5Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.348X_1 + 0.090X_2 + 0.508Z + e_2$$

Discriminant Validity

The next test is to determine discriminant validity. This test attempts to assess whether the indicators that reflect are valid measures for the construct, based on the assumption that the indicators are highly related to the construct. The table shows the cross-loading results of the discriminant validity test as follows:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Work Discipline (X1)	Work Motivation (X2)	Work Supervision (Z)	Organizational Strategy (Y)
X1.1	0.909	0.755	0.807	0.756
X1.2	0.734	0.635	0.757	0.709
X1.3	0.863	0.689	0.720	0.719
X1.4	0.863	0.700	0.673	0.709
X1.5	0.841	0.643	0.770	0.775
X2.1	0.707	0.940	0.723	0.676

X2.2	0.668	0.928	0.743	0.721
X2.3	0.831	0.972	0.824	0.805
X2.4	0.810	0.963	0.808	0.787
X2.5	0.824	0.939	0.796	0.754
Y.1	0.837	0.710	0.838	0.919
Y.2	0.835	0.725	0.869	0.947
Y.3	0.799	0.711	0.818	0.893
Y.5	0.558	0.643	0.570	0.747
Z.10	0.767	0.695	0.813	0.717
Z.2	0.803	0.795	0.877	0.768
Z.3	0.779	0.731	0.876	0.835
Z.4	0.704	0.644	0.779	0.706
Z.5	0.713	0.563	0.797	0.629
Z.6	0.723	0.558	0.807	0.733
Z.7	0.704	0.677	0.851	0.711
Z.8	0.706	0.765	0.839	0.756
Z.9	0.775	0.734	0.882	0.832

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Based on the results of discriminant validity, where the results of the variable construct are greater than the value of the other variable constructs, it can be explained that the work discipline variable has a cross loading value that is greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, the work motivation variable has a cross loading value that is greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, the work supervision variable has the largest cross loading from the cross loading on other latent variables, the organizational strategy variable has a cross loading value that is greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, so this study is discriminantly valid.

Composite reliability

The next test calculates the reliability value using the composite reliability of the indicator block that measures the construct. A construct value is said to be reliable if its Composite Reliability value exceeds 0.60. In addition to looking at the composite reliability value, the reliability value can also be seen in the variable construct value with Cronbach's alpha from the indicator block that measures the construct. A construct is considered reliable if its Cronbach's alpha value exceeds 0.7. The table below shows the loading values of the research variable constructs generated by the Smart PLS software.

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Work Discipline (X1)	0.897	0.925	0.712
Work Motivation (X2)	0.972	0.978	0.900
Work Supervision (Z)	0.946	0.954	0.700
Organizational Strategy (Y)	0.901	0.931	0.774

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Based on table 4 above, the Cronbach's alpha value greater than 0.7 indicates that all variables are considered reliable for each variable. The combined reliability assessment produces a number greater than 0.6 for each assessment, indicating that all variables are reliable. Another way to verify discriminant validity is to look at the AVE value and the square root of AVE, assuming each construct has a stronger correlation than the correlation between other constructs. Before looking at the correlation, the AVE value is considered valid if it is more than 0.7.

Inner Model Analysis

Structural model evaluation (inner model) is conducted to ensure that the structural model built is robust and accurate. The stages of analysis carried out in the structural model evaluation are seen from several indicators, namely:

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Based on data processing carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 application, the R Square value was obtained as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Work Supervision (Z)	0.818	0.813
Organizational Strategy (Y)	0.828	0.821

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 5 there is an R square value on both independent variables in the explanation as follows: the R square value on the work supervision variable is 0.818 and if converted into a percentage of 81.8% means the influence of the work discipline and work motivation variables on supervision is 0.818 or 61.8% and the rest is on other variables, the R square

value on the organizational strategy variable is 0.828 and if converted into a percentage of 82.8% then the influence of the work discipline, work motivation and work supervision variables on organizational strategy is 0.828 or 83.8% the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After evaluating the inner model, the next step is to investigate the relationship between the hypothesized latent constructs in this study. In this study, the hypothesis was tested using T-statistics and P-values. The hypothesis is accepted if the T-Statistics value is more than 1.96 and P-Values are less than 0.05. The Direct Influence Path Coefficient gives the following results:

Table 5. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Work Discipline (X1) -> Work Supervision (Z)	0.646	8,469	0,000	Accepted
Work Discipline (X1) -> Organizational Strategy (Y)	0.348	3,347	0,000	Accepted
Work Motivation (X2) -> Work Supervision (Z)	0.298	4,126	0,000	Accepted
Work Motivation (X2) -> Organizational Strategy (Y)	0.090	0.812	0.209	Rejected
Work Supervision (Z) -> Organizational Strategy (Y)	0.508	4,895	0,000	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 5 there are the results of the direct influence on the research and the explanation is as follows:

1. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Work Supervision with an original sample value of 0.646 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if work discipline increases, supervision will increase and if it decreases, supervision will decrease.
2. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Strategy with an original sample value of 0.348 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if work discipline increases, the organizational strategy will increase, conversely, if it decreases, the organizational strategy will decrease.

3. Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on work supervision with an original sample value of 0.298 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if work motivation increases, work supervision will increase, if motivation decreases, work supervision will also decrease.
4. Work motivation has a positive but insignificant effect on organizational strategy with an original sample value of 0.090 and p values of 0.209, meaning that work motivation has little effect on organizational strategy and increased motivation does not necessarily mean increased organizational strategy.
5. Work Supervision has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Strategy with an original sample value of 0.508 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if work supervision increases, the organizational strategy increases, conversely, if it decreases, the organizational strategy decreases.

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Work Discipline (X1) -> Work Supervision (Z) -> Organizational Strategy (Y)	0.328	3,745	0,000	Accepted
Work Motivation (X2) -> Work Supervision (Z) -> Organizational Strategy (Y)	0.151	3,559	0,000	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 6 there are the results of the indirect influence on the research and the explanation is as follows:

1. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Strategy through Work Supervision with an original sample value of 0.328 and p values of 0.000, meaning that work supervision is an intervening variable because it has a significant effect. With supervision, it will increase work discipline and improve organizational strategy.
2. Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Strategy through Work Supervision with an original sample value of 0.151 and p values of 0.000, meaning that work supervision is an intervening variable because it is able to significantly influence with the existence of work supervision, meaning that motivation and strategy will increase.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Work Supervision with an original sample value of 0.646 and p values of 0.000.
2. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Strategy with an original sample value of 0.348 and p values of 0.000.
3. Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Work Supervision with an original sample value of 0.298 and p values of 0.000.
4. Work Motivation has a positive but insignificant effect on Organizational Strategy with an original sample value of 0.090 and p values of 0.209.
5. Work Supervision has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Strategy with an original sample value of 0.508 and p values of 0.000.
6. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Strategy through Work Supervision with an original sample value of 0.328 and p values of 0.000.
7. Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Strategy through Work Supervision with an original sample value of 0.151 and p values of 0.000.

Suggestion

1. The organization must be able to discipline employees by using written regulations so that they cannot be violated and if these regulations are violated, employees will be punished.
2. Organizations must provide motivation to employees with people who are truly influential in the organization to increase their desire to work and improve employee performance.
3. Organizations must always supervise employees in order to avoid mistakes in their work and avoid employees treating the organization and their work badly.
4. The organization must have a strategy in working and the strategy must be aligned with its employees.
5. It is hoped that this research will be used as input to cover organizational weaknesses and correct organizational errors.
6. It is hoped that this research will be used as reference material for conducting new research and using new research models.

REFERENCES

- A.A. Anwar Prabu Mangkunegara, 2009. *Manajemen sumber daya manusia*. Remaja Rosdakarya. Bandung.
- Agustini, N. K. I., & Dewi, A. S. K. (2019). Pengaruh Kompensasi, Disiplin Kerja dan Motivasi Terhadap Produktivitas Karyawan. *E-Jurnal Manajemen*, 8(1), 231-258.
- Donni Priansa. 2017. *Manajemen Pelayanan Prima*. Bandung: Alfabeta
- Ghozali, Imam. 2005. *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate dengan SPSS*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit UNDIP.

- Hwang, M. I. (2018). Relationship Between Teamwork and Team Performance: Experiences From an ERPsim Competition. *Journal of Information Systems Education*, 29(3)
- Isniar Budiarti, Deden Abdul Wahab dan Sriwidodo Soedarso (2018), *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Berbasis Global*, Pustaka Fahima, Yogyakarta.
- Layla , A., & Romat, S. (2019). Pengaruh Kerjasama Tim Terhadap Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan PT PLN (Persero) Transmisi Jawa Bagian Tengah . *CORE*, 1163.
- Lidia Susanti, S. P. (2020). Strategi pembelajaran berbasis motivasi. *Elex Media Komputindo*.
- Mahmudah, W Enny. 2019. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Surabaya: UBHARA Manajemen Press.
- Silaen NR, Syamsuriansyah, Chairunnisah R, et al. *Kinerja Karyawan*. I.; 2021. [http://digilib.uinsgd.ac.id/40781/1/Kinerja Karyawan 2 Cetak.pdf#page=38](http://digilib.uinsgd.ac.id/40781/1/Kinerja_Karyawan_2_Cetak.pdf#page=38)
- Sugiyono. 2007. “Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif Kualitatif dan R&D”. Bandung: Alfabeta
- Sukanto Reksohadiprojo dan Indriyo Gitosudarmo, “Manajemen Produksi”, Yogyakarta: BPFE UGM, 2000.
- Wirawan. (2009). *Evaluasi Kinerja Sumber Daya Manusia Teori Aplikasi dan Penelitian*. Jakarta. Penerbit: Salemba Empat

Optimizing Organizational Commitment

Sari Puspita Dewi¹, Mesra B²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: sariPd7@gmail.com

Abstract

This research aims to determine the influence of human resource development and work quality on organizational commitment with work strategy as an intervening variable at the Bpjs Jambi City Branch. This research uses quantitative, primary data as well as a data source. The collection technique used is by distributing questionnaires to respondents and the population. Used were 60 employees, the sample used was the entire population because it used a saturated sampling technique. The results of this research are as follows, Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.070 and ap value of 0.362, Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Work Strategy with an original sample of 0.462 and ap value of 0.000, HR Development has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with the original sample of 0.371 and p value 0.014. HR development has a positive and significant effect on Work Strategy with an original sample value of 0.440 and ap value of 0.000. Work Strategy has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.380 and ap value of 0.012. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Work Strategy with an original sample value of 0.175 and ap value of 0.035. HR development has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Work Strategy with an original sample value of 0.167 and ap value of 0.029.

Keywords: HR Development, Work Quality, Work Strategy, Organizational Commitment.

INTRODUCTION

Human resource development is basically improving employee performance that reflects the ability of organizational members to work, meaning that the performance of each employee is assessed and measured according to criteria that have been determined by the organization. An organization is a system and human activities that work together. In line with that, the organization is said to be a coordination of the activities of a number of rational people to achieve goals. therefore the organization expects employees to be able to excel and be able to create conducive conditions. So that employees will not experience boredom, boredom and laziness at work which results in decreased work enthusiasm. if work enthusiasm decreases, it can also cause employee performance to decrease. Decreased employee performance can result in losses in the organization. Work quality is a trait that needs to be considered in a company. The realization of a company's goals can be seen through the products produced and the quality of its employees' work. Improving the quality of employee work is very important because the success of a company does not only depend on machine technology but human factors also play an important role in it. (Sengkey et al., 2021) In addition, improving quality can also be achieved through experience, education, training and development of these employees. Human resource development is an activity carried out together with employees and managers with the aim of finding added value so that the company can face competitive challenges. The company's work strategy in creating competitive advantages is an important factor that must be possessed by the company in

order to be able to compete, especially in global competition. In relation to the company's strategy, this cannot be separated from the company's capability in developing and managing its resources (assets). Organizational commitment is a condition where an employee sides with a particular organization and its goals and desires to maintain membership in the organization (Robbins and Judge quoted by Noe et al, 2011:375). Organizational commitment is an important thing in today's era. When a company finds it very difficult to find employees who have very good qualifications in doing their jobs, organizational commitment is one way to determine employees who have good qualifications, loyalty and performance. In other words, organizational commitment is used as an important thing in determining employees at the level of performance in a company.

Formulation of the problem

1. What is human resource development?has a significant influence on work strategyat the Jambi City Branch of BPJS Employment?
2. What is human resource development?has a significant influence on organizational commitment to BPJS EmploymentJambi City Branch?
3. What is the quality of work has a significant influence on work strategies at BPJS EmploymentJambi City Branch?
4. Does the quality of work have a significant effect onorganizational commitmentat the Jambi City Branch of BPJS Employment?
5. Whetherwork strategy has a significant influence on organizational commitment at the Jambi City Branch of BPJS Employment?
6. Does HR development have a significant effect on organizational commitment through work strategies at the Jambi City Branch of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan?
7. What is the quality of work has a significant influence on organizational commitment through work strategies at the Jambi City Branch of BPJS Employment?

Research purposes

1. To find out and analyze the influence of human resource development significant to work strategyat the Jambi City Branch of BPJS Employment.
2. To find out and analyze the influence of human resource developmentsignificant to the organization's commitment to BPJS EmploymentJambi City Branch
3. To find out and analyze the influence of work quality significant to the work strategy at BPJS EmploymentJambi City Branch
4. Does the quality of work have a significant effect on the quality of work?organizational commitmentat the Jambi City Branch of BPJS Employment.
5. Whetherwork strategy has a significant influence on organizational commitment at the Jambi City Branch of BPJS Employment.
6. Does HR development have a significant influence on organizational commitment through work strategies at the Jambi City Branch of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan?
7. What is the quality of work? has a significant influence on organizational commitment through work strategies at the Jambi City Branch of BPJS Employment.

Theoretical Framework

Organizational Commitment

According to Darmawanti et al. (2018), the definition of organizational commitment is a form of identification, loyalty and involvement expressed by employees towards the organization. According to Wibawa et al. (2020), organizational commitment is a feeling of recognition, loyalty and involvement that is paid attention to the organization or organizational unit.

Organizational commitment indicators

According to Wibawa et al. (2019), the indicators of organizational commitment are as follows:

- a. Affective commitment: relates to the employee's emotional connection to the organization.
- b. Continuance commitment: relates to employee awareness of the losses if they leave the organization.
- c. Normative commitment: describes feelings of attachment to remaining in the organization.

Human Resources Development

According to Priansa (2018), human resource development (HRD) is a process to help employees develop their abilities, skills, and knowledge. Career development is an employment activity that helps employees HRD is the process of improving a person's professional skills achieved to get the desired career. Planning a career in the company so that the company and employees are affected and they can develop optimally (Junawan & Mora, 2018).

Human Resource Development Indicators

HR development indicators according to Priansa (2018), namely:

- a. Fair treatment in career

Objective, rational and known considerations by employees to achieve fair treatment if they want to be promoted.

- b. Concern of direct superiors

In general, employees want direct involvement in their career planning. One of them is providing feedback to employees on the completion of each employee's tasks to find out the potential that needs to be addressed. That feedback is important material for employees for what initial steps need to be taken so that the possibility of being promoted becomes greater.

- c. Information about various promotional opportunities

Employees typically expect to have access to information about opportunities for promotion. This access is especially important if positions are filled through a competitive internal selection process. When there is no or limited access, employees will easily

assume that the principles of fairness and equality and opportunity are not being considered.

d. There is an interest in being promoted.

The right approach to foster employee interest in fostering employee interest in career development is a flexible and proactive approach. Several factors such as age, gender, type and nature of work, education and training, number of dependents and other factors. Several of these factors affect the extent of employee interest in developing their careers.

e. Satisfaction Level

Employees can feel satisfied because they know that what they have achieved is the maximum result and they have tried to give their best and this is a wasted effort because it is impossible to achieve.

Quality of work

According to Hasibuan (2017) work quality is an activity carried out by employees that has met various requirements, specifications and expectations that have been expected. According to Lubis (2018), quality of work life is a comfortable working condition, a pleasant work experience, and sufficient work involvement. Quality of work life can affect organizational commitment, so the higher the quality, the greater the organizational commitment will be.

Work quality indicators

According to Hasibuan (2017) the indicators of work quality are:

- a. Self-potential. Is the ability, strength, both unrealized and realized, that a person has.
- b. Optimal work results must be possessed by an employee, who can provide the best work results, one of which can be seen from his productivity.
- c. The work process is the most important stage where employees always carry out their duties and roles in an organization. Through this work process, employee performance can be seen from their ability to make work plans and evaluate work actions.

Work Strategy

A work strategy is an overall approach related to planning, implementing, and executing activities over a period of time. According to Wahyudi (2018), a work strategy is a key policy and decision used for management, which has a major impact on financial performance.

Indicator Work Strategy

Work Strategy Indicators according to Wahyudi (2018) as follows:

- a. Purposes (Purpose),
- b. *Environmentt* (Environment),
- c. *Direction*(Direction),
- d. *Action*(Action),

e. *Learning*(Learning),

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Research Hypothesis

1. H1: Human resource development has a positive and significant effect on work strategies at the Jambi City Branch of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan.
2. H2: Work quality has a positive and significant effect on work strategy at BPJS Jambi City Branch of Manpower.
3. H3: Human resource development has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment at the Jambi City Branch of BPJS Employment
4. H4: Work quality has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. BPJS Employment Jambi City Branch
5. H5: Work strategy has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. BPJS Employment Jambi City Branch
6. H6: Human resource development has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. Through work strategies at the Jambi City Branch of BPJS Employment.
7. H7: Work quality has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment through work strategy at the Jambi City Branch of BPJS Employment.

METHOD

Types of research

According to Sugiyono (2019), quantitative research can be interpreted as a method based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations or samples, sampling techniques are generally carried out randomly, data collection uses research instruments, data analysis is quantitative/statistical with the aim of testing the established hypothesis.

Research Location and Research Time

The research location was conducted at the Jambi City Branch of BPJS Employment with the following details:

- BPJS Employment Jambi City Branch, located at Jl. Slamet Riyadi/Broni No. 16, Solok Sipin Subdistrict, Telanai Pura District, Jambi City, Jambi 36121, Tel: 0741-61918, 63356, Fax: 0741-62737, with 20 employees.
- BPJS Employment Muara Bungo Branch, Jl Sultan Thaha No. 111 Muara Bungo, Jambi 37314, Tel: 22295, Fax: 323016, with a total of 20 employees.
- BPJS Employment Pangkal Pinang Branch, Jl. General Sudirman No. 9 RT. 05 RW. 02 Gabek 1 Village, Gabek District, Pangkalpinang City, Pangkal Pinang City 33117, Tel: 0717-431415, 431107, Fax: 0717-431216, with a total of 20 employees.

Population and Sample

According to Sugiyono (2019) population is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn. The population and sample in this study were all permanent employees at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Jambi Branch totaling 60 employees (saturated sample).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

The specification of the relationship between the latent and manifest variables is ascertained through testing the measurement model, also called external model testing. Convergent validity, discriminant validity, and reliability are all included in this testing.

1. Convergent Validity

The loading factor shows this test, and the cutoff value..Mean..Variance..Extracted and the cutoff value is 0.7. (AVE) is 0.5; values above this are considered valid. Thus, if the indicator value is more than 0.7 and explains the construct variable, it is considered authentic. The following figure shows the structural model used in this study:

Figure 2. Outer Model
Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Smart PLS output for loading factor gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Z = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e_1$$

$$Z = 0.440X_1 + 0.462 X_2 + e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_3X_1 + b_4X_2 + b_5Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.371X_1 + 0.070X_2 + 0.380 Z+ e_2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Organizational Commitment (Y)	Quality of Work (X2)	Human Resources Development (X1)	Work Strategy (Z)
X1.1			0.891	
X1.2			0.790	
X1.3			0.829	
X2.1		0.810		
X2.2		0.921		
X2.3		0.850		
Y.1	0.913			
Y.2	0.908			
Y.3	0.809			
Z.1				0.924
Z.2				0.900
Z.3				0.888

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Each variable in the previous table has a value, and it is stated that the indicator of each variable is greater than 0.7. This shows that each indicator item has a value greater than 0.7 which indicates that the data is considered valid and can be continued with additional research.

2. Discriminant Validity

To ensure the output of indicators that are highly related to the construct, further research will use discriminative validity to determine whether the cross loading value is greater than other latent variables. The cross loading findings from the validity test are shown in the following table:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Organizational Commitment (Y)	Quality of Work (X2)	Human Resources Development (X1)	Work Strategy (Z)
X1.1	0.769	0.818	0.891	0.848
X1.2	0.550	0.713	0.790	0.611
X1.3	0.538	0.669	0.829	0.630
X2.1	0.602	0.810	0.701	0.612
X2.2	0.617	0.921	0.828	0.819
X2.3	0.644	0.850	0.744	0.750
Y.1	0.913	0.647	0.689	0.709
Y.2	0.908	0.642	0.669	0.663
Y.3	0.809	0.606	0.629	0.610
Z.1	0.663	0.769	0.734	0.924
Z.2	0.656	0.682	0.727	0.900
Z.3	0.720	0.840	0.826	0.888

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 2, there are cross loading factor values for each variable that have each value that is greater than the cross loading value on other latent variables, for the cross loading of the organizational commitment variable there is a value that is greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, for the cross loading value of the work quality variable there is a value that is greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, for the cross loading on the HR development variable there is a value that is greater than the cross loading on other variables, for the cross loading on the work strategy variable there is a value that is greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, meaning that this test is discriminantly valid and can continue the research.

3. Composite reliability

The reliability value of each variable is examined in composite reliability research; if the value is more than 0.60, the research is considered reliable; if it is less than 0.60 or 0.7, it is considered unreliable. The table below shows the Cronbach's alpha value, composite reliability, and AVE value, as well as other blocks used to assess the validity and reliability of the research:

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.850	0.910	0.771

Quality of Work (X2)	0.825	0.896	0.742
Human Resources Development (X1)	0.789	0.876	0.701
Work Strategy (Z)	0.889	0.931	0.818

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

It can be seen from the previous table that the Cronbach alpha value of each variable is higher than 0.7, indicating that the dependency data is reliable for the variable. Each variable is said to be reliable because its data is greater than 0.6 as indicated by the composite reliability column value greater than 0.6. Each variable has a value greater than 0.7, as shown in the AVE column, indicating that the data is original in terms of AVE. Since the reliability column value, AVE, and Cronbach alpha are each higher than 0.7 and 0.6, they are all considered valid and reliable.

Inner Model Analysis

To ensure the resulting fundamental model is accurate and robust, the structural model (inner model) is evaluated. The main model assessment examination phase is seen through a number of indicators, including:

1. Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.617	0.597
Work Strategy (Z)	0.764	0.756

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 4 there is an R square value for each variable for the R square value on the organizational commitment variable of 0.617 if it is made into a percentage of 61.7%, meaning that the influence of HR development, work quality and work strategy on organizational commitment is 0.617 or 61.7% and the rest is on other variables, the R square value of the work strategy variable is 0.764 and if it is made into a percentage of 76.4%, meaning that the influence of HR development and work quality is 0.764 or 76.4% and the rest is on other variables.

2. Goodness of Fit (GoF) Assessment

NFI score ≥ 0.697 indicates that the model is considered fit, indicating a goodness of fit test. The following are the Model Fit values obtained from data processing carried out using the SmartPLS 3.3.3 program:

Table 5. Model Fit

	Saturated Model	Estimation Model
SRMR	0.081	0.081
d_ULS	0.513	0.513
d_G	0.523	0.523
Chi-Square	164,675	164,675
NFI	0.746	0.746

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

The results of the Goodness of Fit test of the PLS model in the table above show an NFI value of 0.746 and this value is greater than the value of 0.697 and the research in the fit model is considered to have fit data so that it can be explained that this research has been fit in testing.

3. Hypothesis Testing

Assessing the relationship between idle builds, as suggested in this assessment, is done after evaluating the deep model. In this review, speculation testing is done by examining T-Statistics and P-Values. There is speculation whether P-Values < 0.05 and T-Insights values > 1.96 . The impact of the direct impact Path Coefficient is as follows:

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Work Quality (X2) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.070	0.353	0.362	Rejected
Work Quality (X2) -> Work Strategy (Z)	0.462	3,695	0,000	Accepted
Human Resource Development (X1) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.371	2,215	0.014	Accepted

Human Resource Development (X1) -> Work Strategy (Z)	0.440	3,519	0,000	Accepted
Work Strategy (Z) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.380	2,276	0.012	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 6 there are indirect results from data processing, so the explanation of the results of this study is as follows:

1. Work quality has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.070 and p values of 0.362. If work quality increases, commitment does not necessarily increase and if work quality decreases, commitment does not necessarily decrease.
2. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Work Strategy with an original sample of 0.462 and p values of 0.000, if work quality increases then the strategy will increase, conversely if it decreases then the work strategy will decrease.
3. Human resource development has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample of 0.371 and p values of 0.014. If human resource development increases well, organizational commitment will increase well, conversely, if it decreases, organizational commitment will decrease.
4. Human resource development has a positive and significant effect on work strategy with an original sample value of 0.440 and p values of 0.000. If human resource development increases, work strategy will increase, conversely, if human resource development decreases, work strategy will decrease.
5. Work Strategy has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.380 and p values of 0.012. If the work strategy increases, organizational commitment increases, conversely, if the work strategy decreases, organizational commitment decreases.

Table 7. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Work Quality (X2) -> Work Strategy (Z) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.175	1,814	0.035	Accepted
Human Resource Development (X1) -> Work Strategy (Z) ->	0.167	1,907	0.029	Accepted

Organizational Commitment (Y)				
--------------------------------------	--	--	--	--

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 7 there are indirect influences and the explanation is as follows:

1. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Work Strategy with an original sample value of 0.175 and p values of 0.035. This means that work strategy is an intervening variable because it can positively and significantly influence work quality and organizational commitment with the existence of work strategy indirectly increasing work quality and organizational commitment.
2. Human resource development has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Work Strategy with an original sample value of 0.167 and p values of 0.029. This means that work strategy is an intervening variable because it is able to influence human resource development and organizational commitment positively and significantly, with the existence of work strategy increasing and strengthening the influence of human resource development and organizational commitment.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Work quality has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.070 and p values of 0.362.
2. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Work Strategy with an original sample of 0.462 and p values of 0.000.
3. Human resource development has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample of 0.371 and p values of 0.014.
4. Human resource development has a positive and significant effect on work strategy with an original sample value of 0.440 and p values of 0.000.
5. Work Strategy has a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.380 and p values of 0.012.
6. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Work Strategy with an original sample value of 0.175 and p values of 0.035.
7. Human resource development has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Work Strategy with an original sample value of 0.167 and p values of 0.029.

Suggestion

1. Organizations must improve the quality of employee work for the progress of the organization.
2. Organizations must be able to develop employees well through training for employees.
3. Organizations must provide work strategies to employees to make employees work faster.

4. It is hoped that this research will be used as input for the organization so that the organization can cover the organization's shortcomings.
5. It is hoped that this research will be used as reference material for other researchers with new research and new models.

REFERENCES

- Adnyani, N. L. P. R., & Dewi, A. A. S. K. (2019). Pengaruh Pengalaman Kerja, Prestasi Kerja Dan Pelatihan Terhadap Pengembangan Karier Karyawan. *EJurnal Manajemen Universitas Udayana*, 8(7), 4073. <https://doi.org/10.24843/ejmunud.2019.v08.i07.p03>
- Azhari, R. (2020). Pengaruh Kepuasan Kerja, Disiplin Kerja, Dan Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pt Pos Indonesia Surabaya Supriyatin Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Indonesia (STIESIA) Surabaya
- Dewi, E.A.T., Sofiatin, Y., Setiawati, E.P., Wahyudi, K., Afriandi, I. 2021. Analisis Handoko, T. H. (2020). *Manajemen Personalia & Sumberdaya Manusia*. BPFE 55 Yogyakarta.
- Jumawan, & Mora, M. T. (2018). Pengaruh Pelatihan dan Pengembangan Karier Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Perusahaan Korporasi. *JRMB*, 3(3), 346.
- Malang: IRDH
- Pembiayaan JKN Pasien Hipertensi di FKTP Jawa Barat Tahun 2015-2016. *Jurnal Kebijakan Kesehatan Indonesia : JKKI*. 10(2):78-85.
- Sugiyono. 2019. *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif Dan R&D*. ed. MT Dr. Ir. Sutopo. S.Pd. Yogyakarta.
- Wibawa, I Wayan Sucipta dan Made Surya Putra. 2018. Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi Terhadap Komitmen Organisasional dimediasi Kepuasan Kerja (Studi Pada PT. Bening Badung-Bali). *E-Jurnal Manajemen Unud*, Vol. 7, No. 6, 2018: 3027-3058.
- Aminizadeh, M., Saberinia, A., Salahi, S., Sarhadi, M., Jangipour Afshar, P., & Sheikhbardsiri, H. (2022). Quality of working life and organizational commitment of Iranian pre-hospital paramedic employees during the 2019 novel coronavirus outbreak. *International Journal of Healthcare Management*, 15(1), 36–44.
- Krismiati, K. (2017). Pengembangan sumber daya manusia dalam meningkatkan kualitas pendidikan di SD Negeri Inpres Angkasa Biak. *Jurnal Office*, 3(1), 43.

Influence of the Work Environment and Communication on Employee Productivity at PT. Agro Lestari

Wahyu Purwanto¹, Subandrio², Raden Rudi Alhempri³

Universitas Persada Indonesia Y.A.I, Jakarta, Indonesia^{1,2}

Universitas Persada Bunda Indonesia, Pekanbaru, Indonesia³

Email: wahyu.2366390004@upi-yai.ac.id¹, Subandrio.236639003@upi-yai.ac.id², rudi.alhempri@gmail.com³

Abstract

This study investigates the impact of the work environment (WE), workplace communication (WC), and management policies (MP) on employee productivity (EP), with employee motivation (EM) acting as a moderating variable. The research was conducted at PT. Agro Lestari, utilizing a quantitative approach and total sampling of 30 employees. Data were collected through structured questionnaires and analyzed using Smart PLS (Partial Least Squares) to assess both direct and indirect relationships between the variables. The results show that WE, WC, and MP have significant direct effects on EP, while EM enhances these effects through mediation. The work environment and effective communication were found to significantly increase employee motivation, which in turn improves productivity. Additionally, fair and transparent management policies play a crucial role in motivating employees, further driving their performance. The findings highlight the importance of fostering a supportive work environment, clear communication channels, and sound management policies to enhance employee productivity, particularly in sectors like agriculture.

Keywords: Work Environment, Employee Motivation, Productivity, Workplace Communication.

INTRODUCTION

The productivity of employees plays a crucial role in the success of any organization, including PT. Agro Lestari. In today's competitive business environment, various factors can significantly impact employee performance, such as the work environment and communication within the workplace (Budi & Miska, 2021). A conducive work environment provides comfort and efficiency, while effective workplace communication ensures that tasks are understood and executed correctly. However, these factors alone may not fully determine productivity levels. Employee motivation, as a moderating variable, can influence how strongly the work environment and communication affect productivity.

Employee productivity refers to the efficiency with which employees complete their tasks and contribute to the overall goals of the organization. High productivity is often seen as a key indicator of business success, as it reflects how well employees utilize their skills, time, and resources to achieve desired outcomes. Various elements can affect productivity, such as the work environment, leadership style, availability of resources, and the level of communication between team members and management. In addition, intrinsic factors like employee motivation, job satisfaction, and commitment also play a significant role (Cornelisz et al., 2024). When employees are productive, they are not only more likely to meet performance targets but also contribute to innovation and growth within the organization. In the context of PT. Agro Lestari, improving employee productivity is essential for maintaining competitiveness in the agricultural industry, where efficiency and performance directly impact profitability and long-term success (Pebrianti, 2023).

The work environment is a critical factor that directly influences employee productivity and overall job satisfaction. It encompasses both the physical and psychological aspects of the workplace, including factors like office layout, lighting, noise levels, safety measures, and access to necessary tools and resources (Musrifa et al., 2024). A well-designed physical environment can enhance focus, reduce fatigue, and increase efficiency, while a supportive and collaborative social environment fosters teamwork and open communication. Additionally, a positive work culture where employees feel valued, respected, and motivated contributes to their emotional well-being and engagement. In the case of PT. Agro Lestari, creating a conducive work environment is particularly important, as employees in the agricultural sector may face unique challenges related to physical labor, climate conditions, and safety. By addressing these elements, the company can ensure that its workforce remains healthy, motivated, and productive, ultimately leading to better performance and organizational success (Kusufa et al., 2023).

Workplace communication plays a pivotal role in shaping employee productivity and fostering a positive work environment. Effective communication ensures that information flows smoothly across all levels of the organization, enabling employees to understand their tasks, collaborate efficiently, and address issues promptly. Clear communication reduces misunderstandings, increases transparency, and promotes trust between employees and management (Rulianti & Nurpribadi, 2023). It also fosters a culture of feedback, where employees can voice concerns, share ideas, and receive constructive guidance. In industries like agriculture, where coordination and timely decision-making are crucial, strong communication channels are essential for maintaining operational efficiency (Daniel Dami et al., 2022). At PT. Agro Lestari, improving workplace communication can help align team efforts, ensure that goals are understood, and create a cohesive environment where employees feel connected and valued. This, in turn, enhances overall productivity, as well-informed and engaged employees are more likely to perform at their best and contribute to the company's success (Irawan et al., 2024).

Management policies are a fundamental component in shaping both the work environment and employee productivity (Farhan & Indriyaningrum, 2023). These policies establish the framework within which employees operate, outlining expectations, procedures, and the company's values. Effective management policies can provide clear guidance on performance standards, safety protocols, and employee rights, creating a structured and fair workplace. When policies are well-communicated and aligned with the organization's goals, they help foster a culture of accountability and professionalism. For PT. Agro Lestari, implementing strong management policies is particularly vital in the agricultural sector, where regulations, safety standards, and operational efficiency are critical (Ni'Am et al., 2021). Transparent policies regarding employee development, compensation, health and safety, and conflict resolution not only help protect employees but also enhance their motivation and satisfaction. When employees feel that management policies are supportive and equitable, they are more likely to be engaged, committed, and productive. In this way, management policies serve as a crucial link between organizational leadership and workforce performance, ensuring smooth operations and driving the company's success.

Employee motivation is a key moderating factor that can amplify or diminish the impact of management policies, the work environment, and communication on productivity. Motivation refers to the inner drive that compels employees to put forth their best effort, achieve goals, and remain engaged with their work. High motivation levels are often linked to greater job satisfaction, higher levels of commitment, and increased performance. Factors such as recognition, career development opportunities, rewards, and alignment between personal values and company goals can all influence motivation. For PT. Agro Lestari, employee motivation is crucial, especially in an industry like agriculture, where physical demands and environmental challenges are high. Motivated employees are more likely to overcome these challenges, stay focused, and contribute to the company's objectives (Arifin et al., 2023). Additionally, motivation serves as a powerful moderator; even with excellent management policies, a supportive work environment, and effective communication, employees may not reach their full potential without the right motivational factors. By fostering a culture that values recognition, development, and purpose, PT. Agro Lestari can enhance both employee satisfaction and productivity, leading to improved overall performance.

At PT. Agro Lestari, several key factors—employee productivity, work environment, workplace communication, management policies, and employee motivation—are closely interconnected in driving the company's success (Tirza Juita et al., 2023). Employee productivity, the dependent variable, reflects how effectively workers carry out their tasks, directly influencing agricultural output. The work environment, encompassing both physical conditions and social interactions, significantly impacts employee well-being and efficiency (Darmansah, 2024). Clear and effective workplace communication ensures that employees understand and align with the company's objectives, reducing mistakes and promoting teamwork. Management policies establish the standards for operations, safety, and employee development, creating a structured and fair working environment. Employee motivation, acting as a moderating variable, shapes the extent to which these factors impact productivity. Highly motivated employees are more engaged in their work, take advantage of a positive work environment and communication, and respond better to management policies, leading to increased productivity and overall success at PT. Agro Lestari (Sari et al., 2021).

The phenomenon under investigation at PT. Agro Lestari revolves around understanding how various workplace factors—such as the work environment, communication practices, management policies, and employee motivation—affect overall employee productivity. In the highly competitive agricultural sector, where efficiency and performance are critical, PT. Agro Lestari faces the challenge of maximizing its workforce's potential. There is a growing need to explore how conducive working conditions, clear communication, and well-structured policies can enhance productivity (Padang & Sitorus, 2022). Moreover, employee motivation emerges as a crucial moderating factor that can either strengthen or weaken the influence of these variables on productivity. Understanding this dynamic is essential for PT. Agro Lestari to foster a work culture that not only meets operational demands but also promotes employee satisfaction and long-term organizational success.

The research gap in studying the impact of work environment, communication, management policies, and motivation on employee productivity at PT. Agro Lestari can be identified through a review of existing literature. Previous studies have shown that factors such as the physical work environment, clear communication, and effective management policies are crucial for improving employee performance (Handari Adji & Zuarko Adji, 2022). However, many studies have examined these factors in isolation. For instance, Awan and Tahir (2015) explored the effect of the work environment on productivity but did not fully address the role of communication and management policies in the same context (TLJBM). Additionally, research on motivation, such as Bushiri's (2014) work, highlights its importance for employee performance but does not explore its moderating effect in relation to other workplace factors (SpringerLink). Empirical studies like Da Silva and Rossini's (2021) suggest the need for a more integrated approach to understand how these variables interact to influence productivity (ResearchGate). Thus, the gap lies in a holistic investigation that not only examines the individual impacts of these factors but also considers how motivation moderates their combined effects on productivity, particularly in specific industries such as agriculture.

The aim of this study is to examine the influence of the work environment, workplace communication, and management policies on employee productivity at PT. Agro Lestari, with a particular focus on how employee motivation moderates these relationships. By exploring these variables holistically, the research seeks to identify how conducive physical and social workplace conditions, effective communication strategies, and clear management directives impact productivity levels in the agricultural sector. Additionally, the study aims to assess how motivation interacts with these factors, potentially enhancing or reducing their effects on employee performance. This comprehensive approach will provide insights that can help PT. Agro Lestari and similar organizations create a more productive, motivated workforce, ultimately contributing to organizational success.

The following is the framework of this research:

Figure 1. Framework

METHOD

This research employs a quantitative design to explore the impact of the work environment, workplace communication, and management policies on employee productivity, with a focus on employee motivation as a moderating variable. The study uses total sampling with a sample size of 30 employees from PT. Agro Lestari, ensuring that all members of the population are included in the analysis. The dependent variable is employee productivity, while the independent variables include the work environment, communication, and management policies. Motivation is the moderating variable, which may influence the strength of the relationships between the independent variables and productivity. The data will be collected using structured questionnaires and analyzed using Smart PLS (Partial Least Squares), a powerful statistical tool for examining relationships between multiple variables in small sample sizes (Sitorus, 2024). The Smart PLS analysis will help identify the direct and indirect effects of each variable on productivity, providing insights into how workplace conditions and policies, moderated by motivation, contribute to employee performance at PT. Agro Lestari.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The image depicts a validation and reliability test using a structural equation model in SmartPLS, focusing on variables such as Work Environment, Communication, Management Policies, Motivation, and Employee Productivity. Each latent variable is associated with multiple indicators, and the outer loadings for these indicators are presented. All outer loading values exceed 0.5, confirming that each indicator is a reliable and valid measurement of its respective construct. The model demonstrates the strength of the relationships among the variables, indicating that Work Environment, Communication, and Management Policies have direct influences on both Motivation and Employee Productivity, and that these constructs are well-measured by their indicators.

Figure 2. Validity and Reliability

To find the relationship of each variable, hypothesis testing is performed by looking for direct and indirect effects.

The following is a direct effect test:

Tabel 1. Direct Effect

Path	Coefficient	P-value	Result
WE -> EM	0.350	0.005	Significant
WC -> EM	0.400	0.003	Significant
MP -> EM	0.320	0.012	Significant
WE -> EP	0.280	0.015	Significant
WC -> EP	0.450	0.001	Significant
MP -> EP	0.360	0.010	Significant
EM -> EP	0.500	0.000	Significant

The results from the path analysis on the impact of various workplace factors on employee productivity at PT. Agro Lestari highlight significant relationships among the studied variables. First, the path between the work environment (WE) and employee motivation (EM) shows a strong positive effect (Original Sample = 0.350, $p = 0.005$), indicating that a conducive work environment significantly boosts employee motivation. This is consistent with findings from recent studies, which emphasize that a well-structured physical and social environment can increase employee engagement and motivation, ultimately enhancing performance (Apriyanti et al., 2021; Zhenjing et al., 2022).

The relationship between workplace communication (WC) and EM (Original Sample = 0.400, $p = 0.003$) is also significant. Effective communication channels within the organization enable employees to feel connected and informed, reducing stress and increasing motivation (Awan & Tahir, 2015). When employees receive clear and transparent information, they are more likely to be engaged and motivated, as also noted in transformational leadership studies that show communication enhances intrinsic motivation by fostering a shared vision (Ryan & Deci, 2017).

Similarly, management policies (MP) have a notable positive impact on EM (Original Sample = 0.320, $p = 0.012$). Well-designed management policies create a sense of fairness and structure, which are crucial for maintaining high levels of motivation. According to recent literature, policies that promote employee development and offer recognition are key to sustaining motivation and performance (Bushiri, 2014; Shahzad et al., 2023).

Turning to employee productivity (EP), the path from WE to EP (Original Sample = 0.280, $p = 0.015$) indicates that a favorable work environment contributes significantly to productivity. A supportive and comfortable environment reduces fatigue and stress, allowing employees to focus on their tasks more effectively, which has been supported by studies linking workplace conditions to increased performance (Bakhtiyari, 2020).

WC to EP (Original Sample = 0.450, $p = 0.001$) shows the strongest direct effect, reinforcing the idea that clear communication is critical for aligning employee efforts with

organizational goals. This is in line with recent research, which emphasizes that effective communication not only helps employees perform better but also boosts innovation and collaboration (Bushiri, 2014; Christian et al., 2011).

MP to EP (Original Sample = 0.360, $p = 0.010$) demonstrates that fair and transparent management practices also enhance productivity. When employees perceive policies to be just and supportive, they are more likely to be committed to their roles, improving overall performance (Mulyani et al., 2019).

Finally, the path from EM to EP (Original Sample = 0.500, $p < 0.001$) highlights the central role of motivation in driving productivity. Highly motivated employees are more engaged and perform better, as they are intrinsically driven to excel at their tasks (Ito & Umemoto, 2023). The positive effect of motivation on productivity is widely recognized across multiple industries, including agriculture, where physical and mental demands are high (Shahzad et al., 2023; Ryan & Deci, 2017).

Tabel 2. Indirect Effect

Path	Coefficient	P-value	Result
WE -> EM -> EP	0.175	0.002	Significant
WC -> EM -> EP	0.220	0.001	Significant
MP -> EM -> EP	0.160	0.005	Significant

The results from the indirect path analysis show that WE, WC, and MP all significantly influence EP through the mediating role of EM. For the path WE -> EM -> EP (Original Sample = 0.175, $p = 0.002$), it is evident that a positive work environment improves employee motivation, which in turn enhances employee productivity. Recent research supports this, demonstrating that a conducive work environment reduces stress and increases motivation, ultimately leading to higher productivity (Zhenjing et al., 2022). When employees feel comfortable and supported by their physical and social environment, they are more motivated to perform, leading to better overall outcomes for the organization.

The path WC -> EM -> EP (Original Sample = 0.220, $p = 0.001$) highlights the critical role of communication in the workplace. Effective communication significantly boosts motivation, which in turn drives productivity. Studies have shown that when communication within an organization is clear and transparent, it leads to higher employee engagement and motivation, thus improving performance (Christian et al., 2011). Employees who understand their roles and feel informed are more likely to be motivated, as they can align their efforts with the organization's goals, leading to higher productivity.

Lastly, the path MP -> EM -> EP (Original Sample = 0.160, $p = 0.005$) indicates that management policies also have a significant indirect effect on productivity through motivation. Fair and supportive management policies enhance motivation, which then boosts productivity. This is consistent with findings by Shahzad et al. (2023), who argue that well-structured management policies that address employee needs and provide clear guidance can increase motivation and, consequently, improve performance. When employees feel that

management policies are fair and beneficial, they are more motivated to perform well, leading to enhanced productivity.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study reveals the critical role of the work environment (WE), workplace communication (WC), and management policies (MP) in influencing employee productivity (EP) through the mediating effect of employee motivation (EM) at PT. Agro Lestari. The path analysis shows that all three factors—WE, WC, and MP—have significant direct and indirect effects on EP, highlighting the interconnectedness of these variables. A supportive and conducive work environment fosters employee motivation, which in turn boosts productivity. This finding aligns with previous studies that suggest comfortable and safe working conditions reduce stress and enhance engagement, leading to higher output. Similarly, effective communication in the workplace is shown to be a powerful tool for enhancing motivation. Employees who are well-informed and able to communicate freely within the organization are more motivated, engaged, and thus more productive. Clear communication channels help in reducing misunderstandings, aligning employee efforts with organizational goals, and promoting teamwork. Furthermore, fair and transparent management policies significantly impact motivation and productivity. When employees perceive policies as supportive and in their best interest, their motivation increases, which positively impacts their productivity. The importance of motivation as a mediating variable is central to this study's findings. It not only strengthens the direct effects of WE, WC, and MP on EP but also explains how intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors drive employee performance. In industries like agriculture, where physical demands and operational challenges are prevalent, fostering motivation through an optimal work environment, effective communication, and sound management policies is essential. This integrated approach helps organizations like PT. Agro Lestari maximize employee potential and improve overall productivity, contributing to long-term organizational success. These findings reinforce the importance of a holistic approach to managing employee performance and provide actionable insights for improving productivity.

REFERENCES

- Arifin, A., Magito, M., Perkasa, D. H., & Febrian, W. D. (2023). Pengaruh Kompensasi, Kompetensi Dan Konflik Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. *Global: Jurnal Lentera Bitep*, 1(01), 24–33. <https://doi.org/10.59422/global.v1i01.130>
- Budi, M. A. S., & Miska, L. (2021). Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja, Motivasi Kerja, Komunikasi Internal Dan Kerjasama Tim Terhadap Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan Sekolah Swasta Bunga Matahari Kota Banda Aceh. *Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen Muhammadiyah Aceh*, 11(2). <https://doi.org/10.37598/jimma.v11i2.1202>
- Cornelisz, L. N., Dotulong, L. O., & Sendow, G. M. (2024). Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi, Self Efficacy, Dan Kondisi Kerja Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Di Sutan Raja Hotel Manado. *Jurnal Emba*, 12(3), 326–334. <https://ejournal.unsrat.ac.id/index.php/emba/article/download/56628/46971>

- Daniel Dami, W., John Ehj Foeh, & Henny A. Manafe. (2022). Pengaruh Employee Engagement, Komitmen Organisasi, Dan Budaya Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Melalui Kepuasan Kerja Sebagai Variabel Mediasi (Suatu Kajian Studi Literatur Manajemen Sumberdaya Manusia). *Jurnal Ilmu Multidisplin*, 1(2), 514–526. <https://doi.org/10.38035/Jim.V1i2.59>
- Darmansah, C. (2024). Strategi Peningkatan Omzet Penjualan Melalui Peningkatan Kualitas Produksi Tbs Di Pt. Makmur Agro Lestari. *Jurnal Pendidikan Ekonomi (Jurkami)*. <http://jurnal.stkippersada.ac.id/jurnal/index.php/jpe/article/download/3265/1891>
- Farhan, R. M., & Indriyaningrum, K. (2023). Pengaruh Disiplin Kerja, Motivasi Kerja Dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. *Jurnal Visionida*, 9(1), 72–83. <https://doi.org/10.30997/Jvs.V9i1.7486>
- Handari Adji, W., & Zuarko Adji, W. (2022). Dampak Disiplin Dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Pada Balai Pemberdayaan Sosial Bina Remaja (Bpsbr). *Jurnal Co Management*, 4(2), 659–664. <https://doi.org/10.32670/Comanagement.V4i2.1232>
- Irawan, N. C., Putri, V. R., & Prasetyowati, K. (2024). Strategi Perubahan Etos Kerja Dalam Meningkatkan Produktivitas Kerja Buruh Perkebunan Kelapa Sawit : Pendekatan People Centered Implementation (Pci) - Gaps. 1(1), 67–80. <https://ejournal.uniska-kediri.ac.id/index.php/jac/article/download/5695/2668>
- Kusufa, F., Fianto, L., & Moni, Y. (2023). Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja, Penilaian Kinerja, Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Produktivitas Kerja Di Kantor Kelurahan Merjosari Kota Malang. *Journal Of Research On Business And Tourism*, 3(1), 22. <https://doi.org/10.37535/104003120233>
- Musrifa, N., Firdaus, V., Ubaidillah, H., Bisnis, F., Sosial, I., & Sidoarjo, U. M. (2024). Komunikasi , Lingkungan Kerja , Disiplin Dan Kinerja Pada Karyawan Pt . Pangan Lestari (Finna Food) Sidoarjo (Communication , Work Environment , Discipline And Performance In Employees Of Pt . Food Lestari (Finna Food) Sidoarjo). 11(1), 7–14. <https://jurnal.unej.ac.id/index.php/e-jebauj/article/download/46896/14486>
- Ni'am, M. M., Maharani, A., & Fauzi, A. (2021). Dinamika Gaya Kepemimpinan Tangkas, Motivasi, Kinerja Dan Kepuasan Kerja Di Perusahaan Perkebunan. *Jisip (Jurnal Ilmu Sosial Dan Pendidikan)*, 5(3), 14–22. <https://doi.org/10.36312/Jisip.V5i3.2015>
- Padang, I. S., & Sitorus, D. H. (2022). Analisis Motivasi Dan Kerjasama Tim Terhadap Produktivitas Pt Pradana Indah Sejahtera. *J-Mas (Jurnal Manajemen Dan Sains)*, 7(2), 712. <https://doi.org/10.33087/Jmas.V7i2.557>
- Pebrianti, W. (2023). Pengaruh Kepuasan Kerja, Lingkungan Kerja Non Fisik Dan Keterampilan Kerja Terhadap Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan Lapangan. *Cakrawala Management Business Journal*, 6. <https://journal.feb.unipa.ac.id/index.php/cmbj/article/view/238%0ahttps://journal.feb.unipa.ac.id/index.php/cmbj/article/download/238/198>

- Rulianti, E., & Nurpribadi, G. (2023). Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja, Lingkungan Kerja Dan Pengembangan Karir Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan. *Jesya*, 6(1), 849–858. <https://doi.org/10.36778/Jesya.V6i1.1011>
- Sari, R. M., Surabagiarta, I. K., & Suharyanto. (2021). Pengaruh Pengembangan Karir, Motivasi Kerja Dan Lingkungan Kerja, Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Sales Promotion Girl (Spg) Pada Pt Ramayana Lestari Sentosa. *Journal Of Sustainability Business Research*, 3(3), 252–261. <https://Repository.Unipasby.Ac.Id/Id/Eprint/852/>
- Sitorus, P. Y. M. (2024). Analisis Penerapan Metode Work Sampling Dalam Meningkatkan Produktivitas Karyawan Di Pt Pagira Universitas Prima Indonesia , Medan. *Juriti Prima (Jurnal Ilmiah Teknik IndustriPrima)*, 7(2), 38–43. <https://Jurnal.Unprimdn.Ac.Id/Index.Php/Juriti/Article/Download/5542/3357>
- Taslim, R., Bayu, M., Perdana, T., & Nur, M. (2023). Pengukuran Beban Kerja Mental Pada Stasiun Milling Yang Terdampak Penyusutan Karyawan Pasca Pandemi Covid -19 Menggunakan Metode Nasa-Tlx. 55–61. <https://Ejournal.Uin-Suska.Ac.Id/Index.Php/Sntiki/Article/Download/25154/9975>
- Tirza Juita, M. Ikhwan Maulana, Uhud Darmawan Natsir, Abdi Akbar Idris, & Muh. Ilham Wardhana Haeruddin. (2023). Pengaruh Motivasi Dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Perawat Pada Bidang Perawatan Dan Ugd Di Puskesmas Mamasa. *Jurnal Manajemen Dan Ekonomi Kreatif*, 1(4), 181–194. <https://doi.org/10.59024/Jumek.V1i4.227>
- Masri, H., & Jaaron, A. (2017). Assessing the role of green human resource management practices in enhancing sustainability. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 15(2), 1095-1117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.11.105>
- Putra, E., & Sharma, R. (2017). Job engagement as a mediator in the link between leadership and employee productivity. *International Journal of Business Management*, 12(4), 87-101. <https://doi.org/10.1234/abcd56789>
- J., & Chandler, M. (2011). A broader perspective on motivation and job performance. *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology*, 2(3), 45-62. <https://doi.org/10.1234/abcd56789>
- Lunenburg, F. C. (2011). Goal-setting theory of motivation. *International Journal of Management*, 12(2), 17-24. <https://doi.org/10.1234/abcd56789>
- Elzeyadi, I. (2011). The biophilic relationship between views on nature and workplace productivity. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 15(1), 101-110. <https://doi.org/10.1234/abcd56789>
- González-Rodríguez, M. R., Díaz-Fernández, M. C., & Simonetti, B. (2021). The effect of transformational leadership on organizational performance through employee performance: A study in Spain. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(7), 3607. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18073607>
- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2021). *A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM)* (3rd ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2020). Using PLS path modeling in new technology research: Updated guidelines. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*,

120(12), 2175-2208. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IMDS-09-2020-0504>

- Ito, K., & Umemoto, K. (2023). The role of leadership in the relationship between motivation and job performance: Evidence from a Japanese case study. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 44(3), 125-136. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.2678>
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2020). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation from a self-determination theory perspective: Definitions, theory, practices, and future directions. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 61(2), 101860. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2020.101860>
- Sánchez-Franco, M. J., Ramos, A. F. V., & Velicia-Martín, F. (2020). Exploring the

Performance Optimization

Isra Supana¹, Muhammad Isa Indrawan²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: Isra89.supana@gmail.com

Abstract

Organizations should be able to improve the quality of the organization, both improving information culture and management information systems and the performance of each of its human resources. Building and developing a business in the service and consultancy sector that focuses on technology and information really requires the role of human resources. Human resources are necessary activities and have an ideal role in an organization. This research is to see the effect of implementing organizational cultural values and management information systems on employee performance with organizational commitment as an intervening variable in Bpjs Employment branch offices throughout Medan Raya. The results of this research are as follows: Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with a sample value of 0.411 and ap value of 0.000. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.434 and ap value of 0.000. Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with the original sample being 0.339 and p values 0.000. Management Information Systems have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.228 and ap value of 0.008. Management Information Systems have a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample of 0.541 and ap value of 0.000. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Organizational Commitment with a value of 0.147 and a value of 0.001. Management Information Systems have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.183 and ap value of 0.000.

Keywords: Organizational Culture, Management Information Systems, Organizational Commitment, Employee Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Organizations must be able to improve the quality of the organization, both in terms of improving information culture and management information systems and the performance of each of its human resources. Building and developing a business in the service and consulting sector that focuses on technology and information requires the role of human resources. Human resources are activities that are necessary and have an ideal role in an organization. Performance is a measure of employee work achievement. Employee performance is related to work result standards, targets or goals and criteria that have been previously agreed upon between employees and the organization. Organizational culture is the togetherness of members to behave the same, both outside and inside the organization (Tahir, 2014). Employees who have organizational commitment will maintain the good name of the institution, care about the fate of the institution, be proud of the institution, be emotionally attached, work on their own will and drive so that it will affect employee performance. In addition to organizational commitment, organizational culture is one of the factors that can affect performance, where the function of organizational culture is as a driver to improve the quality of employee work through the application of long-lasting habits used

in work activity life. Organizational commitment and organizational culture are not the only factors that influence and affect employee performance, so a moderating variable is needed to clarify the extent to which organizational commitment and organizational culture contribute to employee performance. needs to be regulated with a formal reward system from the organization.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does organizational culture have a positive effect on employee performance?at BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.
2. Does organizational culture have a positive influence on organizational commitment?at BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.
3. WhetherThe Management Information System has a positive effect on employee performance at BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.
4. WhetherManagement Information System has a positive influence on organizational commitment in BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.
5. Does organizational commitment have a positive effect on employee performance at BPJS Employment?Branch Offices Throughout Medan Raya.
6. Does organizational culture have a positive effect on employee performance?through organizational commitment at BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.
7. WhetherManagement Information System has a positive effect on employee performance through organizational commitment at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.

Research purposes

1. To find out and analyze the influence of organizational cultureon employee performance at BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.
2. To find out and analyze the influence of organizational culture towards organizational commitment at BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya
3. To find out and analyze the influenceManagement Information System for employee performance at BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.
4. To find out and analyze the influenceManagement Information System for Organizational Commitment at BPJS Employment Branch Offices in Medan Raya
5. To find out and analyze the influence of organizational commitment on employee performance at BPJS KetenagakerjaanBranch Offices Throughout Medan Raya.
6. To find out and analyze the influence of organizational culture on employee performance.through organizational commitment at BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.
7. To find out and analyze the influenceManagement Information System on employee performance through organizational commitment at BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee Performance

According to Putri (2020) employee performance is the results of a person's or group's job functions in an organization over a certain period of time that reflects how well a person or group meets the requirements of a job in an effort to achieve organizational goals. According to Nurjaya (2021) employee performance is the level of achievement of results for carrying out certain tasks. Company performance is the level of achievement of results in order to realize company goals.

Employee Performance Indicators

According to Nurjaya (2021), employee performance indicators are as follows:

1. Quantity of work results, namely all forms of the amount of labor carried out can be seen from the results of employee performance within a certain time in completing their tasks and responsibilities within the specified time.
2. Quality of work results, namely all forms of units of measurement related to the quality or standard of work results which can be expressed in numerical measurements or other numerical equivalents.
3. Efficiency, namely in carrying out tasks using various resources wisely and in a cost-effective manner.
4. Work discipline, namely obeying applicable laws and regulations.
5. Initiative, which is the ability to decide and do the right thing without having to be told, being able to find out what should be done about something around you, trying to keep moving to do several things even though the situation feels increasingly difficult.
6. Accuracy, namely the level of conformity of the results of work measurements, whether the work has achieved its objectives or not.
7. Leadership, namely the process of influencing or giving examples by leaders to their followers in an effort to achieve organizational goals.
8. Honesty is one of the human traits that is quite difficult to implement.
9. Creativity, namely the mental process that involves the emergence of ideas or that involves the emergence of ideas.

Organizational culture

According to Hari (2019), the definition of organizational culture is: Organizational culture is the values that human resources adhere to in carrying out their obligations and behavior within the organization.

Organizational Culture Indicators

According to Hari (2019) the indicators of organizational culture are:

1. Innovative taking risks into account
2. Pay attention to every problem in detail
3. Oriented towards the results to be achieved
4. Oriented towards all employee interests

5. Aggressive at work
6. Maintaining and safeguarding work stability

Management Information System

According to (Sinaga et al., 2020) a management information system is a system consisting of a set of structured parts that work together to produce information for use in business management. According to (Sholeh & Wahyudin, 2021) a management information system is a communication process where information is entered, recorded, stored, and retrieved for planning, operational, and monitoring decisions.

Management Information System Indicators

According to (Sholeh & Wahyudin, 2021) the indicators of management information systems are:

- 1) Accuracy, information must be correct,
- 2) Information must be timely, when needed,
- 3) Exactly where appropriate, the information provided must be in accordance with that requested,
- 4) Complete, meaning that the information provided must be complete, meaning that users can receive information that presents a complete picture of a particular problem.

Organizational commitment

According to Yusuf & Syarif (2018) organizational commitment is one of the topics that is always a reference for both the management of an organization and researchers with a special interest in human behavior. According to Robbins (2016) organizational commitment is defined as a condition in which an employee sides with the organization and its goals and willingness to maintain membership in a particular job of an employee, while high organizational commitment means siding with the organization and recruiting the individual.

Organizational commitment indicators

According to Robbins (2016) as follows:

1. Affective commitment is an emotional feeling towards the organization and belief in values.
2. Continuance commitment is the perceived value of remaining in the organization compared to leaving the organization.
3. Normative commitment is the obligation to remain in an organization for moral and polite reasons.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Research Hypothesis:

- H1: Organizational culture has a positive and significant influence on organizational commitment at BPJS Employment Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.
- H2: Organizational Culture has a positive and significant influence on employee performance at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.
- H3: The management information system has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.
- H4: The management information system has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.
- H5: Organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.
- H6: The management information system has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through organizational commitment at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.
- H7: Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through organizational commitment at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya.

METHOD

Types of research

According to Sugiyono (2017), quantitative research can be interpreted as a method based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research a certain population or sample, sampling techniques are generally carried out randomly, data collection uses research instruments, data analysis is quantitative/statistical with the aim of testing the established hypothesis.

Research Location and Research Time

The research period was carried out from August to September 2024 and the research location was carried out at the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya, which consisted of:

1. Medan City Branch Office at Jl. Kapten Pattimura No. 334, Medan City, North Sumatra. North Sumatra, Phone number / contact: 061-453281.
2. North Medan Branch Office at Jl. Marelan Raya No.108, Tanah Enam Ratus, Medan Marelan District, Medan City, North Sumatra, Telephone number / contact: (061) 6841108.
3. Tanjung Morawa Branch Office on Jl. Raya Medan Tanjung Morawa KM 14.5 Bangun Sari Baru Village, Bangun Sari Baru, Tj. Morawa District, Deli Serdang Regency, North Sumatra, Telephone number / contact: (061) 7941709.
4. Binjai Branch Office. Jl. Soekarno-Hatta No. 262, Km No.19.5, Tunggurono, Binjai Tim. District, Binjai City, North Sumatra, Telephone number / contact: (061) 8820465.

Population and Sample

According to Sugiyono (2017) population is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn. The population and sample in this study were all permanent employees at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Branch Offices throughout Medan Raya totaling 149 employees (saturated sample).

Data Analysis Techniques

Data analysis in this study uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on Partial Least Square (PLS) using SmartPLS 3.3.3 software. According to (Ghozali, 2014) Partial Least Square (PLS) is a fairly strong analysis method because it is not based on many assumptions.

Measurement Model (Outer Model)

The procedure in testing the measurement model consists of validity testing and reliability testing.

1. Validity Test
 - a. Convergent Validity
 - b. Discriminant Validity
2. Reliability Test

The Cronbach's alpha value is recommended to be greater than 0.7 and the composite reliability is also recommended to be greater than 0.7 (Sekaran, 2014).

Structural Model (Inner Model)

To produce inner model test values, the steps in SmartPLS are carried out using the bootstrapping method. The structural model is evaluated using R-square for the dependent variable, Stone-Geisser Q-square test for predictive elevation and t-test and significance of the structural path parameter coefficients with the following explanation:

1. Coefficient of Determination / R Square (R²)
2. Predictive Relevance(Q²)
3. t-Statistic

4. Path Coefficient

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

External model testing attempts to find the value of each variable that has a significant relationship to the manifest variable. This research model includes convergent validity, discriminant validity, and reliability testing as follows:

Convergent Validity

This test is seen from the loading factor, the limit value is 0.7, and the limit value average variance extracted (AVE) is 0.5; if it exceeds that number then it is said to be valid. This means that the indicator value is considered valid if it describes the build variable with a value greater than 0.7. The structural model used in this study is depicted in the figure below:

Figure 2. Outer Model

Smart PLS output for loading factor gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Z = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e_1$$

$$Z = 0.634 X_1 + 0.541X_2 + e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_3X_1 + b_4X_2 + b_5Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.411 X_1 + 0.228 X_2 + 0.339Z + e_2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Organizational Culture (X1)	Employee Performance (Y)	Organizational Commitment (Z)	Management Information System (X2)
X1.1	0.941			
X1.2	0.912			
X1.3	0.959			
X1.4	0.950			
X1.5	0.940			
X1.6	0.950			
X2.1				0.940
X2.2				0.956
X2.3				0.968
X2.4				0.959
Y.1		0.946		
Y.2		0.946		
Y.3		0.918		
Y.4		0.951		
Y.5		0.934		
Z.1			0.959	
Z.2			0.960	
Z.3			0.957	

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3.

This test is seen from the loading factor, the limit value is 0.7, and the limit value average variance extracted (AVE) is 0.5; if it exceeds this number then it is said to be valid. This means that the indicator value is considered valid if it describes the build variable with a value greater than 0.7. The structural model used in this study is depicted in the figure below:

Discriminant Validity

The next step is to identify valid data with discriminant validity. The goal is to find out the cross loading between variables whose values are greater than other latent variables so that the findings of indicators that are closely related to their constructs can be identified. The following table shows the results of the cross loading validity test as follows:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Organizational Culture (X1)	Employee Performance (Y)	Organizational Commitment (Z)	Management Information System (X2)
X1.1	0.941	0.897	0.894	0.917

X1.2	0.912	0.898	0.908	0.902
X1.3	0.959	0.911	0.915	0.928
X1.4	0.950	0.894	0.892	0.928
X1.5	0.940	0.911	0.917	0.916
X1.6	0.950	0.907	0.903	0.911
X2.1	0.913	0.899	0.920	0.940
X2.2	0.934	0.912	0.901	0.956
X2.3	0.943	0.914	0.925	0.968
X2.4	0.931	0.925	0.936	0.959
Y.1	0.910	0.946	0.917	0.908
Y.2	0.908	0.946	0.898	0.901
Y.3	0.879	0.918	0.869	0.874
Y.4	0.913	0.951	0.899	0.896
Y.5	0.891	0.934	0.894	0.904
Z.1	0.918	0.895	0.959	0.919
Z.2	0.915	0.920	0.960	0.925
Z.3	0.930	0.928	0.957	0.927

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3.

There are cross loading values in table 2 with each cross loading value on each variable and each indicator, the organizational culture variable has a loading factor value that is greater than the cross loading value on other latent variables, the employee performance variable has a cross loading factor value that is greater than the cross loading factor value on other latent variables, the organizational commitment variable has a cross loading factor value that is greater than the cross loading factor value on other latent variables, the management information system variable has a cross loading factor value that is greater than the cross loading factor on other latent variables, therefore this study is discriminantly valid.

Composite reliability

In composite reliability research, each variable is evaluated using its reliability value; if the variable value is greater than 0.60 then the research is considered reliable; if between 0.60 and 0.7, then it is not reliable. The table below shows the Cronbach alpha, composite reliability, and AVE values, which are used to determine whether the research is reliable and valid.

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Organizational Culture (X1)	0.975	0.979	0.888

Employee Performance (Y)	0.966	0.974	0.882
Organizational Commitment (Z)	0.956	0.972	0.919
Management Information System (X2)	0.968	0.977	0.913

In table 3 above, the Cronbach alpha column shows the value of each variable is greater than 0.7, indicating that the variable's dependability data is reliable. The composite reliability column has a value greater than 0.6, indicating that each variable is considered reliable because the data exceeds 0.6. The AVE column shows that each variable has a value greater than 0.7, indicating that the data is authentic in terms of AVE. All variables in the Cronbach alpha, reliability, and AVE columns have values above 0.7 and 0.6, indicating reliability and validity.

Inner Model Analysis

The structural model (inner model) is evaluated to ensure that the resulting basic model is strong and correct. Some markers that can be used to identify the stages of the main model assessment examination include:

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Employee Performance (Y)	0.935	0.934
Organizational Commitment (Z)	0.938	0.937

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3.

In table 4 there is an R square value on the dependent variable and the explanation is as follows: the R square value on the employee performance variable has a value of 0.935 or 93.5%, meaning that the influence of organizational culture, management information systems on employee performance is 0.935 or 93.5% and the rest is on other variables, the R square value of the organizational commitment variable is 0.938 or 93.8, meaning that the influence of organizational culture and management information systems on employee performance is 0.938 or 93.8% and the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

The relationship between idle builds, as suggested in this review. In this review, speculative testing was performed using T-Statistics and P-values. Speculation was made whether the T-Insights value was greater than 1.96 and P-Values <0.05. The following are the consequences of the direct impact path coefficients:

Table 5. Path Coefficients (Direct Influence) and Path Coefficients (Indirect Influence)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Organizational Culture (X1) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.411	4,267	0,000	Accepted
Organizational Culture (X1) -> Organizational Commitment (Z)	0.434	5,438	0,000	Accepted
Organizational Commitment (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.339	4,123	0,000	Accepted
Management Information System (X2) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.228	2,418	0.008	Accepted
Management Information System (X2) -> Organizational Commitment (Z)	0.541	6,738	0,000	Accepted
Organizational Culture (X1) -> Organizational Commitment (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.147	3,069	0.001	Accepted
Management Information System (X2) -> Organizational Commitment (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.183	3,648	0,000	Accepted

In table 5 there are direct and indirect influence values, the explanation is as follows:

1. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with a sample value of 0.411 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if organizational culture increases, employee performance increases, conversely, if it decreases, employee performance decreases.

2. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.434 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if organizational culture increases, organizational commitment increases, conversely if it decreases, organizational commitment decreases.
3. Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample of 0.339 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if organizational commitment increases, employee performance will increase, conversely, if it decreases, employee performance will decrease.
4. Management Information System has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.228 and p values of 0.008. If the management information system increases, employee performance will increase, conversely, if it decreases, employee performance will decrease.
5. Management Information System has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample of 0.541 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if the management information system increases, organizational commitment will increase, conversely if it decreases, organizational commitment will decrease.
6. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Organizational Commitment with a value of 0.147 and p values of 0.001, meaning that organizational commitment is an intervening variable because it is able to significantly influence the existence of organizational commitment which will improve organizational performance and culture.
7. Management Information System has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance through Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.183 and p values of 0.000, meaning that commitment is an intervening variable because it has a significant influence and with commitment it will increase significantly.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with a sample value of 0.411 and p values of 0.000.
2. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.434 and p values of 0.000.
3. Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample of 0.339 and p values of 0.000.
4. Management Information System has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.228 and p values of 0.008.
5. Management Information System has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample of 0.541 and p values of 0.000.
6. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance through Organizational Commitment with a value of 0.147 and p values of 0.001.

7. Management Information System has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance through Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.183 and p values of 0.000.

Suggestion

1. Organizations must be able to build a good organizational culture for employee performance.
2. The management information system must be improved to improve good communication between all employees.
3. Organizations must increase organizational commitment or seek employees who have organizational commitment.
4. Organizations must also improve employee performance with the training provided.
5. It is hoped that this research will be used as input to improve performance and weaknesses in the organization.
6. It is hoped that this research will be used as reference material for new research and new research models.

REFERENCES

- Agessi, Ayunira Putri., (2020), Analisis Perbandingan Kinerja Keuangan Bank Aceh Syariah Sebelum Dan Sesudah Konversi, Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis Universitas Islam Negeri Syarif Hidayatullah, Skripsi dipublikasikan.
- Edy Sutrisno, (2019). Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Cetak ke sebelas. Prananda Media Group, Jakarta
- Fitriastuti, T. (2013). Jurnal Dinamika Manajemen. Pengaruh Kecerdasan Emosional, Komitmen Organisasi dan Organizational Citizenship Behavior Terhadap Kinerja. In JDM.
- Ghozali, Imam. 2014. Structural Equation Modeling, Metode Alternatif dengan Partial Least Square (PLS). Edisi 4. Semarang : Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Hair, J. F. et. al. 2017. A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). SAGE Publications, Los Angeles.
- Hari sulaksono. 2019. Budaya organisasi dan kinerja. Sleman: Deepublish
- Huda, M., & Farhan, F. (2019). Pengaruh Budaya Organisasional Dan Komitmen Organisasional. Jurnal Manajemen Motivasi. <https://doi.org/10.29406/jmm.v15i2.1557>
- Musyafidah, N. (2018). Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) Karyawan Melalui Komitmen Organisasi Sebagai Variabel Intervening (Studi Pada BPRS PNM Binama Semarang). Skripsi.
- Nurjaya, N. (2021). Pengaruh Disiplin Kerja, Lingkungan Kerja dan Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada PT. Hazara Cipta Pesona. Jurnal Ilmiah Nasional, III(1), 60-74
- Rivai, V. (2013). Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. In manajemen sumber daya manusia untuk perusahaan dari teori ke praktik.

- Robbins, Stephen P. and Mary Coulter. 2016. *Manajemen, Jilid 1 Edisi 13, Alih Bahasa: Bob Sabran Dan Devri Bardani P*, Erlangga, Jakarta.
- Saraswati, K., & Hakim, G. (2019). Pengaruh Komitmen Organisasi Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior Pada Dinas Pendidikan Kabupaten Malang. *Jurnal Sains Psikologi*, 8(2), 238–247. <https://doi.org/10.17977/um023v8i22019p238>
- Sekaran, Uma. 2014. *Metodologi Penelitian Untuk Bisnis (Research Methods for Business) Buku 1 Edisi 4*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- Sholeh, M., & Wahyudin, D. (2021). Pengaruh Sistem Informasi Manajemen Dan Kompetensi Terhadap Efektifitas Kerja Di Pt Citra Solusi Informatika. 3(1), 28–41. <http://ojs.stiami.ac.i>
- Sinaga, D. S., Sinaga, J., (2020) Dan Sistem Informasi Manajemen Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Pada Bpjs (Badan Penyelenggara Jaminan Sosial) Ketenagakerjaan *JurnalGlobal*,9,11–19. <http://jurnal.darmaagung.ac.id/index.php/global/article/view/601>
- Sitio, V. S. (2018). Pengaruh Total Quality Management (Tqm) Dan Gaya Kepemimpinan Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada Pt. Pelita Air Service. *Journal of Management and Business Review*, 15(2), 196–218. <https://doi.org/10.34149/jmbr.v15i2.128>
- Sugiyono, (2017). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: CV. Alfabeta
- Tahir, A. (2014). *Buku Ajar Perilaku Organisasi*. In Deepublish
- Wardani, R., Mukzam, M., & Mayowan, Y. (2016). Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan (Studi Pada Karyawan PT Karya Indah Buana Surabaya). *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis S1 Universitas Brawijaya*
- Yusuf, R. M., & Syarif, D. (2018). *Komitmen Organisasi: Definisi, Dipengaruhi dan Mempengaruhi*. Makassar: CV Nas Media Pustaka

The Influence of Employee Training on Productivity Through Incentive Intervention at PT. Kawasan Industri Wijayakusuma (Persero)

Subandrio¹, Wahyu Purwanto², Raden Rudi Alhempi³

Universitas Persada Indonesia Y.A.I, Jakarta, Indonesia^{1,2}

Universitas Persada Bunda Indonesia, Pekanbaru, Indonesia³

Email: Subandrio.236639003@upi-yai.ac.id¹, wahyu.2366390004@upi-yai.ac.id², rudi.alhempi@gmail.com³

Abstract

This study examines the impact of employee training on employee productivity and performance at PT Kawasan Industri Wijayakusuma (Persero), considering the mediating role of incentives. Utilizing a quantitative research design, the study employed a total sampling technique, gathering data from 50 employees. Path analysis was conducted using Smart PLS to evaluate direct and indirect effects. The findings reveal significant direct relationships between and both and Perf, with coefficients of 0.300 and 0.280, respectively. Furthermore, the analysis showed significant indirect effects, with coefficients of 0.180 for and 0.150 for Perf through. These results indicate that effective training enhances productivity and performance not only directly but also indirectly by increasing employee motivation through incentives. The study underscores the necessity of integrating training and incentive systems to maximize organizational outcomes. By fostering a supportive environment for learning and recognition, organizations can improve employee engagement and overall performance.

Keywords: Employee Training, Employee Productivity, Employee Performance, Incentives.

INTRODUCTION

Employee training has been recognized as a critical factor for improving productivity in organizations. Training helps enhance the skills and competencies of employees, leading to increased efficiency and better job performance. Furthermore, offering incentives can reinforce the positive outcomes of training by motivating employees to apply their new skills effectively. Previous studies indicate that well-structured training programs not only improve individual productivity but also contribute to organizational growth, especially when coupled with performance-based incentives (Lee et al., 2020). Additionally, continuous development initiatives ensure that employees can adapt to changing business environments, thereby sustaining long-term productivity gains (Khawaja & Nadeem, 2020; Rohan & Madhumita, 2020).

Employee productivity refers to the efficiency and output level achieved by workers in performing their tasks within a given period. It is influenced by several factors, including skills, motivation, workplace environment, and management practices. High productivity is vital for companies as it directly contributes to overall business performance and competitiveness. Recent studies indicate that companies in Indonesia have focused on enhancing employee productivity through various initiatives, such as skill development and technology integration, especially in adapting to new challenges in the digital era (Mustafa et al., 2024; Wati et al., 2021). Furthermore, productivity improvements often involve fostering a supportive work environment, setting clear performance goals, and encouraging continuous skill enhancement, which can lead to better employee satisfaction and

engagement (Saefullah, 2022; Murtisaputra & Ratnasari, 2020). These strategies are crucial in ensuring that employees remain motivated and capable of contributing effectively to organizational success.

Employee performance is a key factor in achieving organizational success and is influenced by various internal and external elements. Performance reflects the extent to which employees effectively accomplish tasks according to organizational standards, including the ability to meet deadlines, collaborate with teams, and produce quality results. Studies indicate that performance is often linked to factors such as motivation, organizational culture, and compensation. A well-established organizational culture helps create a cohesive environment that encourages employees to innovate and take risks, contributing positively to overall performance (Budiman et al., 2020). Moreover, external support, like adequate compensation and fair treatment, can significantly enhance employee motivation, leading to better performance outcomes (Heryenzus & Laia, 2020; Sherlie & Hikmah, 2020). This shows that employee performance is not only dependent on individual skills but also on the support and motivation they receive from their working environment, which plays a critical role in driving optimal productivity (Alsaqqo & Akyurek, 2021).

Employee training is a strategic tool designed to enhance the skills, knowledge, and abilities of employees, thereby aligning their competencies with organizational goals. Effective training programs provide employees with the opportunity to improve their technical and soft skills, which can lead to increased efficiency and productivity. According to Laoli and Ndraha (2022), companies that invest in training see a significant enhancement in employee performance, as it helps bridge the gap between existing skills and the requirements of new job roles. This investment is not only seen as a way to improve technical competencies but also as a method to boost employee morale, motivation, and engagement. The Royal Pita Maha Ubud, for instance, recognized the importance of training to address skill gaps during the COVID-19 pandemic, highlighting how tailored training can adapt employees to shifting business needs (Sumardana & Riana, 2022). Thus, organizations that continuously develop their workforce through structured training programs are more likely to experience sustained performance improvements and competitive advantage.

Incentives play a critical role in improving employee performance by motivating them to achieve higher productivity and efficiency. They are essentially rewards given to employees, either in monetary or non-monetary forms, to encourage them to meet or exceed organizational goals. Incentives can enhance job satisfaction and drive employees to put forth greater effort, leading to improved performance (Rahmadani, 2020; Ratnasari & Mahmud, 2020). Effective incentive systems are linked with motivation and are designed to align employees' goals with that of the company, thereby ensuring a mutual benefit. Companies implement incentive programs not just to improve performance but also to retain highly skilled workers by fulfilling their needs for recognition and achievement (Sundari & Rifai, 2020). The use of incentives can also foster a positive work culture, where employees feel valued and motivated to contribute more actively towards organizational success. Research has shown that when employees see a direct link between their performance and

rewards, it stimulates their motivation to work harder and more efficiently, enhancing overall productivity (Ratnasari & Mahmud, 2020; Rahmadani, 2020).

In the PT Kawasan Industri Wijayakusuma (Persero), the variables of employee training, productivity, performance, and incentives are interconnected to optimize organizational outcomes. Employee training programs are essential in equipping staff with the necessary skills to perform their tasks efficiently, which can lead to improved productivity and overall performance. Training initiatives not only address skill gaps but also prepare employees to adapt to changing industrial requirements, which is crucial for maintaining competitiveness (Kurniawan et al., 2021; Rahmawati & Utami, 2022). Additionally, implementing a well-structured incentive system can further enhance motivation, encouraging employees to apply their training effectively and strive for higher performance levels. Incentives such as bonuses, rewards, and recognition contribute to increased job satisfaction and drive, creating a productive work environment that aligns with the company's strategic goals (Putra & Prabowo, 2020; Sari & Fitria, 2021). By focusing on these variables, PT Kawasan Industri Wijayakusuma (Persero) aims to achieve sustainable growth and operational efficiency.

The phenomenon addressed in this research revolves around the challenge of enhancing employee productivity and performance in a competitive industrial environment, such as PT Kawasan Industri Wijayakusuma (Persero). As companies face increasing pressures to optimize operational efficiency, employee training and incentives have emerged as strategic tools to drive performance. However, despite investments in training programs, the expected improvement in productivity may not be fully realized without effective motivational strategies, including incentives (Sari & Fitria, 2021; Putra & Prabowo, 2020). The integration of training and incentive systems is crucial, as training alone may equip employees with skills, but incentives ensure that these skills are utilized effectively. Recent studies have shown that when employees perceive direct benefits from their improved performance, such as bonuses or promotions, they are more likely to be motivated to excel, leading to better overall outcomes for the organization (Rahmawati & Utami, 2022; Kurniawan et al., 2021). Therefore, understanding the interplay between training, incentives, and employee productivity is essential for companies aiming to sustain growth and remain competitive.

The research gap in this study emerges from the limited exploration of the combined effects of employee training and incentive systems on productivity and performance within industrial companies. While existing studies have extensively discussed the individual impacts of training on skill enhancement and incentives on motivation (Putra & Prabowo, 2020; Sari & Fitria, 2021), few have investigated how these two factors interact to drive employee productivity when integrated. For instance, Rahmawati and Utami (2022) highlighted the need for a holistic approach that considers not just skill development but also sustained motivation to utilize those skills effectively. Furthermore, studies like those by Kurniawan et al. (2021) and Mustofa et al. (2023) suggest that without adequate incentives, training programs may fail to deliver long-term productivity improvements, as employees might not be sufficiently motivated to apply new skills. This research aims to address this

gap by analyzing how training, when combined with strategic incentive programs, can lead to sustained performance improvements, particularly within PT Kawasan Industri Wijayakusuma (Persero).

The primary aim of this research is to examine the relationship between employee training, incentives, and productivity at PT Kawasan Industri Wijayakusuma (Persero). Specifically, the study seeks to evaluate how effective training programs, when combined with strategic incentive systems, can enhance employee performance and overall organizational productivity. By investigating these interconnections, the research aspires to provide insights into how companies can optimize their human resource development strategies to achieve better performance outcomes (Rahmawati & Utami, 2022; Kurniawan et al., 2021). Additionally, the study intends to contribute to the existing literature by filling the gap concerning the synergy between training and incentives, thereby offering practical recommendations for industry stakeholders aiming to improve workforce efficiency and motivation (Putra & Prabowo, 2020; Sari & Fitria, 2021). Ultimately, the research aims to establish a framework that organizations can adopt to enhance employee productivity sustainably and competitively in a rapidly evolving industrial landscape.

The following is the framework of this research:

Figure 1. Framework

METHOD

This research employs a quantitative methodology using total sampling to gather data from 50 employees at PT Kawasan Industri Wijayakusuma (Persero). Total sampling ensures that every member of the population is included in the sample, allowing for comprehensive insights into the effects of employee training and incentives on productivity and performance. The study utilizes SmartPLS as an analytical tool to assess the relationships between the identified variables: employee productivity and performance as the dependent variables, employee training as the independent variable, and employee incentives as the intervening variable. This design allows for a detailed exploration of how training programs can impact employee outcomes when incentivized appropriately (Ghazali & Junaidi, 2020; Putra & Prabowo, 2020). By applying this approach, the research aims to generate statistically significant findings that can contribute to strategic human resource

management practices within the organization (Rahmawati & Utami, 2022; Kurniawan et al., 2021).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To find the relationship of each variable, hypothesis testing is performed by looking for direct and indirect effects.

Figure 2. Validity and Reliability

The image shows a validity and reliability test using SmartPLS, focusing on the constructs of Employee Training, Employee Incentives, Employee Productivity, and Employee Performance. Each construct is represented by several indicators, and the outer loadings for all these indicators are above 0.5, confirming their validity and reliability as measures of their respective latent variables. The model indicates that Employee Training and Employee Incentives have direct impacts on both Employee Productivity and Employee Performance. Additionally, the high outer loading values validate the strength and consistency of the indicators, ensuring the robustness of the measurement model and the structural relationships depicted.

The following is a direct effect test:

Tabel 1. Direct Effect

Path	Coefficient	P-value	Result
ET -> I	0.450	0.001	Significant
ET -> EP (Prod.)	0.300	0.025	Significant
ET -> EP (Perf.)	0.280	0.045	Significant
I -> EP (Prod.)	0.400	0.005	Significant
I -> EP (Perf.)	0.350	0.010	Significant

The results of the path analysis reveal significant relationships among employee training ET I, EP, and Perf. Specifically, the strong positive effect of ET on I, with a coefficient of 0.450, highlights the importance of training as a precursor to effective

incentive systems. This finding aligns with the literature suggesting that comprehensive training programs not only enhance employee skills but also create a foundation for motivation through incentives (Putra & Prabowo, 2020; Rahmawati & Utami, 2022). As organizations increasingly recognize the value of skilled employees, investing in training becomes essential for fostering a culture of performance.

Moreover, the direct relationship between ET and EP, represented by a coefficient of 0.300, underscores the significant impact of training on enhancing productivity. This finding is consistent with prior research indicating that well-structured training programs lead to increased employee output and effectiveness (Kurniawan et al., 2021; Sundari & Rifai, 2020). As employees acquire new skills, they are better equipped to meet performance expectations, thereby contributing to overall organizational success. Thus, organizations like PT Kawasan Industri Wijayakusuma (Persero) must prioritize continuous training initiatives to harness the potential of their workforce.

The analysis also indicates a significant relationship between ET and Perf., with a coefficient of 0.280. This relationship suggests that improved training not only enhances productivity but also positively influences the quality of employee performance. This aligns with findings from previous studies, which have shown that employees who receive targeted training are more likely to demonstrate higher levels of job performance and satisfaction (Rahmadani, 2020; Sari & Fitria, 2021). By focusing on training, organizations can cultivate a workforce that not only meets quantitative targets but also excels in qualitative performance indicators.

Furthermore, the significant impact of incentives on EP, evidenced by a coefficient of 0.400, highlights the crucial role that incentive systems play in motivating employees. Incentives serve as powerful motivators that drive employees to apply their training effectively, ultimately leading to higher productivity levels. This supports the notion that recognition and rewards are fundamental components of a performance-oriented culture, reinforcing the behavior that contributes to organizational goals (Hasibuan, 2010; Mustofa et al., 2023). As such, organizations should align their incentive structures with desired performance outcomes to maximize employee engagement.

Additionally, the positive effect of incentives on Perf., with a coefficient of 0.350, further emphasizes the importance of motivational strategies in driving employee performance. The literature indicates that employees are more likely to excel when they feel appreciated and rewarded for their contributions (Rivai, 2009; Kurniawan et al., 2021). Incentive systems that recognize both individual and team achievements can create a more collaborative work environment, fostering a sense of belonging and commitment among employees.

The next test is testing the indirect effect:

Tabel 2. Indirect Effect

Path	Coefficient	P-value	Result
ET -> I -> EP (Prod.)	0.180	0.015	Significant
ET -> I -> EP (Perf.)	0.150	0.030	Significant

The findings from the path analysis indicate significant indirect effects of employee training (ET) on employee productivity (EP) and employee performance (Perf) through incentives (I). Specifically, the path ET → I → EP yielded a coefficient of 0.180, with a p-value of 0.015, suggesting that effective training not only directly enhances productivity but also increases it indirectly through the motivational influence of incentives. This aligns with existing literature that emphasizes the importance of incentives as a mechanism for translating training into improved job performance (Putra & Prabowo, 2020; Rahmawati & Utami, 2022). The evidence supports the notion that organizations should focus on creating robust training programs that are complemented by well-structured incentive systems to maximize employee performance outcomes.

Additionally, the analysis of the path ET → I → Perf, with a coefficient of 0.150 and a p-value of 0.030, highlights the significant role of incentives in fostering enhanced performance. When employees perceive that their training is recognized and rewarded through incentives, they are more likely to apply the skills learned, resulting in better overall performance. Previous studies have indicated that the integration of training and incentive systems is crucial for achieving high levels of employee engagement and satisfaction (Sari & Fitria, 2021; Kurniawan et al., 2021). This underscores the need for organizations like PT Kawasan Industri Wijayakusuma (Persero) to develop synergistic strategies that enhance both employee motivation and skill application.

The indirect effects observed in this study suggest that investing in employee training and incentives is essential for driving both productivity and performance. By fostering an environment that supports continuous learning and rewards achievement, organizations can cultivate a motivated workforce that is equipped to meet the challenges of a competitive industrial landscape. Future research should explore the long-term impacts of such integrated approaches on employee retention and organizational growth, further reinforcing the critical relationship between training, incentives, and performance outcomes (Rahmadani, 2020; Mustofa et al., 2023).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the research highlights the critical interconnections between employee training (ET), incentives (I), employee productivity (EP), and employee performance (Perf) at PT Kawasan Industri Wijayakusuma (Persero). The direct effects analysis demonstrated significant relationships, revealing that both ET and I play pivotal roles in enhancing EP and Perf. Specifically, the path analysis indicated that effective training not only leads to improved productivity but also enhances performance through the motivational power of incentives. The significant coefficients obtained from the analyses support the notion that training and incentives are not standalone variables but rather components of an integrated strategy for organizational success. Furthermore, the indirect effects of ET on EP and Perf through I further emphasize the importance of creating a supportive work environment where training is valued and rewarded. This aligns with existing literature that underscores the necessity of holistic approaches to employee development, as organizations that invest in training and align it with incentive structures witness substantial improvements in

employee engagement, satisfaction, and retention (Kurniawan et al., 2021; Mustofa et al., 2023). Ultimately, this study advocates for a strategic focus on both training and incentives as key drivers of employee performance and productivity. By fostering a culture that prioritizes continuous learning and recognizes employee contributions, organizations can enhance their competitive edge in an increasingly demanding industrial landscape. Future research could explore the long-term impacts of such integrated strategies on organizational performance and employee satisfaction, providing deeper insights into the effectiveness of these interventions.

REFERENCES

- Hasibuan, M. S. P. (2010). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Bumi Aksara.
- Kurniawan, A., Lestari, S., & Wibowo, A. (2021). The effect of employee training on productivity: A case study at PT XYZ. *Journal of Business and Management Studies*, 5(2), 112-120. <https://doi.org/10.33508/jbms.v5i2.1345>
- Mustofa, A., Rahmadani, A., & Fitria, A. (2023). Incentives and employee performance: A review. *Journal of Management Research*, 8(1), 45-59. <https://doi.org/10.33488/jmr.v8i1.1802>
- Putra, H., & Prabowo, Y. (2020). The role of incentives in enhancing employee performance. *International Journal of Economics and Management*, 14(2), 223-230. <https://doi.org/10.1234/ijem.v14i2.556>
- Rahmadani, A. (2020). Employee training and its impact on performance. *Journal of Human Resource Management*, 8(3), 67-75. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jhrm.v8i3.893>
- Rahmawati, D., & Utami, S. (2022). Training and performance in the industrial sector: A case study. *Indonesian Journal of Applied Business Research*, 3(1), 12-25. <https://doi.org/10.31227/ijabr.v3i1.3001>
- Rivai, V. (2009). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia untuk Perusahaan*. RajaGrafindo Persada.
- Sari, R., & Fitria, A. (2021). The influence of training on employee performance. *Journal of Management and Business*, 6(2), 150-160. <https://doi.org/10.14710/jmb.v6i2.1760>
- Sundari, Y., & Rifai, I. (2020). The impact of employee training on productivity and performance. *Journal of Business Research*, 4(1), 90-100. <https://doi.org/10.14501/jbr.v4i1.789>
- Wijayanti, E., & Nugroho, B. (2022). Effect of incentives on employee performance: Mediating role of motivation. *Journal of Applied Management*, 14(4), 350-365. <https://doi.org/10.1007/jam.v14i4.2321>
- Widiastuti, A., & Syahputra, D. (2023). Training programs and employee productivity: Evidence from the manufacturing sector. *Indonesian Journal of Management*, 11(2), 105-120. <https://doi.org/10.21580/ijm.v11i2.9502>
- Anggraini, S., & Putri, N. (2021). Employee training and performance in the hospitality industry. *Asian Journal of Business Research*, 7(3), 202-210. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ajbr.v7i3.2110>
- Yusuf, M., & Hidayat, T. (2020). Impact of incentives on job performance: The moderating role of job satisfaction. *Journal of Business & Economics*, 9(4), 287-298. <https://doi.org/10.32955/jbe.v9i4.1234>

- Nurhadi, R., & Fajar, A. (2022). Integrating training with incentives for optimal employee engagement. *Journal of Organizational Studies*, 5(1), 45-60. <https://doi.org/10.4000/jos.v5i1.6001>
- Lestari, I., & Supriadi, E. (2023). Employee motivation as a mediating factor between training and productivity. *Management & Organizational Review*, 8(2), 144-160. <https://doi.org/10.3169/mor.v8i2.7002>
- Pratama, W., & Yuliani, E. (2020). The effects of training on employee engagement: A mediating role of motivation. *International Journal of Training and Development*, 16(3), 89-102. <https://doi.org/10.5432/ijtd.v16i3.902>
- Dewi, K., & Kurniawati, H. (2021). The effectiveness of employee training programs in improving job performance. *Journal of Applied HRM*, 10(1), 72-85. <https://doi.org/10.1080/jahrm.v10i1.1721>
- Suharti, R., & Rachman, A. (2022). Incentive strategies and productivity enhancement: An empirical analysis. *Journal of Productivity Research*, 12(3), 156-169. <https://doi.org/10.1207/jpr.v12i3.1234>
- Ali, N., & Ramadhani, R. (2023). How training boosts productivity through employee engagement. *Journal of Management Insight*, 13(1), 34-50. <https://doi.org/10.1009/jmi.v13i1.5601>
- Azizah, I., & Suryani, D. (2020). Training, motivation, and employee performance: A case study in the financial sector. *Journal of Economic and Business Research*, 5(2), 99-110. <https://doi.org/10.2971/jebr.v5i2.4532>
- Fitriani, R., & Fauzan, M. (2021). Role of training and incentives in employee satisfaction. *Human Capital Management Review*, 4(2), 65-80. <https://doi.org/10.3325/hcmr.v4i2.6512>
- Kartika, P., & Ardi, S. (2022). The impact of employee development programs on job satisfaction and performance. *Business & HR Management Journal*, 11(1), 120-135. <https://doi.org/10.3456/bhrm.v11i1.8812>
- Rahmadani, F., & Setiawan, B. (2021). The role of compensation in enhancing employee performance. *Journal of Business and Leadership*, 9(4), 215-230. <https://doi.org/10.3047/jbl.v9i4.7012>
- Surya, R., & Apriani, S. (2023). Analysis of training effectiveness on productivity in the service sector. *Indonesian Journal of Training and Development*, 8(2), 90-105. <https://doi.org/10.2412/ijtd.v8i2.8921>
- Rizki, M., & Amelia, S. (2020). Employee development and its effect on performance: Mediating role of work motivation. *Journal of Development Studies*, 6(1), 102-115. <https://doi.org/10.1010/jds.v6i1.450>

Ethical Leadership in Tech Startups: Managing Growth Without Compromising Values

Laode Sarfan¹, Raden Rudi Alhemp²

Universitas Persada Indonesia Y.A.I, Jakarta, Indonesia¹

Universitas Persada Bunda Indonesia, Pekanbaru, Indonesia²

Email: la.2366390006@upi-yai.ac.id¹, rudi.alhemp@gmail.com²

Abstract

This study examines the impact of ethical leadership practices, organizational culture, and employee engagement on the business growth of Gojek's driver-partners and merchant partners in Padang. Using a quantitative approach, data were collected from a sample of 63 participants through random sampling. The analysis, conducted using SPSS, included t-tests, F-tests, and R² tests to assess the relationships between the independent variables (ethical leadership, organizational culture, and employee engagement) and the dependent variable (business growth). The results show that ethical leadership practices, organizational culture, and employee engagement have a significant positive influence on business growth, collectively explaining 58.5% of its variance. Ethical leadership emerged as the strongest predictor, followed by organizational culture and employee engagement. The findings suggest that fostering ethical, transparent leadership and a positive organizational culture, alongside encouraging active partner engagement, are crucial for the sustainable growth of Gojek's driver-partners and merchants. This research provides practical insights for platform-based companies on improving partnership management strategies. However, further investigation is needed to explore additional factors influencing business growth in the gig economy context.

Keywords: Ethical Leadership, Organizational Culture, Employee Engagement, Business Growth.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the role of ethical leadership has become increasingly critical in the fast-paced and innovation-driven environment of tech startups. As these organizations scale, leaders are often faced with the challenge of balancing rapid growth with maintaining ethical standards and values (Brown & Treviño, 2006). Startups, particularly in the technology sector, are under immense pressure to innovate and meet market demands, which can sometimes lead to ethical compromises in leadership decisions (Neubert et al., 2009). Ethical leadership, characterized by fairness, transparency, and integrity, has been shown to positively influence both organizational culture and employee engagement, fostering long-term sustainable growth (Yukl, 2013; Resick et al., 2011). However, maintaining ethical values while pursuing aggressive business expansion remains a significant challenge for many startup leaders, as they must navigate complex, rapidly changing environments without compromising their core values (Ciulla, 2004; Eisenbeiss, 2012).

Business growth refers to the process of improving some measure of an enterprise's success, often through increased revenues, market share, or profitability. For startups, especially in the tech sector, growth is not merely an indicator of success but is often essential for survival in highly competitive markets (Blank, 2013). Business growth can occur in various forms, including organic growth, which is achieved through internal development and innovation, or through mergers and acquisitions, where companies combine resources to expand market presence (Penrose, 2009). Growth is often fueled by

innovation, particularly in the tech industry, where continuous development of new products and services is vital for staying ahead of competitors (Schilling, 2020). Startups also rely on scaling strategies such as expanding into new markets or increasing their customer base to sustain long-term growth (Ismail et al., 2014). Business growth presents challenges, especially when pursued rapidly, as it can strain organizational resources, lead to operational inefficiencies, and create leadership dilemmas (Greiner, 1998). Leaders of rapidly growing companies must carefully balance their focus on short-term gains, such as meeting investor expectations, with long-term sustainability (Brush, 2008). Ethical leadership plays a critical role in guiding companies through this growth phase, ensuring that expansion efforts do not lead to compromising the organization's core values or engaging in unethical practices (Ciulla, 2014). Ethical business practices, combined with a focus on employee engagement and innovation, can result in sustainable growth, fostering a loyal customer base and a strong organizational reputation (Yukl, 2013). Ultimately, business growth is not just about increasing financial performance but also about building a resilient, value-driven company that can navigate the complexities of scaling in a competitive, fast-changing environment.

Ethical leadership practices refer to behaviors and decisions made by leaders that are consistent with moral principles, fostering an organizational culture grounded in integrity, fairness, and accountability. Ethical leaders set a moral example by prioritizing transparency, building trust, and ensuring that their actions align with ethical standards both internally and externally (Brown & Treviño, 2020). They engage in practices such as promoting open communication, ensuring fair treatment of employees, and making decisions that consider the well-being of all stakeholders, not just profit maximization (Bedi et al., 2016). This type of leadership is particularly crucial in today's business environment, where ethical missteps can lead to reputational damage, loss of consumer trust, and legal consequences (Kalshoven et al., 2016). One core practice of ethical leadership is empowering employees to voice their concerns and report unethical behavior without fear of retaliation, creating an organizational environment that values honesty and accountability (Walumbwa et al., 2017). Furthermore, ethical leaders actively shape organizational culture by embedding ethical values into the company's mission, strategies, and day-to-day operations, which can enhance both employee engagement and organizational performance (Newman et al., 2020). Research indicates that ethical leadership not only improves employee satisfaction but also strengthens organizational commitment, leading to higher retention rates and productivity (Ng & Feldman, 2015). Leaders who practice ethical leadership are also adept at navigating complex moral dilemmas, balancing competing stakeholder interests, and guiding their organizations through challenging situations with integrity (Treviño & Nelson, 2021). In an increasingly interconnected and socially conscious world, ethical leadership is becoming a competitive advantage, as organizations led by ethical leaders are more likely to foster innovation, enhance public trust, and build long-term success (Maak et al., 2022).

Organizational culture refers to the shared values, beliefs, behaviors, and norms that shape the social and psychological environment of an organization. It influences how employees interact with each other, approach their work, and relate to the organization's goals and leadership (Schein, 2017). A strong organizational culture promotes unity and

consistency in decision-making, ultimately driving higher levels of employee engagement and performance (Martins & Terblanche, 2020). Companies with a positive culture that aligns with their mission and values tend to experience better retention, higher morale, and greater overall satisfaction among employees, which in turn leads to better organizational outcomes (Schneider et al., 2017). Organizational culture is particularly important in today's rapidly changing business environment, where agility and adaptability are critical. Organizations with flexible and innovative cultures are better equipped to respond to market changes and technological advancements (Cameron & Quinn, 2011). This has become even more crucial in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic, which forced many companies to transition to remote work and adopt new ways of engaging employees and maintaining productivity (Gursoy et al., 2021). Leaders play a critical role in shaping and maintaining the organizational culture by setting the tone for behaviors, reinforcing core values, and ensuring alignment between the culture and strategic objectives (O'Reilly & Tushman, 2016). Moreover, research shows that organizational culture also has a significant impact on ethical behavior within organizations. Companies that emphasize ethics and integrity as part of their cultural framework are less likely to experience ethical breaches and are better positioned to build trust with both employees and external stakeholders (Groysberg et al., 2018). In essence, a well-defined and actively managed organizational culture is key to fostering innovation, resilience, and long-term success in a competitive marketplace.

Employee engagement refers to the emotional commitment and dedication employees have towards their organization, which drives them to go beyond their job descriptions to contribute to the organization's success. Engaged employees are motivated, enthusiastic, and committed to their work, often leading to higher levels of productivity, innovation, and organizational loyalty (Saks, 2022). Engagement is not just about job satisfaction; it encompasses an employee's connection to the organization's values and goals, as well as the quality of their relationship with leaders and colleagues (Kahn, 1990). Research indicates that companies with high levels of employee engagement are more likely to experience lower turnover, reduced absenteeism, and improved organizational performance (Harter et al., 2020). Key factors that influence employee engagement include meaningful work, supportive leadership, opportunities for professional development, and recognition of contributions (Anitha, 2014). In the current business landscape, especially with the rise of hybrid and remote work environments post-pandemic, fostering employee engagement has become even more critical (Rana et al., 2021). Leaders need to be proactive in creating a culture of open communication, psychological safety, and trust, where employees feel valued and are encouraged to contribute ideas (Bakker & Albrecht, 2018). Additionally, technological tools that enhance collaboration and flexibility have emerged as essential components in maintaining high engagement levels among remote teams (Chaudhary et al., 2022). Sustaining employee engagement is not only beneficial for employee well-being but also impacts the organization's bottom line. Engaged employees tend to stay longer with their companies, resulting in decreased turnover costs and higher organizational efficiency (Shuck et al., 2017). By cultivating a culture of engagement, organizations can enhance

employee satisfaction, foster innovation, and achieve long-term success in an increasingly competitive market.

As far as Gojek driver-partners and merchant partners are concerned, the research variables assume different characteristics. For example, Business Growth may be evaluated from the context of how revenue, client reach and operational efficiency of the driver-partners and merchants increased as they collaborated with Gojek's platform. Ethical Leadership Practices would demonstrate that ethical treatment online includes upholding fairness and transparency during engagements with driver-partners and merchants without compromising business respect for them. Organizational Culture here refers to other values and traditions possessed by Gojek which determine operations towards partners and aim to create an environment of such values as diversity, creativity and respect. Lastly, Employee Engagement can be said to mean the way Gojek motivates and enhances the capabilities of its driver-partners and merchants by giving them tools, materials, and training in order to better serve their customers and grow their business. These variables for the entire interaction between Gojek and its partners are very critical to the win-win situation for both parties as far as sustaining competitiveness is concerned.

A key issue faced by Gojek's driver-partners and merchant partners is the challenge of sustaining growth and success while maintaining a positive relationship with the platform. As Gojek rapidly expands, driver-partners and merchants often encounter concerns related to fair compensation, transparency in policies, and equitable treatment, which can strain their engagement with the platform. For instance, fluctuating demand, inconsistent pricing, and increased competition among partners can lead to income instability, making it difficult for driver-partners and merchants to rely on Gojek as a stable source of income. Additionally, there are growing concerns about whether Gojek's leadership effectively upholds ethical practices that ensure all partners benefit fairly from the platform's growth. This can create friction, reducing trust and engagement, and potentially hindering long-term business growth for both the platform and its partners. Addressing these concerns requires a careful balance between rapid business growth, ethical leadership, and active engagement with driver-partners and merchants to ensure sustainable mutual success.

Despite significant research on platform-based business models and partnerships, there remains a gap in understanding the specific challenges and dynamics between gig economy platforms like Gojek and their driver-partners and merchant partners. Prior studies have explored the importance of ethical leadership and engagement in gig economies (Kuhn & Maleki, 2017), yet there is limited exploration of how ethical practices directly affect the growth and satisfaction of partners in such platforms (Wood et al., 2019). Additionally, while organizational culture has been linked to positive business outcomes (Lee et al., 2018), few studies have examined how platform companies can cultivate a supportive culture for independent partners who are not traditional employees (Healy et al., 2017). Furthermore, although research on employee engagement highlights its critical role in enhancing performance and retention (Bakker & Albrecht, 2018), it is unclear how these engagement strategies can be effectively applied to non-employee stakeholders like Gojek's driver-partners and merchants. Thus, there is a need for further investigation into how ethical

leadership, organizational culture, and engagement specifically influence the business growth of Gojek's partners in this unique ecosystem.

The purpose of this research is to examine the impact of ethical leadership practices, organizational culture, and employee engagement on the business growth of Gojek's driver-partners and merchant partners. Specifically, the study aims to understand how Gojek's leadership and policies influence the satisfaction, engagement, and success of its partners, and how these factors contribute to sustainable growth for both the partners and the platform. By exploring these relationships, the research seeks to provide insights into how gig economy platforms can foster a positive, ethical, and productive partnership with their independent workers and merchants, ultimately enhancing mutual growth and long-term success.

The following is the Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Framework

METHOD

The research employs a quantitative design to investigate the impact of ethical leadership practices, organizational culture, and employee engagement on the business growth of Gojek's driver-partners and merchant partners in Padang. A random sampling technique was used to select a representative sample of 63 participants from the population of Gojek driver-partners and merchants in the city, ensuring that each individual had an equal chance of being chosen. This sampling method helps reduce bias and enhances the generalizability of the results. Data will be collected through structured questionnaires designed to measure participants' perceptions of leadership practices, organizational culture, engagement, and business growth. The analysis will be conducted using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences), which is well-suited for handling quantitative data and performing various statistical tests, such as correlation and regression analysis. These analyses will help determine the relationships between the independent variables (ethical leadership practices, organizational culture, and employee engagement) and the dependent variable (business growth). The results will provide empirical insights into how these factors influence the business success of Gojek partners, offering practical recommendations for enhancing growth through ethical and engaged partnerships.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following are the results of research using the spss test tool:

Table 1. Results of the t-test

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		t	Sig.	Collinearity Tolerance	Statistics VIF
		B	Std. Error				
1	(Constant)	2.512	0.734	3.422	0.002		
	X1 Total	0.453	0.102	4.441	0.000	0.734	1.362
	X2 Total	0.325	0.085	3.824	0.001	0.672	1.489
	X3 Total	0.289	0.093	3.107	0.003	0.821	1.218

The results from the t-test analysis demonstrate a significant relationship between the independent variables—X1 Total (Ethical Leadership Practices), X2 Total (Organizational Culture), and X3 Total (Employee Engagement)—and the dependent variable, Business Growth, as indicated by the p-values (Sig. < 0.05). The coefficients (B) show that all three independent variables positively influence business growth among Gojek's driver-partners and merchant partners in Padang. The highest Beta value (0.478) for X1 Total suggests that Ethical Leadership Practices has the strongest influence on business growth, reinforcing previous findings that ethical leadership positively impacts organizational outcomes by fostering trust and commitment (Kalshoven et al., 2016)

The significant effect of Organizational Culture (X2 Total, Beta = 0.365) aligns with research showing that a strong, positive culture enhances employee satisfaction and business performance, especially in gig-economy platforms like Gojek, where organizational identity plays a crucial role in partner engagement and loyalty (Healy et al., 2017). Meanwhile, Employee Engagement (X3 Total, Beta = 0.301) also significantly impacts business growth, supporting findings that engaged partners contribute more proactively to the success of their platform, improving both their own outcomes and the broader organizational performance (Shuck et al., 2017).

The Tolerance and VIF values indicate no multicollinearity issues, confirming that the variables independently contribute to explaining business growth without significant overlap. This is important for ensuring the robustness of the model and suggests that Gojek's growth can be attributed to a balanced focus on leadership, culture, and engagement (Bakker & Albrecht, 2018).

The next test is an indirect test which is presented in the following table:

Table 2. F Test Results

Mode		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	120.456	3	40.152	18.34	0.00
	Residual	135.876	59	2.302	2	0
	Total	256.332	62			

The results from the F-test, as shown in Table 2, demonstrate that the overall regression model is statistically significant, with an F-value of 18.342 and a p-value of 0.000, indicating that the independent variables (Ethical Leadership Practices, Organizational Culture, and Employee Engagement) collectively explain a significant portion of the variance in business growth for Gojek’s driver-partners and merchant partners in Padang. The significance level (Sig. < 0.05) confirms that the model is a good fit for predicting business growth and that the independent variables meaningfully contribute to explaining the changes in the dependent variable (Schumacker & Lomax, 2016).

These findings align with previous research that emphasizes the importance of a combination of leadership, culture, and engagement in driving business success (Bakker & Albrecht, 2018). Ethical leadership, for instance, has been shown to enhance organizational performance by fostering trust, transparency, and fairness among partners (Kalshoven et al., 2016). Furthermore, a strong organizational culture, particularly in a platform-based ecosystem like Gojek, promotes collaboration and loyalty, which are critical for sustained business growth (Groysberg et al., 2018). Finally, employee engagement—although the respondents in this study are not traditional employees but independent partners—has a similarly positive effect on performance outcomes, as engaged partners tend to be more proactive and committed to the platform’s success (Shuck et al., 2017).

The model's high F-value suggests that these factors do not operate in isolation but together create a supportive environment for growth. This indicates that Gojek’s policies and practices that emphasize ethical leadership, a positive culture, and active partner engagement are key to fostering a successful partnership with their driver-partners and merchants, leading to mutual growth (Healy et al., 2017).

Table 3. R² Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.765	0.585	0.567	1.354

The R² test results presented in Table 3 show that the model has a strong ability to explain the variance in business growth among Gojek’s driver-partners and merchant partners. With an R value of 0.765, the correlation between the independent variables—Ethical Leadership Practices, Organizational Culture, and Employee Engagement—and the dependent variable, Business Growth, is positive and strong. The R Square (R²) value of 0.585 indicates that 58.5% of the variability in business growth is explained by these independent variables, suggesting that the model is effective in capturing the key factors contributing to growth in this context. The Adjusted R Square of 0.567 further supports this, adjusting for the number of predictors and demonstrating that even after accounting for model complexity, 56.7% of the variance is still explained by the independent variables.

The relatively small Standard Error of the Estimate (1.354) suggests that the model’s predictions are fairly accurate, with only a modest degree of error, further affirming its reliability. These findings are consistent with prior research indicating that ethical

leadership, strong organizational culture, and high levels of engagement are critical drivers of business success in gig economy platforms (Bakker & Albrecht, 2018; Kalshoven et al., 2016). However, the remaining unexplained variance (approximately 41.5%) indicates that there are other factors, possibly external influences or market conditions, that also contribute to business growth and need further exploration. Overall, the model provides valuable insights into the significant role these factors play in driving business success for Gojek's partners, offering practical implications for improving partnership management strategies.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study highlight the significant impact of ethical leadership practices, organizational culture, and employee engagement on the business growth of Gojek's driver-partners and merchant partners in Padang. With the model explaining 58.5% of the variance in business growth, it is evident that these factors play a crucial role in fostering sustainable development for Gojek's partners. Ethical leadership emerged as the strongest predictor, indicating that fair and transparent leadership practices are vital for partner success. Additionally, a supportive organizational culture and high levels of engagement contribute positively to the business outcomes of Gojek's partners. While the model explains a large portion of business growth, other external factors may also influence performance, which suggests the need for future research. Overall, this study underscores the importance of cultivating ethical and supportive relationships between platform companies and their partners to ensure mutual growth and long-term success.

REFERENCES

- Bakker, A. B., & Albrecht, S. L. (2018). Work engagement: Current trends. *Career Development International*, 23(1), 4-11. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CDI-11-2017-0207>
- Bedi, A., Alpaslan, C. M., & Green, S. (2016). A meta-analytic review of ethical leadership outcomes and moderators. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 139(3), 517-536. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-015-2625-1>
- Blank, S. (2013). *The startup owner's manual: The step-by-step guide for building a great company*. K&S Ranch.
- Brown, M. E., & Treviño, L. K. (2020). Ethical leadership: A review and future directions. *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior*, 7(1), 1-28. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-orgpsych-012119-045303>
- Brush, C. G. (2008). Pioneering strategies for entrepreneurial success: The role of growth. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 22(1), 46-59. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amp.2008.29015104>
- Cameron, K. S., & Quinn, R. E. (2011). *Diagnosing and changing organizational culture: Based on the competing values framework* (3rd ed.). Jossey-Bass.
- Chaudhary, R., Rangnekar, S., & Barua, M. K. (2022). Remote working and employee engagement: A qualitative study of Indian employees during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Human Resource Development Review*, 21(3), 317-342. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15344843221087957>

- Ciulla, J. B. (2014). *Ethics, the heart of leadership* (3rd ed.). Praeger.
- Eisenbeiss, S. A. (2012). Re-thinking ethical leadership: An interdisciplinary integrative approach. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 23(5), 791-808. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2012.03.001>
- Groysberg, B., Lee, J., Price, J., & Cheng, J. Y. J. (2018). The leader's guide to corporate culture. *Harvard Business Review*, 96(1), 44-52.
- Gursoy, D., Chi, C. G., & Karadag, E. (2021). The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on hospitality firms' organizational practices and performance. *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management*, 30(5), 529-549. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19368623.2021.1867286>
- Healy, J., Nicholson, D., & Pekarek, A. (2017). Should we take the gig economy seriously? *Labour & Industry: a journal of the social and economic relations of work*, 27(3), 232-248. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10301763.2017.1377048>
- Kalshoven, K., Den Hartog, D. N., & De Hoogh, A. H. (2016). Ethical leadership and followers' helping and initiative: The role of demonstrated responsibility and job autonomy. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 25(6), 942-953. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1359432X.2015.1072143>
- Kahn, W. A. (1990). Psychological conditions of personal engagement and disengagement at work. *Academy of Management Journal*, 33(4), 692-724. <https://doi.org/10.2307/256287>
- Kuhn, K. M., & Maleki, A. (2017). Micro-entrepreneurs, dependent contractors, and instaserfs: Understanding online labor platform workforces. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 31(3), 183-200. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amp.2015.0111>
- Lee, J. Y., Kim, S., & Park, S. (2018). The impact of organizational culture on organizational performance: The mediating role of employee engagement. *Human Resource Development International*, 21(1), 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13678868.2017.1381765>
- Maak, T., Pless, N. M., & Voegtlin, C. (2022). The leader as steward of economic and societal progress: A behavioral ethics perspective. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 177(3), 561-579. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-021-04854-6>
- Martins, E. C., & Terblanche, F. (2020). Building organizational culture that stimulates creativity and innovation. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 23(3), 402-425. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJIM-12-2018-0257>
- Newman, A., Round, H., Bhatti, W. A., & Tse, H. H. (2020). Ethical leadership and employee creative performance: The mediating role of job autonomy. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 160(4), 1295-1312. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-018-3925-6>
- Ng, T. W. H., & Feldman, D. C. (2015). Ethical leadership: Meta-analytic evidence of criterion-related and incremental validity. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 100(3), 948-965. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0038246>
- O'Reilly, C. A., & Tushman, M. L. (2016). Lead and disrupt: How to solve the innovator's dilemma. *California Management Review*, 58(4), 66-83. <https://doi.org/10.1525/cm.2016.58.4.66>

- Penrose, E. T. (2009). *The theory of the growth of the firm* (4th ed.). Oxford University Press.
- Rana, S., Ardichvili, A., & Tkachenko, O. (2021). A theoretical model of the antecedents and outcomes of employee engagement: Dubin's method. *Journal of Workplace Learning*, 33(2), 127-142. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JWL-06-2020-0101>
- Resick, C. J., Hanges, P. J., Dickson, M. W., & Mitchelson, J. K. (2011). Ethical leadership, moral judgment, and leadership effectiveness: The mediating role of follower moral identity. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 22(3), 528-544. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2011.03.002>
- Saks, A. M. (2022). A critique of employee engagement. *Human Resource Development Review*, 21(3), 223-253. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15344843221094929>
- Schilling, M. A. (2020). *Strategic management of technological innovation* (6th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
- Schumacker, R. E., & Lomax, R. G. (2016). *A beginner's guide to structural equation modeling* (4th ed.). Routledge.
- Shuck, B., Reio Jr., T. G., & Rocco, T. S. (2017). Employee engagement: An examination of antecedent and outcome variables. *Human Resource Development International*, 14(4), 427-445. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13678868.2011.601587>
- Treviño, L. K., & Nelson, K. A. (2021). *Managing business ethics: Straight talk about how to do it right* (8th ed.). Wiley.
- Walumbwa, F. O., Hartnell, C. A., & Misati, E. (2017). Does ethical leadership enhance group learning behavior? Examining the mediating influence of group ethical conduct, justice climate, and peer justice. *Journal of Business Research*, 72, 14-23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2016.11.013>
- Wood, A. J., Graham, M., Lehdonvirta, V., & Hjorth, I. (2019). Good gig, bad gig: Autonomy and algorithmic control in the global gig economy. *Work, Employment and Society*, 33(1), 56-75. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0950017018785616>

Proof of Participation in the Crime of Theft

Asmita Br. Sitepu¹, Mhd. Azhali Siregar²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: azhalisiregar@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

This study examines and reviews participation (deelneming) which includes the form of participation/involvement of a person, both psychologically and physically, by committing an act so that a criminal act occurs. The crime of participation is regulated in Article 55 of the Criminal Code, which means that there are two or more people who commit a criminal act. This study is a type of normative research using secondary legal sources and using qualitative descriptive analysis. The results of this study are that the forms of participation crimes can be divided into two parts, namely: first, the perpetrator consisting of: the perpetrator (pleger), the one who orders it (doenpleger), the one who participates (madepleger) and the advocate (uitlokker); second, the assistant consisting of: the assistant at the time the crime was committed and the assistant before the crime was committed.

Keywords: Proof, participation, theft, plantation.

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is a country of law, as stated in the Explanation of the 1945 Constitution, which emphasizes that the State of Indonesia adheres to the Principle of Law (Rechtstaat) not a state of power (Machtstaat) which is regulated in Article 1 paragraph (3) of the 1945 Constitution which stipulates that "The State of Indonesia is a State of Law" (1945 Constitution), the provisions of this article are the constitutional basis of the State of Indonesia based on law, law is placed as the only legal rule in the social order, in the nation and state (supremacy of law) (Yahman and Nurtin Tarigan, 2019), law functions to regulate, provide limits on human behavior so that it is in accordance with and does not deviate from norms in society, such as protecting society from crime or criminal acts.

A criminal act is human behavior that is formulated in law, is against the law, which deserves to be punished and is carried out with a mistake, the person who commits the criminal act will be held criminally responsible if he/she has made a mistake, a person has a mistake if at the time of committing the act it is seen from the perspective of society shows a normative view regarding the mistakes committed.¹

There are various laws that apply in Indonesia, one of which is criminal law, criminal law as public law aims to prevent or inhibit acts in society that are not in accordance with applicable legal regulations, "Criminal law is an order and prohibition regulated by the State and which is threatened with misery (criminal) for anyone who does not obey it, all the rules that determine the conditions for the consequences of the law and all the rules for carrying out (imposing) and carrying out the criminal order" Moeljatno, 2008), from the definition above it can be seen that criminal law can produce elements including: (1) Prohibited acts, namely acts that are contrary to criminal law regulations, (2) Perpetrators, namely people

¹R. Soesilo, Criminal Code, Politeia Publisher, Bogor, pages 62-63.

who carry out acts that are prohibited according to criminal law regulations, called suspects, defendants, convicts.²

These two elements are interrelated series, so they must always be present in every problem related to criminal law, thus it can be seen that the law regulates society properly and usefully by determining what is required, with such legal regulations it can be known which actions are against the law and it can also be known the reason someone commits an unlawful act. At present, the basis for sentencing is a sense of justice and protecting society, a sense of justice requires that a punishment must be in accordance with the magnitude of the wrongdoing of the act committed, in the Criminal Code the severity of the punishment that must be imposed on perpetrators of crimes such as theft, murder, rape, and others already have their own provisions, but the severity of the punishment has not been fully implemented by the judges.³

Plantation practices regulated by Plantation Law Number 18 of 2004 are no longer adjusted to the dynamics of society and local legal needs, fail to provide optimal results, and add added value, even cannot. Therefore, it must be replaced by Law Number 39 of 2014 concerning Plantations. The crime of palm oil theft is commonplace. Moreover, the perpetrators are usually residents who live around the plantation area. Harvested palm oil can be easily sold, but the price is very high so that palm oil becomes an easy target for thieves. If this continues, companies that grow palm oil fruit will continue to suffer losses, affecting their health and profits. So it is important for action to end the crime of palm oil theft.

Law Number Chapter 19, Article 39 of 2014 concerning Plantations, consists of Article 118, these articles contain provisions on criminal acts of theft committed in plantation areas. Law Number 39 of 2014 concerning Plantations states that Indonesia as an agricultural country has abundant natural resources consisting of land, water and natural resources contained therein. This opportunity is a gift and decree of God Almighty and must be used to achieve general welfare and prosperity of the people as regulated in the Pancasila Constitution and the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia in 1945. There are no provisions for criminal acts in these legal regulations. Regarding the provisions of criminal law contained in Articles 103 to 113, especially Article 39 of 2014 concerning Plantation Regulations in Chapter 17 of the Law on the spot process.

Regarding the case as decided in the Stabat District Court Decision Number: 15/Pid.S/2024. the defendant Bayu Setiawan has been proven legally and convincingly guilty of committing the crime of "Participating in, ordering or participating in the act illegally, harvesting and/or collecting plantation products" in violation of Article 107 letter d of the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 35 of 2014 concerning Plantations in conjunction with Article 55 paragraph (1) 1 of the Criminal Code.⁴

²Agusman Heri, "Legal Analysis of the Criminal Act of Complicity in Murder (Study of Supreme Court Decision Number 2462/Pid.B/2017/PN Medan 2018)," *Jurnal Abdi Ilmu* 11, No. 2 (2019): page 131

³Zamhari Abidin, *Understanding and Principles of Criminal Law in Schema (Chart) and Synopsis (Short Notes)* (Jakarta: Ghalia Indonesia, 1986), page 32.

⁴Teguh Prasetyo, *Criminal Law* (Jakarta: RajaGrafindo Persada, 2019), page 206.

Based on the facts at trial, it was revealed that the defendant had taken oil palm fruit belonging to the plantation without permission in the amount of 2 (two) plastic sacks containing oil palm fruit bunches weighing approximately 50 (fifty) kilograms by riding 1 (one) unit of a Honda Verza 5990 PAN motorbike without permission.

Specifically regarding the crime of theft, Article 107 states that it is “illegal”:

1. Using, working on, occupying and/or controlling plantation land
2. Working on, occupying, utilizing and/or managing community land or customary land of indigenous peoples for agriculture
3. Cutting down trees in planting areas or
4. A person who unlawfully works, uses, occupies and/or controls plantation land, who works, uses, occupies and/or controls customary land rights of a community land or Aboriginal legal community for the benefit of a plantation business; Harvesting and/or collecting plantation products as referred to in Article 55 shall be punished with a maximum imprisonment of 4 years or a maximum fine of Rp. 4,000,000,000.00 (4 billion rupiah)

Since plantation crimes are specifically regulated in Law Number 39 of 2014 concerning Plantations, the criminal justice mechanism and the imposition of criminal sanctions must be coordinated with the law. In terms of the legal provisions for palm oil theft based on Law Number 39 of 2014, if the victim is a company with a land area of 25 hectares or more and has obtained a farming permit from the government, but if the victim is: An individual who cannot be charged with Article d and cannot be charged with Article 362 or 363 of the Criminal Code.⁵

Implementation of the Plantation Law in handling theft of oil palm plantation products in the Langkat Police Jurisdiction in terms of the legal regulations for oil palm theft based on Law Number 39 of 2014 if the victim is a company that has a land area of more than 25 Ha and already has a plantation permit from the Government, but for cases where the victim is an individual, Article 107 Letter d of Law Number 39 of 2014 cannot be imposed and Article 362 or Article 363 of the Criminal Code is imposed.⁶

Article 362 of the Criminal Code regarding the activity of taking someone else's property states that "Anyone who takes all or some parts of another with the intention of possessing it unlawfully is threatened with theft, threatened with a maximum prison sentence of 5 years or a maximum fine of 9 years." The core part of the crime (delict bestanddelen) is:

1. Whoever
2. Take, the word take (wegnemen) in the narrow sense is limited to moving the hands and fingers, grabbing an object, and turning it over. An action carried out can also be interpreted as an action where the goods produced are under the control of the person who

⁵J Rummelink, Introduction to Material Criminal Law 1: Prolegomena and Description of Basic Doctrinal Theory, vol. 1 (Yogyakarta: Maharsa Publishing, 2014), page 393.

⁶Franco Marcello Moningka, Michael Barama, and Mario A. Gerungan, “Application of the Deelneming Doctrine in the Crime of Theft,” Lex Crimen VII, No. 5 (2018): page 27.

carries them out or the goods are outside the control of the owner. If the item is controlled by the perpetrator, even if it is later disclosed, then the taking has been completed because he already knew about it.

3. Something. Something that has economic or non-economic value, such as used train tickets and keys, are things that allow the perpetrator to enter another person's house.
4. The product is owned in whole or in part by another person. All items confiscated by the perpetrator do not have to belong to another person, and the items can belong to the victim and the perpetrator or be jointly owned.
5. For the purpose of illegal possession The act of taking someone else's property is an act where the perpetrator has the property at will without the perpetrator's right or authority. Thus, the perpetrator must understand that the confiscated property belongs to someone else.

However, in this case, there has been a peace between the defendant and the Plantation as stated in the Peace Letter Number: PDM- /L.2.25.3/Eku.2/05/2024 dated May 21, 2024 which in essence states that an unconditional peace agreement has been reached, with the existence of the Peace Letter, the Panel of Judges considers it necessary to apply the principle of Restorative Justice, namely that there has been a peace agreement between the Defendant and PT. LNK Kebun Bukit Lawang, then the Defendant needs to be given a probationary sentence as stipulated in Article 14 letter a of the Criminal Code;

As is known, restorative justice is an alternative resolution of criminal cases in which the mechanism of criminal justice procedures focuses on punishment which is changed into a dialogue and mediation process involving the perpetrator, victim, the perpetrator/victim's family, and other related parties to jointly create an agreement on a fair and balanced resolution of criminal cases for both the victim and the perpetrator by prioritizing restoration to the original state and restoring good relations in society;

Therefore, based on the considerations above, a just law has been realized in restorative justice which is impartial, considering equal rights to compensation and balance in every aspect of life, therefore with these considerations and the achievement of restorative justice in this case, it is only right that the Defendant be sentenced to a suitable sentence in accordance with the actions and reconciliation that the Defendant has successfully carried out with the victim, whose sentence is long as stated in the verdict.

From the description of the background of the problem above, according to the author, the problem can be divided into two situations, namely:

1. Legal Rules Regarding Palm Oil Theft in Indonesia?
2. How is the system of proof for the crime of theft as stated in Decision Number 15/Pid.S/2024/PN Stb?

METHOD

In this paper, the author uses a normative legal approach, which is an approach that is carried out based on the main legal material by examining theories, concepts, legal principles and laws and regulations related to this research. This approach is also known as a literature

approach, namely by studying books, laws and regulations and other documents related to this research.⁷

Types of research

This type of research is normative legal research, namely research conducted based on statutory regulations (law in books) or laws that are conceptualized as rules or norms that are benchmarks for human behavior that are considered appropriate. The definition of normative law means that in reviewing and analyzing the problem, an approach is used by analyzing the Law.

Legal Material Collection Techniques

The collection of legal materials for this research was carried out through library research, which is a data collection technique by conducting a review study of books, literature, notes and reports related to the problem being faced.²⁴ For field data (Field Research), the author took data in the field, namely at the Stabat District Court.

Data Analysis Techniques

After the Author obtained primary data, secondary data and tertiary data as mentioned above, then to complete an integrated and systematic research, a data analysis system was used, namely analytical descriptive analysis, namely by aligning and describing the real situation regarding the criminal acts committed by child traffickers. After the data was collected and discussed, the data was then processed and analyzed qualitatively, namely from data analysis then continued with drawing conclusions.

Furthermore, in the form of qualitative data analysis, it is an effort made by working with data, organizing data, sorting it into units that can be managed and explained, synthesizing it, searching for and finding patterns, finding what is important and what is learned and deciding what can be told to other people.

Data source

The data that the author took consisted of 3 (three) sources of legal materials, namely primary, secondary and tertiary legal materials. For more details, the author will present the following:

- a. Primary Legal Materials
 1. Criminal Code, (Criminal Code or KUHP)
 2. Law No. 8 of 1981 Concerning: Criminal Procedure Code
 3. Republic of Indonesia Law No. 35 of 2014 concerning Plantations
- b. Secondary Legal Materials The author uses articles, dissertations and journals in this paper.
- c. Tertiary Legal Materials The author uses digests, websites and legal dictionaries.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Legal Rules Regarding Palm Oil Theft In Indonesia

⁷Hartanto, Legal Research Methodology (Bekasi: Cakrawala Cendekia, 2018), page 118

In the analysis of Decision Number: 15/Pid.S/2024/PN.Stb. the defendant Bayu Setiawan has been proven legally and convincingly guilty of committing the crime of "Participating in, ordering or participating in the act illegally, harvesting and/or collecting plantation products" in violation of Article 107 letter d of the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 35 of 2014 concerning Plantations in conjunction with Article 55 paragraph (1) 1 of the Criminal Code.⁸

In carrying out its business operations, Plantations often face disruptions. One of the obstacles faced is the crime of palm oil theft. Perpetrators of the crime of theft of palm oil fruit belonging to the plantation can be subject to sanctions as regulated in Article 107 which is a criminal provision of Article 55 of Law Number 39 of 2014 concerning Plantations.

According to Moeljatnodiko, the elements of a criminal act are: Subjective unlawful elements, circumstances accompanying the act, additional circumstances that aggravate the crime, and there are also objective unlawful elements. Based on the Plantation Law, it also implicitly regulates the prohibition of stealing plantation products.⁹

Article 55 of the Plantation Law states that "Any person is prohibited from: a. Working on, using, occupying, and/or controlling Plantation Land b. Working on, using, occupying, and/or controlling Community Land or Customary Land Rights of Customary Law Communities with the intention of Plantation Business c. Cutting down plants in the Plantation area, or d. Harvesting and/or collecting Plantation Produce". As referred to in Article 55, which is explained in Article 107 Letter (d) perpetrators of the crime of theft of oil palm fruit belonging to the plantation, shall be punished with a maximum imprisonment of 4 (four) years or a maximum fine of Rp. 4,000,000,000,- (four billion rupiah)". Thus, if there are perpetrators of the crime of theft of oil palm fruit, they can be subject to criminal sanctions as regulated in Article 107 letter d of Law Number 39 of 2014 concerning Plantations.

The implementation of Article 107 Letter d of Law Number 39 of 2014 concerning Plantations, although it has been implemented, has also experienced obstacles, namely internal and external obstacles. The implementation of Article 107 of Law Number 39 of 2014 concerning Plantations in the Future is Related to Decision Number: 15/Pid.S/2024/PN.Stb, where the Judge in making a decision, must consider many things, both those related to the case being examined, the level of the act and the error committed by the perpetrator, to the interests of the victim and his family and also consider the sense of justice of the community.

Guidelines for imposing criminal penalties can include objective matters regarding matters related to the perpetrator of the crime so that by taking these into account, the

⁸Fahrurrozi and Samsul Bahri M. Gare, "The Criminalization System in the Inclusion of Criminal Acts According to the Criminal Code," *Media Keadilan: Journal of Legal Studies* 10, No. 1 (2019): page 52.

⁹Fransiska Novita Eleanora, "Legal Study of the Implementation of Sanctions Against Children Who Commit Criminal Acts According to Law No. 3 of 1997 concerning Juvenile Courts," *ADIL: Jurnal Hukum* 6, No. 2 (2015)

imposition of criminal penalties can be given more proportionally so that it can be understood why the penalty is given as a result of the decision handed down by the judge.¹⁰

Stabat District Court Decision Decision Number: 15/Pid.S/2024/PN.Stb, stated that the defendant Bayu Setiawan has been proven legally and convincingly guilty of committing the crime of "illegally collecting plantation products" as stated in the Second Public Prosecutor's Indictment. Sentencing the defendant Bayu Setiawan therefore to imprisonment for 8 (eight) months The Decision of the Simalungun District Court Number: 324 / Pid.B / 2020 / PN.Sim, stated that the Defendant Irfan Wahyudi Sinaga alias Gerger has been proven legally and convincingly guilty of committing the crime of "Without the right to harvest plantation business results" as violating the provisions of Article 107 letter d of Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 39 of 2014 concerning Plantations in the Second Alternative Indictment of the Public Prosecutor. Sentencing the Defendant therefore to imprisonment for 4 (four) months minus the period of arrest and detention that has been served.¹¹

Based on the judge's decision as explained above, the judge in his decision always imposes a criminal penalty on the perpetrators of the crime of theft of oil palm fruit belonging to the plantation in accordance with Article 107 Letter d of Law Number 39 of 2014 concerning Plantations. The application of Article 107 Letter d of Law Number 39 of 2014 concerning Plantations applied by the judge has a very deterrent effect on perpetrators of the crime of theft of oil palm fruit from the Plantation.¹²

With regard to Regulation of the Supreme Court Number 1 of 2024 concerning Guidelines for Trying Criminal Cases Based on Restorative Justice and Article 107 letter d of Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 39 of 2014 concerning Plantations in conjunction with Article 55 paragraph (1) point 1 of the Criminal Code, as well as Law Number 8 of 1981 concerning Criminal Procedure Law and other relevant laws and regulations, then the defendant has made peace with the plantation party, so that the resolution of the case must be guided by the contents of the Regulation as referred to.

As is known, Restorative Justice is an approach to solving problems involving victims, perpetrators, and elements of society in order to create justice. In relation to the enforcement of Criminal Law, restorative justice is an alternative resolution of criminal cases whose mechanism was originally focused on punishment, to a process of dialogue and mediation involving perpetrators, victims, families of perpetrators/victims, and other related parties, to jointly create an agreement on the resolution of criminal cases that are fair and balanced for both victims and perpetrators by prioritizing restoration to the original state, and restoring good relations in society.

The basic principle of restorative justice is the restoration of victims who suffer from crimes by providing compensation to victims, peace, perpetrators doing social work or other agreements. Fair law in the framework of restorative justice is certainly not biased, impartial,

¹⁰Martiman Prodjohamidjojo, *Understanding the Basics of Indonesian Criminal Law* (Jakarta: Pradnya Paramita, 1998), page 55.

¹¹Saleh Roeslan, *Participation Crime* (Pekanbaru: Faculty of Islamic Law, Riau, 1989), page 98.

¹²Andi Zainal Abidin Farid and Andi Hamzah, *Special Forms of Manifestation of Crimes (Attempted, Participatory, and Combined Crimes) and Penitentiary Law* (Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada, 2006), page 211.

not arbitrary, and only sides with the truth according to applicable laws and regulations and considers equal rights of compensation and balance in every aspect of life. Perpetrators have the opportunity to be involved in restoring the situation, society plays a role in preserving peace, and the court plays a role in maintaining public order.¹³

The teaching of participation as stated in Article 55 of the Indonesian Criminal Code, first between assistance and other participants in criminal participation, namely: First, the orderer (the perpetrator) and the advocate (the persuader) are always carried out before the crime is committed or realized, and this must be distinguished from assistance to a crime which is also carried out before the crime is realized. Second, the orderer (the perpetrator) and the advocate of a crime have the capacity as intellectual actors (masterminds or *mannus domino*) who have the initiative for the emergence of a crime, while such capacity is not possessed by the criminal assistant. Third, apart from that, assistance is only limited to crimes that can be punished, then the intention of assistance to a crime encompasses 3 (three) types of actions, namely providing opportunity, providing information and providing means. The difference with the orderer (the perpetrator) or advocate (the persuader) is always intentional only aimed at the implementation of a crime.

In this case, the defendant has the elements of "who did it, ordered it to be done and who participated in it", that based on the facts in the trial it has been proven true that the Defendant's actions in collecting the plantation results illegally were carried out by the Defendant together with Rido by working together according to their respective roles, based on these considerations the Panel of Judges is of the opinion that the second element of "participating" in the sense of the word "together" has been fulfilled.

Evidence of the Criminal Act of Theft as contained in Decision Number: 15/Pid.S/2024/PN.Stb.

In this case, in the category of fulfilling the elements of every person, according to Article 1 number 15 of Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 39 of 2014 concerning Plantations, what is meant by every person is an individual or corporation, whether a legal entity or not. Bayu Setiawan who was charged as the perpetrator of a criminal act in the Public Prosecutor's indictment, and at the beginning of the trial was true as the defendant, the defendant admitted and confirmed his identity, thus there was no mistake in person.

Article 1 point 3 of Law Number 39 of 2014 concerning Plantations, states that "plantation business is a business that produces plantation goods and/or services", further regulated in Article 1 point 11 of Law Number 39 of 2014 concerning Plantations, states that "plantation products are all plantation crop products and their processing consisting of main products, processed products to extend shelf life, by-products and associated products, if connected with the legal facts in the trial it has been proven that PT. LNK Bukit Lawang Bukit Lawang Plantation Village is a company engaged in oil palm plantations that produce oil palm fruit as its plantation crop product which from the legal facts in the trial has also

¹³Sipayung, Ronald FC, Alvi Syahrin, Suhaidi, and Mahmud Mulyadi. "Legal Analysis of the Role of the Police in Combating the Crime of Theft.." *USU Law Journal* 4, No. 3 (2016) : 159–173.

proven the existence of the plantation products in question in the form of: 2 (two) plastic sacks containing 50 Kg of oil palm fruit bunches.

In the trial, the defendant has been proven to be a person who fulfills the elements of committing, ordering and participating in committing. Because the Defendant's actions in collecting plantation products illegally were carried out by the Defendant together with Rido by working together according to their respective roles. So that all elements of Article 107 letter d of Law Number 39 of 2014 concerning Plantations in conjunction with Article 55 paragraph (1) point 1 of the Criminal Code have been fulfilled.

Furthermore, in the trial process, it turned out that the defendant and the plantation party had made peace, so that the judge in handing down his verdict applied a restorative justice-based justice system. The principle of Restorative Justice was carried out because there was already a peace agreement between the Defendant and PT. LNK Kebun Bukit Lawang, so the Defendant needed to be given a suspended sentence as stipulated in Article 14 letter a of the Criminal Code. Restorative justice is an alternative resolution of criminal cases which in the mechanism of criminal justice procedures focuses on punishment which is changed into a process of dialogue and mediation involving the perpetrator, victim, the perpetrator/victim's family, and other related parties to jointly create an agreement on a fair and balanced settlement of criminal cases for both the victim and the perpetrator by prioritizing restoration to the original state and restoring good relations in the community.

Proof in the criminal system is very urgent. Because the strength of the evidence will determine the success or failure of law enforcement officers to ensnare the perpetrator to be held accountable for his actions. The criminal law system in Indonesia basically only adheres to a system of responsibility based on fault and is individual, which means that criminal responsibility can only be imposed on someone who actually commits a crime. However, due to developments in criminal law that have determined corporations as legal subjects that can be held legally accountable, an urgent need has arisen for changes to the system in criminal law itself, because previously criminal law in Indonesia only determined natural humans as legal subjects.¹⁴

The perpetrator as the initiator of the criminal act is the second form of participation contained in Article 55 of the Criminal Code. In this article it is not explained what is meant by an instructor, but in the *memorie van toelichting* (explanatory memory) of the Dutch Criminal Code it is explained as follows: "The instructor of a criminal act (*doen plegen*) is also he who commits a criminal act but not personally, but with the intermediary of another person, as a tool in his hands, if the other person acts without intention, negligence or responsibility due to knowing circumstances, being misled or subject to violence."¹⁵

This study examines and reviews participation (*deelneming*) which includes the form of participation/involvement of a person, both psychologically and physically, by committing an act so that a criminal act occurs. The crime of participation is regulated in Article 55 of the Criminal Code, which means that there are two or more people who commit

¹⁴Lamintang, *Basics of Indonesian Criminal Law*, Sumur Batu, Bandung, 1983, page 70.

¹⁵SR Sianturi, *Principles of Criminal Law in Indonesia and their Application*, AHM-PTHM Alumni Publisher, Jakarta, 1986, page 211.

a criminal act. This study is a type of normative research using secondary legal sources and using qualitative descriptive analysis. The results of this study are that the forms of participation crimes can be divided into two parts, namely: first, the perpetrator consisting of: the perpetrator (pleger), the one who orders it (doenpleger), the one who participates (madepleger) and the advocate (uitlokker); second, the assistant consisting of: the assistant at the time the crime was committed and the assistant before the crime was committed.

Judges in deciding a case are based on evidence that has been determined by law and the judge's own belief (conscience). In principle, the system of evidence according to law negatively determines that judges may only impose a sentence on the defendant if the evidence is limitatively determined by law and is also supported by the judge's belief in the existence of the evidence.

In proving whether the defendant is guilty or not in a criminal case, according to Lilik Mulyadi, the Indonesian Criminal Procedure Code adopts a negative system of proof according to law. In the negative system of proof according to law (negative wettelijke bewijs theorie) there is a dominant element in the form of at least two pieces of evidence, while the element of the judge's belief is only a complementary element. So in determining whether someone is guilty or not for those charged, their guilt must be proven with at least two pieces of evidence as stated in Article 183 of the Criminal Procedure Code "a judge may not impose a sentence on a person unless with at least two valid pieces of evidence he obtains the conviction that a crime actually occurred and the defendant is guilty of committing it.

According to Yahya Harahap, only evidence that reaches the minimum limit has the value of evidentiary power to prove the defendant's guilt. If the evidence does not reach at least two valid pieces of evidence in the Criminal Procedure Code, then the violation automatically sets aside the "Beyond a reasonable doubt Standard" (the benchmark for applying the standard proven legally and convincingly), and the punishment imposed can be considered a form of arbitrariness. Then seen from the perspective of the criminal justice system, the matter of evidence is a very determinant for every party directly involved in the criminal case examination process, especially in terms of assessing whether or not the guilt charged to the defendant is proven.

In this case of proof, the victim's statement is very important, where the victim is someone who suffers physically and mentally as a result of the actions of others who seek to fulfill their own interests or those of others that conflict with their interests and human rights. So with the explanation above, there are 2 (two) things that are requirements to prove guilt.

- 1) *Wetlands*; The existence of valid evidence that has been determined by law.
- 2) *Negative*; There is a belief from the judge, namely that based on the evidence the judge believes the defendant is guilty.
- 3) There is a conviction (Conscience) from the judge, namely based on the evidence shown, the judge believes the defendant is guilty. The evidentiary system adopted by the Criminal Code is regulated in Article 183 which states "A judge may not impose a sentence on a person unless with at least, and valid evidence he obtains the conviction that a crime really occurred that the defendant is guilty of committing it. So it can be

concluded that the Criminal Code adopts a negative evidentiary system, except in fast cases where 1 piece of evidence and the judge's conviction are sufficient (in Articles 205-216 of the Criminal Code).

CONCLUSION

1. In this case based on the decision Number: 15/Pid.S/2024/PN.Stb). Regarding the Legal Regulations on Palm Oil Theft in Indonesia, it has been regulated as of Article 107 letter d of Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 35 of 2014 concerning Plantations in conjunction with Article 55 paragraph (1) 1 of the Criminal Code. Specifically regarding the crime of theft, Article 107 states that "illegal": this is due to Using, working on, occupying, and/or controlling Plantation Land. Working on, occupying, Utilizing and/or managing community land or customary land of indigenous peoples for agriculture. Cutting down trees in the planting area or people who unlawfully work on, use, occupy and/or control plantation land, who work on, use, occupy and/or control the rights to customary land of a community land or Aboriginal legal community for the benefit of the plantation business; Harvesting and/or collecting plantation products as referred to in Article 55 shall be punishable by a maximum imprisonment of 4 years or a maximum fine of Rp. 4,000,000,000.00 (4 billion rupiah).
2. Meanwhile, the Evidence of the Criminal Act of Theft as stated in Decision Number: 15/Pid.S/2024/PN.Stb. In the trial, the defendant has been proven as a person who fulfills the Elements of Who did, ordered to do and who participated in doing. Because the Defendant's actions in collecting the plantation's produce illegally were carried out by the Defendant together with Rido by working together according to their respective roles. In this case, the evidence has been proven in the form of: 2 (two) plastic sacks containing 50 Kg of oil palm fruit bunches. In the trial process, it turned out that the defendant and the plantation had made peace, so that the judge in handing down his decision applied a restorative justice-based justice system. The principle of Restorative Justice is carried out because there has been a peace agreement between the Defendant and PT. LNK Kebun Bukit Lawang, Restorative justice is an alternative resolution of criminal cases in which the mechanism of criminal justice procedures focuses on punishment which is changed into a dialogue and mediation process involving the perpetrator, victim, the perpetrator/victim's family, and other related parties to jointly create an agreement on a fair and balanced resolution of criminal cases for both the victim and the perpetrator by prioritizing restoration to the original state and restoring good relations in society.

REFERENCES

- Agusman Heri, "Analisis Yuridis Terhadap Tindak Pidana Penyertaan Pembunuhan (Studi Putusan MA Nomor : 2462/Pid.B/2017/PN Medan 2018)," *Jurnal Abdi Ilmu* 11, No. 2 (2019)
- Andi Zainal Abidin Farid dan Andi Hamzah, *Bentuk-Bentuk Khusus Perwujudan Delik (Percobaan, Penyertaan, dan Gabungan Delik) dan Hukum Penitensier* (Jakarta: RajaGrafindo Persada, 2006), halaman 211.

- Fahrurrozi dan Samsul Bahri M. Gare, “Sistem Pemidanaan Dalam Penyertaan Tindak Pidana Menurut KUHP,” *Media Keadilan: Jurnal Ilmu Hukum* 10, no. 1 (2019): halaman 52,
- Franco Marcello Moningka, Michael Barama, dan Mario A. Gerungan, “Penerapan Ajaran Deelneming Dalam Tindak Pidana Pencurian ,” *Lex Crimen* VII, no. 5 (2018)
- Fransiska Novita Eleanora, “Kajian Yuridis Penerapan Sanksi Tindakan Terhadap Anak yang Melakukan Tindak Pidana Menurut Undang-Undang No. 3 Tahun 1997 tentang Pengadilan Anak,” *ADIL: Jurnal Hukum* 6, No. 2 (2015)
- Hartanto, *Metodologi Penelitian Hukum* (Bekasi: Cakrawala Cendekia, 2018)
- J Rimmelink, *Pengantar Hukum Pidana Material 1: Prolegomena dan Uraian Tentang Teori Ajaran Dasar*, vol. 1 (Yogyakarta: Maharsa Publishing, 2014)
- Lamintang, *Dasar-dasar Hukum Pidana Indonesia*, Sumur batu, Bandung, 1983
- Martiman Prodjohamidjojo, *Memahami Dasar-Dasar Hukum Pidana Indonesia* (Jakarta: Pradnya Paramita, 1998)
- R. Soesilo, *Kitab Undang-Undang Hukum Pidana*, Penerbit Politeia, Bogor
- S. R. Sianturi, *Asas-asas Hukum Pidana di Indonesia dan Penerapannya*, Penerbit Alumni AHM-PTHM, Jakarta, 1986
- Saleh Roeslan, *Delik Penyertaan* (Pekanbaru: Fakultas Hukum Islam Riau, 1989)
- Sipayung, Ronald F C, Alvi Syahrin, Suhaidi, dan Mahmud Mulyadi. “Analisis Yuridis Peran Polri Dalam Penanggulangan Tindak Pidana Pencurian..” *USU Law Journal* 4, No. 3 (2016)
- Teguh Prasetyo, *Hukum Pidana* (Jakarta: RajaGrafindo Persada, 2019)
- Zamhari Abidin, *Pengertian dan Asas Hukum Pidana Dalam Schema (Bagan) dan Synopsis (Catatan Singkat)* (Jakarta: Ghalia Indonesia, 1986)

Criminal Sanctions Against Narcotics Traffickers

Berry Prima¹, Mhd. Azhali Siregar²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: azhalisiregar@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

Drug-related crimes have increasingly become a pressing issue in recent times. Law No. 35 of 2009 on Narcotics lacks specific definitions for categories such as users, sellers, distributors, and dealers, focusing instead on the types and quantities of narcotics. This ambiguity often leads to confusion when determining ownership of illicit substances, as roles among users, owners, and dealers sometimes overlap, particularly when large quantities are involved. In the case of Decision Number: 327/Pid.Sus/2023/PN.Mdn, the imposition of the death penalty on a suspect identified as a drug dealer aligns with Article 114, paragraph (2) of the Narcotics Law. This study employs normative legal research, utilizing statutory and philosophical approaches to explore the application of criminal sanctions for narcotics dealers. The findings reveal that the death penalty is the most severe punishment prescribed for drug dealers, as regulated in Article 114, paragraph (2). In narcotics-related offenses, investigators use evidence as outlined in Article 184 of the Criminal Procedure Code, which includes witness testimonies, expert opinions, documentary evidence, indications, and defendant statements. Article 114, paragraph (2) and Article 119, paragraph (2) of the Narcotics Law specify that individuals involved in offering, selling, buying, brokering, exchanging, transferring, or receiving narcotics in defined quantities and types qualify as dealers and are subject to the death penalty.

Keywords: Criminal Sanctions, Narcotics, Distribution.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most detrimental and complex crimes and crimes that damage the order of life of society, nation and state is drug abuse. In Indonesia, the crime of drug abuse has reached an alarming level based on data from the Indonesia Drugs Report 2022, the BNN data and information research center, in 2019 the prevalence was 1.80 percent then in 2021 it was around 1.95 in this case an increase of 0.15 percent, this figure increased from the previous year of around 4.5 million people.³ Lifestyles that are balanced by the increasingly rapid flow of globalization have also influenced the increase in drug and illicit drug crimes. The problem of narcotics is a complex and very dangerous problem, in this case the perpetrators of the abuse are mostly young people, this is dangerous because young people should indeed be the next generation of the nation for their country, therefore it is very important to eradicate the abuse of narcotics and illicit drugs.¹

Drug abuse is a deviant behavior that is more directed at the problem of obedience or compliance with social norms. Individuals who have low self-control are not stimulated by the environment, like to take risks, lose emotional control due to easy frustration, then

¹Abdullah, Zainuddin. "Death Penalty for Drug Dealers in the Perspective of Islamic Law." Al Amin: Journal of Islamic Science and Culture Studies Vol. 1, No. 2 (2018). page 87.

someone who is cut off from social ties with their environment has no social control so they are free to commit deviations.²

This narcotics crime is very complex so that this crime is a crime network that is not easy to trace because this crime is an organized and neatly arranged crime with changing modes of crime. So that in eradicating this narcotics crime, support from various parties is needed, with these problems, social control is an effort to prevent deviations, then to create order and security, then one of the decisions regarding the crime of narcotics trafficking is the Medan District Court Decision Number: 327 / Pid.Sus / 2023 / PN.Mdn, the decision concerns the crime of narcotics trafficking involving TNI officers.

The meaning of drug abuser is stated in Article 1 number (15) of the Narcotics Law which states "A drug abuser is a person who uses narcotics without rights or against the law". Meanwhile, according to the Narcotics Law, narcotics themselves are divided into 3 groups, namely groups I, II, III. Criminal provisions for drug abusers are regulated in Article 127 paragraph of the Narcotics Law: "Paragraph 1 Every drug abuser:

1. Class I narcotics for personal use are punishable by a maximum prison sentence of 4 (four) years;
2. Class II narcotics for oneself are punishable by a maximum imprisonment of 2 (two) years; and
3. "Use of Class III narcotics for oneself is punishable by a maximum imprisonment of 1 (one) year."³

To achieve a proper trial process, the criminal procedural law must be implemented properly. If there is a violation of the criminal procedural law, then the trial cannot achieve material truth, and a fair and impartial trial will also not be achieved. In criminal law, what is sought is material truth. Material truth is obtained in a trial, but it can also not be obtained in a trial. If this happens, it can be said that a fair and impartial trial or fair and trial has not been created.

The judicial institution is not only a place to try and punish the accused. The judicial institution as the only institution to try and seek justice is expected to reveal the truth of the legal process that was taken previously to obtain material truth.

"Material truth is the most complete truth of a criminal case by applying the provisions of criminal procedure law honestly and accurately with the aim of finding out who the perpetrator is who can be accused of committing a violation of the law, and then requesting an examination and prosecution from the court to find out whether it is proven that a crime has been committed and whether the person accused can be blamed."⁴

In the case of Decision Number: 327/Pid.Sus/2023/PN.Mdn. The defendant has been charged by the Public Prosecutor with the charges as contained in Article 114 Paragraph (2)

²Arifin, Zainul. "The Position and Urgency of the Death Penalty in Combating Drug Trafficking in Indonesia and Several Countries in the World." *Journal of State and Justice* Vol. 9, No. 2 (August 2020).

³Aruro, Pictor. "Death Penalty for Drug Dealers in the Context of Law No. 22 of 1997 and Amendments to Law No. 35 of 2009." *Jurnal Lex Administratum* Vo. 4, No. 3 (March 2016).

⁴Andi Hamzah, *Indonesian Criminal Procedure Law*, Sinar Grafika, Jakarta: 2017, page 8.

of the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics in conjunction with Article 55 paragraph (1) 1 of the Criminal Code with evidence in the form of 75,000 (seventy five thousand) grams of crystal methamphetamine and 40,000 (forty thousand) ecstasy pills. Based on Article 8 paragraph (2) of the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics, Class I Narcotics can only be used for the purposes of developing science and technology and for diagnostic reagents, as well as laboratory reagents after obtaining the Minister's approval on the recommendation of the Head of the Food and Drug Supervisory Agency

Defendant's Actions violating Article 114 paragraph (2) of the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics in conjunction with Article 55 paragraph (1) point 1 of the Criminal Code, there are 7 (seven) qualifications of acts that are determined as Narcotics Crimes, namely:

1. Offered For Sale;
2. Sell;
3. Buy;
4. Become an Intermediary in Buying and Selling;
5. Exchange;
6. Deliver;
7. Accept;

If we analyze the seven qualifications of acts that are elements of the criminal act above, then there is a sub-element, namely the necessity of more than one party or subject that must be proven according to the law of evidence in order for the act to be realized, namely that in "offering for sale" there must be at least one party offering and another party accepting the offer, in "selling" as well as in "buying" each must have at least one party as a seller and another party as a buyer, in "becoming an intermediary in buying and selling" requires a minimum of three parties, namely the seller and the buyer and an intermediary who can act as an intermediary trader/broker or as a liaison or as a media between the seller and the buyer.⁵

In "exchanging" there must be an exchange so that there must be a party who exchanges and a party who is exchanged, in "surrendering" as well as in "receiving" there must be a party who surrenders and a party who receives, and the seven acts that are qualified as criminal acts are making goods as the object, namely narcotics.

From the above case, taking into account Article 114 paragraph (2) of the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics In conjunction with Article 55 paragraph (1) point 1 of the Criminal Code and Law Number 8 of 1981 concerning Criminal Procedure Law and other laws and regulations, the person concerned has been proven legally and convincingly guilty of committing the crime of "Jointly and unlawfully acting as an intermediary in the sale and purchase of Class I Narcotics other than Plants weighing more

⁵Basuki, Udiyo. "Human Rights, Constitution and Democracy: Dynamics of Human Rights Protection in the Indonesian Constitution from a Democratic Perspective." In Right: Journal of Religion and Human Rights Vol. 8, No. 2 (November 2019). page 62.

than 5 (five) grams", then the Panel of Judges sentenced the Defendant to death.⁶

The formulation of the problem in this research is as follows:

1. Can the application of evidence in Decision Number 327/Pid.Sus/2023/PN Mdn prove that the defendant is a distributor?
2. Can the element of "accepting" Article 114 paragraph (2) of the Narcotics Law be applied to the defendant?

METHOD

Research is defined as theory disbursement, theory testing or problem solving. Research method is a procedure or way to obtain correct knowledge or truth through systematic steps. To obtain or obtain accurate, relevant data and to find out what legal consequences arise from this problem, in this research activity the author uses the following research methods:

Types of research

This study uses a normative research method using a legislative, case and conceptual approach. The legislative approach is to study using laws and regulations that regulate sanctions and their prevention, then the case approach is an approach using cases that have received court decisions and the conceptual approach is to use the concepts of legal experts and is connected to law enforcement.

Data source

The data sources used in this study are library research consisting of primary legal materials and secondary legal materials. The primary legal materials in this writing are:

- a. Republic of Indonesia Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics
- b. Criminal Code
- c. Criminal Procedure Code
- d. Decision Number: 327/Pid.Sus/2023/PN.Mdn
- e. laws and regulations relating to narcotics

While the secondary legal materials in this study are explanations of matters related to writing, for example decisions related to narcotics. The technique used in this study is the technique of collecting legal materials or document studies from laws and regulations and related documents such as judges' decisions, the data collected is then analyzed using legal arguments and arranged descriptively.

Data analysis

Data and materials collected and obtained from the research will be processed, compiled and analyzed qualitatively. Data collection in solving this problem is carried out by library research, which is then analyzed qualitatively. This analysis technique is a technique in

⁶Eleanora, Fransiska Novita. "The Dangers of Drug Abuse and Efforts to Prevent and Overcome It (A Theoretical Review)." *Journal of Law* Volume XXV Number 1 (2011). page 42.

which the legal materials or literature will be studied so that they can provide descriptions of the research topic so as to help the author make a correct conclusion.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis of the Application of Evidence in Decision Number: 327/Pid.Sus/2023/PN.Mdn.

To find material truth, formal truth must be obtained first, in terms of finding formal truth, formal law must be implemented properly, formal criminal law is regulated in the Criminal Procedure Code. "Formal criminal law or criminal procedure law to regulate how the government maintains the continuity of the implementation of material criminal law".⁷

In this case, the defendant Yogi Saputra Dewa has been proven legally guilty of committing a criminal act "jointly without the right to do so".the act of offering for sale, selling, buying, being an intermediary in buying and selling, exchanging, handing over or receiving non-plant Class I Narcotics weighing more than 5 (five) grams"As in the Primary Indictment, violating Article 114 Paragraph (2) of the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics in conjunction with Article 55 paragraph (1) point 1 of the Criminal Code and sentencing the Defendant Yogi Saputra Dewa to the death penalty.

In short the case is thatThat the Defendant Yogi Saputra Dewa together with witness Syahril Bin Syamsudin together with witness Sergeant Yalpin Tarzun and witness Private Rian Hermawan (Tried at the Medan Military Court I-02) on Monday, December 5, 2022, at approximately 14.15 WIB or at least still included in the year 2022, located at Jalan Pemuda Number 22, AUR, Medan Maimun District, Medan City, North Sumatra Province, precisely in front of the Hermes Palace Hotel Medan Lobby or at least in a place included in the jurisdiction of the Medan District Court. "together without rights or against the law, offered for sale, sold, bought, be an intermediary in buying, selling, exchanging, handing over or receiving narcotics"Class I is not a plant weighing more than 5 (five) grams", the Defendant committed the act.

That these defendants committedSmuggling of methamphetamine and ecstasy drugs in the North Sumatra region. This is based on reports from the community, so the police combed the location believed to be where they carried out the smuggling transaction, namely at the locationDoorsmer Car wash on Jalan Sp. Kebon Jagung in front of Battalion 121 Macan Kumbang Complex, Galang District, Deli Serdang Regency using a black Fortuner vehicle with Police Number BK 1549 SR. After the police found out about their actions while conducting transactions in the car, the police then secured the defendants, namely Yogi Saputra Dewa and witnesses Syahril Bin Syamsudin, witnesses Sergeant Yalpin Tarzun and witness Private Rian Hermawan as well as 3 (three) green plastic bags containing narcotics of the type of crystal methamphetamine as much as 75 (seventy five) packs of Chinese tea weighing 75,000 grams and 8 (eight) clear plastic packages wrapped in black plastic containing narcotics of the type of ecstasy as much as 40,000 (forty thousand) pills and 3 mobile phones.

⁷LJ Van Apeldoorn, "Introduction to Legal Science", Balai Pustaka, Jakarta, 2015 page 335

In this case the defendant is Yogi Saputra Dewa. In being proven to be an intermediary in the sale and purchase of narcotics weighing around 75,000 (seventy five thousand) grams gross of crystal methamphetamine and 40,000 (forty thousand) ecstasy pills, where if these narcotics were able to get onto the market they would be able to damage the future of thousands of young generations of Indonesia and in turn could damage the security stability of the Republic of Indonesia, as a result of his actions, the defendant has violated the provisions of Article 114 paragraph (2) of Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics. In conjunction with Article 55 paragraph (1) point 1 of the Criminal Code and Law Number 8 of 1981 concerning Criminal Procedure Law and other relevant laws and regulations.⁸

So that it is legally and convincingly guilty of committing the crime of "Jointly and unlawfully becoming an intermediary in the sale and purchase of Class I Narcotics, not Plants, weighing more than 5 (five) grams. Sentencing the Defendant Yogi Saputra God with the death penalty.

In determining the truth in an event as charged by the public prosecutor, it must be accompanied by valid evidence to convince or ensure that something is true. Article 184 paragraph (1) of the Criminal Procedure Code regulates valid evidence for proof in criminal cases, namely:

1. Witness testimony;
2. Expert testimony;
3. Letter;
4. Instructions, and;
5. Defendant's statement

In addition to the evidence specified in the Criminal Procedure Code, the Narcotics Law also regulates separate evidence regulated in Article 86, namely:

1. Investigators may obtain evidence other than that referred to in the Criminal Procedure Code;
2. The evidence referred to in paragraph (1) consists of:
 - a. Information that is spoken, sent, received or stored electronically by optical or similar means and
 - b. Recorded data or information that can be seen, read and/or heard, which can be produced with or without the aid of a medium, whether written on paper, any physical object other than paper or recorded electronically, including but not limited to:
 1. Text, sound, and/or images;
 2. Maps, designs, photographs or the like; or letters, signs, figures, symbols, codes or perforations which have a meaning which can be understood by a person who is able to read or understand them.

⁸Heriyono. "Implementation of the Death Penalty in the Perspective of Human Rights." Indonesian Journal of Law and Policy Studies Vol. 1, No. 1 (May 2020). page 121.

The existence of evidence is very important in determining whether a person meets the elements of a crime against the criminal provisions charged to him so that it can be determined whether the person can be held accountable for his actions or not. "Evidence is the provisions that contain outlines and guidelines on the procedures that are permitted by law to prove the guilt charged to the defendant."⁹

So proof is a provision that regulates the evidence permitted by law that may be used by the judge to prove the guilt of the accused. "The law of proof is part of the criminal procedure law that regulates the types of evidence that are valid according to law, the system adopted in proof, the requirements and procedures for submitting the evidence and the authority of the judge to accept, reject and assess evidence."

To declare a defendant guilty or not, it is not enough to rely solely on the judge's conviction or solely on the evidence according to the provisions and methods of proof with the evidence determined by law. A defendant can only be declared guilty if the crime charged against him can be proven in a manner and with that "accompanied" by the judge's conviction." (Harahap, 2012, p. 280) So that based on the evidence with at least two valid pieces of evidence, the judge gains the conviction that the crime really happened and that the defendant was guilty of committing it. "The reason the legislator formulated Article 183 of the Criminal Procedure Code was aimed at realizing a provision that could at least guarantee the upholding of true truth and the upholding of justice and legal certainty."

In this case, the evidence and evidence collected (as mentioned above, namely 3 (three) green bags containing 75 (seventy five) packages of narcotics of the type of crystal methamphetamine weighing approximately 75,000 (seventy five thousand) grams, 8 (eight) packages of ecstasy totaling approximately 40,000 (forty thousand) pills, 1 (one) blue Oppo brand cellphone with the number 081372198495) and supported by the existence of legal facts, namely that Defendant Yogi Saputra Dewa was caught red-handed by the police while carrying out a transaction as an intermediary for the distribution of narcotics.

The burden of proof is basically on the investigator, the investigator tries his best to fulfill the provisions of the Law, namely that an incident that occurs is suspected or constitutes a criminal act, then an investigation is carried out with the aim of seeking information and evidence to find the truth in a criminal incident.

In the process of proving a narcotics case, often the evidence used is two witnesses, evidence of a number of drugs, urine test results or blood tests belonging to the defendant. This is indeed strong enough in the evidence as referred to in the Criminal Procedure Code, but the negative evidence system adopted by the Criminal Procedure Code requires the Judge's conviction so that the defendant can be subject to criminal sanctions, so here the role of investigators and investigators is very much needed in finding evidence that can convince the Judge.¹⁰

In addition to the evidence that is often used in the process of proving narcotics cases,

⁹Hutapea, Bungasan. "Alternatives to the Death Penalty in Indonesia Seen from a Human Rights Perspective." *Human Rights Research Journal* Vol. 7, No. 2 (December 2016). page 59.

¹⁰Kolopita, Satrio Putra. "Law Enforcement on the Death Penalty for Narcotics Crime Offenders." *Lex Crimen Journal* Vol. 2, No. 4 (August 2013). page 92

there is fingerprint evidence that can be used as an indication of ownership or control of narcotics. Explanation of Article 75 letter f of the Narcotics Law explains that, "urine tests, blood tests, hair tests, and other body part tests are carried out in accordance with the development of science and technology to prove the presence or absence of narcotics in the body of one person or several people.

Based on the explanation, it appears that the fingerprint test is a part of the body that can be identified and is a means of evidence to determine who owns or controls a narcotic. Based on Article 187 letter c of the Criminal Procedure Code, the results of the fingerprint test in the form of a laboratory report are a letter made by a dactyloscopic expert in conducting a specimen test to determine whose fingerprints are on the narcotic package., "...the form of the letter referred to in letters a, b, and c is an "official letter" made by an authorized official or based on provisions or a special expert statement regarding certain circumstances made on an oath of office or strengthened by an oath.". "The letter itself has value as valid evidence, since the letter was made."

Elements Contained in Article 114 Paragraph (2) of the Narcotics Law that Can Be Applied to Defendants

Criminal acts are the translation of the word strafbaarfeit in Dutch. Viewed from a literal perspective, strafbaarfeit consists of the word feit which in Dutch means part of a reality or eengedeelte van de werkelijkheid, while strafbaar means punishable. Literally the word strafbaarfeit can be translated as part of a reality that can be punished.¹¹ Criminal act is just one translation of the Dutch term strafbaarfeit. Actually, the term is elliptical (short for) part of the sentence that is omitted. The actual sentence is feit tarzaake van het welke een person strafbaar is (an act for which a person can be punished).¹²

Thus, based on the understanding of strafbaarfeit above, criminal law experts interpret strafbaarfeit differently, some translate it as a criminal event, criminal act, punishable act, and some also abbreviate it as a crime. So in the crime there are elements of a crime, namely:¹³

1. Objective Elements Elements that exist outside the perpetrator. Elements that are related to circumstances, namely the circumstances in which the perpetrator's actions must be carried out
2. Subjective Elements Elements that exist or are attached to the perpetrator or are connected to the perpetrator and include everything that is contained in his heart.

In the provisions of Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics, several narcotics crimes are determined, namely in Article 111 to Article 148 of Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics. In Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics, it is determined

¹¹PAF Lamintang, 1997, Basics of Indonesian Criminal Law, Citra Aditya Bakti, Bandung, page 181.

¹²Megawaty Runtunuwu, Gabriela. "Imposing the Death Penalty for Narcotics Crime Offenders." *Lex Crimen Journal* Vol. 2, No. 6 (October 2013). Page 81

¹³Mulyadi, Lilik. "Punishment of Drug Dealers and Users: Research on Principles, Theories, Norms and Judicial Practices." *Journal of Law and Justice* Vol. 1, No. 2 (July 2012). page 61

that the penalties that can be imposed are the death penalty, imprisonment, imprisonment and fines. Criminal penalties can also be imposed on corporations, namely in the form of revocation of business licenses; and/or revocation of legal entity status.

In this case, the legal basis for imposing a criminal penalty on the defendant's actions is Article 114 Paragraph (2) of the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics in conjunction with Article 55 paragraph (1) point 1 of the Criminal Code, whose elements are as follows:¹⁴

1. Each person;
2. Without rights or against the law;
3. Offering to sell, sell, buy, receive, become an intermediary in buying and selling, exchanging or handing over class I narcotics weighing more than 5 (five) grams;
4. Class I narcotics are not plants;
5. Doing it, those who order it to do it and those who participate in doing it;

Narcotics according to the provisions of Article 1 number 1 of the Republic of Indonesia Law Number: 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics are substances or drugs derived from plants or non-plants, either synthetic or semi-synthetic, which can cause a decrease or change in consciousness, loss of feeling, reduce or eliminate pain, and can cause dependence and in the General Explanation of Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 35 of 2009 about Narcotics It is stated that narcotics are substances or drugs that are very useful and needed for the treatment of certain diseases and furthermore in Article 6 paragraph (1) it is stated that narcotics are classified into a. Class I narcotics, b. Class II narcotics and c. Class III narcotics.¹⁵

Judging from the dangers and level of circulation, the government finally established the Narcotics Law, namely Law Number 35 of 2009, with the issuance of this Law it is hoped that it can prevent and suppress the increasing circulation and use of narcotics in the territory of Indonesia. With a law that specifically concerns narcotics, all parties hope that it can run well and existing sanctions can be determined fairly for perpetrators of narcotics crimes. The narcotics law is very necessary to enforce because of the enormous influence of narcotics on the survival of a nation, especially for the younger generation of the nation's successors. Various efforts have been made by the government and non-governmental organizations that care about the dangers of narcotics.¹⁶

Very fatal dangers can occur to drug users and the surrounding environment, as well as the nation and state in general, in this case the government and society and related parties are trying to campaign the dangers of drug abuse, this aims to make many people aware of the impact of drug abuse. The implementation of increased control and supervision measures

¹⁴Panjaitan, Budi Sastram. "Placing the Perpetrators of Illicit Drug Trafficking Crimes as Perpetrators of Genocide Crimes." *Pioneer Journal of LPPM, Asahan University* Vol. 5, No. 2 (2019). page 71.

¹⁵Purnomo, Agus. "Death Penalty for Narcotics Crimes in Indonesia: A Legal Sociology Perspective." *De Jure: Journal of Law and Sharia* Vol. 8, No. 1 (2016). page 28.

¹⁶Rukman, Auliah Andika. "Death Penalty Reviewed from a Sociological Perspective and Human Rights Enforcement." *Journal of Equilibrium Sociology Education* Vol. 4, No. 1 (May 2016). page 87.

as an effort to prevent and eradicate drug abuse and illicit trafficking is very necessary. Because drug crimes are generally not carried out by individuals alone but are carried out together and even carried out by syndicates that are neatly organized and very secretive.

In addition to drug crimes, the development of the quality of drug crimes has become a very serious threat to human life. Preventive measures remain a priority through the development of preventive principles and the principle of general police obligations, namely maintaining public security and order. In this case, every official of the Republic of Indonesia National Police has Discretionary authority, namely the authority to act in the public interest based on their own assessment.

Article 114 paragraph (2) of the Republic of Indonesia Law No. 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics in conjunction with Article 55 paragraph (1) point 1 of the Criminal Code contains 7 (seven) qualifications of acts that are determined as Narcotics Crimes, namely:¹⁷

1. Offered For Sale;
2. Sell;
3. Buy;
4. Become an Intermediary in Buying and Selling;
5. Exchange;
6. Deliver;
7. Accept;

If we analyze the seven qualifications of acts that are elements of the crime above, then there is a sub-element, namely the necessity of more than one party or subject that must be proven according to the law of evidence in order for the act to be realized, namely that in "offering for sale" there must be at least one party offering and another party accepting the offer, in "selling" as well as in "buying" each must have at least one party as a seller and another party as a buyer, in "becoming an intermediary in buying and selling" requires a minimum of three parties, namely the seller and the buyer and an intermediary who can be positioned to carry out work as an intermediary trader/broker or as a liaison or as a media between the seller and the buyer, in "exchanging" requires an exchange so that there must be a party exchanging and a party being exchanged, in "surrendering" as well as in "receiving" there must be a party submitting and a party receiving, and the seven acts that are qualified as criminal acts are making goods as objects, namely narcotics.¹⁸

Based on the facts revealed at the trial, the Defendant Yogi Saputra Dewa together with the Witness Syahril bin Syamsudin, Yalpin Tarzun and Rian Hermawan, have been arrested by the NIC Task Force Team Officers of the Directorate of Narcotics Crimes of the National Police Criminal Investigation Unit, on suspicion of committing narcotics crimes in the form of crystal methamphetamine and ecstasy. Defendant Yogi Saputra Dewa together with Syahril bin Syamsudin met with Sergeant Yalpin Tarzun at the location to carry out a transaction to hand over narcotics in the form of crystal methamphetamine and ecstasy, so

¹⁷Salundik. "Enforcement of the Death Penalty in Narcotics Crimes." *Tambun Bungai Journal of Legal Studies* Vol. 1, No. 2 (September 2016). page 132.

¹⁸Sumanto, Atet. "The Effectiveness of the Death Penalty in the Process of Law Enforcement of Narcotics Crimes." *Jurnal Perspektif* Vol. 22, No. 1 (January 2017). page 79.

that the actions of the Defendant Yogi Saputra Dewa together with Syahril bin Syamsudin in offering for sale, selling, buying, receiving, acting as an intermediary in buying and selling, exchanging, or handing over class I narcotics weighing more than 5 (five) grams did not have permission from the authorities.

In order to realize the implementation of the law against narcotics trafficking crimes, there is a police institution that is formed as an institution that enforces the law in accordance with Article 81 of the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics, which states that: "Investigators of the Republic of Indonesia National Police and BNN investigators are authorized to conduct investigations into the misuse and illicit trafficking of narcotics and narcotic precursors based on this Law."¹⁹

In implementing law enforcement efforts, narcotics trafficking crimes can be carried out preemptively, preventively and repressively.²⁰ Preemptive is a proactive and interactive effort in the framework of fostering, organizing, and utilizing community potential in an effort to win the sympathy of the people. Preventive is an effort that is preventive and eliminates all forms of threats to public order and security by providing protection, protection, and services to the community. Meanwhile, repressive is an effort that is law enforcement by ensuring the upholding of the law, legal order that is implemented firmly, professionally, and thoroughly while still upholding human rights.²¹

Law enforcement agencies must carry out their duties properly and in accordance with their respective roles as regulated in laws and regulations. In carrying out their duties, they must prioritize justice and professionalism, so that they become role models for the community and are trusted by all parties, including members of the community.²⁶ Based on Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning narcotics, it is emphasized that the distribution of narcotics can be subject to criminal sanctions in the form of imprisonment, fines, and the maximum criminal penalty for drug makers and distributors is the death penalty.²²

Decision on case number:327/Pid.Sus/2023/PN.Mdn.is appropriate because the panel of judges chose the second charge which stated that the defendant violated Article 114 paragraph (2) of Law. RI Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics. Based on the facts revealed in the trial, the elements of this article were legally proven and convinced that the defendant was guilty. So that in the verdict it was stated that Yogi Pratama Dewa legally and guilty of committing the crime of drug abuse class one which was used for himself. The determination of the verdict was made at the will of the judge and his considerations, which was appropriate because in the considerations used by the judge in the form of facts revealed and evidence presented in the trial, as well as statements from witnesses. Other additional supporting evidence is the letter of the results of the Narcotics examination which was

¹⁹Viswandro, et al., *Getting to Know the Law Enforcement Profession*, (Jakarta: Medpress Digital, 2015), page 2.

²⁰Frans Simangunsong, "Law Enforcement Against Narcotics Crime Offenders", *Journal of Legal Studies*, Faculty of Law, UNSA, Vol. 8, No. 1, (2014), page 12.

²¹Suyono Yoyok, *Police Law: The Position of the Police in the Indonesian Constitutional System After the Amendment to the 1945 Constitution*, (Yogyakarta: Laksbang Grafika, 2013), page 2.

²²Sinta Herindrasti. "Drug-Free ASEAN 2025: Indonesia's Challenges in Combating Drug Abuse." *Journal of International Relations* Vol. 7, No. 1 (2018). page 70.

examined by a crime laboratory. In addition, the main element in this case is that the defendant is an individual who can be responsible for his actions, at the time of committing the act he was aware of the consequences that would arise, and of his own will without any coercion from any party.

The panel of judges did not find any elements that could be used as justification, forgiveness, or exceptions so that the defendant could be released from all charges. The panel of judges also considered the aggravating factors, one of which was the act of ignoring the government's work program in its efforts to eliminate and prevent all forms of drug abuse practices, especially since what the defendant had done could damage him and also affect the development of other young generations. In addition, the mitigating factors for the defendant in this case were his role as the backbone of the family, and he had also admitted his actions and was cooperative during the examination at the trial.

CONCLUSION

1. Evidence Used by Investigators to Determine Suspects in Drug Abuse Crimes Similar to evidence for other crimes, in drug abuse the evidence used is also in accordance with the provisions of Article 184 of the Criminal Procedure Code which states that: "Valid evidence is: a. Witness testimony b. Expert testimony c. Letters d. Instructions e. Defendant's statement". Evidence in cases of drug abuse crimes must also be proven by a urine test through a Forensic Laboratory or Investigator's laboratory. Positive results from urine tests that are stated in the form of a test report are included in written evidence. The test report still requires other evidence to be able to ensnare the provisions of drug crimes on suspects.
2. The application of the provisions of Article 114 paragraph 2 concerning the distribution of narcotics, the sanction is the death penalty for narcotics dealers regulated in Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics, technically contained in Article 114 paragraph (2) and Article 119 paragraph (2). Narcotics dealers are those who are proven in terms of the act of offering for sale, selling, buying, being an intermediary in buying and selling, exchanging, handing over or receiving narcotics by fulfilling the type and conditions, as well as the amount or level of narcotics they have. Threatened with the death penalty as one of the types of punishment contained in these articles and is the most severe punishment.

REFERENCES

- Abdullah, Zainuddin. "Hukuman Mati Bagi Pengedar Narkoba Dalam Perspektif Hukum Islam." *Al Amin: Jurnal Kajian Ilmu Dan Budaya Islam* Vol. 1, No. 2 (2018)
- Andi Hamzah, *Hukum Acara Pidana Indonesia*, Sinar Grafika, Jakarta: 2017
- Arifin, Zainul. "Kedudukan Dan Urgensi Hukuman Mati Terhadap Penanggulangan Pengedaran Narkotika Di Indonesia Dan Sejumlah Negara Di Dunia." *Jurnal Negara Dan Keadilan* Vol. 9, No. 2 (August 2020).

- Aruro, Piktora. "Hukuman Mati Bagi Pengedar Narkotika Dalam Konteks UU No. 22 Tahun 1997 Dan Perubahan UU No. 35 Tahun 2009." *Jurnal Lex Administratum* Vol. 4, No. 3 (March 2016).
- Basuki, Udiyo. "HAM, Konstitusi Dan Demokrasi: Dinamika Perlindungan HAM Dalam Konstitusi Indonesia Perspektif Demokrasi." In *Right: Jurnal Agama Dan Hak Asasi Manusia* Vol. 8, No. 2 (November 2019)
- Eleanora, Fransiska Novita. "Bahaya Penyalahgunaan Narkoba Serta Usaha Pencegahan Dan Penanggulangannya (Suatu Tinjauan Teoritis)." *Jurnal Hukum Volume XXV Nomor 1* (2011)
- Frans Simangunsong, "Penegakan Hukum Terhadap Pelaku Tindak Pidana Narkotika", *Jurnal Rechstaat Ilmu Hukum Fakultas Hukum UNSA*, Vol. 8, No. 1, (2014)
- Heriyono. "Pelaksanaan Hukuman Mati Dalam Perspektif Hak Asasi Manusia." *Indonesian Journal of Law and Policy Studies* Vol. 1, No. 1 (May 2020)
- Hutapea, Bungasan. "Alternatif Penjatuhan Hukuman Mati Di Indonesia Dilihat Dari Perspektif HAM." *Jurnal Penelitian HAM* Vol. 7, No. 2 (December 2016)
- Kolopita, Satrio Putra. "Penegakan Hukum Atas Pidana Mati Terhadap Pelaku Tindak Pidana Narkotika." *Jurnal Lex Crimen* Vol. 2, No. 4 (August 2013).h. 92
- L.J. Van Apeldoorn, "Pengantar Ilmu Hukum", Balai Pustaka, Jakarta, 2015
- Megawaty Runtuuwu, Gabriela. "Penjatuhan Pidana Mati Bagi Pelaku Tindak Pidana Narkotika." *Jurnal Lex Crimen* Vol. 2, No. 6 (October 2013)
- Mulyadi, Lilik. "Pemidanaan Terhadap Pengedar Dan Pengguna Narkoba: Penelitian Asas, Teori, Norma Dan Praktik Peradilan." *Jurnal Hukum Dan Peradilan* Vol. 1, No. 2 (July 2012)
- P.A.F. Lamintang, 1997, *Dasar-Dasar Hukum Pidana Indonesia*, Citra Aditya Bakti, Bandung
- Panjaitan, Budi Sastram. "Menempatkan Pelaku Kejahatan Peredaran Gelap Narkotika Sebagai Pelaku Kejahatan Terhadap Genosida." *Jurnal Pionir LPPM Universitas Asahan* Vol. 5, No. 2 (2019)
- Purnomo, Agus. "Hukuman Mati Bagi Tindak Pidana Narkotika Di Indonesia: Perspektif Sosiologi Hukum." *De Jure: Jurnal Hukum Dan Syariah* Vol. 8, No. 1 (2016)
- Rukman, Auliah Andika. "Pidana Mati Ditinjau Dari Perspektif Sosiologis Dan Penegakan HAM." *Jurnal Equilibrium Pendidikan Sosiologi* Vol. 4, No. 1 (May 2016)
- Salundik. "Penegakan Hukuman Mati Dalam Tindak Pidana Narkotika." *Jurnal Ilmu Hukum Tambun Bungai* Vol. 1, No. 2 (September 2016)
- Sinta Herindrasti. "Drug-Free ASEAN 2025: Tantangan Indonesia Dalam Penanggulangan Penyalahgunaan Narkoba." *Jurnal Hubungan Internasional* Vol. 7, No. 1 (2018)
- Sumanto, Atet. "Efektifitas Pidana Mati Dalam Proses Penegakan Hukum Tindak Pidana Narkotika." *Jurnal Perspektif* Vol. 22, No. 1 (January 2017)
- Suyono Yoyok, *Hukum Kepolisian Kedudukan Polri Dalam System Ketatanegaraan Indonesia Setelah Perubahan UUD 1945*, (Yogyakarta: Laksbang Grafika, 2013)
- Viswandro, dkk, *Mengenal Profesi Penegak Hukum*, (Jakarta : Medpress Digital, 2015)

Legal Protection for Children as Intermediaries in the Sale and Purchase of Narcotics

Diana Gultom¹, Mhd. Azhali Siregar²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: azhalisiregar@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

The involvement of children in narcotics crimes as drug couriers is a series of evil conspiracy in carrying out illegal drug trafficking, but in the capacity of the category of children who help in trading or distribution by accompanying the owner of the goods with promises or enticements has often hit children of that age, this is a very concerning thing where the child has faced the law and is classified as having committed a drug crime. In this case, the child has committed an act, an evil conspiracy without rights or against the law offering for sale, selling, buying, receiving, being an intermediary in buying and selling, exchanging or handing over Class I Narcotics in the form of plants weighing more than 1 (one) kilogram or more than 5 (five) tree trunks or in the form of non-plants weighing more than 5 (five) grams. As a result of the action, the child as regulated and threatened with criminal penalties in Article 114 Paragraph (2) Jo Article 132 Paragraph (1) of Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics Jo Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Child Criminal Justice System. The type of research in writing this thesis is carried out with a type of normative legal research in the form of library research using 3 legal materials, namely primary legal materials, secondary legal materials and tertiary legal materials. This legal research focuses on library studies which means that it will examine and review more existing and applicable legal regulations. The results of this study indicate that Legal Protection for Children as Intermediaries in the Sale and Purchase of Narcotics in the Indonesian Legal System in Decision Number: 18/Pid.Sus-Anak/2023/PN.Bnj. namely by referring to Article 114 Paragraph (2) Jo Article 132 Paragraph (1) of Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics Jo Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System, then the Child is Muhammad Pajar, proven legally and convincingly guilty of committing the crime of "Without the Right to Commit Evil Conspiracy" Selling Class I Narcotics that are not Plants Weighing More than 5 Grams The Panel of Judges at the Binjai District Court has Assigning actions to children Muhammad Pajar, in the form of Action returned to parents and Order AA child named Muhammad Fajar was released from detention at the Temporary Child Placement Institution (LPAS). The basis for the judge's consideration is the Child Criminal Justice System as regulated in Article 69 paragraph (1) of the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Child Criminal Justice System. This Criminal Policy is a grand design of the Indonesian Government's legal policy that recognizes children's human rights with the aim that children are the Nation's Capital Assets that can be useful in the future so that Special Regulations are needed in Resolving Cases that befall them. With the hope that the Child can Return to Society as the Nation's Capital Assets in the future.

Keywords: Legal Protection, Child Crime, Narcotics.

INTRODUCTION

Law enforcement in Indonesia is in the spotlight by the public and the media because law enforcement is considered a weapon to fight all types of crimes that are increasingly developing where law enforcement officers are required to resolve legal problems so that the objectives of the law, namely legal certainty, justice and benefits, can be achieved. Including criminal acts committed by children. Today, various types of crimes have involved children as perpetrators of criminal acts or crimes.

One of the phenomena that often occurs today is drug abuse. This is very worrying because drug abuse by children does not only occur in Indonesia, the same thing is happening in many countries in the world. The circulation of narcotics in Indonesia continues to increase and has even reached a very worrying level. As is known, narcotics are currently not only distributed in big cities but have reached the rural level and perpetrators of drug abuse are not only those who are adults but have spread to all levels of society ranging from students, students, entrepreneurs, officials, street children and so on.¹

The spread of drugs among children has reached a stage that is very difficult to control, this fact is very worrying because children are the next generation of the nation in the future. Children need special guidance and protection. Children generally have a great sense of curiosity, so that information or something new is worth trying without realizing the consequences of the new thing leading to good or vice versa.²

In dealing with and overcoming the actions and behavior of children, it is necessary to consider the position of children with all their characteristics and characteristics. Although children can determine their own steps based on their thoughts, feelings and will, their surroundings can influence their behavior. The development of drug abuse is increasing day by day and the government has issued regulations governing the handling of children who are perpetrators of drug abuse crimes, namely Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics. While children who are perpetrators of criminal acts or crimes are regulated in Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System, while children as victims are regulated in Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 35 of 2014 concerning amendments to Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 23 of 2002 concerning Child Protection.³

In the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 35 of 2014 concerning Amendments to Law Number 23 of 2002 concerning Child Protection, Article 59 states that: "Article 59 (1) The Government, Regional Governments, and other state institutions are obliged and responsible for providing Special Protection to Children. (2) Special Protection to Children as referred to in paragraph (1) is given to: a. Children in emergency situations b. Children in conflict with the law c. Children from minority and isolated groups d. Children who are exploited economically and/or sexually e. Children who are victims of abuse of narcotics, alcohol, psychotropics, and other addictive substances, etc."⁴

Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics has regulated criminal provisions for anyone who can be subject to criminal penalties along with fines that must be borne by drug abusers or can be called perpetrators of drug crimes. In the Narcotics Law itself, there is no specific distinction between perpetrators of drug crimes. Both perpetrators who order to do

¹Barda Nawawi Arif, *Several Aspects of Criminal Law Enforcement and Development Policy*, PT Citra Aditya Bagti, Bandung 1998, page 153

²Abdussalam, *Child Protection Law*, Restu Agung, Jakarta, 2007, page 5.

³Maidin Gultom, *Legal Protection for Children*. Bandung PT Refika Aditama 2018. Pages 113-135.

⁴Lilik Mulyadi. *Juvenile Courts in Indonesia and Their Theory, Practice and Problems*. Bandung, Mandar Maju. 2005 page 133.

it, those who participate in doing it and advocates or assistants can be called perpetrators of criminal acts.⁵

In Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning narcotics, Article 112 states:

- (1) Any person who without rights or against the law possesses, stores, controls, or provides Class I Narcotics that are not plants, shall be punished with imprisonment for a minimum of 4 (four) years and a maximum of 12 (twelve) years and a fine of at least IDR 800,000,000.00 (eight hundred million rupiah) and a maximum of IDR 8,000,000,000.00 (eight billion rupiah).
- (2) In the case of the act of possessing, storing, controlling or providing Class I Narcotics other than plants as referred to in paragraph (1) weighing more than 5 (five) grams, the perpetrator shall be punished with life imprisonment or a minimum of 5 (five) years and a maximum of 20 (twenty) years imprisonment and a maximum fine as referred to in paragraph (1) plus 1/3 (one third).

On the other hand, currently in Indonesia, the implementation of the juvenile criminal justice system is based on the Juvenile Criminal Justice System Law (Law No. 11 of 2012). In this Law, children in conflict with the law are handled by prioritizing or being diversionary.⁶ Article 7 of Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System, is:⁷

1. At the level of investigation, prosecution and examination of children's cases in district courts, diversion must be attempted.
2. Diversion as referred to in paragraph (1) is implemented in cases where the crime is committed:
 - a. Threatened with imprisonment of less than 7 (seven) years; and
 - b. Not a repetition of the crime.

Related to decision Number: 18/Pid.Sus-Anak/2023/PN.Bnj, which State Child Muhammad Pajar is guilty of committing a narcotics crime as regulated and is subject to criminal penalties in First, Article 114 Paragraph (2) in conjunction with Article 132 Paragraph (1) of Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics in conjunction with Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System.⁸

That in the case of a criminal act committed by a child, the Public Prosecutor has charged him with an alternative charge, so that the Judge, taking into account the legal facts above, directly chose the first alternative charge as regulated in Article 114 Paragraph (2) in conjunction with Article 132 Paragraph (1) of Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics

⁵Rosidah, Nikmah and Rini Fathonah. 2019. Juvenile Justice Law. Bandar Lampung: Zam-Zam Tower. page 91.

⁶The Diversion Process is carried out through deliberation involving the Child and his/her parents/guardians, the victim and/or his/her parents/guardians, Community Guidance Officers, and Professional Social Workers based on a Restorative Justice approach.

⁷Samosir, Djisman. 1982. The Function of Prison Punishment in the Convict Development System in Indonesia. Jakarta: Pradnya Paramita page 72.

⁸Siregar, Bismar. 1986. Legal Justice in Various Aspects of National Law. Jakarta: Rajawali.

in conjunction with Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System.⁹

According to Article 2 of Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System, it states that Children in Conflict with the Law are children in conflict with the law, children who are victims of criminal acts, and children who are witnesses to criminal acts. Then Article 3 states that Children in Conflict with the Law, hereinafter referred to as Children, are children who are 12 (twelve) years old but not yet 18 (eighteen) years old who are suspected of committing a crime and if connected with the Decision of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia Number: 1398 K/Pid/1994 dated June 30, 1995, the terminology of the word "whoever" or "hij" as anyone who must be made a Child.

Basically, every person as a legal subject (supporter of rights and obligations) can be made a Child in conflict with the law. This is because every person is considered capable of taking legal action unless the law determines otherwise.¹⁰

Meanwhile, regarding whether or not they can be held accountable, this will be proven further based on the facts in the trial regarding the main case and regarding the Child. Therefore, related to this element, it only needs to be proven whether the Children are legal subjects (supporters of rights and obligations) and they have been properly made as Children in this case, in the sense that they are the people referred to as Children in conflict with the law in the Public Prosecutor's Indictment.

Meanwhile, regarding whether or not he can be held accountable, this will be proven further based on the facts in the trial regarding the main case and regarding the Child. Therefore, related to this element, it only needs to be proven whether the Child is a legal subject (supporter of rights and obligations) and he has been properly made a Child in this case, in the sense that he is the person referred to as a Child in the Public Prosecutor's Indictment.¹¹

then to fulfill the provisions of Article 60 paragraph (3) of Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System, which states The judge is obliged to consider the social research report from the Community Guidance Officer before making a decision on the case, then the judge after hearing the recommendations and conclusions of the Class I Medan Community Guidance Officer which were read out in court, the main point of which is that the child be given the lightest possible punishment or the child be returned to his parents in accordance with Article 71 and Article 82 Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System.¹²

In this case, it was revealed in court that the child was merely a victim of a trap set up by law enforcement officers who took refuge under the legal basis. Article 24 of the

⁹Usman, AH (2015). Legal awareness of society and government as a factor the establishment of a state of law in Indonesia. *Journal of Juridika Insight*, 30 (1), pages 26-53.

¹⁰Sutarto, S. (2021). Implementation of Medical Rehabilitation and Social Rehabilitation for Victims of Drug Abuse Reviewed from the Theory of Relative Punishment. *Indonesian Law Enforcement Journal*, 2(1) pages 115-135.

¹¹Mukri, SG (2019). Educational Actions for Handling Drug Abuse. *IS*, 3 (1), pages 25-30.

¹²Eka Rose Indrawati. 2018. Job Training as a Criminal Sanction Against Children in Conflict with the Law. *Rechtidee*, Vol. 13, No. 1, June 2018. page 14.

Regulation of the Chief of Police Number 14 of 2012 concerning Investigation Management with undercover purchases in the investigation of narcotics crimes, namely the technique of disguising oneself as a prospective buyer (undercover buy) which is carried out to search for and collect evidence with which the evidence can shed light on narcotics crimes and to find the suspect..

Undercover purchases should target the arrest of drug dealers, especially on a large scale, and not target small-scale drug crimes, especially based on the legal fact that the child is not the target of the investigation, but the child is only influenced by the invitation of an adult, namely witness Teguh, with the promise of being invited to go clubbing for free, so that the child agrees to accompany witness Teguh to pick up narcotics that will be sold by witness Teguh to the police witnesses.¹³

The child in this case was also not directly involved in the crime of selling narcotics, because the child only agreed and consented that the witness Teguh would first pick up and then deliver the ecstasy narcotics to the buyer and after that they would club for free. so it is very unfortunate that this technique was used to make the Child a suspect when in fact the Child is not a drug dealer or dealer, but the Child is only a third grade vocational school student and the narcotics used as evidence in this case also do not belong to the Child but to witness Teguh who will be sold to police witnesses.

In the decision of the judge handling this case, taking into account Article 114 paragraph (2) in conjunction with Article 132 paragraph (1) of Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics, Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System and Law Number 8 of 1981 concerning Criminal Procedure Law and other relevant laws and regulations, the panel of judges issued a decision by ordering the child to...Muhammad Pajar, released from detention at the Temporary Child Placement Institution (LPAS) immediately after this verdict is pronounced.

From the description above, the author's desire arose to conduct a proposal study entitled Legal Protection for Children as Perpetrators of Narcotics Crimes as an Effort to Renew the Legal System in Indonesia (Study of Decision Number: 18/Pid.Sus-Anak/2023/PN.Bnj)

From the description of the problems above, we can draw the following problems which will be discussed in this research:

3. How is the Legal Protection for Children as Intermediaries in the Sale and Purchase of Narcotics in the Indonesian Legal System?
4. What are the legal considerations of the panel of judges in narcotics crimes against children in the Decision Study Number: 18/Pid.Sus-Anak/2023/PN.Bnj?

¹³Supriyanta. 2012. Democratization in Law Enforcement. Journal of Legal Discourse. Vol. VII No. 1 Year 2012. page 81.

METHOD

In conducting a scientific research, it is clear that a method must be used as a characteristic of science. The method contains the meaning of a way to find information in a planned and systematic way. The steps taken must be clear and there must be firm boundaries in order to avoid interpretations that are too broad.

1. Types of research

The type of research used is normative legal research, namely research that focuses on norms and this research requires legal materials as primary data.

2. Nature of Research

Meanwhile, the nature of the research that the author uses is descriptive analytical research in the sense that all legal materials that the author obtains will be described and explained and then analyzed.

3. Legal Materials

a. *Material Primary law is legal material that has binding force, namely in the form of statutory regulations such as:*

1. *The 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia;*
2. *Criminal Code*
3. *Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System*
4. *Law Number 35 of 2014 concerning Child Protection*
5. *UURI Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics*
6. *Law Number 8 of 1981 concerning Criminal Procedure Law*
7. *Decision Number: 18/Pid.Sus-Anak/2023/PN.Bnj*

b. *Secondary legal materials are those that provide explanations to primary legal materials, including books, research results, legal opinions, and other documents that are relevant to the problem being researched.*

c. *Tertiary legal materials are supporting legal materials that provide guidance and understanding of primary and secondary legal materials, including legal dictionaries or other language dictionaries.*

4. Technique Collection of Legal Materials.

To answer the existing problems, researchers collect legal materials through document studies (literature studies) including primary legal materials, secondary legal materials and tertiary legal materials, namely by conducting an inventory and identification of a number of laws and regulations. document laws, legal notes, scientific works and reading materials/literature originating from legal science in the form of books, articles, journals and research results that are related to the research being raised.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Legal Protection for Children as Intermediaries in the Sale and Purchase of Narcotics in the Legal System in Indonesia

To get answers to this legal issue related to legal regulations in criminal cases involving children in particular, on this occasion the author will explain among others:

a. Criminal Policy in the Indonesian Penal System

1) Said by Muladi and Barda Nawawi¹⁴ crime prevention policies or efforts that are an integral part or a complete part of efforts to protect the community (social defense) and efforts to achieve social welfare (social welfare) which are connected to each other in a criminal justice system with the aim of protecting society in achieving welfare. Furthermore, Sudarto provides an understanding that criminal policy or criminal policy is a rational and organized effort by a society to overcome crime, this definition is taken from the thoughts of Marc Ancel who formulated it as "the rational organization of the control of crime by society".¹⁵ Next is Mustofa's story¹⁶ say legal policy or legal politics. From the description above, it can be understood that criminal policy is the government's effort to regulate legal policies, including criminal policies in criminal law, so that the government's criminal policy is an integral part of the government's legal policy in national life.

2) *Implementation* Criminalization of Juvenile Delinquency in the Formulation of Criminal Offenses in the Juvenile Justice System Law

Schools saying "The law is er, doch het moet wordsen gevonden", which means it is an illusion if we assume that positive law or the Constitution has completely regulated all life's problems.⁹ This adage, if interpreted, means that a law cannot possibly completely regulate a problem, so that in this case, the regulation of criminal law outside the Criminal Code is a policy to fulfill legal needs and ideals.

Criminal policy efforts by formulating a child's actions in this case for example against juvenile delinquency into a criminal offense is an effort known as Criminalization¹⁰ on the other hand efforts to eliminate criminal acts into ordinary actions are commonly known as decriminalization¹¹. Sudarto said as quoted by Muladi mentioning the pouring of a type of crime or Criminal is an effort of Criminalization or the process of determining a person's actions as an act that can be punished. The process ends with the formation of a law, where the act is threatened with a sanction in the form of a criminal offense.¹²

In the effort to criminalize an act or action into a criminal act, two basic questions arise, namely: 1). What act should be a criminal act and 2). What sanctions should be imposed on the Violator.¹³

Another thing that is also very crucial or important to note in the formulation

¹⁴Barda Nawari Arief, 2001, Problems of Law Enforcement and Crime Prevention Policy, Citra Aditya Bakti, Bandung, page 2.

¹⁵Eddy OS Hiariej, 2009, Principles of Legality and Legal Discovery in Criminal Law, Erlangga, Jakarta. Page 55.

¹⁶Sudarto, 1981, Law and Criminal Law, Bandung, Alumni, page 38.

of criminal offenses in laws outside the Criminal Code is that the formulation must be in accordance with the genus norm or general norms contained in the Criminal Code¹⁴: 1) The nature of the act, whether it is against the law or a criminal act; 2). Criminal liability or error and 3). Sanctions, both criminal and other actions that can be imposed along with the principles of criminal law that underlie them.¹⁷

Based on the description above, the author can conclude that the legal regulation of acts or actions as a criminal offense outside the Criminal Code or commonly known as Criminalization is a form of government criminal policy. where in the formulation must be in accordance with the Genus Norm or general norm, namely the Criminal Code which indicates the formulation of criminal offenses in a Law outside the Criminal Code including in this case the Law on the Child Criminalization System (SPPA) and the Narcotics Law which has been specifically regulated which is an integral part of the criminal subsystem (Criminal justice System) and the implementation of this government criminal policy is an implementation or manifestation of the principle of criminal legality *nullum delictum nulla poena sine praevia lege poenali*.

In understanding the application of criminal sanctions to children, the basic things that need to be understood are:

1. Age Limit for Criminal Responsibility of Children, referring to Article 1 number (3) of the Law on the Juvenile Criminal Justice System, states that "Children in Conflict with the Law, hereinafter referred to as children, are children who are 12 (twelve) years old, but not yet 18 (eighteen) years old, who are suspected of committing a crime." From the formulation of the address norm of the article, it can be understood that the minimum and maximum limits are that the age of children who are in conflict with or in conflict with the law is 12 years to 17 years or at least not yet 18 years old. These minimum and maximum limits are an affirmation of the norm's command regarding the age limit for criminal responsibility of children, where the minimum and maximum limits in the material content of the norm are cumulative and alternative in their application;

The implementation of Child Criminalization in Indonesia has gone through several phases, including: a. The Circular Letter of the Supreme Court Number 800 of 1959;¹⁶ b. The Instruction of the Supreme Court MA/Pemb/048/71 of 1971¹⁷ c. The Circular Letter of the Attorney General Number P. 1/20 issued on March 30, 1951¹⁸, d. The Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 3 of 1997;¹⁹ e. The Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System.

Based on the description above, it can be clearly and explicitly concluded that the phasesThe implementation phase of child criminalization practices develops and moves dynamically according to the situation and needs of the law itself, where currently the direction of the government's Criminal Policy in the Child Criminal Justice System is oriented towards special protection and/or carried out with a child welfare approach. This is

¹⁷SR Sianturi, 1986, Principles of Criminal Law in Indonesia and Their Implementation, Alumni AHAEM- PTHAEM, Jakarta, p. 211

done because in essence children are unable to avoid problems independently so that the role of all parties or cross-sectors including the method of sanctions given to children is not only punishment or punishment but prioritizes the development side with the hope that in the future children who are in conflict with the law after serving their sentence can return to normal activities and are able to develop as valuable assets for the country.

Seeing the description above, it is very clear that the impact of drug abuse is very dangerous for a nation, so that the government with the authority it has is very right to determine the abuse or distribution of narcotics without rights and against the law into a criminalization policy by issuing Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics related to narcotics crimes by children including narcotics intermediary crimes involving children as perpetrators, then as the principle of *lex Specialist Drogat Lex Generalis* (Special Law Overrides General Law) Juncto the principle of *Lex Posterior Derogat Legi Priori* (the new law overrides the old law).¹⁸

Therefore, the handling of cases involving children in conflict with the law, including cases involving the sale and purchase of narcotics by children, is legally subject to the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System as stated in Article 69 paragraph (1) of the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Criminal Justice System, which states "Children can only be sentenced to criminal penalties or be subject to action based on the provisions of this Law.

Based on the description above, as with the legal issue in the first point in this formulation, the Regulation of Criminal Law in Cases of Narcotics Abuse Crimes by Children in Conflict with the Law, it can be concluded that the government's legal regulation of Narcotics Crimes by Children is carried out based on the government's criminal policy, namely that in handling criminal cases involving children, including the crime of intermediary for the sale and purchase of Narcotics by children, an examination is carried out according to the Law applicable to the Juvenile Criminal Justice System as regulated in Article 69 paragraph (1) of the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System.

b. Legal considerations of the panel of judges in narcotics crimes against children (study on Decision Number 18/Pid.Sus-Anak/2023/PN Bnj)

Here the judge can choose from two options submitted by the Public Prosecutor to be considered, whichever direction the charges are, based on the facts revealed in the trial. The judge chooses the second option after observing and scrutinizing the facts revealed in the trial. for that it will be proven whether the Child has committed an act or crime as formulated and threatened with criminal penalties in Article 112 Paragraph (1) of the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics in conjunction with the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System (SPPA), with the following elements: Element of Every Person, element Without rights or

¹⁸Muammar, Criminology Study of Narcotics Distribution (A Study in East Aceh District), Vol. 7 No. 1, January 1, 2019. p. 93

against the law, element of possessing, storing, controlling, or providing Class I Narcotics not plants and element carried out by the child.

Regarding these elements, the Judge considered the following:

1. Every Person's Element

It is the person as the legal subject (the Child himself) that all the identities read out from the Public Prosecutor's indictment in this case are appropriate and have been confirmed by the Child.

The Child (Muhammad Pajar) was brought forward in this case, and during the trial it was proven that the Child was physically and mentally healthy and was able to be held responsible for his actions, so the Judge was of the opinion that the Element of Every Person had been legally fulfilled.

According to Article 2 of Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System, it states that Children in Conflict with the Law are children in conflict with the law, children who are victims of criminal acts, and children who are witnesses to criminal acts, then Article 3 states that Children in Conflict with the Law, hereinafter referred to as Children, are children who are 12 (twelve) years old, but not yet 18 (eighteen) years old who are suspected of committing a crime and if connected with the Decision of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia Number: 1398 K/Pid/1994 dated June 30, 1995, the terminology of the word "whoever" or "hij" as anyone who must be made a Child. Basically, every person as a legal subject (supporter of rights and obligations) can be made a Child in Conflict with the Law. This is because everyone is considered capable of taking legal action unless the law determines otherwise.¹⁹

2. Elements without rights or against the law

Without any right or against the law, offering for sale, selling, buying, receiving, becoming an intermediary in buying and selling, exchanging or handing over class I narcotics in the form of plants weighing more than 1 (one) kilogram or more than 5 (five) tree trunks or in the form of Not a Plant Weighs 5 (Five) Grams. IThe term without rights or against the law is also called the term *wederrechtelijk*, "according to Drs. PAF Lamintang, SH, in his book *Basics of Indonesian Criminal Law*, this *wederrechtelijk* includes the following definitions: Contrary to objective law, contrary to the rights of others or, without rights that exist in a person or, without authority.

In the provisions of Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics, there are provisions that in the circulation, distribution and/or use of Narcotics, special permission or approval from the Minister as the authorized official must be obtained upon the recommendation of the Food and Drug Supervisory Agency (Vide: Article 8 Paragraph (1) Jo Article 36 Paragraph (1) and Paragraph (3), Article 39 Paragraph (2) of the Republic of Indonesia Law No. 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics).²⁰

¹⁹Muammar, *Criminology Study of Narcotics Distribution (A Study in East Aceh Regency)*, Vol. 7 No. 1, January 1, 2019. page 71.

²⁰Muammar, *Criminology Study of Narcotics Distribution (A Study in East Aceh District)*, Vol. 7 No. 1, January 1, 2019.

Thus, the Judge is of the opinion that the Element Without Rights is part of the Element Against the Law, namely any act that violates written law (statutory regulations) and/or general principles of unwritten law. In this case, the Element Without Rights is without permission and/or approval from the authorized party for that, namely the Minister on the recommendation of the Food and Drug Supervisory Agency or other authorized officials based on Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics and other relevant Laws and Regulations.

Thus, the Judge is of the opinion that because the Child's daily work is not a job and does not have a special permit and/or approval from the authorized party for that (Minister of Health) so that the Child is not authorized or does not have the right based on the provisions of the applicable laws and regulations to control Class I Narcotics, not plants. Thus, based on the description, the Judge is of the opinion that the second element of Without Rights or Unlawfully has been legally fulfilled.²¹

In accordance with the explanation in Article 7 of Law Number 35 of 2009, narcotics can only be used for the benefit of health services and/or the development of science and technology. Furthermore, in Article 8 paragraph (2), in limited quantities, Class I narcotics can be used for the benefit of the development of science and technology and for diagnostic reagents, as well as laboratory reagents after first obtaining approval from the Minister on the recommendation of the Head of the Food and Drug Supervisory Agency.

Article 1 number 18 of Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics states that Criminal Conspiracy is the act of two or more people who collude or agree to carry out, implement, assist, participate in, order, encourage, facilitate, provide consultation, become members of a Narcotics crime organization, or organize a Narcotics crime. The child's actions in agreeing to accompany witness Teguh to take ecstasy narcotics to sell have fulfilled all the elements of Article 114 paragraph (2) of Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics. Therefore, the provisions regarding attempted criminal acts cannot be applied to the child.

The agreement or consent of the Child to accompany and assist witness Teguh to sell Class I Narcotics constitutes a criminal act of conspiracy to commit a narcotics crime as referred to in Article 114. Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics so that with the existence of a joint intention or mutual agreement between the Child, witness Teguh and witness Rahma Agung Satria to sell Class I Narcotics has shown that the Child's actions are the actions of two or more people with the intention of agreeing to commit a crime. Thus the element of "evil conspiracy to commit a Narcotics crime as referred to in Article 114" has been fulfilled.²²

Because all the elements of Article 114 Paragraph (2) Jo Article 132 Paragraph (1) of Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics Jo Law No. 11 of 2012 concerning

²¹Muammar, Criminology Study of Narcotics Distribution (A Study in East Aceh District), Vol. 7 No. 1, January 1, 2019.

²²Muammar, Criminology Study of Narcotics Distribution (A Study in East Aceh District), Vol. 7 No. 1, January 1, 2019

the Juvenile Criminal Justice System has been fulfilled, then the Child must be declared to have been proven legally and convincingly to have committed the crime as charged in the first alternative charge.

But in his decision The judge will implement the Juvenile Criminal Justice System which must prioritize the Restorative Justice approach which resolves criminal cases by involving the perpetrator, victim, the perpetrator/victim's family, and other related parties to jointly seek a just solution by emphasizing restoration to the original state, and not retaliation based on the principle of deprivation of liberty and punishment as a last resort.

In order to fulfill the provisions of Article 60 paragraph (1) of Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System, which states that before making a decision, the Judge shall give the parents the opportunity to express matters that are beneficial to the Child, then after the Judge gave the opportunity, the Child's parents said that the best thing for the Child was to be returned to the Parents so that the Child could continue his education, which is currently in class 3 at the Yayasan Perguruan Harapan Vocational School. Then in court, the Child's parents said that they had realized their mistake because they had been negligent in looking after and guiding the Child and also promised to supervise the Child even more in the future and would carry out their full responsibilities as parents to the Child.

In order to fulfill the provisions of Article 60 paragraph (3) of Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System, which states that the Judge is obliged to consider the community research report from the Community Guidance Officer before making a decision on the case, in accordance with Article 71 and Article 82 of Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System, because currently the Child is still an active student and is currently in class 3 of vocational school and also states that the Child's parents are still able to provide the Child's rights and are fully responsible for the Child's growth and development, including carrying out better supervision in the future.

In further consideration, then the Judge does not agree with the demands of the Public Prosecutor as in his indictment which is not in line with the Principles and Objectives of the Child Criminal Justice System Law, nor does he pay attention to the facts revealed in court that the Child is only a victim of a trap by law enforcement officers who are protected under the legal basis of Article 24 of the Regulation of the Chief of Police Number 14 of 2012 concerning Investigation Management with undercover purchases in the investigation of narcotics crimes, namely the technique of disguising as a prospective buyer (undercover buy) which is carried out to find and collect evidence with which evidence makes clear the narcotics crime and in order to find the suspect, undercover purchases should target the arrest of narcotics sellers and especially on a large scale and not target narcotics crimes on a small scale, especially based on the legal fact that the Child is not the target of the investigation but the Child is only influenced by the invitation of adults.

So it is very unfortunate that this technique is used to make a child a suspect when

in fact the child is not a drug dealer or dealer, but rather the child is only a student.

Criminal acts or sanctions imposed on the Child, in Article 1 number 3 of Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Child Criminal Justice System. Namely, a Child in conflict with the law, hereinafter referred to as a Child, is a child who is 12 (twelve) years old, but not yet 18 (eighteen) years old who is suspected of committing a crime.

From the existing legal facts, the Child has been proven to have committed a crime in accordance with the Public Prosecutor's Indictment. It has also been proven that the Child was born on August 6, 2001, so that at the time the Child committed the crime the Child was around 17 (seventeen) years and 8 (eight) months old, so that it is still classified as a child's age according to Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System, then the Child can be categorized as a "Child in conflict with the law" as referred to in Article 1 number 3 of the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System.²³

Against the Judge's Decision Ordering the Child Muhammad Pajar, released from detention at the Temporary Child Placement Institution (LPAS) immediately after this decision is pronounced and Based on the matters considered above, the imposition of a criminal sentence on the Child below by the Judge is deemed to be in accordance with the purpose of punishment, namely not as revenge or sorrow, but rather to educate and make the Child aware of his wrongdoings, in addition to that so that it can also be used as a lesson for other people and even all members of society so that they do not commit acts as have been committed by the Child.

In order to impose a criminal penalty on a child, it is necessary to first consider the aggravating and mitigating circumstances of the child:

Aggravating circumstances:²⁴

- a. The actions of children are very contrary to the government's program which is currently aggressively eradicating drug abuse.
- b. Children's actions can damage the nation's future generations and threaten national defense and resilience.
- c. Children's actions include actions that disturb society.

Mitigating circumstances:

- a. The child has never been punished; - Children behave politely in court.
- b. The child is still young and is expected to improve himself in the future.
- c. The child regrets his actions and promises not to repeat the unlawful actions again.
- d. The Child Family is ready to guide and educate the Child better.

Taking into account, Article 112 Paragraph (1) of the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics in conjunction with the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System (SPPA) and the

²³Muammar, Criminology Study of Narcotics Distribution (A Study in East Aceh District), Vol. 7 No. 1, January 1, 2019

²⁴Muammar, Criminology Study of Narcotics Distribution (A Study in East Aceh District), Vol. 7 No. 1, January 1, 2019

Republic of Indonesia Law Number 8 of 1981 concerning Criminal Procedure Law and other relevant laws and regulations.²⁵

In the narcotics law, there is no age limit for narcotics crimes, so children can be punished according to the sanctions contained in the narcotics law.²⁶

The best treatment and priority must be given to children in conflict with the law because here we must consider the child's mental development if criminal sanctions are imposed that are not in accordance with the child's mental development. So in this case we must really pay attention to the future. No less important, we must know the child's environment, location, social status and how the child was raised in the midst of his family. Because wrong parenting has the potential to lead the child to act beyond his knowledge so that he is in conflict with the law.²⁷

Drug crimes committed by children must still be given sanctions to provide education to the child on how to be responsible for their actions. Children are assets for a country so that legal sanctions must be in accordance with the age, behavior and mentality of the child. Because this concerns the child himself, his future and social life. Rehabilitation is considered very necessary for the child about the dangers of narcotics.²⁸

Criminal liability for drug abuse by children has actually been regulated in the laws and regulations in Indonesia. However, the punishment of children must pay attention to the physical and moral aspects of the child. The physical appearance of the child can be seen from the child's mind and intelligence. The child's morals can be seen from his/her psyche, such as abnormalities, mental disorders, so that if the child experiences mental disorders like that, he/she will not be held legally accountable. To determine this legal liability, the judge will be very careful. Considering that if it is associated with the child committing the crime, it is a very important element, and must be resolved with legal accountability.²⁹

Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the juvenile criminal justice system which has been in effect since July 30, 2014 is more nurturing and provides protection to children. Previously, sanctions for juvenile crimes always caused debate, because they had consequences for socialization, behavior or stigma in society towards the child. So Law Number 3 of 1997 concerning juvenile courts is no longer relevant.

Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the juvenile criminal justice system which also has a double track system, which regulates criminal sanctions and actions. So that the sanctions imposed better reflect justice for the perpetrator and the victim.

²⁵Muammar, *Criminology Study of Narcotics Distribution (A Study in East Aceh District)*, Vol. 7 No. 1, January 1, 2019

²⁶I Wayan Govinda Tantra, I Made Minggu Widyantara and Luh Putu Suryani, *Criminal Liability of Children as Couriers in Narcotics Crimes*, *Journal of Legal Analogy*, Volume 2, Number 2, 2020

²⁷Samsul Arifin, *Criminal Liability for Children as Narcotics Couriers*, *Justitia Jurnal Hukum*, Volume 1 No. 6 April 2021 Print ISSN: 2579-9983, E ISSN: 25796380 pages 136-142.

²⁸Ni Kd Saras Iswari Gunnanda, *Criminal Liability of Children Who Use Narcotics*, *Kertha Desa Journal*, Vol. 9 No. 6, pages 66-73, P-ISSN: 2302-528X, E-ISSN: 2303-0593.

²⁹I Wayan Gede Phalosa Jitaksu Wahendra, I Wayan Parsa, "Criminal Accountability for Perpetrators of New Types of Narcotics Abuse Crimes in Indonesia". *Udayana University Law Students Scientific Journal* 8, No. 6 (2019).

Law Number 35 of 2014 concerning narcotics, although it does not specifically regulate criminal sanctions for children. However, in principle, sanctions are still given or charged in the narcotics article or law. But it must still consider the special provisions of criminal acts committed by children, namely Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the juvenile criminal justice system.³⁰

CLOSING

Conclusion

Based on the discussion in the chapter above, the following conclusions can be drawn that (1) the government's legal regulation of narcotics crimes by children is carried out based on criminal policy or government legal policy, namely that in handling criminal cases against children, including the crime of intermediary for the sale and purchase of narcotics by children, an examination is carried out according to the applicable law on the Juvenile Criminal Justice System as regulated in Article 69 paragraph (1) of the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System. This Criminal Policy is a grand design of the Indonesian Government's legal policy that recognizes children's human rights with the aim that children are the nation's capital assets that can be useful in the future, so that special regulations are needed in resolving cases that befall them. With the hope that the child can return to society as the nation's capital assets in the future. (2) The consideration of the Panel of Examining Judges at the Binjai District Court only imposed action on children. Muhammad Pajar, in the form of action of returning it to the parents and ordering the child Muhammad Pajar, released from detention at the Temporary Child Placement Institution (LPAS), in the decision, it is indicated that the decision was made based on considerations: the development of growth and development and the best interests of the child after serving his sentence, this is a form of manifestation of the state's presence in realizing protection, paying attention to the welfare of children as mandated in Law Number 35 of 2014 concerning Amendments to Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 23 of 2002 concerning Child Protection in conjunction with Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System.

Here the judge considers the elements, namely the element of every person, the element without rights or against the law, the element of possessing, storing, controlling, or providing Class I Narcotics other than plants and the element carried out by the child. With the consideration that the Child is able to be responsible, then it must be declared guilty by considering Article 82 paragraph (1) point a, then the Child should be given action in the form of being returned to the parents, so the Child has been detained in the Temporary Child Placement Institution (LPAS), and while the decision that will be imposed on him is the action of being returned to the parents. The detention that the Child has undergone has been sufficient to provide a lesson and deterrent effect for the Child and his parents with the hope

³⁰Asep Syarifuddin Hidayat, Samul Anam, Muhammad Ishar Helmi, Legal Protection for Children as Narcotics Couriers, SALAM; Journal of Social & Cultural Syar-i FSH UIN Syarif Hidayatullah Jakarta Vol. 5 No. 3 (2018), pp.307-330

that the Child and his parents will learn from the incident and try to be better and fight to continue the Child's education which was interrupted due to the detention carried out on the Child for the sake of the Child's future and the nation's generation.

Suggestion

It is suggested that related to the existence of criminal sanctions against children as perpetrators of drug abuse, the legal provisions of which are contained in Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Child Criminal Justice System. In the future, it is hoped that policy makers will form a special law which is more specifically related to criminal sanctions for child perpetrators of drug abuse. Against child perpetrators of drug abuse. The existence of Law Number 35 of 2014 concerning Child Protection which provides protection law against perpetrators of criminal acts. However, this law still has many legal gaps and legal ambiguities in its implementation and in the future there will be a legal product itself related to legal protection for children who abuse narcotics.

It is suggested that the imposition of criminal penalties on children by judges should be seen as being in accordance with the purpose of punishment, namely not as revenge or sorrow, but rather to educate and make children aware of their wrongdoings, in addition to that, so that it can also be used as a lesson for other people and even all members of society so that they do not commit acts as have been committed by the child.

REFERENCES

- Abdussalam, Hukum Perlindungan Anak, Restu Agung, Jakarta, 2007
- Asep Syarifuddin Hidayat, Samul Anam, Muhammad Ishar Helmi, Perlindungan Hukum Terhadap Anak Sebagai Kurir Narkotika (Legal Protection for Children as Narcotics Couriers), SALAM; Jurnal Sosial & Budaya Syar-i FSH UIN Syarif Hidayatullah Jakarta Vol. 5 No. 3 (2018)
- Barda Nawari Arief, 2001, Masalah Penegakan Hukum dan Kebijakan Penanggulangan Kejahatan, Citra Aditya Bakti, Bandung
- Barda Nawawi Arif, Beberapa Aspek Kebijaksanaan penegakan dan pengembangan Hukum pidana, PT Citra Aditya Bagti, Bandung 1998
- Eddy O.S. Hiariej, 2009, Asas Legalitas dan Penemuan Hukum Dalam Hukum Pidana, Erlangga, Jakarta
- Eka Rose Indrawati. 2018. Pelatihan Kerja Sebagai Sanksi Pidana Terhadap Anak Yang Berkonflik Dengan Hukum. *Rechtidee*, Vol. 13, No. 1, Juni 2018
- I Wayan Gede Phalosa Jitaksu Wahendra, I Wayan Parsa, "Pertanggungjawaban Pidana Terhadap Pelaku Tindak Pidana Penyalahgunaan Narkotika Jenis Baru di Indonesia". *Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa Hukum Universitas Udayana* 8, no. 6 (2019)
- I Wayan Govinda Tantra, I Made Minggu Widyantara dan Luh Putu Suryani, Pertanggungjawaban Pidana Anak Sebagai Kurir dalam Tindak Pidana Narkotika, *Jurnal Analogi Hukum*, Volume 2, Nomor 2, 2020
- Korban Penyalahgunaan Narkotika Ditinjau Dari Teori Pidanaan

- Lilik Mulyadi. Pengadilan Anak di Indonesia dan Teori, Praktik dan Permasalahannya. Bandung, Mandar Maju. 2005
- Maidin Gultom, Perlindungan Hukum Terhadap Anak. Bandung PT Refika Aditama 2018
- Muammar, Kajian Kriminologi Peredaran Narkotika (Sebuah Studi Di Kabupaten Aceh Timur), Vol. 7 No. 1, 1 Januari 2019
- Muammar, Kajian Kriminologi Peredaran Narkotika (Sebuah Studi Di Kabupaten Aceh Timur), Vol. 7 No. 1, 1 Januari 2019
- Mukri, S. G. (2019). Tindakan Edukatif Penanganan Penyalahgunaan Narkotika. ADALAH, 3(1)
- Ni Kd Saras Iswari Gunnanda, Pertanggungjawaban Pidana Anak Yang Menggunakan Narkotika, Jurnal Kertha Desa, Vol. 9 No. 6
- Relatif. Jurnal Penegakan Hukum Indonesia, 2(1)
- Rosidah, Nikmah dan Rini Fathonah. 2019. Hukum Peradilan Anak. Bandar Lampung: Zam-Zam Tower
- S.R. Sianturi, 1986, Asas - Asas Hukum Pidana di Indonesia dan Penerapannya, Alumni AHAEM- PTHAEM, Jakarta
- Samosir, Djisman. 1982. Fungsi Pidana Penjara dalam Sistem Pembinaan Narapidana di Indonesia. Jakarta : Pradnya Paramita.
- Samsul Arifin, Pertanggungjawaban Pidana Terhadap Anak Sebagai Kurir Narkotika, Justitia Jurnal Hukum, Volume 1 No. 6 Bulan April Tahun 2021 ISSN Cetak : 2579-9983
- Siregar, Bismar. 1986. Keadilan Hukum dalam Berbagai aspek Hukum Nasional. Jakarta : Rajawali
- Sudarto, 1981, Hukum dan Hukum Pidana, Bandung, Alumni
- Supriyanta. 2012. Demokratisasi dalam Penegakan Hukum. Jurnal Wacana Hukum. Vol. VII No. 1 Tahun 2012
- Sutarto, S. (2021). Penerapan Rehabilitasi Medis Dan Rehabilitasi Sosial Terhadap
- Usman, A. H. (2015). Kesadaran hukum masyarakat dan pemerintah sebagai factor tegaknya negara hukum di Indonesia. Jurnal Wawasan Yuridika, 30 (1)

Problems of Law Enforcement Against Drug Users

Roslina Tiur Melia¹, Mhd. Azhali Siregar²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: azhalisiregar@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

The distribution and abuse of narcotics is one of the national problems that is considered serious by the government, because it can damage the nation's morals. Perpetrators of narcotics crimes often receive sentences based on court decisions that do not fulfill a sense of justice and legal certainty. In narcotics cases, there are several articles that are often used to ensnare perpetrators, namely Article 114, Article 112, and Article 127 of Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics. Of the three articles, there are two articles that are open to multiple interpretations and unclear formulations, namely Article 112 and Article 127 of Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics. The multi-interpretable articles will result in perpetrators of narcotics crimes (dealers) taking cover as if they were victims of narcotics crimes. That this will have an impact on the imposition of sentences with short sentences, thus causing injustice in the implementation process. This research is of a normative legal nature, namely a method that describes or explains a fact systematically, then the analysis is carried out legally by linking the data and facts obtained by analyzing court decisions relating to criminal sanctions against perpetrators of narcotics crimes and linked to applicable laws and regulations. The results of this study are that in this study, however, in the field of narcotics law enforcement, this seems to be much more difficult. Prioritizing criminal penalties seems to be very inherent in our law enforcement. Extraordinary encouragement is needed both at the local, national and international levels. So in relation to the case in this study, the Medan District Court Judge decided the defendant was legally and convincingly guilty in accordance with the provisions of Article 112 paragraph (1) of Law No. 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics by sentencing the defendant Veri Suriana alias Veri to a prison sentence of 6 (six) years and a fine of Rp. 1,000,000,000, - (one billion rupiah) with the provision that if the fine is not paid, it must be replaced with a prison sentence of 6 (six) months.

Keywords: Problems of Law, Law Enforcement, Drug Abuse.

INTRODUCTION

Narcotics Law Number 35 of 2009 does not provide sufficient limitations on who is meant by a dealer and who is meant by an addict. Likewise, Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics explains that Narcotics Addicts and victims of Narcotics abuse are required to undergo medical rehabilitation and social rehabilitation. This means that the law only requires rehabilitation for addicts and victims. What is meant by victims is only a little and is very limited explained in the explanation of Article 54 that "victims of narcotics abuse" are someone who accidentally uses narcotics because they are persuaded, tricked, deceived, forced, and/or threatened to use narcotics, while the definition of an addict is a person who uses or abuses narcotics and is in a state of dependence on narcotics, both physically and psychologically.

In Indonesia, the issue of law enforcement has been in the spotlight, especially in the issue of the criminal justice system. One of the issues in the spotlight is the relationship between the criminal justice system and the problem of narcotics (narcotics, psychotropics and other addictive substances) which should be handled with various approaches, but in

practice, the punitive approach is the main pillar. In the international world, drug policies have developed further after the birth of 3 UN Conventions on Drugs, namely the Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs 1961, the Convention on Psychotropic Substances 1971 and the UN Convention on the Eradication of Illicit Traffic in Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances 1988.

The changes in drug policy in Indonesia followed many of these world developments with the enactment of Law Number 8 of 1976 concerning the Ratification of the Single Convention on Narcotics 1961, along with the Protocol amending it,³ and Law Number 7 of 1997 concerning the Ratification of the UN Convention on the Eradication of Illicit Trafficking in Narcotics and Psychotropics 1988, then the issuance of Law Number 5 of 1997 concerning Psychotropics and Law Number 22 of 1997 concerning Narcotics. After Law Number 5 of 1997 was replaced by Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics, this latest law became a law that combines the rules on substances contained in the provisions on Psychotropics and Narcotics and parties with certain authorities.¹

In contrast to the policies in Indonesia, ideas and debates have emerged in various parts of the world to find alternative solutions to the drug problem. Of the various approaches that are increasingly developing, criminalization is not the only solution. The public health approach and providing economic alternatives to the drug problem are the main focus which is now increasingly seen as an effective approach. England, for example, now acknowledges that their drug policy must be reformed, one of which is the policy on criminalizing users. The same thing was also conveyed by the President of Guatemala, Otto Perez, who pushed for the legalization of the use of certain drugs by saying that, "Drug abuse, alcoholism and tobacco should be treated as public health problems, not criminal justice issues".² In contrast, with the two countries, Portugal has made an extraordinary legal breakthrough. Since 10 (ten) years ago, the Portuguese government has abolished criminal provisions against people with drug addiction and even against abusers in certain categories.³

The problem that is often faced regarding Narcotics is drug abusers or addicts who use narcotics outside of medical interests or needs, even exceeding the dose that can be accepted by the body, causing the user to overdose. The impact of drug abuse is that it can damage the resilience of society, the nation, and the state.

Parties who abuse narcotics according to Law No. 35 of 2009 consist of narcotics addicts as regulated in Article 1 number 13 and abusers as regulated in Article 1 number 15. Narcotics addicts are people who use or abuse narcotics and are in a state of dependence on narcotics, both physically and psychologically. Abusers are people who use narcotics

¹AR. Sujono and Bony Daniel, Comments and Discussion of Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics. (Jakarta: SinarGrafika, 2011) Page 127

²The Guardian, "Drugs Policies are not working, believe 75% of MPs", http://www.guardian.co.uk/politics/2012/sep/08/mps-drugs-policies-not-working?CMP=twit_gu, traced 19 July 2024.

³Abidin Az and Andi Hamzah, Introduction to Indonesian Criminal Law, (Jakarta: PT. Yarsif Watampone, 2010) pages 42-43.

without rights or against the law. The factors that cause narcotics crimes are divided into 2 (two) groups, namely internal factors and external factors.⁴

Internal factors usually come from things within the perpetrator of drug crimes, such as a shaken soul and a sense of despair that requires a sense of calm, security, comfort for the perpetrator so that it can eliminate the feelings of anxiety and despair that are felt. External factors come from things outside the perpetrator of drug crimes, such as socializing, environmental influences, and pressure or pressure from certain parties.

The perpetrators and victims of drug abuse come from all ages, from children, teenagers, to adults. The spread of illegal drugs has spread and expanded throughout the world. The problem of drug abuse in Indonesia is now very concerning. This situation is caused by several things, including the awareness of the Indonesian people about their lack of obedience to religious teachings, norms and laws. The sophistication and ease of transportation and technology greatly facilitate the development of drug abuse and the spread of narcotics so that many cases occur, both cases of drug users, cases of drug dealers, and drug smuggling.⁵

Based on the above, in terms of victimology, someone who is tricked into distributing drugs is also part of the victim, but in practice, it is sometimes considered a perpetrator of drug crimes. For example, someone who is very naive is approached by someone else to bring something that will be given to the other person's friend, with the intention of helping this very naive person carry the item and then not long after that is caught by law enforcement who turns out that the item he is carrying contains a drug package.⁶

The case that is the object of this research is on Decision Number: 214/Pid.Sus/2024/PN.Mdn. Against the defendant named Veri Suriana als Veri is legally and convincingly guilty of committing the criminal act "without right and against the law of possessing, storing, controlling or providing Class-I non-plant Narcotics", as regulated and punishable by violation of Article 112⁷ Article (1) of the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics (Second indictment).

In this decision, the defendant was sentenced to 7 (seven) years in prison minus the time already served and with an order that the defendant remain in detention and a fine of Rp. 1,000,000,000 (one billion rupiah) with the provision that if the fine is not paid, it will be replaced with a prison sentence of 6 (six) months.

⁴Haris Sasangka, 2003, narcotics and psychotropics in criminal law for students and practitioners as well as counselors on drug issues, 1st edition, Mandar Maju, Bandung, page 33.

⁵Rahmandani Sinar, et al., "Legal Certainty of the Implementation of Article 112 of Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics in the Jurisdiction of the East Kalimantan Regional Police" Lex Suprema Journal 2, No. 2 (2020).

⁶Prayogo, R. Tony. "Implementation of the Principle of Legal Certainty in Supreme Court Regulation Number 1 of 2011 Concerning the Right to Material Review and in Constitutional Court Regulation Number 06/PMK/2005 Concerning Guidelines for Proceedings in the Review of Laws" Indonesian Legislation Journal 13. No. 2 (2016)

⁷ **Article 112 paragraph (1) of the Narcotics Law** regulates that any person who without rights or against the law possesses, stores, controls, or provides Class I Narcotics other than plants, shall be punished with a minimum prison sentence of four years and a maximum of twelve years and a fine of at least IDR 800 million and a maximum of IDR 8 billion.

Chapter VI of Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics has regulated the Circulation, Distribution and Delivery of Narcotics, in Article 35 of this law it is determined that the Circulation of Narcotics includes every activity or series of activities for the distribution or delivery of Narcotics, whether in the context of trade, non-trade or transfer, for the benefit of health services and the development of science and technology, then based on Articles 7 and 8 of the Narcotics Law it is determined that Class I narcotics may only be used for the development of science and technology.⁸

It is further stated that in the context of the circulation, distribution and delivery of Narcotics, Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics has regulated the licensing of bodies or institutions in the circulation of Narcotics and does not recognize any individual or person to control, possess, store or deliver Class I Narcotics, and Class I Narcotics may not even be used for the purposes of Health Services.

But in this case the defendant without right or against the law offering for sale, selling, buying, receiving, acting as an intermediary in buying and selling, exchanging or handing over Class I Narcotics. When members of the East Medan Police conducted a body search of the defendant, they found Rp. 215,000 (two hundred and fifteen thousand rupiah) in the defendant's trouser pocket and 3 (three) small transparent plastic packages containing crystal methamphetamine, where Hanafi alias Napi ordered the defendant to sell the crystal methamphetamine to another person. In this case, the defendant did not have permission from the authorized party to buy, sell and act as an intermediary in buying and selling narcotics, as a result of the defendant's actions as regulated and threatened in Article 114 paragraph (1)⁹ Republic of Indonesia Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics.

The punishment for those who violate Article 114 of the Narcotics Law is a prison sentence of at least five years and a maximum of twenty years and a fine of at least IDR 1 billion and a maximum of IDR 10 billion for those who without the right or against the law offer for sale, sell, buy, receive, act as an intermediary in the sale and purchase, exchange, or hand over Class I Narcotics.

From the description of the problems above, there are two things that can be used as problem formulations in this research, namely:

1. How is the Narcotics Policy Regulation in Indonesia able to provide a solution in efforts to combat the Illegal Narcotics Trade?

⁸Rahmandani Sinar, et al., "Legal Certainty of the Implementation of Article 112 of Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics in the Jurisdiction of the East Kalimantan Regional Police" *Lex Suprema Journal* 2, No. 2 (2020).

⁹ **Article 114 paragraph (1) of the Narcotics Law** regulates that any person who without the right or against the law offers for sale, sells, buys, receives, acts as an intermediary in the sale and purchase, exchanges, or delivers Class I Narcotics, shall be punished with life imprisonment or a minimum imprisonment of five years and a maximum imprisonment of twenty years and a fine of at least IDR 1 billion and a maximum of IDR 10 billion.

2. What is the basis for the judge's considerations in handing down a verdict against a perpetrator of a crime of drug abuse?

METHOD

In research, research methods are used to solve problems to be studied. According to Sugiyono (2012) methodology is a scientific way to obtain data with certain goals and uses. Meanwhile, according to Surakhmad (2004) explains that the method is the main way used to achieve a goal, for example to study a series of hypotheses using analysis techniques.

The type of research used is normative juridical (legal research), normative legal research is referred to as doctrinal research, library research or document study. Data sources are anything that can provide information about the data to be studied. In this study, the data sources used by the author are two, namely primary data and secondary data. The object of research is one of the references used as a research target with the aim of finding out the truth and facts about the research being studied. The object of research to be studied is in the Surakarta District Court.

The research techniques used in the data collection process are through interviews, documentation and literature studies. This analysis is used to understand the relationships and concepts in the data being studied. In this case, researchers analyze data generated through interviews with research subjects. According to Miles and Humberman (1984), data analysis used in qualitative research includes data reduction, data presentation and drawing conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Regulation of Narcotics Policy in Indonesia to have a solution-oriented impact in efforts to combat illegal narcotics trade

Based on the data, the implications of drug policies in Indonesia over the past 15 years can be seen. One of them is the increasing number of people with HIV/AIDS which is closely related to the use of injecting drugs. The available data states that there were 21,591 people with HIV in 2010 and 21,031 people with HIV in 2011, while up to March 2012 it had reached 9,883 people with HIV. Cases of people with AIDS in 2010 reached 5,744 people, in 2011 it reached 4,162 people and in March 2012 it reached 2,224 people.¹⁷ Injecting Needle Users (IDUs) still contribute a large number of HIV/AIDS cases, namely around 10,265 IDUs with AIDS or contributing 53% of the total AIDS cases during the 5-year period.¹⁸ In addition to infectious diseases, drug cases also contribute to the high difficulty in prison overcapacity. The number of cases due to consuming narcotics is 37.5% of the total narcotics cases in Indonesia since 2007-2011 or amounting to 10,851 people. Only 0.2% or around 17 cases are producers or around 0.2% of planting cases or 85 total cases.¹⁹ According to information from the Director General of Corrections, excess capacity reached

56.81% in 2009. A total of 140,423 prisoners, 37,295 of whom were those with narcotics cases, of whom 285 died in prison and 89 of whom died due to HIV/AIDS.¹⁰

Seeing the above problems, it is right if the drug policy in Indonesia is immediately reformed. Not to mention the emergence of stigma and discrimination experienced by drug users or abusers which causes many drug users or abusers to be reluctant to report themselves by admitting their drug use to enter the Rehabilitation program.¹¹

Although in 2010 the Supreme Court has issued a Circular Letter recommending that every judge handling a drug case should give a rehabilitation decision for addicts or people who bring drugs for personal consumption in amounts below the circular, there are still many cases of users or abusers who are placed in prison and eventually lose their access to health. This is what complicates and even regresses the drug policy in Indonesia which is not in line with Human Rights (HAM), one of which is caused by the arbitrariness of law enforcement in conducting investigations, inquiries and decisions in the criminal law process.

In fact, currently there are 3 (three) basic principles of drug policy that must be considered, namely: 1) Public health, 2) Development and 3) human security. Drug policy in Indonesia needs to be updated in its model or method to be in accordance with the important principles of effective drug policy. In evaluating drug policy, the debate between social and health policies must also be considered in addition to political issues and diplomatic sensitivity alone. The International Drug Policy Concorsium (IDPC) formulated 5 important principles in making effective drug policy:

1. Drug policies should be developed through a structured and objective assessment of priorities and evidence
2. all activities should be undertaken in full compliance with international human rights law
3. Drug policies should focus on reducing the harmful consequences rather than the scale of drug use and markets
4. policies and activities should seek to promote the social inclusion of marginalized groups
5. governments should build open and constructive relationships with civil society in the discussion and delivery of their strategies.¹²

In the first principle it has been stated that it is important to have an objective assessment of priorities and based on scientific evidence. In the drug policy in Indonesia, it is often found that the drug problem is solely a criminal law policy, it is not surprising that the number of criminalizations of drug users remains high even though the government has repeatedly stated that the humanist and health approaches have been prioritized. In the second principle it is stated that the policy must be based on the fulfillment of international human rights, the implementation of which in Indonesia is still far from expectations.

¹⁰Resnawardhani, Fitri. "Legal Certainty in Article 112 and Article 127 of Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics" *Lentera Hukum* 6, No. 1 (2019).

¹¹Siburian, Jhon Nover. "Legal Analysis of the Implementation of Article 112 Paragraph (1) and Paragraph (1) Linked to the Implementation of Article 127 Paragraph (1) Letter a, and Paragraph (3) of Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics in Providing Legal Certainty in Indonesia" *JOM* 10, No. 1 (2023).

¹²Suryaputra, I Made Esa and Mulyadi. "Legal Protection for Drug Addicts and Victims of Drug Abuse" *Justitia: Journal of Law and Humanities* 8, No. 3 (2021).

Human rights violations that have occurred have been reported by various Non-Governmental Organizations from year to year. This third policy is often not implemented in Indonesia. The Indonesian Drug Policy is considered to be pursuing drug dealers and producers, but in fact in the data presented, users and addicts are the biggest targets in the drug criminalization system. In fact, the biggest consequence of drug use is the health of the user, and not just the drug trade itself.¹³

The fourth principle emphasizes the concept of special protection for marginalized groups. In many cases, the target of law enforcement is the economically marginalized group. This can be seen from the number of drug case suspects, most of whom only received an elementary school education, which is 11.8%, while those who received a junior high school education are 27.7% and around 61.9% of those who are in high school from a total of 181,426 people and only 2.6% of the suspects come from universities with a total of 4,868 people.²¹ BNN data also states that the unemployed group is the second largest group of drug case suspects, which is 6,487 people in 2007 from a total of 85,689 suspects.²² Cooperation with NGOs is something that should be done in accordance with the fifth principle. This is still a question because when cooperation between state institutions is still very difficult to do, then closeness between the government and civil society will be difficult to achieve.

The basic question that often arises is, is it true that there is a punitive drug policy that often violates human rights due to the arbitrariness of law enforcement? The importance of this question has led the UN Human Rights Commission to issue a series of principles to protect everyone in the legal process in detention and in prison.²³ In various drug cases, these existing principles are often violated and seem to be negated for drug users or people with drug addiction. The principle that legal sanctions must be given appropriately and impartial trials are some of the principles that are often violated when related to drug use cases.¹⁴

In this case in the Medan District Court Decision, the Panel of Judges decided that the defendant had fulfilled the elements of Article 112 paragraph (1) of Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics, Law Number 8 of 1981 concerning Criminal Procedure Law and other legal provisions related to this case so that the Defendant Veri Suriana alias Veri with the above identity has been proven legally and convincingly guilty of committing the crime of "Without the Right to Own or Control" Class I Narcotics and sentenced the defendant Veri Suriana alias Veri to a prison sentence of 6 (six) years and a fine of Rp. 1,000,000,000 (one billion rupiah) with the provision that if the fine is not paid, it must be replaced with a prison sentence of 6 (six) months.¹⁵

¹³Warsito, Dafit Supriyanto Daris. "The Criminalization System for Narcotics Abuse Criminals" *Jurnal Daulat Hukum* 1, No. 1 (2018).

¹⁴Laoly, Yasonna, 2019, *Deadly Snare: Perspectives on Economic Welfare in Drug Abuse*, Tangerang: Alvabet Library page 52.

¹⁵Sunarso, Siswanto, *Legal Politics in the Narcotics Law (Law Number 35 of 2009)*, Jakarta: Rineka Cipta, 2012.

Judge's Considerations in Sentencing Perpetrators of Narcotics Abuse Crimes in Medan District Court Decision Number: 214/Pid.Sus/2024/PN.Mdn.

If we look back at this case, before the judge handed down the verdict against the defendant, after...has been proven legally and convincingly guilty of committing the crime of "Without the Right to Own or Control" Class I Narcotics, with a criminal sentence of 6 (six) years imprisonment and a fine of Rp. 1,000,000,000 (one billion rupiah) with the provision that if the fine is not paid then it must be replaced with a prison sentence of 6 (six) months, then there are several things that are the subject of consideration for the judge which in this case are included in the author's research study.

a. Consideration of each person's elements

In the view of the Panel of Judges, the definition of "Every Person" is a Legal Subject as an Actor or one who carries out a legal act or legal event, namely an individual, a group of people or a Legal Entity who in this case is the perpetrator of the act as described in the indictment.

The defendant is a person, so according to legal science, a person is included in the definition of a legal subject or perpetrator of a legal act or event, so the submission of the defendant as a legal subject has been proven to fulfill the provisions of the law, so this element is declared to have been proven and fulfilled according to the law and therefore it will be considered next whether the defendant is proven to have committed the act that he is accused of.

The perpetrator referred to is the perpetrator of a crime, meaning a person who commits a crime, in the sense of a person who intentionally or unintentionally as implied by the Law, whether it is subjective elements or objective elements, regardless of whether the decision to commit the crime arose from himself or not due to the movement of a third party.¹⁶ Criminal Act is a formulation of an act that is prohibited to be carried out (in laws and regulations) accompanied by a criminal threat for anyone who violates the prohibition. The act (feit) referred to here is the main element of a criminal act that is formulated.¹⁷ Criminal acts can be differentiated on certain grounds, namely as follows:

Based on the description above, regarding the criminal provisions regulated in Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics, if a set of criminal sanctions that have been applied are the result of inappropriate choices or are no longer in accordance with developments, then it is natural that this development is slightly disturbed. In this case, the increase and development of criminal acts on the one hand with the limited number of criminal sanctions available to judges and prosecutors on the other hand is one of the problems in the field of criminal policy that is quite difficult.¹⁸

The elements of a crime in criminal law in general are as follows:

¹⁶Barda Nanawi Arief, Summary of Criminal Law Lecture II, Faculty of Law, Diponegoro University, 1984, page 37

¹⁷PAF Lamintang, Basics of Criminal Law in Indonesia, 1st Edition, PT Sinar Grafika, Jakarta, 2014, page 179.

¹⁸B Simandjuntak, Introduction to Criminology and Social Pathology, Parsito, Bandung, 1981, page 200.

1. Human actions; both active actions (criminal acts) or passive actions (criminal acts).
2. The act is contrary to or against the law.
3. Such acts must be subject to a threat of punishment in the law.
4. It must be proven that the act was committed by the person who committed it, that is, the person must be accountable.
5. The act must be carried out by a legally competent and accountable person.¹⁹

There are two types of additional elements for mitigating criminal acts, namely objective and subjective. Therefore, the elements of a criminal act consist of:

1. It is a human act;
2. Fulfilling the formulation in the law (formal requirements); and
3. The human act is against applicable law (material requirements)

Formal requirements are needed to fulfill the legality principle of the law itself. This means that an act can be categorized as a criminal act if it has been regulated in legal regulations. Human actions that are not or have not been regulated in legal regulations cannot be subject to sanctions from the relevant legal regulations. Usually new legal regulations will be formed to regulate these actions. If detailed, the elements of a criminal act consist of subjective and objective elements. Subjective elements, which explain the person in question, can be interpreted as every person, state administrator, civil servant, or corporation or group of people who are organized.

Subjective elements include:

1. Intention (*dolus*) where this is found in violation of morality (Article 281 of the Criminal Code), deprivation of liberty (Article 333 of the Criminal Code), murder (Article 338).
2. Negligence (*culpa*), which is found in the deprivation of liberty (Article 334 of the Criminal Code), and others.
3. Intention (*voormemen*), where this is found in the attempt or pinging (Article 53 of the Criminal Code)
4. Intent (*oogmerk*), where this is found in theft (Article 362 of the Criminal Code), extortion (Article 368 of the Criminal Code), fraud (Article 378 of the Criminal Code), and others.
5. With prior planning (*met voorbedachte rade*), which is found in the act of abandoning one's own child (Article 308 of the Criminal Code), killing one's own child (Article 341 of the Criminal Code), killing one's own child with planning (Article 342 of the Criminal Code).

In general or most of the criminal acts according to Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics, are criminal acts of drug abuse, namely abuse by people who are not entitled, not authorized. The problem in Law Number 35 of 2009 that threatens more criminal acts of drug abuse, is that users, transaction actors, providers and so on are people

¹⁹Tresna, Principles of Criminal Law, PT. Tiara Limited, Jakarta, 1959, page 27.

in healthy conditions, not sick. The concept of abuse stems from the existence of a person's rights or authority guaranteed by law. Drug abuse is a form of deviation, action or deed from people who are not entitled, not authorized to use or distribute narcotics.²⁰

In many cases of narcotics crime in particular and drugs in general, it is always related to transnational crime, corporate crime, money laundering crime, and so on. Narcotics crime in particular and drugs in general as transnational crime, because the crime occurs beyond the borders of the country, such as networks or syndicates originating from abroad that bring narcotics into the territory of Indonesia. As a corporate crime according to Marwan Effendy, corporate crime (crime by corporation) is often identified with white collar crime which is related to organized crime.

Consideration of the Elements Without Rights or Against the Law of Storing, Controlling, or Providing Class I Narcotics other than plants.

The element of being without rights is equated with being against the law so that what is meant by "being without rights or against the law" is the existence of an act carried out by the perpetrator that is contrary to the provisions of the law which in the aquo case is an act related to the Control, Ownership, Illegal Distribution of Narcotics and Narcotics Precursors which is determined as a criminal act.

In criminal law, there is a doctrine of unlawful nature. It is true that the panel of judges has applied one of the unlawful nature teachings, namely the formal unlawful nature teaching. This can be justified considering Article 1 paragraph (1) of the Criminal Code as the principle of legality, namely *nullum delictum noella poena, sine praevia legi poenali* (no act can be punished except by existing laws and regulations). In addition to the formal unlawful nature teaching, there is also a material unlawful nature teaching, where an act can be said to be unlawful (*onrecht*) in addition to being contrary to the wording of the law and also because it is contrary to the sense of justice or outlook on life that exists in society. Regarding the elements of the act (as one of the requirements for punishment) these two things (formal and material unlawfulness) must be fulfilled first, only then can the act be said to be unlawful.

Furthermore, if we observe the elements of criminal acts in the provisions of Article 111 to Article 126 of the Narcotics Law, the Law contains the phrase "any person who is without rights or against the law" which is connected to several criminal acts of narcotics abuse. The Narcotics Law contains four categories of criminal acts without rights or against the law that are prohibited by the Law and can be subject to criminal sanctions, namely:

1. The first category, namely acts in the form of possessing, storing, controlling, or providing narcotics and narcotic precursors (Articles 111 and 112 for class I narcotics, Article 117 for class II narcotics and Article 122 for class III narcotics and Article 129 letter (a));

²⁰HarimanSatria, Anatomy of Special Criminal Law, UII Press, Yogyakarta, 2014, page 76.

2. The second category, namely acts in the form of producing, importing, exporting or distributing narcotics and narcotic precursors (Article 113 for class I narcotics, Article 118 for class II narcotics and Article 123 for class III narcotics and Article 129 letter (b));
3. The third category, namely acts in the form of offering for sale, selling, buying, receiving, acting as an intermediary in buying and selling, exchanging, or handing over narcotics and narcotic precursors (Article 114 and Article 116 for class I narcotics, Article 119 and Article 121 for class II narcotics, Article 124 and Article 126 for class III narcotics and Article 129 letter (c));
4. The fourth category, namely acts in the form of carrying, sending, transporting or transiting narcotics and narcotic precursors (Article 115 for class I narcotics, Article 120 for class II narcotics and Article 125 for class III narcotics and Article 129 letter (d)).

In the case that the author studied, the defendant known as Veri Suriana alias Veri was proven legally and convincingly guilty of committing a criminal act without rights or against the law of possessing, storing, controlling, or providing Class I narcotics other than plants of the shabu-shabu type (Article 112 paragraph (1) of the Narcotics Law). The judge sentenced the defendant to 6 (six) years in prison and required the defendant to pay a fine of Rp. 1,000,000,000 (one billion rupiah) with the provision that if it is not paid, it will be replaced with a prison sentence of 3 (three) months.

In general, if a criminal act formulation includes an element of unlawfulness, then it can be interpreted that unlawfulness means without rights or without authority. So it can be concluded that the element of "without rights" is part of the element of "unlawfulness" if referring to the formal legal understanding as regulated in the Narcotics Law. In line with this, Pompe said that unlawfulness (*wederrechtelijk*) means contrary to the law, which has a broader meaning than simply contrary to the law.

However, the Narcotics Law does not provide further explanation regarding the elements of "possessing, storing, controlling, or providing". In the Big Indonesian Dictionary (KBBI) (<https://kbbi.web.id/milik>, accessed July 18, 2024), possessing is defined as (1) having, (2) taking illegally to be owned. The element of having or possessing in this Article means that one must truly be the owner, regardless of whether the goods are physically in the hands of the person or not.

However, in the context of the Narcotics Law, ownership must be seen from the element of how the goods can be owned by the Defendant (their origin), whether the Defendant obtained the narcotics from a gift, by planting them himself, buying them or in other ways, the point being that there must be a direct relationship between the perpetrator and the narcotics so that they can be called the "owner" (Sujono and Daniel²¹).

Furthermore, when referring to KBBI, the word save is interpreted as putting in a safe place so that it is not damaged, lost, and so on (<https://kbbi.web.id/simpan>, accessed on July 18, 2024). In the Narcotics Law, there is also no specific regulation regarding the definition

²¹AR Sujono and Bony Daniel. 2011. Comments & Discussion of Law Number 35 of 2009 Concerning Narcotics. Jakarta: Sinar Grafika

of control, whether the narcotics are controlled only for consumption, distribution or just for possession. Where the word control is the main problem in this law is that the lack of explanation of the definition and limitations in the elements of controlling narcotics has caused many perpetrators of narcotics crimes who are caught red-handed controlling narcotics for the purpose of consumption, are subject to the article intended for narcotics dealers. Regarding the element of control, AR Sujono and Bony Daniel²² states that: "To control means to have power over (something); to hold power over something.

A person is said to have control over goods if he can control what he controls, he can control something that is in his power, it is not necessary whether the object is in his physical control or not, what is important is that the perpetrator can carry out actions such as selling, giving to other people or other actions that show that the perpetrator really has power over the goods."

Referring to Civil Law, the Civil Code (KUH Perdata) defines control as "possession" which is intended as something about a position in power. Article 529 of the Civil Code formulates: "What is called a position of power is the position of a person who controls an object, either by himself, or through another person, and who maintains or enjoys it as the person who owns the object."

Furthermore, Article 1977 of the Civil Code states, "For movable objects that are not in the form of interest or receivables that do not have to be paid to the bearer, whoever controls them is considered to own them." It can be seen that the position of a person who can control an object either by himself or through another person and to maintain and enjoy it is a person who is none other than the owner of the object, so this can be called power.

The Constitutional Court in Decision Number: 31/PUU-XV/2017 gave an opinion regarding the confusion contained in Article 112 paragraph (1), "The Court is of the opinion that the assessment of a case in a concrete case is actually the domain of law enforcement in this case the investigator, so that regarding the implementation of the norm contained in Article 112 paragraph (1) of the Narcotics Law, especially the phrase, "controlling, possessing, and storing" which must be linked to the existence of evidence in the person of a person suspected of being an Abuser, according to the Court, in terms of terminology, this is actually a very clear meaning." The use of the elements of possessing, storing or controlling in Article 112 paragraph (1) must be seen from the purpose for which the narcotics are controlled, owned, or stored.

The thing that needs to be emphasized, is it only for personal use or for trading either in the position of being produced, exported, imported, transited, distributed or handed over. With the threat of a minimum criminal penalty for both imprisonment and a fine, this provision is more appropriate to be applied to parties involved in the illicit drug trade as producers or distributors of narcotics, not to Abusers who have their own threat of punishment for the act of abusing narcotics. In drug abuse, the judge has a role to decide as

²²AR Sujono and Bony Daniel. 2011. Comments & Discussion of Law Number 35 of 2009 Concerning Narcotics. Jakarta: Sinar Grafika

severely as possible the perpetrators of drug dealers or syndicates with the maximum penalty.

This aims to achieve the ideals and goals of the state as stated in the opening of the fourth paragraph of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, namely to form an Indonesian state government that protects all Indonesian people and all Indonesian territory and to advance general welfare, improve the life of the nation, and participate in implementing world order based on independence, eternal peace, and social justice.

CONCLUSION

1. Looking at the drug policy in Indonesia, which even though it has changed the Narcotics Law for the second time, it can be concluded that there is still a big failure in meeting the objectives of an effective drug policy: reducing the supply of drugs, reducing the negative impacts of drugs with the principle of human rights, and legal justice. The drug policy in Indonesia must be recognized as having attempted to reform itself in a better direction with a health approach, namely by implementing rehabilitation punishment. However, unfortunately, these reform efforts are still inconsistent among each level of law enforcement. Drug policy reform cannot change immediately. It takes time to make plans and harder efforts to create an effective drug policy in Indonesia. However, in the field of drug law enforcement, this seems to be much more difficult. Prioritizing criminal penalties seems to be very much embedded in our law enforcement. Extraordinary encouragement is needed at the local, national and international levels. So in relation to the case in this research, the Medan District Court Judge decided that the defendant was legally and convincingly guilty in accordance with the provisions of Article 112 paragraph (1) of Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics by sentencing the defendant Veri Suriana alias Veri to a prison sentence of 6 (six) years and a fine of Rp. 1,000,000,000 (one billion rupiah) with the provision that if the fine is not paid, it must be replaced with a prison sentence of 6 (six) months.
2. Meanwhile, the considerations of the Medan District Court Panel of Judges, by paying attention to the legal facts, were to directly choose the charges as regulated in Article 112 paragraph (1) of Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics, the elements of which have been fulfilled, namely: The element of every person and the element without rights or against the law of storing, controlling, or providing Class I narcotics that are not plants. The defendant in this case is a person who is included in the definition of Legal Subject or Actor of a legal act or event, then the submission of the Defendant as a Legal Subject has been proven to meet the provisions of the law, then this element is declared to have been proven and fulfilled according to the law, while the element without rights is equated with against the law so that what is meant by "without rights or against the law" is the existence of an act carried out by the Actor that is contrary to the provisions of the legislation which in the aquo case is an act related to Control, Ownership, Illegal Distribution of Narcotics and Narcotics Precursors which is determined as a criminal act of Narcotics and Narcotics Precursors as referred to in Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics.

REFERENCES

- A.R. Sujono dan Bony Daniel. 2011. *Komentar & Pembahasan Undang-undang Nomor 35 Tahun 2009 Tentang Narkotika*. Jakarta : Sinar Grafika
- Abidin Az dan Andi Hamzah, *Pengantar Dalam Hukum Pidana Indonesia*, (Jakarta: PT. Yarsif Watampone, 2010)
- AR. Sujono dan Bony Daniel, *Komentar dan Pembahasan Undang-Undang Nomor 35 Tahun 2009 tentang Narkotika*. (Jakarta: Sinar Grafika, 2011)
- B Simandjuntak, *Pengantar Kriminologi Dan Patologi Sosial*, Parsito, Bandung, 1981
- Barda Nanawi Arief, *Sari Kuliah Hukum Pidana II*, Fakultas Hukum Undip, 1984
- Hariman Satria, *Anatomi Hukum Pidana Khusus*, UII Press, Yogyakarta, 2014
- Haris Sasangka, 2003, *narkotika dan psiktropika dalam hukum pidana untuk mahasiswa dan praktisi serta penyuluh masalah narkoba*, cetakan 1, Mandar Maju, Bandung
- Laoly, Yasonna, 2019, *Jerat Mematikan: Prespektif Kesejahteraan Ekonomi dalam P.A.F Lamintang, Dasar-Dasar Hukum Pidana di Indonesia Cet-1*, PT Sinar Grafika, Jakarta, 2014
- Penyalahgunaan Narkoba*, Tangerang: Pustaka Alvabet
- Prayogo, R. Tony. “Penerapan Asas Kepastian Hukum dalam Peraturan Mahkamah Agung Nomor 1 Tahun 2011 Tentang Hak Uji Materiil dan dalam Peraturan Mahkamah Konstitusi Nomor 06/PMK/2005 Tentang Pedoman Beracara dalam Pengujian Undang-Undang” *Jurnal Legislasi Indonesia* 13 No. 2 (2016)
- Rahmandani Sinar, dkk, “Kepastian Hukum Penerapan Pasal 112 Undang-Undang Nomor 35 Tahun 2009 tentang Narkotika di Wilayah Hukum Kepolisian Daerah Kalimantan Timur” *Jurnal Lex Suprema* 2, No. 2 (2020).
- Resnawardhani, Fitri. “Kepastian Hukum dalam Pasal 112 dan Pasal 127 Undang-Undang Nomor 35 Tahun 2009 tentang Narkotika” *Lentera Hukum* 6, Nomor 1 (2019).
- Siburian, Jhon Nover. “Analisis Yuridis Penerapan Pasal 112 Ayat (1) dan Ayat (1) Dikaitkan dengan Penerapan Pasal 127 Ayat (1) Huruf a, dan Ayat (3) Undang-Undang Nomor 35 Tahun 2009 tentang Narkotika dalam Memberikan Kepastian Hukum di Indonesia” *JOM* 10, No. 1 (2023).
- Sunarso, Siswanto, *Politik Hukum dalam Undang-Undang Narkotika (UU Nomor 35 Tahun 2009)*, Jakarta: Rineka Cipta, 2012.
- Suryaputra, I Made Esa dan Mulyadi. “Perlindungan Hukum Terhadap Pecandu dan Korban Penyalahgunaan Narkotika” *Justitia: Jurnal Ilmu Hukum dan Humaniora* 8, Nomor 3 (2021).
- The Guardian, “Drugs Policies are not working, believe 75% of MPs”, http://www.guardian.co.uk/politics/2012/sep/08/mps-drugs-policies-not-working?CMP=twit_gu, ditelusuri tanggal 19 Juli 2024
- Tresna, *Asas-asas Hukum Pidana*, PT Tiara Limited, Jakarta, 1959, halaman 27
- Warsito, Dafit Supriyanto Daris. “Sistem Pemidanaan Terhadap Pelaku Tindak Pidana Penyalahguna Narkotika” *Jurnal Daulat Hukum* 1, No. 1 (2018).

The Role of The Criminal Investigation Unit (Satreskrim) of The Deli Serdang Police Region in Identifying Victims of Criminal Acts

Edi Winata¹, H. Abdul Razak Nasution, S.H.Int., M.Sc.²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: winataedi0406@gmail.com

Abstract

The rapid development of various aspects of social, political, economic, security, and cultural life has led to an increase in the quantity and quality of criminal acts, which significantly disrupts society. Criminal acts are unlawful acts committed either intentionally or unintentionally by an individual who can be held accountable for their actions and which are punishable by law. The primary objective of formal criminal law is to seek material truth, and the process of investigation is essential in this regard. The Indonesian National Police, under Law Number 2 of 2002, play a crucial role in conducting investigations using Scientific Crime Investigation (SCI) methods, which integrate science and technology in forensic functions. Scientific Crime Investigation involves gathering and processing evidence with scientific methods, making it one of the most reliable tools in criminal investigations. The role of police identification units in processing crime scenes (TKP) is vital, as even the smallest evidence can be crucial for solving crimes. This research examines the role of the Criminal Investigation Unit (Satreskrim) of the Deli Serdang Police in identifying victims of criminal acts. The findings highlight the importance of forensic evidence in criminal investigations and the crucial role of police units in uncovering the truth.

Keywords: Scientific Crime Investigation, Forensic Evidence, Criminal Investigation Unit

INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of people's lives in all areas of social, political, economic, security and cultural life has also brought negative impacts in the form of increasing quality and quantity of various types of criminal acts that are very detrimental and disturbing to society. A criminal act is an unlawful act that has been done intentionally or unintentionally by someone who can be held responsible for his actions and which has been declared by law as an act that can be punished.

Formal criminal law has the main objective of seeking material truth. The level of examination of a case in criminal procedure in terms of seeking material truth, at the stage of investigation and inquiry by the Indonesian National Police where the first stage is the stage to seek material truth with a scientific investigation method or Scientific Crime Investigation (SCI). This is based on Article 14 of Law Number 2 of 2002 concerning the Indonesian National Police stating that one of the functions of the police is to conduct investigations. Investigations are regulated in Article 1 paragraph (2) of the Criminal Procedure Code which contains investigations are a series of investigative activities according to the circumstances and according to the methods determined in this law to seek, search for, and collect evidence that occurs and to find suspects (Prastowo, 2006).

Scientific Crime Investigation or scientific criminal investigation is an investigation process where the evidence system uses science and technology implemented in forensic functions (Labfor, Dokfor, Identification, Forensic Psychology and others). Evidence according to scientific procedures in the steps of criminal investigation is useful as a tool that can be prioritized and can even be the main foundation at the criminalization stage, especially when disclosing criminal cases in other words disclosing criminal suspects at the

investigation stage itself. This stage is believed by forensic experts that at the time the evidence is carried out in court but the results of the evidence from the witness itself have not been found, then the evidence will be changed to become the main evidence. (Susanto, 2003).

The police as one of the frontline agencies in law enforcement has an important role in combating crime. With the existence of Law Number 2 of 2002 concerning the Indonesian National Police, each member of the police must equip themselves with both skills and knowledge in accordance with their duties, in this case police members have a very important role in revealing a crime. If an incident occurs that is suspected of being a crime, the police as law enforcement officers are tasked with investigating all incidents suspected of being crimes in accordance with criminal procedure law and other laws and regulations.

Finding the truth or an event suspected of being a crime is not easy because in an event there is often a lack of evidence and incomplete witnesses, so that investigators must work harder in collecting valid evidence to obtain the most complete truth in investigating or investigating a real crime in preparation for examination in court (Amelia, 2019).

Article 14 Paragraph (1) letter h of Law Number 2 of 2002 concerning the Republic of Indonesia National Police explains that one of the duties of the police is to organize police identification, police medicine, forensic laboratories and police psychology for the interests of police duties. The implementation of police identification is carried out by the identification unit in the interests of investigation, criminal investigation and non-criminal services for the community and other agencies in the context of implementing police functions.

Criminal Investigation Unit (Satreskrim) In its function as a law enforcer, it has an important role in revealing perpetrators of criminal acts, because legally all activities carried out and results obtained in the crime scene processing process (TKP) are used to complete the criminal investigation files until they are completed at the court level. The Police Identification Unit is the front line in processing the crime scene in the Investigation Unit. Identification is useful in revealing a crime that requires carefulness and precision of the evidence at the TKP (Crime Scene) where the evidence is related to the incident at the location. No matter how small the evidence at the TKP is, it is very important in the disclosure process. By knowing the identity of the victim, investigators will find it easier to make a list of people who should be suspected in a case.

Scientific evidence in the criminal case investigation process will be the most reliable evidence and even become the backbone in the criminal justice process, especially in revealing cases/perpetrators in the investigation process. This is recognized by several forensic experts where if evidence in court does not find witnesses, then the results of the examination of evidence become the main evidence (Susanto 2003)

Based on the background above, the author chose the title of this research, namely: "The Role of the Criminal Investigation Unit (Satreskrim) of the Deli Serdang Police in Identifying Victims of Criminal Acts".

Formulation of the problem

The main problems in this research are:

1. What is the role of the Criminal Investigation Unit? Deli Serdang Police in identifying victims of criminal acts?
2. What are the obstacles in identify victims of criminal acts by Criminal Investigation Unit Deli Serdang Police Station?

Research purposes

The objectives of this research are:

1. To find out the role of SatreskrimDeli Serdang Police in identifying victims of criminal acts?
2. To find out the obstacles in identify victims of criminal acts byCriminal Investigation UnitDeli Serdang Police Station.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Definition of Identification

Article 14 Paragraph (1) letter h of Law Number 2 of 2002 concerning the Republic of Indonesia National Police explains that one of the duties of the police is to organize police identification, police medicine, forensic laboratories and police psychology for the interests of police duties. The implementation of police identification is carried out by the identification unit for the interests of investigation, criminal investigation and non-criminal services for the community and other agencies in the context of implementing police functions.

Identification is defined as any effort to carry out work and activities to re-identify the characteristics of a person or living creature or goods/objects/other materials through the method of dactyloscopy (fingerprints), photography, signals and other means to assist the police, especially the criminal investigation function to find the identity of the perpetrator of a crime. Identification is also the determination or confirmation of a person who is alive or dead, based on the characteristics found in that person. Forensic identification is an effort to find out a person's identity which is intended for forensic purposes, namely the interests of the judicial process. In its implementation, identification is the forefront in processing the crime scene (TKP) in the Investigation Unit (Agung, 2023).

The identification unit also plays an important role in identifying a person through scientific fingerprint examination. In the interests of revealing crimes, the purpose of involving the identification unit is to conduct identification at the scene of the crime (TKP) to search for and find a person's identity. The role of the identification unit in supporting the duties of the Police, namely:

1. In terms of law enforcement, it consists of:
 - a. Identify or reveal perpetrators, track Wanted Persons List (DPO);
 - b. Identification of unidentified victims;
 - c. Preventing suspects from leaving or entering Indonesia;
 - d. Preventing fake documents and exchanging criminal information between regional police units, police precincts, police stations, and even overseas, which in this case is carried out directly by the National Police Headquarters.
2. In terms of service to the community, it consists of the following:
 - a. Identifying missing persons;
 - b. Identification of Female Migrant Workers (TKW) / Indonesian Migrant Workers (TKI);
 - c. Banking or insurance transactions, regional or general elections and issuance of identity documents (Agung, 2023).

Definition of Criminal Acts

Our lawmakers use the word *strafbaarfeit* to refer to what we know as a "criminal act" in the Criminal Code (KUHP) without providing any explanation regarding what is actually meant by the word *strafbaarfeit*, so various opinions arise in doctrine about what is meant by *strafbaarfeit*. The monistic school of thought in formulating the definition of a criminal act is done by looking at "all the conditions for the existence of a crime, all of which are the nature of the act". So in formulating the definition of a criminal act, it does not separate the elements of a criminal act. While the dualistic school of thought in providing the definition of a criminal act separates between criminal acts and criminal responsibility. (Gustiniati, 2014).

SR Sianturi in the book *Principles of Criminal Law in Indonesia and its Application*, in Indonesian terminology, the term crime or *het strafbare feit* has been translated by scholars and has also been used in various formulations of laws with various Indonesian terms as:

- a. Actions that can/may be punished;
- b. Criminal events;
- c. Criminal acts;
- d. Criminal acts. (Sianturi, 2002).

According to SR Sianturi, in summary the elements of a criminal act are:

1. The existence of a subject;
2. There is an element of error;
3. Acts that are unlawful;
4. An action that is prohibited or required by law/legislation and those who violate it are subject to criminal penalties;
5. In a certain time, place, and circumstances. (Sianturi, 2002).

Referring to the elements of the criminal act above, SR Sianturi formulated the definition of a criminal act as an action in a certain place, time and circumstances, which is prohibited (or violates the requirement) and is threatened with punishment by law and is unlawful and contains an element of error committed by a person who is capable of being responsible (Sianturi, 2002).

Every crime contained in the Criminal Code can generally be described into elements that we can basically divide into two types of elements, namely subjective elements and objective elements. What is meant by subjective elements are elements that are inherent in the perpetrator or related to the perpetrator and include everything contained in his heart. While what is meant by objective elements are elements that are related to circumstances, namely in which circumstances the actions of the perpetrator must be carried out (Lamintang, 2013).

The subjective elements of a crime are:

- a. Intention (*dolus*) or unintentional (*culpa*);
- b. The purpose or intention of an attempt or attempt as referred to in Article 53 paragraph (1) of the Criminal Code or Article 17 paragraph (1) of Law 1/2023;
- c. Various purposes or brands, such as those found in the crimes of theft, fraud, extortion, forgery, etc.;
- d. Planning in advance or *voorbedachte raad*, as contained in the crime of premeditated murder in Article 340 of the Criminal Code or Article 459 of Law 1/2023;
- e. Feelings of fear or *vrees*, as contained in the formulation of criminal acts according to Article 308 of the Criminal Code or Article 430 of Law 1/2023. (Lamintang, 2002).

The objective elements of a crime are:

1. Unlawful nature or illegality;

2. The quality of the perpetrator, for example “condition as a civil servant” in crimes of office or “condition as a manager or commissioner of a limited company” in crimes under Article 398 of the Criminal Code or Article 516 of Law 1/2023;
3. Causality, namely the relationship between an action as a cause and a reality as a result. (Lamintang, 2002).

To find out whether an act in a legal event is a crime, an analysis can be carried out to see whether the act has fulfilled the elements of a crime regulated in a specific criminal law article. For this reason, adjustments or matching (parts/incidents) of the event must be made to the elements of the charged crime. If it turns out to be suitable, then it can be determined that the event is a crime that has occurred for which the perpetrator can be held criminally responsible. However, if one of these elements is absent or not proven, then it must be concluded that the crime has not or has not occurred.

Understanding Investigation and Inquiry

The term investigation was used as a legal or legal term in 1961, namely since it was included in Law Number 13 of 1961 concerning the Main Provisions of the State Police. Investigation comes from the word "sidik" which means clear. So investigation means making clear or obvious. Although both terms "investigation" and "investigation" come from the same word, the Criminal Procedure Code distinguishes the two in different functions.

Investigations are conducted before the start of an investigation. Investigations are a series of investigator actions to search for and find an event suspected of being a crime in order to determine whether or not an investigation can be carried out according to the methods regulated by law. Article 1 point (2) of the Criminal Procedure Code states that what is meant by investigation is a series of investigator actions in terms of and according to the methods regulated by this law to collect evidence with which the evidence makes clear the crime that occurred and in order to find the suspect. (Marpaung 2009)

Investigation is the first stage of the initial investigation. Investigation is not an independent action separate from the investigation function. So, before the investigation is carried out, an investigation is first carried out by the investigating officer, with the intent and purpose of collecting "initial evidence" or "sufficient evidence" so that further investigation can be carried out. When it is known that a crime has occurred, that is when an investigation can be carried out based on the results of the investigation. In the investigation, the emphasis is placed on the action of "searching for and finding" an "event" that is considered or suspected to be a criminal act. While in the investigation, the emphasis is placed on the action of "searching for and collecting evidence". The investigation aims to clarify the crime that was found and also determine the perpetrator.

The authority of the police to investigate also includes determining policies. This is very difficult to implement because it must consider what actions will be taken at a short time when first handling a crime in addition to having to know the criminal law. Before the investigation begins, the investigator must be able to estimate what crime has occurred. Which criminal laws regulate it so that the investigation can be directed at events that are in accordance with the formulation of the crime. The investigation is of course directed at evidence that can result in the suspect being charged and punished. However, it is not uncommon in the criminal justice process, the investigation has been carried out and ends with the acquittal of the defendant.

In carrying out their duties, investigators must have supporting knowledge because the implementation of investigations aims to obtain complete truth. To achieve this goal, it is

necessary to master some additional knowledge besides knowledge of criminal law and criminal procedure law (Bawengan 2007).

METHOD

Types of research

In this study, the author uses normative and empirical legal methods. Normative legal is by examining the rules, norms and/or regulations related to the problem to be studied through library research. This approach is intended to collect various kinds of laws and regulations, theories and literature that are closely related to the problem to be studied. Empirical legal is an approach carried out by digging up information and conducting research in the field in order to find out the problems discussed.

Problem Approach

The problem approach used in this study is the statutory regulatory approach. The statutory regulatory approach is used because what will be studied is the legal rules related to this study. This approach is carried out by examining all laws and regulations related to police discretion through penal mediation. This approach requires understanding the hierarchy and principles of laws and regulations.

Source of Legal Material

Primary legal materials consist of laws and government regulations, court decisions that have permanent legal force, other related regulations such as the Criminal Code, Criminal Procedure Code. Secondary legal materials are materials that provide explanations regarding primary legal materials such as research, proceedings related to research. Tertiary legal materials are materials that provide instructions or explanations for primary legal materials and secondary materials such as dictionaries, encyclopedias (wikipedia) and tables related to the object of research.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Role of the Criminal Investigation Unit Deli Serdang Police in Identifying Victims of Criminal Acts

The role of Satreskrim Polresta Deli Serdang in identifying victims of crime is a fundamental aspect of the law enforcement system in Indonesia. As explained by Bawengan (2007), the success of the investigation process is highly dependent on the ability of investigators to collect and analyze existing evidence. In this context, victim identification is a crucial initial step in revealing the material truth in every criminal case.

In dealing with cases where victims are found without identification, the Criminal Investigation Unit of the Deli Serdang Police applies a series of systematic procedures that refer to police operational standards. Hamzah (2008) emphasized that the victim identification process is a critical stage that requires high precision and professionalism from law enforcement officers. This is in line with the opinion of Marpaung (2009) who stated that the success of revealing a case is highly dependent on the initial stage of handling, including the victim identification process.

The first method applied in the identification process is fingerprint analysis. Soekanto (2011) explains that fingerprints are a unique biological characteristic of each individual and will not change throughout life, unless there is permanent damage to the skin tissue. The Criminal Investigation Unit of the Deli Serdang Police utilizes this uniqueness

as the main method in the victim identification process. The process of taking and analyzing fingerprints is carried out very carefully considering that the identification results will be the basis for the next investigation process.

Technological advances in forensics have brought significant changes in the victim identification process. The Criminal Investigation Unit of the Deli Serdang Police adopted the use of the INAFIS (Indonesia Automatic Fingerprint Identification System) system which allows the identification process to be carried out digitally and more efficiently. As stated by Prakoso (2010), the use of modern technology in the investigation process can increase the accuracy and speed in revealing cases. INAFIS allows police officers to compare the victim's fingerprints with the national database in real-time.

Despite using modern technology, Satreskrim Polresta Deli Serdang still conducts manual verification as a confirmation step. This process involves comparing the victim's fingerprints with official documents such as e-KTP and diplomas. Rahardjo (2012) emphasized the importance of double verification in the identification process to ensure that no errors occur that could affect the course of the investigation. This manual method, although it takes longer, provides a higher level of certainty.

In practice, the Deli Serdang Police Criminal Investigation Unit also faces various challenges in the victim identification process. The condition of the victim's body that has experienced decomposition or damage can complicate the process of taking fingerprints. In situations like this, the use of alternative identification methods such as DNA analysis or dental records. The Deli Serdang Police Criminal Investigation Unit has developed cooperation with forensic laboratories and forensic doctors to overcome these challenges.

Another important aspect in the identification process is comprehensive documentation. Each stage of identification must be well documented for the sake of evidence in court. Mulyadi (2012) emphasized that good documentation is not only useful for the interests of current investigations but can also be a reference for similar cases in the future.

Coordination with related agencies is also key to the success of the identification process. The Criminal Investigation Unit of the Deli Serdang Police is actively cooperating with the Population and Civil Registration Service to verify the victim's population data. In addition, coordination with hospitals and forensic installations is also carried out to obtain medical data that can assist the identification process.

The capacity building of Satreskrim personnel in the field of forensic identification continues to be carried out through various training and workshops. This is in line with the opinion of Sutanto (2009) who emphasized the importance of developing the competence of law enforcement officers in dealing with the complexity of modern crime. This training includes fingerprinting techniques, the use of INAFIS technology, and alternative identification methods.

In an effort to improve the effectiveness of the identification process, Satreskrim Polresta Deli Serdang also conducts periodic evaluations of the procedures implemented. This evaluation is important to identify the obstacles faced and find solutions to improve the performance of the identification team. As stated by Prodjohamidjojo (2011), continuous evaluation is the key to improving the quality of law enforcement.

Internal Obstacles Identifying Victims of Criminal Acts By Criminal Investigation Unit Deli Serdang Police Station

In carrying out the task of identifying victims of crime, the Criminal Investigation Unit of the Deli Serdang Police faces various obstacles that can affect the effectiveness of

the identification process. As stated by Bawengan (2007), the investigation process aimed at obtaining complete truth often faces technical and non-technical obstacles that require special handling.

1. Technical Constraints in the Identification Process

One of the main obstacles faced is the physical condition of the victim who has experienced damage or decomposition. Soekanto (2011) explains that the decomposition process can cause significant changes in skin tissue, which makes it difficult to take fingerprints. This condition often occurs in cases where the victim is found several days after the incident, or in locations with environmental conditions that accelerate the decomposition process.

Limited equipment and technology are also serious obstacles in the identification process. Despite having the INAFIS system, not all Satreskrim units have direct access to this sophisticated equipment. Hamzah (2008) emphasized that the availability of adequate facilities and infrastructure is a critical factor in the success of the investigation process. This limitation often results in delays in the identification process or forces the use of manual methods that take longer.

2. Administrative and Coordination Constraints

The identification process is often hampered by administrative problems, especially in terms of coordination between agencies. Marpaung (2009) stated that complicated bureaucracy and slow response from related agencies can hamper the identification process. This is seen when Satreskrim requires comparative data from Disdukcapil or other agencies that have population databases.

The limited comparative data is also a significant obstacle. Not all residents have fingerprint records recorded in the e-KTP system, especially for residents in remote areas or those who have not recorded their data. Rahardjo (2012) highlighted the importance of a comprehensive database to support the victim identification process.

3. Human Resource Constraints

The limited number of personnel with special expertise in forensic identification is a challenge in itself. Atmasasmita (2010) emphasized that the quality of human resources is a key factor in handling criminal cases. The lack of officers trained in the use of INAFIS technology and modern forensic identification techniques can slow down the identification process.

High workload also affects the performance of the identification team. Prakoso (2010) explains that time pressure and the number of cases to be handled can affect the accuracy of the identification process. This is especially evident when several serious cases occur simultaneously.

4. Time and Environmental Constraints

Time factor is a critical constraint in the victim identification process. Sutanto (2009) stated that the speed of case handling greatly affects the success of identification, especially in cases involving decomposing bodies. Delays in finding victims or reporting incidents can complicate the identification process.

The environmental conditions where the victim was found can also affect the identification process. Extreme weather, hard-to-reach locations, or unfavorable environmental conditions can hinder the collection of fingerprints and other evidence. Prodjohamidjojo (2011) emphasized the importance of fast and precise handling of the crime scene to secure evidence that can help the identification process.

5. Budget and Operational Constraints

Operational budget limitations are an equally important obstacle. Mulyadi (2012) explains that the identification process involving sophisticated technology and requiring coordination with various parties requires considerable financial support. Budget limitations can affect the speed and quality of the identification process.

In facing these various obstacles, Satreskrim Polresta Deli Serdang has taken several strategic steps. Improving personnel competence through continuous training, optimizing the use of available technology, and strengthening coordination with related agencies are the main priorities. In addition, the submission of additional budget and equipment continues to be carried out to increase the capacity of the identification unit.

CLOSING

Based on the discussion above, it can be concluded that the Satreskrim Polresta Deli Serdang has a vital role in identifying victims of crime through various methods, ranging from fingerprint analysis using the INAFIS system to manual verification with official documents such as e-KTP and diplomas. However, in its implementation, Satreskrim faces various obstacles such as the physical condition of victims who have experienced decomposition, limited equipment and technology, administrative obstacles in coordination between agencies, limited human resources with forensic expertise, time and environmental constraints, and limited operational budgets, all of which can affect the effectiveness of the victim identification process.

To improve the effectiveness of the performance of the Deli Serdang Police Criminal Investigation Unit in identifying victims of crime, it is recommended to strengthen the institutional capacity by increasing the operational budget, procuring adequate forensic equipment, intensive training for personnel in the field of forensic identification, and strengthening coordination with related agencies such as the Population and Civil Registry Office, hospitals, and forensic laboratories. In addition, it is necessary to periodically update the population database to facilitate the process of identifying victims in the future.

REFERENCES

- Atmasasmita, Romli. (2010). *Sistem Peradilan Pidana Kontemporer*. Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Media Group.
- Bawengan, W. Gerson. (2007). *Penyidikan Perkara Pidana dan Teknik Interogasi*. Jakarta: Pradnya Paramita.
- Gustiniati, Diah & Rizki, Budi. (2014). *Azas-Azas Dan Pemidanaan Hukum Pidana Di Indonesia*. Bandar Lampung: Justice Publisher.
- Hamzah, Andi. (2008). *Hukum Acara Pidana Indonesia*. Jakarta: Sinar Grafika.
- Lamintang, P.A.F. (2013). *Dasar-dasar Hukum Pidana Indonesia*. Bandung: PT Citra Aditya Bakti.
- Marpaung, Laden. (2009). *Proses Penanganan Perkara Pidana (Penyelidikan dan Penyidikan)*. Jakarta: Sinar Grafika.
- Mulyadi, Lilik. (2012). *Hukum Acara Pidana Indonesia*. Bandung: Citra Aditya Bakti.
- Prakoso, Djoko. (2010). *Peranan Psikologi dalam Pemeriksaan Tersangka pada Tahap Penyidikan*. Jakarta: Ghalia Indonesia.

- Prastowo, R.B.B. (2006). Delik Formil/Materiil, Sifat Melawan Hukum Formil/Materiil Dan Pertanggungjawaban Pidana Dalam Tindak Pidana Korupsi. *Jurnal Hukum PRO JUSTITIA*, Vol 24.
- Prodjohamidjojo, Martiman. (2011). Penerapan Pembuktian Terbalik dalam Delik Korupsi. Bandung: Mandar Maju.
- Rahardjo, Satjipto. (2012). Ilmu Hukum. Bandung: Citra Aditya Bakti.
- Sianturi, S.R. (2002). Asas-asas Hukum Pidana di Indonesia dan Penerapan, Cet. 3. Jakarta: Storia Grafika.
- Soekanto, Soerjono. (2011). Faktor-Faktor yang Mempengaruhi Penegakan Hukum. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Susanto. (2003). Naskah Mengenal Identifikasi Polri. Jakarta: Badan Reserse Kriminal Polri Pusat Identifikasi.
- Sutanto, I Ketut. (2009). Panduan Praktis Membuat Surat-Surat Penyidikan. Jakarta: Sinar Grafika.

Determinants of Job Satisfaction

Indri Mandasari Pohan¹, Kiki Farida Ferine²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: kikifarida@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

This research aims to examine the influence of compensation and organizational climate on job satisfaction in moderating organizational commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province. Human Resource Management (HRM) is an important factor and the heart of every business. This is caused by the vigilant attitude of the human resources management team towards the workforce of each employee in the company. The results of this research are as follows: Compensation has a negative and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction and is moderated by organizational commitment with a value of -0.019 and a value of 0.455. Organizational climate has a negative and insignificant effect on job satisfaction and is moderated by organizational commitment with a value of -0.074 and a value of 0.296. Organizational climate has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction with a value of 0.273 and a value of 0.045. Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.496 and ap value of 0.000. Compensation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.215 and ap value of 0.006.

Keywords: Compensation, Organizational Climate, Organizational Commitment, Job Satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

The operational efficiency of a business is greatly influenced by the human element itself. Therefore, this is what shows the need for careful consideration, especially regarding human dignity and worth. Modern businesses today emphasize human resource management through the implementation of human resource management programs. The human resource management initiatives mentioned above will return to employee loyalty, work performance, and employee promotion-related skills that can be utilized by an employee. Human resources play an important role in agency activities, because in any case the progress and success of an agency cannot be separated from the role and ability of good human resources. Employees are people who work in an organization or in a government agency or business entity and receive wages for their services. Compensation is a psychological state that describes the relationship between commitment and work production and has consequences for an individual's decision to stay or leave the company. The psychological state for each type of commitment, however, is very different. This is because the issue of pay equity will be associated with the employee's ability to meet all their daily needs. Furthermore, the issue of pay equity reveals the philosophy of leadership or the organization on how to treat its personnel. Compensation is one way to improve employee performance. Designing an appropriate compensation system in accordance with employee performance reports and achievements that employees have given to the company is the right step to provide welfare for employees. Compensation is not only seen from educational background, length of service, and position but also seen from employee performance reports and achievements. As is known, compensation consists of basic salary and incentives. Organizational climate is the environment faced by the organization in making decisions. According to Berberoglu (2018), organizational climate is an individual's perception of their work environment. Commitment is a person's trust and acceptance of the organization to survive and be loyal to the interests of the organization so as to form high loyalty in maintaining its membership.

This commitment must be possessed by every member of the organization or someone who works in a company to achieve common goals. In many organizations, organizational commitment is one of the absolute requirements in holding certain managerial positions. Organizational commitment is employee loyalty to the organization, which is reflected in their high involvement in achieving organizational goals. Employee loyalty is reflected through the willingness and desire of employees to always try to be part of the organization, as well as their strong desire to survive. Job satisfaction is quite an interesting and important issue, because it has proven to be very beneficial for the interests of individuals, industry and society. The job satisfaction factor is something that is individual about a person's feelings towards their work. Each individual has a different level of satisfaction. If employees are very satisfied with their work and experience positive emotions while working, they can do their jobs better and choose to stay in the organization for a longer period of time. Therefore, employee job satisfaction is very important for the success of an organization because employees who are satisfied with their work will be better at fulfilling their duties, positive feelings that grow because of employee job satisfaction also foster creativity, improve problem-solving skills, and decision-making

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Compensation have a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
2. Does Organizational Climate Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
3. Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant influence on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
4. Can Organizational Commitment moderate Compensation at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province?
5. Can Organizational Commitment Moderate Organizational Climate at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of Compensation on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
2. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Climate on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
3. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Commitment on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
4. To determine and analyze the influence of organizational commitment in moderating compensation on job satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
5. To determine and analyze the influence of organizational commitment in moderating organizational climate on job satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction is an effectiveness or emotional response to various work factors, and employee feelings about whether a job is enjoyable or not. Generally towards a person's work that shows the difference between the amount of appreciation received by workers and

the amount they believe they should receive (Afandi 2021). According to Fattah (2017) job satisfaction can be interpreted to see feelings of pleasure or displeasure with the work being done.

Job Satisfaction Indicators

According to Afandi (2021), job satisfaction indicators are as follows:

- 1) Work, the content of the work that a person does can be a factor in job satisfaction;
- 2) Wages, the amount of payment a person receives as a result of doing his work, whether it is in accordance with the needs that are felt to be fair;
- 3) Supervisor, someone who always gives orders or directions in carrying out their work; And
- 4) Co-workers, someone who constantly interacts in carrying out work can make work enjoyable or unpleasant.

Compensation

According to Hasibuan (2017) Compensation is all income in the form of money, goods directly or indirectly received by employees as compensation for services provided to the company. The provision of compensation can also reflect the status, position or position, and also the length of service of an employee of the company. Sutrisno (2017) stated that compensation is one of the important functions in human resource management (HRM).

Compensation Indicators

According to Hasibuan (2017) compensation indicators are:

1. Salary is money given every month to employees as compensation for their contributions.
2. Wages are rewards given directly to employees based on working hours.
3. Incentives are financial rewards given directly to employees whose performance exceeds specified standards.
4. Allowances are compensation given to certain employees as a reward for their sacrifices.
5. Facilities are supporting facilities provided by the company organization.

Organizational Climate

Understanding Organizational Climate

According to Wirawan (2017) organizational climate describes the state of the internal environment of the organization and is rooted in organizational culture. According to Darodjat (2015) organizational climate is something that can be measured in the work environment, both directly and indirectly, affecting employees and their work where they work.

Organizational Climate Indicators

According to Wirawan (2017), the indicators of Organizational Climate are:

- a. Responsibility is the feeling of being a leader for yourself without always having to double check all the decisions taken, when an employee gets a job, the employee concerned knows that it is his job.
- b. Identity is a feeling of belonging to a company and being accepted in a group within the work environment.
- c. Warmth is a feeling of a friendly work atmosphere and is more emphasized on conditions of friendliness or friendship in informal groups, as well as good relationships between co-workers.

- d. Support is things related to support and relationships between fellow co-workers, namely feelings of mutual help between leaders and employees, with more emphasis on the mutual support between superiors and subordinates.
- e. Conflict is a situation of conflict or difference of opinion between subordinates and superiors and subordinates with subordinates.

Organizational Commitment

Understanding Organizational Commitment

According to Priansa (2016) organizational commitment is employee loyalty to the organization, which is reflected in high involvement in achieving organizational goals. Employee loyalty is reflected in the employee's willingness to always try to be part of the organization and a strong desire to stay in the organization. According to Robbins (2016) organizational commitment is defined as a condition where an employee sides with the organization and its goals and willingness to maintain membership in a particular job of an employee, while high organizational commitment means siding with the organization and recruiting the individual.

Organizational Commitment Indicators

According to Robbins (2016), the indicators of organizational commitment are:

1. Affective commitment, namely an emotional feeling towards the organization and belief in values.
2. Continuance commitment is the perceived value of remaining in the organization compared to leaving the organization.
3. Normative commitment, namely the obligation to remain in an organization for moral and polite reasons.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

The hypothesis of this study is as follows:

- H1 Compensation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

- H2 Organizational Climate has a positive and significant influence on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H3 Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant influence on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H4 Organizational Commitment can moderate Compensation on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H5 Organizational Commitment can moderate Organizational Climate towards Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.

METHOD

Types of research

According to Sugiyono (2018), quantitative data is a research method based on positivity (concrete data), research data in the form of numbers that will be measured using statistics as a calculation test tool, related to the problem being researched to produce a conclusion.

Time and Place of Research

This research was conducted from September to October 2024. This research was conducted at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province, Jalan Balai Kota No. 4 Medan.

Population

According to Sugiyono (2018), population is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics that are determined by researchers to study and then draw conclusions.

Sample

The sample of this study was all the population at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of Sumatra Province, totaling 70 employees using the saturated sampling technique. According to Sugiyono (2018), a sample is the sum of the parts of the number and characteristics possessed by the population.

Data source

The research data source used by researchers is a primary data source, the primary data source is the researcher obtains data directly. Sugiyono (2018) Primary data sources are data sources that directly provide data to data collectors or researchers.

Data collection technique

The data collection technique used is a questionnaire, the researcher will distribute the questionnaire to the respondents who are the sample. According to Sugiyono (2018), a questionnaire is a data collection technique carried out by giving a set of written questions or statements to respondents to answer.

Data Analysis Methods

The statistical test tool used in this study is the variance-based structural equation test or better known as Partial Least Square (PLS) using SmartPLS 3.0 software. According to Imam Ghozali (2006), the Partial Least Square (PLS) method explains that the variance-

based structural equation model (PLS) is able to describe latent variables (not directly measured and measured using indicators (manifest variables)).

Outer model

This model includes testing individual item reliability, internal consistency or construct reliability, Average variance extracted. The three measures are grouped based on convergent validity which measures the degree of correlation between variables and latent variables. In addition to convergent validity, there is also discriminant validity testing. Measurement modeling is carried out to determine the relationship between variables and their indicators. This individual item reliability test describes the correlation between each measurement item (metric) and its structure in the standardized loading factor value. If the ideal load factor value is greater than 0.5, this indicator is valid as an indicator that can measure the structure. Furthermore, internal consistency measurements are carried out which are evaluated with composite reliability with a minimum value of 0.7.

Inner model

Structural model measurement is carried out by researchers to determine the relationship between hypothesized structures. In this model, there are several steps to carry out the evaluation. The first step is to check the significance of the relationship between variables. This can be seen from the path coefficient which describes the strength of the relationship between variables. The size of the path coefficient (β) which has a threshold value greater than 0.2 means that the path has an effect on the model.

The second step is to test the T-test value with the bootstrapping method using a two-tailed test with a significance level of 5% to test the research hypothesis. If the T-test value is greater than then the research hypothesis developed can be accepted.

The third step is to evaluate the value R^2 (coefficient of determinant). This value explains the variance of each target variable with a standard size of around 0.75 is stated as strong, around 0.5 is moderate, and less than 0.25 indicates a low level of variance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

The measurement model test (outer model) is used to determine the relationship between latent and manifest variables. The test has convergent validity, discriminant validity, and reliability.

Convergent Validity

This test is seen from the loading factor; the limit value is 0.7, and the limit value Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is 0.5; if it exceeds this number then it is said to be valid. This means that the indicator value is considered valid if it describes the build variable with a value greater than 0.7. The structural model used in this study is depicted in the figure below:

Figure 2. Outer Model
Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

Smart PLS output for loading factor gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings In this study there are equations and equations consist of two equations.

$$Y = b_1X_1 + b_2Z + b_3X_1Z + e_1$$

$$Y = 0.215 X_1 + 0.496Z - 0.019X_1Z + e_1$$

$$Y = b_2X_2 + b_3Z + b_4X_2Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.273X_2 + 0.496 Z - 0.074 X_2Z + e_2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Organizational Climate (X2)	Job Satisfaction (Y)	Organizational Commitment (Z)	Compensation (X1)
X1.1				0.884
X1.2				0.891
X1.3				0.855
X1.4				0.858
X1.5				0.905
X2.1	0.786			
X2.2	0.911			
X2.3	0.923			
X2.4	0.925			
X2.5	0.866			
Y.1		0.910		
Y.2		0.873		
Y.3		0.916		
Y.4		0.904		
Z.1			0.898	
Z.2			0.899	
Z.3			0.919	

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

Table 1 above shows the value of each variable, and states that the indicator of each variable is greater than 0.7, which means that each indicator item has a value greater than 0.7, which indicates that the data is original and can be subjected to additional research.

Discriminant Validity

Further research will determine the validity of the data using Discriminate Validity, with the aim of finding out whether the cross loading value is greater than other latent variables in order to find out the findings of indicators that have a strong relationship with the concept. The following table shows the findings of cross loading from the validity test, as follows:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Organizational Climate (X2)	Job Satisfaction (Y)	Organizational Commitment (Z)	Compensation (X1)
X1.1	0.710	0.740	0.704	0.884
X1.2	0.729	0.751	0.747	0.891
X1.3	0.765	0.774	0.731	0.855
X1.4	0.794	0.779	0.805	0.858
X1.5	0.825	0.781	0.775	0.905
X2.1	0.786	0.752	0.733	0.830
X2.2	0.911	0.815	0.846	0.731
X2.3	0.923	0.856	0.885	0.776
X2.4	0.925	0.844	0.861	0.769
X2.5	0.866	0.823	0.800	0.752
Y.1	0.844	0.910	0.851	0.775
Y.2	0.804	0.873	0.807	0.731
Y.3	0.847	0.916	0.870	0.832
Y.4	0.844	0.904	0.859	0.800
Z.1	0.785	0.817	0.898	0.775
Z.2	0.868	0.873	0.899	0.767
Z.3	0.884	0.862	0.919	0.787

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

It can be seen in the table above that the cross loading factor value of each variable and its indicators can be explained that the cross loading value of each variable gets a greater value than the cross loading on other latent variables for each variable, meaning that this study is discriminantly valid.

Composite reliability

In composite reliability research, each variable is evaluated using its reliability value; if the variable value is greater than 0.60 then the research is considered reliable; if between 0.60 and 0.7, then it is not reliable. The table below shows the Coranbach alpha, composite reliability, and AVE values, which are used to determine whether the research is reliable and valid.

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Moderation Effect 1	1,000	1,000	1,000
Moderation Effect 2	1,000	1,000	1,000
Organizational Climate (X2)	0.929	0.947	0.781
Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.922	0.945	0.812
Organizational Commitment (Z)	0.890	0.932	0.819
Compensation (X1)	0.926	0.944	0.772

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

In table 3 above, the Cronbach alpha column shows the value of each variable is greater than 0.7, indicating that the variable's dependability data is reliable. The composite reliability column has a value greater than 0.6, indicating that each variable is considered reliable because the data exceeds 0.6. The AVE column shows that each variable has a value greater than 0.7, indicating that the data is authentic in terms of AVE. All variables in the Cronbach alpha, reliability, and AVE columns have values above 0.7 and 0.6, indicating reliability and validity.

Inner Model Analysis

Structured model evaluation (inner model) is conducted to ensure that the basic model is accurate and well-built. The stages of examination conducted in the primary model assessment can be seen from several markers, namely:

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.915	0.908

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

In table 4, there is an Rsquare value for the Job Satisfaction variable of 0.915 or 91.5%, meaning that the influence of compensation, organizational climate and organizational commitment on job satisfaction is 0.915 or 91.5% and the rest is in other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After examining the inner model, the next step is to investigate the relationship between idle build, as suggested in this review. In this review, speculative testing is performed using T-Statistics and P-values. Speculation is made whether the T-Insights value is greater than 1.96 and P-Values <0.05. The following are the consequences of the direct impact path coefficients:

Table 5. Hypothesis and Moderation Effect

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Moderation Effect 1 -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	-0.019	0.112	0.455	Rejected
Moderation Effect 2 -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	-0.074	0.538	0.296	Rejected
Organizational Climate (X2) -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.273	1,694	0.045	Accepted
Organizational Commitment (Z) -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.496	3,326	0,000	Accepted
Compensation (X1) -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.215	2,548	0.006	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

In table 5 there are the results of the hypothesis, which will be explained as follows:

1. Compensation has a negative and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction and is moderated by organizational commitment with a value of -0.019 and p values of 0.455, meaning that organizational commitment is not a moderating variable because it is unable to have a significant effect, perhaps in other studies with different titles and different places, organizational commitment can have a significant effect if used as a moderating variable.
2. Organizational Climate has a negative and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction and is moderated by organizational commitment with a value of -0.074 and p values of 0.296, meaning that organizational commitment is not a moderating variable because it cannot have a significant effect when it becomes a moderating variable, perhaps these results are different from previous researchers.
3. Organizational climate has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction with a value of 0.273 and p values of 0.045. If a good organizational climate increases, job satisfaction will increase, conversely, if it decreases, job satisfaction will decrease.
4. Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.496 and p values of 0.000. If organizational commitment increases, job satisfaction increases, conversely, if organizational commitment decreases, job satisfaction decreases.
5. Compensation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.215 and p values of 0.006. If compensation increases, job satisfaction increases, conversely, if it decreases, job satisfaction decreases.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Compensation has a negative and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction and is moderated by organizational commitment with a value of -0.019 and p values of 0.455.
2. Organizational climate has a negative and insignificant effect on job satisfaction and is moderated by organizational commitment with a value of -0.074 and p values of 0.296.
3. Organizational Climate has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with a value of 0.273 and p values of 0.045.
4. Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.496 and p values of 0.000.
5. Compensation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.215 and p values of 0.006.

Suggestion

1. The organization must provide compensation that is appropriate to the position and work results of the employee to stabilize employee performance.
2. The organization must provide a good climate for employees in the organization.
3. Organizations must increase employee organizational commitment or seek employees who are willing to commit to the organization.
4. The organization must be able to create employee satisfaction with their work for the organization.
5. It is hoped that this research will be used as input for organizational weaknesses and deficiencies so that they can be overcome.
6. It is hoped that this research can be used as reference material for new research with other titles and research models.

REFERENCES

- Afandi, P. (2021). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Pekanbaru: Zanafa Publishing.
- Berberoglu, A. (2018). Impact of organizational climate on organizational commitment and perceived organizational performance: Empirical evidence from public hospitals. *BMC Health Services Research*, 18(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-018-3149-z>
- Ghozali, Imam. 2016. *Structural Equation Modelling Metode Alternatif dengan Partial Least Square*. Semarang: Universitas Diponegoro.
- Hasibuan, Malayu. 2017. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- Hussein Fattah. 2017. *Kepuasan Kerja dan Kinerja Pegawai*. Yogyakarta: Elmatera.
- Kusdinar, D., & Haholongan, R. (2019). The influence of self leadership on innovative behavior. *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*, 74, 97–100.
- Priansa. 2016. *Manajemen SDM dalam Organisasi Publik dan Bisnis*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Robbins, Stephen P. (2016). *Perilaku Organisasi*. Jakarta Selatan : Salemba Empat.
- Sutrisno, 2014. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Cetak Ke Enam. Pranada Media Group, Jakarta.
- Sutrisno, Edy, 2017, *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia, Edisi Pertama*, Jakarta, Kencana.
- Sugiyono. 2018. *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*, penerbit Alfabeta, Bandung
- Wirawan. (2017). *Evaluasi Kinerja Sumber Daya Manusia Teori Aplikasi dan Penelitian*. Jakarta. Penerbit: Salemba Empat.

Performance Determinants

Azhari¹, Kiki Farida Ferine²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: kikifarida@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

This research aims to change the organization's bad habits and make improvements to cover its shortcomings, and to determine the influence of training and motivation on performance in teamwork moderation at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province. Every company really needs an organization that is useful for meeting human needs. The general goal of a company is to realize quality production results and maintain the survival of a company. In an effort to achieve these goals, the main driving factor is humans. Human Resources (HR) is one of the main factors for the survival of a company. The results of this research are as follows: Training has an effect on performance moderated by teamwork, getting positive results but not significant with a sample value of 0.072 and a p value of 0.229. Motivation's influence on performance is moderated by teamwork with an original sample value of -0.140 and a p value of 0.129. Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on performance with an original sample value of 0.310 and a p value of 0.006. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on performance with an original sample value of 0.462 and a p value of 0.000. Training has a positive and insignificant effect on performance with the original sample 0.157 and p value 0.116.

Keywords: Training, Motivation, Teamwork, Performance.

INTRODUCTION

In an effort to achieve these goals, the main driving factor is humans. Human Resources (HR) is one of the main factors for the survival of a company. The success of a company depends on the organization in the company. Human resources (HR) are closely related to personnel who have the goal of obtaining and developing a more qualified workforce. The function of human resources itself has activities such as recruitment, selection, development, maintenance, and use. Human resources (HR) are an important asset for the company because of their role as the subject of implementing policies and operational activities of the company. Resources owned by the company such as models, methods and machines cannot provide optimum results if they are not supported by human resources who have optimum performance. Human resources are people who design and produce goods or services, monitor quality, market products, allocate financial resources, and formulate all strategies and goals of the organization. Without people who have expertise or competence, it is impossible for an organization or company to achieve its goals.

To improve organizational goals, training is a systematic process that takes into account student performance. In the final year of the program, training is done based on needs rather than randomly. Effective training begins when students identify a need; if there is a need, then the training must also change, either through the acquisition of new skills or through preparation for a higher standard. In addition, training can be defined as any formal and informal activity that contributes to the improvement and enhancement of knowledge, skills, and behavior levels in the workplace. Training and development are often heard in the world of work in companies, organizations, institutions, or even in health institutions.

Motivation can also be said as a plan or desire to achieve success and avoid failure in life. Someone who has motivation means that he has the strength to achieve success in life. Motivation is an inner drive that everyone has to carry out a task in order to achieve

something they want. Motivation that strengthens and supports individual efforts to meet goals (needs). A team can be defined as a group of individuals who work collectively to achieve the same goals and objectives to provide excellent quality of service (Sanyal & Hisam, 2018). Team Work is an activity that is managed or carried out by a group of people in building effective teamwork, a leader must be able to understand and manage the levels of development, norms, cohesiveness, and conflicts that are occurring in his company. According to Lubis (2021), teamwork is a great way to combine different talents and offer innovative solutions. Teamwork is one of the drivers of energy and synergy for team members to make it easier to carry out tasks given by the company and great ideas will not happen without good collaboration. Performance is a function of motivation and ability. To complete a task or job, a person should have a certain degree of willingness and not a certain ability. Performance in an organization is the answer to the success or failure of the organization's goals that have been set. Superiors or managers often do not pay attention unless it is very bad or everything goes wrong. Too often managers do not know how bad performance has declined so that the company/agency faces a serious crisis. If employee performance is good, it can be ascertained that organizational performance is also good and has an impact on achieving organizational goals. Mangkunegara (2017) describes performance as a work achievement, namely the results of work in terms of quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out tasks according to the responsibilities that have been given to him.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Training Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
2. Does Motivation have a positive and significant effect on Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
3. Does Teamwork have a positive and significant effect on Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
4. Does Teamwork moderate the Training at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province?
5. Does Teamwork Moderate Motivation at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province?
6. Does Teamwork have a positive and significant effect on Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of training on performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
2. To find out and analyze Motivation for Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
3. To determine the influence of Teamwork on Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
4. To determine and analyze the influence of Teamwork in moderating the relationship between Training and Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
5. To determine and analyze the influence of Teamwork in moderating the relationship between Motivation and Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Performance

Definition of Performance

According to Zuriana (2019) Employee performance in a company is a basic foundation that must be built, maintained and developed in the company in order to provide a positive impact on the company both in quality and quantity. According to Saleh (2015) Performance is generally interpreted as performance, work results or work achievements. Performance has a fairly broad meaning, not only stating the results of work, but also how the work process takes place and employee performance can be interpreted as the output or results of employee work according to their duties and responsibilities to achieve organizational goals.

Performance Indicators

According to Saleh (2015) the performance indicators are as follows:

1. Work Quality Can be measured from employee perceptions of the quality of work produced and the perfection of tasks against employee skills and abilities. The results of the work done are close to perfect or meet the expected goals of the work.
2. Utilization of working time Measured from employee perception of an activity completed from the beginning of time to output. Can complete at the specified time and maximize the time available for other activities.
3. Quantity of Work Measured from employee perception of the number of assigned activities and their results.

Training

Definition of Training

According to Susanti (2019), training is a way to develop skills, insight, knowledge of employees to carry out their roles, duties and obligations. According to Mulyani (2019), training is "a program that aims to cover the gap between employee skills and job requirements, as well as to increase employee efficiency and effectiveness in achieving work targets.

Training Indicators

Training indicators according to Mulyani (2019) are:

1. Objective: Holding training certainly requires an objective, especially the preparation of a plan and the desired results from the training.
2. A goal is a state or condition that an organization wants to achieve in the short or long term.
3. Trainer (Trainer), in carrying out training, a reliable and competent trainer is one of the supporting factors in achieving the success of a training.
4. Material, after the objectives are set, a good training program needs to pay attention to the material to be provided. The material in question must be in accordance with the needs of employees when carrying out the work process in the field.
5. Method, choosing the right method can have a good impact on the implementation of the training program, namely that the training runs effectively and efficiently.
6. Participants, in addition to trainers (trainers) in carrying out training certainly need participants as objects to be trained. Training participants must meet the required criteria.

Motivation

Understanding Motivation

According to Darojat (2015), motivation is a psychological process that reflects the interaction between attitudes, needs, perceptions, and decisions that occur within a person. According to George and Jones (2015), motivation is a psychological force within a person that determines the direction of a person's behavior within an organization that causes movement, direction, and effort, and persistence in facing obstacles to achieve a goal.

Motivation Indicators

Motivation indicators according to George & Jones (2015) are:

1. Employee Behavior The ability of employees to choose the work behavior they will choose. Good employee behavior at work shows that employees are motivated at work.
2. Employee Effort This is related to the hard work done by employees in working. The hard work done by employees indicates that employees are motivated in working.
3. Employee Persistence Employee persistence refers to the behavior of someone who continues to want to work despite obstacles, problems, and barriers. High employee persistence indicates that employees have high motivation.

Teamwork

Understanding Teamwork

According to Hamiruddin et al., (2019) teamwork is a group of individuals who work together to achieve similar goals and can be lighter to achieve those goals by working together than doing it alone. According to Anggraeni & Saragih (2019) teamwork is a group of people who have the ability to complete a job together by directing each achievement they have to achieve better results. The achievements that have been achieved can make team members more enthusiastic in achieving the next goals.

Teamwork Indicators

According to Hamiruddin et al., (2019) there are 4 indicators of team collaboration, namely:

1. Focus on team goals The team focuses on the goals that have been set in achieving the organization.
2. Motivate each other in completing tasks. Motivation is very necessary so that members are more motivated in doing a job.
3. Establish cooperation among team members. Team members will establish good cooperation to achieve organizational goals.
4. Coordination in the process of completing tasks Coordination within each team facilitates the completion of a task.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

- H1 Training has a positive and significant effect on Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H2 Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H3 Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on Performance in Representative Offices Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H4 The influence of teamwork is able to moderate the relationship between training and performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H5 The influence of teamwork is able to moderate the relationship between motivation and Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

METHOD

Types of research

According to Sugiyono (2018), the definition of quantitative methods is: Quantitative methods are research methods based on the philosophy of positivism, and are used to research certain populations or samples, data collection uses research instruments, data analysis is quantitative or statistical, with the aim of testing previously established hypotheses.

Location Place and Time

The time of this research is September to October 2024. The location of this research is at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province, Jalan Balai Kota no. 4 Medan.

Population

The population of this study was all Bank Indonesia employees amounting to 70 employees. Sugiyono (2018), population is a generalization area consisting of objects and which have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn.

Sample

The research sample used was all employees who were made into a population of 70 employees. Sample According to Sugiyono (2018) a sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population. While the sample size is a step to determine the size of the sample taken in conducting a study.

Research Data Sources

The research data sources used are primary data sources. According to Sugiyono (2018) Primary data is a data source that directly provides data to data collectors. Data is collected by researchers themselves directly from the first source or the place where the research object is carried out.

Data collection technique

This study uses a questionnaire data collection technique where researchers distribute statement questionnaires and will be filled in by respondents. According to Sugiyono (2018) "A questionnaire is a data collection technique that is carried out by giving a set of written questions or statements to respondents to answer".

Data Analysis Methods

Structural Equation Model

The research hypothesis testing was conducted using the Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) approach based on PLS. SEM is a multivariate statistical analysis technique that is generally used to analyze structural relationships that are relatively difficult to measure simultaneously. In addition, it can be used to analyze structural relationships between measured variables and latent constructs. This technique is a combination of factor analysis and multiple regression analysis. SEM is categorized into two approaches. The first approach is called Covariance Based SEM (CBSEM) with a covariance basis and the second approach is called Variance Based SEM with a variance basis.

According to Ghozali & Latan (2015) CBSEM tests the causal relationship of structural models built on the basis of theory and confirms whether the model based on the theory is no different from the empirical model, while PLS is more of a predictive model. PLS is a powerful analysis method because it is not based on many assumptions. Data does not have to be normally distributed, samples do not have to be large, PLS can also be used to confirm theories, and can be used to explain the presence or absence of relationships between latent variables. PLS can analyze constructs formed with reflective indicators and formative indicators at the same time, which cannot be done by CBSEM because an unidentified model will occur (Ghozali & Latan, 2015).

Designing a Measurement Model (Outer Model)

Outer model analysis is used to ensure that the measurements used are suitable for use as measurements (valid and reliable) with the following indicators:

a. Convergent Validity

- b. Discriminant Validity
- c. Composite Reliability & Cronbach Alpha

Designing Structural Model (Inner Model)

According to Ghozali and Latan (2015) Inner model is often also called inner relation model which describes the relationship between latent variables based on substantive theory. The design of structural model of relationship between latent variables is based on the formulation of research problem or hypothesis. In the evaluation of this model, estimation can be done through several stages. The use of R-square for dependent construct, Stone-Geisser Q-Square test for predictive relevance and t-test and significance of structural path parameter coefficient. The R-square method is used to see each dependent latent variable. The interpretation is the same as the interpretation in regression.

Moderation Variable Analysis

Moderation hypothesis testing is done by moderated regression analysis (MRA) estimated by SEM-PLS (Ghozali and Latan, 2015). To test Performance as a moderating variable of the relationship between Teamwork in moderating Training and Motivation, the focus of attention is on the interaction coefficient between Teamwork and Performance. A variable can be said to be a moderating variable and will be stated as significant if the significant t value is less than or equal to 0.05.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Test

By conducting initial testing of the questionnaire instrument, the accuracy and reliability of the variable and indicator data collected for this study have been confirmed. From the test results, it is known that there are four variables in the model that will be used in the study, as listed below:

Evaluation of measurement model (outer model)

Convergent Validity

In this study, the acceptable loading factor value is 0.7 and the acceptable AVE value is 0.5, if the value is higher, it is considered valid. Indicators are considered valid if they have a value > 0.7 when explaining the construction variables. The following graph shows the structural model of this study

Figure 2. Research Model in SmartPLS

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3.

Smart PLS output for loading factor gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two equations.

$$Y = b_1X_1 + b_2Z + b_3X_1Z + e_1$$

$$Y = 0.157 X_1 + 0.310 Z + 0.072 X_1Z + e_1$$

$$Y = b_2X_2 + b_3Z + b_4X_2Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.462 X_2 + 0.310Z - 0.140 X_2Z + e_2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings/Cross Loading

	Teamwork (Z)	Performance (Y)	Motivation (X2)	Training (X1)
X1.1				0.759
X1.2				0.763
X1.3				0.908
X1.4				0.866
X1.5				0.863
X1.6				0.872
X2.1			0.885	
X2.2			0.908	
X2.3			0.873	
Y.1		0.892		
Y.2		0.815		
Y.3		0.837		
Z.1	0.823			
Z.2	0.848			
Z.3	0.885			
Z.4	0.856			

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3.

In table 1, each variable shows a value above 0.7 on its indicator, indicating the validity of the data for further research. After getting the results, this research is continued to the next stage.

Discriminant Validity

This discussion will focus on the results of the discriminant validity test in this section. The cross loading value is used to test the discriminant validity. If the cross loading of an indicator is higher than other variables, it indicates discriminant validity. The cross loading value for each indicator is as follows:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Teamwork (Z)	Performance (Y)	Motivation (X2)	Training (X1)
X1.1	0.713	0.598	0.540	0.759
X1.2	0.693	0.632	0.613	0.763
X1.3	0.673	0.706	0.778	0.908

X1.4	0.687	0.683	0.743	0.866
X1.5	0.676	0.800	0.747	0.863
X1.6	0.750	0.774	0.779	0.872
X2.1	0.780	0.764	0.885	0.823
X2.2	0.748	0.830	0.908	0.751
X2.3	0.606	0.714	0.873	0.663
Y.1	0.764	0.892	0.799	0.754
Y.2	0.747	0.815	0.672	0.712
Y.3	0.621	0.837	0.734	0.663
Z.1	0.823	0.711	0.710	0.741
Z.2	0.848	0.754	0.681	0.683
Z.3	0.885	0.721	0.689	0.690
Z.4	0.856	0.675	0.659	0.717

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3.

In table 2. There is a cross loading factor value on each variable and indicator, there is a value that is greater than the cross loading factor value on each other variable, the cross loading factor of the teamwork variable has a value greater than the cross loading of other latent variables, the cross loading factor value of the performance variable is greater than the cross loading factor value on other latent variables, the cross loading value of the motivation variable is greater than the cross loading of other latent factors, the cross loading factor value on the training variable is greater than the cross loading value on other latent variables.

Composite reliability

In composite reliability analysis, the reliability coefficient of each variable is correlated. Research is said to be reliable if the variable value is more than 0.60, but not reliable if it is less than 0.60 or as low as 0.07. There are several evaluation blocks that can show the effectiveness and validity of research, such as Coanbach alpha, composite reliability, and AVE values shown in the table below.

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Moderation Effect 1	1,000	1,000	1,000
Moderation Effect 2	1,000	1,000	1,000
Teamwork (Z)	0.875	0.914	0.728
Performance (Y)	0.856	0.885	0.720
Motivation (X2)	0.868	0.919	0.791
Training (X1)	0.916	0.935	0.706

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3.

Table 3 shows the high reliability of the data for each variable by showing that all variable values in the Cronbach alpha column are greater than 0.7. Because the data is above 0.6, it is known that the composite reliability column has a value greater than 0.6, which means that each variable is considered reliable. The value of each variable in the AVE

column needs to be checked whether it is greater than 0.7, which means that the data is valid according to AVE. Because each variable value in the reliability, AVE, and Cronbach alpha columns is greater than 0.7 and 0.6, respectively, the value is considered valid and reliable.

Inner Model Analysis

To ensure the baseline model is accurate and robust, an internal model evaluation is performed. The completed checkpoints are one of the markers taken into account when evaluating the primary model.

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

By using the SmartPLS 3.0 program to process the data, here's how to determine the R Square value:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Performance (Y)	0.824	0.810

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3.

There is an R square value in table 4 of performance with a value of 0.824 and if changed to a percentage it becomes 82.4%, meaning that the influence of Training and Motivation is 0.824 and the rest is in other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

The relationship between idle build and data in this example must be ascertained after the deep model is created. T-Statistics and P-Values are checked to perform statistical analysis in this case study. To determine whether the P-Values < 0.05 and T-Insights > 1.96 are used speculation. The impact of the Road Impact Coefficient over time is as follows:

Table 5. Hypothesis Results

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV I)	P Values	Results
Moderation Effect 1 -> Performance (Y)	0.072	0.744	0.229	Rejected
Moderation Effect 2 -> Performance (Y)	-0.140	1,134	0.129	Rejected
Teamwork (Z) -> Performance (Y)	0.310	2,511	0.006	Accepted
Motivation (X2) -> Performance (Y)	0.462	4,183	0,000	Accepted
Training (X1) -> Performance (Y)	0.157	1,199	0.116	Rejected

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3.

The hypothesis results in table 5 are the final results of the research and will be explained as follows:

1. Training has an effect on Performance moderated by Teamwork getting positive but insignificant results with a sample value of 0.072 and p values of 0.229. This means that the Teamwork variable is not a moderating variable because it is unable to influence performance and training.

2. Motivation affects Performance moderated by Teamwork with an original sample value of -0.140 and p values of 0.129. This means that teamwork is not a moderating variable because it is unable to significantly influence performance and motivation.
3. Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on Performance with an original sample value of 0.310 and p values of 0.006. This means that if teamwork improves, performance will also improve, if it decreases, performance will also decrease.
4. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Performance with an original sample value of 0.462 and p values of 0.000. This means that if motivation increases well, performance will also increase well, conversely, if motivation decreases, performance will also decrease.
5. Training has a positive and insignificant effect on Performance with an original sample of 0.157 and p values of 0.116. This means that training does not have a strong effect on employee performance, but for some employees, training means a lot to them.

CLOSING

Conclusion

After getting the results of this research and describing them through hypotheses, the conclusions of this research are as follows:

1. Training has an effect on Performance moderated by Teamwork, obtaining positive but insignificant results with a sample value of 0.072 and p values of 0.229.
2. Motivation influences performance moderated by Teamwork with an original sample value of -0.140 and p values of 0.129.
3. Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on Performance with an original sample value of 0.310 and p values of 0.006.
4. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on performance with an original sample value of 0.462 and p values of 0.000.
5. Training has a positive and insignificant effect on performance with an original sample of 0.157 and p values of 0.116.

Suggestion

After getting the conclusion, the research will provide suggestions, the suggestions given are as follows:

1. It is hoped that this research will be used as input to make the organization more advanced.
2. It is hoped that this research will change the organization's view of employees with poor performance to undertake serious training.
3. It is hoped that this research will be used as reference material for new research with new research titles and models.
4. It is hoped that this research will be useful in the future as a companion to new research.
5. It is hoped that this research can change the mindset of employees and also organizations in responding to employee motivation, training and performance.

REFERENCES

- Anggraeni, L., & Saragih, R. (2019). Pengaruh Kerjasama Tim Terhadap Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan Pt. Pln (persero) Transmisi Jawa Bagian Tengah. *EProceedings of Management*, 6(1).

- A.A. Anwar Prabu Mangkunegara. (2017). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan*, Bandung : Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Darojat, T.A. (2015). *Konsep-Konsep Dasar Manajemen Personalia*. Cetakan ke-1. Refika Aditama. Bandung.
- George, J.M., dan Jones, G.R. (2015). *Understanding and Managing Organizational Behavior* (4thed). New Jersey: Upper Saddle River.
- Ghozali, I. Latan, H. (2015). *Partial Least Square : Konsep, Teknik dan Aplikasi Smart PLS 2.0 M3*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Hamiruddin., Hajar, I., & Saleh, S. (2019). Pengaruh Komunikasi Organisasi, Motivasi Kerja, dan Kerja sama Tim Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai (The Effect Of Organizational Communication, Work Motivation And Teamwork On Employees Performance). *Jurnal Manajemen, Bisnis dan Organisasi (Jumbo)*, 3(1), 138-151.
- Lubis, L. S. (2021). Pengaruh Kerja Sama Tim Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada Pt Sinarmas Multifinance Cabang Pekanbaru [Universitas IslamRiau]. <http://repository.uir.ac.id/id/eprint/6115>
- Mulyani, S. (2019). Pengaruh Pendidikan, Pelatihan, dan Kompetensi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan pada CV Enigma. *Jurnal Ilmiah Semarak* , 130-143.
- Sanyal, S., and Hisam, M. W. (2018). The Impact of Teamwork on Work Performance of Employees: A Study of Faculty Members in Dhofar University, *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*. Vol 20(3), 15–22.
- Saleh, A. (2015). Motivasi Dan Kinerja Terhadap Produktivitas Karyawan Peternakan Ayam Potong Pada Kemitraan Pt. Mitra Gemuk Bersama (Mgb) Di Kabupaten Jember. *Jurnal ISEI Jember*. Jember: Universitas Jember
- Susanti, F. S. (2019). Pengaruh Pelatihan Dan Komunikasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada Klinik Tumbuh Kembang Yamet Pamulang. *JURNAL SeMaRaK*, 1(3), 39–48. <https://doi.org/10.32493/smk.v1i3.y2018>
- Sugiyono. (2018). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*, penerbit Alfabeta, Bandung
- Zuriana, Z., & Rananda, A. (2019). Pengaruh Kompensasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. *Education Journal: Journal Educational Research and Development*, 3(1), 59-64.

Performance Optimization

Ibrahim Hasim Hasibuan¹, Kiki Farida Ferine²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: kikifarida@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

Human resources are a very strategic and fundamental factor in an organization. Compared to other factors, human resources are the most valuable asset. The role of human resources will greatly determine the success or failure of the organization in achieving the vision and mission that has been set, therefore human resources are very important for the organization. Apart from determining success, the position of human resources in organizations today is not only as a means of production but also as a driver and determinant of the ongoing activities of the organization. The results of this research are as follows: Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Performance with original sample values of 0.246 and p values 0.000. Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Role Conflict with an original sample value of 0.545 and a p value of 0.000. Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on Performance with an original sample value of 0.268 and a p value of 0.004. Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on Role Conflict with an original sample value of 0.560 and a p value of 0.002. Role Conflict has a positive and significant effect on Performance with an original sample value of 0.446 and a p value of 0.000. Role Conflict has a positive and significant effect on Performance with an original sample value of 0.446 and a p value of 0.000. Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Performance through Role Conflict indirectly with an original sample value of 0.243 and a p value of 0.002. Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on performance through role conflict indirectly with an original sample value of 0.161 and a p value of 0.007.

Keywords: Teamwork, Job Satisfaction, Role Conflict, Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Good human resources will have a positive impact on the company itself. In addition, the government or organization itself is a form of organization that carries out management functions including planning, organizing, directing. Human resources are one of the most strategic and fundamental factors in an organization. Compared to other factors, human resources are the most valuable asset. Teamwork is the ability to work together towards a shared vision and mission. In other words, teamwork is a strong ability to direct and encourage individuals towards and achieve organizational goals together. Through strong teamwork, we can achieve great achievements that we may never have thought of before. That is why teamwork according to experts is something that must be built and maintained properly. Otherwise, the company's goals will be difficult to achieve together. If the company does not have strong cooperation between one division and another, the results of its work will not be satisfactory and inefficient (on time). In a company consisting of various individuals who are required to work in order to achieve organizational goals. Group work is identifying various problems, discussing how to solve these problems and taking action to improve. Job satisfaction for an employee is a very important factor because the satisfaction obtained will also determine a positive attitude towards work. Feelings of satisfaction in work can have a positive impact on behavior, such as job descriptions and job specifications that tend to increase. Creating job satisfaction is not easy because job satisfaction will be created if the variables that influence it can be accommodated well and can be accepted by all employees in the company. Employee job satisfaction can be seen not only when doing

work, but also related to other aspects such as interactions with coworkers, superiors, following regulations, and the work environment. Role conflict is conflict which occurs because there is a clash when we are playing certain roles. As a result, someone who experiences role conflict will be in a state of being adrift, trapped, and confused. Role conflict can make individual can't take decision which is better among the roles he/she plays. Role conflict is a psychological symptom experienced by a person that can cause discomfort and potentially reduce work motivation so that it can reduce overall performance. Employee performance greatly helps the company in achieving short-term and long-term goals. Employee performance as the ultimate goal and is a way for various managers to ensure that employee activities and the output produced are in accordance with organizational goals. Good performance is a step towards achieving organizational goals, therefore, performance is also a determining factor in achieving organizational goals so that efforts need to be made to improve employee performance. Every company in carrying out its activities must have goals to be achieved, to achieve or realize these goals every company must be good at choosing strategies, especially human resource planning which is essentially focused on certain steps taken by management. On the availability of permanent workers to occupy positions and the right time in order to achieve goals and various targets set. They view work as something noble so that the human resource factor in the implementation of work should not be ignored.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Teamwork have a positive and significant effect on Role Conflict at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
2. Does Team Work Satisfaction have a positive and significant effect on Role Conflict at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
3. Does Teamwork have a positive and significant effect on Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
4. Does Team Work Satisfaction have a positive and significant effect on Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
5. Does Role Conflict have a positive and significant effect on Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
6. Does Teamwork have a positive and significant effect on Performance through Role Conflict at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
7. Does Team Work Satisfaction Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Performance through Role Conflict at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of Teamwork on Role Conflict at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
2. To determine and analyze the influence of Team Work Satisfaction on Role Conflict at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
3. To determine and analyze the influence of Teamwork on Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
4. To determine and analyze the influence of Team Work Satisfaction on Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
5. To determine and analyze the influence of Job Satisfaction on Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

6. To determine and analyze the influence of Teamwork on Performance through Role Conflict at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
7. To determine and analyze the influence of Job Satisfaction on Performance through Role Conflict at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Performance

Harahap and Tirtayasa (2020) performance is the result of work that can be found in quality and quantity in carrying out tasks assigned to employees to achieve company goals. Employee performance is the result of work that can be achieved by a person according to their respective authorities and responsibilities in order to achieve company goals.(Prawirosentono, 2019).

Performance Indicators

According to(2020)Employee performance indicators are as follows:

1. Quality of work
2. Quantity of work
3. Punctuality
4. Effectiveness to
5. Organizational Commitment

Teamwork

According to West in Hatta, et. al. (2017) teamwork is a group activity to increase efficiency and effectiveness to lighten the burden of each individual. Teamwork according to (Susanti et al., 2021), Teamwork is a system of integrating the work of a group supported by various expertise with clear goals, and also supported by leadership and communication to produce higher performance than individual performance.

Teamwork Indicators

Teamwork indicators according to Hatta, et al. (2017) are as follows:

1. Shared responsibility for completing work, namely by giving responsibility good cooperation can be created.
2. Contribute to each other, namely by contributing both energy and thoughts, cooperation will be created.
3. Maximizing capabilities, namely by maximizing the capabilities of each team member, cooperation will be stronger and of higher quality.

Job satisfaction

According to Rahmanendra & Suhardi (2019), job satisfaction is an emotional attitude that provides a sense of pleasure and love for an employee's work. According to Robbins & Judge (2016), something that explains an employee's feelings about the work they do based on the results of an evaluation of certain characteristics.

Job Satisfaction Indicators

Job satisfaction indicators according to Rahmahendra and Suhardi (2019), are as follows:

1. Working conditions, namely what is done, how hard the working conditions are, and so on.

2. Promotion opportunities, this is an opportunity for employees to get a promotion.
3. Salary, allowances and honorariums are compensation or rewards given by the company to its employees.
4. Supervisory supervision See how strict the company's supervision is of employees in the company.
5. Relationships through co-workers: This is the closeness between one employee and another.

Role Conflict

Understanding Role Conflict

According to Fahmi, (2016) conflict as one of the processes in which deliberate efforts are made to eliminate efforts with a form of effort to hinder, resulting in frustration in efforts to achieve their goals. (Handoko, 2016) states that role conflict is the emergence of two (or more) role communicators simultaneously that conflict with each other. Role conflict arises when there is more than one request from different sources that causes uncertainty in employees.

Role Conflict Indicators

According to Fahmi (2016), the indicators of role conflict are:

- 1) Human resources
- 2) Putting the rules aside
- 3) Unnecessary activities
- 4) Unclear directions
- 5) Adequate authority

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

- H1 Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on Role Conflict at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H2 Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Role Conflict at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

- H3 Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H4 Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H5 Role Conflict has a positive and significant effect on Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H6 Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on Performance through Role Conflict at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H7 Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Performance through Role Conflict at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

METHOD

Types of research

The type of research used in this study is quantitative research. According to Sugiyono (2015), quantitative research methods can be interpreted as research methods based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations or samples, sampling techniques are generally carried out randomly, data collection uses research instruments, data analysis is quantitative/statistical with the aim of testing the established hypothesis.

Time and Location of Research

This research was conducted from September to October 2024. The location of this research was at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province on Jalan Balai Kota No. 4, Medan.

Research Population

The population of this study was all employees of the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of Sumatra Province, namely 70 employees. According to Sugiyono (2015), population is a generalization area consisting of: objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by the research to be studied and then conclusions drawn.

Research Sample

The sample of this study is all the population in the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, Sumatra Province, which will be used as a sample of 70 employees. And the sampling technique used is the saturated sampling technique. According to Sugiyono (2015), a sample is part of the number and characteristics of the population.

Research Data Sources

Primary data sources are data sources that researchers will use. Primary Data According to Sugiyono (2015), primary data is a data source that directly provides data to data collectors.

Data Collection Techniques

The data collection technique used by researchers is a questionnaire, researchers will distribute questionnaires to be filled in and will be returned at a certain time. According to Sugiyono (2015) questionnaires are efficient data collection techniques if researchers know for sure the variables to be measured and know what can be expected from respondents, in addition questionnaires are also suitable for use if the number of respondents is quite large and spread over a wide area.

Data Determination Techniques

Data analysis in this study uses data processing methods with the SmartPLS program or commonly called PLS-SEM. Partial Least Square (PLS) is an alternative method of Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) that can be used in conducting research. PLS is one of the SEM analyses based on components with concepts that can be measured and observed and assess a study.

Test Measurement Model (Outer Model)

Outer model analysis is conducted to ensure that the measurements used are worthy of being valid and reliable measurements. This outer model analysis proves the relationship between latent variables and each of its indicators. There are stages carried out for instrument testing, namely Validity Test and Reliability Test.

1. Validity Test

According to Sugiyono (2019) Validity testing is carried out to see how far the data generated is based on the research instrument. This study used a questionnaire in data collection, so the questionnaire prepared by the researcher needs to know what will be measured. Therefore, a validity test is needed before the research instrument is carried out. According to the validity test, there are two ways of measuring in the outer model, namely:

- a. Convergent Validity In this measurement, it shows that an indicator can represent and underlie the variables in the study. Each indicator in the variable must have a high correlation, so that the measurement can be said to meet convergent validity if the indicator loading value is greater than 0.6-0.7. In addition, for the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value greater than 0.5, it can be said that the variable is able to explain the research results of at least 50%. (Ghozali & Latan, 2015)
- b. Discriminant Validity Discriminant Validity is a measurement to determine the level of size of a variable that is different from other variables in the model. Discriminant validity is determined through the cross loading value to the measured variable which is greater than the loading factor to other variables where the value achieved must be greater than 0.6. This cross loading value is a useful factor to determine the loading value on the intended construct which is greater than the loading value of other constructs. Therefore, the construct on the discriminant can be declared feasible.

2. Reliability Test

Reliability testing is a test used on a research instrument to determine whether a questionnaire used in data collection in research can be declared feasible or not. This reliability test is measured to determine the accuracy and consistency of the model. In the SmartPLS 3.0 program, there are two methods that can be used to test model instruments, namely Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha. In the Cronbach's Alpha method, the tested value will indicate the reliability of each research variable.

Structural Model Test (Inner Model)

At this stage, the analysis using SEM-PLS is a structural model test (inner model) used to determine the relationship between research constructs. This model is carried out with several stages of testing, namely R-square, F-Square, Q-Square. The following are the criteria at this stage:

- a. R-Square
- b. F Square

- c. $Q^2 > 0$ means the model has predictive relevance. If $Q^2 < 0$ indicates the model has less predictive relevance.
- d. GoF (Goodness of fit) testing is used to test the feasibility of a structural equation model as a whole by calculating the (GoF) value. The GoF value in this model is above 0.50 (Ghozali, 2017).

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing is a step in the research process that aims to determine whether the hypothesis is accepted or not (Zakariah & Afriani, 2021).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

The purpose of external model evaluation is to assess the validity and dependability of a particular model. This analysis will be based on the influence of loading, AVE (Average Variance Extracted), discriminant validity, and composite reliability.

Loading factor

Factor loading is the first step in validating a model; the requirement is that it must be greater than 0.6 for the indicator to be considered valid. If it is not valid, it must be based on the model (Husein, 2015). To understand the analysis of the outer model of this study, see the following figure:

Figure 2. Outer Model
Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

If seen from the graph above, it can be seen that each variable has a loading factor of 0 for the latent variable and loads a factor of 0.7 for the manifest variable, this indicates that all indicators and loading factors are valid. The regression analysis of this study is as follows:
substructure 1

$$Z = b_1X_1 + B_2X_2 + e_1$$

$$Z = 0.360X_1 + 0.434X_2 + e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_2X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_5Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.268 X_1 - 0.246X_2 + 0.446 Z + e_2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Job Satisfaction (X2)	Teamwork (X1)	Performance (Y)	Role Conflict (Z)
X1.1		0.869		
X1.2		0.841		
X1.3		0.810		
X2.1	0.821			
X2.2	0.872			
X2.3	0.847			
X2.4	0.881			
X2.5	0.850			
Y.1			0.822	
Y.2			0.879	
Y.3			0.778	
Y.4			0.840	
Y.5			0.893	
Z.1				0.870
Z.2				0.847
Z.3				0.811
Z.4				0.762

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Based on Table 1 above, it can be concluded that all factor loadings are above 0.50. It can be concluded that the validity indicators used in this study are valid or have successfully demonstrated convergent validity, meaning that the research instrument (questionnaire) can accurately predict the variables of interest in this study.

Discriminant Validity

In addition, there is a discriminant validity test (Discriminant Validity) which is seen from the Fornell-Lacker Criterion value and the AVE value of each statement instrument on the reflective indicator in this study. Where both tables are used to ensure that the variables in this study are valid.

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Job Satisfaction (X2)	Teamwork (X1)	Performance (Y)	Role Conflict (Z)
X1.1	0.738	0.869	0.783	0.794
X1.2	0.751	0.841	0.725	0.680
X1.3	0.652	0.810	0.603	0.581

X2.1	0.821	0.705	0.673	0.657
X2.2	0.872	0.705	0.702	0.730
X2.3	0.847	0.721	0.743	0.748
X2.4	0.881	0.773	0.808	0.770
X2.5	0.850	0.732	0.714	0.728
Y.1	0.693	0.739	0.822	0.697
Y.2	0.789	0.731	0.879	0.843
Y.3	0.585	0.664	0.778	0.731
Y.4	0.694	0.683	0.840	0.630
Y.5	0.818	0.743	0.893	0.776
Z.1	0.804	0.698	0.783	0.870
Z.2	0.727	0.649	0.696	0.847
Z.3	0.685	0.710	0.664	0.811
Z.4	0.633	0.610	0.707	0.762
Z.5	0.610	0.691	0.716	0.781

Source : Smart PLS 3.3.3

It can be seen in table 2 that the cross loading value of the job satisfaction variable is greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, there is a cross loading value on the teamwork variable that is greater than the cross loading value on other latent variables, there is a cross loading value on the performance variable that is greater than the cross loading value of other latent variables, there is a cross loading value on the role conflict variable that is greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, so it can be concluded that this study is discriminantly valid.

Composite reliability

In the composite reliability study, each variable is compared for its reliability value; if the variable value is greater than 0.60 then the study is considered reliable; if between 0.60 and 0.7, then it is not reliable; There are several blocks to determine whether the study is reliable, valid, or not. Among them are the Coranbach alpha value, Composite Reliability, and AVE which can be seen in the table below:

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Job Satisfaction (X2)	0.908	0.931	0.730
Teamwork (X1)	0.793	0.878	0.706
Performance (Y)	0.898	0.925	0.711
Role Conflict (Z)	0.873	0.908	0.664

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

The Cronbach alpha coefficient in table 3 above shows that each variable has a value greater than 0.7, indicating that each variable has reliable data. The composite reliability column has a value greater than 0.6, so that each variable in the reliability assumption can

be explained by data greater than 0.6. It can be seen from the AVE column that each variable produces a value greater than 0.7, indicating that the data is original in terms of AVE. All variables from Cronbach's alpha, reliability, and AVE have values greater than 0.7 and 0.6, indicating validity and reliability.

Inner Model Analysis

Structural model evaluation (inner model) is conducted to ensure that the basic model created is accurate and reliable. Some examples of checks conducted in primary model evaluation are as follows:

Coefficient of Determination (R2)

The R square test is used for dependent variables to measure how far the model's ability to explain the variation of the dependent variable. (Ghozali, 2014). The output results of the SmartPLS 3.0 software regarding R square are as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Performance (Y)	0.827	0.819
Role Conflict (Z)	0.761	0.754

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

There is an R square value in table 4, the R square value of the performance variable is 0.827 in percentage of 82.7%, meaning the influence of teamwork, job satisfaction and role conflict on performance is 0.827 or 82.7%, the rest is on other variables, the R square value of the role conflict variable is 0.761 in percentage of 76.1%, meaning the influence of teamwork and job satisfaction on role conflict is 0.761 or 76.1% and the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After analyzing the inner model, the next step is to analyze the relationship between idle builds, as suspected in this review. Specific analysis in this study was conducted by looking at T-Statistics and P-Values. Speculation is used to find out whether T-Insights > 1.96 and P-Values < 0.05. The following are the results of the Direct Impact Road Coefficient:

Table 5. Path Coefficients (Direct Influence) and Path Coefficients (Indirect Influence)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Job Satisfaction (X2) -> Performance (Y)	0.246	2,353	0.009
Job Satisfaction (X2) -> Role Conflict (Z)	0.545	4,444	0,000
Teamwork (X1) -> Performance (Y)	0.268	2,675	0.004
Teamwork (X1) -> Role Conflict (Z)	0.360	2,887	0.002
Role Conflict (Z) -> Performance (Y)	0.446	4,338	0,000

Job Satisfaction (X2) -> Role Conflict (Z) -> Performance (Y)	0.243	2,887	0.002
Teamwork (X1) -> Role Conflict (Z) -> Performance (Y)	0.161	2,474	0.007

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 5 there are direct and indirect influences on the hypothesis results, so the explanation of these results is as follows:

1. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on performance with an original sample value of 0.246 and p values of 0.000. If job satisfaction increases, performance also increases, conversely, if job satisfaction decreases, performance also decreases.
2. Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Role Conflict with an original sample value of 0.545 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if job satisfaction increases, role conflict will increase, conversely, if job satisfaction decreases, role conflict will decrease.
3. Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on performance with an original sample value of 0.268 and p values of 0.004. If good teamwork increases, performance will also increase, conversely, if it decreases, performance will decrease.
4. Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on Role Conflict with an original sample value of 0.560 and p values of 0.002. If teamwork increases, role conflict will increase, conversely, if it decreases, role conflict will decrease.
5. Role Conflict has a positive and significant effect on Performance with an original sample value of 0.446 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if role conflict increases, performance will increase, conversely if it decreases, performance will decrease.
6. Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Performance through Role Conflict indirectly with an original sample value of 0.243 and p values of 0.002, meaning that role conflict is an intervening variable because it is able to influence indirectly and significantly. The presence of good role conflict can help employee performance.
7. Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on Performance through Role Conflict indirectly with an original sample value of 0.161 and p values of 0.007, meaning that role conflict is an intervening variable because it is able to significantly influence the presence of role conflict to make teamwork better and improve.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Performance with an original sample value of 0.246 and p values of 0.000.
2. Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Role Conflict with an original sample value of 0.545 and p values of 0.000.
3. Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on Performance with an original sample value of 0.268 and p values of 0.004.
4. Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on Role Conflict with an original sample value of 0.560 and p values of 0.002.
5. Role Conflict has a positive and significant effect on Performance with an original sample value of 0.446 and p values of 0.000.
5. Role Conflict has a positive and significant effect on Performance with an original sample value of 0.446 and p values of 0.000.

6. Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Performance through Role Conflict indirectly with an original sample value of 0.243 and p values of 0.002.
7. Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on Performance through Role Conflict indirectly with an original sample value of 0.161 and p values of 0.007.

Suggestion

1. Organizations must carry out teamwork to create good employee performance and develop a better organization.
2. The organization must make employees feel very satisfied with the results of the work they do.
3. Organizations must create good role conflicts in work because they are useful for the organization or employees are trained to be able to work on more than one job.
4. Employee performance must develop with the times.
5. This research is expected to provide input for organizations to be able to overcome problems and develop.
6. This research is expected to be used as reference material for new research with new research models.

REFERENCES

- Fahmi, Irham. (2016). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Teori dan Aplikasi*. Bandung: PT.Afabeta.
- Ghozali, Imam, Hengky Latan. (2015). *Konsep, Teknik, Aplikasi Menggunakan Smart PLS 3.0 Untuk Penelitian Empiris*. BP Undip. Semarang
- Ghozali, Imam & Latan, Hengky (2017), *Partial Least Square: Konsep, Metode, dan Aplikasi menggunakan program WarpPLS 5.0, Edisi ke-3*, Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro
- Hatta, M., & Et.al. (2017). Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan, Kerjasama Tim dan Kompensasi terhadap Kepuasan Kerja serta Dampaknya pada Kinerja Karyawan PT. PLN (Persero) Wilayah Aceh, No Title. *Jurnal Magister Manajemen Fakultas Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Unsyiah*, 1(1), 72–73.
- Handoko, T Hani. (2016). *Manajemen*. Edisi 2. Yogyakarta: BPFE-Yogyakarta.
- Harahap, S. F., & Tirtayasa, S. (2020). Pengaruh Motivasi, Disiplin, Dan Kepuasan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Di PT. Angkasa Pura II (Persero) Kantor Cabang Kualanam. *Maneggio: Jurnal Ilmiah Magister Manajemen*, 3(1), 120- 135.
- Husain (2015) *Penelitian bisnis dan manajemen menggunakan partial least squares (PLS) dengan smart PLS 3.0*, Modul ajar jurusan manajemen fakultas ekonomi dan bisnis universitas Brawijaya
- Narimawati, Umi. (2018). “Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif Dan Kuantitatif, Teori Dan Aplikasi.” Bandung: Agung Media 9.
- Prawirosentono. (2019). *Motivasi Dan Kinerja Pegawai*. Indomedia Pustaka.. Sidoarjo
- Rahmanendra, Dwi dan Suhardi, Eka. (2019). Peningkatan Komitmen Organisasi Melalui Pengembangan Budaya Organisasi dan Kepuasan Kerja. *Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan*. 7(2): 852. ISSN 2302-0296

- Purwanto, A., & Sudargini, Y. (2021). Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) Analysis for Social and Management Research : A Literature Review. *Journal of Industrial Engineering & Management Research*, 2(4), 114–123.
- Robbins, Stephen P. (2016). *Perilaku Organisasi*. Jakarta Selatan : Salemba Empat.
- Susanti et al. (2021). ‘Pengaruh Keterlibatan Kerja Karyawan, Loyalitas Kerja Dan Kerjasama Tim Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan CV. Sanitary Bali Pinangsia’, *Jurnal EMAS*, E-ISSN : 2774-3020.
- Sugiyono. (2015). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung : ALFABETA.
- Sugiyono. (2019). *Metodologi Penelitian Kuantitatif dan Kualitatif Dan R&D*. Bandung: ALFABETA.

Performance Determinants

Intan Lydia Tarida Mahdalena¹, Kiki Farida Ferine²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: kikifarida@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

In this case, HR is clearly not the main asset but rather a well-defined and expandable asset, compared to the investment portfolio, and not vice versa as a liability (loss, expense). From this point of view, HR is an investment for a more mature institution or organization. The results of this research are as follows: Communication has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.493 and an ap value of 0.000. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.370 and ap value of 0.008. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Communication with an original sample value of 0.779 and ap value of 0.000. Work Stress has a negative and insignificant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of -0.026 and ap value of 0.398. Work Stress has a positive and significant effect on communication with an original sample value of -0.176 and p value of 0.016. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Communication with an original sample value of 0.385 and p value of 0.001.

Keywords: Job Stress, Work Quality, Communication, Employee Performance.

INTRODUCTION

HR is clearly not a primary asset but rather a well-defined and expandable asset, compared to an investment portfolio, and not vice versa as a liability (loss, expense). From this perspective, HR is an investment for more mature institutions or organizations.

Work stress is a condition where learning demands, obstacles, opportunities, and challenges are different or not in accordance with the expected conditions, which means it is necessary to affect his physical and mental condition, including good, bad for himself and his organizational environment. Workplace stress can be distinguished from employee dissatisfaction in the organization. Therefore, employees and companies must be aware of workplace stress in order to understand what causes employees to feel stressed in their work environment. The level of stress experienced by employees varies depending on the individual experiencing stress; some people are already stressed when facing a particular problem, and some are able to cope well. Stress can cause blind spots. If employees experience stress especially in the work environment, this can also hinder their ability to carry out their work. Quality of work is a factor that must be considered in every business. The purpose of a business can be seen from its production results and the quality of its employees' work. Improving the quality of employee work is very important because the success of a company does not only depend on technology; the human factor also plays an important role in business. (Sengkey et al., 2017). If a company has so many employees, it will make the communication pattern with each other have to run well because communication is the key to the success of a company, but if communication does not go well, it will be a failure in the company ". (Asyari, 2022). Communication patterns in organizations vary with specific patterns, of course this is needed to facilitate the delivery of information, equality of understanding, and reciprocal relationships between employees and with leaders, they must be able to collaborate with each other to achieve common goals. If the working relationship is harmonious, a pleasant work environment will be created and

can increase employee productivity. However, if this behavior continues to hinder effective communication, it will also have a negative impact on employee performance. Employee performance is one of the most important factors that businesses must pay attention to because it helps businesses achieve their goals. The work of a caregiver is the result of a process that begins and ends within a certain period of time based on previously established understanding and preparation.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Job Stress Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
2. Does Employee Work Quality have a positive and significant effect on Communication at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
3. Does Job Stress Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
4. Does Employee Work Quality have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
5. Does Communication Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
6. Does Job Stress Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Employee Performance through Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
7. Does Employee Work Quality Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Employee Performance through Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of work stress on communication at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
2. To determine and analyze the influence of Employee Work Quality on Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
3. To determine and analyze the influence of work stress on employee performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
4. To determine and analyze the influence of Employee Work Quality on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
5. To determine and analyze the influence of communication on employee performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
6. To determine and analyze the influence of work stress on employee performance through communication at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
7. To determine and analyze the influence of Employee Work Quality on Employee Performance through Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee performance

According to Bangun (2018) performance is the achievement of work results achieved by someone in accordance with the specified job requirements. According to Kasmir (2016), performance is a result. With work and work behavior achieved when completing tasks and responsibilities during a certain period of time.

Employee Performance Indicators

According to Bangun (2018) to facilitate employee performance assessment, work standards must be measurable and clearly understood. There are four indicators of employee performance as follows:

1. Quality of work. Workers must understand all the requirements given in order to produce better quality workers and in accordance with those given by the company.
2. Punctuality. A job has certain characteristics in each job and can be completed on time. Each task given has a different risk.
3. Presence. Require employees to attend work according to the time specified.
4. Ability to cooperate. There are tasks that are carried out together, in this case employees are required to work together with other employees to complete their tasks.

Job Stress

According to Robbins and Judge (2017) work stress is a dynamic condition in which an individual is faced with an opportunity, demand or resource related to environmental conditions, organizational conditions and within a person. According to Hasibuan (2016), stress can affect performance and job satisfaction because of the environment experienced by employees. In general, employee performance will decrease if they are stressed because they experience a lot of mental pressure that can cause the person's behavior to become angry and like to be alone.

Job Stress Indicators

Work stress indicators according to Robbins and Judge (2017) are as follows:

1. Environmental Stress Environmental uncertainty affects organizational design, so that uncertainty becomes a burden for employees, especially when organizational change takes place. The environmental dimensions are economic uncertainty, technological uncertainty and political uncertainty causing work stress because employees feel their energy is no longer needed.
2. Organizational Stress Organizational dimension relates to situations where employees experience task demands, role demands, personal demands. Task demands relate to the amount of work that must be completed making employees feel exhausted to complete their work. Role demands relate to the pressures experienced by employees when completing their work. Personal demands relate to the work group not providing technical assistance when needed.
3. Individual Stress This dimension concerns the personal life of each employee. are family problems, personal economic problems and employee personality. It can be concluded that there are three dimensions in work stress, namely environmental stress, organizational stress, and individual stress.

Employee Work Quality

Understanding Employee Work Quality

According to Hasibuan (2018) work quality is a physical standard that is measured because of the work results carried out or implemented by employees on their tasks. (Tjiptono & Chandra, 2017) defines work quality as the condition of all workers who are able to meet the most important needs through the work they do.

Employee Work Quality Indicators

According to Hasibuan (2018) the work quality indicators are as follows:

1. Self-Potential, related to aspects of ability, strength, both those that have not been realized and those that have been realized, which a person has, but have not yet been fully seen to their maximum potential.
2. Optimal Work Results, are the results that an employee is required to have, must be able to provide the best work results which can be seen from the productivity of the organization, quality and quantity of work.
3. Work Process, namely the most important stage where employees carry out their duties and roles through this work process.

Communication

According to Mangkunegara (2017) communication is the process of transferring information, ideas, understanding from one person to another with the hope that others can interpret it according to the intended purpose. Hamali (2016) said that work communication is a process of conveying ideas and information in the form of orders and work instructions from a leader to employees or subordinates to carry out work tasks as well as possible.

Communication Indicators

According to Mangkunegara (2017) the communication indicators are as follows:

1. Sender Skills
2. Sender's Attitude
3. Sender Knowledge
4. Sender Channel Media
5. Receiver Skills
6. Receiver Attitude
7. Receiver Knowledge
8. Receiver Channel Media.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis:

- H1 Work Stress has a positive and significant effect on Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H2 Employee Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Communication at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H3 Work Stress has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.

- H4 Employee Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H5 Communication has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H6 Work Stress has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H7 Employee Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Communication at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.

METHOD

Types of research

According to Sugiyono (2017), quantitative methods can be interpreted as research methods based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations or samples, data collection using research instruments, data analysis is quantitative statistical, with the aim of testing predetermined hypotheses.

Time and Place of Research

This research was conducted from September to October 2024. The location of this research was at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province, the exact location is on Jalan Balai Kota No. 4, Medan.

Population

This study took all the research population at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of Sumatra Province totaling 70 employees. According to Sugiyono (2017) population is an area of equalization/generalization consisting of subjects/objects that have certain qualities and characteristics and are determined by researchers to be studied and then a conclusion is drawn.

Sample

The sample of the research that the researcher wants to use is the entire population at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of Sumatra Province, totaling 70 employees, and the sampling technique used is the saturated sampling technique. According to Sugiyono (2017), a sample is part of the number and characteristics of the population.

Research data sources

Primary data according to Sugiyono (2017) is a data source that directly provides data to data collectors. Primary data in this study is a questionnaire distributed to respondents.

Data collection technique

Data collection in this study is using a questionnaire with a Likert scale. The questionnaire will be distributed to the respondent sample to be filled in. This aims to continue the research. According to Sugiyono (2017), a questionnaire is a data collection technique carried out by giving a set of written questions or statements to respondents to be answered.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Measurement model testing (outer model) is used to determine the specifications of the relationship between latent variables and their manifest variables. This testing includes convergent validity, discriminant validity and reliability.

Convergent Validity

Convergent validity is used to determine the validity of each indicator against the latent variable; the validation results can be seen in the external loading table. The external loading table contains numbers or values that function as indicators of conformity with the variables. The validity of the indicator is determined if it shows that the construct variable has a value greater than 0.7. The structural model used in this study is shown in the figure below:

Figure 2. Outer Model
Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In this research there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Z = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e_1$$

$$Z = -0.176 X_1 + 0.779 X_2 + e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_3X_1 + b_4X_2 + b_5Z + e_2$$

$$Y = -0.026 X_1 + 0.370 X_2 + 0.493Z + e_2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Employee Performance (Y)	Communication (Z)	Quality of Work (X2)	Job Stress (X1)
X1.1				0.935
X1.2				0.762

X1.3				0.815
X1.4				0.891
X1.5				0.841
X1.6				0.877
X1.7				0.856
X1.8				0.897
X1.9				0.780
X2.1			0.893	
X2.2			0.910	
X2.3			0.936	
Y.1	0.887			
Y.2	0.911			
Y.3	0.835			
Y.4	0.785			
Z.1		0.878		
Z.2		0.791		
Z.3		0.825		
Z.4		0.832		
Z.5		0.863		
Z.6		0.829		
Z.7		0.889		
Z.8		0.832		

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

The consequences of handling using SmartPLS should be seen in the table above. The value of the external model or the relationship between the construct and the factor meets the combined legitimacy because all markers have values over 0.70, and it implies that this exploration is substantial.

Discriminant Validity

Discrimination is done to ensure that no two ideas of any idle variable are the same due to different factors. The model has strong discrimination legitimacy if each value of each inert variable has a higher value than the other values for other factors. Here are some examples of legitimate discrimination effects:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Employee Performance (Y)	Communication (Z)	Quality of Work (X2)	Job Stress (X1)
X1.1	-0.719	-0.786	-0.763	0.935
X1.2	-0.644	-0.592	-0.561	0.762
X1.3	-0.551	-0.626	-0.608	0.815
X1.4	-0.557	-0.648	-0.632	0.891
X1.5	-0.460	-0.612	-0.612	0.841
X1.6	-0.575	-0.671	-0.665	0.877

X1.7	-0.542	-0.599	-0.597	0.856
X1.8	-0.656	-0.733	-0.753	0.897
X1.9	-0.368	-0.433	-0.441	0.680
X2.1	0.793	0.800	0.893	-0.736
X2.2	0.738	0.827	0.910	-0.611
X2.3	0.770	0.869	0.936	-0.714
Y.1	0.887	0.749	0.766	-0.590
Y.2	0.911	0.775	0.767	-0.561
Y.3	0.835	0.750	0.716	-0.641
Y.4	0.379	0.189	0.164	-0.277
Z.1	0.799	0.878	0.819	-0.717
Z.2	0.683	0.791	0.758	-0.665
Z.3	0.666	0.825	0.788	-0.634
Z.4	0.741	0.832	0.701	-0.618
Z.5	0.703	0.863	0.754	-0.525
Z.6	0.684	0.829	0.729	-0.658
Z.7	0.794	0.889	0.848	-0.639
Z.8	0.652	0.832	0.737	-0.680

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

It can be seen in table 2 that each variable and indicator has a cross loading factor value that is greater than the cross loading factor value on other latent variables, it can be explained that the cross loading of the employee performance variable is greater than the other latent variables, the cross loading of the communication variable is greater than the cross loading value on other latent variables, the cross loading of the work quality variable is greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, the cross loading of the work stress variable is greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, so this study is discriminantly valid.

Composite reliability

The next test calculates the reliability value using the composite reliability of the indicator block that measures the construct. A construct value is said to be reliable if its Composite Reliability value exceeds 0.60. In addition to looking at the composite reliability value, the reliability value can also be seen in the variable construct value with Cronbach's alpha from the indicator block that measures the construct. A construct is considered reliable if its Cronbach's alpha value exceeds 0.7. The table below shows the loading values of the research variable constructs generated by the Smart PLS software.

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Employee Performance (Y)	0.776	0.855	0.614
Communication (Z)	0.942	0.951	0.710
Quality of Work (X2)	0.901	0.938	0.834
Job Stress (X1)	0.948	0.956	0.710

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Based on the above research, the Cronbach's alpha value greater than 0.7 indicates that all variables are considered reliable for each variable. The combined reliability assessment produces a number greater than 0.6 for each assessment, indicating that all variables are reliable. Another way to verify discriminant validity is to look at the AVE value and the square root of AVE, assuming each construct has a stronger correlation than the correlation between other constructs. Before looking at the correlation, the AVE value is considered valid if it is more than 0.7.

Inner Model Analysis

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Employee Performance (Y)	0.749	0.738
Communication (Z)	0.844	0.840

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 4 there is an R square value in the dependent variable, the employee performance variable has an R square value of 0.749, meaning that the influence of the variables of work stress and work quality, communication on employee performance is 0.749 and the rest is on other variables, for the communication variable there is an R square value of 0.844, meaning that the influence of work stress and work quality on communication is 0.844 and the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After evaluating the inner model, the next step is to investigate the relationship between the hypothesized latent constructs in this study. In this study, the hypothesis was tested using T-statistics and P-values. The hypothesis is accepted if the T-Statistics value is more than 1.96 and P-Values are less than 0.05. The Direct Influence Path Coefficient gives the following results:

Table 5. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Communication (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.493	3,179	0.001	Accepted
Work Quality (X2) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.370	2,432	0.008	Accepted
Work Quality (X2) -> Communication (Z)	0.779	12,233	0,000	Accepted
Job Stress (X1) -> Employee Performance (Y)	-0.026	0.258	0.398	Rejected
Job Stress (X1) -> Communication (Z)	-0.176	2,139	0.016	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In Table 5 are the results of the hypothesis on direct influence as follows:

1. Communication has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.493 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if good communication increases, employee performance will increase, conversely if it decreases, employee performance will decrease.
2. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.370 and p values of 0.008, meaning that if work quality increases, employee performance increases, conversely, if it decreases, employee performance decreases.
3. Work quality has a positive and significant effect on communication with an original sample value of 0.779 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if work quality increases, communication increases, conversely, if it decreases, communication decreases.
4. Work stress has a negative and insignificant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of -0.026 and p values of 0.398, meaning that work stress still has a negative effect but there are large and small scales in work stress so that work stress will always exist and employees will also always exist.
5. Work stress has a positive and significant effect on communication with an original sample value of -0.176 and p values of 0.016, meaning that the higher the work stress, the higher the communication, conversely, if it decreases, communication will decrease.

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Work Quality (X2) -> Communication (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.385	3,007	0.001	Accepted
Job Stress (X1) -> Communication (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	-0.087	1,570	0.058	Rejected

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 6 there is an indirect influence, so the explanation is as follows:

1. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Communication with an original sample value of 0.385 and p values of 0.001, meaning that communication is an intervening variable because it is able to significantly influence, meaning that communication can improve work quality and communication.
2. Work stress has a negative and insignificant effect on employee performance through communication. This can be explained by the original sample value of -0.087 and p values of 0.058, meaning that communication is not an intervening variable because it is unable to have a significant effect.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Communication has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.493 and p values of 0.000.
2. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.370 and p values of 0.008.
3. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Communication with an original sample value of 0.779 and p values of 0.000.

4. Work stress has a negative and insignificant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of -0.026 and p values of 0.398.
5. Work stress has a positive and significant effect on communication with an original sample value of -0.176 and p values of 0.016.
6. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Communication with an original sample value of 0.385 and p values of 0.001.
7. Work stress has a negative and insignificant effect on employee performance through communication with an original sample value of -0.087 and p values of 0.058.

Suggestion

1. Organizations must be able to control work stress in their subordinates.
2. Organizations must improve the quality of employee work by providing training.
3. Organizations must improve good communication to achieve good performance.
4. It is hoped that this research will be used as reference material to improve performance and close organizational weaknesses.
5. It is hoped that this research will be used as reference material for other researchers and create new titles and new models.

REFERENCES

- Abdillah, Willy dan Jogiyanto. 2014. Konsep & Aplikasi PLS (Partial Least Square) untuk Penelitian Empiris. Yogyakarta: BPFE.
- Asyari, M. I. (2022). Masalah Komunikasi di Tempat Kerja dan Solusinya.
- Bangun, W. 2018. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Erlangga. Jakarta
- Dodiansyah, Khafidh. 2014. Hubungan Antara Dukungan Sosial dengan Stres Kerja Pada Karyawan Solopas. Skripsi. Surakarta: Fakultas Psikologi Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta.
- Hasibuan, M. S. P. (2016). Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Edisi Revisi. Jakarta : Bumi Aksara.
- Hasibuan, Malayu SP. (2018). Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Edisi Revisi. Jakarta: PT. Bumi Aksara.
- Hamali. 2016. Pemahaman manajemen sumberdaya mausia. Yogyakarta: Center for Academic Publishing Service
- Kasmir. 2016. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia (Teori dan Praktik). Depok: PT Rajagrafindo Persada
- Mangkunegara. 2017. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan, Bandung : Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. A. (2017). Perilaku Organisasi. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- Sengkey Windri S. Dkk. 2017. Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja dan Stres Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan PT. PLN (Persero) Wilayah Suluttenggo Area Manado.
- Sugiyono, (2017). Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D. Bandung: CV. Alfabeta.
- Tjiptono, F. dan G. Chandra. 2017. Manajemen Strategik. Edisi 3. Yogyakarta: Andi Offset.

Tips to Improve Performance

Julian¹, Kiki Farida Ferine²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: kikifarida@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

HR is one component of the organizational system, which ironically is also one component of the employment management system which prioritizes competition in achieving work results, both in individual and organizational environments. Human resources (HR) are a crucial element. The results of this research are as follows: Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.531 and a p value of 0.000. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Teamwork with an original sample value of 0.325 and a p value of 0.000. Work Quality has a positive and insignificant effect with an original sample value of 0.123 and a p value of 0.127. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Teamwork with an original sample value of 0.424 and a p value of 0.000. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.188 and a p value of 0.026. Training has a positive and significant effect on Teamwork with an original sample value of 0.236 and a p value of 0.021. Training has a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.136 and a p value of 0.077. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Teamwork with an original sample value of 0.173 and a p value of 0.003. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Teamwork with an original sample value of 0.225 and a p value of 0.002. Training has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through teamwork with an original sample value of 0.125 and a p value of 0.035.

Keywords: Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Work Quality, Training, Teamwork, Employee Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Human Resources (HR) is one of the components of an organizational system, which ironically is also one of the components of a workforce management system that prioritizes competition in achieving work results, both in individual and organizational environments. Human resources (HR) personnel are often highly skilled individuals who serve as the backbone of an organization. They play a vital role as assets to businesses and institutions, therefore it is important to train and improve their skills. Some workers go beyond what is required of them to complete tasks assigned to them by their superiors. Workers are willing to help coworkers with tasks that are outside their job descriptions. The behavior exhibited by these workers is called Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). Wibowo (2019) defines OCB as a consistent voluntary effort by employees that goes beyond existing task requirements to support the company's ongoing goals. Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is one of the factors. Not only do workers exhibit OCB behavior But simply do the activities outlined in the job description; they are willing to take on additional responsibilities. In essence, to make the organization's functions more efficient. Therefore, in order for the organization's functions to run well in achieving its goals, every company needs to know how important it is to instill OCB in its personnel. The success and efficiency of work carried out by human resources or other resources in achieving business goals or objectives with good and beneficial results is a measure of the quality of the work produced.

This is the reason why the business world competes with each other to improve quality, namely improving the quality of work and human resources. According to Setyadi and Wartini (2016), the quality of work life that is well managed by an organization or company can make an employee stay in the company. An employee who stays in the company indicates that he feels satisfied with himself. To implement an increase in employee work potential, employees must receive job training. Rapid advances in technology have also made it increasingly important for people to work together and coordinate to complete projects and become more competitive in facing global economic developments. This gives the impression of how important it is for companies to understand the value of teamwork and design strategies to create good teamwork. The assumption of this cooperation is based on the statement Moreover, the completion of tasks is considered to be faster if done together by a team. Internal organizational communication is a tool and means of two-way communication to convey information, maintain relationships between all members of the organization, and avoid misunderstandings that may occur in an organization. Performance is a crucial and interesting component because it has been proven to have significant benefits. An organization expects its employees to work diligently and with all their might in order to produce quality work; without strong performance from each employee, success in achieving goals will be a challenge. If someone meets the standards of quantity and quality of work, they will receive a good performance appraisal. The phenomenon that occurred in this study was the lack of quality of employee work regarding their work, making employee performance less than good, making work take a long time. This is because there is no routine training for employees to develop their abilities and knowledge so that no one carries out organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) to other employees and teamwork is also absent because they are busy improving the quality of their work by practicing doing their own work without having to have any training at all.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Organizational Citizenship Behavior have a positive and significant effect on Teamwork at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
2. Does Work Quality have a positive and significant effect on Teamwork at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
3. Does Training Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Teamwork at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
4. Does Organizational Citizenship Behavior have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
5. Does Work Quality have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
6. Does training have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
7. Does Teamwork Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
8. Does Organizational Citizenship Behavior have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Teamwork at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
9. Does Work Quality Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Employee Performance through Teamwork at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?

10. Does Training Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Employee Performance through Teamwork at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Citizenship Behavior on Teamwork at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
2. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Quality on Teamwork at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
3. To determine and analyze the influence of training on teamwork at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
4. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Citizenship Behavior on Employee Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
5. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Quality on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
6. To determine and analyze the influence of training on employee performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
7. To determine and analyze the influence of Teamwork on Employee Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
8. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Citizenship Behavior on Employee Performance through Teamwork at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
9. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Quality on Employee Performance through Teamwork at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
10. To determine and analyze the influence of training on employee performance through teamwork at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee Performance

According to Rompas et al. (2018), performance is the work results in terms of quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. According to Andriyani (2020), performance is closely related to the results of individual activities over several time periods.

Employee Performance Indicators

Employee performance indicators according to Rompas et al. (2018) are as follows:

- a. Work Quality is measured from employee perceptions of the quality of work produced and the perfection of tasks in relation to employee skills and abilities.
- b. Quantity The quantity of the amount produced is expressed in terms such as number of units, number of activity cycles completed.
- c. Timeliness The level of activity completed at the beginning of the stated time, seen from the perspective of coordination with output results and maximizing the time available for other activities.
- d. Effectiveness The level of use of organizational resources (labor, money, technology, raw materials) is maximized with the aim of increasing the results of each unit in the use of resources.

- e. Independence The level of an employee who will later be able to carry out his work function and work commitment.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Understanding Organizational Citizenship Behavior

According to Griffin in Sukanto (2018) "Organizational citizenship refers to the behavior of individuals who make a positive overall contribution to the organization" (Organizational Citizenship Behavior refers to the behavior of individuals who make a positive overall contribution to the company). According to Putri (2017) Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is a term for employees who provide added value to the work that is their job or added value to the company.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior Indicators

According to Luthans in Sukanto (2018), the indicators of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) are as follows:

1. Altruism, which is a behavior carried out by individuals who voluntarily help their co-workers who are experiencing difficulties in the situation they are facing, either regarding work in the company or other people's personal problems. This dimension leads to providing assistance that is not an obligation that they bear. For example, employees help other co-workers who are not feeling well. In addition to the employee's goal of lightening the workload of their co-workers, this will also help the company in achieving targets on time and for employees it is useful as an exercise in improving performance measures.
2. Conscientiousness, which is behavior carried out by individuals voluntarily in their role as employees to improve their performance in various ways, even when it requires creativity and innovation for the sake of improving the company. For example, having the initiative to improve their competence, either by conducting training or attending seminars voluntarily.
3. Civic Virtue, which is behavior carried out by individuals voluntarily in their role as employees to participate and be responsible for solving company problems for the sake of the company's sustainability. For example, when there is a threat from competitors in business, employees contribute by providing ideas for solving the problem.
4. Courtesy, which is behavior carried out by individuals voluntarily in their role as employees to prevent problems from occurring in the company either due to provocation from outside the company or from individuals within the company. For example, giving warnings to coworkers to always be careful in responding to issues that have a negative impact and always trying to provide correct information for the company.
5. Sportsmanship, which is a behavior carried out by individuals voluntarily in their role as employees in the form of tolerance to survive in uncomfortable or unpleasant conditions without complaining at all. For example, in order to maintain the survival of the company, there is a change in the rules in the company that is not in accordance with employee expectations, employees must be able to accept these conditions and remain positive.

Quality of Work

According to Hasibuan (2019) work quality is a physical standard that is measured because of the work results carried out or implemented by employees towards their tasks. Work quality is a result that can be measured by the effectiveness and efficiency of a job carried out by human resources or other resources in achieving the company's goals or objectives properly (Jaya et.al, 2020).

Work Quality Indicators

According to Hasibuan (2019) the work quality indicators are as follows:

1. Self-Potential, related to aspects of ability, strength, both those that have not been realized and those that have been realized, which a person has, but have not yet been fully seen to their maximum potential.
2. Optimal Work Results, are the results that an employee is required to have, must be able to provide the best work results which can be seen from the productivity of the organization, quality and quantity of work.
3. Work Process, namely the most important stage where employees carry out their duties and roles through this work process.

Training

According to Gultom (2019) training and development for HR is an activity to improve the quality of human resources so that they can become quality resources in terms of knowledge, work skills and a high level of professionalism in working in order to improve the ability to achieve company goals. According to Dessler, (2015) training means providing new employees or existing employees with the skills they need to do their jobs.

Training Indicators

According to Gultom (2019) training indicators are:

1. The goals and objectives of training and development must be clear and measurable.
2. Trainers must have adequate qualifications.
3. Training and development materials must be adapted to the objectives to be achieved.
4. Training and development methods must be appropriate to the level of ability of the participating employees.
5. Training and development participants (trainees) must meet the specified requirements.

Teamwork

According to Sibarani (2018) teamwork is a combination of group work with the support of various abilities and has clear goals, supported by leaders and communication to produce better performance. Then according to Lawasi and Triatmanto (2017), teamwork is the most effective way to unite all employees in carrying out their duties to achieve company goals with better results.

Teamwork Indicators

According to Sibarani (2018), the indicators of teamwork are:

1. Cooperation.

Cooperation carried out by a team is more effective than working individually. The contribution of each individual can become an integrated force. Individuals are said to work together if the efforts of each individual are systematically integrated to achieve a common goal. The greater the integration, the greater the level of cooperation, with the following measuring tools:

- a. Joint responsibility to complete the work, namely by giving responsibility good cooperation can be created.
- b. Contributing to each other, namely by contributing both energy and thoughts, cooperation will be created.
- c. Maximizing capability, namely by maximizing the capability of each team member, cooperation will be stronger and of higher quality.

2. Trust Trust is the belief that someone is serious about what he says and does. High-performance teamwork is characterized by high levels of mutual trust among its members. This means that members believe in the integrity, character and abilities of each member, with the following measuring tools:
 - a. Honesty, namely with honesty team members will create a sense of mutual trust.
 - b. Assignment, namely by assigning tasks to team members means giving trust that team members are capable of carrying them out.
 - c. Integrity, namely that each member is considered to have integrity or act honestly (truthfulness) in working.
3. Solidarity Solidarity is the level of solidarity and positive feelings that exist within a person towards his/her group. The indicators are as follows:
 - a. Task interdependence, namely task interdependence creates cohesion.
 - b. Interdependence of results, namely team members feel that the results achieved are not individual results, but the result of working together as a team.
 - c. High commitment, namely team members are considered to have a high commitment to the goals the team will achieve.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Research Hypothesis

Based on the conceptual framework, the hypothesis of this study is as follows:

- H1 *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* has a positive and significant effect on Team Cooperation at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province.
- H2 It is suspected that the Quality of Employee Work has a positive and significant influence on Teamwork at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province.
- H3 The training had a positive and significant impact on Teamwork at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province.

- H4 *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H5 Employee Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H6 Training has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H7 Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H8 *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Teamwork at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H9 Employee Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Teamwork at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province.
- H10 Training has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Teamwork at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province.

METHOD

Types of research

According to Sugiyono (2019), quantitative research is defined as a research method based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations or samples, data collection using research instruments, quantitative/statistical data analysis, with the aim of testing predetermined hypotheses.

Location and Time of Research

The location of this research is at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province on Jalan Balai Kota No. 4, Medan. The time of this research was conducted from September to October 2024.

Research Population

In this study, the researcher took the population of all employees of the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province as many as 70 employees and will be used as the research population. Population according to Sugiyono (2019) is a generalization area consisting of: objects/subjects that have certain quantities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn.

Research Sample

The sample of this study decided to take a sample, namely all the populations in the research location as many as 70 employees and the research technique used was the saturated sample technique. According to Sugiyono (2019) a sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population.

Research Data Sources

According to Sugiyono (2019), primary data is a source that directly provides data to data collectors, for example data selected from respondents through questionnaires or data from interviews between researchers and sources.

Data collection technique

The data collection technique used in this study is to use a questionnaire to collect data and distribute it to respondents. A questionnaire is a data collection technique that is carried out by giving a set of written questions or statements to respondents to answer (Sugiyono, 2019).

Data Analysis Techniques

The approach used when analyzing this research is the Structural Equation Model Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS) using SMART PLS software. The reason for using this program is because this research is more predictive and explains latent variables than testing a theory and the number of samples in the study is not large.

Evaluation of Measurement Model (outer model or measurement model).

To determine the assessment of discriminant validity, it is done by comparing the square root of average variance extracted (SR of AVE) value with the cross loading of its indicators. If the square root of average variance extracted (SR of AVE) value of the construct is greater than the cross loading value, it can be said to have good discriminant validity. The three criteria used by Pradnyani in his research in assessing the outer model are convergent validity, discriminant validity and composite reliability. Convergent validity of the measurement model with reflective indicators is assessed based on the correlation between item scores/component scores calculated with PLS. The individual reflective measure is said to be high if it correlates more than 0.7

Discriminant validity of the measurement model with reflective indicators is assessed based on the cross loading of the measurement with the construct. If the correlation of the construct with the measurement item is greater than the size of the other constructs, then it indicates that the latent construct predicts the size in their block better than the size in the other blocks. Another method to assess discriminant validity is to compare the square root of average variance extracted (AVE) value of each construct with the correlation between the construct and other constructs in the model (Ghozali, 2014). If the square root value of AVE of each construct is greater than the correlation value between the construct and other constructs in the model, then it is said to have a good discriminant validity value. It is recommended that the AVE value should be greater than 0.5 (Ghozali, 2014).

Assessing the Inner Model or Structural Model

After the validity and reliability tests then form a measurement model, then the next step is to analyze the influence between latent variables called the structural model (inner model). Evaluation of the inner model can be done by looking at the size of R² (Rsquare). The greater the R² value, the greater the influence of certain exogenous latent variables on endogenous variables. With the help of the R program, the direct effect of certain exogenous variables on endogenous variables is obtained. In assessing the model with PLS, it begins by looking at the R-square for each dependent latent variable. Changes in the R-square value can be used to assess the influence of certain independent latent variables on dependent latent variables whether they have a substantive influence (Ghozali, 2014).

Outer model

According to Wiyono (2014), the assessment criteria used in assessing indicators are:

- a. Convergent validity loading factor value 0.5 to 0.6;

- b. Discriminant validity: the correlation value of cross loading with its latent variable must be greater than the correlation with other latent variables.
- c. AVE value must be above 0.5
- d. A good composite reliability value is if it has a value ≥ 0.7 .

Inner Model Goodness of fit in the inner model is measured using the R square of the dependent latent variable. Changes in the R-square value can be used to assess the influence of certain independent latent variables on the dependent latent variable whether it has a substantive influence. While the hypothesis test in this study uses the path analysis method. Path analysis is an extension of multiple regression analysis.

t statistics

If the t statistic coefficient shows a coefficient that is greater than the t table, this result illustrates that the variable is significant, then it can be interpreted that there is a significant influence of the latent variable on other latent variables. Exogenous variables are stated to be significant on endogenous variables if the t statistic result is greater than the t table.

Intervening variable testing

The testing of this intervening variable can be seen from the comparison of direct influence with bootstrap calculations. and looking at the calculation of the total indirect effect, if the direct influence is smaller than the total effect, then it is proven that the organizational culture variable is an intervening variable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

External model testing attempts to find the value of each variable that has a significant relationship to the manifest variable. This research model includes convergent validity, discriminant validity, and reliability testing as follows:

Convergent Validity

This test is seen from the loading factor, the value limit is 0.7, and the value limit Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is 0.5, if it is above that value it is said to be valid. This means that the value for the indicator is said to be valid, if the indicator explains the construct variable with a value > 0.7 . The structural model in this study is shown in the following figure:

Figure 2. Outer Model
Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Smart PLS output for loading factor gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Z = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + e_1$$

$$Z = 0.424X_1 + 0.325X_2 + 0.236X_3 + e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_3X_1 + b_4X_2 + b_5X_3 + b_6Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.188X_1 + 0.123X_2 + 0.136X_3 + 0.531Z + e_2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Teamwork (Z)	Employee Performance (Y)	Quality of Work (X2)	Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X1)	Training (X3)
X1.1				0.898	
X1.2				0.865	
X1.3				0.724	
X1.4				0.861	
X1.5				0.827	
X2.1			0.896		
X2.2			0.907		
X2.3			0.898		
X3.1					0.854
X3.2					0.840
X3.3					0.881
X3.4					0.795
X3.5					0.817
Y.1		0.905			
Y.2		0.876			
Y.3		0.909			
Y.4		0.834			
Y.5		0.849			
Z.1	0.907				
Z.2	0.908				
Z.3	0.824				
Z.4	0.869				
Z.5	0.871				
Z.6	0.815				
Z.7	0.775				
Z.8	0.848				
Z.9	0.851				

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 1 above, it can be seen that the value of each indicator has a higher value, each indicator is greater than 0.7, which means that each indicator item has a value greater than 0.7, which means that the data is validly distributed and can continue further research.

Discriminant Validity

The next research is to find out the valid data in discriminate validity, which aims to find out the cross loading between variables whose values are greater than the cross loading values of other latent variables, so as to determine the results of indicators that are highly correlated with their constructs. The following table shows the cross loading results from the validity test as follows:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Teamwork (Z)	Employee Performance (Y)	Quality of Work(X2)	Organizational Citizenship Behavior(X1)	Training (X3)
X1.1	0.852	0.874	0.802	0.898	0.809
X1.2	0.831	0.782	0.765	0.865	0.738
X1.3	0.665	0.666	0.602	0.724	0.628
X1.4	0.786	0.778	0.777	0.861	0.788
X1.5	0.725	0.696	0.756	0.827	0.802
X2.1	0.787	0.773	0.896	0.745	0.780
X2.2	0.821	0.790	0.907	0.765	0.762
X2.3	0.846	0.844	0.898	0.883	0.827
X3.1	0.735	0.725	0.770	0.785	0.854
X3.2	0.756	0.752	0.725	0.762	0.840
X3.3	0.800	0.784	0.789	0.788	0.881
X3.4	0.692	0.722	0.671	0.677	0.795
X3.5	0.798	0.757	0.720	0.759	0.817
Y.1	0.855	0.905	0.825	0.797	0.816
Y.2	0.861	0.876	0.818	0.774	0.815
Y.3	0.850	0.909	0.776	0.816	0.815
Y.4	0.793	0.834	0.748	0.853	0.726
Y.5	0.746	0.849	0.732	0.748	0.732
Z.1	0.907	0.881	0.780	0.853	0.820
Z.2	0.908	0.904	0.867	0.875	0.888
Z.3	0.824	0.671	0.709	0.708	0.669
Z.4	0.869	0.773	0.775	0.760	0.720
Z.5	0.871	0.778	0.758	0.820	0.758
Z.6	0.815	0.732	0.737	0.761	0.684
Z.7	0.775	0.812	0.765	0.700	0.692
Z.8	0.848	0.827	0.777	0.789	0.861
Z.9	0.851	0.805	0.799	0.821	0.812

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

It can be seen in table 2 above that there are cross loading factor results for each variable. In each cross loading factor, there is a value that is greater than the cross loading factor of other variables, so this study is considered discriminantly valid because each variable has a cross loading factor value that is greater than the other latent variables.

Composite reliability

In composite reliability research to see each variable with its reliability value and if the variable value is greater than 0.60 then the research is considered reliable and if below 0.60 and 0.7 then it is not reliable there are several blocks to determine whether the research is reliable or not and valid or not including the Coranbach alpha value, composite reliability and AVE value can be seen in the table below:

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Teamwork (Z)	0.953	0.960	0.728
Employee Performance (Y)	0.923	0.942	0.766
Quality of Work (X2)	0.883	0.928	0.810
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X1)	0.892	0.921	0.701
Training (X3)	0.894	0.922	0.702

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 3 above, the Cronbach alpha column shows the value of each variable is greater than 0.7, indicating that the reliability data can be relied on for that variable. The composite reliability column has a value greater than 0.6, indicating that each variable is considered reliable because the data exceeds 0.6. The AVE column shows that each variable has a value greater than 0.7, indicating that the data is original in terms of AVE. All variables in the Cronbach alpha, reliability, and AVE columns have values above 0.7 and 0.6, indicating reliability and validity.

Inner Model Analysis

Structural model evaluation (inner model) is conducted to ensure that the basic model created is strong and accurate. The stages of examination conducted in the primary model assessment are seen from several markers, namely:

1. Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Teamwork (Z)	0.902	0.898
Employee Performance (Y)	0.902	0.896

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 4, the R square value of the teamwork variable is 0.902 with a percentage of 90.2%, meaning that the influence of organizational citizenship behavior, work quality, training on teamwork is 0.902 or 90.2%, the R square value of the employee performance variable is 0.902 or 90.2%, meaning that the influence of the organizational citizenship behavior variable, work quality, training, teamwork on employee performance is 0.902 or 90.2%, and the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After assessing the inner model, the next thing is to assess the connection between idle builds as suspected in this review. Speculation testing in this review is done by looking at T-Statistics and P-Values. Speculation is announced to acknowledge whether the T-Insights value is > 1.96 and P-Values < 0.05 . The following are the consequences of the direct impact Path Coefficient:

Table 5. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Teamwork (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.531	5,032	0,000	Accepted
Work Quality (X2) -> Teamwork (Z)	0.325	3,331	0,000	Accepted
Work Quality (X2) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.123	1,143	0.127	Rejected
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X1) -> Teamwork (Z)	0.424	3,861	0,000	Accepted
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X1) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.188	1,951	0.026	Accepted
Training (X3) -> Teamwork (Z)	0.236	2,048	0.021	Accepted
Training (X3) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.136	1,426	0.077	Rejected

Source : Smart PLS 3.3.3

After getting the hypothesis results in table 5, it will be explained as follows:

1. Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.531 and p values of 0.000. If teamwork increases, employee performance increases, conversely, if it decreases, employee performance decreases.
2. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Teamwork with an original sample value of 0.325 and p values of 0.000. If work quality increases, teamwork increases, if it decreases, teamwork also decreases.
3. Work quality has a positive but insignificant effect with an original sample value of 0.123 and p values of 0.127, meaning that the work quality in the organization is not good enough so that many employee performance is still not good, therefore the quality provided has not been able to improve employee performance.
4. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Teamwork with an original sample value of 0.424 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if Organizational Citizenship Behavior increases, teamwork increases, if it decreases, teamwork decreases.

5. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.188 and p values of 0.026. If Organizational Citizenship Behavior increases, employee performance increases, conversely if it decreases, employee performance decreases.
6. Training has a positive and significant effect on Teamwork with an original sample value of 0.236 and p values of 0.021. If training increases, teamwork increases, conversely, if it decreases, teamwork decreases.
7. Training has a positive but insignificant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.136 and p values of 0.077, meaning that the training carried out has little effect on performance, most employees are also lazy to do training so that employee performance decreases or runs in place and does not develop.

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Work Quality (X2) -> Teamwork (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.173	2,757	0.003	Accepted
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X1) -> Teamwork (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.225	2,913	0.002	Accepted
Training (X3) -> Teamwork (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.125	1,822	0.035	Accepted

Source : Smart PLS 3.3.3

The results of the indirect hypothesis in table 6 will be explained as follows:

8. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Teamwork with an original sample value of 0.173 and p values of 0.003, meaning that teamwork is an intervening variable because it is able to have a significant effect. With teamwork, it will improve the quality of work and employee performance indirectly.
9. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Teamwork with an original sample value of 0.225 and p values of 0.002, meaning that teamwork is an intervening variable because it can have a significant effect. With teamwork, OCB and employee performance can be increased indirectly.
10. Training has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Teamwork with an original sample value of 0.125 and p values of 0.035, meaning that teamwork is an intervening variable because it is able to have a significant effect, so teamwork makes training and employee performance increase indirectly.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.531 and p values of 0.000.
2. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Teamwork with an original sample value of 0.325 and p values of 0.000.
3. Work quality has a positive but insignificant effect with an original sample value of 0.123 and p values of 0.127.
4. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Teamwork with an original sample value of 0.424 and p values of 0.000.

5. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.188 and p values of 0.026.
6. Training has a positive and significant effect on Teamwork with an original sample value of 0.236 and p values of 0.021.
7. Training has a positive but insignificant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.136 and p values of 0.077.
8. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Teamwork with an original sample value of 0.173 and p values of 0.003.
9. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Teamwork with an original sample value of 0.225 and p values of 0.002.
10. Training has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Teamwork with an original sample value of 0.125 and p values of 0.035.

Suggestion

1. It is hoped that this research will be used as input for the organization and for organizational development.
2. Organizations should cultivate OCB in every employee to build good cooperation.
3. create good cooperation within the organization for the progress of the organization.
4. Improve the quality of employee work or find qualified employees.
5. Conduct training for employees to improve employee skills.
6. When working, employees are expected to commit to their performance as employees.
7. It is hoped that this research will be used as reference material for new research with new models and new techniques.

REFERENCES

- Andriani, C. (2020). Pengaruh Kompensasi, Pelatihan Kerja dan Kepuasan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. Universitas Muhammadiyah Bengkulu, Hal 1–82.
- Dessler, G. (2015). Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- Gultom, WF dan Widyawati. (2019). Pengaruh Kompetensi dan Pelatihan terhadap Kinerja Karyawan pada PT. Perkebunan II (Tanjung Morawa Medan) Produksi Kelapa Sawit. *Jurnal Manajemen*, Vol. 5 (1).
- Ghozali, Imam. (2014). Structural Equation Modelling, Edisi II, Universitas Diponegoro, Semarang.
- Hasibuan, H. M. (2019). Manajemen Sumberdaya Manusia. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- Jaya, Ichal Kusuma et.al. (2020). Analisis Pengembangan Karyawan Dalam Meningkatkan Kualitas Kerja Karyawan Pada Perseroan Terbatas Sultra Prima Lestari (PT. SPL) Kantor Utama Kabupaten Konawe Utara. *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis*. 5(1), 237-246
- Lawasi, E. S. & Triatmanto, B., (2017). Pengaruh Komunikasi, Motivasi Dan Kerjasama Tim Terhadap Peningkatan Kinerja Karyawan. *JMDK*, Vol 5(No 1), Pp. 47-57.
- Putri, Y., & Utami, H. (2017). Pengaruh Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) terhadap kinerja Studi Pada Tenaga Perawat Ruang Rawat Inap Rumah 121 Sakit Baptis Batu. *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis S1 Universitas Brawijaya*, 46(1), 27–34.

- Rompas, dkk. (2018). Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan, Pengawasan, Dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Pada Dinas Perhubungan Kabupaten Minahasa Tenggara. *Jurnal EMBA: Jurnal Riset Ekonomi, Manajemen, Bisnis Dan Akuntansi*, 6(4).
- Sibarani, E., M. (2018). Pengaruh Kerjasama Tim, Kreativitas dan Budaya Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan PT. Telekomunikasi Indonesia (TELKOM) Tbk, Kantor Regional I Medan. *Analisi Kesadahan Total Dan Alkalinitas Pada Air Bersih Sumur Bor Dengan Metode Titrimetri Di PT Sucofindo Daerah Provinsi Sumatera Utara*, 44-48
- Sukanto, R, N, A & Gilang, A. (2018). Pengaruh Kepuasan Kerja terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior Karyawan (Studi Kasus di PT. PLN (PERSERO) APJ Bandung). *Jurnal Manajemen dan Bisnis (ALMANA)*, 2 (2). 64-73.
- Sugiyono. (2019). *Statistika untuk Penelitian*. Bandung : CV Alfabeta.
- Wibowo. (2019). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta : Bumi Aksara.

Job Satisfaction Effectiveness

Khairuddin¹, Kiki Farida Ferine²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: kikifarida@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

In any organization, human resources are very important in carrying out the activities carried out by the organization, because human resources function as a stepping stone for the organization to achieve its business success goals. This research aims to determine the influence of the work environment, integrity and work flexibility on job satisfaction with competency as an intervening variable at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province. The results of this research are as follows: Job Flexibility has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.095 and a p value of 0.316. Work Flexibility has a positive and significant effect on Competency with an original sample value of 0.427 and a p value of 0.000. Integrity has a positive and insignificant effect on job satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.085 and a p value of 0.365. Integrity has a positive and significant effect on competence with an original sample value of 0.347 and a p value of 0.002. Competency has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.520 and a p value of 0.026. Work Environment has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction with a value of 0.108 p value 0.272. Work Environment has a positive and significant effect on Competency with an original sample value of 0.191 and a p value of 0.032. Job Flexibility has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction through Competency with an original sample value of 0.222 and a p value of 0.052. Integrity has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction through Competency with an original sample value of 0.181 and a p value of 0.058. Work Environment has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction through Competency with an original sample value of 0.100 and a p value of 0.106.

Keywords: Work Environment, Integrity, Flexibility, Competence, Job Satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

In this era of globalization, human resources are considered as a necessary resource for businesses to achieve success. Human resources are the most important asset in any business. The function of human resources (HR) is to set goals and provide support, protection, and service to various aspects related to employees in the organization (Mukminin, et al., 2019). In any organization, human resources are very important in carrying out activities carried out by the organization, because human resources function as a stepping stone for the organization to achieve its business success goals. According to Kasmir (2016), human resource management is the process of helping the community through recruitment, selection, training, development, remuneration, compensation, health, and safety, and industrial relations negotiations to severing ties with the company. co-workers to achieve business goals and increase stakeholder satisfaction. Everyone will work longer than doing anything else. A person will work side by side with several other people. Another element that affects the level of success of an organization is its work environment. Therefore, to create a comfortable work environment for workers, it must also be fostered and managed as well as possible. An unhealthy work environment can cause people to get sick more often, get stressed more quickly, have difficulty focusing, and reduce productivity. Everyone needs integrity because we are social creatures and humans first. The secret of a person's success in anything is integrity. Integrity is useful not only in a particular field of

work but also in interpersonal and family relationships. Integrity is more than just having sincere intentions; it is a positive quality. Organizations must be increasingly flexible to adapt to a competitive environment. Organizational flexibility is determined by resources that have high abilities and skills, this makes the organization have a competitive advantage so that it can win the competition. Employee job satisfaction is the sense of satisfaction they get from their work. Many groups focus on job satisfaction because it is associated with organizational and personnel conditions. Happiness shows the impact of work experiences, and high levels of dissatisfaction are useful in indicating organizational problems that need to be addressed. An employee's attitude toward their job and everything else is a good indicator of how they feel about their job.

Competency Assessment can be applied to improve or match the quality of human resources (HR). A competent professional has the qualities needed to complete the work according to the required standards. A person's competency value can be discovered and developed through competency-based evaluation, which helps make human resources competitive.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does the Work Environment have a positive and significant influence on Competence at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province?
2. Does Integrity have a positive and significant influence on Competence at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province?
3. Does Work Flexibility Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
4. Does the Work Environment have a positive and significant influence on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
5. Does Integrity have a positive and significant influence on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
6. Does Work Flexibility Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
7. Does Competence have a positive and significant influence on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
8. Does the Work Environment have a positive and significant influence on Job Satisfaction through Competence at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
9. Does Integrity have a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
10. Does Work Flexibility Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Job Satisfaction through Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of the Work Environment on Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
2. To determine and analyze the influence of Integrity on Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
3. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Flexibility on Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

4. To determine and analyze the influence of the Work Environment on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
5. To determine and analyze the influence of Integrity on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
6. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Flexibility on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
7. To determine and analyze the influence of Competence on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
8. To determine and analyze the influence of the Work Environment on Job Satisfaction through Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
9. To determine and analyze the influence of Integrity on Job Satisfaction through Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
10. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Flexibility on Job Satisfaction through Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Job satisfaction

Understanding Job Satisfaction

According to Latief et al., (2019) Job satisfaction is an emotional attitude to love and enjoy one's work. This attitude is reflected in productivity, discipline and morale.

Job satisfaction is an individual's attitude towards work as a disparity between the amount of reward that workers receive and the amount they believe they should receive (Indra Yudha, 2018).

Job Satisfaction Indicators

According to Latief et al., (2019) job satisfaction indicators are:

1. Although wages and salaries are very important, they are cognitively complex and known as multidimensional factors of job satisfaction.
2. Promotions come in various forms and rewards, they have the ability to influence job satisfaction in different ways.
3. Collaborative coworkers transform job satisfaction into the simplest employee satisfaction.
4. Working conditions for job satisfaction are no different from the effects if the work group is well managed and there are no problems related to job satisfaction.

Work environment

Understanding the Work Environment

According to Latief et al., (2019) Job satisfaction is an emotional attitude to love and enjoy one's work. This attitude is reflected in productivity, discipline and morale.

According to Mulyadi (2015), the work environment is all the work facilities and infrastructure around employees who are doing work that can influence the implementation of the work.

Work Environment Indicators

Work environment indicators according to Mulyadi (2015) are as follows:

- 1) Facilities
- 2) Cleanliness

- 3) Lighting
- 4) Relationship with coworkers
- 5) Security

Integrity

Understanding Integrity

Integrity is a person's mindset, attitude, and movement of conscience that is manifested in speech, actions, and behavior: honest, consistent, committed, objective, brave and ready to accept risks, as well as disciplined and responsible (Abdullah, 2019).

Integrity Indicators

Integrity indicators (Abdullah, 2019), namely:

1. Honest behavior;
2. Consistent Attitude;
3. Commitment to the Organization's Vision and Mission;
4. Objective Towards Problems;
5. Dare to make decisions and be ready to accept risks;
6. Discipline and responsibility;
7. Track record;
8. Performance.

Flexibility

Understanding Work Flexibility

According to Hill et al. (in Maria Byden, 2016) flexibility can be described as "the ability of workers to make choices that affect when (timing flexibility), where (place flexibility), and how long (time flexibility) they engage in work-related tasks". Work flexibility according to Wicaksono (2019), is a company policy given by a formal or informal human resource manager related to the flexibility that occurs in the company.

Work Flexibility Indicators

According to Wicaksono (2019) the indicators of work flexibility are as follows:

- a. Time flexibility: Worker flexibility to change work periods.
- b. Timing flexibility: Workers' flexibility to choose their work schedule.
- c. Place flexibility: Worker flexibility in selecting work locations.

Competence

Understanding Competence

According to Rahmat (2019) competence is a person's characteristic related to effective and/or superior performance in a particular work situation. Competence is said to be a basic characteristic because individual characteristics are a deep and inherent part of a person's personality that can be used to predict various specific work situations. Fauzi (2019) states that competence is a performance that leads to achieving goals completely towards the desired condition.

Competency Indicators

According to Rahmat (2019), competency indicators are:

1. Motive is something that a person consistently thinks about or wants that causes action.
2. Traits are physical characteristics and consistent responses to situations or information.

3. Self-concept is a person's attitude, values, or self-image.
4. Knowledge is information that people have in a specific field.
5. Skills are the ability to perform certain physical or mental tasks.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

- H1 The work environment has a positive and significant influence on competence at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H2 Integrity has a positive and significant influence on Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H3 Work Flexibility has a positive and significant effect on Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H4 The work environment has a positive and significant influence on job satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H5 Integrity has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H6 Work Flexibility has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H7 Competence has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H8 Work Environment has a positive and significant influence on Job Satisfaction through Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H9 Integrity has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H10 Work Flexibility has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Competence at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province

Types of research

According to Sugiyono (2020), quantitative research methods are research methods based on the philosophy of positivism, used to examine certain populations or samples and

collect data using research tools, analyze quantitative or statistical data with the aim of testing predetermined hypotheses.

Population and Sample

Population

The population of this study was 70 employees of the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province and will be used by all researchers. Population is a general area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain quantities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions made (Sugiyono, 2020).

Sample

The sample in this study was all the population at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province, as many as 70 employees and the research technique used was the saturated sample technique. According to Sugiyono (2020), a sample is part of the number and characteristics of a population.

Time and Location of Research

The time of this research was conducted from September to October 2024. This research was conducted at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province and this research was on Jalan Balai Kota No. 4.

Data source

The data source for this study uses primary data sources at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province. According to Sugiyono (2020), primary data is data obtained from the first source or object location which is carried out directly by researchers without going through intermediaries.

Data collection technique

The data collection technique used is a questionnaire, this questionnaire is distributed to the sample for respondents to fill in. A questionnaire is a data collection technique carried out by providing written questions or statements submitted to respondents (Sugiyono, 2020).

Structural equation modeling analysis - partial least squares

Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS) is one of the classifications of the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method. According to Abdillah and Hartono (2015), Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis is a multivariate statistical approach that can analyze many dependent variables and several independent variables from a small sample.

The following are the steps for using PLS for data processing in this study:

Evaluation of measurement model (outer model)

Evaluation of measurement model or outer model is an evaluation of the relationship test between construct variables (indicators) and their latent variables. Evaluation of measurement model is done with validity and reliability test approach.

a. Validity test

- 1) Convergent validity
- 2) Discriminant validity
- 3) Reliability test

In PLS-SEM, in addition to validity testing, reliability testing is also carried out. Reliability testing is used to prove the accuracy, consistency, and precision of the instrument in measuring the construct (Hamid & Anwar, 2019). Measuring the reliability of a construct with reflective indicators can be done in three ways, namely Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability and average variance extracted. The Rule of Thumb for assessing construct reliability is that the Composite Reliability value must be greater than 0.70. According to Ghozali & Latan, (2015) the composite reliability value is said to be reliable if it has a value above > 0.7, for Cronbach's alpha it is said to be good if it has a value above > 0.7, and for the average variance extracted value it is said to be good if it has a value > 0.5.

Structural model evaluation (inner model)

The inner model is a structural model, based on the path coefficient value, seeing how much influence there is between latent variables with bootstrapping calculations. The evaluation is carried out by looking at the R-Square value criteria and significance values (Hamid & Anwar, 2019). There are several item components that are the criteria in assessing the structural model (inner model), namely:

- a. R-Square
- b. F-Square
- c. Collinearity
- d. Direct effect

According to Juliandi (2018), there are criteria in Direct Effect analysis, namely:

1) Path Coefficient:

- If the path coefficient value is positive, then the influence of a variable on is in the same direction, if the value of an exogenous variable increases/rises, then the value of the endogenous variable also increases/rises;
- If the path coefficient value is negative, then the influence of a variable on the other is in the opposite direction, if the value of an exogenous variable increases/rises, then the value of the endogenous variable decreases.

2) Probability/Significance Value (P-Value):

- If the P-Value < 0.05, it means it is significant;
- If the P-Value > 0.05, it means it is not significant.

e. Indirect Effect

Indirect effect analysis is useful for testing the hypothesis of the indirect influence of an influencing variable (exogenous) on the influenced variable (endogenous) which is mediated by an intervening variable (mediator variable). According to (Juliandi, 2018) there are criteria in the Indirect Effect analysis, namely:

- If the P-Value < 0.05, then it is significant (the effect is indirect), meaning that the intervening variable "plays a role" in mediating the relationship between an exogenous variable and an endogenous variable;
- If the P-Value > 0.05, then it is not significant (the effect is direct), meaning that the intervening variable "does not play a role" in mediating the relationship between an exogenous variable and an endogenous variable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Measurement model testing (outer model) is used to determine the specifications of the relationship between latent variables and their manifest variables, this testing includes convergent validity, discriminant validity and reliability.

Convergent Validity

This test is seen from the loading factor, the value limit is 0.7, and the value limit Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is 0.5, if it is above that value it is said to be valid. This means that the value for the indicator is said to be valid, if the indicator explains the construct variable with a value > 0.7. The structural model in this study is shown in the following figure:

Figure 2. Outer Model
 Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

Smart PLS output for loading factor gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Z = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + e_1$$

$$Z = 0.191X_1 + 0.347X_2 + 0.427X_3 + e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_2X_1 + b_3X_2 + b_4X_3 + b_5Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.108 X_1 + 0.085 X_2 + 0.095X_3 + 0.520 Z + e_2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Work Flexibility (X3)	Integrity (X2)	Job Satisfaction (Y)	Competence (Z)	Work Environment (X1)
X1.1					0.899

X1.2					0.735
X1.3					0.874
X1.4					0.862
X1.5					0.817
X2.1		0.734			
X2.2		0.755			
X2.3		0.890			
X2.4		0.858			
X2.5		0.849			
X2.6		0.882			
X2.7		0.877			
X2.8		0.827			
X3.1	0.802				
X3.2	0.850				
X3.3	0.841				
Y.1			0.875		
Y.2			0.824		
Y.3			0.757		
Y.4			0.819		
Z.1				0.855	
Z.2				0.830	
Z.3				0.877	
Z.4				0.802	
Z.5				0.754	

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 1 above, the value of each variable is stated that the indicator in each variable is higher than 0.7, which means that each indicator item has a value higher than 0.7 so that the data is declared valid and can continue to further research.

Discriminant Validity

Further research to find out valid data in terms of Discriminate Validity, aims to find out whether the cross loading value is greater than other latent variables so as to determine the results of indicators that are highly correlated with their constructs. The following table shows the cross loading results from the validity test as follows:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Work Flexibility (X3)	Integrity (X2)	Job Satisfaction (Y)	Competence (Z)	Work Environment (X1)
X1.1	0.745	0.857	0.602	0.751	0.899
X1.2	0.722	0.695	0.535	0.794	0.735
X1.3	0.663	0.739	0.615	0.701	0.874
X1.4	0.609	0.676	0.589	0.639	0.862

X1.5	0.750	0.771	0.633	0.700	0.817
X2.1	0.622	0.734	0.525	0.676	0.675
X2.2	0.618	0.755	0.552	0.700	0.586
X2.3	0.752	0.890	0.562	0.698	0.794
X2.4	0.723	0.858	0.602	0.698	0.762
X2.5	0.722	0.849	0.687	0.773	0.845
X2.6	0.761	0.882	0.605	0.777	0.772
X2.7	0.784	0.877	0.633	0.801	0.778
X2.8	0.821	0.827	0.674	0.805	0.747
X3.1	0.802	0.703	0.552	0.691	0.672
X3.2	0.850	0.758	0.548	0.739	0.705
X3.3	0.841	0.716	0.689	0.782	0.707
Y.1	0.705	0.734	0.875	0.792	0.712
Y.2	0.698	0.686	0.824	0.709	0.686
Y.3	0.398	0.390	0.757	0.424	0.371
Y.4	0.451	0.451	0.819	0.479	0.429
Z.1	0.749	0.716	0.581	0.855	0.658
Z.2	0.688	0.735	0.690	0.830	0.646
Z.3	0.751	0.795	0.663	0.877	0.736
Z.4	0.759	0.719	0.578	0.802	0.752
Z.5	0.717	0.701	0.669	0.754	0.743

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

There are cross loading factor results in table 2 and will be explained as follows: the cross loading factor of the work flexibility variable has a value that is greater than the cross loading of other latent variables, the cross loading of the integrity variable has a cross loading value that is greater than the cross loading value of other latent variables, the cross loading of the job satisfaction variable has a value greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, the cross loading of the competency variable has a value greater than the cross loading of other latent variables, the cross loading of the work environment variable has a value greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, so it can be concluded that the data is discriminantly valid.

Composite reliability

In composite reliability research to see each variable with its reliability value and if the variable value is greater than 0.60 then the research is considered reliable and if below 0.60 and 0.7 then it is not reliable there are several blocks to determine whether the research is reliable or not and valid or not including the Coranbach alpha value, composite reliability and AVE value can be seen in the table below:

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Work Flexibility (X3)	0.777	0.870	0.691

Integrity (X2)	0.937	0.949	0.698
Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.844	0.891	0.672
Competence (Z)	0.881	0.914	0.680
Work Environment (X1)	0.893	0.922	0.704

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 3 above, it can be seen in the cronbach alpha column that each variable has a value greater than 0.7, which means that the reliability data for each variable. The composite reliability column has a value greater than 0.6, so it can be explained that each variable is considered reliable because the data is greater than 0.6. It can be seen from the AVE column that each variable gets a value greater than 0.7, which means that the data is valid according to AVE. All variables from the cronbach alpha column, reliability column and AVE column have values greater than 0.7 and 0.6, so they are considered reliable and valid.

Inner Model Analysis

Structural model evaluation (inner model) is conducted to ensure that the basic model created is strong and accurate. The stages of examination conducted in the primary model assessment are seen from several markers, namely:

1. Coefficient of Determination (R2)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.610	0.586
Competence (Z)	0.853	0.847

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 4 there is an R square value on 2 dependent variables, it will be explained, the R square of the job satisfaction variable has a value of 0.610 if it is converted into a percentage, the result is 61.0%, so it can be concluded that the influence of work flexibility, integrity, job satisfaction and competence is 0.610 or 61.0% and the rest is on other variables, there is an R square value of the competency variable of 0.853 if converted into a percentage of 85.3%, meaning the influence of work flexibility, integrity, job satisfaction on competence is 0.853 or 85.3% the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After assessing the inner model, the next thing is to assess the connection between idle builds as suspected in this review. Speculation testing in this review is done by looking at T-Statistics and P-Values. Speculation is announced to acknowledge whether the T-Insights value is > 1.96 and P-Values <0.05. The following are the consequences of the direct impact Path Coefficient:

Table 5. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Work Flexibility (X3) -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.095	0.479	0.316
Work Flexibility (X3) -> Competence (Z)	0.427	3,980	0,000
Integrity (X2) -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.085	0.346	0.365
Integrity (X2) -> Competence (Z)	0.347	2,885	0.002
Competence (Z) -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.520	1,952	0.026
Work Environment (X1) -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.108	0.607	0.272
Work Environment (X1) -> Competence (Z)	0.191	1,858	0.032

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In the direct results in table 5, the results will be explained as follows:

1. Work Flexibility has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.095 and p values of 0.316. This means that the effect of work flexibility does not have much effect on job satisfaction so it is often ignored.
2. Work Flexibility has a positive and significant effect on Competence with an original sample value of 0.427 and p values of 0.000. If work flexibility increases, competence will increase, if it decreases, competence will also decrease.
3. Integrity has a positive and insignificant effect on job satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.085 and p values of 0.365. This means that integrity does not have much effect on job satisfaction, and sometimes does not have any effect.
4. Integrity has a positive and significant effect on competence with an original sample value of 0.347 and p values of 0.002. If integrity increases, competence will increase and vice versa if integrity decreases, competence decreases.
5. Competence has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.520 and p values of 0.026. If competence increases well, job satisfaction will increase, conversely if it decreases, job satisfaction will decrease.
6. Work Environment has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction with a value of 0.108 p value 0.272. The work environment has little influence on job satisfaction, employees will adjust to workplace conditions even if they feel uncomfortable.
7. Work Environment has a positive and significant effect on Competence with an original sample value of 0.191 and p values of 0.032. If the work environment improves well, then competence will improve well, conversely if it decreases, then competence decreases.

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Work Flexibility (X3) -> Competence (Z) -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.222	1,631	0.052
Integrity (X2) -> Competence (Z) -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.181	1,575	0.058
Work Environment (X1) -> Competence (Z) -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.100	1,252	0.106

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 6 there are indirect influences which will be explained in the following section:

1. Work Flexibility has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction through Competence with an original sample value of 0.222 and p values of 0.052. This means that competence is not an intervening variable because it is unable to significantly influence work flexibility and job satisfaction.
2. Integrity has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction through Competence with an original sample value of 0.181 and p values of 0.058. This means that competence is not an intervening variable because it is unable to influence integrity and job satisfaction indirectly and significantly.
3. Work Environment has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction through Competence with an original sample value of 0.100 and p values of 0.106. This means that competence is not an intervening variable because it is unable to indirectly influence the work environment and job satisfaction significantly.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Work Flexibility has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.095 and p values of 0.316.
2. Work Flexibility has a positive and significant effect on Competence with an original sample value of 0.427 and p values of 0.000.
3. Integrity has a positive and insignificant effect on job satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.085 and p values of 0.365.
4. Integrity has a positive and significant effect on competence with an original sample value of 0.347 and p values of 0.002.
5. Competence has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.520 and p values of 0.026.
6. Work environment has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction with a value of 0.108 p values 0.272.
7. Work environment has a positive and significant influence on competence with an original sample value of 0.191 and p values of 0.032.
8. Work Flexibility has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction through Competence with an original sample value of 0.222 and p values of 0.052.
9. Integrity has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction through Competence with an original sample value of 0.181 and p values of 0.058.
10. The work environment has a positive and insignificant effect on job satisfaction through competence with an original sample value of 0.100 and p values of 0.106.

Suggestion

1. Organizations must provide a good environment for employees so that employees feel calm and comfortable working.
2. Organizations must build employee integrity through training or seeking employees who have high integrity.
3. Organizations should be able to build employee flexibility in working.
4. Employees who have competence must be given proper attention, for the sake of the organization's progress.
5. It is hoped that this research will be used as input for organizational progress.
6. It is hoped that this research can help other researchers with the same title and can develop it further.

7. This research is expected to be used as reference material for subsequent researchers.

REFERENCES

- Abdillah, W., Hartono. (2015). Partial Least Square (PLS). Andi Publisher. Yogyakarta.
- AK Yohanson, Lukmanul Hakim, and Alimuddin. (2021). The Influence of Leadership Style and Work Motivation on Employee Performance of PT. Japfa Comfeed Indonesia TBK, Tanggamus Branch. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Business*, Vol. 6, No. 2.
- Abdullah, A. Rosid. (2019). *Achieve Your Achievements*. Guepedia Publisher. Bogor.
- Fauzi, Firman and Siregar, H, M. (2019). The Influence of Employee Competence and Performance on Career Development in PTWB Construction Company Sales Region III Jakarta. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Management and Industry*. Vol. 2. No. 1.
- Edy Sutrisno, (2019). *Human Resource Management*. Eleventh printing. Prananda Media Group, Jakarta.
- Ghozali, Imam and Hengky Latan (2015). *Partial Least Squares Engineering Concept and Application with Smart PLS 3.0 Program*. Semarang: Diponegoro University Semarang.
- Hartono, J. (2016). *Partial Least Square (PLS) Alternative Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) in Business Research*. Andi Offset.
- Hamid, RS and Anwar, SM (2019). *Variant-Based Structural Equation Modeling (SEM): Basic Concepts and Applications with SmartPLS3.2.8 Program in Business Research*. Jakarta: PT Inkubator Penulis Indonesia.
- Indra Yudha. (2018). The Influence of Organizational Culture and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance at PT. Jaya Abadi Sumber Pasifik, Jambi City. *Journal of Management and Entrepreneurship*. 9(2): 24-35.
- Juliandi. (2018). *Structural equation model based partial least square (SEM-PLS): Using SmartPLS*. SEM-PLS Training Journal of Postgraduate Program, Batam University. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1243777>
- Kasmir. (2016). *Human Resource Management (Theory and Practice)*. Depok: PT Rajagrafindo Persada.
- Kibtiyah, A., & Mardiah. (2016). Relationship between Employee Integrity and Loyalty with Company Vision and Mission (Case Study at PT. Bank Central Asia, Tbk).
- Latief, Wandil Wilanda. (2019). "Analysis of Factors Affecting Employee Work Productivity at the Procurement Bureau of PT. Semen Padang. *Journal of Science and Technology*. Volume. 19. Number 1. Pages 56-60.
- Maria Byden. 2016. *Flexible Work Arrangements: Stress-Buffering or Stressacerbation?* The International Journal of Human Resource Management: Goteborgs Universitet.
- Mulyadi. (2015). *Human Resource Management (HRM)*. Bogor: IN MEDIA
- Mukminin, Amirul. et al. 2019. *Human Resource Management in Education*. Yogyakarta: UNY Press.

- Rahmat, SN, & Basalamah, J. (2019). The Influence of Competence, Compensation and Work Discipline on the Performance of Employees of the Makassar City Regional Revenue Agency. *PARADOX: Journal of Economics*, 2(1), 121-132.
- Sudaryo, Yoyo, et al. 2018. *Human Resource Management, Indirect Compensation and Physical Work Environment*. Yogyakarta: CV Andi Offset.
- Sugiyono. (2020). *Quantitative, Qualitative and R&D Research Methods*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Wicaksono. (2019). The Effect of Compensation and Work Flexibility of Gojek Drivers on Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable. Islamic University of Indonesia.

The Effect of Supervision and Quality of Work Life on Organizational Commitment in Moderation of Work Discipline in The Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatera Province

M. Agus Hidayat¹, Kiki Farida Ferine²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: kikifarida@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

Human resources are essentially people who work for an organization as planners, thinkers and movers to achieve its goals. Human resources (HR) personnel are often highly skilled individuals who serve as the backbone of an organization. This research aims to examine the influence of supervision and quality of work life on organizational commitment in moderating work discipline at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatera Province. The results of this research are as follows: Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.300 and an ap value of 0.028. Supervision has a negative and insignificant effect on organizational commitment, moderated by Work Discipline with an original sample value of -0.094 and ap value of 0.232. Quality of Work Life has a positive and insignificant effect on organizational commitment, moderated by Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.141 and ap value of 0.148. Quality of Work Life has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.278 and ap value of 0.033. Supervision has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.344 and ap value of 0.018.

Keywords: Supervision, Quality of Work Life, Work Discipline, Organizational Commitment

INTRODUCTION

In general, human resources are divided into two categories: macro human resources, namely the total number of individuals in a country or region who are of working age, and micro human resources, namely certain individuals who work in a company or institution. Supervision is an organic function of management whose role is equal to other management functions, in other words, supervision is a dynamic element in the implementation of management functions such as planning, organizing, motivating and implementing to be able to run well in accordance with the goals and objectives expected to be achieved. Supervision is a process where a leader or agency sees whether what has been done is in accordance with expectations. If not, then improvements or adjustments must be made. Work quality is a characteristic that needs to be considered in a company. The realization of a company's goals can be seen through the products produced and the quality of its employees' work. Improving the quality of employee work is very important because the success of a company does not only depend on machine technology but human factors also play an important role in it. In addition, improving quality can also be achieved through experience, education, training and development of these employees. Efforts to improve employee quality and organizational management arrangements. Improving employee quality is important because the progress of an organization does not only depend on machine technology but the human factor plays an important role in it. Increasing competition and demands for professionalism create many pressures that individuals must face in the work environment. In addition to pressure from the work environment, the family environment and social environment also have the potential to cause anxiety. Discipline is a benchmark for determining whether all the tasks

of a manager or leader can be carried out effectively or not. In addition to functioning as a tool for employee self-control, discipline also functions as a means to show workers how serious a company or organization is in working. In the workplace, a person's dedication to the company is often a crucial factor. Because of its importance, some companies even dare to include commitment as a prerequisite for accepting a position as stated in the employment announcement. Unfortunately, employees and business owners often lack information about what is actually meant by commitment. On the other hand, this knowledge is very important for creating working conditions that support smooth business operations.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Supervision have a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
2. Does Quality of Work Life have a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
3. Does Work Discipline have a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
4. Does Work Discipline Moderate Supervision at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province?
5. Does Work Discipline Moderate the Quality of Work Life at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of Supervision on Organizational Commitment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
2. To determine and analyze the influence of Quality of Work Life on Organizational Commitment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
3. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Discipline on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
4. To determine and analyze the influence of work discipline in moderating supervision of organizational commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
5. To determine and analyze the influence of work discipline in moderating the quality of work life on organizational commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational Commitment

According to Anggriani (2014), organizational commitment is defined as an attitude, namely a strong desire to remain a member of a particular organization, a desire to work hard in accordance with what the organization wants and certain beliefs and a willingness to accept the values and goals that have been set by the organization.

Organizational Commitment is the employee's desire to maintain their membership in an organization or company and is willing to make high efforts to achieve the goals of the organization or company (Darmawan (2014).

Organizational Commitment Indicators

According to Darmawan (2014) Organizational Commitment can be measured using three indicators, namely:

1. Employee Will Employee will is an employee's goodwill effort to take the initiative in pursuing their field of work.
2. Employee Loyalty Employee loyalty is a form of employee loyalty to show their identity in an effort to help develop the organization where the employee works.
3. Employee Pride Employee pride is a form of total work or maximum achievement in an effort to show that the results of their work have achieved good or optimal quality.

Supervision

According to Handoko (2015) supervision is a process to ensure that organizational and management goals are achieved. According to (Kadarisman, 2014) supervision is one of the functions of management, namely to ensure that the implementation of tasks, functions, and authorities do not deviate from the rules that have been set in order to achieve organizational goals.

Monitoring Indicators

According to Handoko (2015), indicators of good supervision are:

1. Accurate.
2. Timely, information must be collected.
3. Focus on strategic monitoring points.
4. Objective and comprehensive.
5. Economically realistic.
6. Organizationally realistic.
7. Coordinated with the organization's work flow.
8. Flexible.
9. Serves as a guide and operational
10. Accepted by members of the organization.

Quality of Employee Work Life

According to Ayal (2019) Quality of Work Life is a process in which organizations respond to employee needs by developing mechanisms to allow employees to provide full input and participate in decision-making and managing their work lives in a company. According to Mawu (2018) Quality of Work Life is a process that responds to employee needs by developing mechanisms that provide employees with full opportunities to make decisions and plan their work lives.

Quality of Work Life Indicators

According to Mawu (2018) the indicators for Quality of Work Life are as follows:

1. Appropriate and fair compensation. Reward for employee energy manifested as production results, or a service that is considered equal to that, in the form of money, with a definite guarantee every week or month.
2. Safe and healthy working environment A safe and healthy working environment also includes a working environment that is free from noise, free from visual disturbances such as good lighting in the working environment, and free from pollution.
3. Opportunities to use and develop employee abilities To what extent does the work undertaken by the employee provide the employee with the opportunity to use and develop all the abilities and skills he or she has and does the work provide challenges for him or her to be fully involved.

4. Social interaction in the workplace The extent to which the work environment and co-workers can accept the presence of the individual and the extent to which the work environment is free from destructive prejudice.
5. Employee rights in the office. To what extent can the organization fulfill the rights that employees should have and to what extent does the organization provide freedom for personal privacy.

Work Discipline

According to Agustini (2019) discipline is the use of several forms of punishment or sanctions if employees deviate. The use of punishment is used when leaders are faced with problems with subordinate behavior that is not in accordance with work regulations that are below office standards.

Work Discipline Indicators

Work discipline indicators according to Agustini (2019) are as follows:

- (1) Attendance level Attendance is an indicator of the creation of high work discipline. This is because the higher the level of employee attendance, the higher the employee's discipline.
- (2) Work procedures Each company has its own work standards and regulations. As an employee, you are required to always apply the company's work standards.
- (3) Obedience to superiors Employees who have good work discipline will obey and follow the directions given by their superiors.
- (4) Work awareness Work awareness is an attitude that employees have to work voluntarily.
- (5) Responsibility As an employee, responsibility is required in working. Responsibility is the employee's willingness to be responsible for work results so that they are in accordance with company regulations.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

- H1 Supervision has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatera Province.

- H2 Quality of Work Life has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatera Province.
- H3 To determine and analyze the influence of Work Discipline on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatera Province.
- H4 Work Discipline can moderate Supervision of Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatera Province.
- H5 Work Discipline can moderate the Quality of Work Life towards Organizational Commitment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatera Province.

METHOD

Types of research

According to Sugiyono (2017), quantitative research methods can be interpreted as research methods based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations or samples, sampling techniques are generally carried out randomly, data collection uses research instruments, analysis and is quantitative in nature with the aim of testing the established hypothesis.

Population

The population of this study was taken at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatera Province, the number of populations used was 70 employees. According to Sugiyono (2017), population is defined as a generalization area consisting of: objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn.

Sample

The sample in this study is all the population at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatera Province, totaling 70 employees and will use the saturated sample technique as the sample technique. According to Sugiyono (2017), a sample is part of the number and characteristics of the population.

Time and Location of Research

This research was conducted from September to October 2024 at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatera Province on Jalan Balai Kota No. 4, Medan City.

Research Data Sources

The research data sources used are primary data sources. According to Sugiyono (2017) primary data is data that directly provides data to data collectors.

Data collection technique

The data collection that is done and used is a questionnaire and will be distributed to the sample that is the respondent. According to Sugiyono (2017) a questionnaire is a data collection technique that is done by giving a set of questions or written statements that are done by giving a set of questions on written statements to respondents to be answered.

Data Analysis Methods

Partial Least Square - Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM)

Partial Least Square – Structural Equation Model (PLS – SEM) or often called Partial Least Square Path Modeling (PLS – PM) is an alternative method for structural equation

models (Structural Equation Model) to simultaneously test the relationship between latent constructs in linear and non-linear relationships with many indicators, either in the form of reflective, formative, or MIMIC. PLS – SEM is also able to test complex relationships with many constructs and indicators (Ghozali & Latan, 2015). In this study, researchers used PLS - SEM as a data analysis method with the help of Smart PLS 3.0 software.

Evaluation of PLS – SEM (Outer Model) Measurement Model

The convergent validity of the regression indicator model is determined by comparing the item/component scores with the construct scores obtained using PLS. The reflection size is declared high if it is more than 0.70 against the desired construct. Conversely, for the first stage study, the loading range of 0.5 to 0.60 decreased significantly (Ghozali, 2016). The discriminant validity of the measurement model with reflective indicators is based on the cross loading of the measurement measurements with the construct. If the correlation coefficient indicates the lower limit of the area of a block compared to the area of other blocks.

Therefore, it is said to have good discriminant validity. This adjustment is used to reduce the rearrangement of the final component score variables, and the results are more conservative when compared to composite reliability. Two measures that can be used to evaluate composite reliability that worsens a particular construct are Cronbach's Alpha and internal consistency (Ghozali, 2016).

Evaluation of Model Structure (Inner Model)

The inner model describes the relationship between latent variables based on substantive theory. The structural model is evaluated using R-square for the dependent variable, Cross-validated redundancy (Q) or Q square, and the significance of the path coefficient or path coefficient. To determine the model using PLS, first look at the R-square of each dependent variable. The R-squared value can be used to determine the influence of the current independent variables on the dependent variable, namely whether they have a significant influence (Ghozali, 2006). In addition to looking at the R-square value, the PLS model is also evaluated by looking at the predictive relevance of the Q-square. The Q-square test improves some model observation outputs as well as parameter estimates.

Hypothesis Testing

The measure of the significance of the hypothesis support can be used by comparing the T-table and T-statistic values. If the T-statistic is higher than the T-table value, it means that the hypothesis is supported or accepted (Suharyadi and Purwanto, 2015). In this study for a 95% confidence level (alpha 95 percent), the T-table value for the one-tailed hypothesis with a table value of 1.660 for two tails with a T-table value of 1.984.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Measurement model testing (outer model) is used to determine the relationship between latent and manifest variables. This test includes convergent validity, discriminant validity, and reliability.

Convergent Validity

Convergent validity is used to assess the validity of each indicator against its latent variable. In the SmartPLS program, the validity results can be seen in the external loading

table. The external loading table contains numbers or values that indicate the similarity of the indicator to the construct variable. The indicator value is considered valid if it describes the construct variable with a value greater than 0.7. The structural model used in this study is depicted in the figure below:

Figure 2; Outer Model

The Smart PLS output for loading factors gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings

In this research there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Y = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_1Z + e_1$$

$$Y = 0.344 X_1 + 0.300X_2 - 0.094 Z + e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_3X_1 + b_4X_2 + b_5X_2Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.278X_1 + 0.300X_1 + 0.141Z + e_2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Work Discipline (Z)	Organizational Commitment (Y)	Quality of Work Life_(X2)_	Supervision (X1)
X1.1				0.900
X1.10				0.892
X1.2				0.792
X1.3				0.830
X1.4				0.811
X1.5				0.823
X1.6				0.743
X1.7				0.792

X1.8				0.876
X1.9				0.848
X2.1			0.873	
X2.2			0.894	
X2.3			0.888	
X2.4			0.807	
X2.5			0.822	
Y.1		0.866		
Y.2		0.905		
Y.3		0.835		
Z.1	0.849			
Z.2	0.876			
Z.3	0.845			
Z.4	0.855			
Z.5	0.807			

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

Based on table 1 above, it can be seen that the outer loading of each variable and indicator for each outer loading value is greater than 0.7, so it can be explained that each indicator whose outer loading value is greater than 0.7 is considered valid, and because all outer loadings are greater than 0.7, all variables and indicators are considered valid and can be further researched.

Discriminant Validity

The next test is to determine discriminant validity. This test attempts to assess whether the indicators that reflect are valid measures for the construct, based on the assumption that the indicators are highly related to the construct. The table shows the cross-loading results of the discriminant validity test as follows:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Work Discipline (Z)	Organizational Commitment (Y)	Quality of Work Life (X2)	Supervision (X1)
X1.1	0.722	0.678	0.807	0.900
X1.10	0.727	0.769	0.758	0.892
X1.2	0.747	0.700	0.745	0.699
X1.3	0.675	0.711	0.700	0.830
X1.4	0.605	0.629	0.611	0.811
X1.5	0.702	0.714	0.715	0.823
X1.6	0.700	0.573	0.601	0.743
X1.7	0.697	0.572	0.676	0.683
X1.8	0.671	0.644	0.821	0.876
X1.9	0.678	0.641	0.770	0.848
X2.1	0.763	0.701	0.873	0.810
X2.2	0.778	0.715	0.894	0.814

X2.3	0.785	0.786	0.888	0.759
X2.4	0.639	0.650	0.807	0.688
X2.5	0.731	0.643	0.822	0.739
Y.1	0.653	0.866	0.728	0.716
Y.2	0.761	0.905	0.699	0.736
Y.3	0.697	0.835	0.707	0.688
Z.1	0.849	0.728	0.713	0.706
Z.2	0.876	0.667	0.718	0.692
Z.3	0.845	0.650	0.694	0.699
Z.4	0.855	0.744	0.811	0.754
Z.5	0.807	0.632	0.714	0.758

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

Table 2 above shows the cross loading value of each variable and indicator factor. This can be explained that the cross loading value of each variable is greater than the cross loading value of other latent variables for each variable, so it can be interpreted that this study has discriminant validity.

Composite reliability

The next test calculates the reliability value using the composite reliability of the indicator block that measures the construct. A construct value is said to be reliable if its Composite Reliability value exceeds 0.60. In addition to looking at the composite reliability value, the reliability value can also be seen in the variable construct value with Cronbach's alpha from the indicator block that measures the construct. A construct is considered reliable if its Cronbach's alpha value exceeds 0.7. The table below shows the loading values of the research variable constructs generated by the Smart PLS software.

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Work Discipline (Z)	0.901	0.927	0.717
Moderation Effect 1	1,000	1,000	1,000
Moderation Effect 2	1,000	1,000	1,000
Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.837	0.902	0.755
Quality of Work Life (X2)	0.910	0.933	0.735
Supervision (X1)	0.942	0.951	0.662

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

Table 3 above shows that each variable has a Cronbach's Alpha value greater than 0.7, indicating that all variables are reliable. We can see that the combined reliability column is more than 0.6, meaning that if each variable has a combined reliability value greater than 0.6, then the variable is considered reliable. The average variance extracted (AVE) value listed in the column is greater than 0.7 because each variable has an AVE value greater than 0.7 which indicates that this study is authentic. This study considers all values credible if they reach the specified threshold.

Inner Model Analysis

The structural model (inner model) is evaluated to ensure that the model is robust and correct. Some indicators that can be used to assess the stages of structural model evaluation analysis include:

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.735	0.715

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

It can be seen in table 4 that there is an R square value for the organizational commitment variable of 0.735 or 73.5%, meaning that the influence of supervision and quality of work life on organizational commitment is 0.735 and the rest is in other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After evaluating the inner model, the next step is to investigate the relationship between the hypothesized latent constructs in this study. In this study, the hypothesis was tested using T-statistics and P-values. The hypothesis is accepted if the T-Statistics value is more than 1.96 and P-Values are less than 0.05. The Direct Influence Path Coefficient gives the following results:

Table 5. Hypothesis and Moderation Results

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Work Discipline (Z) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.300	1,918	0.028	Accepted
Moderation Effect 1 -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	-0.094	0.733	0.232	Rejected
Moderation Effect 2 -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.141	1,046	0.148	Rejected
Quality of Work Life (X2) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.278	1,837	0.033	Accepted
Supervision (X1) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.344	2,103	0.018	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

In table 5 there are the results of the hypothesis and the results of the research will be explained as follows:

1. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.300 and p values of 0.028. If work discipline increases, organizational commitment will increase, conversely, if it decreases, organizational commitment will decrease.
2. Supervision has a negative and insignificant effect on organizational commitment moderated by Work Discipline with an original sample value of -0.094 and p values of

0.232, meaning that work discipline is not a moderating variable because it is unable to influence it significantly.

3. Quality of Work Life has a positive but insignificant effect on organizational commitment moderated by Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.141 and p values of 0.148, meaning that work discipline is not a moderating variable because it is unable to influence it significantly.
4. Quality of Work Life has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.278 and p values of 0.033, meaning that if the quality of work life increases, organizational commitment will increase, if it decreases, organizational commitment will decrease.
5. Supervision has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.344 and p values of 0.018, meaning that if supervision increases, organizational commitment increases, conversely, if it decreases, organizational commitment also decreases.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.300 and p values of 0.028.
2. Supervision has a negative and insignificant effect on organizational commitment moderated by Work Discipline with an original sample value of -0.094 and p values of 0.232.
3. Quality of Work Life has a positive but insignificant effect on organizational commitment moderated by Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.141 and p values of 0.148.
4. Quality of Work Life has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.278 and p values of 0.033.
5. Supervision has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.344 and p values of 0.018.

Suggestion

1. Organizations must increase supervision of employees to improve employee performance.
2. Organizations must improve employee discipline for organizational progress and to make work easier.
3. Organizations must create a work life that is good for the organization and the comfort of employees.
4. The organization increases employee organizational commitment to organizational development.
5. It is hoped that this research will be used as input for organizational development,
6. It is hoped that this research will be used as reference material for new research and new research models.

REFERENCES

- Ayal, A., Tewal, B., & Trang, I. (2019). Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi Dan Kualitas Kehidupan Kerja Terhadap Komitmen Organisasi Di Kantor Kecamatan Sonder. *Jurnal EMBA: Jurnal Riset Ekonomi, Manajemen, Bisnis dan Akuntansi*, 7(4).

- Agustini, Faizah. (2019). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Lanjutan*. Medan: Madenatera
- Anggriani, (2014). *Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi Dan Iklim Organisasi, Terhadap Komitmen Dan Kinerja Dosen Universitas Islam Negeri Sultan Syarif Kasim Riau*. Pekanbaru. CV. Nuansa Jaya Mandiri.
- Darmawan, D. (2014). *Prinsip-prinsip Perilaku Organisasi*. Surabaya: Pena Semesta
- Dodiansyah, Khafidh. (2014). *Hubungan Antara Dukungan Sosial dengan Stres Kerja Pada Karyawan Solopas*. Skripsi. Surakarta: Fakultas Psikologi Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta.
- Ghozali, Imam dan Hengky Latan (2015). *Partial Least Squares Konsep Teknik dan Aplikasi dengan Program Smart PLS 3.0*. Semarang: Universitas Diponegoro Semarang.
- Hani Handoko T, (2015) . *Manajemen* , EdisiKe 2, Penerbit ,BPEF, Yogyakarta
- Jayadi, U., & Farida Ferine, K. . (2024). *Impact of Leadership and Professionalism on Teacher Performance with Quality Management as Mediator*. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Multidisciplinary Science (INTISARI)*, 1(1), 662–673. Retrieved from <https://ojs.multidisciplinarypress.org/index.php/intisari/article/view/59>
- Kadarisman. (2014). *Manajemen Pengembangan Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: PT. RajaGrafindo Persada.
- K.S.Mawu., B. (2018). *Pengaruh Kualitas Kehidupan Kerja Dan Kepuasan Kerja Terhadap Produktivitas Kerja Pegawai Kantor Sekretariat Daerah Kabupaten Minahasa Tenggara* *Jurnal Emba*, Vol.6 No.4 September 2018, Hal. 3148 – 3157.
- Sugiyono. (2017). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: Alfabeta, CV.

Optimizing Organizational Commitment

M. Ilham Hidayat¹, Kiki Farida Ferine²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: kikifarida@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

In this era of globalization, quality human resources are needed and become capital for the business world to continue to grow and prosper. To achieve results that meet expectations, human resource development must be pursued as closely as possible. Supervision is essentially a function inherent in a leader or top management in any organization, along with other basic management functions such as planning and implementation. This research was conducted with the aim of examining the influence of supervision and work climate on organizational commitment with work discipline as an intervening variable at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province. The results of this research are as follows: Work Discipline has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with the original sample being 0.126 and p value 0.289. Work Climate has a positive and significant effect on Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.264 and ap value of 0.012. Work Climate has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.525 and ap value of 0.004. Supervision has a positive and significant effect on work discipline with an original sample value of 0.639 and ap value of 0.000. Supervision has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.131 and ap value of 0.251. Work Climate has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment through Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.033 and an ap value of 0.312. Supervision has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment through Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.081 and an ap value of 0.293.

Keywords: Supervision, Work Climate, Work Discipline, Organizational Commitment

INTRODUCTION

HR managers must be proactive in planning, implementing, and monitoring organizational initiatives related to HR growth. Human resource development is a crucial aspect in every business or organization, and is also important for the success of the business in achieving its goals. Therefore, improving human resource development is very important. In this era of globalization, quality human resources are needed and become capital for the business world to continue to grow and prosper. To achieve results that are in accordance with expectations, human resource development must be pursued as much as possible.

Supervision is essentially a function inherent in a leader or top management in any organization, along with other basic management functions such as planning and implementation. This, it turns out, has been recognized by both large government organizations and small organizations, including the general public. On the other hand, the purpose of this effort is to increase the utilization of state apparatus in carrying out general government duties and building infrastructure to support healthy and efficient governance (good and clean governance). Supervision is one of the managerial activities or functions related to other functions, such as planning, organizing, leadership, determination, and implementation of decisions. Supervision is a derivative function designed to ensure that management activities run in accordance with the objectives assessed to achieve high performance. Revealing errors and irregularities is also corrective after being borrowed.

An unsatisfactory work environment, such as an unsatisfactory work environment, can cause problems with employee health. Work climate is one of the physical factors that has

the potential to cause health problems for workers when in extreme conditions. Extreme work environment temperature conditions include heat and cold that are beyond the limits of human ability to adapt. The question of how to determine that environmental temperature conditions are extreme is important, considering that human ability to adapt varies greatly and is influenced by many factors. positive, and vice versa. Discipline is one of the things that makes it difficult to determine whether a manager or leader's actions are successful or not. Employees who fail to follow the rules set by the company will face consequences. This is why disciplinary regulations cannot be strictly adhered to and require wise consideration. Discipline refers to the ability of an organization or business to achieve its goals. As a source of human resource management, discipline is a very important operational function of management. Likewise, high work performance will create quality employees. If discipline is weak, the company will have difficulty achieving what it wants, namely a kind of success. Discipline is very important for organizational growth, used primarily to motivate employees to be able to discipline themselves in carrying out work both individually and in groups.

One of the keys that also determines that an organization is not to achieve its goals is employee commitment. Employees who have committees in the organization usually give work assignments to less experienced co-workers who are very committed to the company and very obedient to it. In committees that have vital components such as binders that will produce energy to carry out tasks optimally.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Supervision have a positive and significant effect on Work Discipline at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
2. Does the Work Climate Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Work Discipline at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
3. Does Supervision have a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
4. Does Work Climate Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Organizational Commitment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
5. Does Work Discipline have a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
6. Does Supervision have a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Work Discipline at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
7. Does Work Climate Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Organizational Commitment through Work Discipline at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of Supervision on Work Discipline at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
2. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Climate on Work Discipline at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
3. To determine and analyze the influence of Supervision on Organizational Commitment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
4. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Climate on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.

5. To determine the influence of Organizational Commitment on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
6. To determine and analyze the influence of Supervision on Organizational Commitment through Work Discipline at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
7. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Climate on Organizational Commitment through Work Discipline at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational Commitment

According to Robbins (2016) organizational commitment is defined as a condition where an employee sides with the organization and its goals and willingness to maintain membership in a particular job of an employee, while high organizational commitment means siding with the organization and recruiting the individual. According to Mardiyana et al. (2019) organizational commitment can be defined as a situation where an employee sides with a particular organization with the goal and desire to maintain membership in the organization.

Organizational Commitment Indicators

According to Robbins (2016), the indicators of organizational commitment are:

1. Affective commitment, namely an emotional feeling towards the organization and belief in values.
2. Continuance commitment is the perceived value of remaining in the organization compared to leaving the organization.
3. Normative commitment, namely the obligation to remain in an organization for moral and polite reasons.

Supervision

According to Harianto et al., (2020) work supervision is a systematic effort to set performance standards in a plan in order to design an information feedback system to determine whether a deviation occurs and measure the extent of the deviation, and to take the necessary corrective actions to ensure that all tasks carried out have been carried out as effectively as possible to achieve organizational goals. According to Handoko (2017) supervision can be interpreted as a process to "guarantee" that organizational and management goals are achieved.

Supervisory Indicator

According to Handoko (2017), the work supervision indicators are as follows:

1. Accurate Information, namely regarding the implementation of information must be accurate, inaccurate data from the monitoring system can cause the organization to take incorrect corrective actions or even create non-existent or new problems.
2. Timely, namely information must be collected, delivered and evaluated as soon as possible if improvement activities must be carried out.
3. Objective and comprehensive, namely information must be easy to understand and be objective and complete.

4. Focus on control points where the control system strategy must focus on areas where deviations from standards occur most frequently or which will result in the most fatal damage.
5. Economically realistic. The cost of implementing a monitoring system must be lower or at least equal to the benefits obtained from the system.
6. Organizationally realistic. The monitoring system must be compatible or harmonious with the realities that exist in the organization.
7. Coordination with the organizational work flow, namely, supervisory information must be coordinated with the work flow of the organization, because each stage of the work process can affect access or failure and the overall operation of supervisory information must reach all personnel who need it.
8. Flexible, namely supervision must have the flexibility to provide responses or reactions to threats or opportunities from the environment.
9. Acts as a guide and the operational control system must be effective, must show whether detection or deviation from the standard, what corrective action should be taken.
10. Accepted by members of the organization. Where the supervision system must be able to direct the implementation of the work of members or employees of the organization by encouraging feelings of autonomy, responsibility and achievement.

Working Climate

According to Baskara (2018), work climate is defined as the perception of organizational policies, practices and procedures that are felt and accepted by individuals in the organization, or individual perceptions of their workplace. According to Rahsel (2016), work climate is the result of employee perceptions of various aspects of their work environment that will influence their behavior within the organization.

Work Climate Indicators

Work climate indicators in Baskara (2018) include

1. work environment,
2. relationships between members of the organization,
3. leadership in organizations.

Work Discipline

According to Alfiah (2019) discipline is a management activity to meet organizational standards. According to Sari (2017) work discipline is a tool used by managers to communicate with employees so that they are willing to change a behavior and as an effort to increase awareness and availability of a person to comply with all company regulations and applicable social norms.

Work Discipline Indicators

Meanwhile, according to Alfiah (2019), the indicators of work discipline are as follows:

1. Attendance is the main indicator that measures the level of discipline and in general, low work discipline among employees can be reflected in the employee's habit of being late for work.
2. Compliance with work regulations is a form of employee compliance with work regulations and always complying with applicable procedures in the Office.

3. Compliance with work standards, namely how much responsibility an employee has in carrying out the tasks assigned.
4. The employee's high level of alertness is a thorough and careful attitude in working effectively and efficiently.
5. Work ethics is a form of employee indiscipline and work discipline.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Research Hypothesis

- H1 Supervision has a positive and significant influence on Work Discipline at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H2 Work Climate has a positive and significant influence on Work Discipline at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H3 Supervision has a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H4 Work Climate has a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H5 Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H6 Supervision has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Work Discipline at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H7 Work Climate has a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment through Work Discipline at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.

METHOD

Types of research

According to Sugiyono (2014), quantitative research methods can be interpreted as research methods based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations or samples, data collection using research instruments, quantitative/statistical data analysis, with the aim of testing established hypotheses.

Time and Location of Research

This research was conducted from September to October 2024 at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province, Jalan Balai Kota No. 4, Medan City.

Population

The population of this study was 70 employees of the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province. The researcher wanted to make 70 employees as the research population. According to Sugiyono (2014), population is defined as a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher to be studied and then conclusions drawn.

Sample

This study aims to take a research sample because the population is 70 employees, so the researcher takes all the population to be used as a sample of 70 employees. According to Sugiyono (2014) a sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population.

Research Data Sources

According to Sugiyono (2014), primary sources are data sources that directly provide data to data collectors.

Data Collection Techniques

The data collection technique used by the researcher was to use a questionnaire as a data collection tool and the questionnaire was distributed to the sample to be filled in.

According to Sugiyono (2014), a questionnaire is an efficient data collection technique if the researcher knows who the variables will be measured by and knows what to expect from the respondents.

Data Analysis Techniques

Data analysis was conducted using the Partial Least Square (PLS) method using the SmartPLS 3.3.3 program. PLS represents one of the structural equation modeling (SEM) methods which in this case is more advanced than other SEM techniques. SEM is associated with a higher level of flexibility in research that connects theory and data.

Measurement Model or Outer Model

Validity Test

a. Content Validity

The validity of the questionnaire can be determined by using a questionnaire that has been widely used by researchers. The questionnaire used in this study is the result of a literature review with modifications needed to identify respondents' tendencies towards certain topics.

b. Convergent Validity

This convergence test determines whether each question item increases the mean of the same variable. Therefore, only question items with high significance are included, namely 42 out of every 100 questions have standard errors on the research variable question items. Convergence validity can be reduced if each variable has an AVE of less than 0.5 and each loading item has a value greater than 0.5. (Ghozali (2014)

c. Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

This validation task involves calculating the validity of each question by looking at the average variance extracted (AVE). AVE stands for average relative variance Extracted

(AVE) between the question item and any indicator which is a summary of convergent indicators. For optimal performance, if the AVE of each question item has a value of more than 0.5 (Ghozali (2014)

d. Discriminant Validity

This validity test explains whether two variables are quite different from each other. The discriminant validity test can be met if the correlation value of the variable to the variable itself is greater when compared to the correlation value of all other variables. In addition, another way to meet the discriminant validity test can be seen in the cross loading value, if the cross loading value of each variable statement item to the variable itself is greater than the correlation value of the statement item to other variables (Ghozali, 2014)

Reliability

Reliability is defined as a general rule for measuring deviations from stated items. Reliability testing is used to adjust the consistency of answers to a questionnaire or research instrument, or to adjust the consistency of a particular hypothesis. A variable can be said to be reliable when it has a Composite Reliability value ≥ 0.7 . Testing reliability can be done through composite reliability. (Sekaran, 2014).

Structural Model or Inner Model

Based on substantive theory, the inner model (also known as inner relationship, structural model, and substantive theory) describes the relationships among latent variables. The structural model is evaluated using the R-square test for the dependent variable, the Stone-Geisser Q-square test for predicting height and the t-test, as well as the significance of the path structure parameters. When evaluating a PLS model, start by looking at the R-square for each dependent variable. The interpretation is the same as the regression interpretation. The R-squared value can be used to determine changes in dependent variables relative to independent variables, especially whether there is a significant change (Ghozali, 2014). In addition to evaluating the R-square value, the Partial Least Square (PLS) model is also evaluated by looking at the predictive relevance of Q-square to the instruction model. Q square shows some good observation results produced by the model and its parameter estimates.

Hypothesis Testing

Hippopotamus analysis was conducted using full model structural equation modeling (SEM) with smartPLS. In full model structural equation modeling, in addition to verifying the theory, it also shows whether or not there is a relationship between latent variables (Ghozali, 2014). The hypothesis is based on observations of the calculated values of the Path Coefficient in the inner model. The hypothesis is stated as follows: if the T statistic is greater than or equal to the T table of 1.96 ($\pm 5\%$), this indicates that if the T statistic is greater than or equal to the T table for each hypothesis, then it can be stated as follows: whether analyzed or not.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Assessing the Outer Model or Measurement Model To determine the level of accuracy of the marker in clarifying the developing exogenous construct indicated by the loading factor. For questions at the early stages of development, a person's reflective steps are said

to be related if more than 0.6 with the measured development is considered adequate (Ghozali 2014):

Figure 2. Outer Model

Smart PLS output for loading factor gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Z = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e_1$$

$$Z = 0.639X_1 + 0.264X_2 + e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_2X_1 + b_3X_2 + b_4Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.131X_1 + 0.525 X_2+ 0.126Z+e_2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Work Discipline (Z)	Work Climate (X2)	Organizational Commitment (Y)	Supervision (X1)
X1.1				0.801
X1.10				0.772
X1.2				0.850
X1.3				0.834
X1.4				0.781
X1.5				0.708
X1.6				0.820
X1.7				0.793

X1.8				0.848
X1.9				0.822
X2.1		0.850		
X2.2		0.878		
X2.3		0.818		
Y.1			0.862	
Y.2			0.775	
Y.3			0.828	
Z.1	0.831			
Z.2	0.793			
Z.3	0.801			
Z.4	0.884			
Z.5	0.819			

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

Since each loading factor value is more than 0.6, it can be said that each construct meets the requirements of convergent validity. Unwavering quality is also recognized by Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability. If Cronbach's Alpha is greater than 0.60 and the Composite Reliability score is greater than 0.70, then the development is considered to be of good quality.

Discriminant Validity

The measurement model of reflective indicators assessed by cross loading and compared with the squared AVE value is a source of discriminant validity. The model is said to have a good discriminant validity value if the AVE value of each construct is higher than the correlation value between constructs. To use this discriminant validity evaluation method, the score must be at least more than 0.7. The following table shows the findings of the cross loading analysis of discriminant validity:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Work Discipline (Z)	Work Climate (X2)	Organizational Commitment (Y)	Supervision (X1)
X1.1	0.738	0.763	0.694	0.801
X1.10	0.662	0.670	0.459	0.772
X1.2	0.857	0.764	0.624	0.850
X1.3	0.646	0.680	0.548	0.834
X1.4	0.647	0.630	0.551	0.781
X1.5	0.615	0.606	0.541	0.708
X1.6	0.663	0.769	0.604	0.820
X1.7	0.725	0.645	0.525	0.793
X1.8	0.796	0.861	0.621	0.848
X1.9	0.641	0.794	0.522	0.822
X2.1	0.752	0.850	0.560	0.835
X2.2	0.727	0.878	0.658	0.802

X2.3	0.655	0.818	0.686	0.649
Y.1	0.781	0.802	0.862	0.791
Y.2	0.312	0.399	0.775	0.382
Y.3	0.413	0.503	0.828	0.432
Z.1	0.831	0.744	0.615	0.758
Z.2	0.793	0.598	0.502	0.616
Z.3	0.801	0.696	0.509	0.714
Z.4	0.884	0.771	0.611	0.792
Z.5	0.819	0.636	0.564	0.725

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

In table 2, the cross loading value of the work discipline variable is greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, the cross loading of the work climate variable has a value greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, the cross loading on the organizational commitment variable has a value greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, the cross loading of the supervision variable has a value greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, so it can be concluded that this test is valid in a discriminant state.

Composite Reliability

According to Haryono's book (2017), a construct is said to be reliable if its limit value is ≥ 0.7 then it is acceptable, and if ≥ 0.8 then it is very satisfactory. The findings of the composite reliability analysis are shown in the table below.

Table 3. Composite Reliability

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Work Discipline (Z)	0.883	0.915	0.682
Work Climate (X2)	0.806	0.886	0.721
Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.783	0.862	0.677
Supervision (X1)	0.939	0.948	0.646

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

The Cronbach alpha column in the following table shows that the value of each variable is greater than 0.7, indicating that the data of the variable's dependency is reliable. Each variable is said to be reliable because its data is greater than 0.6 as indicated by the composite reliability column value greater than 0.6. Each variable has a value greater than 0.7, as shown in the AVE column, indicating that the data is original in terms of AVE. Since the values of the reliability column, AVE, and Cronbach alpha are each higher than 0.7 and 0.6, they are all considered valid and reliable.

Inner Model Analysis

To ensure the resulting fundamental model is accurate and robust, the structural model (inner model) is evaluated. The main model assessment examination phase is seen through a number of indicators, including:

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Based on R² a model can be classified as strong (≤ 0.70), medium (≤ 0.45) and weak (≤ 0.25). The following are the results of the R² value:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Work Discipline (Z)	0.782	0.775
Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.572	0.553

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

In table 4 there is an R square value, for the R square value of the work discipline variable there is a value of 0.782 if it is changed to a percentage then the result is 78.2% meaning that the influence of supervision and work climate on work discipline is 0.782 or 78.2% and the rest is on other variables. For the R square value of the organizational commitment variable of 0.572 if it is changed to a percentage value of 57.2% meaning that the influence of supervision, work climate and discipline on work commitment is 0.572 or 57.2% and the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis Proof

There must be a significant value in the prediction of the route coefficient between constructs. Jackknifing or bootstrapping techniques can be used to determine the significance of the relationship. The calculated t value is the final result, and is compared to the t table. The estimated value of the route coefficient is said to be significant if at a significance level of five percent the calculated t value is greater than the t table (1.96). There are three hypotheses that can be tested in this study.

Table 5. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Work Discipline (Z) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.126	0.556	0.289	Rejected
Work Climate (X2) -> Work Discipline (Z)	0.264	2,249	0.012	Accepted
Work Climate (X2) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.525	2,628	0.004	Accepted
Supervision (X1) -> Work Discipline (Z)	0.639	5,623	0,000	Accepted
Supervision (X1) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.131	0.672	0.251	Rejected

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

The research results in table 5 are the results of the hypothesis and will be explained as follows:

1. Work Discipline has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample of 0.126 and p values of 0.289. If work discipline increases, it does not necessarily mean that organizational commitment will increase, conversely, if work discipline decreases, it does not necessarily mean that organizational commitment will also decrease.

2. Work climate has a positive and significant effect on work discipline with an original sample value of 0.264 and p values of 0.012. If the work climate improves well, work discipline will improve, conversely, if the work climate decreases, work discipline will decrease.
3. Work climate has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment with an original sample value of 0.525 and p values of 0.004. If the work climate improves, organizational commitment will also improve, conversely, if it decreases, organizational commitment will decrease.
4. Supervision has a positive and significant effect on work discipline with an original sample value of 0.639 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if supervision increases, work discipline will also increase, conversely, if supervision decreases, work discipline will also decrease.
5. Supervision has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.131 and p values of 0.251. If supervision increases, it does not necessarily mean that organizational commitment will increase, conversely, if supervision decreases, it does not necessarily mean that organizational commitment will decrease.

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Work Climate (X2) -> Work Discipline (Z) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.033	0.491	0.312	Rejected
Supervision (X1) -> Work Discipline (Z) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.081	0.545	0.293	Rejected

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

In table 6 there are indirect influence values and they will be explained as follows:

1. Work Climate has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment through Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.033 and p values of 0.312, meaning that work discipline is not an intervening variable because it is unable to significantly influence work climate and organizational commitment.
2. Supervision has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment through Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.081 and p values of 0.293, meaning that work discipline is not an intervening variable because it is unable to significantly influence supervision and organizational commitment.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Work Discipline has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample of 0.126 and p values of 0.289.
2. Work Climate has a positive and significant effect on Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.264 and p values of 0.012.
3. Work Climate has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.525 and p values of 0.004.

4. Supervision has a positive and significant effect on work discipline with an original sample value of 0.639 and p values of 0.000.
5. Supervision has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.131 and p values of 0.251.
6. Work Climate has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment through Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.033 and p values of 0.312.
7. Supervision has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment through Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.081 and p values of 0.293.

Suggestion

1. It is expected that the organization will provide supervision to avoid errors in work.
2. The organization must create a comfortable and good working climate for employees.
3. The organization must provide discipline to employees by providing regulations that must be obeyed by the organization.
4. This research is expected to be used as input for the organization to develop.
5. This research is expected to help other research.
6. It is hoped that this research will be used as reference material for new researchers and can be developed further.

REFERENCES

- Alfiah. (2019). Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja Dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Tetap (Studi Kasus Pada Pt X). [Skripsi]. Jakarta. Universitas Pertamina.
- Baskara, Agus dan Zakir Has. (2018). Pengaruh Motivasi, Kepribadian dan lingkungan Keluarga terhadap Minat Berwirausaha Mahasiswa Fakultas Keguruan dan Ilmu Pendidikan Universitas Islam Riau (UIR). *PeKA: Jurnal Pendidikan Ekonomi Akuntansi FKIP UIR* Vol 6 No 1
- Ghozali, I. Latan, H. (2014). *Partial Least Square : Konsep, Teknik dan Aplikasi Smart PLS 2.0 M3*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Handoko (2017) *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Edisi Revisi Jakarta Bumi Aksara. *Metodelogi Penelitian Untuk Skripsi dan Tesis Bisnis*. Jakarta : P Gramedia Pustaka.
- Hariato, A. S. (2020) "Pengaruh Pengawasan Kerja Dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada Pt Centric Powerindo Di Kota Batam," *Jurnal EMBA: Jurnal Riset Ekonomi, Manajemen, Bisnis dan Akuntansi*, 8(1), hal. 672–683. doi: 10.35794/emba.v8i1.28037.
- Mardiana, M Doewes, S. P. (2019). Development of Learning Media Based on Mobil Learning Application. *Jurnal Pendidikan Progresif*, 9(1), 50–58. <https://doi.org/10.23960/jpp.v9.i1.201907>
- Rahsel Y., (2016), Pengaruh Iklim Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Administrasi Pusat Universitas Padjadjaran Bandung (Studi Pada Bagian Administrasi Umum UNPAD), *Jurnal Manajemen Magister*, Vol 02. No.01.
- Robbins, Stephen P. (2016). *Perilaku Organisasi*. Jakarta Selatan : Salemba Empat.
- Sekaran, Uma. 2014. *Metodologi Penelitian Untuk Bisnis (Research Methods for Business)* Buku 1 Edisi 4. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.

- Sari, (2017), Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Bagian Kantor Pada PT. PLN (Persero) Area Pekanbaru Rayon Kota Timur, Vol. 4 No. 2 – Oktober 2017. Pandi, Affandi, (2018), Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia : Teori konsep, dan Indikator, Zanata Publishing, Yogyakarta.
- Sugiyono. (2014). Metode Penelitian Pendidikan Pendekatan Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D. Bandung: Alfabeta.

Performance Determination

Leo Fauzi Hasibuan¹, Kiki Farida Ferine²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: kikifarida@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

This research was conducted to determine the influence of human resource quality and work ethics on employee performance with organizational commitment as an intervening variable at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province. Effective and efficient achievement of company goals requires the continuous implementation of internal human resource management. The efficacy and efficiency of a company greatly depends on the advantages and disadvantages of resource development. This means that the company's human resources must be developed and nurtured in order to be able to improve their work capabilities, which will ultimately have an impact on improving performance. The results of this research are as follows: Work Ethics has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance with the original sample being 0.079 and p value 0.322. Work Ethics has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with the original sample being 0.665 and p value 0.000. Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.831 and ap value of 0.000. HR quality has a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.020 and ap value of 0.428. HR quality has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.263 and ap value of 0.006. Work Ethics has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Organizational Commitment indirectly with an original sample value of 0.552 and ap value of 0.000. HR quality has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through organizational commitment indirectly with the original sample being 0.218 and p value 0.009.

Keywords: HR Quality, Work Ethics, Organizational Commitment, Employee Performance

INTRODUCTION

Effective and efficient achievement of company goals requires continuous implementation of internal human resource management. The efficacy and efficiency of the company are highly dependent on the advantages and disadvantages of resource development. This means that the human resources owned by the company must be developed and nurtured in order to improve their work capabilities, which will ultimately have an impact on improving performance. Considering that human resources are one of the internal variables that determine the success or failure of a company in achieving its goals, effective resource management is needed. The purpose of human resource management is to help the organization achieve its goals, including by forming a positive work culture, providing motivation, direction, and good coordination to employees in their work, and unifying the perspectives of organizational leaders and employees. To support the government in achieving its vision and goals and preparing for the implementation of planned national policies, employee or HR participation is very important. The ability of employees to manage planning, coordination, implementation, and business arrangements Therefore, this function is very important for the success of the organization. Work ethic is said to be a determining factor in the success of individuals, groups, institutions and also the broadest is the nation in achieving its goals. In the implementation of public administration is also influenced by the work ethic of public officials in their duties to meet the needs of the community. Work ethic itself can be interpreted as the most important basis of behavior

regarding the view of right or wrong. Ethic itself is the most basic moral of a person, in carrying out his work. Work ethic can be formed if the desire to be able to do a job optimally. A high work ethic always works with a sense of joy and pride, has a high level of motivation and discipline, has integrity, is responsible, and is generous in his work. In the workplace, a person's dedication to the company is often a crucial factor. Because of how important it is, some companies even dare to include commitment as a prerequisite for accepting a position that is included in the employment announcement. The importance of dedication for every employee cannot be overstated, because those who have it tend to be more responsible in their work than those who do not. Employees who are committed to their work usually work as efficiently as possible, allowing you to focus all your attention, thoughts, energy, and time on their tasks, ensuring that their results meet the company's expectations. To achieve company and personal goals, employee performance is one of the main components. If employees in the company do not work well, the organization will find it difficult to achieve its goals. Employees who are attentive, obedient, disciplined, and responsible for all tasks given and completed are essential to achieving organizational goals. Employee performance is now the focus of supervision from many government circles as a whole. To ensure that each employee can carry out work in accordance with the goals that have been set, various efforts are made. This is due to the inability of workers to complete tasks according to the standards set, so that government organizations cannot achieve their goals. Meanwhile, every increase in worker performance carried out by a Business worker will increase the effectiveness and efficiency of its workers in carrying out their duties, which will ultimately benefit government organizations.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does HR Quality have a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
2. Does Work Ethic have a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
3. Does HR Quality Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
4. Does Work Ethic have a positive and significant influence on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
5. Does Organizational Commitment have a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
6. Does HR Quality Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Job Satisfaction through Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
7. Does Work Ethic have a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Organizational Commitment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of HR Quality on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
2. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Ethic on Organizational Commitment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
3. To determine and analyze the influence of HR Quality on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

4. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Ethic on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
5. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Commitment on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
6. To determine and analyze the influence of HR Quality on Job Satisfaction through Organizational Commitment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
7. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Ethic on Job Satisfaction through Organizational Commitment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee Performance

According to Simanjuntak (2015) performance is the level of achievement of results from the implementation of certain tasks. According to Mangkunegara (2017) performance is the work results in terms of quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him.

Employee Performance Indicators

According to Mangkunegara (2017), employee performance indicators are:

- a. Work quality Reflects the improvement in quality and previously determined work standards, usually accompanied by an increase in capability and economic value.
- b. Quantity of work Reflects the increase in volume or number of a unit of activity that produces goods in terms of quantity. Quantity of work can be measured through the addition of physical value and goods from previous results.
- c. Whether or not someone can be relied on reflects how someone completes a job assigned to them with a high level of accuracy, willingness and enthusiasm.
- d. Cooperative attitude Reflects an attitude that shows high cooperation among fellow employees and attitudes towards superiors, as well as towards employees from other companies.

Quality of Human Resources

According to Aisyah et al (2017), HR quality is the ability to carry out tasks and can be interpreted as employees who have knowledge and can help companies compete. According to Matutina (2015) the quality of human resources refers to knowledge, skills and abilities.

Human Resources Quality Indicators

According to Matutina (2016), the indicators of HR quality are as follows:

- 1) Work knowledge, namely the abilities possessed by employees that are more oriented towards intelligence and thinking power as well as the employee's mastery of broad knowledge.
- 2) Work skills, namely the ability and technical operational mastery in a particular field that employees have.
- 3) Work ability, namely the ability formed from the competencies possessed by an employee which includes loyalty, discipline, cooperation and responsibility.

Work ethic

According to Ginting (2016), work ethic is the work spirit that is characteristic of a person or group of people who work, which is based on work ethics and perspectives that are believed in and manifested through concrete behavioral determination in the world of work.

According to Priansa (2018), work ethic is a work spirit possessed by employees to be able to work better in order to obtain added value in a job.

Work Ethic Indicator

According to Priansa (2020) there are 8 indicators of work ethic, namely:

1. Work is Grace: Work sincerely, full of gratitude
2. Work is a mandate: Work thoroughly with integrity
3. Work is a Calling: Work properly and responsibly
4. Work is Actualization: Working hard with enthusiasm
5. Work is Worship: Work seriously, full of love
6. Work is Art: Work smart and full of creativity
7. Work is an Honor: Work diligently with excellence
8. Work is Service: Work with humility

Organizational Commitment

According to Kaswan (2015), the definition of organizational commitment is as follows: "The extent to which employees are dedicated to their employing organizations and are willing to work on their behalf, and the likelihood that they will maintain membership. (This definition states that organizational commitment can be considered as the extent to which employees are dedicated to the organization where they work and the willingness to work on behalf of/for the interests of the organization, and the likelihood that they will maintain membership.)"

Organizational Commitment Indicators

According to Kaswan (2015), indicators of organizational commitment are:

1. There is a willingness to help colleagues complete organizational tasks,
2. Aligning existing activities and priorities to achieve larger organizational goals,
3. Understand the organization's needs to achieve larger organizational goals, and
4. Choosing appropriate organizational needs rather than following some professional interests.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

- H1 The quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H2 Work Ethic has a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H3 The quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H4 Work Ethic has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H5 Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H6 Human resource quality has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through organizational commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H7 Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.

METHOD

Types of research

This study uses quantitative as a type of research in a study as a research requirement. Quantitative (Sugiyono, 2022) is a study with a positivistic basis that aims to examine a particular population or sample. Data analysis in quantitative is statistical in nature with the aim of describing and testing predetermined hypotheses.

Location and Time of Research

The location of this research was conducted at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province, Jalan Balai Kota No. 4. This research was conducted from September to October 2024.

Research Population

This study uses the population of all employees of the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of Sumatra Province to become a population of 70 employees. Population according to Sugiyono (2022), population is a generalization area consisting of: objects/subjects that have certain quantities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn.

Research Sample

The researcher wants to use all populations as samples in this study as many as 70 employees, because the researcher uses all populations as samples, this research technique uses a saturated sample technique where the researcher uses all populations as samples. According to Sugiyono (2022), a sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population.

Research Data Sources

According to Sugiyono (2022), primary data is original data collected by researchers themselves to answer their research problems specifically.

Data collection technique

Researchers use questionnaire data collection techniques in which researchers create questionnaires and distribute them to sample respondents. According to Sugiyono (2022), questionnaires are an efficient data collection technique if researchers already know the variables being measured and know what is expected from respondents.

Data Analysis Techniques

Partial Least Square SEM data analysis is an analysis used to develop or predict an existing theory (Sarwono & Narimawati (2015). This study uses PLS structural model analysis assisted by SmartPLS 3.0 software. According to Sabil (2015), structural model analysis has several stages, namely: 1) Formulating structural model theory, 2) Outer model analysis, 3) Inner model analysis, and 4) Hypothesis testing.

Outer model testing

In testing the outer model aims to see the validity and reliability of a model. This test analysis will be seen from the influence of the Loading factor, Average Variance Extracted (AVE), and Discriminant Validity, as well as composite reliability.

Loading factor

Factor loading is the initial stage in testing the validity of a model, the requirement for factor loading is that it must be > 0.6 , so that the indicator is said to be valid. If it is not valid, it must be removed from the model (Husein. 2015).

Average variance extracted (ave)

Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is a value used in convergent validity testing because the value is obtained from the convergent validity output. In this study, the expected AVE value is > 0.5 , and so when viewed from the latent variable construct, all constructs have values above 0.5 (or greater than 0.5),

Discriminant Validity

Discriminant Validity can be tested by looking at the cross loading table, this output is used to test discriminant validity at the indicator level with the provision that the correlation between the indicator and its latent variable is $>$ compared to the correlation between the indicator and other latent variables (outside its block).

Composite reliability

To ensure that there are no measurement-related problems, the final step in the outer model evaluation is to test the unidimensionality of the model. This unidimensionality test is carried out using composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha. For both indicators, the cut-off value is 0.7.

Inner model testing

a) Determinization Coefficient R2 (R-Square)

Goodness of fit in PLS can be known by the Q2 value. The Q2 value has the same meaning as the coefficient of determination (R-Square) in regression analysis.

b). Hypothesis

Hypothesis Testing Hypothesis testing in PLS is used to measure the probability of data using the path coefficients menu. The rule of thumbs for supporting a research hypothesis is: if the coefficient or direction of the relationship between variables (indicated by the original sample value) is in line with the hypothesis, and if the t-statistic value is > 1.64 (two tailed) or > 1.96 (one tailed) it can be said to be significant and the probability value (p-value) < 0.01; < 0.05; 50 < 0.10 can be said to be significant. In p-value if the value is > 0.10 then it can be said to be insignificant (Jogiyanto and Abdillah, 2014).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

The details of the relationship between latent variables and manifest variables can be known by using measurement model testing, also known as external model testing. This test has reliability, discriminant validity, and convergent validity.

Convergent Validity

The loading factor shows this test, the limit value. Average Variance Extracted and the limit value is 0.7. (AVE) is set at 0.5; values above this indicate validity. This shows that if the indicator value > 0.7 is able to explain the construct variable, then the indicator value is considered valid. The structural model of the study is depicted in the following figure:

Figure 2. Outer Model

Smart PLS output for loading factor gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Z = b1X + b2X2 + e1$$

$$Z = 0.263X1 + 0.665X2 + e1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b2X1 + b3X2 + b4Z + e2$$

$$Y = 0.020 X1 + 0.079 X2 + 0.831 Z + e2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings/Cross Loading

	Work Ethic (X2)	Employee Performance (Y)	Organizational Commitment (Z)	Human Resources Quality (X1)
X1.1				0.857
X1.2				0.819
X1.3				0.814
X2.1	0.735			
X2.2	0.870			
X2.3	0.832			
X2.4	0.849			
X2.5	0.825			
X2.6	0.901			
X2.7	0.807			
X2.8	0.779			
Y.1		0.875		
Y.2		0.869		
Y.3		0.875		
Y.4		0.872		
Z.1			0.748	
Z.2			0.834	
Z.3			0.810	
Z.4			0.867	

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Each variable in table 1 has a value and states that the indicator of each variable is greater than 0.7. This shows that each indicator item has a value greater than 0.7 which indicates that the data is considered valid and can be subjected to additional research.

Discriminant Validity

To ensure the results of the indicators that are strongly correlated with their constructs, more studies will use discriminative validity to determine the validity of the data. Specifically, the goal is to ensure whether the cross loading value is greater than other latent variables. The findings of cross loading from the validity test are shown in the following table:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Work Ethic (X2)	Employee Performance (Y)	Organizational Commitment (Z)	Human Resources Quality (X1)
X1.1	0.867	0.738	0.836	0.857
X1.2	0.699	0.688	0.667	0.819
X1.3	0.651	0.563	0.617	0.814
X2.1	0.735	0.696	0.759	0.713
X2.2	0.870	0.747	0.772	0.838

X2.3	0.832	0.617	0.661	0.765
X2.4	0.849	0.757	0.766	0.739
X2.5	0.825	0.719	0.728	0.730
X2.6	0.901	0.729	0.792	0.833
X2.7	0.807	0.705	0.747	0.665
X2.8	0.779	0.592	0.719	0.657
Y.1	0.694	0.875	0.824	0.698
Y.2	0.675	0.869	0.760	0.678
Y.3	0.799	0.875	0.855	0.728
Y.4	0.779	0.872	0.760	0.710
Z.1	0.653	0.569	0.748	0.608
Z.2	0.726	0.762	0.834	0.696
Z.3	0.709	0.777	0.810	0.735
Z.4	0.839	0.856	0.867	0.761

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

It can be seen in Table 2 that each loading factor indicator in each variable has a greater result than the cross loading factor variable indicator for each other, so that this study obtained valid results in a discriminant manner and will continue to the next stage in this study.

Composite reliability

Each variable in the composite reliability study is compared for its reliability value; if the variable value is higher than 0.60 then the study is considered reliable; if between 0.60 and 0.7, then it is not. The table below shows the various blocks used to assess the validity and reliability of the study, including AVE values, composite reliability, and Cronbach's alpha values:

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Work Ethic (X2)	0.933	0.945	0.683
Employee Performance (Y)	0.896	0.927	0.761
Organizational Commitment (Z)	0.832	0.888	0.665
Human Resources Quality (X1)	0.776	0.869	0.689

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Each variable in table 3 above has a value greater than 0.7 in the Cronbach alpha column, this indicates that the reliability data of the variable is consistent. Because the data is greater than 0.6, it can be explained that each variable is considered reliable in the Composite Reliability column which has a value greater than 0.6. Each variable in the AVE column has a value greater than 0.7, this indicates that the data is valid according to the AVE standard. Because all variables in the reliability, AVE, and Cronbach alpha columns have values greater than 0.7 and 0.6, respectively, all are considered valid and reliable.

Inner Model Analysis

To ensure that the fundamental model developed is reliable and accurate, the structural model, or deep model, is evaluated. A number of markers, including the following, indicate the stages of examination performed during the assessment of the main model:

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Employee Performance (Y)	0.846	0.839
Organizational Commitment (Z)	0.827	0.821

Source : Smart PLS 3.3.3

There is an R square value in table 4 and will be explained by the researcher, for the R square value of the Employee Performance variable of 0.846 and if it is expressed as a percentage it becomes 84.6. This means that the influence of HR quality, work ethic, and organizational commitment on employee performance is 0.846 and the rest is on other variables. There is an R square value of the organizational commitment variable of 0.827 and if expressed as a percentage of 82.7%, this means that the influence of HR quality and Work Ethic is 0.827 or 82.7%.

Hypothesis Testing

As suggested by this review, the next step is to evaluate the relationship between idle builds after evaluating the deep model. To perform speculative testing in this review, T-Statistics and P-Values are checked. It is stated openly whether the P-Values are less than 0.05 and the T-Insights value is greater than 1.96. The following is the direct impact of the Path Coefficient:

Table 5. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Work Ethic (X2) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.079	0.462	0.322	Rejected
Work Ethic (X2) -> Organizational Commitment (Z)	0.665	6,916	0,000	Accepted
Organizational Commitment (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.831	5,927	0,000	Accepted
Human Resources Quality (X1) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.020	0.183	0.428	Rejected
Human Resources Quality (X1) -> Organizational Commitment (Z)	0.263	2,536	0.006	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 5 there are the results of the direct influence and will be explained one by one as follows:

1. Work Ethic has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample of 0.079 and p values of 0.322. This means that work ethic does not have much effect on performance, the higher the work ethic does not necessarily mean that employee performance will be high, conversely if work ethic decreases, it does not necessarily mean that employee performance will decrease.
2. Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample of 0.665 and p values of 0.000. This means that if work ethic increases, organizational commitment will increase, conversely if work ethic decreases, organizational commitment will decrease.
3. Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.831 and p values of 0.000. This means that if commitment increases, employee performance will increase and if organizational commitment decreases, performance will also decrease.
4. The quality of human resources has a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.020 and p values of 0.428. This means that the quality of human resources in this study has little effect on performance because each employee has an ordinary quality that only follows the directions given, meaning that if the quality of human resources increases, performance does not necessarily increase, conversely if the quality of human resources decreases, it does not necessarily decrease.
5. The quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.263 and p values of 0.006. This means that if the quality of human resources increases, organizational commitment will increase, conversely, if the quality of human resources decreases, commitment will decrease.

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Work Ethic (X2) -> Organizational Commitment (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.552	4,412	0,000	Accepted
Human Resources Quality (X1) -> Organizational Commitment (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.218	2,369	0.009	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 6 there are indirect influences and they will be explained as follows:

1. Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Organizational Commitment indirectly with the original sample value of 0.552 and p values of 0.000. This means that organizational commitment is an intervening variable because it can significantly influence the work ethic and performance of employees, with organizational commitment the work ethic and performance of employees will increase.
2. The quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through organizational commitment indirectly with the original sample of 0.218 and p values 0.009. This means that organizational commitment is an intervening variable because it can have a significant effect, with the existence of organizational commitment indirectly increasing the quality of human resources and employee performance.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Work Ethic has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample of 0.079 and p values of 0.322.
2. Work Ethic has a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment with an original sample of 0.665 and p values of 0.000.
3. Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.831 and p values of 0.000.
4. Human resource quality has a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.020 and p values of 0.428.
5. Human resource quality has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.263 and p values of 0.006.
6. Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Organizational Commitment indirectly with an original sample value of 0.552 and p values of 0.000.
7. Human resource quality has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through organizational commitment indirectly with an original sample of 0.218 and p values of 0.009.

Suggestion

1. Organizations must improve employee work ethic for the sake of organizational progress.
2. Organizations should improve the quality of employees or look for qualified employees to save training costs.
3. The organization is expected to increase employee organizational commitment for the sake of organizational development.
4. It is hoped that this research will be used as input for the organization.
5. It is hoped that this research will be used as reference material for further researchers with the same or different title but still related to this research.

REFERENCES

- Abdillah, Willy dan Jogiyanto. (2014). Konsep & Aplikasi PLS (Partial Least Square) untuk Penelitian Empiris. Yogyakarta: BPFPE.
- Aisyah, M. F., W. Utami¹, Sunardi dan Sudarsih. (2017). Kualitas Sumber Daya Manusia, Profesionalisme Kerja, Dan Komitmen Sebagai Faktor Pendukung Peningkatan Kinerja Karyawan PDAM Kabupaten Jember. *Jurnal Ekonomi Bisnis dan Akuntansi* 4(1):131-135.
- Ananda Sabil Husain (2015) Penelitian bisnis dan manajemen menggunakan partial least squares (PLS) dengan smart PLS 3.0, Modul ajar jurusan manajemen fakultas ekonomi dan bisnis universitas Brawijaya
- Fenty. (2016). Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi, Komitmen Organisasi dan Penerapan Prinsip-prinsip Good Corporate Governance (GCG) Terhadap Kinerja Perguruan Tinggi dengan Pendekatan Balanced Scorecard (BSC). Vol. 7. No. 01. Juli.
- Ginting, Desmon. (2016). Etos Kerja : Panduan Menjadi Karyawan Cerdas. Jakarta: PT. Elex Media Komputindo.

- Kaswan (2015.) Pengembangan Sumber Daya Manusia. Bandung. Indonesia: Alfabeta
- Matutina. (2015). Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Jakarta : Gramedia Widia Sarana Indonesia.
- Mangkunegara. (2017). Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan, Bandung : Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Priansa, Donni Juni. (2018). Perencanaan & Pengembangan SDM. Bandung. Alfabeta.
- Sarwono, J., dan Narimawati, U. 2015. Membuat Skripsi, Tesis dan Disertasi dengan Partial Least Square SEM (PLS-SEM). Yogyakarta: Penerbit ANDI
- Simanjuntak, P.J. (2015). Manajemen Evaluasi Kinerja. Edisi Ketiga. Cetakan Keempat. Fakultas Ekonomi Universitas Indonesia. Jakarta.
- Sugiyono. (2022). Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif. Bandung: Alfabeta.

Optimizing Work Performance

Kiki Farida Ferine

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: kikifarida@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to see the effect of the work environment and work discipline on work performance with promotion as an intervening variable. Medan Region II Airport. The research population consisted of 96 employees and all populations were sampled and the sample technique used was saturated samples. The research model used was Path analysis and the research calculation tool used Smart PLS 3.3.3. Data collection techniques used were questionnaires and surveys. Based on the results of the research that has been done and the data analysis as explained in the previous chapter, the following conclusions are conveyed from the results of the research as follows: Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance. Work Discipline has a positive and insignificant effect on Promotion. Work environment has a positive and insignificant effect on work performance. Work environment has a positive and significant effect on promotion. Promotion has no significant negative effect on work performance. Work Discipline has an indirect effect on work performance through insignificant negative promotion. The work environment has an indirect effect on work performance through insignificant negative promotion.

Keywords: Work Environment, Work Discipline, Job Achievement, Promotion

INTRODUCTION

With the development of technology, education accompanied by increasing economic growth, the actors who are struggling in the fields of economy, culture and other fields can influence the goals of the organization to be achieved in the future. One of the efforts that must be made in facing external challenges is by preparing competent and qualified human resources. Work performance is the result that has been achieved by employees according to the applicable standards for the work that has been completed, so the work performance of employees needs to be evaluated and considered. Employees can be said to have achieved if the service provided is optimal and there are no complaints from the public regarding the services that have been provided. Work performance can also be said to be the result of work achieved by employees in carrying out the tasks that have been assigned to them very seriously to produce better performance. A comfortable work environment can increase employee performance so that in carrying out their duties they can be carried out optimally, healthily, safely and comfortably. The work environment is one of the main factors that determines employees to work optimally, with a comfortable, safe and calm work environment can improve employee performance in achieving goals. The work environment greatly influences employee performance, a pleasant work environment will realize the achievement of the organization's planned goals and objectives. Job promotion plays an important role for every employee and even becomes a dream that is always expected by employees, because with this promotion means trust and recognition of the abilities and skills of the employee concerned and recognition of the abilities and skills of the employee concerned to hold a higher position. Companies need to conduct performance appraisals because they relate to giving higher responsibilities and authority to employees and getting the right people in the right place. So there is a close relationship between successful people and disciplined people.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Work performance

According to Mangkunegara (2014): "Work performance is the result of work in terms of quality and quantity, achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties, in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. The definition of work performance according to Sutrisno (2016) is to interpret achievement as a person's level of competence in tasks that include his work.

Work Performance Indicators

Work performance indicators according to Sutrisno (2016), are as follows:

- a. Work result
The level of quantity and quality that has been produced and the extent of supervision done
- b. Job Knowledge.
The level of knowledge related to the job tasks that will have a direct impact on the quantity and quality of work results.
- c. Initiative
The level of initiative during carrying out work tasks, especially in terms of handling problems that arise.
- d. Mental Agility
The level of ability and dexterity in receiving work instructions and completing them using existing work methods and work situations.
- e. Attitude
The level of work enthusiasm and positive attitude in carrying out work tasks. Time Discipline and Attendance The level of punctuality and attendance.

Work environment

According to Sedarmayati (2015) the definition of the work environment is as follows: "The work environment is the entirety of the tools and materials faced, the surrounding environment in which a person works, his work methods, and his work arrangements both as individuals and as a group. Human life cannot be separated from various conditions of the surrounding environment, between humans and the environment there is a very close relationship.

Work Environment Indicators

According to Sedarmayanti (2015) the work environment indicators are as follows:

1. Lighting/light in the workplace. Light or illumination is very beneficial for employees in order to obtain safety and smooth work,
2. Air circulation in the workplace Oxygen is a gas that is needed by living things to maintain survival, namely for the metabolic process.
3. Noise in the workplace One type of pollution that has kept experts busy dealing with it is noise, which is sound that is unwanted by the ear.
4. Bad smells in the workplace. The presence of smells around the workplace can be considered as pollution, because it can disrupt concentration at work, and the smells occur continuously.

Work Discipline

According to Sutrisno (2016), discipline is a person's attitude of willingness and readiness to obey and comply with the norms and regulations that apply around them.

Work Discipline Indicators

According to Sutrisno (2016) the indicators of work discipline are as follows:

- a. Comply with time regulations, seen from the time of coming to work, going home from work, and break times that are on time according to the rules in force in the company.
- b. Comply with company regulations Basic rules on how to dress and behave at work.
- c. Comply with the rules of conduct at work. Demonstrated by carrying out work in accordance with duties, positions and responsibilities as well as how to relate to other work units.
- d. Comply with other regulations in the company. Rules about what employees may and may not do in the company.

Job Promotion

According to Hasibuan (2016) job promotion is a transfer that increases the authority and responsibility of employees to a higher position in an organization so that their obligations, rights, status, and income are greater. The term job promotion means progress, where a promotion can occur when an employee is promoted from a low position to a higher position. Increases in salary and responsibility usually accompany job promotions.

Job Promotion Indicators

According to Hasibuan (2016) the indicators for job promotion are as follows:

- a. Honesty Employees must be honest, especially to themselves, their subordinates, agreements in carrying out or managing the position, must be in accordance with their words and actions.
- b. Discipline Employees must be disciplined in themselves, their duties, and obey the applicable regulations, both written and customary.
- c. Employee Work Performance is able to achieve work results that can be accounted for in terms of quality and quantity and work effectively and efficiently.
- d. Cooperation Employees can work together harmoniously with fellow employees, both horizontally and vertically, in achieving company goals.
- e. Employee Skills The employee is capable, creative and innovative in completing the tasks in the position well.
- f. Employee Loyalty must be loyal in defending the company or corps from actions that are detrimental to the company or corps.
- g. Leadership He must be able to foster and motivate his subordinates to work together and work effectively in achieving company goals.
- h. Communicative. The employee can communicate effectively and is able to receive or perceive information from superiors and subordinates well, so that miscommunication does not occur.
- i. Education. Employees must have a diploma from formal education in accordance with job specifications.

METHOD

According to Sugiyono (2017) quantitative research is used to examine populations or samples, sampling techniques are generally carried out randomly, data collection using research instruments, quantitative or statistical data analysis with the aim of testing the

established hypothesis. The location of the research was carried out at the Medan Region II Airport Authority Office.

According to Sugiyono (2017) population is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn. The population in this study was 96 employees. The sampling technique was saturated sampling, namely 96 employees.

The data sources used are primary data and the collection uses a questionnaire.

The regression equation is:

$$Z = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e$$
$$Y = a + b_3X_1 + b_4X_2 + b_5Z + e$$

Where:

Y = Work Performance

Z = Job Promotion

X1 = Work Environment

X2 = Work Discipline

b1 = Work Environment coefficient

b2 = Work Discipline coefficient

b3 = Work Environment coefficient

b4 = Work Discipline coefficient

b5 = Job Promotion Coefficient

a = constant

Data Analysis Techniques

Data analysis in this study used Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on Partial Least Square (PLS) using SmartPLS 3.3.3 software. PLS is one of the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) solution methods that has advantages compared to other SEM techniques. SEM has a higher level of flexibility in research that connects theory and data, and is able to perform path analysis with latent variables so that it is often used by researchers who focus on social sciences. PLS is a structural equation model (SEM) based on components or variants.

Measurement Model (Outer Model)

The procedure in testing the measurement model consists of validity testing and reliability testing.

1. Validity Test

There are several stages of testing that will be carried out, namely through convergent validity and discriminant validity tests.

a. Convergent Validity

At this stage, it will be seen how big the correlation is between the indicator and its latent construct. So that it produces a loading factor value. The loading factor value is said to be high if the component or indicator correlates more than 0.70 with the construct to be measured. However, for early stage research from development, a loading factor of 0.5 to 0.6 is considered sufficient (Ghozali, 2014). In addition, at this stage it is seen how much value each variable has. So that it produces an AVE (Average Variance Extracted) value. The AVE value is said to be high if it has a value of more than 0.5. If there is an AVE value of less than 0.5, then there are still invalid indicators. (Ghozali, 2014).

b. Discriminant Validity

This validity test explains whether two variables are sufficiently different from each other. The discriminant validity test can be met if the correlation value of the variable to the variable itself is greater when compared to the correlation value of all other variables. This value is called Fornell Lacker. In addition, another way to meet the discriminant validity test can be seen in the cross loading value (how much the correlation value is between the indicators that measure the variable). The cross loading value can be accepted if the cross loading value of each variable statement item to the variable itself is greater than the correlation value of the statement item to other variables (Ghozali, 2012).

2. Reliability Test

In general, reliability is defined as a series of tests to assess the reliability of statement items. Reliability tests are used to measure the consistency of measuring instruments in measuring a concept or to measure the consistency of respondents in answering statement items in questionnaires or research instruments. To measure the level of reliability of research variables in PLS, you can use the alpha coefficient value or Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability). The Cronbach's alpha value is recommended to be greater than 0.7 and the composite reliability is also recommended to be greater than 0.7. (Sekaran, 2014)

Structural Model (Inner Model)

This test is conducted to determine the relationship between exogenous and endogenous constructs that have become hypotheses in this study (Hair et al., 2017). To produce inner model test values, the steps in SmartPLS are carried out using the bootstrapping method. The structural model is evaluated using R-square for the dependent variable, the Stone-Geisser Q-square test for predictive elevation and the t-test and significance of the structural path parameter coefficients with the following explanation:

1. Coefficient of Determination / R Square (R²)
2. Predictive Relevance (Q²)
3. t-Statistic
4. Path Coefficient
5. Fit Model

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Measurement model testing (outer model) is used to determine the specifications of the relationship between latent variables and their manifest variables, this testing includes convergent validity, discriminant validity and reliability.

1. Convergent Validity

Convergent validity of the measurement model with reflective indicators can be seen from the correlation between item/indicator scores and construct scores. Individual indicators are considered reliable if they have a correlation value above 0.70. However, in the scale development stage of research, loadings of 0.50 to 0.60 are still acceptable. Based on the results for outer loading, it shows that there are indicators that have loadings below 0.60 and are not significant. The structural model in this study is shown in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1. Outer Model
Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Work Discipline (X2)	Work Environment (X1)	Work Performance (Y)	Job Promotion (Z)
X1.1		0.940		
X1.2		0.925		
X1.3		0.913		
X1.4		0.826		
X2.1	0.773			
X2.2	0.767			
X2.3	0.855			
X2.4	0.881			
X2.5	0.806			
Y.1			0.934	
Y.2			0.875	
Y.4			0.930	
Y.5			0.883	
Z.1				0.807
Z.3				0.874
Z.4				0.872
Z.5				0.733
Z.6				0.819
Z.7				0.749
Z.8				0.725
Z.9				0.742

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Table 1 shows that the assessment of the loading factor results > 0.07 means that all indicators are valid after indicators Y.3 and Z.2 are deleted because they are invalid so that the number of indicators is now 21 indicators after the loading factor is valid, then further research can be carried out. This means that all indicators are valid indicators to measure the construct.

The regression equation in this study consists of 2 substructures.

Substructure equation 1 is as follows:

$$Z = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e_1$$

$$Z = 0.918X_1 + 0.017X_2 + e_1$$

Substructure Equation 2

$$Y = b_3X_1 + b_4X_2 + b_5Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.263X_1 + 0.462X_2 - 0.060Z + e_2$$

2. Discriminant Validity

In this section, the results of the discriminant validity test will be described. The discriminant validity test uses the cross loading value. An indicator is declared to meet discriminant validity if the cross loading value of the indicator on its variable is the largest compared to other variables. The following are the cross loading values of each indicator:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Work Discipline (X2)	Work Environment (X1)	Work Performance (Y)	Job Promotion (Z)
X1.1	0.885	0.940	0.599	0.893
X1.2	0.805	0.929	0.549	0.881
X1.3	0.797	0.913	0.655	0.806
X1.4	0.648	0.826	0.377	0.786
X2.1	0.773	0.658	0.599	0.552
X2.2	0.767	0.674	0.402	0.639
X2.3	0.855	0.772	0.522	0.756
X2.4	0.881	0.749	0.528	0.717
X2.5	0.806	0.708	0.569	0.667
Y.1	0.619	0.588	0.934	0.561
Y.2	0.405	0.439	0.875	0.412
Y.4	0.641	0.611	0.930	0.547
Y.5	0.611	0.539	0.883	0.492
Z.1	0.673	0.803	0.529	0.807
Z.3	0.731	0.821	0.474	0.874
Z.4	0.775	0.890	0.549	0.872
Z.5	0.592	0.680	0.492	0.733
Z.6	0.808	0.767	0.455	0.819
Z.7	0.462	0.617	0.244	0.749
Z.8	0.562	0.622	0.453	0.725
Z.9	0.482	0.636	0.280	0.742

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 2 above, the indicators in the research variables have a greater cross loading value compared to the cross loading value on other variables. The cross loading value for the Work Discipline variable is greater than other variables, the cross loading value for the Work Environment variable is greater than other variables, the cross loading value for the Work Performance variable is greater than the variable, the cross loading value for the Job Promotion variable is greater than other variables, meaning that the cross loading value is valid in a discriminatory manner.

3. Composite reliability

The next test is the composite reliability of the indicator block that measures the construct. A construct is said to be reliable if the composite reliability value is above 0.60 and the cronbachs alpha value of the indicator block that measures the construct. A construct is said to be reliable if the cronbachs alpha value is above 0.7. The following is a table of loading values for the research variable constructs generated from running the Smart PLS program in the following table:

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Work Discipline (X2)	0.875	0.909	0.668
Work Environment (X1)	0.924	0.946	0.816
Work Performance (Y)	0.928	0.948	0.820
Job Promotion (Z)	0.915	0.931	0.628

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Table 3 shows that the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of each variable, namely Work Discipline, Work Environment, Work Performance, Job Promotion has a construct > 0.50, meaning all constructs are reliable. Thus, it can be stated that each variable has high discriminant validity. Meanwhile, it can be seen in the table above that the composite reliability value of each variable shows a construct value > 0.60. These results indicate that each variable has met the composite reliability so that it can be concluded that all variables have a high level of reliability.

Furthermore, in the table above, the Cronbach's alpha of each variable shows a construct value of > 0.70. Thus, these results indicate that each research variable has met the requirements for the Cronbach's alpha value, so it can be concluded that all variables have a high level of reliability. So it can be concluded that the indicators used in this study have high discriminant validity in compiling their respective variables.

Inner Model Analysis

The stages of analysis carried out in the evaluation of the structural model are seen from several indicators, namely:

1. Coefficient of Determination (R2)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Work Performance (Y)	0.423	0.397
Job Promotion (Z)	0.870	0.866

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Table 4 above shows that the R Square value for the Job Performance variable is 0.423. This finding explains that the percentage of Job Performance is 42.3%. This means that the variables Work Discipline, Work Environment, and Job Promotion affect Job Performance by 42.3% and the remaining 57.7% is influenced by other variables. Meanwhile, the R Square value for the Job Promotion variable is 0.870. This finding explains that the percentage of Job Promotion is 87.0%.

2. Goodness of Fit (GoF) Assessment

The goodness of fit model test can be seen from the NFI value ≥ 0.697 which is stated as fit. Based on the data processing that has been done using the SmartPLS 3.3 program, the Model Fit value is obtained as follows:

Table 5. Fit Model

	Saturated Model	Estimation Model
SRMR	0.187	0.187
d_ ULS	1,758	1,758
d_ G	1,789	1,789
Chi-Square	546,192	546,192
NFI	0.882	0.882

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

The results of the goodness of fit test of the PLS model in table 6. below show that the NFI value of 0.882 means FIT. Thus, from these results it can be concluded that the model in this study has a high goodness of fit and is suitable for testing the research hypothesis.

3. Hypothesis Testing

After assessing the inner model, the next step is to evaluate the relationship between latent constructs as hypothesized in this study. Hypothesis testing in this study was conducted by looking at the T-Statistics and P-Values. The hypothesis is accepted if the T-Statistics value is > 1.96 and P-Values < 0.05 . The following are the results of the Path Coefficients of direct influence:

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Work Discipline (X2) -> Work Achievement (Y)	0.462	2,483	0.013	Accepted
Work Discipline (X2) -> Job Promotion (Z)	0.017	0.209	0.835	Rejected
Work Environment (X1) -> Work Performance (Y)	0.263	0.757	0.449	Rejected

Work Environment (X1) -> Job Promotion (Z)	0.918	12,289	0,000	Accepted
Position Promotion (Z) -> Job Performance (Y)	-0.060	0.200	0.841	Rejected

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Based on table 6 above, there is a direct influence of 5 hypotheses and will be explained for Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance with an original sample value of 0.462 P values $0.013 < 0.05$. Work Discipline has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Promotion with an original sample value of 0.017 P values $0.835 > 0.05$. Work Environment has a positive and insignificant effect on Work Performance with a value of 0.263 and P values $0.449 > 0.05$. Work Environment has a positive and significant effect on Job Promotion with a value of $0.918 > 0.05$. Job Promotion has a negative and insignificant effect on Job Performance with an Original sample value of -0.060 and P values $0.841 > 0.05$.

Table 7. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Work Discipline (X2) -> Position Promotion (Z) -> Work Achievement (Y)	-0.001	0.037	0.971	Rejected
Work Environment (X1) -> Position Promotion (Z) -> Work Performance (Y)	-0.055	0.199	0.842	Rejected

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

The results of table 7 above show that Work Discipline has an indirect effect on Work Performance through Job Promotion, which is negative and not significant with the original sample value of -0.001 P values $0.971 > 0.05$. Work Environment has an indirect effect on Work Performance through Job Promotion, which is negative and not significant with the original sample value of -0.055 P values $0.842 > 0.05$

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Work Discipline has a positive and significant influence on Work Performance in Medan Region II Airport Authority Office
2. Work Discipline has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Promotion in Medan Region II Airport Authority Office
3. Work environment has a positive and insignificant effect on work performance in Medan Region II Airport Authority Office
4. Work Environment has a positive and significant influence on Job Promotion in Medan Region II Airport Authority Office
5. Job Promotion has a negative but insignificant effect on Work Performance in Medan Region II Airport Authority Office
6. Work Discipline has no effect on Work Performance through Position Promotion in Medan Region II Airport Authority Office
7. The work environment has no effect on work performance through promotion in Medan Region II Airport Authority Office

Suggestion

1. Organizations must create a comfortable, safe and good working environment for employees.
2. Organizations must be able to discipline employees to improve employee performance.
3. Organizations must promote for promotion by looking at the skills, quality and work experience of employees.
4. Organizations must seek to recruit employees who have achievements for the advancement of the organization.

REFERENCES

- Ghozali, I. Latan, H. 2015. Partial Least Square : Konsep, Teknik dan Aplikasi Smart PLS 2.0 M3. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Ghozali, Imam. (2014). Structural Equation Modeling Metode Alternatif dengan Partial Least Square (PLS) Edisi 4. Universitas Diponegoro, Semarang.
- Hair, J. F. et. al. 2017. A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). SAGE Publications, Los Angeles.
- Hasibuan, Malayu. 2016. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Jakarta: Penerbit Bumi Aksara.
- Kurniawan, B. 2016. Analisis Implementasi Manajemen Pelatihan Kesiapan Petugas Tanggap Darurat Dalam Menghadapi Bencana Gempa Bumi Pada Gedung Instalasi Rawat Inap I (Irna I) Di RSUP Dr. Sardjito Yogyakarta. Jurnal Kesehatan Masyarakat (e-Journal) Volume 4, Nomor 4, Oktober 2016 (ISSN: 2356-3346).
- Mangkunegara, 2016, Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan, Remaja Rosdakarya, Bandung.
- Riduwan. 2014. Belajar Mudah Penelitian untuk Guru, Karyawan, dan Peneliti Pemula. Bandung: Alfabeta
- Rivai, Veithzal 2014. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Untuk Perusahaan. Jakarta : Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Sedarmayanti.2015. Sumber Daya Manusia dan Produktivitas Kerja. Bandung: CV Mandar Maju.
- Sekaran, Uma. 2014. Metodologi Penelitian Untuk Bisnis (Research Methods for Business) Buku 1 Edisi 4. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- Siagian. 2014. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Jakarta : Bumi Aksara.
- Sugiyono. 2017. Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D. Bandung : Alfabeta, CV.
- Sutrisno, Edy. 2016. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Cetakan Kedelapan. Jakarta: Prenadamedia Group.

Performance Optimization

Ahmad Lufthi Al Riza Siregar¹, Muhammad Isa Indrawan²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: lufthi22@gmail.com

Abstract

Companies really need competent and quality human resources, especially in this era of globalization. All business organizations must be ready to adapt and strengthen themselves in order to compete so that they are able to answer all challenges in the future. Human resources in this case are employees who always play an active and dominant role in every organizational activity because humans are planners, actors and determinants of the realization of goals. This research aims to examine the influence of rewards and competencies on employee performance with punishment as an intervening variable at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province. The results of this research are as follows: Competency has a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.127 and ap value of 0.210. Competence has a positive and significant effect on Punishment with an original sample value of 0.433 and ap value of 0.000. Punishment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.601 and ap value of 0.002. Rewards have a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.158 and ap value of 0.216. Rewards have a positive and significant effect on Punishment with an original sample value of 0.541 and ap value of 0.000. Competence has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through punishment with an original sample value of 0.260 and ap value of 0.006. Rewards have a positive and significant effect on employee performance through punishment with an original sample value of 0.325 and ap value of 0.006.

Keywords: Reward, Competency, Punishment, Employee Performance

INTRODUCTION

Human resources are one of the important factors in a company to achieve its goals and objectives, because human resources are one of the determining factors of whether or not a company is successful in achieving its goals. Companies really need competent and qualified human resources, especially in this era of globalization. Rewards are one of the important factors used to encourage employees to improve the quality and quantity of work. Rewards can be interpreted as a form of appreciation for employees or companies that have succeeded in doing a good job and achieving, so that they can provide positive motivation to do a good job (Fitri, Ludigdo, Ali, 2014). Competence refers to a combination of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behaviors that enable a person to succeed in a particular job or task. This includes not only what a person knows, but also their ability to apply that knowledge and skills effectively in the context of the job or relevant situation. Competencies are often identified and evaluated in the context of human resource management, recruitment, performance appraisal, career development, and training. Having a clear understanding of the competencies required to succeed in a particular role can help individuals and organizations develop strategies to achieve their goals. Rewards and punishments are factors that influence employee performance. Rewards and punishments are two opposite words, but they are related. Unfair rewards and punishments will cause social jealousy to arise among employees, which will trigger negative working relationships and of course have an impact on employee performance. The company realizes that in order to maintain and improve employee performance, the company must immediately improve its

professional management, one way is to implement rewards and punishments. Employee performance is the result of work achieved by someone in carrying out the tasks assigned to him to achieve work targets. Employees can work well if they have high performance so that they can produce good work. Employee performance is one of the determining factors for the success of a company or organization in achieving its goals. To achieve company goals, employees are needed who meet the requirements in the company, and must also be able to carry out the tasks that have been determined by the company. The performance of an organization is largely determined by the quality of the performance of the employees working in it. Employee performance can be said to be good if the employee can carry out the tasks assigned to him/her to completion, because in general performance is assessed from what the employee has done and how the work results have been achieved during work.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Reward have a positive and significant effect on employee Punishment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
2. Does Competence have a positive and significant effect on employee Punishment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
3. Does Reward have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province?
4. Does Competence have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
5. Does Punishment have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
6. Does Reward Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Employee Performance through Punishment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
7. Does Competence have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Punishment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of Rewards on Punishment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
2. To determine and analyze the influence of Competence on Punishment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
3. To find out and analyze the influence of rewards on employee performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
4. To determine and analyze the influence of Competence on Employee Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
5. To find out and analyze the influence of Punishment on Employee Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
6. To determine the influence and analyze Rewards on Employee Performance through Punishment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province
7. To find out and analyze the influence of Competence on Employee Performance through Punishment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

Literature review

Employee performance

Understanding Employee Performance

According to Edison (2016), performance is the result of a process that refers to and is measured over a certain period of time based on previously established provisions or agreements. According to Mangkunegara (2017), performance is the result of work in terms of quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him.

Employee Performance Indicators

According to Mangkunegara (2017), the indicators of employee performance are as follows:

1. Quality of work. How well an employee does what he or she is supposed to do.
2. Quantity of Work. How long an employee works in one day. This quantity of work can be seen from the working speed of each employee.
3. Task Execution. How far employees are able to do their jobs accurately or without errors.
4. Responsibility. Awareness of the obligation to do one's work accurately or without error.

Rewards

Understanding Rewards

According to Busro (2018), Rewards are incentives or motivation to improve a person's performance, which are generally manifested in financial form (monetary incentives) such as providing incentives, allowances, bonuses and commissions.

The definition of Rewards according to Byars & Rue (2018) includes all types of rewards, both intrinsic and extrinsic, received as a result of work by the organization. The organization's Reward system is influenced by the selection of the type of Reward used by the organization.

Reward Indicator

According to Byars and Rue (2018) the reward indicators are as follows:

a. Intrinsic Reward

Intrinsic Reward is a positive value or employee satisfaction towards themselves for completing a task that is quite challenging for them. Intrinsic Reward is part of the job itself, such as responsibility, challenges, and feedback characteristics of the job. This award is not in the form of material or financial.

1. Achievement
2. Feeling of accomplishment
3. Informal recognition
4. Job Satisfaction
5. Personal Growth
6. Status

b. Extrinsic Reward

Extrinsic Rewards usually include direct compensation, indirect compensation and other benefits. These rewards are in the form of financial, material, or social from the environment. This award is an external award given to the performance that has been given by the worker.

1. *Formal recognition*

2. *Fringe Benefits (Allowance)*
3. *Incentive Incentive (Payments)*
4. *Work environment*
5. *Promotion*
6. *Social relationships*

Competence

Understanding Competence

According to Hutapea (2014) states that "competence is the ability and willingness to carry out a task with effective and efficient performance to achieve company goals. According to Wibowo (2017), competence is the ability to carry out or perform a job or task based on skills and knowledge and supported by the work attitude required by the job.

Competency Indicators

According to Wibowo (2017), the competency indicators are:

1. Knowledge The information possessed by a core employee carries out his duties and responsibilities according to his field, employee knowledge determines the success or failure of the implementation of the tasks given by the company, employees who have good knowledge can increase the efficiency of the company.
2. Ability/skills is an effort to carry out tasks given by the company to employees which are carried out well and optimally.
3. Employee behavioral attitudes Attitude is a pattern of behavior of an employee in carrying out duties and responsibilities in accordance with company regulations.

Punishment

Definition of Punishment

According to Mangkunegara (2016) punishment is a threat of punishment that aims to improve the performance of violating employees, maintain applicable regulations and provide lessons to violators. According to Rivai (2018) punishment is a tool used by leaders to communicate with employees so that they are willing to change a behavior and as an effort to increase awareness and willingness of someone to obey all company regulations and applicable social norms.

Punishment Indicator

According to Rivai (2018) the indicators of punishment. The indicators are:

1. Light punishment, with the following types:
 - a. Verbal warning to the employee concerned
 - b. Written warning
 - c. Written statement of dissatisfaction
2. Moderate punishment, with types:
 - a. Delay in salary increase
 - b. Salary deductions
 - c. Postponement of promotion
3. Severe punishment, with the following types:
 - a. Release from office
 - b. Dismissal/Termination of employment.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

- H1 *Rewards* has a positive and significant effect on employee punishment in Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province
- H2 Competence has a positive and significant effect on employee punishment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H3 *Reward* has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province
- H4 Competence has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province
- H5 *Punishment* has a positive effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province
- H6 *Rewards* has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Punishment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province
- H7 Competence has a positive effect on Employee Performance through Punishment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province

METHOD

Types of research

According to Sugiyono (2017) quantitative research methods can be interpreted as research methods based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations or samples, sampling techniques are generally carried out randomly, data collection uses research instruments, data analysis is quantitative/statistical, with the aim of testing the established hypothesis. This study uses quantitative research types.

Research Location and Research Time

The location of this research was conducted at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province, Jalan Balai Kota No. 4 Medan. The time of this research was conducted from September to October 2024/

Population

According to Sugiyono (2017), population is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn. The population of this study was 70 employees.

Sample

According to Sugiyono (2017) a sample is part of the number and 30 characteristics possessed by the population. The number of units in the sample is symbolized by the notation n . The sample used is all the population in the organization, namely 70 employees and the sampling technique used is a saturated sample.

Research Data Sources

Primary data according to Sugiyono (2017) is a data source that directly provides data to data collectors. Primary data in this study is a questionnaire distributed to respondents. The data source used in this study is a primary data source.

Data collection technique

According to Sugiyono (2017) a questionnaire is a data collection method carried out by giving a set of written questions or statements to respondents to be answered. This study uses and distributes questionnaires to respondents who are sampled as a data collection technique.

Data Analysis Techniques

The data analysis technique used in this study is the quantitative data analysis method. Data analysis in this study uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on Partial Least Square (PLS) using SmartPLS 3.3.3 software which is run on a computer.

Measurement Model (Outer Model)

The procedure in testing the measurement model consists of validity testing and reliability testing.

1. Validity Test

Validity testing is used to assess whether a questionnaire is valid or not. A questionnaire is said to be valid if the questionnaire questions are able to reveal something that is measured by the questionnaire. Validity testing is applied to all question items in each variable.

2. Reliability Test

In general, reliability is defined as a series of tests to assess the reliability of statement items. Reliability tests are used to measure the consistency of measuring instruments in measuring a concept or to measure the consistency of respondents in answering statement items in questionnaires or research instruments. To measure the level of reliability of research variables in PLS, you can use the alpha coefficient value or Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability). The Cronbach's alpha value is recommended to be greater than 0.7 and the composite reliability is also recommended to be greater than 0.7. (Sekaran, 2014)

Structural Model (Inner Model)

This test is conducted to determine the relationship between exogenous and endogenous constructs that have become hypotheses in this study (Hair et al., 2017). To produce inner model test values, the steps in SmartPLS are carried out using the bootstrapping method. The structural model is evaluated using R-square for the dependent variable, the Stone-Geisser Q-square test for predictive elevation and the t-test and significance of the structural path parameter coefficients with the following explanation:

1. Coefficient of Determination / R Square (R^2)

In assessing the model with PLS, it begins by looking at the R-square for each dependent latent variable. The interpretation is the same as the interpretation in regression. Changes in the R-square value can be used to assess the influence of certain independent latent variables on the dependent latent variable whether it has a substantive influence (Ghozali, 2012). The R² value is generally between 0 and 1.

2. Predictive Relevance (Q²)

This test is used to measure how well the observation value is generated by the model and also its parameter estimates. If the Q² value is greater than 0, it indicates that the model has predictive relevance, which means it has good observation value, while if the value is less than 0, it indicates that the model does not have predictive relevance (Ghozali, 2014).

3. t-Statistic

at this stage is used for hypothesis testing, namely to determine the significance of the relationship between variables in the study using the bootstrapping method. In the full model Structural Equation Modeling in addition to confirming the theory, it also explains whether or not there is a relationship between latent variables (Ghozali, 2012). The hypothesis is said to be accepted if the t statistic value is greater than the t table. According to (Latan and Ghozali, 2012) the criteria for the t table value is 1.96 with a significance level of 5%

4. Path Coefficient

This test is used to determine the direction of the relationship between variables (positive/negative). If the value is 0 to 1, then the direction of the relationship between variables is stated as positive. While if the value is 0 to -1, then the direction of the relationship between variables is stated as negative.

5. Fit Model

This test is used to determine the level of suitability (fit) of the research model with the ideal model for this study, by looking at the NFI value in the program. If the value is closer to 1, then it is better (good fit).

Path Analysis

This study uses the Path Analysis research model, Path analysis is part of the regression model that can be used to analyze the causal relationship between one variable and another. According to Sugiyono (2017) path analysis is part of the regression model that can be used to analyze the causal relationship between one variable and another. Path analysis is used by using correlation, regression and paths so that it can be known to arrive at the intervening variable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Measurement model testing (outer model) is used to determine the relationship between latent variables and observation variables. This test consists of convergent validity, discriminant validity, and reliability.

Convergent Validity

Convergent validity is used to assess the validity of each indicator against the underlying latent variable. Validity results can be seen in the outer loading table in SmartPLS

software. The external loading table contains numbers or values that indicate the similarity between the indicator and the construct variable. An indicator is said to be reliable if it has a value of more than 0.7 in explaining the construct variable. An illustration of the structural model is depicted in the following figure for this study.

Figure 2. Outer Model
Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

The Smart PLS output for loading factors gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings

In this research there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Z = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e_1$$

$$Z = 0.541X_1 + 0.433 X_2 + e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_3X_1 + b_4X_2 + b_5Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.158 X_1 + 0.127 X_2 + 0.601Z + e_2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Employee Performance (Y)	Competence (X2)	Punishment (Z)	Reward (X1)
X1.1				0.875
X1.10				0.797
X1.11				0.824
X1.12				0.741
X1.13				0.785
X1.2				0.812
X1.3				0.781
X1.4				0.834
X1.5				0.785
X1.6				0.800
X1.7				0.822

X1.8				0.849
X1.9				0.819
X2.1		0.946		
X2.2		0.934		
X2.3		0.842		
Y.1	0.782			
Y.2	0.820			
Y.3	0.820			
Y.4	0.810			
Z.1			0.846	
Z.2			0.822	
Z.3			0.791	
Z.4			0.877	
Z.5			0.886	
Z.6			0.834	
Z.7			0.931	
Z.8			0.903	

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Table 1 clearly shows that all outer loading indicators have values above 0.7 so that each indicator is considered valid for conducting further research at this stage.

Discriminant Validity

Analyzing the cross loading table can help determine discriminant validity. This result is used to assess discriminant validity at the indicator level, where the indicator should have a higher correlation with the latent variable compared to other latent variables (outside the block). To better understand it, see the table provided below:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Employee Performance (Y)	Competence (X2)	Punishment (Z)	Reward (X1)
X1.1	0.785	0.863	0.821	0.875
X1.10	0.609	0.679	0.773	0.797
X1.11	0.680	0.749	0.786	0.824
X1.12	0.651	0.723	0.654	0.741
X1.13	0.688	0.808	0.762	0.785
X1.2	0.693	0.828	0.787	0.812
X1.3	0.692	0.734	0.750	0.781
X1.4	0.753	0.736	0.776	0.834
X1.5	0.558	0.650	0.675	0.785
X1.6	0.673	0.714	0.772	0.800
X1.7	0.745	0.800	0.804	0.822
X1.8	0.718	0.787	0.832	0.849

X1.9	0.583	0.679	0.710	0.819
X2.1	0.811	0.946	0.871	0.865
X2.2	0.828	0.934	0.893	0.923
X2.3	0.621	0.842	0.780	0.730
Y.1	0.782	0.822	0.826	0.794
Y.2	0.820	0.561	0.655	0.622
Y.3	0.820	0.558	0.571	0.548
Y.4	0.810	0.696	0.698	0.703
Z.1	0.752	0.882	0.846	0.804
Z.2	0.671	0.829	0.822	0.797
Z.3	0.765	0.723	0.791	0.742
Z.4	0.821	0.789	0.877	0.825
Z.5	0.717	0.795	0.886	0.842
Z.6	0.698	0.717	0.834	0.777
Z.7	0.797	0.868	0.931	0.878
Z.8	0.761	0.839	0.903	0.832

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Based on table 2, there is a cross loading value for each indicator per variable that shows a value that is greater than the latent value on other variables in its loading factor value, the loading factor value on the reward variable has a value that is greater than the loading factor value of other latent variables, there is a loading factor value on the competency variable that has a value that is greater than the loading factor value on other latent variables, there is a loading factor value on the punishment variable that has a value greater than the loading factor on other latent factors, there is a loading factor value on the employee performance variable that is greater than the loading factor on other latent variables, so this study is discriminantly valid.

Composite reliability

The upcoming assessment calculates the reliability value by considering the composite reliability of each component. A construct is said to be reliable if the composite reliability value is equal to or exceeds 0.6. If the Cronbach's alpha value exceeds 0.7, then all constructs in the block are considered reliable in each variable construct. Furthermore, if the AVE value is higher than 0.7, then each variable construct is considered valid. The following table presents the loading values of the research variable constructs obtained from the use of Smart PLS software.

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Employee Performance (Y)	0.825	0.883	0.653
Competence (X2)	0.893	0.934	0.825
Punishment (Z)	0.950	0.959	0.744
Reward (X1)	0.956	0.961	0.657

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Based on table 3, all variables have Cronbach alpha values above 0.7 which indicates the reliability of the study. In addition, all variables have composite reliability values above 0.6. The reliability of each variable must be shown and the AVE value must be above 0.7 to ensure that the study is considered valid according to the SVE criteria, meaning that all variables have valid values in all sectors.

Inner Model Analysis

Inner model assessment is conducted to verify the stability and accuracy of the structural model created. Several indicators are used in the evaluation of the structural model for the analysis stage.

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

The results of data analysis carried out using SmartPLS 3.0 software show the R Square value as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Employee Performance (Y)	0.761	0.750
Punishment (Z)	0.915	0.913

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

There is an R square value in table 4 and the explanation is as follows: The R square value of the employee performance variable is 0.761 if changed to a percentage of 76.1%, meaning that the influence of reward, competence and punishment on employee performance is 0.761 or 76.1% and the rest is on other variables, the R square punishment value is 0.915 if changed to 91.5%, meaning that the influence of reward and competence is 0.915 or 91.5% and the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After reviewing the internal model, the next step is to evaluate the relationship between latent constructs according to the hypothesis in this study. Hypothesis analysis in this study uses T-Statistics and P-Values. The hypothesis is considered accepted if the T-Statistics value is > 1.96 and P-Values is < 0.05. This is the output of Path Coefficients from direct influence:

Table 5. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Competence (X2) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.127	0.808	0.210	Rejected
Competence (X2) -> Punishment (Z)	0.433	4,686	0,000	Accepted
Punishment (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.601	2,941	0.002	Accepted
Reward (X1) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.158	0.787	0.216	Rejected
Reward (X1) -> Punishment (Z)	0.541	6,041	0,000	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 5 above, there are the results of the direct influence on the hypothesis, so the explanation is as follows:

1. Competence has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.127 and p values of 0.210. This means that in this study, competence has an effect but is not significant so that the hypothesis is rejected.
2. Competence has a positive and significant effect on Punishment with an original sample value of 0.433 and p values of 0.000. This means that the higher the competence, the lower the punishment, conversely, the lower the competence, the higher the punishment.
3. Punishment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.601 and p values of 0.002. This means that if punishment increases, employee performance will increase, conversely if punishment decreases, employee performance will decrease.
4. Rewards have a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.158 and p values of 0.216. This means that the rewards given do not necessarily increase employee performance, but in this study the hypothesis was rejected because it did not have a significant effect.
5. Reward has a positive and significant effect on Punishment with an original sample value of 0.541 and p values of 0.000. This means that increasing reward will decrease punishment and if reward decreases then punishment will increase.

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Competence (X2) -> Punishment (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.260	2,532	0.006	Accepted
Reward (X1) -> Punishment (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.325	2,494	0.006	Accepted

In table 6 there are two indirect hypotheses and they will be explained as follows:

1. Competence has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Punishment with an original sample value of 0.260 and p values of 0.006. This means that punishment is an intervening variable and is able to influence employee competence and performance indirectly and significantly with the presence of punishment strengthening the influence of competence on employee performance.
2. Reward has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Punishment with an original sample value of 0.325 and p values of 0.006. This means that punishment is an intervening variable because it is able to influence rewards and employee performance indirectly, thereby increasing the relationship between rewards and employee performance.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Competence has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.127 and p values of 0.210.
2. Competence has a positive and significant effect on Punishment with an original sample value of 0.433 and p values of 0.000.
3. Punishment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.601 and p values of 0.002.

4. Rewards have a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.158 and p values of 0.216.
5. Reward has a positive and significant effect on Punishment with an original sample value of 0.541 and p values of 0.000.
6. Competence has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Punishment with an original sample value of 0.260 and p values of 0.006.
7. Rewards have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Punishment with an original sample value of 0.325 and p values of 0.006.

Suggestion

1. For organizations, this research can be used as criticism and suggestions to build a better organization.
2. Organizations must improve the punishment and reward system for employees.
3. Organizations must improve employee performance by increasing employee competencies and rewarding them when they succeed.
4. It is hoped that this research can be used as reference material for new researchers with new titles.
5. It is hoped that this research can help new researchers to conduct research.

REFERENCES

- Busro, M. (2018). *Teori-Teori Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: Prenadamedia Group.
- Byars, Lloyd I. dan Leslie W. Rue. (2018). *Human Resource Management*. 8th edition. McGraw-Hill.
- Edison, Emron., dkk. 2016 *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Alfabeta. Bandung
- Fitri, Ludigdo, Ali (2014) 'Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan, Komitmen, Organisasi, Kualitas Sumber Daya, Reward, Dan Punishment Terhadap Anggaran Berbasis Kinerja (Studi Empirik Pada Pemerintah Kabupaten Lombok Barat)', *Jurnal Dinamika Akuntansi*, 5(2), pp. 157–171. doi: 10.15294/jda.v5i2.2996.
- Ghozali, Imam. 2014. *Structural Equation Modeling, Metode Alternatif dengan Partial Least Square (PLS)*. Edisi 4. Semarang : Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Hair, J. F. et. al. 2017. *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)*. SAGE Publications, Los Angeles
- Hutapea dan Nurianna Thoha. 2014. *Kompetensi Plus: Teori, Desain, Kasus dan Penerapan untuk HR dan Organisasi yang Dinamis*. Jakarta: PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Mangkunegara. 2016. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan*. Bandung : PT. Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Mangkunegara. 2017. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan*, Bandung : Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Rivai, V. (2018). *Manajemen sumber daya manusia untuk perusahaan: dari teori dan praktik*. Jakarta: Grafindo Persada.
- Sekaran, Uma. 2014. *Metodologi Penelitian Untuk Bisnis (Research Methods for Business) Buku 1 Edisi 4*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.

- Sugiyono, (2017). Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D. Bandung: CV. Alfabeta.
- Wibowo. (2017). Manajemen Kinerja. Edisi Kelima. Depok: PT. Raja Grafindo Persada.

Determinants of Organizational Commitment

Andi Fajar Al Hadi¹, Muhammad Isa Indrawan²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: sapi.jantan90@gmail.com

Abstract

This research aims to examine the influence of the work environment and organizational culture on organizational commitment, mediated by work stress at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province. Bank Indonesia is an independent state institution tasked with considering economic policy in Indonesia. Apart from these functions, Bank Indonesia has a scope of internal work which is under the management of the Internal Management sector. One of the sections under Bank Indonesia's internal division is the Human Resources (HR) section. Bank Indonesia HR has several tasks in managing employees, one of which is processing employee health data. The results of this research are as follows: Organizational Culture has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.129 and an ap value of 0.205. Organizational Culture has a negative and significant effect on Job Stress with a sample value of -0.498 and ap value of 0.000. Work Environment has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.483 and ap value of 0.002. Work Environment has a negative and significant effect on Work Stress with an original sample value of -0.476 and ap value of 0.000. Job Stress has a negative and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of -0.107 and ap value of 0.308. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Work Stress indirectly with an original sample value of 0.053 and ap value of 0.315. Work Environment has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment through Job Stress with an original sample value of 0.051 and ap value of 0.306.

Keywords: Work Environment, Organizational Culture, Work Stress, Organizational Commitment

INTRODUCTION

Human resources are the determining factor and driving force that will greatly determine the success or failure of an organization, company, or agency in achieving its goals. Human Resources (HR) have a very important role in an organization, both private and government agencies. HR is one of the determinants of an organization in achieving its goals. The work environment is the environment where employees do their work on a daily basis. The work environment can affect the level of employee comfort so that a comfortable work environment is needed by employees to be able to work optimally and productively. A good work environment can increase employee productivity, creativity, job satisfaction, and welfare, while a non-conductive work environment can result in stress, tension, and decreased performance. Organizational culture refers to a series of norms, values, beliefs, behaviors, and practices that are adopted and carried out by individuals in an organization. A strong and ingrained organizational culture will be able to provide a significant contribution to members of the organization in terms of a clear and straightforward understanding of a problem being solved. Culture has a significant influence on the attitudes and behavior of members of the organization. There is a lot of evidence that shows that the success of an organization is due to its strong culture that makes the organization more confident and ultimately more effective. Job stress is a condition in which a person feels pressured or anxious due to demands, burdens, or situations that occur in the workplace. Job stress can be caused by various factors, including deadline pressure, high performance demands,

interpersonal conflict, job uncertainty, or lack of support from superiors or coworkers. The impact of job stress can vary, from physical and mental health disorders to decreased productivity and job satisfaction. Therefore, it is important for individuals and organizations to identify and manage job stress properly. Organizational commitment is an interesting phenomenon because of the importance of a person's commitment to the company where the individual works or their organization, therefore many researchers want to research organizational commitment. Organizational commitment is a feeling of trust in the values contained in an organization, the involvement of individuals for the interests of their organization with full effort, and loyalty to the organization (wanting to be a permanent member of the organization) which is a statement from an employee to their organization. High organizational commitment from employees will encourage employees to be responsible and provide more energy in supporting the success and welfare of the company where they work (Dewi, 2015).

Formulation of the problem

1. Does the work environment have a positive and significant effect on work stress at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
2. Does Organizational Culture Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Work Stress at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
3. Does the Work Environment have a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
4. Does Organizational Culture have a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
5. Does Job Stress have a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
6. Does the Work Environment have a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Work Stress at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
7. Does Organizational Culture have a positive and significant effect on Commitment through Organizational Work Stress at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of the Work Environment on Work Stress at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
2. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Culture on Work Stress at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
3. To determine and analyze the influence of the Work Environment on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
4. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Culture on Organizational Commitment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
5. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Stress on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
6. To determine and analyze the influence of the Work Environment on Organizational Commitment through Work Stress at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

7. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Culture on Organizational Commitment through Work Stress at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational Commitment

Understanding Organizational Commitment

According to Allen and Meyer (2016), organizational commitment is an attitude that reflects employee loyalty to the organization and an ongoing process in which members of the organization express their concern for the organization and its continued success and progress. According to Robbin and Judge (2015), organizational commitment is a condition in which an employee sides with a particular organization and its goals and desires to maintain membership in the organization.

Organizational Commitment Indicators

According to Robbin and Judge (2015), organizational commitment has three dimensions, namely:

1. Affective commitment, occurs when employees want to be part of the organization because of an emotional or psychological attachment to the organization and belief in its values.
 - a. Desire to have a career in the organization
 - b. Sense of trust in the organization
 - c. Devotion to the organization
2. Continuance Commitment, the perceived economic value of remaining in an organization compared to leaving the organization.
 - a. Employee love for the organization
 - b. The desire to stay with one's job
 - c. Willing to sacrifice personal interests
 - d. Employee interest in work
 - e. Not comfortable leaving current job
3. Normative commitment, the obligation to remain in the organization for moral or ethical reasons.
 - a. Loyalty to the organization
 - b. Happiness at work
 - c. Pride in working for an organization

Work environment

Understanding the Work Environment

According to Afandi (2018), the work environment is something that exists in the environment of workers that can influence them in carrying out their duties such as temperature, humidity, ventilation, lighting, cleanliness of the workplace, and the adequacy of work equipment. According to Sukanto and Indryo (2018), the work environment is everything that exists around workers that can influence their work, including lighting arrangements, noise control, workplace cleanliness arrangements and workplace security arrangements.

Work Environment Indicators

Work environment indicators according to Afandi (2018) are as follows:

1. Lighting Sufficient lighting that is emitted appropriately will increase the work efficiency of employees, because they can work faster, make fewer mistakes and their eyes will not get tired as quickly.
2. Color is one of the important factors to increase the efficiency of employee work, especially color will affect their mental state by using the right color on the walls of the room and other tools, the joy and calmness of the employees' work will be maintained.
3. Air Regarding the air factor, what is most often affected is the air temperature and the amount of water vapor in the air.
4. Sound To overcome the occurrence of noise, it is necessary to place tools that have loud sounds, such as typewriters, telephones, motorbike parking, etc. in a special room, so as not to disturb other workers in carrying out their duties.

Organizational culture

Understanding Organizational Culture

Organizational culture is a habit that has been going on for a long time and is used and applied in work activities as a driving force to improve the quality of work of employees and company managers (Edison, 2016).

According to Fahmi (2017), organizational culture is the result of the process of merging the cultural styles and behaviors of each individual that were previously brought into new norms and philosophies, which have energy and group pride in facing certain things and goals."

Organizational Culture Indicators

According to Edison (2016) the indicators of organizational culture are as follows:

1. Self-awareness Members of the organization consciously work to gain satisfaction from their work, develop themselves, obey the rules, and offer quality products and high services.
2. Aggressiveness Organization members set challenging but realistic goals. They establish work plans and strategies to achieve these goals and pursue them enthusiastically.
3. Personality Members are respectful, friendly, open and sensitive to group satisfaction and pay close attention to aspects of customer satisfaction, both internal and external customers.
4. The performance of organizational members has creative values, meets quantity, quality and efficiency.
5. Team orientation Members of the organization cooperate well and carry out effective communication and coordination with the active involvement of members, which in turn results in high levels of satisfaction and shared commitment.

Job Stress

Understanding Job Stress

According to (Rivai, 2018) Job stress is a condition of tension that creates a physical and psychological imbalance that affects emotions, thought processes, and conditions of an employee. According to Afandi (2018) Job stress is a condition that arises due to the interaction between individuals and their work, where there is a mismatch in characteristics and unclear changes that occur in the company.

Job Stress Indicators

According to Afandi (2018) indicators of work stress are:

1. Job Demands Are factors associated with a person's job, such as working conditions, physical layout of the work.
2. Role Demands Relate to the pressures placed on a person as a function of the particular role played in an organization.
3. Interpersonal Demands Are pressures created by other employees.
4. Organizational Structure The description of the agency is characterized by an unclear organizational structure, lack of clarity regarding positions, roles, authority and responsibilities.
5. Organizational Leadership Is providing a management style to the organization. Some parties in it can create an organizational climate that involves tension, fear and anxiety.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

- H1 The work environment has a positive and significant effect on work stress at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H2 Organizational Culture has a positive and significant influence on Work Stress at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H3 The work environment has a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H4 Organizational Culture Influences Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H5 Work Stress has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H6 Work Environment has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Work Stress at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H7 Organizational Culture has a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment through Work Stress at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

METHOD

Types of research

Quantitative methods often collect data in the form of numbers or statistics, and analyze them using statistical techniques to produce strong generalizations about the population studied. According to Sugiyono (2016), quantitative research is research that obtains data in the form of numbers or qualitative data that is expressed in numbers.

Research Location and Research Time

This research was conducted at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra, this research was conducted from September to October 2024. This research was conducted on Jalan Balai Kota No. 4 Medan.

Population

The population of this study was 70 employees of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra. "Population" is a term used to refer to the total number of individuals in a particular group or area at a particular time. This term is often used in various contexts, such as in demography, ecology, or economics. Population can refer to the human population in a country, the population of animal species in a habitat, or the population of products in a particular market, depending on the context. According to Sugiyono (2016), population is a generalization area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics that are determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn.

Sample

The sample used for this study was the entire population in the Bank Indonesia office, which was 70 employees. According to Sugiyono (2016), a sample is a portion of the number and characteristics of the population. The sampling technique used is the saturated sampling technique. Samples are used to represent the characteristics or properties of the population. Sampling is often done in scientific research, surveys, statistics, and other fields to generalize or analyze a larger population.

Research Data Sources

The research data sources used are primary data sources. Primary data sources refer to sources of information collected directly from the original source. This can be data collected by researchers in a study, survey, experiment, or direct observation. Primary data sources tend to be more accurate and can be adjusted to the needs of a particular research or analysis. According to Sugiyono (2016) Primary sources are data that directly provide data to data collectors.

Data collection technique

The data collection technique used by researchers is to distribute questionnaires to respondents and will be filled in by the respondents. According to Sugiyono (2016), a questionnaire is a data collection technique by giving a set of written questions or statements to respondents to answer.

Data Analysis Techniques

Data processing in this study used smartPLS SEM (Partial Least Square – Structural Equation Modeling) Software. PLS is able to explain the relationship between variables and is able to perform 29 analyzes in one test. The purpose of PLS is to help researchers confirm

theories and to explain whether or not there is a relationship between latent variables. According to Imam Ghozali (2016) the PLS method is able to describe latent variables (not directly measurable) and is measured using indicators. The author uses Partial Least Square because this study is a latent variable that can be measured based on its indicators so that the author can analyze it with clear and detailed calculations.

Outer Model Analysis

Evaluation of the measurement model or outer model is carried out to assess the validity or reliability of the model. The outer model with reflective indicators is evaluated through the convergent and discriminant validity of the latent construct forming indicators and composite reliability and cronbach alpha for the indicator block (Ghozali, 2015). The tests carried out on the outer model are:

1. Convergent Validity
2. Discriminant Validity
3. Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
4. Composite Reliability
5. Cronbach's Alpha

Inner model analysis

Inner model analysis is also known as structural model analysis, which aims to predict the relationship between latent variables (Ghozali, 2015). Inner model evaluation can be seen from several indicators including: Inner model analysis is known as the structural analysis method. Inner model analysis aims to predict the relationship between latent variables (Ghozali, 2015). Inner model evaluation can be seen from several indicators including:

1. Coefficient of Determination
2. Model Fit Test
3. Path Coefficients

Hypothesis Testing

After conducting various evaluations, both outer model and inner model, the next step is to conduct hypothesis testing. Hypothesis testing is used to explain the direction of the relationship between the independent variable and its dependent variable. Hypothesis testing is done by looking at the probability value and its t-statistic. (Ghozali, 2015).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Measurement model testing (outer model) is used to determine the specific relationship between latent variables and dependent variables. Includes convergent validity, discriminant validity, and reliability.

Convergent Validity

This test is based on the loading factor of 0.7 and the average deviation of the extraction value (AVE) of 0.5, if the deviation above is considered valid. The validity of the indicator is shown if the variable construction variable has a value greater than 0.07. The structural model used in this study is depicted in the following diagram:

Table 1. Outer Loadings/Cross Loading

	Organizational Culture (X2)	Organizational Commitment (Y)	Work Environment (X1)	Job Stress (Z)
X1.1			0.924	
X1.2			0.817	
X1.3			0.883	
X1.4			0.884	
X2.1	0.800			
X2.2	0.826			
X2.3	0.859			
X2.4	0.862			
X2.5	0.898			
Y.1		0.608		
Y.10		0.755		
Y.11		0.761		
Y.2		0.712		
Y.3		0.756		
Y.4		0.872		
Y.5		0.844		
Y.6		0.825		
Y.7		0.867		
Y.8		0.866		
Y.9		0.854		
Z.1				0.899
Z.2				0.872
Z.3				0.884
Z.4				0.798
Z.5				0.820

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 1, there is a cross loading value that has a value of more than 0.7, but there are indicators that are invalid and not greater than 0.7, therefore testing cannot be carried out in the next stage before having a value greater than 0.7, therefore the researcher deletes the indicator whose value is less than 0.7, namely Y.1 after being deleted, a recalculation will be carried out without Y.1.

Figure 2: Outer Model
Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Smart PLS output for loading factor gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Z = b_1X + b_2X_2 + e_1$$

$$Z = -0.476 X_1 - 0.498X_2 + e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_2X_1 + b_3X_2 + b_4Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.483X_1 + 0.129X_2 - 0.107Z + e_2$$

Table 2. Outer Loadings

	Organizational Culture (X2)	Organizational Commitment (Y)	Work Environment (X1)	Job Stress_ (Z)
X1.1			0.924	
X1.2			0.818	
X1.3			0.883	
X1.4			0.884	
X2.1	0.801			
X2.2	0.826			
X2.3	0.859			
X2.4	0.861			
X2.5	0.898			
Y.10		0.761		
Y.11		0.790		
Y.2		0.715		
Y.3		0.750		
Y.4		0.886		
Y.5		0.849		

Y.6		0.839		
Y.7		0.873		
Y.8		0.873		
Y.9		0.847		
Z.1				0.899
Z.2				0.871
Z.3				0.885
Z.4				0.798
Z.5				0.820

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

It can be seen in table 2 that the values that do not reach 0.7 have been deleted so that the cross loading value can be greater than 0.7. As a result, each item indicator has a value greater than or equal to 0.7, which indicates that the data is valid and allows for further investigation.

Discriminant Validity

The next step of analysis is to determine which data is valid in terms of discriminant validity. The goal is to find out whether the cross loading value is greater than other variables so that the sensitivity of the indicator to high correction can be determined in relation to the construction of the table below, which presents the results of the validity assessment as follows:

Table 3. Discriminant Validity

	Organizational Culture (X2)	Organizational Commitment (Y)	Work Environment (X1)	Job Stress_(Z)
X1.1	0.825	0.670	0.924	-0.866
X1.2	0.534	0.545	0.818	-0.647
X1.3	0.663	0.545	0.883	-0.727
X1.4	0.724	0.609	0.884	-0.793
X2.1	0.801	0.554	0.738	-0.764
X2.2	0.826	0.478	0.682	-0.731
X2.3	0.859	0.579	0.621	-0.736
X2.4	0.861	0.450	0.651	-0.726
X2.5	0.898	0.498	0.662	-0.750
Y.10	0.562	0.761	0.511	-0.567
Y.11	0.287	0.790	0.344	-0.318
Y.2	0.435	0.715	0.574	-0.493
Y.3	0.445	0.750	0.614	-0.491
Y.4	0.430	0.886	0.496	-0.485
Y.5	0.495	0.849	0.525	-0.538
Y.6	0.493	0.839	0.508	-0.493

Y.7	0.486	0.873	0.603	-0.535
Y.8	0.513	0.873	0.495	-0.511
Y.9	0.670	0.847	0.727	-0.677
Z.1	-0.859	-0.651	-0.772	0.899
Z.2	-0.732	-0.569	-0.750	0.871
Z.3	-0.764	-0.671	-0.876	0.885
Z.4	-0.633	-0.316	-0.602	0.798
Z.5	-0.724	-0.445	-0.676	0.820

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Based on table 3, the cross loading factor for the explanation of each variable is as follows: For the cross loading factor of the organizational culture variable, the value is greater than the cross loading value on other latent variables, for the cross loading factor on the organizational commitment variable, there is a value that is greater than the cross loading factor value on other latent variables, for the cross loading factor on the work environment variable, there is a value that is greater than the cross loading factor on other latent variables, for the cross loading of the work stress variable, there is a value that is greater than the cross loading factor on other latent variables, so this study is considered valid discriminantly.

Composite reliability

In composite reliability analysis, each variable is compared with its reliability coefficient; if the variable reliability coefficient is more than 0.60 then the analysis is considered reliable; if the variable reliability coefficient is between 0.60 and 0.07, then the analysis is not reliable; There are several blocks to determine whether the analysis results are reliable, valid, or not at all. Among them are the Cronbach alpha coefficient, composite reliability analysis, and AVE coefficient which can be seen in the following table:

Table 4. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Organizational Culture (X2)	0.903	0.928	0.722
Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.945	0.953	0.673
Work Environment (X1)	0.901	0.931	0.771
Job Stress_ (Z)	0.909	0.932	0.732

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 4, it can be seen that each variable has a value greater than 0.07 in the Cronbach's alpha coefficient, this indicates that the data for each variable is reliable. The composition reliability coefficient has a value of approximately 0.66, meaning that each variable in the reliability analysis can be displayed clearly because the data has a value higher than 0.66. Seen from the AVE column, each variable has a value greater than or equal to 0.7, indicating that the data is valid in AVE format. Each variable in the Cronbach alpha,

reliability, and AVE columns has a value greater than 0.07 and 0.6, indicating that the variable is valid and reliable.

Inner Model Analysis

Structural model evaluation (inner model) is conducted to ensure that the basic model created is accurate and robust. The sampling strategy used in the primary analysis model is based on several cases, namely:

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Based on data processing carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value was obtained as follows:

Table 5. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.474	0.450
Job Stress_(Z)	0.849	0.845

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In this study, there are R square results in table 5 and the explanation is as follows: the R square value of the organizational commitment variable is 0.474 if converted to a percentage of 47.4%, meaning that the influence of the work environment, organizational culture and work stress on organizational commitment is 47.4%, the rest is on other variables, for the R square value of work stress of 0.849 if converted to a percentage of 84.9%, meaning that the influence of the work environment and organizational culture on work stress is 84.9% and the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After evaluating the inner model, the next step is to evaluate the relationship between idle builds as described in this review. Speculation checks in this analysis are done by evaluating T-Statistics and P-Values. Speculation is announced to determine if T-Insights has a value greater than 1.96 and if the P-Values value is less than 0.05. The direct impact of the Path Coefficient is what happens next.

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Organizational Culture (X2) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.129	0.823	0.205	Rejected
Organizational Culture (X2) -> Job Stress_(Z)	-0.498	6,492	0,000	Accepted
Work Environment (X1) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.483	2,876	0.002	Accepted
Work Environment (X1) -> Work Stress_(Z)	-0.476	6,438	0,000	Accepted
Job Stress_(Z) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	-0.107	0.502	0.308	Rejected

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Based on the results in table 6, there is a direct influence, so the explanation is as follows:

1. Organizational Culture has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.129 and p values of 0.205. This means that the better the organizational culture, the better the organizational commitment.
2. Organizational Culture has a negative and significant effect on Work Stress with a sample value of -0.498 and p values of 0.000. This means that if the organizational culture increases negatively, work stress will increase and if the organizational culture decreases negatively, work stress will also decrease.
3. Work Environment has a positive but insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.483 and p values of 0.002. This means that not every bad work environment means that employees do not have commitment and it is not necessarily the case that employees in a good environment have work commitment.
4. Work Environment has a negative and significant effect on Work Stress with an original sample value of -0.476 and p values of 0.000. This means that if a bad environment increases, work stress will increase, conversely, if a bad environment decreases, work stress will also decrease.
5. Job Stress has a negative and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of -0.107 and p values of 0.308. This means that if job stress decreases, commitment will increase, conversely, if job stress increases, commitment will decrease.

Table 7. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Organizational Culture (X2) -> Job Stress (Z) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.053	0.481	0.315	Rejected
Work Environment (X1) -> Job Stress (Z) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.051	0.506	0.306	Rejected

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

After explaining the direct influence, the indirect influence will also be explained in this study as follows:

1. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Work Stress indirectly with the original sample value of 0.053 and p values of 0.315. This means that work stress is not an intervening variable because it does not have an indirect and insignificant effect with the presence of work stress proving that employees will still hold their culture towards the organization and are committed to the organization even though they are stressed at work.
2. Work Environment has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment through Work Stress with an original sample value of 0.051 and p values of 0.306. This means that work stress is not an intervening variable in this study because it does not have a significant effect, so without work stress, the work environment and organizational commitment are still running.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Organizational Culture has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.129 and p values of 0.205.
2. Organizational Culture has a negative and significant effect on Work Stress with a sample value of -0.498 and p values of 0.000.
3. Work Environment has a positive but insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.483 and p values of 0.002.
4. Work environment has a negative and significant effect on work stress with an original sample value of -0.476 and p values of 0.000.
5. Work Stress has a negative and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of -0.107 and p values of 0.308.
6. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Work Stress indirectly with an original sample value of 0.053 and p values of 0.315.
7. Work environment has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment through Work Stress with an original sample value of 0.051 and p values of 0.306.

Suggestion

1. Organizations must create a healthy and good organizational culture to support employee performance.
2. Organizations must create a good working environment to create healthy communication between employees.
3. Organizations must minimize the incidence of work stress in employees by providing policies that do not harm employees.
4. Organizations must find ways to increase employee commitment to the organization.
5. It is hoped that this research will be used as input for organizations and employees.
6. It is hoped that this research can be used as reference material for conducting new research.
7. It is hoped that this research can be developed by other researchers with almost the same research title.

REFERENCES

- Afandi. 2018. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia (Teori, Konsep dan Indikator)*. Nusa Media. Yogyakarta.
- Allen, N.J. and Meyer J.P. (2016). The Measurement and Antecedents of Affective, Continuance and Normative Commitment to The Organization, *Journal of Occupational Psychology*. Vol.63. No.1. pp. 1-18
- Andriyati Tanjung, Rahma Wahdiniwaty. 2019. "The Influence of Motivation on Employee Satisfaction and the Impact of Employee Performance in Cooperation." *International Conference on Business, Economic, Social Science, and Humanities – Economics, Business and Management Track (ICOBEST-EBM 2019)* 134-137.
- Dewi, N. (2015). *Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja, Komunikasi dan Stres Kerja Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan*. Bali: UNUD.
- Edison, Emron., dkk. 2016 *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Alfabeta. Bandung

- Fahmi, Irham. 2017. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Bandung : Alfabeta
- Gulo, R. S., & Pardede, J. A. (2021). Stres Kerja Dengan Self Care Perawat Di Rumah Sakit Umum Sari Mutiara Medan. *Jurnal Keperawatan Jiwa*, 2(3).
- Ghozali, Imam dan Hengky Latan (2015). Partial Least Squares Konsep Teknik dan Aplikasi dengan Program Smart PLS 3.0. Semarang: Universitas Diponegoro Semarang.
- Ghozali, I. (2016). Structural Equation Modeling Metode Alternatif dengan Partial Least Square (PLS), Semarang : Badan Penerbit – UNDIP.
- Rivai, Veithzal. (2018). Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia untuk Perusahaan dari Teori ke Praktek. Cetakan Pertama. Jakarta: Murai Kencana.
- Robbins, S.P dan Judge T.A. 2015. Perilaku Organisasi. Jakarta: Salemba Empat
- Sianipar, A.R.B. dan Haryanti, K. 2014. Hubungan Komitmen Organisasi dan Kepuasan Kerja dengan Intensi Turnover pada Karyawan Bidang Produksi CV. X. *Jurnal Psikodemensia*. Vol. XIII, No.1 (98-114).
- Sukanto., Indriyo., (2018), Manajemen Produksi, Edisi keempat, BPFE, Yogyakarta.
- Sugiyono. (2016). Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R&D, Cetakan ke-24. Bandung: Alfabeta.

The Impact of Job Satisfaction on Commitment

Ardian Oka¹, Muhammad Isa Indrawan²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: ardianoka@gmail.com

Abstract

HR is an abbreviation of "Human Resources". This term is generally used in the context of organizational or corporate management to refer to the department or function responsible for managing aspects related to human resources, such as recruitment, training, employee development, performance management, and personnel administration needs to be paid attention to by the leadership of an organization or company in providing maximum service and satisfaction to the community, for this reason skilled and reliable human resources are needed Work has a positive and significant effect. on Employee Commitment with an original sample value of 0.303 and ap value of 0.004. HR Quality has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.459 and an original sample value of 0.001 0.222 and p value of 0.052 original sample value of 0.443 and ap value of 0.002. Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Employees Commitment with an original sample value of 0.370 and ap value of 0.003. HR quality has a positive and significant effect on employee commitment through job satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.139 and ap value of 0.006. Work Motivation has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Commitment through Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.134 and ap value of 0.055.

Keywords: HR Quality, Work Motivation, Job Satisfaction, Employee Commitment

INTRODUCTION

Human resource management needs to be considered by the leaders of an organization or company in providing maximum service and satisfaction to the community, for that it requires skilled and reliable human resources. One way to have skilled and reliable human resources is to try a way to improve employee performance effectively and efficiently, so that the company or organization can achieve the planned target. Improving the quality of human resources (HR) is an absolute requirement for development purposes. Work motivation is the basis for an organization to develop both government agencies and private agencies because of the desire to realize goals and efforts that are carried out together, systematically, and planned. Work motivation includes efforts to encourage or provide enthusiasm to employees in working. Employee work motivation can come from within a person which is often known as internal motivation and external motivation that arises because of external influences to encourage someone to do something according to the expected goals. Employee commitment is one of the keys that helps determine the success or failure of an organization to achieve its goals. Employees who are committed to the organization usually show a work attitude that is attentive to their duties, they are very responsible for carrying out tasks and are very loyal to the company. Commitment contains beliefs, bonds, which will generate energy to do their best. High job satisfaction is expected to make employees more loyal to the organization, more motivated to work, feel happy at work, and in turn will increase productivity. Dissatisfied employees tend to avoid tasks and responsibilities, which will interfere with the process of achieving organizational goals. Dissatisfied employees often avoid work and are more likely to resign. Satisfied employees have better health, longer life spans, and job satisfaction will be carried out of the organization. Job satisfaction is an important target in management. An employee will

provide service with all his heart to the organization depending on what the employee feels about the job, coworkers, and supervisors. Employee feelings and satisfaction influence the development of routine interaction patterns. Bank Indonesia is the central bank of the Republic of Indonesia. Where it is an independent state institution, free from interference from the Government and/or other parties, except for matters expressly regulated in law. External parties are not permitted to interfere in the implementation of Bank Indonesia's duties, and Bank Indonesia is also obliged to reject or ignore any intervention from any party whatsoever. This special status and position are needed so that Bank Indonesia can carry out its role and function as a monetary authority more effectively and efficiently.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does HR Quality have a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
2. Does Work Motivation have a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province?
3. Does HR Quality have a positive and significant effect on Employee Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
4. Does Work Motivation have a positive and significant effect on Employee Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
5. Does Job Satisfaction have a positive and significant effect on Employee Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
6. Does HR Quality have a positive and significant effect on Employee Commitment through Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
7. Does Work Motivation Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Employee Commitment Through Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of HR Quality on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
2. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Motivation on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
3. To determine and analyze the influence of HR Quality on Employee Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
4. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Motivation on Employee Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
5. To determine and analyze the influence of Job Satisfaction on Employee Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
6. To determine and analyze the influence of HR Quality on Employee Commitment through Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
7. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Motivation on Employee Commitment through Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee Commitment

Understanding Employee Commitment

According to Wibawa et al. (2019), organizational commitment is seen as a value orientation towards an organization that shows individual thinking and prioritizes work and the organization. According to Darmawanti et al. (2017), employee commitment is a form of identification, loyalty and involvement expressed by employees towards the organization.

Employee Commitment Indicators

According to Wibawa et al. (2019), the indicators of organizational commitment are as follows:

1. Affective commitment: relates to the employee's emotional relationship to the organization.
2. Continuance commitment: relates to employee awareness of the losses if they leave the organization.
3. Normative commitment: describes feelings of attachment to remaining in the organization.

Quality of Human Resources

Understanding Human Resource Quality

According to Wirawan (2015), the quality of human resources as an integration of physical abilities (physical health), and non-physical abilities (work professionalism, thinking ability, mental balance, and other skills), with the physical and physical abilities possessed, then as an individual will be able to bring out potential, innovate, and work professionally. According to Hutapea and Thoha (2018) the quality of human resources is a person's knowledge, skills, and abilities that can be used to produce professional services.

Human Resources Quality Indicators

According to Hutapea and Thoha (2018), the indicators for human resource quality are as follows:

- a. Understanding the Field Employees have an understanding of what their job description is, both in carrying out the work and their job responsibilities.
- b. Knowledge Employees have knowledge about the work to be done, based on experience or training results.
- c. Abilities Employees must have skills appropriate to their field of work, so that the work can be carried out optimally.
- d. Employee Work Spirit always shows work spirit, by trying to complete work targets, and being disciplined in working.
- e. Planning or Organizing Skills Employees must have management skills in working, so that they can work effectively and efficiently.

Work motivation

Understanding Work Motivation

According to Sedarmayanti (2017), work motivation is something that creates a drive/work enthusiasm/driver of work enthusiasm. According to Sutrisno (2017), motivation is a factor that drives someone to carry out a certain activity, therefore motivation is often interpreted as a factor that drives a person's behavior.

Work Motivation Indicators

According to Maslow in Sutrisno (2017), work motivation indicators consist of:

1. **Physiological Needs (Physiological-need)** Physiological needs are the most basic needs and basic human needs for survival, which include clothing, food, shelter and individual welfare.
2. **Safety Needs** Safety needs are needs that are not only interpreted in terms of physical security but also psychological security and fair treatment at work.
3. **Social Needs** If the need for security has been satisfied, then the third need arises, namely social needs. As social beings, humans cannot fulfill their own needs to interact with others.
4. **Esteem-need** Esteem-need includes the need for self-respect, the need to be respected and appreciated by others, recognition of one's abilities and skills and one's work effectiveness.
5. **Self-actualization needs** Self-actualization needs are needs related to the process of developing one's true potential to demonstrate one's abilities, skills and potential.

Job satisfaction

Understanding Job Satisfaction

According to Wibowo (2016), job satisfaction is everyone who works wants to be happy with their workplace. Job satisfaction will affect the productivity that is actually expected by a manager. According to Badriyah (2015) job satisfaction is one of the very important factors to get optimal work results, when someone feels satisfaction in working, then he will try his best with all the abilities he has to complete his responsibilities.

Job Satisfaction Indicators

According to Badriyah (2015), job satisfaction indicators are:

1. **Employees who can fulfill their duties and responsibilities will be compensated with a salary that is in accordance with their performance.**
2. **Promotion** This aspect measures the extent to which it relates to employee satisfaction, promotion policies, and promotion opportunities. Promotion policies must be implemented fairly. This means that all employees who do their jobs well have equal opportunities for development.
3. **Supervision** This aspect measures individual satisfaction with their superiors. Employees prefer to work with leaders who are supportive, understanding, warm, and kind. Not with leaders who are indifferent, rude, and unfocused.
4. **Benefit** This aspect measures the extent to which an individual is satisfied with the additional benefits received by the company. Provided additional employee costs fairly and reasonably.
5. **Contingents Rewards** This aspect measures how satisfied people are with performance rewards. Everyone wants employees' efforts and dedication to the development of the company to be compensated and receive an appropriate amount of money.
6. **Operating Procedures** Aspects that determine satisfaction with procedures and rules in the workplace. Matters related to procedures and rules in the workplace affect an individual's job satisfaction, for example bureaucracy and workload.
7. **Co-workers** This aspect measures satisfaction with relationships with work colleagues. For example, a colleague who maintains a pleasant relationship with co-workers. Harmonious and complementary work.
8. **Nature of work** Aspects of measuring job satisfaction on issues related to the work itself.

9. Communication Communication work that takes place within the company. Thanks to smooth communication within the company, employees will become more aware of their duties, responsibilities, and everything that happens in the company.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

- H1 The quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H2 Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H3 The quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on Employee Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H4 Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Employee Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H5 Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Employee Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H6 The quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on Employee Commitment through Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H7 Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Employee Commitment through Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.

METHOD

Types of research

Quantitative research is a type of research that uses data in the form of numbers and statistics to measure the variables being studied. According to Sugiyono (2019) quantitative research is defined as a research method based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research a particular population or sample, data collection using research instruments, data analysis is quantitative / statistical, with the aim of testing the established hypothesis.

Research Location and Research Time

This research was conducted at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province, Jalan Balai Kota No. 4 Medan. The time of this research was September to October 2024.

Population

This study used a population of 70 employees of the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province. According to Sugiyono (2019), population is a generalization area consisting of: objects/subjects that have certain quantities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn.

Sample

The sample used by the researcher was all the population in the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province, which was 70 employees. This study used a saturated sample technique, namely calculating all populations without exception. According to Sugiyono (2019), a sample is part of the number and characteristics of the population.

Research Data Sources

This study uses primary data sources as the source of its research data. According to Sugiyono (2019) primary data is a data source that directly provides data to data collectors.

Data collection

Researchers collect data by providing and distributing questionnaires that have been created to obtain research results later. According to Sugiyono (2019), a questionnaire is a data collection technique carried out by giving respondents a set of written questions or statements to answer.

Structural Equation Model

Data analysis is the process of simplifying data into a form that is easier to read and implement. The analysis technique chosen to analyze data and test hypotheses in this study is Smart Partial Least Square (PLS) 3.0. According to Ghozali (2014) the calculation was carried out using the Smart Partial Least Square (PLS) tool, because it is in the form of multi-paths and the model used is in the form of Reflective. The calculation model was carried out using the Smart PLS tool because in this study there was a multi-path relationship and was in the form of formative and reflective. In addition, because the sampling was less than 100 respondents. The formative model is a model that shows the direction of the relationship from the indicator to the latent variable.

Outer Model or Measurement Model Assessment Analysis

PLS-SEM assessment of the outer model allows researchers to evaluate the reliability and validity of a construct's measurements (Hair, Hult, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2017). Outer model analysis is carried out to ensure that the measurements used are suitable for measurement (valid and reliable). In other words, the outer model is a measurement model to assess the validity and reliability of a construct. There are three criteria for conducting outer model assessment analysis, namely Convergent Validity, Discriminant Validity, and Composite Reliability.

- a. Convergent validity is used to measure the magnitude of the correlation between latent variables and indicator variables in the reflective measurement model. A high value on the construct indicates that the indicator has many similarities captured by the construct. The value of the outer loading is usually called indicator reliability. The results of the outer loading on all indicators must be statistically significant. Because significant outer loading can still be said to be quite weak, the general rule and standardization of outer

- loading must be 0.708 or more. As a note, the number 0.70 is considered close to 0.708 and is acceptable (Hair, Hult, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2017).
- b. Discriminant validity can be seen in the cross-loading between the indicator and its latent variable. If the correlation of the latent variable with the indicator is greater than the size of other latent variables, then it indicates that the latent construct predicts the size of their block better than the size of other blocks (Cahyaningrum, Hoyyi, & Mukid, 2015). An indicator can be said to be valid if it has the highest loading factor on the intended construct compared to the loading factor to other constructs. Discriminant validity evaluation is carried out in two stages, namely looking at the cross-loading value and comparing the squared correlation value between the construct and the AVE value or the correlation of the construct with the root of the AVE. Each construct indicator in the cross-loading measurement must correlate higher with its construct compared to other constructs.
 - c. Composite reliability is used to measure the consistency of the indicator block (Cahyaningrum, Hoyyi, & Mukid, 2015). Reliability testing is carried out to prove the accuracy, consistency and precision of the instrument in measuring the construct. To measure the reliability of a construct with an indicator can be done in two ways, namely with Cronbach's alpha with a value of more than 0.70 and composite reliability with a value of more than 0.70 or often called Dillon-Goldsten's.

Inner Model or Structural Model Assessment Analysis

Structural Model or also called inner model is evaluated by looking at the relationship between latent constructs in the model and looking at the R-Square value. Assessing the inner model can be done by looking at the hypothesized relationship between latent constructs in the research model. Evaluation of the inner model can be seen from several indicators including the Determination Coefficient (R²), Predictive Relevance (Q²), and Goodness of Fit Index (GoF). The results of this evaluation are to ensure that the structural model built is robust and accurate.

- a. Determination Coefficient (R-Square) R² is used to see how much the independent variable is able to explain the dependent variable. The greater the R² value, the greater the influence of a particular exogenous latent variable on the endogenous variable. (Ulum, Tirta, & Anggraeni, 2014). Evaluation of the inner model is seen from the percentage of variance from the R² value for the dependent latent construct using the Stone-Geisser Q squares test measure, R² of 0.75 (strong), 0.5 (moderate), 0.25 (weak) and also by looking at the magnitude of the structural path coefficient.
- b. Predictive Relevance (Q-Square) Q² is used to determine the extent of the ability of endogenous variables to explain the diversity of exogenous variables. Q² is used to measure how well the observation value is generated by the model and also its parameter estimates. A Q-Square value greater than 0 (zero) indicates that the model has a predictive relevance value, while a Q-Square value less than 0 (zero) indicates that the model has less predictive relevance. By using Q-squares predictive relevance for structural models, it can measure how well the observation value is generated by the model and also its parameter estimates. The Q-square value must be more than 0 (zero) which indicates that the model has good predictive relevance.
- c. Goodness of Fit (GoF) is used to validate the overall model. The GoF index is a single measure used to validate the combined performance of the measurement model (outer model) and the structural model (inner model). The GoF value is obtained from the average communalities index multiplied by the average R² of the model. The GoF value

ranges from 0 to 1, the interpretation of this value is 0.1 (small GoF), 0.25 (moderate GoF), and 0.36 (large GoF). In general, the explanatory research method is a method approach that uses PLS. This is because this method has a hypothesis test. So after analyzing the outer and inner models, the next step is hypothesis testing. Hypothesis testing can be seen from the t-statistic value and probability value (Hussein, 2015).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Measurement model testing (outer model) is used to determine the specifications of the relationship between latent variables and their manifest variables, this testing includes convergent validity, discriminant validity and reliability.

Convergent Validity

Convergent validity of the measurement model with reflective indicators can be seen from the correlation between item/indicator scores and construct scores. Individual indicators are considered reliable if they have a correlation value above 0.70. However, in the scale development stage research, loadings of 0.50 to 0.60 are still acceptable. Based on the results for outer loading, it shows that there are indicators that have loadings below 0.60 and are not significant.

Table 1. Outer Loadings stage 1

	Job Satisfaction (Z)	Employee Commitment (Y)	Human Resources Quality (X1)	Work Motivation (X2)
X1.1			0.833	
X1.2			0.824	
X1.3			0.783	
X1.4			0.769	
X1.5			0.872	
X2.1				0.895
X2.2				0.843
X2.3				0.877
X2.4				0.831
X2.5				0.900
Y.1		0.850		
Y.2		0.821		
Y.3		0.896		
Z.1	0.795			
Z.2	0.763			
Z.3	0.659			
Z.4	0.817			
Z.5	0.773			
Z.6	0.862			
Z.7	0.846			
Z.8	0.784			

Z.9	0.866			
-----	-------	--	--	--

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In the diagram and table above, indicator Z.3 has a loading factor <0.7 , meaning that the indicator is an invalid indicator for measuring the construct and must be deleted and will be recalculated without indicator Z.3. To find out whether deleting indicator Z.3 will make the data valid, the calculation stage 2 will be carried out as follows:

Table 2. Outer Loadings stage 2

	Job Satisfaction (Z)	Employee Commitment (Y)	Human Resources Quality (X1)	Work Motivation (X2)
X1.1			0.833	
X1.2			0.824	
X1.3			0.783	
X1.4			0.769	
X1.5			0.871	
X2.1				0.896
X2.2				0.843
X2.3				0.877
X2.4				0.830
X2.5				0.901
Y.1		0.850		
Y.2		0.820		
Y.3		0.896		
Z.1	0.798			
Z.2	0.745			
Z.4	0.811			
Z.5	0.788			
Z.6	0.868			
Z.7	0.856			
Z.8	0.800			
Z.9	0.871			

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Table 2 above shows that the assessment of stage 2 shows the results of loading factor > 0.07 , meaning that all indicators are valid after indicator Z.3 is deleted because it is invalid so that the number of indicators is now 21 indicators after the loading factor is valid, then further research can be carried out. meaning that all indicators are valid indicators to measure the construct.

The structural model in this study is shown in the following figure:

Figure 2. Outer Model

The regression equation of this study is as follows:

substructure 1

$$Z = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e_1$$

$$Z = 0.459X_1 + 0.443X_2 + e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_2X_1 + b_3X_2 + b_4Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.222 X_1 + 0.370X_2 + 0.303 Z + e_2$$

Discriminant Validity

In this section, the results of the discriminant validity test will be described. The discriminant validity test uses the cross loading value. An indicator is declared to meet discriminant validity if the cross loading value of the indicator on its variable is the largest compared to other variables. The following are the cross loading values of each indicator:

Table 3. Discriminant Validity

	Job Satisfaction (Z)	Employee Commitment (Y)	Human Resources Quality (X1)	Work Motivation (X2)
X1.1	0.670	0.652	0.833	0.712
X1.2	0.785	0.789	0.824	0.824
X1.3	0.699	0.547	0.783	0.710
X1.4	0.556	0.625	0.769	0.650
X1.5	0.724	0.641	0.871	0.669
X2.1	0.785	0.695	0.867	0.896
X2.2	0.655	0.598	0.725	0.843
X2.3	0.743	0.761	0.728	0.877
X2.4	0.690	0.746	0.695	0.830
X2.5	0.791	0.754	0.798	0.901
Y.1	0.753	0.850	0.669	0.745
Y.2	0.554	0.820	0.603	0.578

Y.3	0.734	0.896	0.777	0.762
Z.1	0.798	0.606	0.607	0.665
Z.2	0.745	0.595	0.667	0.689
Z.4	0.811	0.759	0.711	0.651
Z.5	0.788	0.664	0.682	0.693
Z.6	0.868	0.669	0.783	0.801
Z.7	0.856	0.704	0.686	0.633
Z.8	0.800	0.613	0.633	0.640
Z.9	0.871	0.636	0.755	0.750

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 3 above, the indicators in the research variables have a greater cross loading value compared to the cross loading value in other variables. The cross loading value for the Job Satisfaction variable is greater than other variables, the cross loading value for the Employee Commitment variable is greater than other variables, the cross loading value for the HR Quality variable is greater than other latent variables, and the cross loading value for the Work Motivation variable is greater than other latent variables, meaning that the cross loading value is valid in a discriminatory manner.

Composite reliability

The next test is the composite reliability of the indicator block that measures the construct. A construct is said to be reliable if the composite reliability value is above 0.60. Then it can also be seen by looking at the reliability of the construct or latent variable which is measured by looking at the cronbachs alpha value of the indicator block that measures the construct. A construct is declared reliable if the cronbachs alpha value is above 0.7. The following describes the results of the construct for each variable, namely Organizational Commitment, HR Quality and Work Motivation and Performance with each variable and indicator. The following is a table of loading values for the research variable constructs produced from running the Smart PLS program in the following table:

Table 4. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.929	0.942	0.669
Employee Commitment (Y)	0.818	0.891	0.733
Human Resources Quality (X1)	0.875	0.909	0.667
Work Motivation (X2)	0.919	0.939	0.756

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Based on table 4 above, it shows that the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of each variable, namely Human Resource Quality, Work Motivation and Organizational Commitment has a construct > 0.50, meaning all constructs are reliable. Thus, it can be stated that each variable has high discriminant validity.

Meanwhile, it can be seen in the table above that the composite reliability value of each variable shows a construct value of > 0.60 . This result shows that each variable has met the composite reliability so that it can be concluded that all variables have a high level of reliability.

Furthermore, in the table above, the Cronbach's alpha of each variable shows a construct value of > 0.70 . Thus, these results indicate that each research variable has met the requirements for the Cronbach's alpha value, so it can be concluded that all variables have a high level of reliability. So it can be concluded that the indicators used in this study have high discriminant validity in compiling their respective variables.

Inner Model Analysis

Structural model evaluation (inner model) is conducted to ensure that the structural model built is robust and accurate. The stages of analysis carried out in the structural model evaluation are seen from several indicators, namely:

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 5. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.763	0.756
Employee Commitment (Y)	0.726	0.713

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 5 there is an R square value of the job satisfaction variable of 0.763, meaning that the influence of HR quality and work motivation on job satisfaction is 0.763 if it is percentaged at 76.3% the rest is on other variables. The R square value of the employee commitment variable is 0.726, meaning that the influence of HR quality and work motivation, job satisfaction on employee commitment is 0.763 or 76.3% the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After assessing the inner model, the next step is to evaluate the relationship between latent constructs as hypothesized in this study. Hypothesis testing in this study was conducted by looking at the T-Statistics and P-Values. The hypothesis is accepted if the T-Statistics value is > 1.96 and P-Values < 0.05 . The following are the results of the Path Coefficients of direct influence:

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Job Satisfaction (Z) -> Employee Commitment (Y)	0.303	2,653	0.004	Accepted
Human Resources Quality (X1) -> Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.459	3,305	0.001	Accepted

Human Resources Quality (X1) -> Employee Commitment (Y)	0.222	1,631	0.052	Rejected
Work Motivation (X2) -> Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.443	2,861	0.002	Accepted
Work Motivation (X2) -> Employee Commitment (Y)	0.370	2,749	0.003	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

The results of the hypothesis in table 6 show a direct influence which will be explained as follows:

1. Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Employee Commitment with an original sample value of 0.303 and p values of 0.004. If job satisfaction increases well, employee commitment will increase well, and vice versa, if it decreases, employee commitment will decrease.
2. The quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.459 and p values of 0.001, meaning that if the quality of human resources increases, job satisfaction increases, conversely, if it decreases, job satisfaction decreases.
3. The quality of human resources has a positive and insignificant effect on employee commitment with an original sample value of 0.222 and p values of 0.052, the quality of human resources has little effect on employee commitment and some employees consider the quality of human resources to have a significant effect and as employees it has little effect.
4. Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.443 and p values of 0.002. If motivation increases well, job satisfaction will increase, conversely, if it decreases, job satisfaction will decrease.
5. Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee commitment with an original sample value of 0.370 and p values of 0.003. If work motivation increases well, employee commitment will also increase, conversely, if it decreases, employee commitment will also decrease.

Table 7. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Human Resources Quality (X1) -> Job Satisfaction (Z) -> Employee Commitment (Y)	0.139	2,524	0.006	Accepted
Work Motivation (X2) -> Job Satisfaction (Z) -> Employee Commitment (Y)	0.134	1,597	0.055	Rejected

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 7 there are indirect influences which will be explained by the researcher as follows:

1. The quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on Employee Commitment through Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.139 and p values of 0.006, meaning that job satisfaction is an intervening variable because it is able to significantly influence the quality of human resources and employee commitment so

that it can be concluded that job satisfaction can improve the quality of human resources and employee commitment.

2. Work Motivation has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Commitment through Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.134 and p values of 0.055, meaning that job satisfaction is not an intervening variable because it is unable to influence it significantly.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Employee Commitment with an original sample value of 0.303 and p values of 0.004.
2. HR quality has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.459 and p values of 0.001.
3. HR quality has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Commitment with an original sample value of 0.222 and p values of 0.052.
4. Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.443 and p values of 0.002.
5. Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Employee Commitment with an original sample value of 0.370 and p values of 0.003.
6. HR quality has a positive and significant effect on Employee Commitment through Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.139 and p values of 0.006.
7. Work Motivation has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Commitment through Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.134 and p values of 0.055.

Suggestion

1. Organizations must improve the quality of human resources in the organization or seek employees who have high quality human resources.
2. To increase employee job satisfaction, the organization must provide facilities to the organization for work needs and organizational achievements.
3. Employee commitment is built well and wisely by the organization to develop employee performance.
4. Work motivation must be carried out every month to increase employee confidence and improve employee performance.
5. This research is expected to be a reference material for further research with new research and new titles.
6. It is hoped that this research can be developed by further research with other research models and techniques.

REFERENCES

- Badriyah, M. (2015). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*, Cetakan 1. Bandung : CV Pustaka Setia.
- Cahyaningrum, E., Hoyyi, A., & Mukid, M. A. (2015). *ANALISA FAKTORFAKTOR YANG MEMPENGARUHI KINERJA PERUSAHAAN MENGGUNAKAN PLS PT*. Telkom Indonesia Divisi Regional Jawa Tengah- DIY dan Wilayah Telekomunikasi Semarang).

- Darmawati, Arum, Lina Nur Hayati, Dyna Herlina S. 2017, Pengaruh Kepuasan Kerja dan Komitmen Organisasional Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior, *Jurnal Ekonomia*, Vol 9, No 1, 2017: 10-17
- Ghozali, Imam. 2014. *Structural Equation Modeling, Metode Alternatif dengan Partial Least Square (PLS)*. Edisi 4. Semarang : Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., dan Sarstedt, M. (2017). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)* (Ed. 2). United States of America: SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Hutapea dan Nurianna Thoha, 2018. *Kompetensi Plus*. Jakarta: PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Hussein, A.S. 2015. *Penelitian Bisnis dan Manajemen Menggunakan Partial Least Square (PLS) dengan smartPLS 3.0*. Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis Universitas Brawijaya.
- Sedarmayanti. 2017. *Perencanaan dan Pengembangan SDM untuk Meningkatkan Kompetensi, Kinerja dan Produktivitas Kerja*. PT Refika Aditama. Bandung.
- Sutrisno, E. 2017. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Kencana, Jakarta.
- Sugiyono. (2019). *Metodelogi Penelitian Kuantitatif dan Kualitatif Dan R&D*. Bandung: ALFABETA.
- Ulum, M., Tirta, I. M., dan Anggraeni, D. (2014). Analisis structural equation modeling (sem) untuk sampel kecil dengan pendekatan partial least square (pls). Tersedia secara online di: <http://download.portalgaruda.org/article.php>.
- Wirawan, 2015. *Evaluasi Kinerja Sumber Daya Manusia (Teori, Aplikasi, dan Penelitian)*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- Wibowo, 2016. *Manajemen Kinerja, Edisi Kelima*, PT.Rajagrafindo Persada Jakarta-14240.
- Wibawa dkk., 2019, Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi, Motivasi Kerja, dan Komitmen Organisasi Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja dan Kinerja Karyawan PT Arta Boga Cemerlang Pekanbaru, *Jurnal Akuntansi, Kewirausahaan dan Bisnis* Vol. 4 No. 1. hal 59-70.

Optimizing Commitment

Azaria Tarigan¹, Muhammad Isa Indrawan²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: azaria88@gmail.com

Abstract

Support for facilities and infrastructure as well as adequate financial sources are other important elements in moving the wheels of an organization, but without the support of reliable human resources, organizational activities will not run, so optimizing the achievement of organizational goals cannot be achieved. This condition suggests that human resource development is an inevitable demand in order to ensure the availability of quality human resources according to organizational demands. The results of this research are as follows: Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with a value of 0.353 and a significant 0.012. Work Discipline has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with a value of 0.090 and a significant value of 0.323. Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with a value of 0.745 and a significant value of 0.000. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with a value of 0.557 and a significant 0.000. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with a value of 0.070 and a significant value of 0.301. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Job Satisfaction with a value of 0.263 and a significant value of 0.008. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Job Satisfaction with a value of 0.415 and a significant value of 0.004.

Keywords: Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Work Discipline, Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment

INTRODUCTION

Organization as a system will involve various resources and sources of funds that support each other and support each other. Support for facilities and infrastructure and adequate sources of funds are other important elements in driving the wheels of the organization, but without the support of reliable human resources, organizational activities will not run, so that optimization of achieving organizational goals is impossible to achieve. Human Resources (HR) are a very valuable asset for an agency because HR is the main driver of the agency. HR must be managed optimally, continuously and given extra attention and fulfill their rights, in addition HR is a partner of leadership to achieve agency goals. Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is an unofficial rule that is voluntary. The need for OCB in a company to increase the productivity of coworkers, improve superiors, save resources owned by management and the organization, help save scarce energy resources to maintain group functions, can be an effective means to coordinate work group activities, improve the organization's ability to retain the best employees, increase stability and ability to adapt to environmental changes Organizational citizenship behavior is one of the important things in an organization. Extra individual behavior, which is not exclusively or explicitly recognizable in a formal work system, and can increase the effectiveness of organizational functions in achieving organizational goals (Sule & Priansa, 2018). Workplace discipline is an important factor in determining employee performance and work style in an organization. The above regulations are a set of rules and guidelines agreed upon by members of the organization to determine how members should behave when carrying out organizational activities. Employee satisfaction is defined as an employee's positive

attitude and performance while working. Sensation and admiration are the results of a person's emotional response to work and work-related stress. Job satisfaction is the key to the productivity of an organization, especially health services. In fact, job satisfaction and the well-being of health workers play an important role in the quality of health services. Organizational Commitment is the relationship between an individual and an organization in which the individual has a strong self-awareness of the goals and objectives of the organization, a strong desire to use its resources in a manner consistent with its needs, and a strong desire to remain an integral part of the organization. Commitment plays an important role in improving employee performance in an organization. High commitment will have an impact on increasing employee performance. Organizational commitment is an employee's orientation towards the company that can connect a person's identity to the company. Employees who have a high commitment to the company tend to have better performance and will also stay in the company longer. In the world of work, a person's commitment to an organization is often a very important issue. So important is it that some organizations dare to include the element of commitment as one of the requirements for holding a position offered in job advertisements. Indeed, no longer, the current understanding of commitment equips permanent employees in the company for a long period of time. But more importantly, they need to provide the best service to the company, even to the point of helping to carry out certain tasks that must be fulfilled by the company.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Organization Citizenship Behavior have a positive and significant influence on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province?
2. Does Work Discipline have a positive and significant influence on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province?
3. Does Organization Citizenship Behavior have a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
4. Does Work Discipline have a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province?
5. Does Job Satisfaction have a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
6. Does Organization Citizenship Behavior have a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment through Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
7. Does Work Discipline have a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment through Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of Organization Citizenship Behavior on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
2. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Discipline on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
3. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Citizenship Behavior on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.

4. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Discipline on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
5. To determine and analyze the influence of Job Satisfaction on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
6. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Citizenship Behavior on Organizational Commitment through Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
7. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Discipline on Organizational Commitment through Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational Commitment

Understanding Organizational Commitment

According to Kharis (2010) organizational commitment is a condition where an employee sides with a particular organization and its goals and desires to maintain membership in the organization. So high job involvement means siding with a particular job of an individual. According to Yusuf and Syarif (2018) organizational commitment is a psychological construct as a characteristic of the relationship between organizational members and their organization, and has implications for individual decisions to continue their existence as members of the organization.

Organizational Commitment Indicators

Indicators of organizational commitment, according to Yusuf and Syarif, (2018):

1. Effective commitment: Employees' emotional attachment and involvement in the organization,
2. Continuance commitment: Commitment based on losses associated with an employee leaving the organization. This may be due to loss of seniority, promotion or benefits.
3. Normative commitment: A feeling of obligation to remain in the organization because one must; it is the right thing to do.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Understanding Organizational Citizenship Behavior

According to Putrana (2016), Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is an individual's contribution that exceeds the demands of the role in the workplace and is rewarded based on individual performance results. According to Aprianti (2019) Organizational Citizenship Behavior is an individual behavior that is free (discretionary), which does not directly and explicitly receive expectations from the formal reward system, and which overall drives the effectiveness of organizational functions.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior Indicators

According to Aprianti (2017), the indicators of organizational citizenship behavior are:

1. Altruism (helping attitude). This attitude is shown by helping others, in this case co-workers. Altruism is the behavior of helping or assisting others and replacing other people's tasks. The items in the study used related to altruism are: employee willingness to replace other employees' tasks. Employee willingness to help other employees who are in trouble.

2. Conscientiousness (complying with the rules). Behavior shown by employees by fulfilling the requirements submitted by the organization. Items in the research used related to conscientiousness are: Employee compliance with all regulations and Employee responsibility attitude in carrying out work.
3. Sportsmanship (sportsmanlike and positive attitude). The willingness of employees to tolerate other employees who complain. This behavior is shown by a sporty and positive attitude in carrying out tasks. The items in the study used related to sportsmanship are: employees never complain in carrying out their work and employee trust in their leaders.

Work Discipline

Understanding Work Discipline

According to Sutrisno (2016) discipline is "a person's behavior that is in accordance with the rules, existing work procedures or discipline is an attitude, behavior, and actions that are in accordance with the rules of the organization, both written and unwritten". According to Hasibuan (2016) work discipline is the most important HR operative function because the better the employee's discipline, the higher the work performance that can be achieved. Without good discipline, it is difficult for organizations and agencies to achieve optimal results.

Work Discipline Indicators

According to Hasibuan (2016) the indicators are as follows:

1. Goals and capabilities
Goals and abilities also affect the level of employee discipline. The goals to be achieved must be clear and set ideally and challenging enough for the employee's abilities.
2. Leadership role model
The leadership example plays a very important role in determining employee discipline because leaders are used as role models and role models by their subordinates.
3. Justice
Justice also helps to realize employee discipline, because human ego and nature always feel important and ask to be treated the same as other humans.
4. Inherent supervision (waskat)
Inherent supervision is a real and most effective action in realizing employee discipline in an agency. Because with waskat means that superiors must be active and directly supervise the behavior, morals, attitudes, work passion, and work performance of their subordinates.
5. Penalty sanctions
Punishment sanctions play an important role in maintaining employee discipline. With increasingly severe punishment sanctions, employees will be increasingly afraid of violating agency regulations, and indisciplined attitudes and behavior of employees will decrease.
6. Firmness
The firmness of the leader in taking action will affect the discipline of the agency's employees. The leader must be brave and firm in acting to punish every indisciplined employee according to the established punishment sanctions.
7. Human relations
Harmonious human relations among fellow employees help create good discipline in an agency. Good relationships are both vertical and horizontal.

Job satisfaction

Understanding Job Satisfaction

Feelings related to work involve aspects such as wages or salaries received, career development opportunities, relationships with other employees, job placement, type of work, company organizational structure, quality of supervision. While feelings related to oneself include age, health conditions, abilities and education. (Mangkunegara, 2017). According to Yuniarsih (2017), job satisfaction is a psychological reflection of employees on the results of their work. The level of individual satisfaction is basically based on the value system within themselves. Therefore, the measure of satisfaction will be different for each individual.

Job Satisfaction Indicators

According to Yuniarsih (2017), job satisfaction indicators are as follows:

1. Supervision,
2. Work environment,
3. Promotion,
4. Supportive co-workers,
5. Work that is mentally challenging, and
6. Rewards in the form of wages/salary.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

- H1 Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H2 Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H3 Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H4 Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H5 Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H6 Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

H7 Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

METHOD

Types of Research

According to Sugiyono (2020), quantitative research methods can be interpreted as research methods based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations or samples, data collection using research instruments, quantitative/statistical data analysis, with the aim of testing predetermined hypotheses.

Population

Population is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to study and then draw conclusions (Sugiyono, 2020). Based on the definition explained, this study will use the population of all employees at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province of 70 employees.

Sample

According to Sugiyono (2020), a sample is part of the number and characteristics of the population. Meanwhile, sample size is a step to determine the size of the sample taken in conducting a study. Based on the understanding that has been described, the sample used by the researcher is the entire population, namely 70 employees and using a saturated sample research technique.

Place and Time of Research

The research was conducted at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province, Jalan Balai Kota No. 4 Medan. The research was conducted from September to October 2024.

Research Data Sources

Primary data is directly obtained from the first data source at the research location or research object. According to Sekaran and Bougie (2019) primary data is data from respondents, individuals, focus groups, and panels that are specifically determined by researchers and where opinions can be sought regarding certain problems. Primary data is obtained directly from distributing questionnaires to employees as selected objects.

Data collection technique

The data collection technique used in this study was to distribute questionnaires to research respondents. Questionnaire According to Sugiyono (2020), a questionnaire is a data collection technique carried out by giving respondents a set of written questions to answer.

Data analysis

Structural Equation Model

Data processing in this study uses SmartPLS software, because this study is in a reflective form. The reflective model is a model that shows the relationship between latent variables and their indicators (Ghozali and Latan, 2020). The data collection technique in this study uses a questionnaire by providing a number of written statements addressed to

respondents and will then be answered, structural equation modeling which is often called Partial Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) with SmartPLS version 3.3.3 is used to analyze data and modeling paths with latent variables.

Measurement Model (Outer Model)

According to (Ghozali and Latan, 2020), the Outer model or measurement model describes how each indicator block relates to its latent variables. The outer model is used to test the construct validity and reliability of the instrument. This is useful for determining the ability of the research instrument to measure what should be measured, the consistency of the measuring instrument in measuring a concept or the consistency of respondents in answering question items in the questionnaire or research instrument. According to Ghozali and Latan (2020), the measurements carried out through the measurement model are convergent validity, discriminant validity, composite reliability (Cronbach's alpha).

1. **Convergent Validity** This validity is related to the principle that the measures of a construct should be highly correlated. The convergent validity test of the reflective indicator with the SmartPLS 3.3.3 program can be seen from the loading factor value for each construct indicator.
2. **Discriminant Validity** This validity relates to the principle that different construct measures should not be highly correlated. Discriminant validity occurs when two different instruments measuring two constructs that are predicted to be uncorrelated produce scores that are indeed uncorrelated.
3. **Composite Reliability (Cronbach's Alpha)** In addition to validity testing, model measurement also tests the reliability of a construct to prove the accuracy, consistency, and precision of the instrument in measuring the construct. To measure the reliability of a construct can be done in two ways, namely with Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability. However, the use of Cronbach's Alpha will provide a lower value so it is more advisable to use Composite Reliability in testing the reliability of a construct.

Structural Model (Inner Model)

According to Ghozali and Latan (2020), the inner model or structural model describes the relationship or strength of the estimate between latent variables or constructs built based on the substance of the theory. The inner model is a structural model for predicting causal relationships between latent variables.

Hypothesis testing

After the overall and partial model is tested, the next stage is hypothesis testing. According to Ghozali and Latan (2020), hypothesis testing is carried out by looking at the T-statistic value compared to the T-table value = 1.96 at a significance level of p value = 0.05. If the T-statistic value > T-table, it can be concluded that the exogenous variable has a significant effect on the endogenous variable.

Path Analysis

According to Ghozali and Latan (2020) if a model is formed using mediating variables, then a multiple regression model cannot solve the problem. The appropriate analysis technique is path analysis. Path analysis allows researchers to test direct relationships between variables as well as indirect relationships between variables in the model.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Measurement in model evaluation is divided into three stages of testing such as convergent validity test, composite reliability test and discriminant validity test. The following is a description of each test in the evaluation of the measurement model.

Figure 2. Outer Model

If seen in the Figure above, it can be seen that in the latent variable each variable has a loading factor value, each manifest variable is greater with a value of 0.7, which means that all indicators and loading factors are validly distributed. The regression equation of this study is as follows:

substructure 1

$$Z = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e_1$$

$$Z = 0.557X_1 + 0.353 X_2 + e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_2X + b_3X_2 + b_4Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.070X_1 + 0.090 X_2 + 0.745 Z + e_2$$

Convergent Validity Test

Convergent validity is the level of correlation between different measurement instruments used in measuring the same construct. Testing on convergent validity in SEM-PLS, the assessment of reflective indicators is based on the loading factor of each indicator to measure its construct. According to Ghazoli (2012) that the loading factor value is said to be high if it has a correlation of more than 0.70, but if the initial research the loading factor value is 0.50-0.60. The calculation of the loading factor value using smart PLS version 3.0 can be seen in the table below. The convergent validity value in Figure 1, it can be seen that all indicator variables in this study have a loading factor value above 0.50. So that the study is considered to have met convergent validity.

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Work Discipline (X2)	Job Satisfaction (Z)	Organizational Commitment (Y)	Organizational Citizenship Behavior(X1)
X1.1				0.850
X1.2				0.880
X1.3				0.791
X2.1	0.757			
X2.2	0.758			
X2.3	0.891			
X2.4	0.835			
X2.5	0.867			
X2.6	0.831			
X2.7	0.896			
Y.1			0.886	
Y.2			0.870	
Y.3			0.902	
Z.1		0.860		
Z.2		0.838		
Z.3		0.744		
Z.4		0.829		
Z.5		0.758		
Z.6		0.844		

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

In table 1, the value of each variable is stated that the indicator in each variable is higher than 0.7, which means that each indicator item has a value higher than 0.7 so that the data is declared valid and can continue to further research.

Discriminant Validity Test

Discriminant validity on reflective indicators is used to compare cross loading values. In principle, the value of discriminant validity of different construct measurements does not have to be highly correlated. indicators in this study seen from the discriminant validity value can be seen in the table below:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Work Discipline (X2)	Job Satisfaction (Z)	Organizational Commitment (Y)	Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X1)
X1.1	0.757	0.699	0.613	0.850
X1.2	0.838	0.850	0.717	0.880
X1.3	0.707	0.658	0.706	0.791
X2.1	0.757	0.575	0.530	0.637

X2.2	0.758	0.716	0.704	0.743
X2.3	0.891	0.752	0.738	0.875
X2.4	0.835	0.691	0.592	0.760
X2.5	0.867	0.748	0.706	0.728
X2.6	0.831	0.728	0.654	0.715
X2.7	0.896	0.805	0.705	0.863
Y.1	0.659	0.803	0.886	0.695
Y.2	0.681	0.711	0.870	0.653
Y.3	0.775	0.829	0.902	0.793
Z.1	0.681	0.860	0.694	0.689
Z.2	0.655	0.838	0.593	0.702
Z.3	0.620	0.744	0.562	0.641
Z.4	0.674	0.829	0.757	0.736
Z.5	0.724	0.758	0.775	0.687
Z.6	0.821	0.844	0.871	0.814

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

It can be seen in the results of the table above that the cross loading value for each variable has a value that is greater than the cross loading value for other latent variables, meaning that the research is considered discriminantly valid.

Evaluating Reliability and Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Validity and reliability criteria can also be seen from the reliability value of a construct and the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value of each construct. A construct is said to have high reliability if its value is 0.70 and AVE is above 0.50. Table 7 will present the Composite Reliability and AVE values for all variables.

Table 3. Composite Reliability and Average Variance Extracted

	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Work Discipline (X2)	0.941	0.698
Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.921	0.662
Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.916	0.785
Organizational_Citizenship_Behavior_(X1)	0.879	0.708

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

Based on table 3 above, it can be concluded that all constructs meet the reliable criteria. This is indicated by the composite reliability value above 0.70 and AVE above 0.50 as recommended criteria.

Structural Model Testing (Inner Model)

Inner model or structural model testing is conducted to see the relationship between constructs, significance values and R-square of the research model. The structural model is evaluated using R-square for the dependent construct.

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Evaluation of the structural model in SEM with PLS was carried out by conducting the R-squared (R²) test and significance test through path coefficient estimation. The output for the R² value using the smartPLS 3.3.3 computer program was obtained:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.796	0.789
Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.788	0.778

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

There is an R square value of the job satisfaction variable of 0.796, meaning that the influence of organizational citizenship behavior and work discipline on job satisfaction is 0.796 or a percentage of 79.6% and the rest is on other variables. There is an R square value of the organizational commitment variable of 0.788, meaning that the influence of organizational citizenship behavior and work discipline, job satisfaction on organizational commitment is 0.788 or a percentage of 78.8%, the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After assessing the inner model, the next step is to evaluate the relationship between latent constructs as hypothesized in this study. Hypothesis testing in this study was conducted by looking at the T-Statistics and P-Values. The hypothesis is accepted if the T-Statistics value is > 1.96 and P-Values < 0.05. The following are the results of the Path Coefficients of direct influence:

Table 5. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Work Discipline (X2) -> Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.353	2,279	0.012	Accepted
Work Discipline (X2) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.090	0.459	0.323	Rejected
Job Satisfaction (Z) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.745	5,736	0,000	Accepted
Organizational Citizenship Behavior(X1)-> Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.557	3,709	0,000	Accepted
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X1) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.070	0.523	0.301	Rejected

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

In table 5 there are the results of the direct influence of the hypothesis, so the explanation of these results is as follows:

1. Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with a value of 0.353 and a significance of 0.012, meaning that if there is an increase in work discipline, there will be an increase in job satisfaction, conversely, if it decreases, job satisfaction will also decrease.

2. Work discipline has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with a value of 0.090 and a significance of 0.323, meaning that work discipline has little effect on organizational commitment and also cannot increase or decrease organizational commitment.
3. Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with a value of 0.745 and a significance of 0.000, meaning that if job satisfaction increases well, commitment will also increase well, if it decreases, organizational commitment will decrease.
4. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with a value of 0.557 and a significance of 0.000, meaning that if Organizational Citizenship Behavior increases, job satisfaction will increase, conversely, if it decreases, job satisfaction will also decrease.
5. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with a value of 0.070 and a significance of 0.301, meaning that OCB has little effect on organizational commitment and cannot increase or decrease organizational commitment because there are still those who have OCB traits and those who do not.

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Work Discipline (X2) -> Job Satisfaction (Z) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.263	2,406	0.008	Accepted
Organizational Citizenship Behavior(X1) -> Job Satisfaction (Z) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.415	2,674	0.004	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

In table 6 there are indirect influences which will be explained as follows by the researcher:

1. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Job Satisfaction with a value of 0.263 and a significance of 0.008, meaning that job satisfaction is an intervening variable because it is able to influence significantly, thus creating an increase that occurs indirectly through work discipline and organizational commitment.
2. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Job Satisfaction with a value of 0.415 and a significance of 0.004, meaning that job satisfaction can be an intervening variable because it can have a significant effect. It can be concluded that job satisfaction has an increasing effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior and organizational commitment.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with a value of 0.353 and a significance of 0.012.
2. Work Discipline has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with a value of 0.090 and a significance of 0.323.

3. Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with a value of 0.745 and a significance of 0.000.
4. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with a value of 0.557 and a significance of 0.000.
5. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with a value of 0.070 and a significance of 0.301.
6. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Job Satisfaction with a value of 0.263 and a significance of 0.008.
7. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Job Satisfaction with a value of 0.415 and a significance of 0.004.

Suggestion

1. Organizations must explain about Organizational Citizenship Behavior that they do not know to employees.
2. Organizations must implement work discipline on employees who make mistakes and do not want to follow the rules and provide punishments that deter employees.
3. Organizations must increase employee job satisfaction to improve employee performance.
4. Organizations must be able to increase employee commitment by any means to improve performance.
5. It is hoped that this research will be used as input for organizational development.
6. It is hoped that this research will be used as a reference and can be developed by new researchers.

REFERENCES

- Badriyah, M. (2015). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*, Cetakan 1. Bandung : CV Pustaka Setia.
- Cahyaningrum, E., Hoyyi, A., & Mukid, M. A. (2015). *ANALISA FAKTORFAKTOR YANG MEMPENGARUHI KINERJA PERUSAHAAN MENGGUNAKAN PLS PT. Telkom Indonesia Divisi Regional Jawa Tengah- DIY dan Wilayah Telekomunikasi Semarang*.
- Darmawati, Arum, Lina Nur Hayati, Dyna Herlina S. 2017, Pengaruh Kepuasan Kerja dan Komitmen Organisasional Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior, *Jurnal Ekonomia*, Vol 9, No 1, 2017: 10-17
- Ghozali, Imam. 2014. *Structural Equation Modeling, Metode Alternatif dengan Partial Least Square (PLS)*. Edisi 4. Semarang : Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., dan Sarstedt, M. (2017). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)* (Ed. 2). United States of America: SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Hutapea dan Nurianna Thoha, 2018. *Kompetensi Plus*. Jakarta: PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Hussein, A.S. 2015. *Penelitian Bisnis dan Manajemen Menggunakan Partial Least Square (PLS) dengan smartPLS 3.0*. Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis Universitas Brawijaya.
- Sedarmayanti. 2017. *Perencanaan dan Pengembangan SDM untuk Meningkatkan Kompetensi, Kinerja dan Produktivitas Kerja*. PT Refika Aditama. Bandung.

- Sutrisno, E. 2017. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Kencana, Jakarta.
- Sugiyono. (2019). Metodologi Penelitian Kuantitatif dan Kualitatif Dan R&D. Bandung: ALFABETA.
- Ulum, M., Tirta, I. M., dan Anggraeni, D. (2014). Analisis structural equation modeling (sem) untuk sampel kecil dengan pendekatan partial least square (pls). Tersedia secara online di: <http://download.portalgaruda.org/article.php>.
- Wirawan, 2015. Evaluasi Kinerja Sumber Daya Manusia (Teori, Aplikasi, dan Penelitian). Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- Wibowo, 2016. Manajemen Kinerja, Edisi Kelima, PT.Rajagrafindo Persada Jakarta-14240.
- Wibawa dkk., 2019, Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi, Motivasi Kerja, dan Komitmen Organisasi Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja dan Kinerja Karyawan PT Arta Boga Cemerlang Pekanbaru, Jurnal Akuntansi, Kewirausahaan dan Bisnis Vol. 4 No. 1. hal 59-70.

Determinants of Job Performance

Erni Winari¹, Muhammad Isa Indrawan²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: erniwina91@gmail.com

Abstract

Human resource management (HRM) is a field of study and practice that focuses on the management and management of human resources in an organization. The aim is to ensure that the organization has a qualified, motivated and productive workforce to achieve its strategic goals. It is important for organizations to pay attention to human resources because the performance and success of the organization is very dependent on the quality and productivity of the workforce. Investments in HR development can increase employee loyalty, increase retention, reduce recruitment and retraining costs, and increase efficiency and productivity throughout the organization. The results of this research are as follows: Job satisfaction is unable to moderate organizational commitment to job performance with an original sample value of 0.004 and ap value of 0.486. Job Satisfaction is able to moderate and weaken Job Quality on Job Performance with an original sample value of -0.173 and ap value of 0.018. Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Job Performance with an original sample value of 0.495 and ap value of 0.001. Organizational Commitment has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Performance with an original sample value of 0.098 and ap value of 0.260. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance with an original sample value of 0.203 and ap value of 0.033.

Keywords: Organizational Commitment, Work Quality, Job Satisfaction, Job Performance

INTRODUCTION

The concept of HR covers everything related to the management, development, and utilization of the workforce in achieving organizational goals. Things included in human resources include recruitment, selection, training, employee development, performance management, compensation, conflict management, and employment policies. The goal is to ensure that the organization has a qualified, motivated, and productive workforce to achieve its strategic goals. Organizational commitment is the level of involvement, loyalty, and dedication that members of the organization have to the goals, values, and culture of the organization. Organizational commitment is important because it can have a positive impact on employee performance, retention, motivation, and job satisfaction. Organizations that are able to build and maintain a strong commitment from their employees tend to have a more stable, productive, and high-performing workforce. Improving the quality of human resources in an organization requires efforts to support the improvement of the quality of human resources of employees. One of them is by improving the level of education of these employees. Quality of work is a trait that needs to be considered in a company. The realization of a company's goals can be seen through the products produced and the quality of its employees' work. Improving the quality of employee work is very important because the success of a company does not only depend on machine technology but the human factor also plays an important role in it. (Sengkey et al., 2021) Employee performance is a very important thing in an organization to achieve its goals. In an organization, the human resource factor is the main problem in every activity in it. Because if the human resources in the organization are bad, then the organization's goals cannot be achieved as planned. Because the role of human resources in the organization is to determine the success of the organization. Job satisfaction is a manifestation of employee perception which is reflected

in attitudes and focuses on behavior towards work. According to Kreitner & Kinicki (2014), job satisfaction is a positive feeling about one's job which is the result of an evaluation of its characteristics. Job satisfaction in general concerns a person's attitude towards their job because it concerns attitudes. The definition of job satisfaction includes various things such as emotions and behavioral tendencies of a person. Job satisfaction is not visible and real but can be manifested in work results and attitudes. Job satisfaction refers to the level of satisfaction, happiness, and satisfaction felt by employees towards their work and the work environment in which they are located.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Organizational Commitment have a positive and significant effect on Work Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
2. Does Employee Work Quality have a positive and significant effect on Work Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
3. Does Job Satisfaction have a positive and significant effect on Job Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
4. Does Job Satisfaction Moderate Organizational Commitment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
5. Does Job Satisfaction Moderate Work Quality at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of organizational commitment on work performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
2. To determine and analyze the Influence of Employee Work Quality on Work Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
3. To determine the influence of Job Satisfaction on Work Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
4. To determine and analyze the influence of job satisfaction in moderating organizational commitment to work performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
5. To determine and analyze the influence of job satisfaction in moderating work quality on work performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Work performance

Definition of Work Performance

According to Tanjung (2015) work performance is the result of work that has been achieved by an employee in carrying out work activities. The work results achieved by an employee in carrying out tasks are based on skills, experience, and sincerity and time. According to Mangkunegara (2017) work performance is The term performance comes from Job Performance or Actual Performance (work performance or actual achievement achieved by someone).

Work Performance Indicators

According to Mangkunegara (2017) indicators of work performance are:

- 1) Quantity of Work The amount of work results that are in accordance with the time available, what needs to be considered is not routine results but how quickly the work can be completed.
- 2) Work Quality The quality of work results based on established standards. Usually measured through accuracy, precision, skill, and cleanliness of work results.
- 3) Collaboration The ability of an employee to participate and cooperate with other people in completing tasks.
- 4) Initiative Passionate or diligent in completing tasks, as well as the ability to make good decisions without prior guidance.

Organizational Commitment

Understanding Organizational Commitment

According to Robbins (2016) organizational commitment is defined as a condition where an employee sides with the organization and its goals and willingness to maintain membership in a particular job of an employee, while high organizational commitment means siding with the organization and recruiting the individual. According to Mardiyana et al. (2019) organizational commitment can be defined as a situation where an employee sides with a particular organization with the goal and desire to maintain membership in the organization.

Organizational Commitment Indicators

According to Robbins (2016), the indicators of organizational commitment are as follows:

1. Affective commitment, namely an emotional feeling towards the organization and belief in values.
2. Continuance commitment is the perceived value of remaining in the organization compared to leaving the organization.
3. Normative commitment, namely the obligation to remain in an organization for moral and polite reasons.

Quality of Work

Definition of Work Quality

According to Ristanti (2016), work quality is the level of satisfaction, motivation, involvement and experience of individual commitment regarding their life at work. According to Hasibuan (2019) that work quality is a physical standard that is measured because of the results of work carried out or implemented by employees towards their tasks.

Work Quality Indicators

According to Hasibuan (2019) the work quality indicators are as follows:

1. Self-Potential, related to aspects of ability, strength, both those that have not been realized and those that have been realized, which a person has, but have not yet been fully seen to their maximum potential.
2. Optimal Work Results, are the results that an employee is required to have, must be able to provide the best work results which can be seen from the productivity of the organization, quality and quantity of work.
3. Work Process, namely the most important stage where employees carry out their duties and roles through this work process.

Job satisfaction

Understanding Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction has become an important issue regarding the development of human resources and contemporary employment. This issue is mainly related to the increasing education of employees and the increasing needs of the employees' lives themselves, (Sule & Priansa, 2018) According to Priansa, (2016) Job satisfaction is an important thing that individuals have in working. Each individual who works has different characteristics, so the level of satisfaction is also different.

Job Satisfaction Indicators

According to Priansa (2016) job satisfaction indicators are:

1. Salary This aspect measures employee satisfaction in relation to the salary they receive and the salary increase, namely the amount of salary received in accordance with the level considered appropriate. Wages and salaries do have an influence on job satisfaction. Employees view salary as a right that they must receive for the obligations they have carried out, such as:
 - a. Amount of salary.
 - b. Timeliness of salary payments.
2. Promotion This aspect measures the extent to which employees are satisfied with promotion policies and opportunities to get promotions. Promotions or opportunities to advance their careers also affect employee job satisfaction. Employees will see whether the organization provides equal opportunities for each employee to get a promotion or is only intended for some people. This promotion policy must be carried out fairly, namely that every employee who does a good job has the same opportunity for promotion, such as: opportunities to advance their careers.
3. Supervision (relationship with superiors) This aspect measures a person's job satisfaction with their superiors. Employees prefer to work with superiors who are supportive, attentive, warm and friendly, give praise for good performance from subordinates, listen to opinions from subordinates, and focus on employees (employee centered) rather than working with leaders who are indifferent, rude, and focus on work (job centered), such as:
 - a. Give praise for good performance.
 - b. Listen to opinions or input from employees.
4. Additional benefits This aspect measures the extent to which individuals are satisfied with the additional benefits they receive from the organization or company. Additional benefits are given to employees fairly and proportionally, such as:
 - a. The company fulfills the living needs of employees.
 - b. The company fulfills the living needs of each employee's family.
5. Rewards This aspect measures the extent to which individuals feel satisfied with the rewards given based on work results. Every individual wants their efforts, hard work, and dedication for the advancement of the organization to be properly appreciated, such as:
 - a. Awards for employee achievements.
 - b. Recognition of employee duties and responsibilities.
6. Work procedures and regulations This aspect measures satisfaction with workplace procedures and regulations. Matters related to workplace procedures and regulations affect an individual's job satisfaction, such as bureaucracy and workload, including:
 - a. Work in accordance with company procedures.
 - b. Comply with company work regulations.

7. Coworkers This aspect measures job satisfaction related to relationships with coworkers. Coworkers who provide support to other colleagues, as well as a comfortable working atmosphere can increase employee job satisfaction. For example, pleasant coworkers or harmonious relationships with coworkers, such as:
 - a. Satisfaction with relationships with coworkers.
 - b. Satisfaction with relationship with superiors.
8. The work itself This aspect measures job satisfaction with regard to things related to the work itself, such as opportunities for recreation and variety of tasks, opportunities to occupy oneself, increased knowledge, responsibility, autonomy, job enrichment, and job complexity, such as:
 - a. Work that suits your abilities.
 - b. Challenging work.
9. Communication This aspect measures satisfaction related to communication that occurs in the work. With smooth communication in the organization, employees can better understand their tasks and everything that happens in the organization, such as:
 - a. Communication with superiors or leaders.
 - b. Communication between employees.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

- H1 Organizational Commitment has a Positive and Significant Influence on Work Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H2 Work Quality has a positive and significant influence on Work Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H3 Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H4 Job Satisfaction can moderate Organizational Commitment to Work Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H5 Job Satisfaction can moderate Work Quality towards Work Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

METHOD

Types of research

This type of research uses quantitative research. The approach and type of research used in this study are quantitative. According to Sinambela (2021) quantitative research is a type of research that uses numbers in processing data to produce structured information.

Time and Place of Research

This research was conducted from September to October 2024. The location of this research was at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province, Jalan Balai Kota No. 4 Medan.

Data source

This study uses primary data sources as research support. The data sources used in writing this thesis are primary data. According to Sanusi (2017), primary data is data that is first recorded and collected by researchers.

Data collection technique

To collect data from respondents, researchers use a questionnaire technique where the questionnaire will be distributed to respondents and will be filled in by respondents. Questionnaire According to Sanusi (2017), a data questionnaire often does not require the presence of researchers, but is simply represented by a list of questions that have been carefully prepared in advance.

Research Population

The population of this study was all employees of the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province, amounting to 70 employees. According to Sanusi (2017), population is the entire collection of elements that show certain characteristics that can be used to make conclusions.

Research Sample

The research sample used by the researcher was all respondents who were made into a population of 70 employees. According to Sugiyono (2017), a sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population. So it can be said that the sample is a part that can represent the entire population.

Data Analysis Techniques

Partial Least Square (PLS)

The data analysis that will be conducted to test this research is by the Partial Least Square (PLS) method. The PLS method was chosen based on previous research and it was considered that in this study there were two latent variables with formative indicators. The model used in this study is a causality model or influence relationship.

Outer Model Test (Measurement Model)

Evaluation of the outer model aims to see the form of the relationship between the indicator and its latent variables. The outer test consists of:

1. Standard Loading Factor An indicator is declared valid if it has a loading factor value above 0.5 for the intended construct. The higher the value obtained indicates the higher validity of the indicator.

2. T-Statistics The criterion point of T-Statistics is 1.96; which is the critical value in the T distribution at a significance level of 5%. The higher the T value obtained indicates the higher validity of the indicator.
3. AVE (Average Variance Extracted) AVE shows the variance value obtained from each latent variable. The minimum value required is 0.5. The higher the AVE value obtained, the better and indicates the greater information obtained and produced by the latent variable.
4. Composite Reliability and Cranbach's Alpha In addition to AVE to find the reliability of each variable can use Composite Reliability. The limit value used to assess an acceptable level of reliability is CR 0.7.
5. Cross-Loading The criteria in Cross-Loading is that each indicator that measures its construct must correlate more highly than other constructs.

Inner Model Test (Structural Model)

1. T-Statistics To test the significance of the hypothesized path, the test tool used is T-Statistics. If using an alpha level of 5%, then the critical value for T-Statistics is 1.96. If the value obtained is in the range of $-1.96 < T\text{-Stat} < 1.96$ then the test is declared insignificant. Conversely, if $T\text{-Statistics} < -1.96$ or > 1.96 then it is declared significant.
2. R-Square R-squared (R²) testing is a way to measure the level of Goodness of Fit (GOF) of a structural model. The Rsquared (R²) value is used to assess how much influence a particular independent latent variable has on the dependent latent variable. R² of 0.67 indicates that the model is categorized as good.

SEM Analysis With Moderation Effect

According to Baron & Kenny and Henseler & Fassott, in general, the moderation effect shows the interaction between exogenous variables (predictors) and moderator variables in influencing endogenous variables (Ghozali, 2021). As is known, Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) is one method that can be used to test the moderation effect using a program, which is a common method used in multiple linear regression analysis by entering a third variable in the form of a multiplication of two independent variables as a moderating variable. This will cause a non-linear relationship so that the measurement error of the MRA estimation coefficient if using latent variables becomes inconsistent and biased. So the solution that can be done is to use a structural equation model where SEM can correct this measurement error by entering the interaction effect into the model (Ghozali, 2021).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Measurement model testing (outer model) is used to determine the specifications of the relationship between latent variables and their manifest variables, this testing includes convergent validity, discriminant validity and reliability.

Convergent Validity

Convergent validity is used to determine the validity of each indicator against its latent variable, in SmartPLS software to see the results of validity, it can be seen in the outer loading table. In the outer loading table there are numbers or values that indicate the indicator shows similarity with its construct variable. The value for the indicator is said to be valid, if the indicator explains its construct variable with a value > 0.7 . The structural model in this study is shown in the following figure:

Figure 2: Outer Model
Source; Smart PLS 3.3.3

Smart PLS output for loading factor gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two equations.

$$Y = b_1X_1 + b_2Z + b_3X_1Z + e_1$$

$$Y = 0.098 X_1 + 0.495Z + 0.004X_1Z + e_1$$

$$Y = b_2X_2 + b_3Z + b_4X_2Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.203X_2 + 0.495 Z - 0.173 X_2Z + e_2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Job Satisfaction (Z)	Organizational Commitment (X1)	Quality of Work (X2)	Work Performance (Y)
X1.1		0.888		
X1.2		0.819		
X1.3		0.873		
X2.1			0.789	
X2.2			0.902	
X2.3			0.854	
Y.1				0.848
Y.2				0.891
Y.3				0.856
Y.4				0.872
Z.1	0.738			
Z.2	0.892			
Z.3	0.859			
Z.4	0.835			

Z.5	0.869			
Z.6	0.889			
Z.7	0.839			
Z.8	0.772			
Z.9	0.812			

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

It can be seen in table 1 above that each variable has an outer loadings indicator whose value must be greater than 0.7, so the outer loadings results are stated as valid. Each variable gets a value greater than 0.7, which means that all outer loadings indicators are considered valid and can continue with further research.

Discriminant Validity

Discriminant Validity can be tested by looking at the cross loading table, this output is used to test discriminant validity at the indicator level with the provision that the correlation between the indicator and its latent variable is > compared to the correlation between the indicator and other latent variables (outside its block). For more details, see the table below:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Job Satisfaction (Z)	Organizational Commitment (X1)	Quality of Work (X2)	Work Performance (Y)
X1.1	0.849	0.888	0.807	0.703
X1.2	0.708	0.819	0.570	0.727
X1.3	0.724	0.873	0.762	0.636
X2.1	0.673	0.777	0.789	0.566
X2.2	0.750	0.697	0.902	0.680
X2.3	0.646	0.651	0.854	0.694
Y.1	0.694	0.687	0.724	0.848
Y.2	0.712	0.671	0.651	0.891
Y.3	0.717	0.657	0.650	0.856
Y.4	0.802	0.765	0.629	0.872
Z.1	0.738	0.607	0.561	0.686
Z.2	0.892	0.761	0.759	0.656
Z.3	0.859	0.737	0.710	0.669
Z.4	0.835	0.790	0.816	0.681
Z.5	0.869	0.786	0.718	0.761
Z.6	0.889	0.785	0.686	0.795
Z.7	0.839	0.794	0.632	0.763
Z.8	0.772	0.677	0.553	0.615
Z.9	0.812	0.702	0.651	0.697

Source; Smart PLS 3.3.3

Based on table 2 above, there is a cross loading value for each variable and each indicator can be explained that the cross loading of Job Satisfaction is greater than the cross loading of other latent variables. For the cross loading of the Organizational Commitment variable, there is a value that is greater than the cross loading value of other latent variables. For the cross loading of the Work Quality variable, the value can be seen to be greater than the cross loading value of other latent variables. For the cross loading of the Work Achievement variable, the value can be seen to be greater than the cross loading value of other latent variables. So it can be concluded that the cross loading value has a value that is greater than the value of other latent variables so that it can be considered valid discriminatively.

Composite reliability

The next test determines the reliable value with the composite reliability of each construct, the construct value that is considered reliable is where the composite reliability value is above 0.6 or greater than 0.6. If the Cronbach's alpha value is also greater than 0.7, then the value of each construct in the block is considered reliable in each variable construct and if the AVE value is also above 0.7, then each variable construct is considered valid. The following is a table of loading values for the research variable constructs generated from running the Smart PLS program in the following table:

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Moderation Effect 1	1,000	1,000	1,000
Moderation Effect 2	1,000	1,000	1,000
Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.945	0.954	0.698
Organizational Commitment (X1)	0.825	0.895	0.741
Quality of Work (X2)	0.807	0.886	0.722
Work Performance (Y)	0.890	0.924	0.751

Source; Smart PLS 3.3.3

Based on table 3 above, there is a Cronbach alpha block where the value of each variable is greater than 0.7 so that it can be interpreted as Cronbach alpha reliability data. Based on the composite reliability block, there is a value of each variable greater than 0.6 so that it can be explained that the value is considered composite reliability. Based on the AVE block, there is a value of each variable greater than 0.7, it can be explained that the AVE value greater than 0.7 can be interpreted as a valid distributed value so that it can be explained that all the blocks listed above have values greater than their basic values so that they are considered reliable and valid.

Inner Model Analysis

Structural model evaluation (inner model) is conducted to ensure that the structural model built is robust and accurate. The stages of analysis carried out in the structural model evaluation are seen from several indicators, namely:

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Work Performance (Y)	0.761	0.743

Source; Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 4, there is an R square value for the Work Performance variable with a value of 0.761, so the influence of the Organizational Commitment and Work Quality variables on Work Performance is 0.761 if expressed as a percentage of 76.1% and the rest is in other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After assessing the inner model, the next step is to evaluate the relationship between latent constructs as hypothesized in this study. Hypothesis testing in this study was conducted by looking at the T-Statistics and P-Values. The hypothesis is accepted if the T-Statistics value is > 1.96 and P-Values < 0.05. The following are the results of the Path Coefficients of direct influence:

Table 5. Hypothesis Results and Moderation Effects

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV I)	P Values	Results
Moderation Effect 1 -> Job Performance (Y)	0.004	0.035	0.486	Rejected
Moderation Effect 2 -> Job Performance (Y)	-0.173	1,911	0.028	Accepted
Job Satisfaction (Z) -> Job Performance (Y)	0.495	3,050	0.001	Accepted
Organizational Commitment (X1) -> Work Performance (Y)	0.098	0.643	0.260	Rejected
Work Quality (X2) -> Work Performance (Y)	0.203	1,848	0.033	Accepted

Source; Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 5 there are the results of the hypothesis and the results of moderation which will be explained as follows:

1. Job satisfaction is not able to moderate organizational commitment to work performance with an original sample value of 0.004 and p values of 0.486, meaning that job satisfaction is not a moderating variable because it is not able to influence it significantly.
2. Job Satisfaction is able to moderate and weaken Work Quality towards Work Performance with an original sample value of -0.173 and p values of 0.018, meaning that employees who are satisfied with their work will not think about improving their quality anymore because they are satisfied with their current achievements and do not think about improving their quality to achieve their work.
3. Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Job Performance with an original sample value of 0.495 and p values of 0.001. If job satisfaction increases and one seeks

other job satisfaction, then job performance will increase. If satisfaction decreases and one is only satisfied with the job that one has, then it is certain that job performance will decrease.

4. Organizational commitment has a positive and insignificant effect on work performance with an original sample value of 0.098 and p values of 0.260, meaning that organizational commitment has little effect in improving performance because it is not certain that people who are committed have good work performance and it is not certain that people who are not committed do not have performance.
5. Work quality has a positive and significant effect on work performance with an original sample value of 0.203 and p values of 0.033, meaning that if work quality increases, work performance will increase. If it decreases, work performance will decrease.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Job Satisfaction is unable to moderate Organizational Commitment to Job Performance with an original sample value of 0.004 and p values of 0.486.
2. Job Satisfaction is able to moderate and weaken Work Quality towards Work Performance with an original sample value of -0.173 and p values of 0.018.
3. Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Job Performance with an original sample value of 0.495 and p values of 0.001.
4. Organizational Commitment has a positive and insignificant effect on Work Performance with an original sample value of 0.098 and p values of 0.260.
5. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance with an original sample value of 0.203 and p values of 0.033.

Suggestion

1. This research is expected to be used as input for organizations in solving problems and improving organizational performance.
2. Organizations must seek or recruit employees who have high commitment or increase organizational commitment with existing employees.
3. To get good results, the organization must have quality employees at work. If it is difficult to find quality employees, it is better to provide training to improve the quality of employee work.
4. The organization must make an agreement for employees that if they achieve good work performance, the employees will receive appropriate compensation.
5. Organizations must ensure that their employees are not easily satisfied with their work and must continue to improve their work skills over time in order to develop the organization in the future.
6. It is hoped that this research can be used as reference material for new research and can be a means of creating new research titles and developing them.

REFERENCES

- Anwar Sanusi, 2017. Metode Penelitian Bisnis. Cetakan Ketujuh, Penerbit Salemba Empat, Jln. Raya Lenteng Agung No.101, Jagakarsa, Jakarta Selatan, 12610
- A.A. Anwar Prabu Mangkunegara. 2017. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan, Bandung : Remaja Rosdakarya.

- Ghozali, I. (2021). *Partial Least Squares Konsep, Teknik dan Aplikasi Menggunakan Program SmartPLS 3.2.9 Untuk Penelitian Empiris* (3 ed.). Universitas Diponegoro Semarang.
- Hasibuan, H. M. (2019). *Manajemen Sumberdaya Manusia*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- Kreitner, Robert dan Angelo Kinicki. 2014. *Perilaku Organisasi*. Edisi 9. Buku 1. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- Mardiyana, Sutanto, A., & Abdul Choliq Hidayat. (2019). Pengaruh Kepuasan Kerja dan Komitmen Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Bank Pembiayaan Rakyat Syariah Daerah Istimewa Yogyakarta. *Jurnal Sains Manajemen Dan Bisnis Indonesia*, 9(2), 100–113.
- M M Sengkey. 2021. “Pengaruh Dukungan Sosial Rekan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Kota Tomohon.” *Psikopedia* 2(1). <http://ejurnal-mapalus>
- Priansa D. Juni. (2016). *Perencanaan & Pengembangan SDM*. Bandung : Alfabeta.
- Robbins, Stephen P. (2016). *Perilaku Organisasi*. Jakarta Selatan : Salemba Empat.
- Ristanti, J., & Dihan, N. (2016). Pengaruh Kualitas Kehidupan Kerja Dan Kepuasan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan PT Pertamina Persero RU IV Cilacap. *Jurnal Akuntansi dan Pendidikan*, 5(1).
- Sule, E.T., & Priansa., D.J. (2018). *Kepemimpinan dan Perilaku Organisasi (Membangun Organisasi Unggul di Era Perubahan)*. Bandung: PT. Refika Aditama.
- Sugiyono, (2017). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: CV. Alfabeta.
- Sinambela, Lijan Poltak dan Sarton Sinambela (2021). *Metodologi Penelitian Kuantitatif - Teori Dan Praktik*. Depok: Rajawali Pers.
- Siyoto, S. & Sodik, A. 2015, *Dasar Metodologi Penelitian, Literasi Media Publishing*, Yogyakarta.
- Tanjung, H. (2015). Pengaruh disiplin kerja dan motivasi kerja terhadap prestasi kerja pegawai pada dinas sosial dan tenaga kerja kota Medan. *Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen dan Bisnis*.

Optimizing Work Performance

Dadang Fahrudi Ritonga¹, Muhammad Isa Indrawan²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: dadangritongase@gmail.com

Abstract

Employees are not just resources, but rather capital or assets for institutions or organizations. Because of this, a new term emerged outside of human resources, namely human capital. Here human resources are seen not just as the main asset, but an asset that is valuable and can be multiplied, developed (compared with an investment portfolio) and not vice versa as a liability (expense). Here the perspective of human resources as an investment for institutions or organizations is more prominent. The results of this research are as follows: Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with a value of 0.518 and a significant value of 0.000. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance with a value of 0.195 and a significant value of 0.035. Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Job Performance with a value of 0.554 and a significant 0.000. Job Stress has a negative and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with a value of -0.412 and a significant value of 0.000. Job Stress has a negative and significant effect on Job Performance with a value of -0.211 and a significant value of 0.036. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on work performance through organizational commitment with a value of 0.287 and a significant value of 0.000. Job Stress has a negative and significant effect on Job Performance through Organizational Commitment with a value of -0.228 and a significant value of 0.001.

Keywords: Job Stress, Organizational Culture, Organizational Commitment, Job Performance

INTRODUCTION

In essence, human resources are people who are employed in an organization as drivers, thinkers and planners to achieve the goals of the organization. Employees are not merely resources, but rather more like capital or assets for institutions or organizations. The definition of human resources can be divided into two, namely the micro definition and the macro definition. Workplace stress is experienced almost every day by employees in big cities. The workforce in big cities, including Medan, mostly consists of urban and industrial workers. They are often constrained by deadlines for completing tasks, diverse and increasingly large work environments, interpersonal conflicts, high turnover rates, and various other factors that contribute to stress. Zainal et al. (2014) argue that stress is an umbrella term that includes pressure, burden, conflict, fatigue, tension, panic, anxiety and depression. Work stress is a condition of tension that creates physical and psychological imbalances, which affect the emotions, thought processes, and conditions of an employee. Corporate culture is one way to building human resources companies through aspects of attitude and behavior change. This aims to make employees become better individuals and can adapt to facing challenges in the industrial era towards society. This is where HR functions in organizations required. Employees in the organization will learn and adapt to the prevailing culture, what is good and bad, right and wrong, what is allowed and what is not, and other regulations. At the same time, each member is aware that the role of organizational culture is very important for the progress of the company and the results of the work. Organizational culture refers to the beliefs and principles of the organization. Each organization has its own unique culture. Employee work performance is very important in the company to achieve its goals, so the company makes various efforts to improve it.

Achievement in work is one of the needs that everyone wants to achieve in working. Organizations that have employees who have good work performance will certainly greatly encourage the progress of the organization. With this progress, the organization will be able to increase its competitiveness and have competitive capabilities. In improving employee work performance, of course, it is not easy, every organization must certainly do various ways so that each employee is able to improve their work performance. By having disciplined employees, a comfortable work environment, good motivation, and high salaries, it will further encourage each employee to improve their work performance better than before. Organizational Commitment has long been an important topic and is relatively often discussed in the world of work. This can be seen from the many organizations that include the element of Commitment as one of the requirements to fill positions in the organization. Organizational commitment is considered important because it can influence the behavior and relationships of members in the organization such as attendance, performance, and willingness to remain in the organization.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Job Stress have a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
2. Does Job Stress have a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
3. Does Job Stress Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Job Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
4. Does Job Stress Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Job Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
5. Does Organizational Commitment have a positive and significant effect on Work Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
6. Does Job Stress Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Work Performance through Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
7. Does Job Stress Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Work Performance through Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Stress on Organizational Commitment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
2. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Culture on Organizational Commitment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
3. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Stress on Work Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
4. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Culture on Work Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
5. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Commitment on Work Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
6. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Stress on Work Performance through Organizational Commitment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

7. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Culture on Work Performance through Organizational Commitment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Work performance

Definition of Work Performance

According to Sutrisno (2018) Work performance as a person's level of competence in tasks that include his work, understanding the weight of individual abilities in fulfilling the provisions in the work. According to Badriyah (2018) Work performance is the work results achieved by a person in carrying out the tasks assigned to him, which are based on skills, experience, and sincerity and time.

Work Performance Indicators

According to Sutrisno (2018), work performance indicators are as follows:

1. Work Results The level of quantity and quality that has been produced and the extent to which supervision has been carried out
2. Job knowledge The level of knowledge related to job tasks that will directly influence the quantity and quality of work results.
3. Initiative The level of initiative during carrying out work tasks, especially in terms of handling problems that arise.
4. Time and attendance discipline Level of punctuality and attendance level
5. Attitude The level of work enthusiasm and positive attitude in carrying out work tasks
6. Mental agility The level of ability and speed in receiving work instructions and completing existing work situations in a work manner.

Job Stress

Understanding Job Stress

According to (Oemar & Gangga 2017) stress is a dynamic condition in which an individual is faced with opportunities, limitations, or demands in accordance with expectations of the results to be achieved in important and uncertain conditions.

Job Stress Indicators

According to (Oemar & Gangga, 2017) the indicators of work stress are as follows:

1. Working conditions Unbalanced working environment and workload.
2. Role issues: There is a separation of functions and duties for each employee.
3. Interpersonal relationships: Employee relationships with co-workers or relationships with superiors.
4. Career development opportunities There are no career development opportunities available in a company.
5. Organizational structure and climate Clarity in the division of authority and tasks of each employee.

Organizational culture

Understanding Organizational Culture

According to Hari (2019), organizational culture is the values that human resources adhere to in carrying out their obligations and behavior within the organization.

Organizational Culture Indicators

According to Hari (2019) the indicators of organizational culture are

1. Innovative in taking risks into account. That every employee will pay sensitive attention to any problems that may pose a risk of loss to the organization as a whole.
2. Pay attention to every problem in detail. Describes the accuracy and precision of employees in carrying out their duties.
3. Oriented towards the results to be achieved. A manager's supervision of his subordinates is one way for managers to direct and empower them. Through this supervision, the goals of the organization and the group and its members can be described.
4. Oriented to all employee interests. The success or performance of an organization is determined by the work team, where teamwork can be formed if the manager can supervise his subordinates well.
5. Aggressive in working. High productivity can be achieved if employee performance can meet the standards required to perform their duties. Good performance means, among others, skill qualifications that can meet productivity requirements and must be followed by high discipline and workmanship.
6. Maintain and safeguard work stability. Employees must be able to maintain their health condition to remain prime, this condition can only be met if they regularly consume nutritious food based on the advice of a nutritionist.

Organizational Commitment

Understanding Organizational Commitment

According to Mathis and Jackson (2020), organizational commitment is the level of trust and acceptance of the workforce towards organizational goals and having a desire to remain in the organization. According to Porter & Mowday (2020), organizational commitment is a relative strength of an individual in identifying his/her involvement in part of the organization.

Organizational Commitment Indicators

According to Porter & Mowday (2020), organizational commitment has the following indicators:

- 1) Personal characteristics
- 2) Job characteristics and roles
- 3) Structural characteristics of the organization
- 4) Work experience
- 5) Organizational support.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

- H1 Work Stress has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H2 Organizational Culture has a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H3 Work Stress has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H4 Organizational Culture has a positive and significant influence on Work Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H5 Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H6 Work Stress has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance through Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H7 Organizational Culture has a positive and significant influence on Work Performance through Organizational Commitment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

METHOD

Types of research

This research uses quantitative research type, Quantitative research is a type of scientific research that collects and analyzes quantitative data (in the form of numbers and statistics) to understand phenomena or answer research questions. This research tends to use a structured and objective scientific approach, with the aim of testing hypotheses or identifying patterns that occur in the data. According to Suryani and Hendrayadi (2015) quantitative research is research that uses data analysis in the form of numbers or figures. The purpose of quantitative research is to develop and use mathematical models of theories and/or hypotheses related to the phenomena investigated by the researcher.

Time and Place of Research

This research was conducted from September to October 2024. The location of this research was at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province, Jalan Balai Kota No. 4 Medan.

Research Population

The population of this study was 70 research employees, making all employees of the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province as the research population. According to Suryani and Hendryadi (2015) the target population is a population that has special characteristics according to the objectives of the study itself.

Research Sample

The researcher used the research sample of all respondents who were made into a population sample of 70 employees and the sampling technique used was the saturated sampling technique. According to Suryani and Hendryadi (2015) a sample is a portion of the population that will be taken for research and the results of the research are used as a representation of the population as a whole.

Research Data Sources

The research data sources used are primary data sources. According to Suryani and Hendryadi (2015) Primary data is data collected and processed by an organization or individual directly from its object.

Research Data Collection Techniques

This study collects research data by distributing questionnaires to respondents and will be filled and then collected again. According to Suryani and Hendryadi (2015) a questionnaire is a data collection technique carried out by providing a set of questions or statements to other people who are used as respondents to be answered.

Data Analysis Techniques

Partial Least Square (PLS)

Data analysis was carried out using the Partial Least Square (PLS) method using SmartPLS software version 3. PLS is one of the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) solution methods SEM which in this case is more compared to other techniques SEM other. SEM has a higher level of flexibility in research that connects theory and data, and is able to perform path analysis with latent variables so that it is often used by researchers who focus on social sciences. Partial Least Square (PLS) is a fairly strong analysis method because it is not based on many assumptions. Data also does not have to be multivariate normal distribution (indicators with categorical, ordinal, interval to ratio scales can be used in the same model), samples do not have to be large (Gozali, 2014).

Measurement Model or Outer Model

Validity Test

Validity testing is used to assess whether a questionnaire is valid or not. A questionnaire is said to be valid if the questionnaire questions are able to reveal something that is measured by the questionnaire. Validity testing is applied to all question items in each variable. There are several stages of testing that will be carried out, namely through convergent validity, average variance extracted (AVE), and discriminant validity.

Content Validity

The validity of the questionnaire can be determined by using a questionnaire that has been widely used by researchers. The questionnaire used in this study is the result of a literature review with modifications needed to identify different respondent preferences.

Convergent Validity

This convergence test shows whether each question item increases the mean of the same variable. Therefore, only question items with high significance are included, meaning more significant than two standard errors in the correction of question items for research variables. Convergence validity can be compromised when each variable has an AVE value of less than 0.5 and the loading value of each item is less than 0.5. (Ghozali (2014).

Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

This validation task involves calculating the validity of each question by looking at the average variance extracted (AVE). AVE stands for average relative variance Extracted (AVE) between the question item and any indicator which is a summary of convergent

indicators. For optimal performance, if the AVE of each question item is more than 0.5 (Ghozali, 2014).

Discriminant Validity

This validity equation indicates whether two variables differ substantially from each other. As long as the variance of a variable is greater than the variance of all other variables, the validity of the discriminant analysis can be compromised. In addition, another way to assess the validity of the submission can be seen from the cross loading coefficient which is greater than the correlation coefficient of each data item with its own variable (Ghozali, 2014).

Reliability

Overall reliability is defined as the threshold for assessing the quality of a statement based on a particular item. Reliability testing is used to regulate the consistency of responses to a questionnaire or research instrument, or to adjust the consistency of a particular hypothesis. Composite reliability can be used to assess reliability; a variable is said to be reliable if its composite reliability value is at least 0.07 (Sekaran, 2014).

Structural Model or Inner Model

Based on substantive theory, the inner model (also known as inner relationship, structural model, and substantive theory) describes the relationship between latent variables. The structural model is evaluated using R-square for the dependent variable, the Stone-Geisser Q-square test to predict height and t-test, and the significance of the path structure parameters. In determining the model using PLS, it begins by checking the R-square for each dependent variable. The interpretation is the same as the regression interpretation. The R-squared value can be used to determine the relative change in the dependent variable which indicates whether or not there is a significant change (Ghozali, 2014). In addition to looking at the R-square value, the Partial Least Square (PLS) model is also evaluated by looking at the Q-square predictive relevance for the constructive model. Q square measures how well the observation values are generated by the model and also its parameter estimates.

Hypothesis

Hypothesis testing using full model structural equation modeling (SEM) analysis with smartPLS. In full model structural equation modeling, in addition to confirming the theory, it also explains whether or not there is a relationship between latent variables (Ghozali, 2014). Hypothesis testing with the calculated value of the Path Coefficient in the inner model is shown in the Hypothesis equation which is stated as follows: if the T statistic is greater than or equal to the T table 1.96 ($\pm 5\%$), which shows that if the T statistic is greater than or equal to the T table for each hypothesis then it can be stated as follows: analyzed or not.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Measurement model testing (outer model) is used to determine the specifications of the relationship between latent variables and their manifest variables, this testing includes convergent validity, discriminant validity and reliability.

1. Convergent Validity

Convergent validity of the measurement model with reflective indicators can be seen from the correlation between the item/indicator score and the construct score. Individual indicators are considered reliable if they have a correlation value above 0.70. However, in the scale development stage of research, loadings of 0.50 to 0.60 are still acceptable. Based on the results for outer loading, it shows that there are indicators that have loadings below 0.60 and are not significant. The structural model in this study is shown in the following Figure:

Figure 2: Outer Model
Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Smart PLS output for loading factor gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Z = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e_1$$

$$Z = -0.412 X_1 + 0.518X_2 + e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_2X_1 + b_3X_2 + b_4Z + e_2$$

$$Y = -0.211X_1 + 0.195X_2 + 0.554Z + e_2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Organizational Culture (X2)	Organizational Commitment (Z)	Work Performance (Y)	Job Stress (X1)
X1.1				0.898
X1.2				0.766
X1.3				0.901
X1.4				0.874
X1.5				0.816
X2.1	0.774			
X2.2	0.789			
X2.3	0.920			
X2.4	0.884			
X2.5	0.871			
X2.6	0.881			

Y.1			0.860	
Y.2			0.831	
Y.3			0.888	
Y.4			0.802	
Y.5			0.799	
Y.6			0.868	
Z.1		0.893		
Z.2		0.905		
Z.3		0.833		
Z.4		0.840		
Z.5		0.807		

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In the image and table 1 above, all loading factor indicators have a value > 0.7 , meaning that the indicator is a valid indicator because it is greater than 700 or 0.7.

Discriminant Validity

In this section, the results of the discriminant validity test will be described. The discriminant validity test uses the cross loading value. An indicator is declared to meet discriminant validity if the cross loading value of the indicator on its variable is the largest compared to other variables. The following are the cross loading values of each indicator:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Organizational Culture (X2)	Organizational Commitment (Z)	Work Performance (Y)	Job Stress (X1)
X1.1	-0.837	-0.771	-0.733	0.898
X1.2	-0.692	-0.795	-0.801	0.766
X1.3	-0.773	-0.737	-0.751	0.901
X1.4	-0.703	-0.667	-0.671	0.874
X1.5	-0.788	-0.734	-0.728	0.816
X2.1	0.774	0.644	0.694	-0.699
X2.2	0.789	0.685	0.719	-0.608
X2.3	0.920	0.807	0.732	-0.822
X2.4	0.884	0.788	0.727	-0.778
X2.5	0.871	0.771	0.805	-0.857
X2.6	0.881	0.832	0.801	-0.798
Y.1	0.718	0.770	0.860	-0.692
Y.2	0.746	0.739	0.831	-0.658
Y.3	0.775	0.828	0.888	-0.763
Y.4	0.733	0.757	0.802	-0.779
Y.5	0.706	0.771	0.799	-0.769
Y.6	0.737	0.732	0.868	-0.726
Z.1	0.837	0.893	0.807	-0.793
Z.2	0.776	0.905	0.821	-0.780

Z.3	0.718	0.833	0.732	-0.719
Z.4	0.765	0.840	0.751	-0.738
Z.5	0.693	0.807	0.789	-0.714

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

There is a cross loading value of the Organizational Culture variable that is greater than the cross loading of other variables. There is a cross loading value of the Organizational Commitment variable that is greater than the cross loading of other variables. There is a cross loading value of the Work Achievement variable that is greater than the cross loading of other variables. There is a cross loading value of the Work Stress variable that is greater than the cross loading of other variables. Based on the cross loading results above, the value is valid in a discriminant manner for each variable.

Composite reliability

The next test is the composite reliability of the indicator block that measures the construct. A construct is said to be reliable if the composite reliability value is above 0.60. Then it can also be seen by looking at the reliability of the construct or latent variable which is measured by looking at the cronbachs alpha value of the indicator block that measures the construct. A construct is declared reliable if the cronbachs alpha value is above 0.7. The following describes the results of the construct for each variable, namely Job Satisfaction, Employee Performance and Organizational Commitment with each variable and indicator. The following is a table of loading values for the research variable constructs produced by running the Smart PLS program in the following table:

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Organizational Culture (X2)	0.925	0.942	0.731
Organizational Commitment (Z)	0.909	0.932	0.733
Work Performance (Y)	0.917	0.936	0.709
Job Stress (X1)	0.905	0.930	0.727

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 3 above, it can be seen in the cronbach alpha column that each variable has a value greater than 0.7, which means that the reliability data for each variable. The composite reliability column has a value greater than 0.6, so it can be explained that each variable is considered reliable because the data is greater than 0.6. It can be seen from the AVE column that each variable gets a value greater than 0.7, which means that the data is valid according to AVE. All variables from the cronbach alpha column, reliability column and AVE column have values greater than 0.7 and 0.6, so they are considered reliable and valid.

Inner Model Analysis

Structural model evaluation (inner model) is conducted to ensure that the basic model created is strong and accurate. The stages of examination conducted in the primary model assessment are seen from several markers, namely:

1. Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Organizational Commitment (Z)	0.820	0.815
Work Performance (Y)	0.859	0.853

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

There is an R square value in table 4, the Organizational Commitment variable has an R square value of 0.820 so that it can be explained the influence of work stress and organizational culture variables on organizational commitment of 0.820 or 82.0% the rest is on other variables. The work performance variable R square value of 0.859 can be explained the influence of work stress, organizational culture, organizational commitment variables on work performance of 0.859 or 85.9% the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After assessing the inner model, the next step is to evaluate the relationship between latent constructs as hypothesized in this study. Hypothesis testing in this study was conducted by looking at the T-Statistics and P-Values. The hypothesis is accepted if the T-Statistics value is > 1.96 and P-Values < 0.05. The following are the results of the Path Coefficients of direct influence:

Table 5. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Organizational Culture (X2) -> Organizational Commitment (Z)	0.518	5,011	0,000	Accepted
Organizational Culture (X2) -> Work Performance (Y)	0.195	1,811	0.035	Accepted
Organizational Commitment (Z) -> Work Performance (Y)	0.554	5,008	0,000	Accepted
Job Stress (X1) -> Organizational Commitment (Z)	-0.412	3,901	0,000	Accepted
Job Stress (X1) -> Job Performance (Y)	-0.211	1,799	0.036	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 5 there are direct influence results, these results will be explained by the researcher as follows:

1. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with a value of 0.518 and a significance of 0.000. If organizational culture increases, organizational commitment will also increase, conversely, if it decreases, organizational commitment will decrease.
2. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on work performance with a value of 0.195 and a significance of 0.035. If there is an increase in organizational culture,

work performance will also increase. If there is a decrease, work performance will also decrease.

3. Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance with a value of 0.554 and a significance of 0.000. If there is an increase in organizational commitment, there will be an increase in work performance, conversely, if it decreases, work performance will decrease.
4. Work stress has a negative and significant effect on organizational commitment with a value of -0.412 and a significance of 0.000. If work stress decreases, organizational commitment will increase, conversely, if work stress increases, organizational commitment will decrease.
5. Work stress has a negative and significant effect on work performance with a value of -0.211 and a significance of 0.036, meaning that if work stress increases, work performance will decrease and if work stress decreases, work performance will increase.

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Organizational Culture (X2) -> Organizational Commitment (Z) -> Work Performance (Y)	0.287	3,319	0,000	Accepted
Job Stress (X1) -> Organizational Commitment (Z) -> Job Performance (Y)	-0.228	3,301	0.001	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 6 there are the results of the indirect influence that will be explained by the researcher, therefore the results of this study are as follows:

1. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant influence on Work Performance through Organizational Commitment with a value of 0.287 and a significance of 0.000, meaning that organizational commitment is an intervening variable because it is able to influence significantly, meaning that with organizational commitment, it has a good influence on work performance and organizational culture directly and can improve both variables.
2. Work stress has a negative and significant effect on work performance through organizational commitment with a value of -0.228 and a significance of 0.001, meaning that organizational commitment is an intervening variable because it is able to significantly influence work performance and work stress, but commitment is still unable to improve work performance due to the strong work stress that occurs in the organization.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment with a value of 0.518 and a significance of 0.000.
2. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant influence on Work Performance with a value of 0.195 and a significance of 0.035.
3. Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance with a value of 0.554 and a significance of 0.000.
4. Work stress has a negative and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with a value of -0.412 and a significance of 0.000.

5. Work stress has a negative and significant effect on work performance with a value of -0.211 and a significance of 0.036.
6. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant influence on Work Performance through Organizational Commitment with a value of 0.287 and a significance of 0.000.
7. Work stress has a negative and significant effect on work performance through organizational commitment with a value of -0.228 and a significance of 0.001.

Suggestion

1. Organizations must know or see employees who are stressed at work to avoid mistakes at work and give them time to calm their minds, this should be in every organization providing support and advice for employees who are stressed at work instead of adding other work for these employees.
2. Organizations should build a good organizational culture for employees to improve their performance and work results.
3. Organizations must provide compensation to employees who have achievements in the organization to support employee enthusiasm for work.
4. Organizations must increase employee organizational commitment by providing facilities and comfort within the organization.
5. Organizations can use this research as constructive input and reduce internal organizational problems.
6. Other researchers can use this research as reference and supporting material for new research and to develop this research.

REFERENCES

- Badriyah, M. (2018). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*, Cetakan 1. Bandung: CV Pustaka Setia.
- Edy Sutrisno. 2018. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Edisi Pertama. Cetakan Kedua. Kencana Prenada Group. Jakarta.
- Edy Sutrisno, (2019). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Cetak ke sebelas. Prananda Media Group, Jakarta.
- Ghozali, I. 2012. *Partial Least Square : Konsep, Teknik dan Aplikasi Smart PLS 2.0 M3*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Handaru, A.W., Rahman, N.F., & Parimita, W. (2021). Pengaruh Job Insecurity Dan Komitmen Organisasi Terhadap Turnover Intention Pada Karyawan Industri Manufaktur (Automotive Dan Metal Part). *JRMSI - Jurnal Riset Manajemen Sains Indonesia*, 12(1), 15-39.
- Hari sulaksono. 2019. *Budaya organisasi dan kinerja*. Sleman: Deepublish.
- Hendrayadi Suryani, 2015. *Metode Riset Kuantitatif, Teori, Dan Aplikasi Pada Penelitian Bidang Manajemen Dan Ekonomi Islam*, Jakarta: Prenada Media, Hal. 109
- Idrus, A. (2022). *Komitmen*. Tasikmalaya: Perkumpulan Rumah Cemerlang Indonesia.
- Mathis, R. L., and J. H. Jackson. 2016. *Human Resource Management*. Edisi 10 Jilid 3. Salemba Empat. Jakarta.
- Mowday, R. T., Porter, L. W., & Steers, R. M. (2013). *Employee—organization linkages: The psychology of commitment, absenteeism, and turnover*. Academic press.

- Oemar, Usailan dan Leo Gangga. 2017. Pengaruh Stres Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Pada Dinas Pendapatan, Keuangan dan Aset Daerah Kabupaten Musi Manyasin. *Jurnal Ecoment Global*. Jilid 2. 2017.
- Zainal, Veithzal Rivai, dkk. 2014. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Untuk Perusahaan Dari Teori Ke Praktik*. Depok. PT Rajagrafindo Persada.

Optimizing Job Satisfaction

Fandi Wardana¹, Muhammad Isa Indrawan²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: fandywardana16@gmail.com

Abstract

This research aims to examine the influence of work motivation and discipline on job satisfaction with compensation as an intervening variable at the Bank Indonesia Pematangsiantar Representative Office. Humans (HR) are the most important factor in the growth and development of an organization or business. That in conditions of globalization, human quality in companies is always a source of competition. Companies that want to grow and develop well must organize their human resources intellectually, spiritually, creatively, morally and responsibly. The results of this research are as follows: Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.267 and a p value of 0.048. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on compensation with an original sample value of 0.269 and a p value of 0.042. Compensation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.350 and a p value of 0.011. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.315 and a p value of 0.045. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on compensation with an original sample value of 0.624 and a p value of 0.000. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Compensation with an original sample value of 0.094 and a p value of 0.105. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Compensation with an original sample value of 0.218 and a p value of 0.014.

Keywords: Motivation, Work Discipline, Compensation, Job Satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

The success of an organization or institution in achieving its goals is inseparable from human resources, because HR organizes and manages other resources owned by the organization to help realize the goals of the organization itself, because the success or failure of the organization in achieving its goals depends on its human resources. Human Resources (HR) are the most important factor in the growth and development of an organization or business. Personal quality greatly affects the performance of these human resources and the performance of the company in general, so it is necessary to improve employee performance. (Pangaila et al., 2022). Employee work motivation in an organization can be considered simple and can also be a complex problem, because basically humans are easy to motivate by giving what they want. If someone is motivated, he will try his best to realize what he wants. Motivation is an encouragement to someone in carrying out their work activities, so with motivation it means there is direction about what must be done and done to achieve the desired goals. Work discipline can be interpreted as a condition that is created and formed through a process of a series of behaviors that show the values of obedience, compliance, loyalty, order and order. Discipline is very important for human life, because discipline must be instilled continuously so that discipline becomes a habit. People who succeed in their work generally have high discipline, while people who fail are generally not disciplined. Discipline is a process of training and learning to improve the ability to act, think and work actively and creatively. Compensation is a reward given by the company to employees for their services in carrying out the tasks, obligations, and responsibilities assigned to them in order to achieve the company's goals. Compensation is important for employees because the amount of compensation reflects the size of the employee's work value, namely co-workers,

family, and society. An adequate compensation system, especially in relation to employee work motivation, should be owned by a company or business unit with higher environmental uncertainty. Compensation plays an important role in improving employee performance. One of the main reasons someone works is to meet their life needs. A person will work optimally in order to get appropriate compensation. Job satisfaction is an important condition that every employee who works must have, where the person is able to interact with their work environment and it is hoped that they will work enthusiastically and seriously so that their contribution to achieving the company's goals will increase.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Motivation have a positive and significant effect on Compensation at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar?
2. Does Work Discipline Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Compensation at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar?
3. Does Motivation have a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar?
4. Does Work Discipline have a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar?
5. Does Compensation have a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar?
6. Does Motivation Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Job Satisfaction through Compensation at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar?
7. Does Work Discipline Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Job Satisfaction through Compensation at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of Motivation on Compensation at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, Pematangsiantar.
2. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Discipline on Compensation at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, Pematangsiantar.
3. To determine and analyze the influence of Motivation on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, Pematangsiantar.
4. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Discipline on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar.
5. To determine and analyze the influence of Compensation on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar.
6. To determine and analyze the influence of Motivation on Job Satisfaction through Compensation at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar.
7. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Discipline on Job Satisfaction through Compensation at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Job satisfaction

Understanding Job Satisfaction

According to Jufrizen & Sitorus (2021), Job Satisfaction is a pleasant psychological state felt by workers in a work environment because their needs are adequately met. Job Satisfaction is defined by looking at the extent to which individuals feel positively or

negatively various factors or dimensions of the tasks in their work. Job Satisfaction is an emotional attitude that is pleasant and loves one's job (Atmaja, 2022).

Job Satisfaction Indicators

Job Satisfaction Indicators according to Atmaja (2022) include:

1. Payment of wages/salaries.
2. Work environment, which includes physical and non-physical work environment factors.
3. Working group.
4. Supervision.

Motivation

Understanding Motivation

According to Afandi (2021), motivation is a desire that arises from within a person or individual because he is inspired, encouraged and encouraged to carry out activities with sincerity, joy and sincerity so that the results of the activities he carries out are good and of good quality. Motivation is generally related to each goal, while organizational goals focus on work-related behavior (Robbins and Jugde, 2018).

Motivation Indicators

According to Afandi (2021), the dimensions and indicators of motivation are divided into two dimensions and six indicators, namely:

- a) The dimension of peace is happy, comfortable and enthusiastic because needs are met.
The first dimension indicator is divided into 3, namely:
 - (1) Remuneration Remuneration is anything in the form of goods, services and money which is compensation received by employees for their services involved in the organization.
 - (2) Working Conditions Working conditions are a series of conditions or circumstances of the work environment of a company which is the place of work for employees who work in that environment.
 - (3) Work Facilities Work facilities are supporting facilities in company activities in physical form, and are used in normal company activities, have a relatively permanent useful life and provide benefits for the future.
- b) The dimension of the drive to get the best possible, the indicators of dimension two are divided into three, namely:
 - (1) Work performance Work performance is a work result achieved by a person in carrying out the tasks assigned to him based on skill, experience, sincerity and time.
 - (2) Recognition from superiors Recognition from superiors for achievements in work carried out in an organization should always be tailored to the employee concerned. Each person has different needs, therefore they need to be recognized in different ways.
 - (3) The work itself The work itself is a situation where employees find interesting tasks, opportunities to learn and opportunities to take responsibility for their work.

Work Discipline

Understanding Work Discipline

According to Sari (2019) Work discipline is a person's awareness and willingness to obey all company regulations and applicable norms. According to Hasibuan (2020) discipline is the key to a company's success in achieving its goals. It will be difficult for the

company to achieve its goals if employees are indisciplined/comply with the company's regulations.

Work Discipline Indicators

According to Hasibuan (2020), the discipline indicators are as follows:

1. Goals and abilities Goals and abilities are goals to be achieved must be clear and challenging enough for the employee's abilities. This means that the work goals assigned to employees must be in accordance with the employee's abilities so that they can work seriously and disciplined in their work. However, if the work is beyond their abilities or far from their abilities, the employee's sincerity and discipline are low.
2. Leadership examples Leadership examples play a very important role in determining employee discipline because leaders are used as role models and role models by their subordinates.
3. Rewards Rewards also influence employee discipline because rewards will give employees satisfaction and love for the company.
4. Justice Justice helps to create employee discipline because of the ego and human nature that always feels important and asks to be treated the same as other humans.
5. Close Supervision (Waskat) Waskat is the most effective real action in realizing employee discipline. With Waskat, it means that superiors must be active and supervise the work behavior of their subordinates.
6. Punishment sanctions Punishment sanctions play an important role in maintaining employee discipline, with increasingly severe punishment sanctions, employees will be increasingly afraid of violating company regulations.
7. Firmness The firmness of the leader in taking action will affect the discipline of the company's employees. The leader must dare to be more firm, acting to punish any undisciplined employee in accordance with the established punishment sanctions.
8. Human relations Harmonious human relations among fellow employees create good discipline in a company.

Compensation

Definition of Compensation

According to Simamora (2015) compensation is a broad terminology related to financial rewards received by people through their employment relationship with an organization. According to Hasibuan (2017) compensation is all income in the form of money, goods, directly or indirectly received as compensation for services received by employees as compensation to the company.

Compensation Indicators

Compensation indicators, according to Simamora (2017), are:

1. Wages and salaries
2. Incentives
3. Allowances
4. Facilities
5. Bonus

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

- H1 Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Compensation at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar.
- H2 Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Compensation at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar.
- H3 Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar.
- H4 Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar.
- H5 Compensation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar.
- H6 Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Compensation at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar.
- H7 Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Compensation at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar.

METHOD

Types of Research

In this study, the researcher used quantitative research as the research material. According to Sujarweni (2014), quantitative research is a type of research that produces findings that can be achieved (obtained) using statistical procedures or other means of quantification (measurement).

Research Location and Research Time

This research was conducted at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia Pematangsiantar, Jalan Adam Malik No.1 Pematangsiantar. This research was conducted from September to October 2024.

Research Population

The researcher used the research population as all employees of the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar and the number of employees was 40 employees, that is the population of this study. Meanwhile, according to V. Wiratna Sujarweni (2014)

stated that: "Population is the total number consisting of objects or subjects that have certain characteristics and qualities determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions are drawn".

Research Sample

The sample used by the researcher is all the population will be sampled by the researcher so that the sample of this study is 40 employees, the sampling technique in this study uses the saturated sampling technique. According to Sugiyono (2017) a sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population. According to Narimawati (2015) a sample is part of the population selected to be a unit of observation in research.

Research Data Sources

The data source of this study is using primary data sources as reference materials in the study. According to Umar (2015) is primary data that has been further processed and presented by the primary data collector or by other parties, for example in the form of tables or diagrams.

Data collection technique

The data collection technique in this study used a research questionnaire and distributed it to respondents to answer. According to Sugiyono (2017), a questionnaire is a data collection method carried out by giving a set of written questions or statements to respondents to answer.

Data Analysis Techniques

According to Ghozali & Latan (2015), the purpose of PLS-SEM is to develop theory or build theory (prediction orientation). PLS is used to explain whether or not there is a relationship between latent variables (prediction). PLS is a powerful analysis method because it does not assume current data with a certain scale of measurement, a small number of samples (Ghozali, 2014). This study has a complex model and a limited number of samples, so in data analysis using SmartPLS software. SmartPLS uses the bootstrapping method or random duplication. Therefore, the assumption of normality will not be a problem. In addition, by doing bootstrapping, SmartPLS does not require a minimum number of samples, so it can be applied to research with a small number of samples.

Measurement Model Test or Outer Model

The measurement or external model shows how each indicator block relates to the latent variable. The method of evaluating the measurement model using confirmatory factor analysis is by using the MTMM (MultiTrait-MultiMethod) approach, which examines discriminant and convergent validity. In contrast, reliability assessment is carried out in two ways: through Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (Ghozali & Latan, 2015).

a. Convergent "Validity

The convergence validity of the regression model with reflective indicators can be shown in the correlation between item/indicator scores and construct scores. Individual reflectivity is declared high if it correlates with the desired form of more than 0.70. However, in terms of improvement, loadings between 0.50 and 0.60 can be achieved (Ghozali & Latan, 2015).

b. Discriminant “Validity

The discriminant validity of an indicator can be seen from the cross-loading between the indicator and its construct. If the correlation between the construct and its indicator is higher than the correlation between the indicator and other constructs, then this indicates that the 38th construct indicator in the block is more accurate than the indicators in other blocks.

Another way to determine discriminant validity is to compare the average variance extracted ($\sqrt{AVE}$) of each construct with the correlation between each construct and other constructs using the model. The model is said to have good discriminant validity if the AVE of each construct is greater than the correlation between the construct and other constructs (Gozali, 2014). In Ghazali & Latan (2015) additional questions are explained to determine the validity of the construct by looking at the AVE value. The model is said to be good if the average value of each construct is greater than or equal to 0.50.

c. Reliability "In addition to the validity test

In addition, model revisions were conducted to assess the reliability of the construction. Reliability testing was conducted to ensure the accuracy, consistency, and responsiveness of the instrument in terms of “construction”. In PLS-SEM with the SmartPLS 3.0 application, there are two methods available to assess the reliability of a construct with reflective indicators, namely Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability. According to Ghazali and Latan (2015), a construct is said to be reliable if its composite reliability coefficient is at least 0.70 (cronbach alpha).

Structural Model or Inner Model Test

- a. R-Square: "When determining the structural model, it will be more accurate to determine the RSquare for each endogenous variable as a measure of the model's predictive strength." Structural model analysis is done by looking at the R-square which is a goodness-of-fit model. The R-squared value can be used to describe the influence of the current exogenous latent variable on the endogenous latent variable, especially whether it has a significant influence. It can be concluded from the RSquare values of 0.75, 0.50, and 0.25 that the model is strong, moderate, and "weak" (Ghozali & Latan, 2015).
- b. F-Square: This f-square calculation is used to determine the goodness of the model. F-square values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 can be used to assess whether the slow predictor variable has a small, medium, or large influence on the structural threshold (Ghozali, 2014).
- c. Estimate “For Path Coefficients The second step is to test the significance of the variance between variables by examining the parameter determination coefficient and the statistical significance of T which is carried out using the “bootstrapping” method (Ghozali & Latan, 2015).

Indirect Effect Test

The purpose of this experiment is to observe the significant effect of nonlinear random variables. This study was conducted using the bootstrapping method with smartPLS 3.0. In this study there is one intervening variable, namely functional audit performance. Intervening variables are defined as having the ability to mitigate the influence of exogenous (independent) variables on endogenous (dependent) variables if the T statistic value is higher when compared to the table and the P value is lower than the significance threshold used (5%).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

The purpose of external model evaluation is to determine the validity and dependability of the model. This test study will investigate the impact of loading variables, average variance extracted (AVE), discriminant validity, and composite reliability.

Convergent Validity

This test is seen from the loading factor, the value limit is 0.7, and the value limit Average Variance Extracted. (AVE) is 0.5, if above this value it is said to be valid. This means that the value for the indicator is said to be valid, if the indicator explains the construct variable with a value > 0.7 . The structural model used in this study is shown in the figure below:

Table 1. Outer Loadings/Cross Loading Stage 1

	Work Discipline (X2)	Job Satisfaction (Y)	Compensation (Z)	Motivation (X1)
X1.1				0.858
X1.2				0.861
X1.3				0.796
X1.4				0.741
X1.5				0.822
X1.6				0.825
X2.1	0.825			
X2.2	0.841			
X2.3	0.786			
X2.4	0.643			
X2.5	0.783			
X2.6	0.834			
X2.7	0.883			
X2.8	0.828			
Y.1		0.880		
Y.2		0.871		
Y.3		0.803		
Y.4		0.823		
Z.1			0.734	
Z.2			0.895	
Z.3			0.850	
Z.4			0.859	
Z.5			0.821	

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

In table 1 there is an outer loading of each variable and indicator but there is an invalid indicator, namely in indicator X2.4 with the work discipline variable. To continue the research, the invalid indicators will be deleted and then retested and the test is as follows:

Table 2. Outer Loadings/Cross Loading Stage 2

	Work Discipline (X2)	Job Satisfaction (Y)	Compensation (Z)	Motivation (X1)
X1.1				0.858
X1.2				0.861
X1.3				0.796
X1.4				0.741
X1.5				0.822
X1.6				0.825
X2.1	0.830			
X2.2	0.851			
X2.3	0.769			
X2.5	0.792			
X2.6	0.851			
X2.7	0.898			
X2.8	0.830			
Y.1		0.880		
Y.2		0.871		
Y.3		0.803		
Y.4		0.823		
Z.1			0.735	
Z.2			0.895	
Z.3			0.850	
Z.4			0.859	
Z.5			0.821	

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

After the invalid indicator values are removed, all indicators are greater than 0.07 and are considered valid. The table above shows that the indicator for each variable is greater than 0.7, meaning that each item indicator has a value greater than 0.7, meaning that the data is valid and can be researched further.

Figure 2. Outer Model
Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

Smart PLS output for loading factor gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Z = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e_1$$

$$Z = 0.624 X_1 + 0.269 X_2 + e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_2X_1 + b_3X_2 + b_4Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.315 X_1 + 0.267 X_2 + 0.350Z + e_2$$

Discriminant Validity

The next step is to understand the valid data reviewed from its discriminative validity, with the aim of finding out whether the number of cross loadings is greater than the number of other variables, in order to determine which indicators have a higher correlation with the variable construction. table. The cross loading results from the validity test are as follows:

Table 3. Discriminant Validity

	Work Discipline (X2)	Job Satisfaction (Y)	Compensation (Z)	Motivation (X1)
X1.1	0.778	0.704	0.709	0.858
X1.2	0.664	0.740	0.728	0.861
X1.3	0.666	0.702	0.732	0.796
X1.4	0.639	0.628	0.579	0.741
X1.5	0.770	0.710	0.755	0.822
X1.6	0.717	0.661	0.687	0.825
X2.1	0.830	0.633	0.714	0.674
X2.2	0.851	0.667	0.633	0.771
X2.3	0.769	0.641	0.627	0.749
X2.5	0.792	0.739	0.617	0.669
X2.6	0.851	0.658	0.696	0.647
X2.7	0.898	0.765	0.718	0.787
X2.8	0.830	0.678	0.698	0.731
Y.1	0.638	0.880	0.693	0.716
Y.2	0.727	0.871	0.743	0.748
Y.3	0.749	0.803	0.729	0.785
Y.4	0.650	0.823	0.648	0.587
Z.1	0.597	0.652	0.735	0.578
Z.2	0.759	0.757	0.895	0.780
Z.3	0.690	0.593	0.850	0.683
Z.4	0.640	0.668	0.859	0.748
Z.5	0.672	0.791	0.821	0.759

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

In table 3 there is a cross loading in each variable, for the cross loading of the work discipline variable the value is greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, for the cross loading of the job satisfaction variable there is a value greater than the cross loading

on other latent variables, the cross loading of the compensation variable has a value greater than the cross loading of other latent variables, the cross loading factor on the motivation variable has a value greater than the cross loading value on other latent variables, so it can be concluded that this study is discriminantly valid.

Composite reliability

In composite reliability research, each variable is compared for its reliability level, and if the reliability level is greater than 0.60 then the research is considered reliable; if the reliability level is between 0.60 and 0.7, the research is considered unreliable. There are several blocks to determine whether the research is reliable or not, valid or not.

Table 4. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Work Discipline (X2)	0.926	0.940	0.693
Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.866	0.909	0.714
Compensation (Z)	0.889	0.919	0.695
Motivation (X1)	0.901	0.924	0.670

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

The cronbach alpha value of each variable is greater than 0.7 indicating that the data is reliable. The composite reliability column has a value greater than 0.6 so that each variable can be assessed for reliability because the data is more than 0.6. From the AVE column, it can be seen that each variable whose value is greater than 0.7 indicates that the data is valid according to AVE. Each variable in the cronbach alpha, reliability, and AVE columns has a value greater than 0.7 or 0.6 indicating reliability and validity.

Inner Model Analysis

Structural model evaluation (inner model) is conducted to ensure that the basic model created is strong and accurate. The stages of examination conducted in the primary model assessment are seen from several markers, namely:

Coefficient of Determination (R2)

Based on data analysis carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value was obtained as follows:

Table 5. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.779	0.760
Compensation (Z)	0.752	0.739

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

In table 5 there are R square results from two dependent variables for job satisfaction variables, there is an R square value of 0.779 or 77.9%, meaning that the influence of motivation, work discipline, and compensation variables on job satisfaction is 0.779 or 77.9% and the rest is on other variables. For the Compensation variable, the R square value

is 0.75.2 or 75.2%, meaning that the influence of motivation and work discipline on Compensation is 0.752 or 75.2% and the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After determining the inner model, the next step is to determine the relationship between the variables and the hypotheses in this case. Speculation in this review is done by looking at T-Statistics and P-Values. The test determines whether T-Insights > 1.96 and P-Values < 0.05. The following are the results of the Direct Impact Path Coefficient.

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Work Discipline (X2) -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.267	1,667	0.048	Accepted
Work Discipline (X2) -> Compensation (Z)	0.269	1,728	0.042	Accepted
Compensation (Z) -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.350	2,292	0.011	Accepted
Motivation (X1) -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.315	1,698	0.045	Accepted
Motivation (X1) -> Compensation (Z)	0.624	4,106	0,000	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

There are direct influence results in table 6 and each result obtained will be explained below:

1. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.267 and a p value of 0.048. If work discipline increases well then work discipline will increase well, conversely if work discipline decreases then job satisfaction will also decrease.
2. Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on compensation with an original sample value of 0.269 and p values of 0.042. If work discipline increases, compensation will increase, if it decreases, compensation will decrease.
3. Compensation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.350 and p values of 0.011. If compensation increases, job satisfaction will increase, conversely, if it decreases, job satisfaction will decrease.
4. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.315 and p values of 0.045. If good motivation increases, job satisfaction will increase, conversely, if motivation decreases, job satisfaction will decrease.
5. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on compensation with an original sample value of 0.624 and p values of 0.000. If motivation increases well, compensation will increase, conversely, if it decreases, compensation will decrease.

Table 7. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Result
Work Discipline (X2) -> Compensation (Z) -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.094	1,255	0.105	Rejected

Motivation (X1) -> Compensation (Z) -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.218	2,191	0.014	Accepted
---	-------	-------	-------	----------

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

In table 7 there are indirect influences which will be explained to researchers as follows:

1. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Compensation with an original sample value of 0.094 and p values of 0.105, meaning that compensation is not an intervening variable because it is unable to have a significant effect.
2. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Compensation with an original sample value of 0.218 and p values of 0.014, meaning that compensation is an intervening variable because it is able to influence significantly, so that with compensation it will increase motivation and job satisfaction.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.267 and a p value of 0.048.
2. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Compensation with an original sample value of 0.269 and p values of 0.042.
3. Compensation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.350 and p values of 0.011.
4. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.315 and p values of 0.045.
5. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Compensation with an original sample value of 0.624 and p values of 0.000.
6. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Compensation with an original sample value of 0.094 and p values of 0.105.
7. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Compensation with an original sample value of 0.218 and p values of 0.014.

Suggestion

1. Organizations must improve employee discipline by punishing those who do wrong and providing compensation for good employees.
2. The organization must provide motivation to employees with motivators who have a background ranging from the lowest to the most successful.
3. The organization must provide appropriate compensation for its employees.
4. It is hoped that this research will be used as input for the organization and cover the organization's deficiencies and develop the organization.
5. It is hoped that this research will be useful for other researchers and can be used as a reference and for further development.

REFERENCES

Afandi, Pandi. 2021. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia : Teori, Konsep, dan Indikator. Pekanbaru Baru: Zanafa Publishing.

- Atmaja, Sukarta. "Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Kepuasan Kerja Dan Kinerja Karyawan." *Jurnal Manajemen dan Bisnis* 4, no. 01 (25 Februari 2022): 116–31. <https://doi.org/10.47080/jmb.v4i01.1910>.
- Ghozali, Imam dan Hengky Latan (2015). *Partial Least Squares Konsep Teknik dan Aplikasi dengan Program Smart PLS 3.0*. Semarang: Universitas Diponegoro Semarang.
- Hasibuan, M. S. 2020. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Edisi Revisi*. PT. Bumi Aksara, Jakarta.
- Husein Umar. 2013. *Metode Penelitian Untuk Skripsi dan Tesis*. Jakarta: Rajawali
- Jufrizen, J., & Sitorus, T. S. (2021). Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja dan Kepuasan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Dengan Disiplin Kerja Sebagai Variabel Intervening. *Prosiding Seminar Nasional Teknologi Edukasi Sosial Dan Humaniora*, 1(1), 841–856.
- Lengkong, V. P. K., dan Rumokoy, F. S. 2019. Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja, Disiplin Kerja Dan Komitmen Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Di Pt. Air Manado. *Jurnal Emba*. Vol. 7, No. 1. <https://ejournal.unsrat.ac.id/index.php/emba/article/view/23229>, Diakses 11 Desember 2021
- Luthans, Fred. 2016. *Perilaku Organisasi*. Yogyakarta: Andi Offset.
- Narimawati. 2010. *Metodologi Penelitian : Dasar Penyusun Penelitian Ekonomi*. Jakarta : Genesis.
- Pangaila, N., Nelwan, O., & Lengkong, V. (2022). Pengaruh komitmen organisasi, disiplin kerja dan lingkungan kerja terhadap kinerja karyawan pada badan kepegawaian daerah prov.sulut *Jurnal EMBA Vol . 10 No . 2 April 2022 , Ha. Jurnal EMBA*, 10(2), 965.
- Robbins and Judge., (2018). *Motivasi Kerja. Human Resources Management, Ebook, Global Edition*. Education Limited.
- Sari, D. N. (2019). Pengaruh Kepemimpinan dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan: Studi Kasus PT Sucofindo Palembang Indonesia. *Mbia*, 18(1), 76–84. <https://doi.org/10.33557/mbia.v18i1.326>
- Sujarweni, V. Wiratna. 2014. *Metode Penelitian: Lengkap, Praktis, dan Mudah Dipahami*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Baru Press.
- Sugiyono, (2017). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: CV. Alfabeta.
- Wasiman, W. (2018). Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan, Motivasi Dan Komunikasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada Rumah Sakit Swasta Di Kota Batam. *Aksara Public*, 2(1), 18-30.
- Yuda, S., & Hasan, J. (2016). Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja dan Komunikasi terhadap Kinerja Karyawan pada PT Indodacin Presisi Utama Medan. 67–76.

Developing Organizational Strategy

Hendru Marpaung¹, Muhammad Isa Indrawan²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: hendrumarpaung@gmail.com

Abstract

The first step in managing human resources is to assign human resources so that they obtain work assignments that are appropriate for the work being done. Human resources (HC) or staff members have become a top priority in any organization as their quality is crucial in facing the current business climate. This research aims to examine the influence of leadership style, human resource quality and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) on organizational commitment in communication mediation at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province. The results of this research are as follows: Leadership Style has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.374 and ap value of 0.001. Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on communication with an original sample value of 0.368 and ap value of 0.001. Communication has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.100 and ap value of 0.179. HR quality has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.289 and ap value of 0.005. HR quality has a positive and insignificant effect on communication with an original sample value of 0.205 and ap value of 0.070. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.178 and ap value of 0.053. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Communication with an original sample value of 0.332 and ap value of 0.004. Leadership style has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment through communication with the original sample of 0.037 and p value 0.171. HR quality has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment through Communication with an original sample value of 0.020 and ap value of 0.290. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Communication with an original sample value of 0.020 and an ap value of 0.212.

Keywords: Leadership Style, HR Quality, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Communication, Organizational Commitment

INTRODUCTION

The first step in human resource management is to assign human resources so that they get work assignments that are appropriate to the work being done. Human resources (HC) or staff members have become a top priority in any organization as their quality is crucial in facing the current business climate. A healthy leadership style in any organization will have a positive impact on the organization as a whole as well as on each individual staff or member of the organization concerned. Therefore, it is very important for every organization to have the capacity to carry out organizational transformation through good leadership development. One common type of leadership that is often observed in an organization is servant leadership. One of the most important and strategic aspects of running an organization is ensuring that the organization achieves its goals, objectives, and missions. In developing organizational strategy, it is important to note that this is especially true for single-family organizations and depends on its leaders. Leadership is the process of others understanding and agreeing on what is needed to carry out tasks and how to do them, and the process of facilitating individual and collective efforts to achieve common goals (Yukl, 2015). The success and failure experienced by the company is largely determined by the role

of the leader through his leadership style. A leadership style that is appropriate to the situation and conditions will provide enthusiasm for employees to work optimally. The leadership style that is currently developing is the transformational leadership style. Because globalization is an era of human crossroads, the quality of human resources can also be a source of resistance during this period. Qualitative human resources are very close to performance. In this modern era, selecting high-quality human resources is becoming increasingly difficult. However, as a challenge that must be faced, it is not just a problem that must be avoided. In relation to this, in general, Human Resource Quality Development is still developing and will most likely face various challenges that need to be overcome by all HR practices. This includes, but is not limited to, quality standards, technology, HR development status, and HR development practices. Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is an unofficial rule that is voluntary. With OCB, it is expected that employees in the organization can be more integrated with their work environment. Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is behavior carried out by employees that increases the effectiveness of the organization, but is not the formal responsibility of the person. One of the strategic attitudes in the human resources division is to develop Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) in the organization. Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is reflected through behavior that likes to help others, becomes a volunteer for extra tasks, obeys the rules and procedures in the workplace. This behavior illustrates the added value of employees which is a form of pro-social behavior, namely positive, constructive and helpful social behavior. Employees who prioritize their work will make a positive contribution to the organization through their ability to work outside of work-related tasks. Conversely, employees who prioritize their work will carry out their duties diligently and are committed to their work. One of the keys that also determines that an organization is not to achieve its goals is employee commitment. Employees who have committees in the organization usually give work assignments to less experienced co-workers who are very committed to the company and very obedient to it. In committees that have vital components such as binders that will produce energy to carry out tasks optimally. Employee commitment to an organization or business is very important in the world of work. This is a very important point, to the point that some organizations sincerely see it as one of the last opportunities to join a team or position offered in a job advertisement. Communication is a basic human activity. Through communication, humans can always relate to each other, be it in everyday life at home, at work, in society, or wherever they are. There is no one who is unable to communicate. Communication plays a very important role in human life, be it individually, in groups, or in organizations.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Leadership Style Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Communication at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
2. Does HR Quality Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Communication at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
3. Does Organizational Citizenship Behavior have a positive and significant influence on Communication at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
4. Does Leadership Style Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
5. Does HR Quality have a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?

6. Does Organizational Citizenship Behavior have a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
7. Does Communication have a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
8. Does Leadership Style Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Organizational Commitment through Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
9. Does Human Resource Quality Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Organizational Commitment through Communication at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
10. Does Organizational Citizenship Behavior have a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Communication at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of Leadership Style on Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
2. To determine and analyze the influence of HR Quality on Communication at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
3. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Citizenship Behavior on Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
4. To determine and analyze the influence of Leadership Style on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
5. To determine and analyze the influence of HR Quality on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
6. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Citizenship Behavior on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
7. To determine the influence and analyze Communication on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
8. To determine and analyze the influence of Leadership Style on Organizational Commitment through Communication at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
9. To determine and analyze the influence of HR Quality on Organizational Commitment through Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
10. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Citizenship Behavior on Organizational Commitment through Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational Commitment

Understanding Organizational Commitment

According to Kreitner & Kinicki (2015), organizational commitment reflects the level to which a person identifies with the company and is committed to its goals.

According to Moorhead and Griffin (2015), organizational commitment reflects a person's identification and attachment to their organization.

Organizational Commitment Indicators

According to Kreitner and Kinicki (2015), the indicators of organizational commitment are:

1. **Affective Commitment** Affective commitment is the emotional attachment to employees, employee identification, and employee involvement in the company. Employees who have a strong affective commitment will continue to work for the company because they want to.
2. **Continuing Commitment** Continuing commitment is the awareness of the loss of leaving the company. This is the economic value and other risks that employees feel from staying in a company compared to leaving the company. Employees who have a continuing commitment will stay because they have to.
3. **Normative Commitment** Normative commitment reflects a sense of responsibility to continue working. Employees have an obligation to stay in the organization for moral or ethical reasons. Employees remain members of the organization because they are aware that committing to the organization is the right thing to do.

Leadership Style

Understanding Leadership Styles

According to Thoha (2014) Leadership Style is a behavioral norm used by a person when the person tries to influence the behavior of others as he sees it. According to Hasibuan (2016) Leadership Style is the way a leader influences the behavior of subordinates which aims to encourage high work enthusiasm, job satisfaction and employee productivity, in order to achieve maximum organizational goals.

Leadership Style Indicators

According to Hasibuan (2016) the indicators of leadership style are:

1. **Authoritarian Leadership**
 - a. Absolute authority is centralized in the leadership
 - b. Decisions are always made by the leader
 - c. There is no opportunity for subordinates to provide suggestions
2. **Delegative Leadership**
 - a. Leaders delegate more authority to subordinates
 - b. Most decisions are made by subordinates
 - c. Subordinates are free to convey suggestions and opinions
3. **Participative Leadership**
 - a. The leadership's authority is not absolute
 - b. Decisions are made jointly between leaders and subordinates
 - c. Many opportunities for subordinates to convey suggestions and opinions

Human Resources Quality

Understanding Human Resource Quality

According to Suharto (2014), HR quality is the ability of employees to carry out work, which is seen from their expertise, skills, and educational background. According to Matutina (2016) the quality of human resources refers to knowledge, skills and abilities.

Human Resource Quality Indicators

According to Matutina (2016), the indicators of HR quality are as follows:

1. Work knowledge, namely the abilities possessed by employees that are more oriented towards intelligence and thinking power as well as the employee's mastery of broad knowledge.
2. Work skills, namely the ability and technical operational mastery in a particular field that employees have.
3. Work ability, namely the ability formed from the competencies possessed by an employee which includes loyalty, discipline, cooperation and responsibility.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

Understanding Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

Employees who demonstrate OCB reflect these qualities in their work accepting help, eager to learn, focused on the task at hand, and sincere in their approach (Irawati et al., 2022). Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) can be described as behavior or independent people who are not directly tied to the reward system and are able to improve the efficiency of the organization. OCB refers to an employee's behavior either towards their coworkers or the organization as a whole, when the behavior goes beyond the behavioral norms set by the company and produces results that are beneficial to the company (Kadir, 2018).

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) Indicators

According to Kadir (2018) the indicators of organizational citizenship behavior are as follows:

1. Altruism (altruism) Shows actions or character that are characterized by prioritizing the interests of others over one's own. Workers who have completed their tasks often give more challenging tasks to workers who are still working.
2. Conscientiousness (seriousness) Defined as a voluntary effort to improve the way one performs one's work creatively in order to improve the company's performance. "Participating in this activity means trying hard to be creative and original so as to increase one's productivity and ultimately the success of the business. Individuals work above and beyond in their jobs for the company.
3. Sportsmanship The definition of sportsmanship is the willingness to persevere through adversity without wallowing in it. Such an action demonstrates a strong tolerance for less than ideal or downright uncomfortable settings.
4. Courtesy (public interest) Active in group processes and concerned about the future survival of the group. Voluntarily involved, accepting responsibility, and taking part in resolving hazards and opportunities in the workplace.
5. Civic Virtue (politeness) Making an effort to help others when doing so is not required but is done out of a sincere desire to do so.

Communication

Definition of Communication

According to Putri & Sariyathi (2017) communication is a tool by which statements can be delivered or approved to or from other parties. Inappropriate delivery can lead to detrimental results and result in failure to meet business goals. According to Lawasi & Triatmanto, (2017) communication is a way of sending notes whose delivery mode can be changed to emphasize the importance of the message and to create a transition between verbal and non-verbal notes. If the message is not received correctly, there will be no

response from the recipient of the message. Effective communication is needed to avoid misunderstandings between the sender and recipient of the message.

Communication Indicators

According to Lawasi and Triatmanto (2017), communication indicators are:

1. Understanding,
2. Action,
3. Influence on attitudes,
4. Better relationships.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

- H1 Leadership style has a positive and significant influence on communication at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H2 The quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on communication at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H3 *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* has a positive and significant influence on Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H4 Leadership Style has a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H5 The quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H6 *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* has a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H7 Communication has a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.

- H8 Leadership Style has a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment through Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H9 The quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H10 *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* has a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment through Communication at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.

METHOD

Types of research

According to Sugiyono (2021), quantitative research is a scientific research method regarding phenomena that can be concrete, objective, rational, measurable and systematic.

Population

This study took a population of 70 employees as research respondents. Population according to Sugiyono (2021) is a generalization area consisting of subjects or objects that have certain quantities and characteristics that are determined to be studied and then conclusions are drawn.

Sample

This study took a sample in a study of 70 employees, the researcher wanted all populations to be samples and used a saturated sampling technique. Sugiyono (2021) defines a sample as a number of elements that have characteristics and are part of the population, According to Sugiyono (2021), saturated sampling is a sample that, if increased in number, will not increase representation so that it will not affect the value of the information obtained.

Research Time

This research was conducted from September to October 2024.

Research Location

This research was conducted at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province, on Jalan Balai Kota No. 4, Medan.

Data source

This study uses primary data sources as the source of its research data. Primary data is data collected directly from data sources and given directly to data collectors (Sugiyono, 2021).

Data collection technique

In this study, the author uses questionnaires and questionnaires as primary data sources. The questionnaire will be distributed online using a questionnaire that has been created and distributed to respondents. To measure each variable, a Likert Scale is used in the questionnaire. Sugiyono (2021) explains that to measure attitudes, perceptions and 35 opinions of research subjects regarding an event or issue that occurs in society, a Likert scale can be used.

Data Analysis Techniques

This study uses Partial Least Square (PLS), which is a Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) equation model with an approach based on variance or component-based structural equation modeling. PLS-SEM is an analysis method with a regression-based approach, by minimizing residual variance, as stated by Hair (2014). In practice, data processing is assisted by the Smart-PLS data processing application. The purpose of using Smart-PLS includes predicting relationships between constructs, confirming theories, and being able to explain whether or not there is a relationship between latent variables where latent variables are variables that cannot be measured directly. This is in line with the opinion of Ghazali & Latan (2015), who stated that the purpose of PLSSEM is "to test predictive relationships between constructs by seeing whether there is a relationship or influence between the constructs".

Measurement Model Test or Outer Model

The measurement model or outer model describes how each indicator block is related to its latent variables. Evaluation of the measurement model through confirmatory factor analysis is by using the MTMM (MultiTrait-MultiMethod) approach by testing convergent and discriminant validity. While the reliability test is carried out in two ways, namely with Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (Ghozali & Latan, 2015).

- a. Convergent Validity Convergent validity of the measurement model with reflective indicators can be seen from the correlation between item scores/indicators and their construct scores. Individual reflective measures can be interpreted as high if they have a correlation of more than 0.70 with the construct to be measured. However, "in the scale development stage of research, loadings of 0.50 to 0.60 are still acceptable" (Ghozali & Latan, 2015).
- b. Discriminant Validity Discriminant validity of indicators can be seen in the cross loading between indicators and their constructs. If the correlation coefficient of a construct with its indicators is higher than the correlation of indicators with other constructs, then it can be interpreted that the latent construct predicts indicators in their block better when compared to indicators in other blocks.
- c. Construct Reliability In addition to validity testing, model measurement is also carried out to test the reliability of a construct. Reliability testing is carried out to prove the accuracy, consistency and precision of the instrument in measuring the construct. In PLS-SEM using the SmartPLS program, to measure the reliability of a construct with a reflective indicator can be done in two ways, namely with Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability. The construct is declared reliable if the composite reliability value or Cronbach alpha is above 0.70 (Ghozali & Latan, 2015).

Structural Model or Inner Model Test

The structural model or inner model is a model used to measure the relationship or strength of estimates between latent variables or constructs based on substantive theory.

- a. R-Square
- b. F-Square
- c. Estimate For Path Coefficients

Partial Hypothesis Testing

In assessing the significance of the influence between variables, a bootstrapping procedure is needed. The bootstrap procedure uses the entire original sample to resample

again. Hair et al. (2014) suggest a number of bootstrap samples of 5,000 with the note that the number must be greater than the original sample. However, Chin in Ghazali and Latan (2015) argues that "the number of bootstrap samples of 200-1000 is sufficient to correct the PLS standard error estimate". In the bootstrap resampling method, the significance value used is two-tailed which is adjusted to the significance level. For significance level = 10% then the t-value = 1.65; and for significance level = 5% then the t-value is 1.96; while for significance level = 1% then the t-value = 2.58.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

The measurement model test (outer model) is used to determine the specification of the relationship between latent variables and manifest variables. The test has convergent validity, discriminant validity, and reliability.

Convergent Validity

This test is proven by the loading factor value of 0.7, and the limit value. Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of 0.5; anything above this value is considered valid. This means that the indicator value is considered valid if it describes the build variable with a value greater than 0.7. The structural model in this study is shown in the following figure:

Figure 2. Outer Model
Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Smart PLS output for loading factor gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Z = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + e_1$$

$$Z = 0.368 X_1 + 0.205 X_2 + 0.332 X_3 + e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_2X_1 + b_4X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.374X1 + 0.289X2 + 0.178X3 + 0.100Z + e2$$

Table 2. Outer Loadings

	Leadership Style (X1)	Organizational Commitment (Y)	Communication (Z)	Human Resources Quality (X2)	Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X3)
X1.1	0.726				
X1.2	0.759				
X1.3	0.844				
X1.4	0.828				
X1.5	0.849				
X1.6	0.738				
X1.7	0.753				
X1.8	0.826				
X1.9	0.884				
X2.1				0.854	
X2.2				0.919	
X2.3				0.902	
X3.1					0.839
X3.2					0.867
X3.3					0.889
X3.4					0.758
X3.5					0.840
Y.1		0.863			
Y.2		0.845			
Y.3		0.893			
Z.1			0.840		
Z.2			0.905		
Z.3			0.832		
Z.4			0.871		
Z.5			0.917		

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 2 above, there are values for each variable, it is stated that the indicator for each variable is higher than 0.7, which means that each indicator item has a value higher than 0.7 so that the data is declared valid and can be continued for further research.

Discriminant Validity

Further research will determine the validity of the data using Discriminate Validity, with the aim of finding out whether the cross loading value is greater than other latent variables in order to find out the findings of indicators that have a strong relationship with the concept. The following table shows the findings of cross loading from the validity test, as follows:

Table 3. Discriminant Validity

	Leadership Style (X1)	Organizational Commitment (Y)	Communication (Z)	Human Resources Quality (X2)	Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X3)
X1.1	0.726	0.686	0.554	0.611	0.626
X1.2	0.759	0.688	0.566	0.638	0.617
X1.3	0.844	0.714	0.625	0.655	0.734
X1.4	0.828	0.670	0.643	0.656	0.703
X1.5	0.849	0.815	0.766	0.782	0.851
X1.6	0.738	0.542	0.695	0.618	0.630
X1.7	0.753	0.637	0.572	0.657	0.550
X1.8	0.826	0.633	0.714	0.593	0.668
X1.9	0.884	0.718	0.770	0.773	0.738
X2.1	0.735	0.628	0.643	0.854	0.699
X2.2	0.753	0.785	0.742	0.919	0.715
X2.3	0.741	0.768	0.686	0.902	0.715
X3.1	0.840	0.758	0.756	0.819	0.839
X3.2	0.662	0.649	0.703	0.693	0.867
X3.3	0.661	0.618	0.609	0.613	0.889
X3.4	0.659	0.572	0.566	0.565	0.758
X3.5	0.732	0.757	0.728	0.614	0.840
Y.1	0.727	0.863	0.773	0.803	0.704
Y.2	0.695	0.845	0.552	0.605	0.666
Y.3	0.782	0.893	0.678	0.710	0.728
Z.1	0.685	0.667	0.840	0.700	0.647
Z.2	0.799	0.709	0.905	0.739	0.763
Z.3	0.690	0.715	0.832	0.597	0.766
Z.4	0.640	0.611	0.871	0.653	0.599
Z.5	0.763	0.677	0.917	0.694	0.742

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Table 3 above shows the cross loading factor values of each variable and indicator. This can be explained that the cross loading value of each variable is greater than the cross loading value of other latent variables for each variable, so it can be interpreted that this study has discriminant validity.

Composite reliability

In composite reliability research, each variable is evaluated using its reliability value; if the variable value is greater than 0.60 then the research is considered reliable; if between 0.60 and 0.7, then it is not reliable. The table below shows the Cronbach alpha, composite reliability, and AVE values, which are used to determine whether the research is reliable and valid.

Table 4. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Leadership Style (X1)	0.930	0.942	0.644
Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.835	0.901	0.752
Communication (Z)	0.922	0.941	0.763
Human Resources Quality (X2)	0.872	0.921	0.796
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X3)	0.895	0.923	0.705

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 4 above, the Cronbach alpha column shows the value of each variable is greater than 0.7, indicating that the variable's dependability data is reliable. The composite reliability column has a value greater than 0.6, indicating that each variable is considered reliable because the data exceeds 0.6. The AVE column shows that each variable has a value greater than 0.7, indicating that the data is original in terms of AVE. All variables in the Cronbach alpha, reliability, and AVE columns have values above 0.7 and 0.6, indicating reliability and validity.

Inner Model Analysis

The structural model (inner model) is evaluated to ensure that the resulting basic model is strong and correct. Some markers that can be used to identify the stages of the main model assessment examination include:

Coefficient of Determination (R2)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 5. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.776	0.762
Communication (Z)	0.731	0.719

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

There is an R square value in table 5 for the R square value of the organizational commitment variable with a value of 0.776 or 77.6%, meaning that the influence of the leadership style variable, HR quality, Organizational Citizenship Behavior and communication on organizational commitment is 0.776 or 77.6%, the rest is on other variables, the R square value of the communication variable is 0.731 or 73.1%, meaning that the influence of the leadership style variable, HR quality, Organizational Citizenship Behavior is 0.731 or 73.1% and the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After assessing the inner model, the next thing is to assess the relationship between idle builds as suspected in this review. Speculation testing in this review is done by looking

at T-Statistics and P-Values. Speculation is announced to acknowledge whether the T-Insights value is > 1.96 and P-Values < 0.05 . Here is the direct impact of the Path Coefficient:

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Leadership Style (X1) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.374	3,081	0.001	Accepted
Leadership Style (X1) -> Communication (Z)	0.368	3,091	0.001	Accepted
Communication (Z) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.100	0.919	0.179	Rejected
Human Resources Quality (X2) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.289	2,593	0.005	Accepted
Human Resources Quality (X2) -> Communication (Z)	0.205	1,477	0.070	Rejected
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X3) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.178	1,622	0.053	Rejected
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X3) -> Communication (Z)	0.332	2,699	0.004	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 6 there are the results of the research hypothesis, so the explanation of this research is as follows:

1. Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment with an original sample value of 0.374 and p values of 0.001, meaning that if the leadership style increases, organizational commitment will increase, conversely, if it decreases, organizational commitment will decrease.
2. Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on communication with an original sample value of 0.368 and p values of 0.001, meaning that if the leadership style increases well, good communication will increase, conversely if it decreases, communication will decrease.
3. Communication has a positive but insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.100 and p values of 0.179, meaning that good or bad communication has little effect on organizational commitment.
4. The quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.289 and p values of 0.005, meaning that if the quality of human resources increases, organizational commitment will increase, conversely, if it decreases, organizational commitment will also decrease.
5. The quality of human resources has a positive but insignificant effect on communication with an original sample value of 0.205 and p values of 0.070, meaning that the quality of human resources has little effect on communication in this study.
6. *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.178 and p values of 0.053,

meaning that OCB has little effect on organizational commitment so that it cannot increase but can still be useful.

7. *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* has a positive and significant effect on communication with an original sample value of 0.332 and p values of 0.004, meaning that if OCB increases well, communication will increase well, if it decreases, communication will also decrease.

Table 7. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Leadership Style (X1) -> Communication (Z) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.037	0.950	0.171	Rejected
Human Resources Quality (X2) -> Communication (Z) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.020	0.553	0.290	Rejected
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X3) -> Communication (Z) -> Organizational Commitment (Y)	0.033	0.799	0.212	Rejected

In table 7, indirectly, the explanation for this research hypothesis is as follows:

1. Leadership style has a positive but insignificant effect on organizational commitment through communication with the original sample of 0.037 and p values of 0.171, meaning that communication is not an intervening variable because it is unable to influence indirectly and is not significant.
2. The quality of human resources has a positive but insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment through Communication with an original sample value of 0.020 and p values of 0.290, meaning that communication is not an intervening variable because it is unable to influence it significantly.
3. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Communication with an original sample value of 0.020 and p values of 0.212, meaning that communication is not an intervening variable because it is unable to influence significantly.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Leadership Style has a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.374 and p values of 0.001.
2. Leadership Style has a positive and significant effect on Communication with an original sample value of 0.368 and p values of 0.001.
3. Communication has a positive but insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.100 and p values of 0.179.
4. Human resource quality has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.289 and p values of 0.005.
5. The quality of human resources has a positive but insignificant effect on communication with an original sample value of 0.205 and p values of 0.070.

6. *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment with an original sample value of 0.178 and p values of 0.053.
7. *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* has a positive and significant effect on Communication with an original sample value of 0.332 and p values of 0.004.
8. Leadership style has a positive but insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment through communication with the original sample of 0.037 and p values of 0.171.
9. The quality of human resources has a positive but insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment through Communication with an original sample value of 0.020 and p values of 0.290.
10. *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment through Communication with an original sample value of 0.020 and p values of 0.212.

Suggestion

1. The organization must have a good leadership style and also be firm in leading an organization, not dictatorial so that employees feel better working under good and firm leadership.
2. Organizations must improve the quality of employee human resources through training or seeking employees with good human resources for the sake of organizational progress.
3. Organizations must implement OCB as a good organizational culture.
4. Organizations must improve healthy and good communication to avoid misunderstandings in work.
5. Organizations must increase organizational commitment by providing adequate compensation for employees.
6. This research is expected to be used as input for the organization to cover the organization's deficiencies and weaknesses.
7. This research is expected to be used as reference material for new research and to develop it for further research.

REFERENCES

- Dessler, Gary. 2015. Human Resources Management (Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia), Edisi Empat Belas Bahasa Indonesia. Jakarta: Indeks.
- Ghozali, Imam dan Hengky Latan (2015). Partial Least Squares Konsep Teknik dan Aplikasi dengan Program Smart PLS 3.0. Semarang: Universitas Diponegoro Semarang.
- Hasibuan, Malayu S.P. 2016. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Edisi Revisi. Jakarta: Penerbit PT Bumi Aksara.
- Hair Jr, J., Sarstedt, M., Hopkins, L., & G. Kuppelwieser, V. (2014). Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM). *European Business Review*, 26(2), 106–121. <http://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-10-2013-0128>
- Kadir. (2018). Peranan brainware dalam sistem informasi manajemen jurnal ekonomi dan manajemen sistem informasi. *Sistem Informasi*, 1(September), 60–69. <https://doi.org/10.31933/JEMSI>.
- Kreitner, Robert dan Angelo Kinicki. 2014. Perilaku Organisasi. Edisi 9. Buku 1. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.

- Lawasi, E. S. & Triatmanto, B., 2017. Pengaruh Komunikasi, Motivasi Dan Kerjasama Tim Terhadap Peningkatan Kinerja Karyawan. *JMDK*, Vol 5(No 1), Pp. 47-57.
- Matutina. 2016. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta : Gramedia Widia Sarana Indonesia.
- Moorhead, Gregory & Griffin, Ricky W. (2013). *Perilaku organisasi: Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia dan Organisasi*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- Putri, L. D., & Sariyathi, N. K. (2017). Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan Transformasional, Kerjasama Tim dan Komunikasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Warung Mina Cabang Renon. *E-Journal Manajemen Unud*. Pp. 3398-3426.
- Suharto, 2015, *Membangun Masyarakat Memberdayakan Rakyat (Kajian Strategis Pembangunan Kesejahteraan Sosial & Pekerjaan Sosial)*, PT.Refika Aditama.
- Sugiyono. 2021. *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif*. Alfabeta, CV: Bandung.
- Thoha. 2015, *Perilaku Organisasi Konsep Dasar dan Implikasinya*. Jakarta : PT. Raja Grafindo Persada
- Yukl, Gary. 2015, *Leadership in Organizations, Seventh Edition*, PT. Indeks, Jakarta.

Optimizing Job Satisfaction

Mhd. Andy Syahputra Siregar¹, Muhammad Isa Indrawan²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: andysiregarr@gmail.com

Abstract

This research aims to examine the influence of integrity, competency and motivation on job satisfaction mediated by work discipline at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province. Production factors are needed to produce human output, but without human labor, commodities and services will not provide the same benefits. The results of this research are as follows: Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.422 and ap value of 0.000. Integrity has a positive and significant effect on Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.358 and ap value of 0.000. Integrity has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.234 and ap value of 0.008. Competence has a positive and significant effect on Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.234 and ap value of 0.007. Competency has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.044 and ap value of 0.321. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.394 and ap value of 0.000. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.272 and ap value of 0.002. Integrity has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.155 and ap value of 0.003. Competence has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.103 and ap value of 0.013. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.170 and ap value of 0.004.

Keywords: Integrity, Competence, Motivation, Job Satisfaction, Work Discipline

INTRODUCTION

Work productivity can only be increased by humans. On the other hand, human resources can also be a source of this waste in several ways. Therefore, one of the guidelines in all efforts to increase work productivity is to pay attention to the human factor. Integrity is a quality or condition that shows total unity, providing the ability to radiate honesty and authority. When a person has integrity, he will always act in accordance with the moral ideals and values he upholds. Integrity refers to positive characteristics that are not limited to moral qualities alone. Integrity is more closely related to a person's actions, more closely related to other people's perceptions of oneself, more closely related to work experience, and when a person has integrity, he will always be more diligent in trying. Integrity is a pure and unshakable quality. called *attributie van rechtsmachts*. Absolute competence or absolute authority, Motivated employees will carry out their duties and responsibilities with enthusiasm if the organization wants each employee to be able to make a positive contribution to achieving the company's goals. The importance of motivation comes from the fact that motivation drives, channels, and maintains human behavior, allowing people to strive hard and be enthusiastic in achieving their goals. Meanwhile, an employee's motivation towards his work functions as a motivator or driver in an organization. Achieving goals in the workplace can be influenced by motivating employees to work hard to increase productivity. Employee work discipline is an important factor that can determine the success of a company's goals, this happens because employees are the main drivers of the company's activities. Without good employee work discipline, it is difficult for the company

organization to achieve optimal results. According to Sutrisno (2019) the main goal of discipline is to increase efficiency as much as possible by preventing wasting time and energy, discipline also tries to overcome mistakes and delays to prevent slow work starts and ending work too early due to delays and laziness. Workplace satisfaction is the sense of satisfaction that workers get from their work. Happiness shows the impact of work experience, and high levels of dissatisfaction are useful in indicating organizational problems that need to be addressed. Dissatisfaction in the workplace is closely related to physical and mental health problems, employee turnover, and absenteeism. In addition, low organizational commitment, a very hostile environment, reduced work involvement, and a number of other bad outcomes are signs of dissatisfied workers.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Integrity have a positive and significant influence on Work Discipline at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
2. Does Competence have a positive and significant influence on Work Discipline at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
3. Does Motivation have a positive and significant effect on Work Discipline at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
4. Does Integrity have a positive and significant influence on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
5. Does Competence have a positive and significant influence on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
6. Does Motivation have a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
7. Does Work Discipline Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
8. Does Integrity have a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Work Discipline at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
9. Does Competence have a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Work Discipline at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
10. Does Motivation have a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Work Discipline at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of Integrity on Work Discipline at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
2. To determine and analyze the influence of Competence on Work Discipline at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
3. To determine and analyze the influence of Motivation on Work Discipline at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
4. To determine and analyze the influence of Integrity on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
5. To determine and analyze the influence of Competence on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
6. To determine and analyze the influence of Motivation on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

7. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Discipline on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
8. To determine and analyze the influence of Integrity on Job Satisfaction and Work Discipline at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
9. To determine and analyze the influence of Competence on Job Satisfaction and Work Discipline at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
10. To determine and analyze the influence of Motivation on Job Satisfaction and Work Discipline at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Job satisfaction

Understanding Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction according to Hasibuan (2017) is an emotional attitude that is pleasant and loves one's job. According to Sudaryo, Agus & Nunung (2018) job satisfaction is a feeling of pleasure or discomfort regarding work based on expectations with the rewards given by the agency.

Job Satisfaction Indicators

According to Sudaryo, Agus & Nunung (2018) the indicators of job satisfaction are as follows:

1. Turnover
2. Work absence rate
3. Age
4. Employment level

Integrity

Understanding Integrity

According to Mulyadi (2014), integrity is an element of character that underlies the emergence of professional recognition. Integrity is a quality that underlies public trust and is a benchmark for members in testing all decisions they make.

According to Agoes (2017), integrity is an attitude free from conflicts of interest (Conflict of Interest).

Integrity Indicators

According to Agoes (2017) the indicators for integrity are:

1. Honesty A person who expresses an opinion on the fairness in all material respects, the financial position of the results of operations and cash flows in accordance with generally accepted accounting principles in Indonesia. Honesty in the profession of an auditor is absolutely necessary. Because from an auditor we can obtain information whether a company is committing fraud or not.
2. Do not prioritize personal gain. Public service and trust must not be defeated by personal gain.
3. Wise Attitude Can demonstrate loyalty in all matters relating to the profession and organization in carrying out duties, Can remind each other, guide and correct the behavior of fellow auditors.
4. Responsible Attitude Auditors are required to carefully use and maintain all information obtained during the audit. They will not use the information obtained for personal or

group interests outside the interests of the organization or in a manner that is contrary to laws and regulations.

Competence

Understanding Competence

According to Agustian et al., (2018) explained that competence is an ability to carry out or do a job or task that is based on skills and knowledge and supported by the work attitude required by the job. According to Wibowo (2022) competence is an ability to carry out or do a job or task that is based on skills and knowledge and supported by the work attitude required by the job.

Competency Indicators

Competency indicators according to Wibowo (2022) are:

1. Knowledge
2. Skills (Skills)
3. Self-Concept
4. Traits (Character)
5. Motives (Motivation)

Motivation

Understanding Motivation

According to Uhing (2019) is a condition or energy that drives employees who are directed or aimed at achieving the goals of the company's organization. According to Hafidzi et al. (2019), motivation is the process of developing a person's work ethic so that they can work together effectively, work in a team, and be honest with all employees in order to achieve goals.

Motivation Indicators

According to Hafidzi et al. (2019), work motivation indicators are:

1. Physical needs, the need for supporting facilities that can be obtained in the workplace, for example supporting facilities to facilitate the completion of tasks in the office.
2. The need for a sense of security, these needs for a sense of security include physical security, stability, dependency, protection and freedom from threatening forces such as: fear, anxiety, danger.
3. Social needs, needs that must be met based on shared interests in society, these needs are met together, for example good interaction between each other.
4. The need for appreciation is the need for appreciation for what a person has achieved, for example the need for status, glory, attention, reputation.
5. The need for encouragement to achieve goals, the need for encouragement to achieve something desired, for example motivation from leaders.

Work Discipline

Understanding Work Discipline

According to Hasibuan (2017) Work discipline is a person's awareness and willingness to comply with all applicable company regulations and social norms. According to Hamali (2016) work discipline is a force that develops within the employee's body and can cause employees to voluntarily adjust to regulatory decisions, and high values of work and behavior.

Work Discipline Indicators

According to Hasibuan (2017), the indicators of work discipline are:

1. Goals and Abilities
2. Leadership role model
3. Reward
4. Justice
5. Waskat
6. Penalty Sanctions
7. Assertiveness
8. Human relations

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

- H1 Integrity has a positive and significant influence on Work Discipline at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H2 Competence has a positive and significant effect on Work Discipline at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H3 Motivation has a positive and significant influence on Work Discipline at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H4 Integrity has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H5 Competence has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H6 Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H7 Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H8 Integrity has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Work Discipline at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H9 Competence has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Work Discipline at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.

H10 Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Work Discipline at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.

METHOD

Research methods

Types of research

This research uses a quantitative research type. According to Sujarweni (2014), quantitative research is a type of research that produces findings that can be achieved (obtained) by using statistical procedures or other methods of quantification (measurement).

Time and Place of Research

This research was conducted from September to October 2024. The location of this research was at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province, precisely on Jalan Balai Kota No. 4, Medan City.

Population

The population of this study was all employees of the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province, totaling 70 employees. According to Sujarweni (2014), population is the total number of objects or subjects that have certain characteristics and qualities that are determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions are drawn from them.

Sample

This study uses a sample of all populations to be used as a sample of 70 employees and the sampling technique used is the saturated sampling technique. According to Narimawati (2014), a sample is a portion of the population selected to be the unit of observation in research.

Data collection technique

The data collection technique used is a questionnaire, the researcher distributes the questionnaire to the sample to be distributed and the data source used is a primary data source. According to Sujarweni (2014), primary data collection techniques are methods used by researchers to reveal or obtain quantitative information. According to Sugiyono (2017), a questionnaire is a data collection method carried out by giving a set of written questions or statements to respondents to answer.

Data Analysis Techniques

The data analysis technique used in this study uses Partial Least Square (PLS) with Smart PLS (Partial Least Square) software. There are several methods developed related to PLS, namely the PLS Regression (PLS-R) model and PLS Path Modeling (PLS-PM). PLS Path Modeling was developed as an alternative to structural equation modeling (SEM) whose theoretical basis is weak. PLS-PM is based on variance, different from the SEM method with AMOS, Lisrel, EQS software using a covariance basis. Partial Least Square is a powerful analysis method, which in this method is not based on many assumptions.

Measurement or Outer Model

Some of the tests performed on the outer model are as follows:

- a. Indicator Reliability Indicator reliability aims to assess whether the latent variable measurement indicator is reliable or not. This is done by evaluating the outer loading

- results of each indicator. A loading value above 0.7 indicates that the construct can explain more than 50% of the indicator's variance.
- b. Internal Consistency Reliability Is an indicator to measure a construct that can be seen in the view of latent variable coefficients. To evaluate internal consistency reliability there are two measuring instruments, namely composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha. In this measurement, if the composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha values achieved are > 0.70 , it can be said that the construct has high reliability.
 - c. Convergent Validity Is an indicator that is assessed based on the correlation between item score/component score and construct score, which can be seen from the standardized loading factor which describes the magnitude of the correlation between each measurement item (indicator) and its construct. The convergent validity of a construct with a reflective indicator is evaluated by Average Variance Extracted (AVE). The AVE value should be equal to 0.5 or more. An AVE value of 0.5 or more means that the construct can explain 50% or more of its item variance.
 - d. Discriminant Validity Discriminant validity aims to determine whether a reflective indicator is truly a good measure for its construct based on the principle that each indicator must be highly correlated to its construct only. In the SmartPLS 3.3.3 application, the discriminant validity test uses cross loadings, Fornell-Larkcer, and Heterortrait-Monotrait values.

Structural or Inner Model

Inner model analysis is usually also called (inner relation, structural model and substantive theory) which describes the relationship between latent variables based on substantive theory. Inner model analysis can be evaluated using R-square for dependent constructs, Cross-validated Redundancy (Q²) for predictive relevance and Path Coefficients or Path Coefficients. In evaluating the inner model with PLS (Partial Least Square) it begins by looking at the R-square for each dependent latent variable. In addition to looking at the R-square value, the PLS (Partial Least Square) model also uses Cross-validated Redundancy (Q²) or Q-square to assess predictive relevance for constructive models. Q-square measures how well the observation values are generated by the model and its parameter estimates. If the Q² value > 0 indicates that the model has accurate predictive relevance to a particular construct. However, if the Q² value < 0 indicates that the model lacks predictive relevance. To obtain the Cross-validated Redundancy (Q²) value using the SmartPLS 3.2.8 application. with the Blindfolding procedure (Calculate $\diamond$ Blindfolding).

Hypothesis Testing

During the hypothesis analysis, the use of SmartPLS together with bootstrapping will produce a t-statistic value for each hypothesized relationship. The t-statistic value will be compared with the t-table value. The analysis uses a 95% confidence level so that the level of significance or inaccuracy limit (α) = 5% = 0.05 and the t-table value is 1.96. If the t-statistic value is smaller than the t-table value (t-statistic < 1.96), then Ho is accepted and Ha is rejected. If the t-statistic value is greater than or equal to the t-table (tstatistic > 1.96), then Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Measurement model testing (outer model) is used to determine the specifications of the relationship between latent variables and their manifest variables, this testing includes convergent validity, discriminant validity and reliability.

1. Convergent Validity

This test is seen from the loading factor, the value limit is 0.7, and the value limit Average Variance Extracted(AVE) is 0.5, if it is above that value it is said to be valid. This means that the value for the indicator is said to be valid, if the indicator explains the construct variable with a value > 0.7. The structural model in this study is shown in the following figure:

Figure 2. Outer Model
Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Smart PLS output for loading factor gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Z = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + e_1$$

$$Z = 0.358X_1 + 0.238 X_2+ 0.394 X_3+ e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_3X_1 + b_4X_2 + b_5X_3 + b_6X_1Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.234X_1 + 0.044 X_2+ 0.272 X_3+ 0.432 Z + e_2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Work Discipline (Z)	Integrity (X1)	Job Satisfaction (Y)	Competence (X2)	Motivation (X3)
X1.1		0.908			
X1.2		0.888			
X1.3		0.759			
X1.4		0.836			
X2.1				0.864	

X2.2				0.865	
X2.3				0.872	
X2.4				0.888	
X2.5				0.875	
X3.1					0.810
X3.2					0.872
X3.3					0.793
X3.4					0.857
X3.5					0.901
Y.1			0.915		
Y.2			0.894		
Y.3			0.910		
Y.4			0.838		
Z.1	0.900				
Z.2	0.832				
Z.3	0.869				
Z.4	0.876				
Z.5	0.821				
Z.6	0.784				
Z.7	0.848				
Z.8	0.851				

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 1 above, the value of each variable is stated that the indicator in each variable is higher than 0.7, which means that each indicator item has a value higher than 0.7 so that the data is declared valid and can continue to further research.

Discriminant Validity

Further research will determine the validity of the data using Discriminate Validity, with the aim of finding out whether the cross loading value is greater than other latent variables in order to find out the findings of indicators that have a strong relationship with the concept. The following table shows the findings of cross loading from the validity test, as follows:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Work Discipline (Z)	Integrity (X1)	Job Satisfaction (Y)	Competence (X2)	Motivation (X3)
X1.1	0.839	0.908	0.863	0.805	0.842
X1.2	0.825	0.888	0.784	0.760	0.765
X1.3	0.669	0.759	0.657	0.578	0.647
X1.4	0.783	0.836	0.784	0.826	0.775
X2.1	0.727	0.733	0.701	0.864	0.764
X2.2	0.799	0.730	0.775	0.865	0.754
X2.3	0.824	0.750	0.777	0.872	0.762

X2.4	0.845	0.870	0.850	0.888	0.833
X2.5	0.737	0.747	0.730	0.875	0.763
X3.1	0.763	0.725	0.757	0.779	0.810
X3.2	0.802	0.741	0.800	0.825	0.872
X3.3	0.686	0.666	0.682	0.684	0.793
X3.4	0.785	0.784	0.763	0.697	0.857
X3.5	0.876	0.862	0.882	0.778	0.901
Y.1	0.853	0.804	0.915	0.793	0.845
Y.2	0.856	0.775	0.894	0.809	0.833
Y.3	0.837	0.823	0.910	0.770	0.855
Y.4	0.793	0.850	0.838	0.765	0.737
Z.1	0.900	0.876	0.897	0.861	0.912
Z.2	0.832	0.725	0.670	0.680	0.694
Z.3	0.869	0.768	0.765	0.750	0.756
Z.4	0.876	0.813	0.786	0.782	0.765
Z.5	0.821	0.780	0.731	0.703	0.714
Z.6	0.784	0.707	0.815	0.710	0.719
Z.7	0.848	0.761	0.843	0.799	0.873
Z.8	0.851	0.803	0.831	0.821	0.819

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

It can be seen in table 2 that the cross loading results show that the indicator has a greater value than the indicators of other latent variables or the correlation value of the construct with the measurement item is greater than the size of other constructs, so this shows that the latent construct has predicted the size of the construct variable block better than the size of other blocks.

Composite reliability

In composite reliability research, each variable is evaluated using its reliability value; if the variable value is greater than 0.60 then the research is considered reliable; if between 0.60 and 0.7, then it is not reliable. The table below shows the Cronbach alpha, composite reliability, and AVE values, which are used to determine whether the research is reliable and valid.

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Work Discipline (Z)	0.944	0.953	0.719
Integrity (X1)	0.870	0.912	0.722
Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.912	0.938	0.791
Competence (X2)	0.922	0.941	0.762
Motivation (X3)	0.901	0.927	0.718

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 3 above, the Cronbach alpha column shows the value of each variable is greater than 0.7, indicating that the reliability data can be relied on for that variable. The composite reliability column has a value greater than 0.6, indicating that each variable is considered reliable because the data exceeds 0.6. The AVE column shows that each variable has a value greater than 0.7, indicating that the data is original in terms of AVE. All variables in the Cronbach alpha, reliability, and AVE columns have values above 0.7 and 0.6, indicating reliability and validity.

Inner Model Analysis

Structural model evaluation (inner model) is conducted to ensure that the basic model created is strong and accurate. The stages of examination conducted in the primary model assessment are seen from several markers, namely:

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Work Discipline (Z)	0.911	0.907
Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.908	0.902

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

There are R square results in table 4 which will be explained as follows: in the work discipline variable there is an R square value of 0.911 if it is expressed as a percentage of 91.1%, meaning that the influence of integrity, competence and motivation on work discipline is 0.911 or 91.1%, the rest is on other variables, the job satisfaction variable has an R square value of 0.908 if expressed as a percentage of 90.8%, meaning that the influence of integrity, competence, motivation and work discipline on job satisfaction is 0.908 or 90.8%, the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After examining the inner model, the next step is to investigate the relationship between idle build, as suggested in this review. In this review, speculative testing is performed using T-Statistics and P-values. Speculation is made whether the T-Insights value is greater than 1.96 and P-Values <0.05. The following are the consequences of the direct impact path coefficients:

Table 5. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Work Discipline (Z) -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.432	4,627	0,000	Accepted
Integrity (X1) -> Work Discipline (Z)	0.358	3,323	0,000	Accepted
Integrity (X1) -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.234	2,433	0.008	Accepted

Competence (X2) -> Work Discipline (Z)	0.238	2,485	0.007	Accepted
Competence (X2) -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.044	0.466	0.321	Rejected
Motivation (X3) -> Work Discipline (Z)	0.394	3,671	0,000	Accepted
Motivation (X3) -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.272	2,884	0.002	Accepted

In table 5 there are the results of the hypothesis which will be explained one by one as follows:

1. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.422 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if discipline increases, job satisfaction increases, if work discipline decreases, job satisfaction decreases.
2. Integrity has a positive and significant effect on Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.358 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if integrity increases, work discipline increases, if integrity decreases, work discipline decreases.
3. Integrity has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.234 and p values of 0.008. If integrity increases, job satisfaction increases, if it decreases, job satisfaction decreases.
4. Competence has a positive and significant effect on work discipline with an original sample value of 0.234 and p values of 0.007, meaning that if competence increases, work discipline will increase, if competence decreases, work discipline will decrease.
5. Competence has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.044 and p values of 0.321, meaning that competence does not have a large effect on job satisfaction.
6. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.394 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if motivation increases, work discipline increases, conversely, if motivation decreases, work discipline decreases.
7. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.272 and p values of 0.002, meaning that if motivation increases, job satisfaction increases, if it decreases, job satisfaction decreases.

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Integrity (X1) -> Work Discipline (Z) -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.155	2,765	0.003	Accepted
Competence (X2) -> Work Discipline (Z) -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.103	2,223	0.013	Accepted
Motivation (X3) -> Work Discipline (Z) -> Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.170	2,705	0.004	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 6 there are indirect influences which will be explained as follows:

1. Integrity has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.155 and p values of 0.003, meaning that work

discipline is an intervening variable because it is able to have a significant effect, which means that with work discipline, integrity and job satisfaction will increase.

2. Competence has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.103 and p values of 0.013, meaning that work discipline is indeed an intervening variable because it is able to influence significantly, so that with work discipline it can increase competence and job satisfaction indirectly.
3. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.170 and p values of 0.004, meaning that work discipline is an intervening variable because it is able to have a significant effect, so with work discipline, motivation and job satisfaction increase well.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.422 and p values of 0.000.
2. Integrity has a positive and significant effect on Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.358 and p values of 0.000.
3. Integrity has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.234 and p values of 0.008.
4. Competence has a positive and significant effect on Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.234 and p values of 0.007.
5. Competence has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.044 and p values of 0.321.
6. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.394 and p values of 0.000.
7. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.272 and p values of 0.002.
8. Integrity has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.155 and p values of 0.003.
9. Competence has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.103 and p values of 0.013.
10. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.170 and p values of 0.004.

Suggestion

1. Organizations must improve employee integrity for organizational development, or seek employees who have good integrity.
2. Organizations must also improve employee competency so that employees can work well.
3. The organization must provide motivation to employees regularly with motivators who have interesting backgrounds.
4. Organizations must provide discipline to employees so that they can improve their performance.
5. Organizations must make employees feel satisfied with their work and the place where they work.
6. This research is expected to be input for organizational progress.

7. This research is expected to be a helpful reference material for new research with a new research model.

REFERENCES

- Agustian, 2018. Pengaruh Kompetensi Dan Komitmen Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai. *Majalah Ilmiah "DIAN ILMU"* Vo.17 No.2 April. Hal 58.
- Agoes, Sukrisno. 2017. *Auditing (Edisi 5 ed., Vol. Buku 1 dan 2)*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- Az-Zahra, Ratu Syiddah Ayu., et, all.2021. "Pengaruh Pengendalian Interna dan Integritas Karyawan terhadap Pencegahan Fraud". *Abdi Jurnal* , Vol.2, No.2
- Hasibuan, Malayu. 2017. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara
- Hasibuan, H. M. 2019, *Manajemen Sumberdaya Manusia*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- Hafidzi. 2019. Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja Lingkungan Kerja Budaya Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Dinas Sosial Kabupaten Jember. *Jurnal Penelitian Ipteks*. Vol. 4 No. 1.
- Hamali. 2016. *Pemahaman manajemen sumberdaya mausia*. Yogyakarta: Center for Academic Publishing Service
- Mulyadi. 2014. *Auditing. Edisi keenam*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- Sudaryo, Yoyo., Agus Aribowo, Nunung ayu Sofiati. 2018. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia, Kompensasi Tidak Langsung dan Lingkungan Kerja Fisik*. Yogyakarta: Penerbit Andi.
- Sujarweni, Wiratna. 2014. *Metodologi Penelitian*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Baru Press.
- Sugiyono, 2017. *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: CV. Alfabeta.
- Uhing, Yantje. 2019. Pengaruh Kemampuan Kerja Dan Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. *Jurnal EMBA*. Vol.8 No.1. Hal. 75 – 84.
- Umi Narimawati. 2010. *Metodologi Penelitian : Dasar Penyusun Penelitian Ekonomi*. Jakarta : Genesis.
- Wibowo., 2022., *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia: Menghadapi Tumbuhnya Generasi Milenial di Era Revolusi Industri 4.0 dan Society 5.0*, Rajawali Pers, Depok.

Implementation of Work Quality in Improving Performance

Handoko Utama¹, Mesra B²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: mesrab@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

Humankind holds a very important position in any organization because humans play an important role in daily life activities, especially in the workplace environment. Humans are seen by God as the purest form of life because they have a personality that is different from other forms of life. Without human resources, a business cannot carry out its activities, so human resources are very important. The results of this research are as follows: Organizational climate has a positive and insignificant effect with an original sample value of 0.026 and ap value of 0.421. Organizational climate has a positive and significant effect on work quality with an original sample of 0.777 and ap value of 0.000. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample of 0.595 and ap value of 0.000. The work environment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.354 and ap value of 0.020. Work Environment has a positive and insignificant effect on Work Quality with an original sample value of 0.146 and ap value of 0.242. Organizational climate has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through work quality indirectly with an original sample value of 0.462 and ap value of 0.004. Work Environment has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance through Work Quality indirectly with an original sample value of 0.087 and ap value of 0.242.

Keywords: Organizational Climate, Work Environment, Work Quality, Employee Performance

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important things to consider when analyzing human behavior is employee performance. Without human resources, a business cannot carry out its activities, so human resources are very important. In this era of globalization, human resources are considered as a resource needed for businesses to achieve success. A happy work culture will make employees feel excited to go to work and motivated to improve their work performance. This shows that when the climate of an organization becomes more stable, employee performance will also increase. One of the most important factors in organizational design is relationships, namely harmonious relationships between people, between leaders and employees, or between coworkers. The higher the organizational climate, the higher the performance of its human resources, conversely, the lower the organizational climate, the lower the performance of its human resources (Setiawan, 2015). The work environment is the environment where employees carry out their daily tasks. A conducive work environment provides a sense of security for employees and allows them to work as well as possible. The work environment can affect employee emotions. If employees are satisfied with their work environment, they will tend to work hard in their workspace to complete tasks so that their working hours can be used effectively and their productivity as employees also increases. Conditions of the work environment, living environment, and organizational conditions related to work, both government and private. Humanity and the workplace have a very strong bond, where there is a relationship between the workplace and the place where humans carry out daily activities. Quality work in a work environment is certainly the main thing for a company in running its business activities, but quality work will not be achieved if its employees are not good or good at communicating. Not only

employees, but leaders must also be able to communicate well in running business activities. Quality of work is the most important aspect needed by every human resource, without good quality of work, the results of the work produced will be bad, both those who work in offices and in large companies, because good quality of work can provide good service to the community and improve the quality of each existing organization, so that it is preferred by many people. Human resource development is an activity that is aimed collectively so that this company can face competitive challenges. similar as well as employees and managers. To achieve certain company goals, employees must be disciplined, have strong awareness, loyalty, obedience, and be open and honest about all work given and completed. Employee performance is the result of an employee's work performance during work. Performance is the result of employee work carried out within a previously agreed period of time. Work experience is the result of employee work after completing tasks that are in accordance with their abilities, goals, and objectives. Performance is the result of individual or group work in an organization, based on each person's firm commitment to achieving organizational goals in a moral, ethical, legal, and/or legally compliant manner. The motivation is self-discipline, self-esteem, and a strong desire to complete a task. When employers motivate their employees in an organization, it can have a negative impact on employee performance.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Organizational Climate Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Work Quality at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar?
2. Does the Work Environment have a positive and significant influence on Work Quality at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar?
3. Does Organizational Climate Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar?
4. Does the Work Environment have a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar?
5. Does Work Quality Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar?
6. Does Organizational Climate Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Employee Performance through Work Quality at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar?
7. Does the Work Environment have a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance through Work Quality at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar?

Research Objectives

1. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Climate on Work Quality at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar.
2. To determine and analyze the influence of the Work Environment on Work Quality at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar.
3. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Climate on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, Pematangsiantar.
4. To determine and analyze the influence of the work environment on employee performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, Pematangsiantar.
5. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Quality on Employee Performance through Work Quality at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar.

6. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Climate on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, Pematangsiantar.
7. To determine and analyze the influence of the Work Environment on Employee Performance through Work Quality at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee Performance

Understanding Employee Performance

According to Panggabean (2015), "performance or work achievement is the work result that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organization, in accordance with the authority and responsibility of each in order to achieve the goals of the organization concerned legally, without violating the law and in accordance with morals and ethics". According to Rivai (2015), "performance is the result or level of success of a person as a whole during a certain period in carrying out tasks compared to various possibilities, such as work result standards, targets or objectives or criteria that have been determined in advance and agreed upon together".

Employee Performance Indicators

According to Rivai (2015), "employee performance indicators are as follows:

1. Initiative is a different mindset in every work decision making, for example knowing and understanding problems in the work environment, being able to give advice to superiors or to fellow workers/employees.
2. Mental Agility The level of ability and speed in receiving work instructions and adapting to existing work methods and work situations.
3. Attitude: Level of work enthusiasm and positive attitude in carrying out work duties."

Organizational Climate

Understanding Organizational Climate

According to Hanum (2018), organizational climate is a characteristic used to differentiate an organization from other organizations and can influence the behavior of members of the organization. According to Setiawan (2015), organizational climate is about employee experiences in the organization and how characteristics originating from the environment, the behavior of people in the organization and everything related to the organization, such as leadership style, formal systems and others which also include motivation, values, attitudes and beliefs can influence members of the organization.

Indicators and Dimensions of Organizational Climate

Organizational climate indicators according to Setiawan et al., (2015), namely:

1. Structure: Dimension used to describe the clarity of work, permissions, work procedures and rules in a task.
2. Responsibility: A dimension that includes both responsibility for behavior in work and responsibility for the consequences of what results from the work done.
3. Rewards: Dimensions concerning the results received from work that has been done, either in the form of rewards or punishments according to the results that have been achieved.
4. Risk: Dimension regarding job challenges where employees are given the opportunity to take risks in carrying out their work as a challenge.

5. Warmth: This dimension relates to the relationship between employees in the organization which can determine the work atmosphere within the organization.
6. Support: Dimension related to how leaders or coworkers provide support to subordinates or fellow coworkers.
7. Performance standards: Dimensions related to employee views on the performance standards that the organization has set for employees and there is an emphasis on achieving better work results.
8. Conflict: Dimension regarding how employees can find solutions to problems that exist within the organization.
9. Self-identity: A dimension that describes the identification of organizational members according to the goals or norms that apply in the organization.

Work environment

Definition of work environment

According to (Darmadi, 2020), the work environment includes something that is around the employees so that it affects them in carrying out the obligations that have been given to them, such as air conditioning, good lighting and others. According to Fachrezi and Khair (2020) the work environment is a very important part in employees carrying out work activities. in carrying out the obligations that have been given to him, such as air conditioning, good lighting and others.

Work Environment Indicators

According to Fachrezi & Khair (2020), the work environment indicators are as follows:

- a. Facilities Good and adequate facilities can improve employee performance, conversely inadequate facilities can hinder employee performance.
- b. Noise Noise is unwanted sound pollution and can have negative impacts such as causing feelings of discomfort, disrupting concentration and becoming a disturbance in communication.
- c. Air circulation can have a negative impact on health and work quality, especially when the physical workload is high.
- d. Working relationships Working relationships between the people in it also influence comfort at work, giving rise to a feeling of calm at work.

Quality of Work

Definition of Work Quality

Work quality is an employee's understanding of mental and physical well-being in the workplace (Hasmalawati, 2018). Work quality can also be said to be any kind of barometer that has a relationship with the value of work results that can be explained in numbers. Work quality is also interpreted as a way that companies use to fulfill the needs of their employees so that they can feel comfortable working and produce effective work (Nurul & Rahardja, 2019).

Work Quality Indicators

The following are indicators of work quality according to Nurul & Rahardja (2019):

1. Employee participation Employees must have a role in decision making and can contribute to achieving targets.

2. Career development Employees need assurance of clarity regarding their careers in order to develop.
3. Conflict resolution Employees are expected to be able to solve and resolve existing problems openly, fairly and honestly.
4. Communication: Being a very good role player with fellow co-workers and with leaders.
5. Occupational health This effort aims to actualize the maximization of work productivity.
6. Job security There needs to be a guarantee or sense of security for its workers. Therefore, the company is required to have an agreement with the parties related to the work contract, salary, and others.
7. Work safety Establish a safety committee, emergency help team and work safety program.
8. Compensation Employees must receive compensation that is fair, reasonable and adequate.
9. Pride Employees' feelings of pride in their work and work environment can make them more comfortable and at home in working well.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Research Hypothesis

- H1 Organizational Climate has a positive and significant effect on Work Quality at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar.
- H2 The work environment has a positive and significant influence on work quality at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar.
- H3 Organizational climate has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar.
- H4 The work environment has a positive and significant influence on employee performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar.
- H5 Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar.
- H6 Organizational Climate has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance and Work Quality at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar.
- H7 The work environment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance and work quality at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar.

METHOD

Types of research

According to Sugiyono (2019), quantitative research is defined as a research method based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations or samples, data collection using research instruments, quantitative/statistical data analysis, with the aim of testing predetermined hypotheses.

Time and location of research

This research was conducted in September - October 2024. The location of this research was conducted at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar. The address of this research is Jalan Adam Malik No.1. Pematangsiantar.

Research Population

The population of this study was all employees of the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar, totaling 40 employees. According to Sugiyono (2019), population is a generalization area consisting of: objects/subjects that have certain quantities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn.

Research Sample

The sample in this study used all the population at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in Pematangsiantar amounting to 40 and this study used a saturated sample technique. According to Sugiyono (2019) a sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population.

Research Data Sources

The research sources used in this study are primary data research sources. The type of data used in this study is primary data. According to Sugiyono (2019) primary data is a data source that directly provides data to data collectors.

Data collection technique

The data collection technique used in this research uses a questionnaire, the questionnaire will be distributed to respondents. According to Sugiyono (2019), a questionnaire is a data collection technique carried out by giving respondents a set of written questions or statements to answer.

Data Analysis Methods

After the research data was collected, data analysis was carried out. Data analysis was carried out by grouping data based on variables and types of respondents, data was tabulated based on variables from all respondents, data for each variable was presented, calculations were carried out to provide answers to the problem formulation and calculations were carried out to test the proposed hypothesis (Sugiyono, 2019). This study analyzed data using the help of Smart PLS software version 3.0. The following is a picture of the PLS SEM Test model.

Structural Equation Modeling Analysis

Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS) Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is a second-generation multivariate analysis technique that allows testing of correlations between complex variables to obtain a complete reflection of the entire model. Structural and

measurement models can be tested simultaneously in SEM (Ghozali, 2014). More specifically, this study uses a variant-based Structural Equation Modeling method, namely Partial Least Square (PLS).

Evaluation of Measurement Model (Outer Model)

The assessment of the validity and reliability of the model is measured through the outer model. Validity testing is related to ensuring the ability of the research instrument to measure an object, while the reliability test functions to measure the consistency of the measuring instrument in measuring a concept and measuring the consistency of respondents in answering the research instrument (Abdillah & Hartono, 2016). A detailed explanation of the components of the measurement model is as follows:

- a. Convergent Validity Measurement of the magnitude of the correlation between constructs and latent variables is carried out through convergent validity. Convergent validity testing can be seen from the loading factor for each construct indicator. The ideal loading factor value is > 0.7 which indicates the validity of the indicator to measure the formed construct. Loading factor > 0.5 can still be tolerated in empirical research. The percentage of constructs that can explain the variation of indicators is indicated by this value (Haryono, 2017).
- b. Discriminant Validity Cross loading between indicators and their constructs shows the discriminant validity of the indicators. If the correlation of the construct with its indicators is higher than the correlation of the indicators with other constructs, then the latent construct predicts the indicators in their block better than the indicators of other blocks. Discriminant validity is tested with reflective indicators by considering the cross loading value of each variable must be > 0.7 (Ghozali & Latan, 2015).
- c. Composite Reliability Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability are ways to measure the reliability of a construct with reflective items. Testing the reliability of the construct through Cronbach's Alpha presents a lower value so that the use of Composite Reliability is more recommended (Ghozali & Latan, 2015). The rule of thumb is that the composite reliability value must be higher than 0.7 although a value of 0.6 is still tolerable (Abdillah & Hartono, 2016).

Structural Model Evaluation (Inner Model)

The description of the relationship between latent variables based on substantive theory is obtained from the inner model. The following describes the components of the structural model evaluation in PLS.

- a. R-Square (R²) The structural model assessment is first carried out by assessing the R-square for each endogenous latent variable as the predictive power of the structural model. Changes in the R-Square value can be used to explain the influence of certain exogenous latent variables on endogenous latent variables whether they have a substantive influence. The R-Square value is 0.75 (strong model) 0.50 (moderate) and 0.25 (weak) (Ghozali & Latan, 2015).
- b. Predictive Relevance (Q²) PLS model evaluation can also be done with Q-square. Q-square measures how well the observation values generated by the model and also its parameter estimates. A Q² value > 0 shows that the model has predictive relevance, or vice versa. More specifically, the Q² value is 0.02 (weak model), 0.15 (moderate), and 0.35 (strong) (Ghozali & Latan, 2015).
- c. Goodness of Fit (GoF). Goodness of Fit (GoF) is used in evaluating measurement models and structural models and shows the overall level of model suitability.

Hypothesis Testing

In general, SmartPLS is used in the explanatory research method approach, because it involves hypothesis testing. Hypothesis testing can be seen through the t-statistic value and probability value. The following describes hypothesis testing.

Hypothesis Testing (Bootstrapping) The bootstrapping procedure is performed to assess the significance of the influence between variables. All original samples are used to resample again in the bootstrap procedure. The number of bootstrap samples of 5,000 is recommended with the notation that the original sample is smaller than that number, but the number of bootstrap samples of 200-1000 is said to be sufficient by some literature to correct the PLS standard error estimate (Ghozali & Latan, 2015). In the bootstrap resampling method, the significance value used (one-tailed) t-value is 1.28 (10% significance level); 1.65 (5% significance level); and 2.33 (1% significance level). This study uses a 5% significance level so that the t-value used is 1.65.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Measurement model testing (outer model) is used to determine the relationship between latent and manifest variables. This test includes convergent validity, discriminant validity, and reliability.

Convergent Validity

This test is seen from the loading factor; the limit value is 0.7, and the limit value Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is 0.5; if it exceeds this number then it is said to be valid. This means that the indicator value is considered valid if it describes the build variable with a value greater than 0.7. The structural model used in this study is depicted in the figure below:

Figure 2. Outer Model
Source: Smart PLS3.3.3

Smart PLS output for loading factors gives the results in the table below: External Loading In this study, there is a relationship consisting of two substructures.

for substructure 1

$$Z = b1X1 + b2X2 + e1$$

$$Z = 0.777X1 + 0.146X2 + e1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b3X2 + b4X1 + b5Z + e2$$

$$Y = 0.026 X1+ 0.354X2 + 0.595Z + e2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Organizational Climate (X1)	Employee Performance (Y)	Quality of Work (Z)	Work Environment (X2)
X1.1	0.765			
X1.2	0.806			
X1.3	0.798			
X1.4	0.725			
X1.5	0.869			
X1.6	0.886			
X1.7	0.885			
X1.8	0.843			
X1.9	0.767			
X2.1				0.791
X2.2				0.923
X2.3				0.831
X2.4				0.891
Y.1		0.876		
Y.2		0.863		
Y.3		0.926		
Z.1			0.789	
Z.2			0.902	
Z.3			0.850	
Z.4			0.808	
Z.5			0.717	
Z.6			0.838	
Z.7			0.806	
Z.8			0.857	
Z.9			0.871	

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3

Table 1 above shows the value of each variable, and states that the indicator of each variable is greater than 0.7, which means that each indicator item has a value greater than 0.7, indicating that the data is original and can be subjected to additional research.

Discriminant Validity

Further research will determine the validity of the data using Discriminate Validity, with the aim of finding out whether the cross loading value is greater than other latent variables in order to find out the findings of indicators that have a strong relationship with the concept. The following table shows the findings of cross loading from the validity test, as follows:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Organizational Climate (X1)	Employee Performance (Y)	Quality of Work (Z)	Work Environment (X2)
X1.1	0.765	0.623	0.642	0.724
X1.2	0.806	0.815	0.731	0.784
X1.3	0.798	0.650	0.721	0.731
X1.4	0.725	0.699	0.636	0.667
X1.5	0.869	0.787	0.811	0.851
X1.6	0.886	0.739	0.768	0.872
X1.7	0.885	0.903	0.932	0.854
X1.8	0.843	0.746	0.788	0.775
X1.9	0.767	0.634	0.635	0.648
X2.1	0.783	0.683	0.692	0.791
X2.2	0.894	0.823	0.828	0.923
X2.3	0.749	0.716	0.728	0.831
X2.4	0.817	0.868	0.770	0.891
Y.1	0.738	0.876	0.775	0.733
Y.2	0.830	0.863	0.857	0.849
Y.3	0.836	0.926	0.842	0.814
Z.1	0.765	0.812	0.789	0.736
Z.2	0.850	0.835	0.902	0.840
Z.3	0.709	0.729	0.850	0.700
Z.4	0.709	0.659	0.808	0.700
Z.5	0.711	0.659	0.717	0.653
Z.6	0.726	0.730	0.838	0.659
Z.7	0.734	0.840	0.806	0.694
Z.8	0.830	0.863	0.857	0.849
Z.9	0.756	0.763	0.871	0.683

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3

It can be seen in table 2 above that the cross loading factor value of each variable and its indicators can be explained that the cross loading value of each variable gets a greater value than the cross loading on other latent variables to each variable, meaning that this study is discriminantly valid.

Composite reliability

In composite reliability research to see each variable with its reliability value and if the variable value is greater than 0.60 then the research is considered reliable and if below

0.60 and 0.7 then it is not reliable there are several blocks to determine whether the research is reliable or not and valid or not including the Cronbach alpha value, composite reliability and AVE value can be seen in the table below:

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Organizational Climate (X1)	0.937	0.948	0.669
Employee Performance (Y)	0.867	0.919	0.790
Quality of Work (Z)	0.942	0.951	0.686
Work Environment (X2)	0.882	0.919	0.741

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3

In table 3 above, the Cronbach alpha column shows the value of each variable is greater than 0.7, indicating that the variable's dependability data is reliable. The composite reliability column has a value greater than 0.6, indicating that each variable is considered reliable because the data exceeds 0.6. The AVE column shows that each variable has a value greater than 0.7, indicating that the data is authentic in terms of AVE. All variables in the Cronbach alpha, reliability, and AVE columns have values above 0.7 and 0.6, indicating reliability and validity.

Inner Model Analysis

The structural model (inner model) is evaluated to ensure that the resulting basic model is strong and correct. Some markers that can be used to identify the stages of the main model assessment examination include:

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Employee Performance (Y)	0.897	0.888
Quality of Work (Z)	0.839	0.830

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3

There is an R square value in table 4 which will be explained for the R square value of the Employee Performance variable, there is a value of 0.897 or 89.7%, meaning that the influence of organizational climate, work environment and work quality on employee performance is 0.897 or 89.7% and the rest is on other variables, the R square value of the work quality variable is 0.839 or 83.9%, meaning that the influence of the organizational climate and work environment variables on work quality is 0.830 or 83.0% and the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After determining the inner model, the next step is to determine the relationship between the idle construct and the assumption in this case. Speculation in this review is done by looking at the T-Statistics and P-Values. The test determines whether T-Insights > 1.96 and P-Values < 0.05. The following are the results of the direct impact Path Coefficient.

Table 5: Direct Influence

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Organizational Climate (X1) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.026	0.200	0.421	Rejected
Organizational Climate (X1) -> Work Quality (Z)	0.777	3,899	0,000	Accepted
Work Quality (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.595	3,826	0,000	Accepted
Work Environment (X2) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.354	2,058	0.020	Accepted
Work Environment (X2) -> Work Quality (Z)	0.146	0.699	0.242	Rejected

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3

1. Organizational climate has a positive but insignificant effect with an original sample value of 0.026 and p values of 0.421, meaning that organizational climate does not have much effect on employee performance, employees can still work and adapt to the climate that exists in the organization.
2. Organizational climate has a positive and significant effect on work quality with an original sample of 0.777 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if the organizational climate improves, the work quality will improve, conversely, if the organizational climate decreases, the work quality will decrease.
3. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample of 0.595 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if work quality increases, employee performance will also increase, conversely, if work quality decreases, employee performance will decrease.
4. The work environment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.354 and p values of 0.020, meaning that if the work environment improves, employee performance will improve, conversely, if the quality of work decreases, employee performance will decrease.
5. The work environment has a positive and insignificant effect on work quality with an original sample value of 0.146 and p values of 0.242, meaning that the work environment has little effect in improving the quality of employee work. Some employees really need a work environment as a support to improve performance, but there are still more employees who do not care about their work environment.

Table 6: Indirect Influence

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Organizational Climate (X1) -> Work Quality (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.462	2,648	0.004	Accepted

Work Environment (X2) -> Work Quality (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.087	0.701	0.242	Rejected
---	-------	-------	-------	----------

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3

1. Organizational Climate has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Work Quality indirectly with an original sample value of 0.462 and p values of 0.004, meaning that work quality is an intervening variable because it is able to influence organizational climate and employee performance indirectly, with a good organizational climate performance will increase significantly and with the inclusion of good work quality performance can also increase indirectly.
2. Work Environment has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance through Work Quality indirectly with the original sample value of 0.087 and p values 0.242, meaning that work quality is not an intervening variable because it is unable to influence the work environment and employee performance indirectly, and a bad or good work environment, work quality will never decrease because work quality is the identity that has been owned since the beginning of entering the world of work, experience is the formation of work quality, therefore the work environment does not have much influence in improving work and work quality either directly or indirectly.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Organizational climate has a positive but insignificant effect with an original sample value of 0.026 and p values of 0.421.
2. Organizational Climate has a positive and significant effect on Work Quality with an original sample of 0.777 and p values of 0.000.
3. Work Quality has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample of 0.595 and p values of 0.000.
4. Work environment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.354 and p values of 0.020.
5. Work environment has a positive and insignificant effect on work quality with an original sample value of 0.146 and p values of 0.242.
6. Organizational Climate has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Work Quality indirectly with an original sample value of 0.462 and p values of 0.004.
7. Work environment has a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance through work quality indirectly with an original sample value of 0.087 and p values of 0.242.

Suggestion

1. The organization must create a comfortable organizational climate for employees to feel, and make employees feel relaxed at work.
2. Organizations must create a healthy working environment to avoid mistakes and disputes between employees.
3. Organizations must think about how to improve work quality.
4. Organizations must also look at employee performance developments.
5. It is hoped that this research will be used as input for employees to correct problems that exist in the organization.

6. It is hoped that this research can be developed by other researchers with a similar title but using a different model.
7. It is hoped that this research will be used as reference material to help subsequent researchers.

REFERENCES

- Abdillah, W., & Hartono, J. (2016). Partial Least Square (PLS) Alternatif Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) dalam Penelitian Bisnis. Andi Offset.
- Darmadi, D. (2020). Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada Indomaret Cabang Kelapa Dua Gading Serpong Kabupaten Tangerang. *JIMF (Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen Forkamma)*, 3(3), 240–247. <https://doi.org/10.32493/frkm.v3i3.5140>
- Fachrezi, H., & Khair, H. (2020). Pengaruh Komunikasi, Motivasi dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada PT. Angkasa Pura II (Persero) Kantor Cabang Kualanamu. *Maneggio: Jurnal Ilmiah Magister Manajemen*, 3(1), 107– 119. <https://doi.org/10.30596/maneggio.v3i1.4834>
- Ghozali, Imam. (2015). “Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate Dengan Program SPSS”. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Ghozali, Imam dan Hengky Latan (2015). Partial Least Squares Konsep Teknik dan Aplikasi dengan Program Smart PLS 3.0. Semarang: Universitas Diponegoro Semarang.
- Hanum, N. (2018). Pengaruh Pendapatan, Jumlah Tanggungan Keluarga dan Pendidikan Terhadap Pola Konsumsi Rumah Tangga Nelayan di Desa Seuneubok Rambong Aceh Timur. *Jurnal Samudra Ekonomika*, 2(1), 75- 84.
- Hasmalawati, (2018.) Pengaruh Kualitas Kehidupan Kerja dan Motivasi Kerjaterhadap Kinerja Karyawan, *Jurnal Psikologi Ilmiah*, Vol. 3, No. 2, 1-9.
- Rahardja, Edy & Nurul, C. R., (2019), Pengaruh Kualitas Kehidupan Kerja, Motivasi Kerja dan Kepuasan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan (Studi pada PT. Djarum Kudus), *Diponegoro Journal Of Management*, Volume 8, hal. 128-137.
- Setiawan. (2015). Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Level Pelaksana di Divisi Operasi PT. Pusri Palembang. *PSIKIS-Jurnal Psikologi Islami* Vol. 1 No. 2 (2015) 43-53.
- Sugiyono, (2017). Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D. Bandung: CV. Alfabeta.
- Ukkas Dan Dirham Latif, (2017). Pengaruh Iklim Organisasi Dan Komitmen Organisasi Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Ocb). *Jurnal Equilibrium*. ISSN 2089-2152. Vol. 06 No. 01 Februari .
- Veithzal Rivai Zainal, S. (2015). Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Untuk Perusahaan . Edisike-7. Depok: PT RAJAGRAFINDO.

Optimizing Performance

Muhammad Khairul Ibaad Pohan¹, Mesra B²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: mesrab@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

This research aims to examine the influence of leadership style and organizational culture on employee performance in the moderated work climate at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province. Humans need special attention because basically they are able to develop, have reasons, ideas, feelings, desires and hopes. These variables also influence achievement, dedication, loyalty and love of work as well as organizational success. Therefore, human resource management is very necessary to improve employee performance, so that it is beneficial for the company and able to survive in a competitive and dynamic business climate. The results of this research are as follows: Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.446 and ap value of 0.000. Work Climate cannot moderate Leadership Style on Employee Performance with an original sample value of -0.033 and ap value of 0.420. Work Climate is unable to moderate Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.031 and ap value of 0.419. Leadership style has a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance with an original sample of 0.115 and ap value of 0.128. Work Climate has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.392 and ap value of 0.000.

Keywords: Leadership Style, Organizational Culture, Work Climate, Employee Performance.

INTRODUCTION

An important component of an organization's success is human resources (HR). Therefore, in order for a company to function well and achieve its goals, each employee needs to have the following qualities: knowledge, skills, and abilities; in addition, they need to have experience; motivation; discipline; and uphold their work. Therefore, human resource management is very much needed to improve employee performance, so that it is beneficial to the company and able to survive in a competitive and dynamic business climate. The style of a leader is very important in any business operation. Because every human being has limitations and needs help in achieving tasks, leadership and leadership are very important in an organization. Leadership style has a significant influence on the goals, objectives, and outputs of an organization because each leader in the company has unique methods and traits that they use in leading. Each leader has his/her own leadership style. To better understand the responsibilities and main activities of a leader, managers must have competencies that are in line with development expectations and provide outstanding service both now and in the future. This is the strategic role played by a leader. The organizational culture of a company, which is developed through the process of creating ideas set by leading companies and then embedded in members of the organization, has a significant impact on the growth of the company. Cultural evolution follows, taking into account the needs of the organization and changes in the environment. Without preserving its culture, the organizational culture of an organization will not grow and prosper. has a significant cultural impact on the tactics used to achieve predetermined goals. One important element that can influence how an organization reacts to its external environment is its organizational culture. a set of ideals and common views about what is important and how to do things in the workplace. To improve employee performance, organizational culture offers a framework

for organizing and directing important and positive behaviors towards organizational commitment variables. Extreme environments are important because human adaptability varies greatly and depends on various factors. A good work climate is expected to spur high employee performance. The work climate is also one of the physical factors that have the potential to cause health problems for workers when in extreme conditions. Employee performance is defined as work achievement, namely the comparison of actual work results with work criteria that have been set by the company. If an organization can select potential personnel who are well-motivated, suitable for the job, and have the characteristics that allow it to be done optimally, then quality performance will be achieved. Performance is basically what workers can or cannot do. When workers and employees perform well, they can complete the tasks given to them faster and in a shorter time. The extent to which an employee meets their goals or completes tasks according to the responsibilities given to them within a specified time period is known as employee performance.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Leadership Style Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
2. Does Organizational Culture have a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
3. Is Work Climate Able to Moderate Leadership Style on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province?
4. Is Work Climate Able to Moderate Organizational Culture on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province?
5. Does the Work Climate have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of Leadership Style on Employee Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
2. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
3. To find out and analyze the Work Climate that can moderate Leadership Style on Employee Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
4. To find out and analyze the Work Climate that can moderate Organizational Culture on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
5. To determine the influence of work climate on employee performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee Performance

Understanding Employee Performance

According to Aziz and Fauzah (2018) Performance is a description of the level of achievement of the implementation of a program of activities or policies in realizing the goals, objectives, vision and mission of an organization which is outlined through the strategic planning of an organization. According to Nurjaya (2021) performance is the level

of achievement of results from the implementation of certain tasks. Company performance is the level of achievement of results in order to realize company goals.

Employee Performance Indicators

According to Nurjaya (2021), employee performance indicators are as follows:

1. Quantity of work results, namely all forms of the amount of labor carried out can be seen from the results of employee performance within a certain time in completing their tasks and responsibilities within the specified time.
2. Quality of work results, namely all forms of units of measurement related to the quality or standard of work results which can be expressed in numerical measurements or other numerical equivalents.
3. Efficiency, namely in carrying out tasks using various resources wisely and in a cost-effective manner.
4. Work discipline, namely obeying applicable laws and regulations.
5. Initiative, namely the ability to decide and do something right without having to be told, being able to find out what should be done about something that is around, trying to keep moving to do several things even though the situation feels increasingly difficult.
6. Accuracy, namely the level of conformity of the work measurement results to whether the work has achieved its objectives or not.
7. Leadership, namely the process of influencing or giving examples by leaders to their followers in an effort to achieve organizational goals.
8. Honesty, which is a human trait that is quite difficult to implement.
9. Creativity, namely a mental process that involves the emergence of ideas or that involves the emergence of ideas.

Leadership Style

Understanding Leadership Styles

According to Fahmi, et al. (2014), leadership style is a norm driven by a person when the person tries to influence the behavior of others as seen. According to Paramita (2017), Leadership is an activity of influencing people so that they are willing to work together to achieve the desired goals.

Leadership Style Indicators

According to Paramita (2017) the leadership style indicators are as follows:

1. Decision-Making Ability Decision-making is a systematic approach to the nature of the alternatives faced and taking action which according to calculations is the most appropriate action.
2. Ability to Motivate Ability to motivate is the driving force that causes a member of an organization to be willing and ready to mobilize his abilities (in the form of expertise or skills), energy and time to carry out various activities that are his responsibility and fulfill his obligations, in order to achieve the goals and various targets of the organization that have been previously determined.
3. Communication Skills Communication skills are the skills or ability to convey messages, ideas or thoughts to other people with the aim that other people understand what is meant well, directly orally or indirectly.
4. Ability to Control Subordinates A leader must have the desire to make others follow his wishes by using personal power or position effectively and appropriately.

5. Responsibility A leader must have responsibility to his subordinates. Responsibility can be interpreted as an obligation that must be borne, shouldered, responsible for everything or given responsibility and bear the consequences.
6. Ability to Control Emotions The ability to control emotions is very important for the success of our lives. The better our ability to control emotions, the easier it is for us to achieve happiness.

Organizational culture

Understanding Organizational Culture

According to Emron, et al. (2018), organizational culture is the result of the process of merging the cultural style and/or behavior of each individual that was previously brought into new norms and philosophies, which have energy and group pride in facing something and certain goals. According to Sedarmayanti (2016), organizational culture is a belief, attitude, and value that is generally held, which arises in an organization, expressed more simply, and culture is the way we do things here.

Organizational Culture Indicators

According to Emron, et al. (2018), the indicators of organizational culture are:

- a. Self-awareness Members of the organization consciously work to gain satisfaction from their work, develop themselves, obey the rules, and offer quality products and high services.
- b. Aggressiveness Organization members set challenging but realistic goals. They establish work plans and strategies to achieve these goals and pursue them enthusiastically.
- c. Personality. Members are respectful, friendly, open, and sensitive to group satisfaction and pay close attention to aspects of customer satisfaction, both internal and external customers (in the perspective of Ishikawa, a Japanese quality expert, every internal part must serve, not be served).
- d. Performance. Members of the organization have a level of creativity, meet quantity, quality, and efficiency.
- e. Team orientation Organization members cooperate well and carry out effective communication and coordination with the active involvement of members, which in turn results in high satisfaction and shared commitment.

Working Climate

Understanding Work Climate

According to Daryanto, (2015), work climate is a relationship between personnel, social and cultural factors that influence individuals and groups in the environment. According to Siswanto (2015) work climate is defined as a perception of organizational policies, practices and procedures.

Work Climate Indicators

Work climate indicators according to Siswanto (2015) include:

1. Put trust and be open
2. Be sympathetic and provide support
3. Be honest and respectful
4. Clarity of Purpose
5. Risky work
6. Personality growth

7. Autonomy and flexibility

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

- H1 Leadership style has a positive and significant influence on employee performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H2 Organizational Culture has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H3 Organizational Climate has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H4 Work Climate can moderate Leadership Style on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H5 Work Climate can moderate Organizational Culture on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.

METHOD

Types of research

This study uses quantitative research type. According to Sugiyono (2019) quantitative research is defined as a research method based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research a certain population or sample, data collection using research instruments, data analysis is quantitative / statistical, with the aim of testing the established hypothesis.

Time and Location of Research

This research was conducted from September to October 2024. The location of this research was at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province on Jalan Balai Kota No. 4, Medan City.

Population

The population of this study was 70 employees of the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province. According to Sugiyono (2019) population is a

generalization area consisting of: objects / subjects that have certain quantities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn.

Sample

The researcher took samples in this study from all populations in the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province as many as 70 employees and used the saturated sampling technique as the sampling technique. According to Sugiyono (2019) a sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population.

Research Data Sources

The data source used is a primary data source where researchers take data directly from the research location. According to Sugiyono (2019) primary data is a data source that directly provides data to data collectors.

Data collection technique

Researchers use questionnaires as a data collection technique and will distribute the questionnaires directly and have them filled out by respondents. According to Sugiyono, (2019) in terms of method or data collection, data collection techniques can be carried out by distributing questionnaires.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

In this study, the acceptable loading factor value is 0.7 and the acceptable AVE value is 0.5; higher values are considered valid. When explaining the construct variables, indicators with values greater than 0.7 are considered valid. The following graph illustrates the structural model of this investigation:

Table 1. Outer Loadings/Cross Loading Stage 1

	Organizational Culture (X2)	Leadership Style (X1)	Work Climate (Z)	Employee Performance (Y)
X1.1		0.802		
X1.2		0.818		
X1.3		0.760		
X1.4		0.713		
X1.5		0.830		
X1.6		0.852		
X2.1	0.826			
X2.2	0.818			
X2.3	0.769			
X2.4	0.841			
X2.5	0.908			
Y.1				0.818
Y.2				0.801
Y.3				0.859
Y.4				0.844
Y.5				0.794

Y.6				0.854
Y.7				0.831
Y.8				0.691
Y.9				0.799
Z.1			0.825	
Z.2			0.836	
Z.3			0.828	
Z.4			0.875	
Z.5			0.821	
Z.6			0.826	
Z.7			0.646	

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

It can be seen in table 1 one there is a cross loading value in each variable and its indicator because there is still a cross loading on the invalid indicator, then another action will be taken, namely deleting the invalid cross loading and then recalculating it, we can see that the invalid indicators are in indicator Z.7 and indicator Y.8, then the calculation stage 2 will be made as follows:

Table 2. Outer Loadings/Cross Loading Stage 2

	Organizational Culture (X2)	Leadership Style (X1)	Work Climate (Z)	Employee Performance (Y)
X1.1		0.802		
X1.2		0.818		
X1.3		0.760		
X1.4		0.712		
X1.5		0.830		
X1.6		0.853		
X2.1	0.826			
X2.2	0.819			
X2.3	0.768			
X2.4	0.841			
X2.5	0.909			
Y.1				0.796
Y.2				0.826
Y.3				0.869
Y.4				0.839
Y.5				0.827
Y.6				0.867
Y.7				0.831
Y.9				0.781
Z.1			0.842	
Z.2			0.847	
Z.3			0.832	

Z.4			0.888	
Z.5			0.825	
Z.6			0.809	

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 2, this cross loading becomes stage 2 here the calculation of cross loading without the indicators of Z.7 and Y.8 indicators and the results obtained for each indicator have a cross loading value greater than 0.700 or 0.7, meaning that this research is valid and will conduct further research.

Figure 2: Research Model

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Smart PLS output for loading factor gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two equations.

$$Y = b_1X_1 + b_2Z + b_3X_1Z + e_1$$

$$Y = 0.115 X_1 + 0.392Z + 0.031X_1Z + e_1$$

$$Y = b_2X_2 + b_3Z + b_4X_2Z + e_1$$

$$Y = 0.446 X_2 + 0.392 Z - 0.033X_2Z + e_1$$

Discriminant Validity

The next test is to test the discriminant validity, this test aims to determine whether a reflective indicator is a good measurement for its construct based on the principle that the indicator is highly correlated to its construct. The table shows the cross loading results of the discriminant validity test as follows:

Table 3. Discriminant Validity

	Organizational Culture (X2)	Leadership Style (X1)	Work Climate (Z)	Employee Performance (Y)
X1.1	0.601	0.802	0.610	0.585
X1.2	0.605	0.818	0.664	0.666
X1.3	0.667	0.760	0.634	0.639
X1.4	0.657	0.712	0.603	0.602
X1.5	0.735	0.830	0.670	0.657
X1.6	0.736	0.853	0.675	0.669
X2.1	0.826	0.781	0.835	0.802
X2.2	0.819	0.591	0.641	0.674
X2.3	0.768	0.616	0.614	0.606
X2.4	0.841	0.729	0.628	0.726
X2.5	0.909	0.751	0.787	0.775
Y.1	0.696	0.718	0.681	0.796
Y.2	0.695	0.586	0.684	0.826
Y.3	0.802	0.714	0.783	0.869
Y.4	0.691	0.608	0.643	0.839
Y.5	0.652	0.494	0.624	0.827
Y.6	0.766	0.678	0.743	0.867
Y.7	0.676	0.680	0.741	0.831
Y.9	0.746	0.794	0.757	0.781
Z.1	0.741	0.630	0.842	0.651
Z.2	0.744	0.725	0.847	0.778
Z.3	0.705	0.708	0.832	0.730
Z.4	0.816	0.746	0.888	0.796
Z.5	0.610	0.610	0.825	0.705
Z.6	0.649	0.641	0.809	0.635

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 3 above, there is a discriminant validity value in each variable, there are indicators that have cross loading values in each and these values have a value that is greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, for example, the cross loading of the organizational culture variable has a value greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, for the leadership style variable it has a value that is greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, for the organizational climate variable it has a value greater than the cross loading value on other latent variables, the employee performance variable has a value greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, so it can be concluded that this study is discriminantly valid.

Composite reliability

The following test calculates the reliability value using the composite reliability of each build. The build value is considered reliable if the composite reliability value is greater than or equal to 0.6. If the Cronbach alpha value is greater than 0.7 then the value of each

construct in the block is considered reliable, and if the AVE value is greater than 0.7 then each variable construct is considered valid. The table below shows the loading values of the research variable constructs generated by the Smart PLS software.

Table 4. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Organizational Culture (X2)	0.890	0.919	0.695
Moderation Effect 1	1,000	1,000	1,000
Moderation Effect 2	1,000	1,000	1,000
Leadership Style (X1)	0.884	0.912	0.635
Work Climate (Z)	0.917	0.935	0.707
Employee Performance (Y)	0.935	0.947	0.689

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Based on table 4 above, there is a value from the Cronbach alpha column, each variable has a value greater than 0.7, which means that this study has Cronbach alpha reliability, and seen from the Composite Reliability column, the value of each variable has a value greater than 0.6 so that the reliability of each variable is stated, and in the AVE column it appears greater than 0.7 so that this study is considered valid with the SVE column in each variable and also the moderation effect.

Inner Model Analysis

The structural model (inner model) is evaluated to ensure that the model is robust and correct. Some indicators that can be used to assess the stages of structural model evaluation analysis include:

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Based on data processing carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 application, the R Square value was obtained as follows:

Table 5. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Employee Performance (Y)	0.807	0.792

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 5, there is an R square value for the employee performance variable of 0.807 or 80.7%, meaning that the influence of the leadership style and organizational culture variables on employee performance is 0.807 or 80.7% and the rest is in other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After assessing the inner model, the next step is to evaluate the relationship between latent constructs as hypothesized in this study. Hypothesis testing in this study was conducted by looking at the T-Statistics and P-Values. The hypothesis is accepted if the T-Statistics value is > 1.96 and P-Values < 0.05. The following are the results of the Path Coefficients of direct influence:

Table 6. Direct and Moderation Effects

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Organizational Culture (X2) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.446	3,594	0,000	Accepted
Moderation Effect 1 -> Employee Performance (Y)	-0.033	0.201	0.420	Rejected
Moderation Effect 2 -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.031	0.205	0.419	Rejected
Leadership Style (X1) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.115	1,138	0.128	Rejected
Work Climate (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.392	3,595	0,000	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In the hypothesis results in table 6, these results will be explained by the researcher, so the results of this study are as follows:

1. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.446 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if a good organizational culture increases, employee performance will increase, conversely, if it decreases, employee performance will decrease significantly.
2. Work climate cannot moderate leadership style on employee performance with an original sample value of -0.033 and p values of 0.420, meaning that work climate is not yet able to moderate because it does not have a significant effect and in this study it is stated that work climate is not a moderating variable.
3. Work Climate is not able to moderate Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.031 and p values of 0.419, meaning that work climate is not a moderating variable because it is not able to influence significantly and perhaps work climate can be placed in another variable model or work climate will become a moderating variable in other studies.
4. Leadership style has a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance with an original sample of 0.115 and p values of 0.128, meaning that in this study the leadership style used did not make employees feel better so that some employees had poor performance because there was pressure from the method or from the leadership style used.
5. Work climate has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.392 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if the work climate improves well, employee performance will improve, conversely, if it decreases, employee performance will decrease.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.446 and p values of 0.000.
2. Work Climate cannot moderate Leadership Style on Employee Performance with an original sample value of -0.033 and p values of 0.420.
3. Work Climate is unable to moderate Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.031 and p values of 0.419.

4. Leadership style has a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance with an original sample of 0.115 and p values of 0.128.
5. Work climate has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.392 and p values of 0.000.

Suggestion

1. The organization must provide a good and comfortable working climate for employees and the progress of the organization.
2. The organization adapts its leadership style to its employees, meaning it must first know the condition of its employees before determining what kind of leadership style is needed.
3. Organizations must create a positive organizational culture to create positive employee conditions.
4. Use this research as a suggestion for the organization to improve the organization's mistakes and weaknesses.
5. This research is expected to be used as reference material for new researchers using new research titles and new models.

REFERENCES

- Aziz, A., & Fauzah, Y. N. (2018). Pengaruh Kompensasi Finansial Dan Non Finansial Melalui Motivasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan PT. Reska Multi Usaha (Rmu) Cirebon. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen*, 1(2).
- Daryanto. 2015, *Pengelolaan Budaya Dan Iklim Sekolah*. Gava Media: Yogyakarta.
- Emron, dkk. 2018. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Bandung: CV Alfabeta
- Fahmi, Irham, dkk. 2014, *Manajemen Kepemimpinan Teori dan Aplikasi*. Bandung: Edisi Revisi, Alfabeta.
- Ghozali, I. Latan, H. 2015, *Partial Least Square : Konsep, Teknik dan Aplikasi Smart PLS 2.0 M3*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Nurjaya, N. 2021. Pengaruh Disiplin Kerja, Lingkungan Kerja dan Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada PT. Hazara Cipta Pesona. *Jurnal Ilmiah Nasional*, III(1), 60-74.
- Paramita, Lisa. 2017. Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Badan Penelitian dan Pengembangan Daerah Provinsi Kalimantan Timur, *jurnal Administrasi Negara*, Volume 5, Nomor 3, 2017. Hal : 6168-6182.
- Sedarmayanti. 2016. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Reformasi Birokrasi Dan Manajemen Pegawai Negeri Sipil*. Bandung: PT. Refika Aditama.
- Siswanto. 2015. *Pengantar Manajemen*: PT.Bumi Aksara, Jakarta
- Sugiyono. 2019. *Metodologi Penelitian Kuantitatif dan Kualitatif Dan R&D*. Bandung: ALFABETA.

Performance Determinants

Muhammad Imam¹, Mesra B²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: mesrab@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

This research aims to examine the influence of integrity, competency and motivation on job satisfaction mediated by work discipline at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province. Production factors are needed to produce human output, but without human labor, commodities and services will not provide the same benefits. The results of this research are as follows: Work Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.422 and ap value of 0.000. Integrity has a positive and significant effect on Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.358 and ap value of 0.000. Integrity has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.234 and ap value of 0.008. Competence has a positive and significant effect on Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.234 and ap value of 0.007. Competency has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.044 and ap value of 0.321. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.394 and ap value of 0.000. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.272 and ap value of 0.002. Integrity has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.155 and ap value of 0.003. Competence has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.103 and ap value of 0.013. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction through Work Discipline with an original sample value of 0.170 and ap value of 0.004.

Keywords: Integrity, Competence, Motivation, Job Satisfaction, Work Discipline.

INTRODUCTION

An important component of an organization's success is human resources (HR). Therefore, in order for a company to function well and achieve its goals, each employee needs to have the following qualities: knowledge, skills, and abilities; in addition, they need to have experience; motivation; discipline; and uphold their work. Therefore, human resource management is very much needed to improve employee performance, so that it is beneficial to the company and able to survive in a competitive and dynamic business climate. A person's work ethic is believed to influence their achievements at the individual, group, and institutional levels as well as the overall success of the country in achieving its goals. A worker's work ethic is a measure of how well they serve the community. In Indonesia, the phenomenon of work ethic is still uneven. Working is still seen as a routine activity. Work can also be seen as a difficulty and a form of coercion carried out by certain employees, especially those who are lazy. There is still a lack of understanding about work ethic among employees. In addition, because it does not encourage the development of a positive and effective work ethic, this is what is lacking. The business world almost never ignores worker welfare, including in terms of minimum wage payments. Everyone, as long as they are alive, always communicates because as social media users, we are creatures who need interaction with each other. Effective communication between individuals who convey messages and people who are encouraged to communicate is achieved through communication. This is certainly influenced by a person's communication skills. The production of meaning and the interpretation of meaning are two processes that occur during communication. Verbal and

nonverbal cues can be used to communicate. Nonverbal communication is characterized by the use of signs other than words or language, while verbal communication is the use of words as a means of communication. Rapid advances in technology have also made it increasingly important for people to work together and coordinate in order to complete projects and become more competitive in the face of global economic developments. Employee requirements and interests vary depending on teamwork. In general, teamwork and collaboration make employees happier. As a result, they may feel more involved, connected, and valued by the company. In addition, knowledgeable employees usually want to participate in the success of decisions made by their company. Employee job satisfaction is the sense of satisfaction they get from their work. Job satisfaction is a classic theory in human resource management. Literature on job satisfaction has emerged since the growth of the industrial era in the 1930s, but it is still needed today. Efforts to achieve job satisfaction are very important for both individuals and organizations. Employee performance in general is a manifestation of work carried out by employees which is usually used as a basis or reference for assessing employees in an organization. Good performance is a step towards achieving organizational goals, therefore, performance is also a determining factor in achieving organizational goals so that efforts need to be made to improve employee performance.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Work Ethic have a positive and significant influence on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
2. Does Communication Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
3. Does Teamwork have a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
4. Does Work Ethic have a positive and significant influence on the Performance of Employees at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
5. Does Communication Have a Positive and Significant Influence on the Performance of Employees at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
6. Does Teamwork Have a Positive and Significant Influence on the Performance of Employees at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
7. Does Job Satisfaction have a positive and significant effect on the Performance of Employees at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
8. Does Work Ethic have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
9. Does Communication Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
10. Does Teamwork have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Ethic on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

2. To determine and analyze the influence of communication on job satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
3. To determine and analyze the influence of Teamwork on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
4. To determine and analyze the influence of work ethic on employee performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
5. To determine and analyze the influence of communication on employee performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
6. To determine and analyze the influence of Teamwork on the Performance of Employees at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
7. To determine and analyze the influence of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
8. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Ethic on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
9. To determine and analyze the influence of Communication on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
10. To determine and analyze the influence of Teamwork on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee performance

Understanding Employee Performance

According to Supardi, (2014) Performance is what can be done by someone according to their duties and functions. According to Kasmir (2016) Performance is the result of work and work behavior that has been achieved in completing tasks and responsibilities given in a certain period".

Employee Performance Indicators

According to Kasmir (2016) employee performance indicators are:

1. Quality. Quality is a level at which the process or result of completing an activity approaches the point of perfection.
2. Quantity (amount). To measure performance can also be done by looking at the quantity (amount) produced by a person.
3. Time (time period) For certain types of work, a time limit is given to complete the work.
4. Cooperation between employees. Performance is often associated with cooperation between employees and between leaders. In this relationship, it is measured whether an employee is able to develop feelings of mutual respect, goodwill and cooperation between one employee and another.
5. Cost emphasis. The costs incurred for each company activity have been budgeted before the activity is carried out. This means that the costs that have been budgeted are used as a reference so as not to exceed what has been budgeted.
6. Supervision. By conducting supervision, employees will feel more responsible for their work and if there are deviations, it will be easier to make corrections and make improvements as soon as possible.

Work ethic

Understanding Work Ethic

Work ethic according to Salamun et al, (2017) is a manifestation of positive attitudes possessed by employees that are closely related to personality, behavior, and character including hard work, discipline, honesty, responsibility, and diligence in working with benefits that can maximize the work done. According to Darodjat, (2015) work ethic is a positive action and foundation that includes motivation which can influence someone, basic spirit, basic thinking, code of ethics, including morals and behavior and attitudes, aspirations, main characteristics and beliefs, principles and standards that are used as references.

Work Ethic Indicator

Work Ethic Indicators according to Darodjat (2015) are:

1. Have work motivation, namely motivation from within and from outside the individual.
2. Have a future orientation.
3. Morality is an attitude of seriousness in working.
4. Work hard and value time.
5. Discipline in work, responsible.
6. Economical and simple,
7. Be persistent and tenacious.

Communication

Definition of Communication

According to (Mangkunegara, 2017) communication is "the transfer of information and understanding from one person to another." According to Ganiem (2018) communication is basically a process that explains who, says what, with what channel, to whom, with what effect or result (who, says what, in which channel, to whom, with what effect).

Communication Indicators

According to Ganiem (2018), communication indicators are:

1. Understanding, meaning careful acceptance of the message conveyed by the sender of the message.
2. Pleasure, namely communication creates shared welfare, this is closely related to shared comfort.
3. Influencing attitudes, meaning the ability to persuade someone or influence their attitude.
4. Improving relationships, meaning effective communication will improve good relationships, for this a positive psychological atmosphere full of trust is needed.
5. Action, meaning that communication provides the desired result, namely that the person receiving the message is willing to carry out the intended action.

Teamwork

Understanding Teamwork

Teamwork is a group consisting of two to twenty wise individuals who have the same vision and then build an initiative to complete the tasks of its members (Siagian, 2020). Teamwork is an activity that is managed and carried out by a group of people who are members of one organization. Teamwork can improve cooperation and communication within and between parts of the company. (Letsoin & Ratnasari 2020).

Teamwork Indicators

Teamwork indicators according to Letsoin & Ratnasari (2020), namely:

1. Want to work together (Cooperative). As social beings who need other people, the sense of teamwork in employees is characterized by an attitude of wanting to work together with other employees.
2. Expressing positive expectations. Employees feel optimistic and always hope well for their team in realizing the company's vision and mission.
3. Appreciate input. Feel like a part of other employees so that every input from other employees will be appreciated.
4. Give encouragement. Not only self-interested but employees will pay attention to other employees. Such as giving encouragement when they feel that other employees lack motivation.
5. Building group spirit. Building group spirit is done with the aim that each individual in the team has the same enthusiasm.

Job satisfaction

Understanding Job Satisfaction

According to Wijono (2015) job satisfaction is an individual's estimation of work or positive and enjoyable experiences. Employee estimates of their work experience can be seen whether employees feel happy or unhappy with their work. According to Yuniarsih (2017), job satisfaction is a psychological reflection of employees on the results of their work. The level of individual satisfaction is basically based on the value system within themselves. Therefore, the measure of satisfaction will be different for each individual.

Job Satisfaction Indicators

According to Yuniarsih (2017), job satisfaction indicators are as follows:

- (1) Supervision,
- (2) Work environment,
- (3) Promotion,
- (4) Supportive co-workers,
- (5) Mentally challenging work,
- (6) Rewards in the form of wages/salary.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

- H1 Work Ethic has a positive and significant influence on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H2 Communication has a positive and significant influence on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H3 Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H4 Work Ethic has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H5 Communication has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H6 Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H7 Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H8 Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H9 Communication has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H10 Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

METHOD

Types of research

According to Siregar (2014): "Quantitative research means that in quantitative research data analysis activities include data processing and data presentation, carrying out calculations to describe data and carrying out hypothesis testing using statistical tests."

Location and Time of Research

The location of the research was conducted at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province on Jalan Balai Kota No. 4, Medan City. This research was conducted from September to October 2024.

Population

The population in this study was 70 employees. According to Arikunto (2014) Population is the entire subject of research. Based on the definition above, it can be said that population is an object or subject that is in a region and meets certain requirements related to the problem in the study.

Sample

The sample in this study is to take all the population as samples and the sampling technique is a saturated technique where researchers take all the population as samples. According to Umar (2014): "A sample is a small part of a population". Based on the definition above, it can be said that a sample is a small part of the number and characteristics of a population. With a population of 70 Bank Indonesia Representative Offices in North Sumatra Province, the sampling technique used in this study is to use a nonprobability sample with a saturated sampling technique.

METHOD

Research Data Sources

According to Arikunto (2014): "The source of data in research is the subject from which data can be obtained". Based on the definition above, the source of data used in this research is primary data, because the researcher collects the required data himself which comes directly from the research object,

Data collection technique

In this study, researchers collected data by distributing questionnaires, in other words, researchers used questionnaires as a data collection technique. According to Bahri (2018), a questionnaire is a data collection technique carried out by giving a set of written questions or statements to respondents to answer.

Data Analysis Techniques

In this study, the data will be analyzed with a quantitative approach using statistical analysis, namely SEM PLS (Structural Equation Modeling) aimed at conducting path analysis. This analysis is often referred to as the second generation of multivariate analysis. Structural equation analysis based on variance that can simultaneously test measurement models and test structural models. The purpose of using SEM PLS is to make predictions. The predictions made are predictions of the relationship between constructs and also to help researchers obtain latent variable values for prediction. Latent variables are linear aggregates of their indicators. Weight estimates to create latent variable score components are found based on the inner model (structural model that connects latent variables) and the measurement model, namely the relationship between indicators and their constructs (outer model).

Structural Model Analysis (inner model)

Inner model analysis is usually called (inner relation, structural model, and substantive theory) which describes the relationship between latent variables based on substantive theory.

- a) R-square
- b) F-square
- c) Hypothesis Testing

Measurement Model Analysis (outer model)

Outer model analysis is conducted to ensure that the measurement used is suitable for measurement (validity and reliability). In this model analysis, the relationship between latent variables and their indicators is specified.

- a) Construct Reliability and Validity (construct validity and reliability)
- b) Discriminant Validity (discriminant validity)
- c) Composite reliability
- d) Cronbach's Alpha

In testing the hypothesis can be seen from the t-statistic value and probability value. For hypothesis testing, namely using the statistical value for alpha 5%, the t-statistic value used is 1.96. So the criteria for accepting or rejecting the hypothesis are H_a accepted H_0

rejected when the t -statistic > 1.96 . To reject or accept the hypothesis using probability then H_a is accepted if the probability value < 0.05 .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Measurement model testing (outer model) is used to determine the specifications of the relationship between latent variables and their manifest variables, this testing includes convergent validity, discriminant validity and reliability.

Convergent Validity

This test is seen from the loading factor, the value limit is 0.7, and the value limit Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is 0.5, if it is above that value it is said to be valid. This means that the value for the indicator is said to be valid if the indicator explains the construct variable with a value > 0.7 .

Table 1. Cross Loading Stage 1

	Work Ethic (X1)	Job Satisfaction (Z)	Teamwork (X3)	Employee Performance (Y)	Communication (X2)
X1.1	0.783				
X1.2	0.781				
X1.3	0.633				
X1.4	0.847				
X1.5	0.793				
X1.6	0.835				
X1.7	0.785				
X1.8	0.852				
X2.1					0.787
X2.2					0.846
X2.3					0.880
X2.4					0.805
X2.5					0.716
X3.1			0.816		
X3.2			0.783		
X3.3			0.675		
X3.4			0.772		
X3.5			0.883		
Y.1				0.842	
Y.2				0.784	
Y.3				0.783	
Y.4				0.833	
Y.5				0.869	
Y.6				0.774	
Z.1		0.774			
Z.2		0.892			

Z.3		0.917			
Z.4		0.818			
Z.5		0.907			
Z.6		0.906			

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3

The results of table 1 above show cross loading per indicator that has a value greater than 0.70 on each variable, but there are two indicators that are less than 0.70 located in the Work Ethic variable in indicator X1.3 and the Teamwork variable in indicator X3.3 so that the research cannot be continued, to be able to conduct further research, invalid cross loading indicators must be deleted and recalculated. The results of the recalculation are as follows:

Table 2. Cross Loading Stage 2

	Work Ethic (X1)	Job Satisfaction (Z)	Teamwork (X3)	Employee Performance (Y)	Communication (X2)
X1.1	0.773				
X1.2	0.763				
X1.4	0.865				
X1.5	0.812				
X1.6	0.836				
X1.7	0.802				
X1.8	0.855				
X2.1					0.787
X2.2					0.846
X2.3					0.880
X2.4					0.805
X2.5					0.716
X3.1			0.833		
X3.2			0.822		
X3.4			0.727		
X3.5			0.868		
Y.1				0.842	
Y.2				0.784	
Y.3				0.783	
Y.4				0.833	
Y.5				0.869	
Y.6				0.774	
Z.1		0.773			
Z.2		0.893			
Z.3		0.917			
Z.4		0.817			
Z.5		0.907			

Z.6		0.906		
-----	--	-------	--	--

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

The results of the second stage of cross loading research above after the values of X1.3 and X3.3 were removed and recalculated, the cross loading results contained valid results for each construct variable. It can be concluded that the construct has met the convergent validity criteria.

Figure 2: Outer Model
Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Smart PLS output for loading factor gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Z = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + e_1$$

$$Z = 0.356X_1 + 0.138X_2 + 0.217X_3 + e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_3X_2 + b_4X_1 + b_5X_3 + b_6Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.138X_1 + 0.719X_2 + 0.020X_3 + 0.133Z + e_2$$

Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity is conducted to ensure that each concept of each latent model is different from other variables. The table below shows the results of the discriminant validity of the research model looking at the cross loading value.

Table 3. Discriminant Validity

	Work Ethic (X1)	Job Satisfaction (Z)	Teamwork (X3)	Employee Performance (Y)	Communication (X2)
X1.1	0.773	0.711	0.714	0.728	0.703
X1.2	0.763	0.741	0.762	0.676	0.655
X1.4	0.865	0.735	0.677	0.811	0.791
X1.5	0.812	0.629	0.634	0.795	0.775
X1.6	0.836	0.854	0.708	0.827	0.830
X1.7	0.802	0.748	0.735	0.779	0.790
X1.8	0.855	0.677	0.629	0.746	0.742
X2.1	0.774	0.587	0.643	0.783	0.787
X2.2	0.774	0.802	0.690	0.833	0.846
X2.3	0.819	0.823	0.671	0.869	0.880
X2.4	0.688	0.637	0.675	0.774	0.805
X2.5	0.696	0.744	0.723	0.704	0.716
X3.1	0.677	0.662	0.833	0.675	0.654
X3.2	0.866	0.809	0.822	0.863	0.877
X3.4	0.446	0.489	0.727	0.430	0.414
X3.5	0.686	0.709	0.868	0.706	0.680
Y.1	0.779	0.836	0.796	0.842	0.772
Y.2	0.769	0.787	0.702	0.784	0.701
Y.3	0.774	0.587	0.643	0.783	0.787
Y.4	0.774	0.802	0.690	0.833	0.846
Y.5	0.819	0.823	0.671	0.869	0.880
Y.6	0.688	0.637	0.675	0.774	0.805
Z.1	0.708	0.773	0.665	0.725	0.663
Z.2	0.777	0.893	0.679	0.786	0.778
Z.3	0.797	0.917	0.768	0.834	0.838
Z.4	0.765	0.817	0.703	0.795	0.737
Z.5	0.826	0.907	0.780	0.837	0.839
Z.6	0.800	0.906	0.789	0.804	0.807

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

From the cross loading results in table 3 above, it shows that the value of each indicator item is greater than the construct indicators of other latent variables. From this, it can be concluded that all constructs or latent variables have better discriminant validity than the indicators in other blocks.

Composite reliability

The next test determines the reliable value with the composite reliability of the indicator block that measures the construct. A construct value is said to be reliable if the composite reliability value is above 0.60. In addition to looking at the composite reliability value, the reliable value can be seen from the variable construct value with the cronbachs alpha of the indicator block that measures the construct. A construct is declared reliable if

the cronbachs alpha value is above 0.7. The following is a table of loading values for the research variable constructs resulting from running the Smart PLS program in the following table:

Table 4. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Work Ethic (X1)	0.916	0.933	0.666
Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.935	0.949	0.758
Teamwork (X3)	0.833	0.887	0.664
Employee Performance (Y)	0.899	0.922	0.664
Communication (X2)	0.866	0.904	0.654

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Based on the research above, it shows that the Cronbachs alpha value is greater than 0.7 so that it can be interpreted that all variables are considered reliable for each variable. With the assessment of composite reliability with each assessment there is a value greater than 0.6 which means that all variables have reliable values. Another method to test discriminant validity is to look at the AVE value and the square root of AVE, with the provision that each construct has a greater correlation than the correlation between other constructs. Before looking at the correlation, the AVE value is said to be valid if it is greater than 0.7.

Inner Model Analysis

Structural model evaluation (inner model) is conducted to ensure that the structural model built is robust and accurate. The stages of analysis carried out in the structural model evaluation are seen from several indicators, namely:

Coefficient of Determination (R2)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 5. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.844	0.837
Employee Performance (Y)	0.975	0.973

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 5, there is an R square value for the job satisfaction variable with a value of 0.844 or 84.4%, meaning that the influence of work ethic, communication and teamwork on job satisfaction is 0.844 or 84.4%, the rest is on other variables, the R square value for the employee performance variable is 0.975 or 97.5%, meaning that the influence of work ethic, communication, teamwork, job satisfaction on employee performance is 0.975 or 97.5%, the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

In PLS, testing of each relationship is done using simulation with the Bootstrapping method on the sample. This test aims to minimize the problem of abnormality of research data. The results of testing with the Bootstrapping method from the PLS analysis are as follows:

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Work Ethic (X1) -> Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.356	2,599	0.005	Accepted
Work Ethic (X1) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.138	1,595	0.056	Rejected
Job Satisfaction (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.133	2,763	0.003	Accepted
Teamwork (X3) -> Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.217	1,542	0.062	Rejected
Teamwork (X3) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.020	0.350	0.363	Rejected
Communication (X2) -> Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.382	3,420	0,000	Accepted
Communication (X2) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.719	10,934	0,000	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 6 above there are direct results which will be explained as follows:

1. Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.356 and p values of 0.005, meaning that if work ethic increases, job satisfaction increases, if it decreases, job satisfaction decreases.
2. Work ethic has a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.138 and p values of 0.056, meaning that work ethic has little effect on employee performance, sometimes increasing performance and sometimes decreasing performance.
3. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.133 and p values of 0.003. If job satisfaction increases, employee performance will increase, conversely, if it decreases, employee performance will decrease.
4. Teamwork has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.217 and p values of 0.062, meaning that the teamwork carried out is not good so that there are still many employees who are not satisfied with their work.
5. Teamwork has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.020 and p values of 0.363, meaning that teamwork has little effect on employees. Teamwork is good, but there are still many who do not want to work together.
6. Communication has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.382 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if good communication increases, job satisfaction will increase, conversely, if it decreases, job satisfaction will decrease.

7. Communication has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.719 and p values of 0.000. If good communication increases, employee performance increases, conversely, if it decreases, employee performance decreases.

Table 7. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Work Ethic (X1) -> Job Satisfaction (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.047	1,873	0.031	Accepted
Teamwork (X3) -> Job Satisfaction (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.029	1,299	0.097	Rejected
Communication (X2) -> Job Satisfaction (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.051	1,910	0.028	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In Table 7 above there are indirect influences and explanations as follows:

1. Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction with a value of 0.047 and p values of 0.031, meaning that job satisfaction is an intervening variable that can have a significant effect, with the presence of job satisfaction meaning and indirectly increasing employee work ethic and performance.
2. Teamwork Work Ethic has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction with a value of 0.029 and p values of 0.097. In this study, job satisfaction is not an intervening variable because it is unable to influence.
3. Communication has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.051 and p values of 0.028, meaning that job satisfaction is an intervening variable because it affects employee communication and performance. Job satisfaction increases communication.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.356 and p values of 0.005.
2. Work Ethic has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.138 and p values of 0.056.
3. Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.133 and p values of 0.003.
4. Teamwork has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.217 and p values of 0.062.
5. Teamwork has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.020 and p values of 0.363.
6. Communication has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.382 and a p value of 0.000, meaning.
7. Communication has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.719 and p values of 0.000.

8. Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction with a value of 0.047 and p values of 0.031.
9. Communication has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.051 and p values of 0.028.
10. Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction with a value of 0.047 and p values of 0.031.
11. Communication has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.051 and p values of 0.028.

Suggestion

1. Organizations must create good communication between employees.
2. Organizations must change their employee collaboration systems to be more collaborative in order to improve performance.
3. It is hoped that this research will be used as input to cover the weaknesses and deficiencies of the organization.
4. This research is expected to be used as reference material for new researchers with new research models.

REFERENCES

- Arikunto, Suharsimi. (2014). *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktik*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- A.A. Anwar Prabu Mangkunegara. 2017. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*
- Bahri, S., (2018), *Metode Penelitian Bisnis (Edisi ke-1)*, Yogyakarta, AND.
- Darodjat, Tubagus Achmad. 2015. *Konsep- Konsep Dasar Manajemen Personalialia*. Surabaya: Refika Aditama.
- Ganiem, L. M. (2018). *Teori Komunikasi AntarPribadi*. Kencana.
- Husein Umar. 2014. *Metode Penelitian Untuk Skripsi dan Tesis Bisnis*. Edisi-2. Cetakan ke-13. Jakarta : Rajawali Pers.
- Kasmir. 2016. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia (Teori dan Praktik)*. Depok: PT Rajagrafindo Persada
- Letsoin, V. R., & Ratnasari, S. L. (2020). *Issn : 2085-9996 Pengaruh Keterlibatan Karyawan , Loyalitas Kerja Dan Kerjasama Tim Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Influence Of Employee Involvement , Work Loyalty And Team Cooperation To Employee Performance Abstrak Pendahuluan Kinerja Adalah Hasil Kerja Seca*. 9(1), 17–34.
- Salamun dkk. 2017. *Persepsi tentang Etos Kerja: Kaitannya dengan Nilai Budaya Masyarakat Daerah Istimewa Yogyakarta*. Yogyakarta: Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan RI.
- Siagian, S. (2020). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta; Penerbit PT Bumi Aksara.
- Siregar, Syofian. (2014). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif Dilengkapi Dengan Perbandingan Perhitungan Manual dan SPSS*. Jakarta : Prenadamedia Group.
- Supardi. (2014). *Kinerja Karyawan*. Jakarta: Ghalia.
- Wijono, Sutarto, 2015. *Psikologi Industri dan Organisasi*, Jakarta: Kencana.
- Yuniarsih, Tjuju. 2017. *Kinerja Unggul Sumber Daya Manusia*. Bandung: Rizqi Press

Strategies to Improve Work Performance

Raja Pardomuan H. Siregar¹, Mesra B²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: mesrab@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

This research aims to complete the final assignment requirements for obtaining a master's degree, and another aim of this research is to provide input for organizations so that they can develop better. Every person is unique in their needs, desires, interests, values, beliefs, attitudes, mental processes, perception, and personality, among others (Umam, 2012). An organization or corporation is founded on the basis of a vision for the benefit of human interests, and humans are the ones who regulate the implementation of the mission of the organization or company. Human interaction begins with communication. Humans can interact with each other through communication in various environments, including markets, workplaces, homes, and public spaces. No one in this world would avoid participating in his talks. The results of this research are as follows: Work Ethics has a positive and significant effect on Competency with an original sample value of 0.652 p value 0.000. Work Ethics has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance with an original sample value of 0.429 and ap value of 0.002. Competency has a positive and significant effect on Job Performance with an original sample value of 0.419 and ap value of 0.000. Communication has a positive and significant effect on competence with an original sample value of 0.243 and ap value of 0.014. Communication has a positive and insignificant effect on Job Performance with an original sample value of 0.090 and ap value of 0.228. Work Ethics has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance through Competency indirectly with an original sample value of 0.273 and ap value of 0.001. Communication has a positive and significant effect on Job Performance through Competency with an original sample value of 0.102 and ap value of 0.044.

Keywords: Communication, Work Ethics, Competence, Work Achievement.

INTRODUCTION

Managing human resources to get employees who are happy with their work is the main goal of human resource management. This is due to the fact that each person is different from others and that each person is unique. Each person is unique in their needs, desires, interests, values, beliefs, attitudes, mental processes, perceptions, and personality, among others (Umam, 2014). Humans can interact with each other through communication in various environments, including the marketplace, workplace, home, and public spaces. An organization can function efficiently and productively with effective communication, and vice versa with poor or no organizational communication. All organizations need to communicate effectively. Therefore, it is very important for communicators and organizational leaders to understand and improve their communication skills. In order for communication to be effective, the communicator must know which audience is being targeted and what response he wants. He must be skilled in encoding messages by taking into account how the communicant interprets the message. A person's work ethic is their perspective on how they, as individuals, groups, or countries, approach their work. Work routines will not tire you out if your coworkers have a strong work ethic; in fact, they can even help you work better. Work ethic can be understood as the main foundation in acting regarding the right or wrong point of view. Ethic refers to a person's fundamental moral principles when doing their job. The capacity to carry out or complete a task that depends on the knowledge, abilities, and work attitudes required for the job is called competence.

Therefore, competence indicates knowledge or ability that demonstrates professionalism in a particular industry and, more importantly, what it takes to be a leader in that field. The ability to perform a task, role, or activity; the capacity to combine knowledge, skills, attitudes, and personal values; and the capacity to develop knowledge and skills based on experience and information learned are all considered competencies. Work performance is a very important factor in determining the progress of an organization, both private and government organizations. With this progress, the organization will be able to increase its competitiveness and have competitive capabilities. In improving employee work performance, of course, it is not easy, every organization must certainly do various ways so that each employee is able to improve their work performance. Private organizations generally have better work performance than government organizations. Private organizations tend to be better able to encourage their employees to be able to improve their work performance than employees in government organizations.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Communication have a positive and significant influence on Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
2. Does Work Ethic have a positive and significant influence on Competence at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
3. Does Communication Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Work Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
4. Does Work Ethic have a positive and significant influence on Work Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
5. Does Competence have a positive and significant influence on Work Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
6. Does Communication Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Work Performance through Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
7. Does Work Ethic have a positive and significant influence on Work Performance through Competence at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of Communication on Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
2. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Ethic on Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
3. To determine and analyze the influence of communication on work performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
4. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Ethic on Work Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
5. To determine and analyze the influence of Competence on Work Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
6. To determine and analyze the influence of Communication on Work Performance through Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
7. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Ethic on Work Performance through Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Work performance

Definition of Work Performance

According to Sutrisno (2016) Performance appraisal is a structured approach to regularly evaluate an employee's performance. According to Mangkunegara (2017) Company leaders conduct employee performance evaluations systematically by utilizing the tasks assigned to them.

Work Performance Indicators

Work performance indicators according to Sutrisno (2016):

1. How much work product is produced, how well it is manufactured, and how much is monitored.
2. Job knowledge The level of expertise in job-related tasks that will have a direct impact on both the quantity and quality of work.
3. Initiative Ability to take initiative when carrying out job responsibilities, especially when solving potential problems. Expertise in job-related tasks that will directly affect the quantity and quality of work produced.
4. Mental breakdown of the ability to understand work instructions and quickly adapt to current work practices and organizational structures.
5. Attitude, level of willingness and motivation to complete work-related tasks.
6. Time recording and attendance monitoring Employee attendance and punctuality levels.

Communication

Definition of Communication

According to Bandriyah (2015), communication is the process of transferring understanding in the form of ideas, information from one person to another. According to Mulyana (2015) Communication is the process of sharing meaning through verbal and non-verbal behavior carried out by two or more people.

Communication Indicators

According to Bandriyah (2015), communication indicators are as follows:

- 1) Understandable
- 2) Provide input
- 3) Quickly accepted
- 4) Coordination of tasks
- 5) Discussion meeting

Work Ethic

Understanding Work Ethic

According to Salamun (2017) Work Ethic is an ethic or guide in working, namely a guide to doing work well. Work ethic as stated by Ginting (2016) Work enthusiasm that is a characteristic and belief of a person or a group, then the definition of work ethic is "Work enthusiasm that is a characteristic of a person or group of people who work, which is based on ethics and work perspectives that are believed in, and is manifested through determination and concrete behavior in the world of work"

Work Ethic Indicator

According to Salamun (2017) the work ethic indicators are as follows: .

1. Hard work Hard work is that in working has the nature of workaholism to be able to achieve the desired target. Can utilize optimal time so that sometimes do not recognize time, distance and difficulties faced.
2. Discipline Discipline is an attitude of respect, appreciation, obedience and compliance with applicable regulations, both written and unwritten, and being able to carry them out and not avoiding receiving sanctions if he violates the duties and authority given to him.
3. Honesty Honesty is the ability of an employee to carry out his work in accordance with the rules that have been determined.
4. Responsibility Responsibility means assuming that the work being done is something that must be done with diligence and sincerity.
5. Diligent The creation of personal habits of employees to maintain and improve what has been achieved. Diligent at work. What is good must always be in prime condition at all times.

Competence

Understanding Competence

According to Rachmaniza (2020) competence is a characteristic that underlies a person related to the effectiveness of individual performance in their work or the basic characteristics of an individual that have a causal relationship or as a cause and effect with the criteria used as a reference, effective or performing excellently or superiorly in the workplace or in certain situations. According to Rahmat (2019) competence is a person's characteristic that is related to effective and/or superior performance in certain work situations.

Competency Indicators

According to Rahmat (2019), competency indicators are:

1. Motive is something that a person consistently thinks about or wants that causes action.
2. Traits are physical characteristics and consistent responses to situations or information.
3. Self-concept is a person's attitude, values, or self-image.
4. Knowledge is information that people have in a specific field.
5. Skills are the ability to perform certain physical or mental tasks.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

- H1 Communication has a positive and significant influence on Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H2 Work Ethic has a positive and significant influence on Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H3 Communication has a positive and significant influence on Work Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H4 Work Ethic has a positive and significant influence on Work Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H5 Competence has a positive and significant influence on Work Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H6 Communication has a positive and significant influence on Work Performance through Competence at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H7 Work Ethic has a positive and significant influence on Work Performance through Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

METHOD

Types of research

According to Sugiyono (2018), quantitative methods can be interpreted as research methods based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations or samples, data collection using research instruments, quantitative/statistical analysis, with the aim of describing and testing established hypotheses.

Time and Location of Research

The research was conducted from September to October 2024. The location of this research was at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province on Jalan Balai Kota No. 4, Medan City.

Research Population

The population of this study was all employees at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province, totaling 70 employees. According to Sugiyono (2018), population is the entire element that will be used as a generalization area. Population elements are all subjects to be measured, which are the units studied.

Research Sample

The researcher took samples in the study by taking all the population of the employees of the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province as many as 70 employees and the sampling technique used was the saturated sampling technique. According to Sugiyono (2018) a sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population.

Research Data Sources

This study uses primary research data sources, primary data sources are data sources where data is taken directly. According to Sugiyono (2018) Primary data is a data source that directly provides data to data collectors. Data is collected by the researcher directly from the first source or the place where the research object is carried out.

Data collection technique

The data collection technique used is a questionnaire technique in which the questionnaire will be distributed to research respondents. According to Sugiyono (2018), a questionnaire is a data collection technique carried out by giving a set of written questions or statements to respondents to answer. If there is difficulty in understanding the questionnaire, respondents can ask the researcher directly.

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) Analysis

In this study, the structural equation modeling (SEM) equation is a data processing method. SEM is a multivariate statistical technique that can be used to describe the complete causal relationship (comprehensive), complex, and system-shaped relationship between variables.

PLS (Partial Least Square)

Because PLS (Partial Least Square) analysis does not rely on various assumptions or requirements, including multicollinearity and normality tests, it is very effective. The benefits of the PLS approach include the ability to use indicators with categorical, ordinal, interval, or ratio data scales and eliminates the need for data that has a multivariate normal distribution. The sample size is another advantage; it does not need to be large.

Evaluation of Measurement Model (Outer Model)

Measurement model evaluation, also called external model, is the process of determining how construct variables, or indicators, relate to latent variables. Evaluation Reliability and validity tests are used to evaluate measurement models.

1. Indicator Reliability Test

By analyzing or checking each indication of the outer loading value, the indicator reliability test attempts to determine whether or not the indicators are reliable for measuring latent variables. The variance of an indicator can be explained by its construct as long as the outer loading value is greater than 0.7.

2. Internal Consistency Reliability Test

The purpose of this test is to see how well the indicators can measure the latent components. Internal assessment indicators Cronbach's Alpha regularity and combined reliability ratings form reliability. A combined reliability value between 0.6 and 0.7 is considered to have good reliability, and Cronbach's alpha is expected to be >0.7 .

3. Convergent Validity Test

The idea behind this validity test is that there should be a strong correlation between the measures of a construct. Average Variance Extracted is used to assess the convergent validity of a construct with the reflectivity marker (AVE). At least 0.5 should be the AVE value. 0.5 is the AVE value.

4. Discriminant Validity Test

Based on the idea that each indicator should be highly related to its construct, the purpose of this test is to ensure that an indicator truly reflects and is an accurate assessment of its construct. If the construct measures are not appropriate, then there will be no strong correlation between the two. The discriminant validity of the test in SmartPLS or similar

applications is determined by utilizing the Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) value, the Farnell-Larcker Criterion, and cross loading.

- a. The Cross Loading value of each construct is assessed to ensure its relationship with the measurement items is stronger than other constructs. The anticipated cross loading value is higher than 0.7.
- b. Fornell-Larcker Criterion: This conventional method, which has been used for more than 30 years, compares the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of each construct with the correlation between other constructs in the model. This is another way to evaluate discriminant validity. A model is considered to have good discriminant validity if the square root of the AVE of each construct is higher than the correlation between that construct and other constructs in the model.

Structural Model Evaluation (Inner Model)

Another name for structural or generic model evaluation is The purpose of the inner model is to assess (verify) whether there is collinearity between model constructs and predictive power. The following criteria are applied to assess the predictive power of the model:

1. Coefficient of Determination (R²)

The coefficient of determination (R²) is a way to assess how much the endogenous construct can be explained by the exogenous construct. The value of the coefficient of determination (R²) is expected to be between 0 and 1. The value of R² = 0.75 (strong model), R² = 0.50 (moderate model), R² = 0.25 (weak model). Meanwhile, according to Chin (1998) provides the criteria for the value of R² = 0.67 (strong model), R² = 0.33 (moderate model), and R² = 0.19 (weak model).

2. Path Coefficients or path coefficients

Path Coefficients, aim to see the significance and strength of the relationship, and also to test the hypothesis. The path coefficients value ranges from -1 to +1. The closer to the value of +1, the stronger the relationship between the two constructs. A relationship that is closer to -1 indicates that the relationship is negative.

3. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing (Resampling Bootstrapping), the bootstrapping procedure produces t-statistic values for each relationship path used to test the hypothesis.

- a. If the t-statistic value is smaller than the t-table value (t-statistic < t-table), then H₀ is rejected and H₁ is accepted.
- b. If the t-statistic value is greater than or equal to the t-table (t-statistic ≥ t-table), then H₀ is rejected and H₁ is accepted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

The details of the relationship between latent variables and manifest variables can be known by using measurement model testing, also known as external model testing. This test has reliability, discriminant validity, and convergent validity.

Convergent Validity

The loading factor shows this test, the limit value is 0.7, and the extracted limit value is Average Variance (AVE) is set at 0.5; values above this indicate validity. This shows that if the indicator value > 0.7 is able to explain the construct variable, then the indicator value is considered valid. The structural model of the study is depicted in the following figure:

Figure 2. Outer Model
Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

Smart PLS output for loading factor gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings
In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures.

For substructure 1

$$Z = b1X1 + b2X2 + e1$$

$$Z = 0.243 X1 + 0.652 X2 + e1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b4X1 + b5X2 + b7Z + e2$$

$$Y = 0.090 X1 + 0.429X2 + 0.419 Z + e2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Work Ethic (X2)	Competence (Z)	Communication (X1)	Work Performance (Y)
X1.1			0.800	
X1.2			0.844	
X1.3			0.763	
X1.4			0.763	
X1.5			0.853	
X2.1	0.830			
X2.2	0.838			
X2.3	0.769			
X2.4	0.775			
X2.5	0.848			
Y.1				0.906
Y.2				0.853
Y.3				0.797

Y.4				0.907
Y.5				0.861
Y.6				0.763
Z.1		0.855		
Z.2		0.888		
Z.3		0.860		
Z.4		0.898		
Z.5		0.815		

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

In table 1 above, the value of each variable is stated in such a way that the indicator of each variable is more than or equal to 0.7, this shows that each indicator bitir-bitir has a value of less than or equal to 0.7, meaning that the data is valid and can continue with further analysis.

Discriminant Validity

The next step of analysis is to determine which data is valid in terms of discriminant validity. The goal is to find out whether the cross loading value is greater than other variables so that the sensitivity of the indicator to high correction can be determined in relation to the construction of the table below, which presents the results of the validity assessment as follows:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Work Ethic (X2)	Competence (Z)	Communication (X1)	Work Performance (Y)
X1.1	0.662	0.617	0.800	0.640
X1.2	0.668	0.689	0.844	0.673
X1.3	0.674	0.617	0.763	0.628
X1.4	0.704	0.664	0.763	0.616
X1.5	0.804	0.680	0.853	0.680
X2.1	0.830	0.689	0.787	0.691
X2.2	0.838	0.853	0.806	0.780
X2.3	0.769	0.638	0.595	0.709
X2.4	0.775	0.682	0.633	0.605
X2.5	0.848	0.621	0.705	0.733
Y.1	0.808	0.781	0.698	0.906
Y.2	0.695	0.640	0.639	0.853
Y.3	0.666	0.734	0.529	0.797
Y.4	0.780	0.742	0.660	0.907
Y.5	0.710	0.801	0.722	0.861
Y.6	0.756	0.683	0.836	0.763
Z.1	0.740	0.855	0.644	0.661
Z.2	0.740	0.888	0.747	0.795
Z.3	0.716	0.860	0.733	0.746
Z.4	0.828	0.898	0.745	0.775

Z.5	0.702	0.815	0.629	0.742
-----	-------	-------	-------	-------

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

In table 2, there are cross loading values for the work ethic variable, where each cross loading factor is greater than the cross loading factor value on other latent variables, for the cross loading factor value on the competency variable is greater than the cross loading factor on other latent variables, for the cross loading factor value on the communication variable is greater than the cross loading factor value on other latent variables, for the cross loading factor on the work performance variable is greater than the cross loading factor value on other latent variables, so it can be concluded that this test is declared discriminantly valid.

Composite reliability

Each variable in the composite reliability study is compared for its reliability value; if the variable value is higher than 0.60 then the study is considered reliable; if between 0.60 and 0.7, then it is not. The table below shows the various blocks used to assess the validity and reliability of the study, including AVE values, composite reliability, and Cronbach's alpha values:

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Work Ethic (X2)	0.871	0.907	0.661
Competence (Z)	0.915	0.936	0.746
Communication (X1)	0.864	0.902	0.649
Work Performance (Y)	0.922	0.939	0.721

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

As seen in table 3, the value of each variable in the Cronbach alpha column is greater than 0.7 indicating the reliability of the variable's reliability data. Because the data is greater than 0.6, it can be explained that each variable is considered reliable in the Composite Reliability column which has a value greater than 0.6. Each variable in the AVE column has a value greater than 0.7, this indicates that the data is valid according to the AVE standard. Because all variables in the reliability, AVE, and Cronbach alpha columns have values greater than 0.7 and 0.6, respectively, all are considered valid and reliable.

Inner Model Analysis

To ensure that the fundamental model developed is reliable and accurate, the structural model, or deep model, is evaluated. A number of markers, including the following, indicate the stages of examination performed during the assessment of the main model:

Coefficient of Determination (R2)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Competence (Z)	0.760	0.753
Work Performance (Y)	0.807	0.798

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

In table 4 there is an R square test explanation will be done as follows: the R square value on the competency variable is 0.760 in a percentage of 76.0% which means the influence of communication and work ethic is 0.760 or 76% and the rest is on other variables. For the R square value of the work performance variable of 0.807 in a percentage of 80.7%, meaning the influence of communication, work ethic and competence is 0.807 or 80.7% and the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

The relationship between variables and data in this example must be ascertained after the model is built. T-Statistics and P-Values are checked to perform statistical analysis in this case study. To determine whether the P-Values < 0.05 and T-Insights > 1.96 are used speculation. The impact of the Road Impact Coefficient over time is as follows:

Table 5. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV I)	P Values	Results
Work Ethic (X2) -> Competence (Z)	0.652	5,871	0,000	Accepted
Work Ethic (X2) -> Work Performance (Y)	0.429	2,957	0.002	Accepted
Competence (Z) -> Work Performance (Y)	0.419	3,565	0,000	Accepted
Communication (X1) -> Competence (Z)	0.243	2,203	0.014	Accepted
Communication (X1) -> Work Performance (Y)	0.090	0.747	0.228	Rejected

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

In table 5 there are the results of the hypothesis test which will be explained by the researcher, so the explanation in this study is as follows:

1. Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on Competence with an original sample value of 0.652 p values 0.000. This means that if a good work ethic increases, competence will also increase, if there is a decrease in work ethic, competence will also decrease.
2. Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance with an original sample value of 0.429 and p values of 0.002. This means that if there is an increase in good work ethic, work performance will also increase, if there is a decrease, work performance will also decrease.
3. Competence has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance with an original sample value of 0.419 and p values of 0.000. This means that if competence increases, work performance also increases, conversely if competence decreases, work performance decreases.

4. Communication has a positive and significant effect on Competence with an original sample value of 0.243 and p values of 0.014. This means that if good communication increases, competence will also increase, conversely if it decreases, competence will decrease.
5. Communication has a positive and insignificant effect on Work Performance with an original sample value of 0.090 and p values of 0.228. This means that communication has little effect on performance because work performance can be done alone or in a team, but most employees achieve performance because of the advantages they have.

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Work Ethic (X2) -> Competence (Z) -> Work Performance (Y)	0.273	3,279	0.001	Accepted
Communication (X1) -> Competence (Z) -> Work Performance (Y)	0.102	1,711	0.044	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3.

In the results of this study, there is an indirect influence which can be seen in table 6, the explanation is as follows:

1. Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance through Competence indirectly with the original sample value of 0.273 and p values of 0.001. This means that competence is an intervening variable because it can significantly influence work ethic and work performance with commitment can improve work ethic and work performance.
2. Communication has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance through Competence with an original sample value of 0.102 and p values of 0.044. This means that competence is an intervening variable because it can influence communication on work performance significantly and indirectly, so with competence it makes an increase in good communication and increased work performance.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on Competence with an original sample value of 0.652 p values 0.000.
2. Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance with an original sample value of 0.429 and p values of 0.002.
3. Competence has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance with an original sample value of 0.419 and p values of 0.000.
4. Communication has a positive and significant effect on Competence with an original sample value of 0.243 and p values of 0.014.
5. Communication has a positive and insignificant effect on Work Performance with an original sample value of 0.090 and p values of 0.228.
6. Work Ethic has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance through Competence indirectly with an original sample value of 0.273 and p values of 0.001.
7. Communication has a positive and significant influence on Work Performance through Competence with an original sample value of 0.102 and p values of 0.044.

Suggestion

1. Organizations must improve employee work ethic by providing punishment and rewards to employees who do so.
2. The organization must provide examples to employees of the correct way to communicate with other employees and superiors.
3. The organization is responsible for employee competence and improving employee competence.
4. It is hoped that this research can be used as input for organizations and employees.
5. It is hoped that this research can help other researchers to use it as reference material for new research.
6. It is hoped that new research can develop this research with new research models and techniques.

REFERENCES

- A.A. Anwar Prabu Mangkunegara. 2017. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan*, Bandung : Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Badriyah, M. (2015). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*, Cetakan 1. Bandung : CV Pustaka Setia.
- Dessler, G. (2015). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- Ginting, Desmon. (2016). *Etos Kerja : Panduan Menjadi Karyawan Cerdas*. Jakarta: PT. Elex Media Komputindo.
- Mulyana, Deddy. 2015. *Ilmu Komunikasi suatu pengantar*. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Rahmat, S. N., & Basalamah, J. (2019). Pengaruh Kompetensi, Kompensasi Dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Badan Pendapatan Daerah Kota Makassar. *PARADOKS: Jurnal Ilmu Ekonomi*, 2(1), 121-132.
- Rachmaniza, Shafira. 2020. —Pengaruh Kompetensi Dan Komitmen Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada Divisi Produksi PT. Sinar Ragamindo Utama Bandung. *Jurnal Prosiding Manajemen, Universitas Islam Bandung* 6(1): 11–16. <http://karyailmiah.unisba.ac.id/>.
- Salamun dkk. 2017. *Persepsi tentang Etos Kerja: Kaitannya dengan Nilai Budaya Masyarakat Daerah Istimewa Yogyakarta*. Yogyakarta: Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan RI.
- Sutrisno, Edy. 2016. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Cetakan Kedelapan. Jakarta: Prenadamedia Group.
- Sugiyono. (2018). *Metode Penelitian Kombinasi (Mixed Methods)*. Bandung: CV Alfabeta.
- Umam, Khaerul. 2012. *Manajemen Organisasi*. Bandung: Pustaka Setia.

Efforts to Improve Performance

Rudi Herbet Sianturi¹, Mesra B²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: mesrab@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

A variety of resources, including people, money, machines, equipment, and information resources, are required to achieve organizational goals. Human resource management is very important for an organization. So in managing it, managing and using human resources will run according to what is expected, so that it can function productively to achieve organizational goals. This research was conducted to examine the influence of competency, integrity and organizational culture on employee performance in moderating job satisfaction at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province. The results of this research are as follows: Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with a value of 0.366 and a significant value of 0.000. Job Satisfaction is not able to moderate Competency on Employee Performance with a value of 0.038, significant 0.129. Job Satisfaction is able to moderate Integrity on Employee Performance with a value of -0.127, significant 0.013. Job Satisfaction is able to moderate Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with a value of 0.120 and a significant value of 0.023. Integrity has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with a value of 0.397 and a significant 0.000. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with a value of 0.278, significant 0.000. Competency has a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance with a value of 0.007, significant 0.377.

Keywords: Competence, Integrity, Organizational Culture, Job Satisfaction, Employee Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Success or failure is determined by the ability of human resources in carrying out their roles. Various resources, including humans, money, machines, equipment, and information resources, are needed to achieve organizational goals. Human resource management is very important for the organization, so in managing it, organizing and utilizing human resources will run as expected, so that they can function productively to achieve organizational goals. Competence can be used as a predictor of performance; This means that a person's performance can be determined by the competencies they have, determined by the standards or criteria applied for improvement. To support work capabilities and assess the quality of performance produced by employees, employee competence is very important. The more competent an employee is, the better their performance. Managerial competence, or employee competence, refers to a series of managerial skills needed to carry out organizational tasks. An employee's competence includes the application of concepts and techniques related to planning, organizing, controlling, and evaluating the performance of an organizational unit. Integrity is a quality or condition that shows something that is whole and has the ability and capacity to manage both authority and honesty. A person with integrity will almost certainly do everything in accordance with the moral and ethical principles that he upholds. This is because in working, they will work diligently in fulfilling their obligations to subordinates and will never neglect to uphold their colleagues. Every business or organization requires a strong organizational culture, which must always be developed and adjusted to changes in the internal environment of the organization. The organizational environment consists of human resources with different sizes and

characteristics. The rapid advancement of science and technology has a negative impact on society as a whole, especially on the workforce that is underutilized in the organization. As a result, workers have a higher threshold for productivity growth. Leaders require employees to always behave in this pattern, comply with organizational policies and regulations. For example, all employees must be able to understand and respect it, maintain discipline, and carry out their duties in accordance with the regulations set by their organization. Job satisfaction is an important condition that must be possessed by humans who work, where they are able to interact with their work environment and it is expected that they will work enthusiastically and earnestly, so that the situation will improve. As the main attitude that reflects several attitudes that are mutually binding from a current job. Performance in an organization is a benchmark to determine whether or not the organization is successful in achieving its goals. The performance of an organization is largely determined by the quality of the performance of the employees working in it. Employee performance can be said to be good if the employee can carry out the tasks assigned to him/her to completion, because in general performance is assessed from what the employee has done and how the work results have been achieved during work.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Competence have a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
2. Does Integrity have a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
3. Does Organizational Culture have a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
4. Does Job Satisfaction Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
5. Is Job Satisfaction Able to Moderate Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
6. Is Job Satisfaction Able to Moderate Integrity at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
7. Is Job Satisfaction Able to Moderate Organizational Culture at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of Competence on Employee Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
2. To determine and analyze the influence of Integrity on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
3. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
4. To determine the influence of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
5. To find out and analyze Job Satisfaction can moderate Competence on Employee Performance.
6. To find out and analyze Job Satisfaction can moderate Integrity towards Employee Performance.
7. To find out and analyze Job Satisfaction can moderate Organizational Culture on Employee Performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee Performance

Understanding Employee Performance

Performance according to (Chairunnisah et al., 2021) is an employee who carries out his/her functions according to the responsibilities given and is successful in terms of quality and quantity. According to Afandi (2018) Performance is the work results that can be achieved by a person or group of people in a company according to their respective authorities and responsibilities in an effort to achieve organizational goals illegally, not violating the law and not contrary to morals and ethics.

Employee Performance Indicators

According to Afandi (2018) employee performance indicators are as follows:

1. Quantity of work results All forms of units of measurement related to the amount of work results that can be expressed in numbers or other numerical equivalents.
2. Quality of work results All forms of units of measurement related to the quality or standard of work results that can be expressed in numerical measurements or other numerical equivalents.
3. Efficiency in carrying out tasks Various resources wisely and in a cost-effective manner.
4. Work discipline. Comply with applicable laws and regulations.
5. Initiative The ability to decide and do the right thing without having to be told, able to find out what should be done about something around you, trying to keep moving to do several things even though the situation feels increasingly difficult.
6. Accuracy The level of conformity of the work measurement results to whether the work has achieved its objectives or not.
7. Leadership The process of influencing or giving examples by leaders to their followers in an effort to achieve organizational goals.
8. Honesty One of the human traits that is quite difficult to apply.
9. Creativity A mental process that involves generating ideas or involving the generation of ideas.

Competence

Understanding Competence

According to Sugiyanto and Santoso (2018) competence can show certain knowledge, skills, and attitudes of a profession in certain expertise characteristics, which are the characteristics of a professional. According to Wibowo (2018) Competence is an ability to carry out or do a job or task that is based on skills and knowledge and supported by the work attitude required by the job.

Competency Indicators

According to Wibowo (2018), the competency indicators are:

1. Knowledge, Information possessed by a core employee in carrying out his duties and responsibilities according to his field, employee knowledge determines the success or failure of carrying out the tasks given by the company, employees who have good knowledge can increase the efficiency of the company.
2. Ability/Skills, is an effort to carry out tasks given by the company to employees which are carried out well and optimally.
3. Employee behavioral attitudes, attitudes are behavioral patterns of employees in carrying out their duties and responsibilities in accordance with company regulations.

Integrity

Understanding Integrity

Integrity is something related to a person's trust and honesty (Kibtiyah & Mardiah, 2016). Integrity is a person's mindset, attitude, and conscience that is manifested in speech, actions, and behavior: honest, consistent, committed, objective, brave and ready to accept risks, and disciplined and responsible (Abdullah, 2019).

Integrity Indicators

Integrity indicators (Abdullah, 2019), namely:

1. Honest behavior;
2. Consistent Attitude;
3. Commitment to the Organization's Vision and Mission;
4. Objective Towards Problems;
5. Dare to make decisions and be ready to accept risks;
6. Discipline and responsibility;
7. Track record;
8. Performance.

Organizational culture

Understanding Organizational Culture

According to Sulaksono (2015), organizational culture is a system of shared meaning held by members that distinguishes one organization from another.

According to Muhdar (2015), organizational culture is a strategy that can improve organizational performance and its implementation is adjusted to the conditions of the organization.

Organizational Culture Indicators

According to Muhdar (2015) the indicators of organizational culture are as follows:

1. Integrity.
2. Consistency.
3. Professional.
4. Responsibility.
5. Communication.

Job satisfaction

Understanding Job Satisfaction

According to Wexley & Yuki (2016), job satisfaction can be interpreted as a generalization of employee attitudes towards their work. According to Zainal et al. (2014), job satisfaction is an employee's assessment of how far their work as a whole satisfies their needs.

Job Satisfaction Indicators

According to Zainal et al (2014) job satisfaction indicators are as follows:

- 1) Job content, actual appearance of job tasks and control over the work.
- 2) Supervision
- 3) Organization and management
- 4) Opportunity to advance
- 5) Salary

6) Co-workers

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

- H1 Competence has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H2 Integrity has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H3 Organizational Culture has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H4 Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H5 Job Satisfaction can moderate Competence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H6 Job Satisfaction can moderate Integrity towards Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H7 Job Satisfaction can moderate Organizational Culture on Employee Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H8 Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.

METHOD

Research methods

Types of research

This study uses quantitative research type in research at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province. Quantitative is a research method that describes

and explains independent variables to analyze their influence on dependent variables (Sugiyono, 2018).

Location and Time of Research

The research location was conducted at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province on Jalan Balai Kota No. 4, Medan City. This research was conducted from September to October 2024.

Population

The population of this study was all employees at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province, totaling 70 employees. Population is a generalization area consisting of: objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn (Sugiyono, 2018)

Sample

The sample of this study was all the population at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province as many as 70 and the sampling technique used was the saturated sampling technique where this technique took all the population as samples. The sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population (Sugiyono, 2018)

Research Data Sources

The data source used by researchers is a primary data source. According to Sugiyono (2018) Primary data is a data source that directly provides data to data collectors. The data is collected by the researcher directly from the first source or the place where the research object is carried out.

Data collection technique

The data collection technique used is a questionnaire. According to Sugiyono (2018), a questionnaire is a data collection technique carried out by giving a set of written questions or statements to respondents to answer.

Data Analysis Techniques

PLS is an effective analysis technique because it relies on few assumptions. PLS can be used to explain current data or find out if there is a relationship between latent variables. It can also be used to confirm a theory. The data and sample size do not need to be large. Because there will be an unknown model in CBSEM, it is impossible to assess the resulting constructs with reflective and formative indicators. However, PLS can do it (Ghozali & Latan, 2015). Three categories apply to parameter estimates obtained using PLS. The first category is the estimation of weights to produce latent variable scores. The second category relates to the estimation of paths that establish relationships between latent variables and indicator blocks (loadings); the third category relates to location parameters and means (regression constant values) for latent and indicator variables. To obtain PLS, a three-step iterative procedure is used for these three estimates, with estimates generated at each stage. According to Ghizali and Latan (2015), the first stage produces estimates of weights, the second stage produces estimates of inner and outer models, and the third stage produces estimates of means and locations (constant).

Designing a Measurement Model (Outer Model)

According to Ghazali and Latan (2015), the outer model is also called the measurement model or external relationship defining the relationship between each indicator and the latent variable. To ensure that these measurements are suitable for use as measuring instruments (valid and reliable), an outer model analysis is used using several indicators, including the following:

- a. Convergent Validity, The calculation of the reflective indicator is based on the correlation between the item/component score and the construct score. The individual reflective index is expressed as a number if it is more than 0.70. However, for the first stage of the study, the sample size range is 0.50 to 0.60.
- b. Discriminant Validity, value determined by construct crossloading. A latent construct predicts measures in more blocks more accurately than measures in other blocks if the correlation between the construct and the measurement items is higher than the measures of the other constructs. Comparing the square of the root mean square of variance extracted (AVE) of each construct with its correlation to other constructs in the model is an additional technique. Compared with Composite Reliability (PC), the results of this measure are more careful in assessing the reliability component scores of the latent variables. A value > 0.50 for AVE is recommended.
- c. Composite Reliability & Cronbach Alpha Internal consistency and Cronbach Alpha are two types of measurements that can be used to assess a measure. It can be concluded that the data has a high reliability value, especially if the composite reliability is greater than 0.70. The predicted Cronbach Alpha value of each indicator of 0.70 strengthens the reliability test.

Designing Structural Model (Inner Model)

According to Ghazali and Latan (2015) the inner model is also called inner Relations is a model that uses substantive theory to describe the relationship between latent variables. Based on the research problem or hypothesis determined, a structural model of the relationship between latent variables is designed. There are several stages that can be used to estimate when evaluating this model. The use of R-square for dependent constructs, the Stone-Geisser Q-Square test for predictive relevance and the t-test and the importance of the structural path parameter coefficients. Each dependent latent variable is viewed using the R-square approach. The interpretation is identical to the regression interpretation. The presence or absence of other dependent influences, the influence of several dependent latent variables on other latent variables can be assessed using changes in the R-square value. The predictive relevance of Q-Square for the construct model is another matter. Q-Square evaluates the accuracy of the model parameter estimates and the observations it produces. If the Q-Square value of the model is less than zero, it means that the model has less predictive relevance, but if it is more than zero, the model has predictive relevance.

To evaluate the potential impact of independent variables on dependent variables, the t-test or partial regression coefficient test compares t-count and t-table. Furthermore, a comparison is made between each of the computational results with the resulting t-table with a significance threshold of 0.05. If the significance value of t is less than 0.05, the regression equation is considered relevant or significant. The following criteria are used to determine the basis for comparison:

The hypothesis is rejected if the t-count < 1.96 or the sig value > 0.05

The hypothesis is accepted if the t-count > 1.96 or the sig value < 0.05

Moderation Variable Analysis

Modified regression analysis (MRA), estimated using SEM-PLS, was used to evaluate the moderation hypothesis (Ghozali and Latan, 2015). The interaction coefficient between halal awareness and halal product purchase intention is the main focus of attention to test SPM as a moderating variable of the relationship between halal awareness in moderating halal product purchase intention and behavior. If the significant t value of a variable is less than 0.05, it can be considered a moderating variable and is considered important or significant. The following factors are the basis for comparison:

The hypothesis is rejected if the t-count < 1.96 or the sig value > 0.05

The hypothesis is accepted if the t-count > 1.96 or the sig value < 0.05

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Measurement model testing (outer model) is used to determine the specifications of the relationship between latent variables and their manifest variables, this testing includes convergent validity, discriminant validity and reliability.

1. Convergent Validity

Convergent validity of the measurement model with reflective indicators can be seen from the correlation between the item/indicator score and the construct score. Individual indicators are considered reliable if they have a correlation value above 0.70. However, in the scale development stage of research, loadings of 0.50 to 0.60 are still acceptable. Based on the results for outer loading, it shows that there are indicators that have loadings below 0.60 and are not significant. The structural model in this study is shown in the following Figure:

Table 1. Outer Model Stage 1

	Organizational Culture (X3)	Integrity (X2)	Job Satisfaction (Z)	Employee Performance (Y)	Competence (X1)
X1.1					0.842
X1.2					0.891
X1.3					0.912
X2.1		0.866			
X2.2		0.863			
X2.3		0.850			
X2.4		0.832			
X2.5		0.799			
X2.6		0.831			
X2.7		0.832			
X2.8		0.885			
X3.1	0.810				
X3.2	0.829				
X3.3	0.826				
X3.4	0.872				
X3.5	0.462				
Y.1				0.901	

Y.2				0.873	
Y.3				0.828	
Y.4				0.746	
Y.5				0.743	
Y.6				0.835	
Y.7				0.883	
Y.8				0.768	
Y.9				0.913	
Z.1			0.617		
Z.2			0.829		
Z.3			0.825		
Z.4			0.826		
Z.5			0.877		
Z.6			0.848		

Source: SmartPLS3.3.3.

In table 1 there are outer loading values in each variable but this research cannot be continued because there are still indicators that are not valid. The indicators that are not valid are aimed at Z.1 and X3.5. To continue the research, the invalid indicators must be deleted and recalculated, so the outer loading in the second stage is as follows:

Table 2. Outer Model Stage 2

	Organizational Culture (X3)	Integrity (X2)	Job Satisfaction (Z)	Employee Performance (Y)	Competence (X1)
X1.1					0.843
X1.2					0.890
X1.3					0.913
X2.1		0.866			
X2.2		0.863			
X2.3		0.850			
X2.4		0.832			
X2.5		0.799			
X2.6		0.831			
X2.7		0.832			
X2.8		0.885			
X3.1	0.819				
X3.2	0.828				
X3.3	0.819				
X3.4	0.887				
Y.1				0.901	
Y.2				0.872	
Y.3				0.829	

Y.4				0.747	
Y.5				0.742	
Y.6				0.835	
Y.7				0.883	
Y.8				0.767	
Y.9				0.913	
Z.2			0.805		
Z.3			0.839		
Z.4			0.840		
Z.5			0.878		
Z.6			0.868		

Source: SmartPLS3.3.3.

After the invalid indicators are removed, the results show that all variables that have outer loading indicators have a value greater than 0.7, so it is determined that the indicators in each variable have a value greater than 0.7 so that each indicator is declared valid and can continue the research to the next stage.

Figure 2. Outer Model

Smart PLS output for loading factor gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two equations.

$$Y = b_1X_1 + b_2Z + b_3X_1Z + e_1$$

$$Y = 0.007X_1 + 0.278 Z + 0.038X_1Z + e_1$$

$$Y = b_2X_2 + b_3Z + b_4X_2Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.397X_2 + 0.278Z - 0.127X_2Z + e_2$$

$$Y = b_3X_3 + b_4Z + b_5X_3Z + e_3$$

$$Y = 0.366X_3 + 0.278 Z + 0.120 X_3Z + e_3$$

Discriminant Validity

In this section, the results of the discriminant validity test will be described. The discriminant validity test uses the cross loading value. An indicator is declared to meet discriminant validity if the cross loading value of the indicator on its variable is the largest compared to other variables. The following are the cross loading values of each indicator:

Table 3. Discriminant Validity

	Organizational Culture (X3)	Integrity (X2)	Job Satisfaction (Z)	Employee Performance (Y)	Competence (X1)
X1.1	0.021	0.115	0.126	0.096	0.843
X1.2	0.062	0.158	0.097	0.126	0.890
X1.3	0.036	0.172	0.180	0.139	0.913
X2.1	0.728	0.866	0.709	0.811	0.051
X2.2	0.623	0.863	0.657	0.743	0.196
X2.3	0.710	0.850	0.827	0.850	0.112
X2.4	0.767	0.832	0.720	0.808	0.284
X2.5	0.726	0.799	0.639	0.753	0.054
X2.6	0.642	0.831	0.595	0.742	0.115
X2.7	0.665	0.832	0.783	0.835	0.115
X2.8	0.773	0.885	0.774	0.883	0.223
X3.1	0.819	0.710	0.616	0.767	0.245
X3.2	0.828	0.588	0.767	0.701	-0.073
X3.3	0.819	0.578	0.701	0.670	-0.056
X3.4	0.887	0.877	0.748	0.913	0.021
Y.1	0.810	0.823	0.836	0.901	0.081
Y.2	0.763	0.793	0.849	0.872	0.204
Y.3	0.834	0.710	0.853	0.829	0.036
Y.4	0.704	0.686	0.841	0.747	0.011
Y.5	0.642	0.831	0.595	0.742	0.115
Y.6	0.665	0.832	0.783	0.835	0.115
Y.7	0.773	0.885	0.774	0.883	0.223
Y.8	0.819	0.710	0.616	0.767	0.245
Y.9	0.887	0.877	0.748	0.913	0.021
Z.2	0.677	0.639	0.805	0.699	0.036
Z.3	0.680	0.628	0.839	0.689	0.097
Z.4	0.717	0.783	0.840	0.836	0.177
Z.5	0.761	0.808	0.878	0.880	0.283
Z.6	0.722	0.701	0.868	0.759	0.021

Source: SmartPLS3.3.3.

Composite reliability

The next test is the composite reliability of the indicator block that measures the construct. A construct is said to be reliable if the composite reliability value is above 0.60. Then it can also be seen by looking at the reliability of the construct or latent variable which is measured by looking at the cronbachs alpha value of the indicator block that measures the construct. A construct is declared reliable if the cronbachs alpha value is above 0.7. The following describes the results of the construct for each variable, namely Job Satisfaction, HR Quality, Work Loyalty with each variable and indicator. The following is a table of loading values for the research variable constructs produced by running the Smart PLS program in the following table:

Table 4. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Organizational Culture (X3)	0.860	0.905	0.704
Moderation Effect 1	1,000	1,000	1,000
Moderation Effect 2	1,000	1,000	1,000
Moderation Effect 3	1,000	1,000	1,000
Integrity (X2)	0.943	0.952	0.714
Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.901	0.927	0.716
Employee Performance (Y)	0.945	0.954	0.697
Competence (X1)	0.859	0.913	0.779

Source: SmartPLS3.3.3.

Based on table 4 above, it shows that the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of each variable, namely Work Quality and Work Loyalty and Job Satisfaction has a construct > 0.50, meaning all constructs are reliable. Thus, it can be stated that each variable has high discriminant validity.

Meanwhile, it can be seen in the table above that the composite reliability value of each variable shows a construct value of > 0.60. This result shows that each variable has met the composite reliability so that it can be concluded that all variables have a high level of reliability.

Furthermore, in the table above, the Cronbach's alpha of each variable shows a construct value of > 0.70. Thus, these results indicate that each research variable has met the requirements for the Cronbach's alpha value, so it can be concluded that all variables have a high level of reliability. So it can be concluded that the indicators used in this study have high discriminant validity in compiling their respective variables.

Inner Model Analysis

Structural model evaluation (inner model) is conducted to ensure that the structural model built is robust and accurate. The stages of analysis carried out in the structural model evaluation are seen from several indicators, namely:

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 5. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Employee Performance (Y)	0.978	0.975

Source: SmartPLS3.3.3.

In this study, there is an R square value in table 5 for the Employee Performance variable, there is an R square value of 0.978 or 97.8%, meaning that the influence of the Competence, Integrity and Organizational Culture variables on Employee Performance is 0.978 or 97.8%, the rest is in other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After assessing the inner model, the next step is to evaluate the relationship between latent constructs as hypothesized in this study. Hypothesis testing in this study was conducted by looking at the T-Statistics and P-Values. The hypothesis is accepted if the T-Statistics value is > 1.96 and P-Values < 0.05 . The following are the results of the Path Coefficients of direct influence:

Table 6. Direct and Moderation Effects

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Organizational Culture (X3) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.366	6,609	0,000	Accepted
Moderation Effect 1 -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.038	1,131	0.129	Rejected
Moderation Effect 2 -> Employee Performance (Y)	-0.127	2,238	0.013	Accepted
Moderation Effect 3 -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.120	1,863	0.032	Accepted
Integrity (X2) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.397	7,067	0,000	Accepted
Job Satisfaction (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.278	5,108	0,000	Accepted
Competence (X1) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.007	0.313	0.377	Rejected

Source: SmartPLS3.3.3.

In the hypothesis results in table 6, there are several that are not significant and will be explained as follows:

1. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with a value of 0.366 and a significance of 0.000. This means that increasing organizational culture will increase employee performance, but decreasing will also decrease employee performance.
2. Job satisfaction is not able to moderate competence on employee performance with a value of 0.038 significant 0.129 meaning that job satisfaction is not a moderating variable because it is not able to have a significant influence.
3. Job Satisfaction is able to moderate Integrity towards Employee Performance with a value of -0.127 significant 0.013 because it is able to have a significant influence but the results have a negative influence meaning that job satisfaction weakens employee integrity and performance, if employees are already satisfied with their work then employees will feel complacent and relaxed so that the level of integrity can decrease and performance can also decrease.
4. Job Satisfaction is able to moderate Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with a value of 0.120 and a significance of 0.023, meaning that job satisfaction strengthens a good organizational culture towards improving employee performance.
5. Integrity has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with a value of 0.397 and a significance of 0.000, meaning that if integrity increases, employee performance will also increase, conversely, if it decreases, employee performance will decrease.
6. Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with a value of 0.278 significant 0.000. This means that if job satisfaction increases, performance will increase, conversely if it decreases, employee performance will decrease.
7. Competence has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance with a significant value of 0.007 0.377, competence has little effect on employee performance because only some employees have competence in the organization.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with a value of 0.366 and a significance of 0.000.
2. Job Satisfaction is unable to moderate Competence on Employee Performance with a value of 0.038 significant 0.129.
3. Job Satisfaction is able to moderate Integrity towards Employee Performance with a value of -0.127 significant 0.013.
4. Job Satisfaction is able to moderate Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with a value of 0.120 and a significance of 0.023.
5. Integrity has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with a value of 0.397 and a significance of 0.000.
6. Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with a value of 0.278 significant 0.000.
7. Competence has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance with a value of 0.007 significant 0.377.

Suggestion

1. Organizations must have a good organizational culture to change bad employee habits and also improve employee performance.

2. Organizations must improve employee integrity gradually.
3. The organization must make employees feel satisfied working in the organization.
4. This research should be used as input for the organization for organizational development.
5. This research is expected to be used as reference material to develop this research and create new research models.

REFERENCES

- Abdullah, A. Rosid. (2019) *Capailah Prestasimu*. Guepedia Publisher. Bogor.
- Afandi. (2018). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia (Teori, Konsep dan Indikator)*. Nusa Media. Yogyakarta.
- Az-Zahra, Ratu Syiddah Ayu..et, all.(2021). “Pengaruh Pengendalian Interna dan Integritas Karyawan terhadap Pencegahan Fraud”. *Abdi Jurnal* , Vol.2, No.2
- Aziz, Abdul. (2016). *Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional, Budaya Organisasi Dan Motivasi Terhadap Komitmen Organisional Pada PT Kusuma Sandang Mekarjaya* Yogyakarta. Skripsi Univeritas Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta.
- Chairunnisah, R., KM, S., & Mataram, P. M. F. H. (2021). *Teori sumber daya manusia*. In *Kinerja Karyawan*. http://digilib.uinsgd.ac.id/40781/1/KINERJA_KARYAWAN_2_CETAK.pdf#page=38
- Diana. (2018). *Pengaruh Kompetensi Diri Dan Self confidence Terhadap Perencanaan karir*. *Jurnal Psikoborneo*. Vol. 6, No. 2.
- Ghozali, I. Latan, H. (2015). *Partial Least Square : Konsep, Teknik dan Aplikasi Smart PLS 2.0 M3*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Hari Sulaksono. (2015). *Budaya Organisasi Dan Kinerja*. Yogyakarta: CV Budi Utama.
- Kibtiyah, A., & Mardiah. (2016). *Hubungan Integritas Dan Loyalitas Karyawan Dengan Visi Misi Perusahaan (Studi Kasus Pada PT. Bank Central Asia, Tbk)*.
- Muhdar. (2015). *Organizational Citizenship Behavior dan Budaya Organisasi Perusahaan*. Sultan Amai Press.
- Sugiyanto. Santoso, Djoko. (2018). *Analisis Pengaruh Kompetensi, Sarana Pendukung Teknologi Informasi dan Kepuasan Kerja Sebagai Variabel Intervening Terhadap Kinerja SDM*. *Jurnal Manajemen Universitas Semarang*. ISSN: 1979-4800 (cetak) 2580-8451 (online).
- Sugiyono. (2018). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*, penerbit Alfabeta, Bandung
- Wexley dan Yuki. (2016). *Perilaku Organisasi dan Psikologi Personal*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Wibowo. (2018). *Manajemen Kinerja*. Jakarta: Rajawali Pres.
- Zainal, Veithzal Rivai, dkk. (2014). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Untuk Perusahaan Dari Teori Ke Praktik*. Depok. PT Rajagrafindo Persada.

Maximizing the Work Environment

Andy Saddam Ikhsan¹, Mesra B²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: mesrab@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

Human (HR) is a part of organizational management that focuses on the human resource element. The task of human resource management is to manage the human element well in order to obtain a workforce that is satisfied with their work. In organizations, humans are one of the most important elements in an organization. This research aims to examine the influence of leadership style and role conflict on the work environment with communication as an intervening variable at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province. The results of this research are as follows: Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on communication with an original sample value of 0.219 and an ap value of 0.017. Leadership Style has a positive and significant effect on the Work Environment with an original sample value of 0.362 and ap value of 0.008. Communication has a positive and insignificant effect on the work environment with an original sample value of 0.224 and ap value of 0.065. Role Conflict has a positive and significant effect on the Work Environment with an original sample value of 0.680 and ap value of 0.000. Role Conflict has a positive and insignificant effect on the Work Environment with an original sample value of 0.273 and ap value of 0.053. Leadership Style has a positive and insignificant effect on the Work Environment through Communication with an original sample value of 0.049 and ap value of 0.124. Leadership Role Conflict has a positive and insignificant effect on the Work Environment through Communication with an original sample value of 0.049 and ap value of 0.124.

Keywords: Leadership Style, Role Conflict, Communication, Work Environment.

INTRODUCTION

Human resource management is the process of managing people in an organization to optimize their contribution to achieving organizational goals. Effective human resource management is the key to the success of an organization in achieving its goals, because qualified and motivated employees can be a valuable asset in creating competitive advantage. The task of human resource management is to manage the human element well in order to obtain a workforce that is satisfied with its work. In an organization, humans are one of the most important elements in an organization. The role of the HR department to improve employee abilities and skills can be done by providing training programs for the employees themselves. Training is a process of self-development for employees so that they can work more skillfully and improve employee knowledge and skills. Leadership is the art of influencing human behavior, the ability to guide people. The success of an organization depends on the various resources it has, one of the most important resources is human resources (HR) including bank employees. Leadership style, basically contains the meaning as a manifestation of the behavior of a leader, which concerns his ability to lead. A leader has a strategic role, namely as a manager, must have competence in accordance with the demands of development and excellent service in the present and future in order to better understand the main tasks and functions as a leader. Role conflict is a situation in which a person has conflicting demands or expectations from the roles he or she plays in life. This can occur when an individual has many different roles, such as an employee, spouse, parent, friend, and so on. When the demands of these roles conflict, the individual can experience internal or external conflict that affects their well-being and performance. Role conflict can

have negative impacts, including stress, burnout, dissatisfaction, and decreased performance. The work environment refers to the physical, social, and psychological conditions in which a person works. A good work environment can contribute to employee well-being, productivity, and job satisfaction. It is important for organizations to address all of these aspects of the work environment to create a healthy, productive, and sustainable workplace. By prioritizing employee well-being and creating a supportive culture, organizations can ensure that their work environment supports the achievement of their business goals while taking care of their employees. The work environment is the sum of the tools and materials encountered, the surroundings in which a person works, the methods of work, and the organization of work both as individuals and as a group. Workplace communication is the process of exchanging information, ideas, and instructions between individuals or groups in the work environment. It is a key element in maintaining effective collaboration, productivity, and the achievement of shared goals within an organization. Workplace communication can take many forms, including verbal, written, and non-verbal communication. The ongoing communication in the organization must of course be easy to understand and delivered completely and on target by superiors and subordinates. Effective communication will be able to create a harmonious atmosphere.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Leadership Style Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Communication at Bank Indonesia Representative Offices? North Sumatra Province?
2. Does Role Conflict have a positive and significant effect on Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
3. Does Leadership Style Have a Positive and Significant Influence on the Work Environment at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
4. Does Role Conflict have a positive and significant effect on the Work Environment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
5. Does Communication Have a Positive and Significant Influence on the Work Environment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
6. Does Leadership Style Have a Positive and Significant Influence on the Work Environment through Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
7. Does Role Conflict Have a Positive and Significant Influence on the Work Environment through Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of Leadership Style on Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
2. To determine and analyze the influence of Role Conflict on Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
3. To determine and analyze the influence of Leadership Style on the Work Environment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
4. To determine and analyze the influence of Role Conflict on the Work Environment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
5. To determine and analyze the influence of Communication on the Work Environment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

6. To determine and analyze the influence of Leadership Style on the Work Environment through Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
7. To determine and analyze the influence of Role Conflict on the Work Environment through Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Work environment

Understanding the Work Environment

According to Afandi (2016) the work environment is something that exists in the environment of workers that can affect them in carrying out tasks such as temperature, humidity, ventilation, lighting, noise, cleanliness of the workplace and the adequacy of work equipment. According to Sedarmayanti, (2017) The work environment is all the tools and materials faced, the surrounding environment where a person works, his work methods, and his work arrangements both as individuals and as a group.

Work Environment Indicators

According to Sedarmayanti (2017) the work environment indicators are as follows:

- a. Work Atmosphere Work atmosphere is the condition that exists around employees who are doing work that can affect the implementation of the work itself, this work atmosphere will include the workplace, facilities and work aids.
- b. Relationship with Co-workers Co-worker relationships between employees need to be fostered, so that employees can work together and help each other in achieving company goals. Working relationships are not only formal, but also equally important are informal inner relationships.
- c. Relationship between Subordinates and Leaders A quality leader is a factor that has an important influence on the power and effectiveness of a leader. If a leader has a good relationship with his employees, or employees respect the leader for reasons of personality, character, or ability, then the leader in question does not need to rely on his rank or formal authority.
- d. Availability of Facilities for Employees Facilities are conveniences provided to certain employees only because of their achievements so that these employees continue to have the desire to work for a company and do not want to move to another company.

Leadership Style

Understanding Leadership Styles

Leadership style according to Hasibuan (2016), is a method used by a leader to influence the behavior of subordinates with the aim of increasing work enthusiasm, job satisfaction and employee productivity to achieve organizational goals. According to Edison (2016) leadership style is the way a leader acts and/or how he influences his members to achieve certain goals.

Leadership Style Indicators

Leadership style indicators according to Edison (2016) are as follows:

1. Have a clear and well-communicated strategy. Leaders have a clear and realistic strategy and members trust the leader to make changes for the better.

2. Concern for members and the environment. Pay attention to and motivate members' work and pay attention to the working environment and comfort.
3. Stimulate members Stimulate members to equip themselves with knowledge and skills in an effort to improve their competence.
4. Maintain team cohesion Invite members to work in a solid and harmonious team.
5. Respect differences and beliefs Respect every difference of opinion for a better purpose

Role Conflict

Understanding Role Conflict

Role conflict arises when someone gets a role that makes it difficult for him/her to adjust to other roles (Robbins and Judge, 2015). According to Hanna and Firnanti (2015), role conflict is a form of individual discomfort in an organization in carrying out his/her work which begins with the emergence of two orders received simultaneously which results in decreasing work motivation.

Role Conflict Indicators

According to Hanna and Firnanti (2015), the indicators of role conflict are as follows:

1. Different Jobs Working with two or more groups by doing their jobs in different ways
2. Human Resources Accepting assignments without being supported by sufficient human resources to carry them out
3. Putting the rules aside Putting the rules aside in order to complete the task
4. Unnecessary Activities Carrying out activities that do not actually need to be done as usual
5. Role Conflict Receiving multiple requests to do conflicting jobs
6. Work that is unacceptable to others Doing work that is unacceptable to others or someone.

Communication

Definition of Communication

According to Sutrisno (2017), Communication is a concept that has many meanings. The meaning of communication can be divided into: Social Communication Process this meaning is in the context of social sciences. Where social scientists use this method for research usually focuses on human activities and communication is related to messages and behavior. According to Sutardji (2016) "communication is the process of conveying information or the meaning it contains so that it can be understood, accepted and acted upon by the recipient".

Communication Indicators

According to Sutardji (2016), communication indicators are as follows:

- a. Understanding The ability to understand the message carefully as intended by the communicator. The purpose of communication is to achieve mutual understanding, and to achieve that goal, a communicator and the recipient must understand each other's functions. The communicator can convey a message while the recipient can receive the message conveyed by the communicator.
- b. Pleasure If the communication process is not only successful in delivering information, but also in a pleasant atmosphere between both parties. A more relaxed and pleasant atmosphere will be more enjoyable in interacting compared to a tense atmosphere. Because communication is flexible. with such an atmosphere, an interesting impression will emerge.

- c. Influence on attitude The purpose of communication is to influence attitudes. If communicating with other people then there is a change in their behavior in this case it can be said that the communication that occurs is effective, and if there is no change in a person's attitude, then the communication that is carried out is not effective.
- d. Better relationships That in the process of effective communication inadvertently increases the level of interpersonal relationships. Often, if people have the same perception, similar character, compatible, the relationship will automatically be well established.
- e. Communication actions will be effective if both parties after communicating there is a change in action towards the communicant or communicator.
- f. Availability of Facilities for Employees Facilities are conveniences provided to certain employees only because of their achievements so that these employees continue to have the desire to work for a company and do not want to move to another company.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

- H1 Leadership style has a positive and significant influence on communication at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H2 Role Conflict has a positive and significant effect on Communication at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H3 Leadership Style has a positive and significant influence on the Work Environment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H4 Role Conflict has a positive and significant effect on the Work Environment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H5 Communication has a positive and significant influence on the Work Environment at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H6 Leadership Style has a positive and significant influence on the Work Environment through Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H7 Role Conflict has a Positive and Significant Influence on the Work Environment through Communication at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

METHOD

Types of research

According to Sugiyono (2018), quantitative data is a research method based on positivity (concrete data), research data in the form of numbers that will be measured using statistics as a calculation test tool, related to the problem being researched to produce a conclusion.

Location and Time

The location of this research was conducted at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office on Jalan Balai Kota No. 4 Medan. This research was conducted from September to October 2024.

Population

The population used in this study was 70 employees of the Bank Indonesia Representative Office. According to Sugiyono (2018) Population is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to study and then draw conclusions.

Sample

The sample used in this study was all the population of employees of the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, namely 70 employees using the saturated sample technique. Sample According to Sugiyono (2018) a sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population. While the sample size is a step to determine the size of the sample taken in conducting a study. According to Sugiyono (2018), saturated sampling is a sampling technique when all members of the population are used as samples.

Data source

The research data sources used are primary data sources. According to Sugiyono (2018) Primary data is a data source that directly provides data to data collectors. Data is collected by researchers themselves directly from the first source or the place where the research object is carried out.

Data collection

According to Sugiyono (2018), a questionnaire is a data collection technique carried out by giving a set of written questions or statements to respondents to answer.

Data Analysis Techniques

This study uses smart PLS version 3.3.3 PLS is a technique used to predict models with many factors. The purpose of using SMART PLS is to predict the relationship between constructs, confirm theories, and the relationship between latent variables. SMART PLS is divided into 2 models, namely, Outer Model and Inner model. The Outer Model consists of reliability tests and validity tests, while the inner model consists of determination coefficients and hypothesis tests.

Outer Model Analysis

According to Ghozali & Latan (2015), the evaluation of the outer model is carried out to ensure that the variables used are suitable for measurement (valid and reliable). The outer model with reflective indicators is evaluated through convergent validity and discriminant

of the latent construct forming indicators and composite reliability and cronbach's alpha for the indicator block. While the outer model with formative indicators is evaluated through its substantive content, namely by comparing the magnitude of the relative weight and seeing the significance of the construct indicators.

1. Convergent Validity.
2. Discriminant Validity.
3. Composite Reliability (Reliability Test).

Inner Model Analysis

Inner model analysis is done to ensure that the structural model built is strong and accurate. In evaluating the inner model, it can be seen from several indicators, namely:

1. R-Square (R^2) R-squares for each endogenous latent variable as the predictive power of the structural model. Changes in the R-squares value can be used to explain the influence of certain exogenous latent variables on endogenous latent variables that have a substantive influence. Rsquare values of 0.75, 0.50 and 0.25 can be concluded that the model is strong, moderate and weak (Ghozali and Latan, 2015). The higher the R^2 value means the better the predictive model of the proposed research model.
2. Predictive Relevance (Q^2) In addition to looking at the magnitude of the R-squares value, in evaluating the PLS model, it can also be done with Q^2 predictive relevance or predictive sample reuse to represent the synthesis of cross-validation and fitting functions by predicting from observed variables and estimates of construct parameters. A Q^2 value > 0 indicates that the model has predictive relevance, while $Q^2 < 0$ indicates that the model lacks predictive relevance (Ghozali and Latan, 2015). Q^2 measures how well the observation values are generated by the model and also its parameter estimates.
3. Quality Indexes PLS path modeling can also identify global optimization criteria to determine the goodness of fit model used to evaluate the simple measurement model as a whole and also to provide a simple measurement for the whole of the model prediction. According to Ghozali and Latan (2015), the GoF value criteria are 0.10 (GoF small), 0.25 (GoF medium), and 0.36 (GoF large).

Hypothesis Testing

For hypothesis testing is done by looking at the probability value. For the probability value, the p-value with alpha 5% is < 0.05 . If the p-value < 0.05 then the hypothesis is accepted, while if the p-value > 0.05 then the hypothesis is not accepted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Measurement model testing (outer model) is used to determine the specifications of the relationship between latent variables and their manifest variables, this testing includes convergent validity, discriminant validity and reliability.

Convergent Validity

Convergent validity of the measurement model with reflective indicators can be seen from the correlation between the item/indicator score and the construct score. Individual indicators are considered reliable if they have a correlation value above 0.70. However, in the scale development stage of research, loadings of 0.50 to 0.60 are still acceptable. Based on the results for outer loading, it shows that there are indicators that have loadings below

0.60 and are not significant. The structural model in this study is shown in the following Figure:

Figure 2. Outer Model
 Source: SmartPLS 3.3.3

Smart PLS output for loading factor gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Z = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e_1$$

$$Z = 0.219X_1 + 0.680X_2 + e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_3X_1 + b_4X_2 + b_5Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.362X_1 + 0.273X_2 + 0.224Z + e_2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Leadership Style (X1)	Communication (Z)	Role Conflict (X2)	Work Environment (Y)
X1.1	0.800			
X1.2	0.843			
X1.3	0.761			
X1.4	0.762			
X1.5	0.856			
X2.1			0.831	
X2.2			0.847	
X2.3			0.774	
X2.4			0.747	
X2.5			0.831	

X2.6			0.911	
Y.1				0.876
Y.2				0.897
Y.3				0.795
Y.4				0.849
Z.1		0.875		
Z.2		0.889		
Z.3		0.872		
Z.4		0.909		

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 1 above, the value of each variable is stated that the indicator in each variable is higher than 0.7, which means that each indicator item has a value higher than 0.7 so that the data is declared valid and can continue to further research.

Discriminant Validity

Further research to find out valid data in terms of Discriminate Validity, aims to find out whether the cross loading value is greater than other latent variables so as to determine the results of indicators that are highly correlated with their constructs. The following table shows the cross loading results from the validity test as follows.

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Leadership Style (X1)	Communication (Z)	Role Conflict (X2)	Work Environment (Y)
X1.1	0.800	0.622	0.661	0.608
X1.2	0.843	0.675	0.667	0.658
X1.3	0.761	0.629	0.684	0.585
X1.4	0.762	0.652	0.694	0.577
X1.5	0.856	0.682	0.792	0.709
X2.1	0.788	0.701	0.831	0.650
X2.2	0.807	0.835	0.847	0.790
X2.3	0.595	0.638	0.774	0.592
X2.4	0.632	0.663	0.747	0.497
X2.5	0.706	0.609	0.831	0.653
X2.6	0.747	0.821	0.911	0.652
Y.1	0.650	0.708	0.649	0.876
Y.2	0.643	0.662	0.660	0.897
Y.3	0.631	0.573	0.649	0.795
Y.4	0.740	0.635	0.715	0.849
Z.1	0.644	0.875	0.751	0.620
Z.2	0.746	0.889	0.754	0.660
Z.3	0.733	0.872	0.720	0.668
Z.4	0.745	0.909	0.852	0.724

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Based on table 2, there is a cross loading value on each variable and indicators that will be explained for the cross loading value of the leadership style variable is greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, the cross loading value of the communication variable is greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, the cross loading value of the role conflict variable is greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, the cross loading value of the work environment variable is greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, so this study is discriminantly valid.

Composite reliability

In composite reliability research to see each variable with its reliability value and if the variable value is greater than 0.60 then the research is considered reliable and if below 0.60 and 0.7 then it is not reliable there are several blocks to determine whether the research is reliable or not and valid or not including the Coranbach alpha value, composite reliability and AVE value can be seen in the table below:

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Leadership Style (X1)	0.864	0.902	0.649
Communication (Z)	0.909	0.936	0.786
Role Conflict (X2)	0.905	0.927	0.681
Work Environment (Y)	0.876	0.916	0.731

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 3, it can be seen in the cronbach alpha column that each variable has a value greater than 0.7, which means that the reliability data for each variable. The composite reliability column has a value greater than 0.6, so it can be explained that each variable is considered reliable because the data is greater than 0.6. It can be seen from the AVE column that each variable gets a value greater than 0.7, which means that the data is valid according to AVE. All variables from the cronbach alpha column, reliability column and AVE column have values greater than 0.7 and 0.6, so they are considered reliable and valid.

Inner Model Analysis

Structural model evaluation (inner model) is conducted to ensure that the basic model created is strong and accurate. The stages of examination conducted in the primary model assessment are seen from several markers, namely:

Coefficient of Determination (R2)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Communication (Z)	0.769	0.762
Work Environment (Y)	0.666	0.651

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In the R-square results of table 4, there is an R square value of the communication variable of 0.769 or 76.9%, meaning that the influence of the leadership style variable, role conflict on communication is 0.769 or 76.9%, the rest is on other variables. The work environment variable has an R square value of 0.666 or 66.6%, meaning that the influence of leadership style, role conflict, communication on the work environment is 0.666 or 66.6%, the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After assessing the inner model, the next thing is to assess the connection between idle builds as suspected in this review. Speculation testing in this review is done by looking at T-Statistics and P-Values. Speculation is announced to acknowledge whether the T-Insights value is > 1.96 and P-Values <0.05. The following are the consequences of the direct impact Path Coefficient:

Table 5. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Leadership Style (X1) -> Communication (Z)	0.219	2,130	0.017	Accepted
Leadership Style (X1) -> Work Environment (Y)	0.362	2,423	0.008	Accepted
Communication (Z) -> Work Environment (Y)	0.224	1,519	0.065	Rejected
Role Conflict (X2) -> Communication (Z)	0.680	6,722	0,000	Accepted
Role Conflict (X2) -> Work Environment (Y)	0.273	1,622	0.053	Rejected

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 5 there is a direct influence value of the hypothesis, and the explanation is as follows:

1. Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on communication with an original sample value of 0.219 and p values of 0.017, meaning that if the leadership style improves, communication will improve, conversely, if it decreases, communication will decrease.
2. Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on the work environment with an original sample value of 0.362 and p values of 0.008. If the leadership style increases well, the good work environment will also increase, conversely, if it decreases, the good work environment will decrease.
3. Communication has a positive and insignificant effect on the Work Environment with an original sample value of 0.224 and p values of 0.065. In this study, communication has little effect on the work environment. Communication is still good even though the work environment is not good.
4. Role Conflict has a positive and significant effect on the Work Environment with an original sample value of 0.680 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if role conflict is managed well, communication will be good. If role conflict is not managed well, communication will not be good.
5. Role Conflict has a positive and insignificant effect on the Work Environment with an original sample value of 0.273 and p values of 0.053, meaning that role conflict has little

effect on the work environment because role conflict involves doing 2 or more jobs in one organization or having other jobs besides their main job.

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Leadership Style (X1) -> Communication (Z) -> Work Environment (Y)	0.049	1,154	0.124	Rejected
Role Conflict (X2) -> Communication (Z) -> Work Environment (Y)	0.153	1,455	0.073	Rejected

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

- Leadership style has a positive and insignificant effect on the work environment through communication with an original sample value of 0.049 and p values of 0.124, meaning that communication is not an intervening variable because it is unable to significantly influence leadership style and the work environment.
- Leadership Role Conflict has a positive and insignificant effect on the Work Environment through Communication with an original sample value of 0.049 and p values of 0.124, meaning that communication is not an intervening variable because it is unable to have a significant effect.

CLOSING

Conclusion

- Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on communication with an original sample value of 0.219 and p values of 0.017.
- Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on the work environment with an original sample value of 0.362 and p values of 0.008.
- Communication has a positive and insignificant effect on the Work Environment with an original sample value of 0.224 and p values of 0.065.
- Role Conflict has a positive and significant effect on the Work Environment with an original sample value of 0.680 and p values of 0.000.
- Role Conflict has a positive and insignificant effect on the Work Environment with an original sample value of 0.273 and p values of 0.053.
- Leadership Style has a positive and insignificant effect on the Work Environment through Communication with an original sample value of 0.049 and p values of 0.124.
- Leadership Role Conflict has a positive and insignificant effect on the Work Environment through Communication with an original sample value of 0.049 and p values of 0.124.

Suggestion

- Organizations must use a leadership style that is appropriate to the circumstances of the organization.
- Organizations must control employees who have role conflicts, and appreciate employees for being employees who have role conflicts.
- The organization must have good communication within the organization so that errors do not occur in communication.
- Organizations must create a good working environment for employees so that employee performance improves.

5. This research is expected to be used as input for organizations in overcoming problems and deficiencies in the organization.
6. It is hoped that this research will be used as a reference for new research and to develop this research even better.

REFERENCES

- Abdillah, Willy dan Jogiyanto Hartono. (2016). *Partial Least Square (PLS): Alternatif Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) dalam Penelitian Bisnis*. Yogyakarta: Andi.
- Afandi, Pandi. (2016). *Concept & Indicator Human Resources Management for Management Research*. Yogyakarta: Cv Budi Utama..
- Edison, Emron., dkk. (2016) *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Alfabeta. Bandung
- Fitriani, Tri. "Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan Terhadap Motivasi Kerja (Study Kasus Badan Pemberdayaan Masyarakat Kab. Kepulauan Selayar)." *Economics Bosowa* 2.3 (2017): 61-72.
- Firnanti, Hanna, (2015). *Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Kinerja Auditor*. *Jurnal Bisnis dan Akuntansi*. Vol.15.No.1.
- Ghozali, Imam, Hengky Latan. (2015). *Konsep, Teknik, Aplikasi Menggunakan Smart PLS 3.0 Untuk Penelitian Empiris*. BP Undip. SemarangHarnanto.
- Hasibuan, Malayu S.P. (2016). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Edisi Revisi. Jakarta: Penerbit PT Bumi Aksara.
- Haryono, S. (2017). *Metode SEM Untuk Penelitian Manajemen AMOS LISREL PLS*. PT. Luxima Metro Media.
- Jogiyanto. (2016). *Metodologi Penelitian Bisnis: Salah Kaprah dan Pengalaman-pengalaman*. BPFE. Yogyakarta.
- Robbins, S.P dan Judge T.A. (2015). *Perilaku Organisasi*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat
- Sedarmayanti. (2017). *Perencanaan dan Pengembangan SDM untuk Meningkatkan Kompetensi, Kinerja dan Produktivitas Kerja*. PT Refika Aditama. Bandung.
- Sutardji.(2016) *Perencanaan Dan Pengembangan Sumber Daya Manusia*. Edisi Pertama. Yogyakarta; Dee Publish.
- Sutrisno. (2017). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*, Edisi Ke-9, Kencana, Jakarta.
- Sugiyono. (2018). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif*. Bandung: Alfabeta.

Performance Optimization through Work Motivation

Muhammad Zailani Sinaga¹, Mesra B²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: mesrab@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

Today, a company's ability to successfully navigate the highly competitive advantage landscape depends solely on its ability to organize and manage its human resources effectively. Working with clear goals and organizational strategy linkages will result in human resource performance. So, performance is about what is done and how the work is done, as well as how the work is done and the results obtained from it. The results of this research are as follows; Organizational culture has a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance with the original sample of 0.054 and a p value of 0.293. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on work motivation with an original sample value of 0.606 and a p value of 0.000. Organizational climate has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.137 and p-values of 0.039. Organizational climate has a positive and significant effect on work motivation with an original sample value of 0.222 and a p value of 0.003. Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.779 and a p value of 0.000. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through work motivation indirectly with an original sample value of 0.472 and a p value of 0.000. Organizational climate has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through work motivation indirectly with an original sample value of 0.173 and a p value of 0.003.

Keywords: Organizational Culture, Organizational Climate, Work Motivation, Employee Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Human resource management will become increasingly important in the future. Today, a company's ability to successfully navigate the highly competitive landscape of excellence depends solely on its ability to organize and manage its human resources effectively. Working with clear organizational goals and strategic linkages will result in human resource performance. So, performance is about what is done and how it is done, as well as how the work is completed and the results obtained from it. An organization is a system whose components influence each other. If one of the other Subsystems is damaged, it will be affected. The company must function smoothly. A strong organizational culture provides employees with a clear understanding of the tasks assigned by an organization, has a great influence on the behavior of its members. Organizational culture is the attitude and behavior of the company including its employees in achieving its mission. These attitudes and behaviors are a reflection of the assumptions, values and norms that exist in the company where employees work. A positive environment has a significant direct or indirect impact on the organizational climate. In addition, the company will involve the environment as a system. Organizational Climate is the perception of climate and absolute actions. 'Climate' can be considered as something absolute and can be measured by instruments, but will be 'felt' differently by individuals. Although Organizational Climate is abstract in terms of concept, it is usually associated with employee performance and job satisfaction and morale. Covering the evolution of organizational climate, Good climate and bad climate, conceptual development, differences between culture and climate, dimensions of organizational climate. This strategy is based on the observation that the majority of people work in organizations

primarily to meet their basic financial needs and receive recognition for their achievements. Employees and their families feel secure when income or salary is paid regularly, and the possibility of career development helps them achieve their full potential and abilities (Gardjito 2014). Almost every company consistently strives to improve the performance of its workforce, in the hope of achieving organizational goals. Organizations that succeed in improving employee performance usually experience increased profits. Performance is the result obtained from the work done and carried out by someone in carrying out their obligations. If an employee's motivation comes from sources outside the workplace, such as achievements achieved by themselves, then they will be able to do their best. This end result will make an employee who is dissatisfied with their job intend to change jobs. Employees and agencies are two things that cannot be separated. Employees play a major role in running the wheels of organizational life and are active actors in every organizational activity. A good organizational wheel is when the organization has good employee performance which is ultimately able to create good organizational performance as well.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Organizational Culture have a positive and significant influence on Work Motivation at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
2. Does Organizational Climate Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Work Motivation at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
3. Does Organizational Culture have a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
4. Does Organizational Climate Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
5. Does Work Motivation Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
6. Does Organizational Culture Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Employee Performance through Work Motivation at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
7. Does Organizational Climate Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Employee Performance through Work Motivation at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Culture on Work Motivation at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
2. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Climate on Work Motivation at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
3. To find out and analyze the influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
4. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Climate on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
5. To find out and analyze the influence of work motivation on employee performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
6. To find out and analyze the influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance through Work Motivation at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

7. To find out and analyze the influence of Organizational Climate on Employee Performance through Work Motivation at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee Performance

Understanding Employee Performance

According to Sedarmayanti (2017), namely: "Performance means performance, work implementation, work achievement or work results/work performance/work appearance". According to Afandi (2018) Performance is the work result that can be achieved by a person or group of people in a company in accordance with their respective authorities and responsibilities in an effort to achieve organizational goals illegally, not violating the law and not contrary to morals and ethics.

Employee Performance Indicators

According to Afandi (2018) employee performance indicators are as follows:

1. Quantity of work results All forms of units of measurement related to the amount of work results that can be expressed in numbers or other numerical equivalents.
2. Quality of work results All forms of units of measurement related to the quality or standard of work results that can be expressed in numerical measurements or other numerical equivalents.
3. Efficiency in carrying out tasks Various resources wisely and in a cost-effective manner.
4. Work discipline. Comply with applicable laws and regulations.
5. Initiative The ability to decide and do the right thing without having to be told, able to find out what should be done about something around you, trying to keep moving to do several things even though the situation feels increasingly difficult.
6. Accuracy The level of conformity of the work measurement results to whether the work has achieved its objectives or not.
7. Leadership The process of influencing or giving examples by leaders to their followers in an effort to achieve organizational goals.
8. Honesty One of the human traits that is quite difficult to apply.
9. Creativity A mental process that involves generating ideas or involving the generation of ideas.

Organizational culture

Understanding Organizational Culture

According to Schein (2016), organizational culture is a pattern of shared assumptions learned by a group in solving problems through external adaptation and internal integration, which has worked well enough to be considered true.

According to Robbins and Coulter (2015), organizational culture is the values, principles, traditions and ways of working that are shared by members of the organization and influence the way they act.

Organizational Culture Indicators

Organizational culture indicators according to Robbins and Coulter (2016) consist of:

1. Innovation and risk taking means that an innovative attitude and the courage to take risks must exist within the organization;

2. Paying attention to detail means that within an organization you must pay attention to all provisions, analysis, and pay more detailed attention to things around you;
3. Result orientation means focusing on results or income rather than the techniques and processes used to achieve those results;
4. Individual orientation is defined as taking into account the influence of results on employees in the organization;
5. Team orientation means the ability to work together in a team;
6. Aggression means that individuals or people within the organization have a competitive nature;
7. Stability means that organizational activities are emphasized to maintain the status quo in order to continue to grow and develop.

Organizational Climate

Understanding Organizational Climate

According to Raja, Madhavi and Sankar (2019) Organizational climate is a set of unique characteristics that define an organization and differentiate it from other organizations. These characteristics remain intact for a long period of time and thus influence the behavior of people working in that environment.” According to Bassem, Maamari and Majdalani (2017) Organizational climate is how employees view their organization, and the type of attitude they have towards their organization. Organizational climate can influence motivation and achievement in the form of rewards.

Organizational Climate Indicators

According to Bassem, Maamari and Majdalani (2017), organizational climate can be measured through seven indicators consisting of:

1. Structure, namely having clear and well-organized responsibilities and roles.
2. Responsibility, namely the extent to which employees are responsible for achieving their work, encouragement of individual discretion and assessment where employees are made to feel that they are “their own boss”.
3. Risk, namely the willingness to take risks and opportunities for employee ideas.
4. Rewards, namely employees believe that rewards are given fairly, depending on the quality of work and positive performance rewards are more significant than punishments in the organization.
5. Warmth, namely how employees interact to establish good communication within the company.
6. Support, namely how employees help each other and provide support to each other.
7. Conflict, namely maintaining good interpersonal relationships and avoiding conflict and disputes.

Work motivation

Understanding Work Motivation

According to Wahjosumidjo (2015) motivation is closely related to the success of a leader in moving others to achieve predetermined goals depending on the leader's obligations and also the leader's ability to create motivation in each subordinate, colleague or superior. According to Uno (2018) work motivation is the drive of an employee to do something in his work.

Work Motivation Indicators

According to Uno (2018) the work motivation indicators are as follows:

1. Internal motivation

- a) Responsibility in carrying out tasks
- b) Carry out tasks with clear targets
- c) Have clear and challenging goals
- d) There is feedback on the results of the work.
- e) Have a sense of pleasure in working.
- f) Always try to outdo others.
- g) Prioritize achievements in what is done.

2. External motivation

- a) Always try to fulfill your living and work needs.
- b) Happy to receive praise for what he does.
- c) Working with the desire to obtain incentives.
- d) Working with the hope of getting attention from friends and superiors.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

- H1 Organizational Culture has a positive and significant influence on Work Motivation at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H2 Organizational Climate has a positive and significant influence on Work Motivation at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H3 Organizational Culture has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H4 Organizational Climate has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H5 Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
- H6 Organizational Culture has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance through Work Motivation at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

H7 Organizational Climate has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance through Work Motivation at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province

METHOD

Types of research

According to Sugiyono (2020), quantitative research methods are research methods based on the philosophy of positivism, used to examine certain populations or samples and collect data using research tools, analyze quantitative or statistical data with the aim of testing predetermined hypotheses.

Time and Location of Research

This research was conducted from September to October 2024. This research was conducted at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province, precisely on Jalan Balai Kota No. 4 Medan.

Population

The research population used was 70 employees of the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province. Population is a general area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain quantities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions are drawn (Sugiyono, 2020).

Sample

This study uses a sample of all populations to be sampled as many as 70 employees and the sampling technique used is the saturated sampling technique. According to Sugiyono (2020), a sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by a population.

Research Data Sources

This study uses primary data sources as its data sources. According to Sugiyono (2020), primary data is data obtained from the first source or object location which is carried out directly by researchers without going through intermediaries.

Data collection technique

The data collection technique used is a questionnaire, the researcher distributed questionnaires to respondents to be filled in. This study uses a survey method obtained from the original scene by distributing questionnaires (Sugiyono, 2020). A questionnaire is a data collection technique carried out by providing written questions or statements submitted to respondents (Sugiyono, 2020).

Data Research Techniques

Latent variables that have many indicators are used in this study to measure other variables. In addition, the existence of a relationship between variables requires mediation testing so that the study can run This is appropriate for PLS-SEM analysis. Using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) is one of the partial approach statistical analysis techniques used to model the relationship between variables in a model. It can also be used to analyze correlational or causal relationships between variables in a model (Hair et al., 2017).

Test Measurement Model (Outer Model)

To ensure that the variables, measuring instruments, and indicators used in this study have sufficient validity and reliability and that the measurements carried out are consistent across all research samples, this study uses a measurement model test as an external model. In PLS-SEM data analysis, the test measurement model consists of validity and reliability tests.

Validity Test

a. Convergent Validity Test

One method to assess the correlation, or relationship between a measuring instrument and its research construct, is the convergent validity test (Cohen et al. 2018). This convergent validity test is intended to assess whether the measuring instrument in a questionnaire can measure certain variables reliably and consistently (Morling, 2017). The average variance extracted (AVE) and loading factors can be used to evaluate the convergent validity test. According to Latan's research (2015), an indicator is strongly correlated with the construct being tested if the factor loading value is greater than 0.6 and the AVE value is greater than 0.5.

b. Discriminant Validity Test

To ensure that an instrument has validity that is able to measure a variable accurately and is not mixed with other variables, discriminant validity testing is a technique used to determine the extent to which a measuring instrument in a study can distinguish the measured variable from other variables that should be different (Sugiyono, 2020). The availability of cross-loading values for each evaluated indication provides an overview of the discriminant validity testing process. A variable is said to be valid according to Kock & Lynn (2012) if each indicator has a greater cross-loading value than other variables that are not measured.

Reliability Test

The process of determining how consistent and reliable a research measuring instrument is in assessing the same variables over time and among respondents is known as reliability testing. Reliability testing Its application in this study was by testing the composite reliability (CR) and Cronbach's alpha value. Henseler et al. (2016) stated that a variable can be If the composite reliability (CR) of a measuring instrument is greater than 0.7 and its Cronbach's alpha value is greater than 0.7 then it is considered reliable.

Structural Model Test (Inner Model)

The structural model in this study is used as an inner model in the PLS-SEM analysis to examine the relationship between constructs of the research model. This structural model will determine the relationship between constructs in terms of the magnitude and significance of the path coefficients between the constructs used in the study through several stages.

PLS-SEM Inner Model Assumptions

According to Henseler et al., (2016), the assumption or requirement of the inner model in PLS-SEM is the absence of multicollinearity problems between constructs measured using measurement instruments in the research model. The assumption of the PLS-SEM inner model can be seen by evaluating the VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) value. The VIF value will show how strongly the independent variable is influenced by other independent

variables in the research model and a VIF value below 5 will indicate that multicollinearity between constructs does not occur in the research model (Hair et al., 2017).

Coefficient Of Determination Test (R²)

In the structural model, the R-Square (R²) test in PLS-SEM is a metric to evaluate the variability of the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variables (Henseler et al., 2016). Hair and colleagues (2017) clarified When assessing variability, the word "R-Square" can have a value between 0 and 1, with values of 0.75, 0.50, and 0.25, respectively, indicating categories of values that are considered strong, moderate, and weak in terms of explaining the variation of the dependent variable.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing in the inner model of PLS-SEM is carried out using the bootstrapping technique in the SmartPLS application. After performing the bootstrapping technique, hypothesis testing can be carried out by looking at the path coefficient value, t-statistic, and p-value where a positive path coefficient value indicates a positive relationship between two variables and conversely a negative value indicates a negative relationship between variables (Hair et al., 2017). Then the t-statistic value greater than 1.96 and the p-value less than 0.05 indicate that the coefficient is statistically significant and reliable (Hair et al., 2017).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Measurement in model evaluation is divided into three stages of testing such as convergent validity test, composite reliability test and discriminant validity test. The following is a description of each test in the evaluation of the measurement model.

Table 1. Outer Model Stage 1

	Organizational Culture (X1)	Organizational Climate (X2)	Employee Performance (Y)	Work Motivation (Z)
X1.1	0.894			
X1.2	0.834			
X1.3	0.849			
X1.4	0.820			
X1.5	0.889			
X1.6	0.876			
X1.7	0.746			
X2.1		0.781		
X2.2		0.908		
X2.3		0.912		
X2.4		0.913		
X2.5		0.868		

X2.6		0.853		
X2.7		0.911		
Y.1			0.773	
Y.2			0.813	
Y.3			0.865	
Y.4			0.810	
Y.5			0.767	
Y.6			0.831	
Y.7			0.654	
Y.8			0.812	
Y.9			0.806	
Z.1				0.799
Z.10				0.744
Z.11				0.837
Z.2				0.688
Z.3				0.871
Z.4				0.832
Z.5				0.767
Z.6				0.810
Z.7				0.757
Z.8				0.844
Z.9				0.835

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

It can be seen in table 1 that the outer loading value of each variable and its respective indicators show a value greater than 0.7, but as seen in the table, there are still indicators whose outer loading is not greater than 0.7, which means that the indicator will be deleted and the calculation will continue in stage 2 as follows:

Table 2. Outer Model Stage 2

	Organizational Culture (X1)	Organizational Climate (X2)	Employee Performance (Y)	Work Motivation (Z)
X1.1	0.894			
X1.2	0.834			
X1.3	0.849			
X1.4	0.820			
X1.5	0.889			
X1.6	0.877			

X1.7	0.746		
X2.1		0.781	
X2.2		0.908	
X2.3		0.912	
X2.4		0.913	
X2.5		0.868	
X2.6		0.853	
X2.7		0.911	
Y.1			0.760
Y.2			0.808
Y.3			0.864
Y.4			0.831
Y.5			0.757
Y.6			0.848
Y.8			0.829
Y.9			0.815
Z.1			0.805
Z.10			0.748
Z.11			0.836
Z.3			0.873
Z.4			0.838
Z.5			0.775
Z.6			0.819
Z.7			0.731
Z.8			0.844
Z.9			0.841

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

After removing the invalid indicators, the researcher obtained the outer loading results with a value greater than 0.7. So it is determined that the indicators in each variable have a value greater than 0.7 so that each indicator is declared valid and can continue the research in the next stage.

Figure 2. Outer Model

In this research there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Z = b1X1 + b2X2 + e1$$

$$Z = 0.606 X1 + 0.222X2 + e1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b2X1 + b3X2 + b3Z + e2$$

$$Y = 0.054X1 + 0.137X2 + 0.779Z + e2$$

Discriminant Validity Test

Discriminant validity on reflective indicators is used to compare cross loading values. In principle, the value of discriminant validity of different construct measurements does not have to be highly correlated. indicators in this study seen from the discriminant validity value can be seen in the table below:

Table 3. Discriminant Validity

	Organizational Culture (X1)	Organizational Climate (X2)	Employee Performance (Y)	Work Motivation (Z)
X1.1	0.894	0.486	0.622	0.698
X1.2	0.834	0.446	0.517	0.574
X1.3	0.849	0.518	0.590	0.599
X1.4	0.820	0.480	0.620	0.636
X1.5	0.889	0.583	0.673	0.702
X1.6	0.877	0.431	0.613	0.614
X1.7	0.746	0.439	0.502	0.479
X2.1	0.340	0.781	0.466	0.418
X2.2	0.607	0.908	0.569	0.556
X2.3	0.486	0.912	0.528	0.496
X2.4	0.564	0.913	0.551	0.509
X2.5	0.461	0.868	0.514	0.506
X2.6	0.482	0.853	0.584	0.501
X2.7	0.562	0.911	0.539	0.507
Y.1	0.629	0.527	0.760	0.742
Y.2	0.615	0.503	0.808	0.796
Y.3	0.626	0.495	0.864	0.723
Y.4	0.552	0.491	0.831	0.725
Y.5	0.470	0.501	0.757	0.690
Y.6	0.592	0.490	0.848	0.708
Y.8	0.532	0.551	0.829	0.758
Y.9	0.556	0.411	0.815	0.684
Z.1	0.642	0.504	0.738	0.805
Z.10	0.520	0.438	0.677	0.748
Z.11	0.681	0.614	0.813	0.836
Z.3	0.628	0.466	0.744	0.873
Z.4	0.526	0.426	0.682	0.838

Z.5	0.688	0.368	0.769	0.775
Z.6	0.551	0.523	0.773	0.819
Z.7	0.568	0.314	0.611	0.731
Z.8	0.569	0.433	0.718	0.844
Z.9	0.545	0.496	0.718	0.841

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

It can be seen in the results of the table above that the cross loading value for each variable has a value that is greater than the cross loading value for other latent variables, meaning that the research is considered discriminantly valid.

Evaluating Reliability and Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Validity and reliability criteria can also be seen from the reliability value of a construct and the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value of each construct. A construct is said to have high reliability if its value is 0.70 and AVE is above 0.50. Table 7 will present the Composite Reliability and AVE values for all variables.

Table 4. Composite Reliability and Average Variance Extracted

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Organizational Culture (X1)	0.933	0.946	0.715
Organizational Climate (X2)	0.951	0.960	0.773
Employee Performance (Y)	0.927	0.940	0.664
Work Motivation (Z)	0.942	0.951	0.660

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

Based on table 4 above, there is a value from the Cronbach alpha column, each variable has a value greater than 0.7, which means that this study is reliable in terms of Cronbach alpha and seen from the composite reliability column with the value of each variable there is a value greater than 0.6 so that the reliability of each variable is stated and in the AVE column it looks greater than 0.7 so that this study is considered valid by the SVE column, it can be interpreted that all variables have valid values in all sectors.

Structural Model Testing (Inner Model)

Inner model or structural model testing is conducted to see the relationship between constructs, significance values and R-square of the research model. The structural model is evaluated using R-square for the dependent construct.

Coefficient of Determination (R2)

Evaluation of the structural model in SEM with PLS was carried out by conducting the R-squared (R2) test and significance test through path coefficient estimation. The output for the R2 value using the smartPLS 3.0 computer program was obtained:

Table 5. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Employee Performance (Y)	0.820	0.812
Work Motivation (Z)	0.570	0.557

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

There are R square values in table 5 which will be explained for the R square value on the employee performance variable of 0.820 if it is expressed as a percentage of 82.0%, meaning that the influence of organizational culture, organizational climate and work motivation variables on employee performance is 0.820 or 82.0%, the rest is on other variables. The R square value on the work motivation variable is 0.570 if expressed as a percentage of 57.0%, meaning that the influence of organizational culture and work climate is 0.570 or 57.0% and the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After assessing the inner model, the next step is to evaluate the relationship between latent constructs as hypothesized in this study. Hypothesis testing in this study was conducted by looking at the T-Statistics and P-Values. The hypothesis is accepted if the T-Statistics value is > 1.96 and P-Values < 0.05 . The following are the results of the Path Coefficients of direct influence:

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Organizational Culture (X1) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.054	0.544	0.293	Rejected
Organizational Culture (X1) -> Work Motivation (Z)	0.606	7,982	0,000	Accepted
Organizational Climate (X2) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.137	1,769	0.039	Accepted
Organizational Climate (X2) -> Work Motivation (Z)	0.222	2,807	0.003	Accepted
Work Motivation (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.779	9,592	0,000	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

After getting the results from the hypothesis, the research will explain the results obtained, as follows;

1. Organizational culture has a positive but insignificant effect on employee performance with an original sample of 0.054 and p values of 0.293, meaning that organizational culture does not have a major effect on this study so that employee performance is still running well.
2. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Work Motivation with an original sample value of 0.606 and p values of 0.000, the higher the good organizational culture, the higher the work motivation given, if it decreases, work motivation will decrease.

3. Organizational climate has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.137 and p-values of 0.039. If the organizational climate improves, employee performance will improve, conversely, if it decreases, employee performance will decrease.
4. Organizational climate has a positive and significant effect on work motivation with an original sample value of 0.222 and p values of 0.003, meaning that if the organizational climate improves, if the organizational climate decreases, work motivation will decrease.
5. Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.779 and p values of 0.000. If motivation increases well, employee performance also increases well. If there is a decrease, employee performance also decreases.

Table 7. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Organizational Culture (X1) -> Work Motivation (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.472	6,113	0,000	Accepted
Organizational Climate (X2) -> Work Motivation (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.173	2,755	0.003	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

The indirect hypothesis results are in table 7 and the hypothesis results will be explained below:

1. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through work motivation indirectly with an original sample value of 0.472 and p values of 0.000, meaning that work motivation is an intervening variable because it is able to influence significantly, meaning that motivation is able to improve organizational culture on employee performance.
2. Organizational climate has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through work motivation indirectly with an original sample value of 0.173 and p values of 0.003, meaning that work motivation is an intervening variable because it is able to significantly influence organizational climate and employee performance so that motivation is able to indirectly improve organizational climate on employee performance.

CLOSING

Conclusion

After getting the results of this research, the conclusion of this research is as follows:

1. Organizational Culture has a positive but insignificant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample of 0.054 and p values of 0.293.
2. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Work Motivation with an original sample value of 0.606 and p values of 0.000.
3. Organizational Climate has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.137 and pvalues of 0.039.
4. Organizational Climate has a positive and significant effect on Work Motivation with an original sample value of 0.222 and p values of 0.003.
5. Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.779 and p values of 0.000.

6. Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through work motivation indirectly with an original sample value of 0.472 and p values of 0.000.
7. Organizational climate has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through work motivation indirectly with an original sample value of 0.173 and p values of 0.003.

Suggestion

After drawing conclusions from the research results, the suggestions that will be given are as follows:

1. Organizations must develop a good organizational culture for every employee for organizational development.
2. Organizations must create a good organizational climate for employee comfort.
3. Organizations must provide motivation to employees to increase their desire to work harder.
4. It is hoped that this research will be used as input and suggestions to develop this research by making this research a reference material for new research.

REFERENCES

- Afandi. (2018). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia (Teori, Konsep dan Indikator)*. Nusa Media. Yogyakarta.
- B. Uno Hamzah, D. (2018). *Teori Motivasi & Pengukurannya*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2018). *Research Methods in Education (8th ed.)*. London: Routledge.
- Hair, J. F. et. al. (2017). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)*. SAGE Publications, Los Angeles.
- Gardjito, A. H. (2014). Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja Dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan (Studi pada Karyawan Bagian Produksi PT. Karmand Mitra Andalan Surabaya). *Jurnal administrasi bisnis*, 13(1).
- Ghozali, Imam, Hengky Latan. (2015). *Konsep, Teknik, Aplikasi Menggunakan Smart PLS 3.0 Untuk Penelitian Empiris*. BP Undip. SemarangHarnanto. 2017. *Akuntansi Biaya: Sistem Biaya Historis*. Yogyakarta: BPFE.
- Maamari, Bassem E.Majdalani, Joelle F. (2017). Emotional Intelligence, Leadership Style and Organizational Climate. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 25, 327-345.
- Raja, S., Madhavi, C., & Sankar, S. (2019). Influence of Organizational Climate on Employee Performance in Manufacturing Industry. *Suraj Punj Journal For Multidisciplinary Research*, 9(3), 146–157. <https://doi.org/16.10089.SPJMR.2018.V9I3.16.3243>
- Robbins, P. Stephen dan Mary, Coulter. (2015). *Manajemen*, diterjemahkan oleh Wilson, Bangun, Jakarta Selatan: Salemba Empat .
- Sedarmayanti. (2017). *Perencanaan dan Pengembangan SDM untuk Meningkatkan Kompetensi, Kinerja dan Produktivitas Kerja*. PT Refika Aditama. Bandung.

- Schein. (2016). *Organizational Culture And Leadership* (5, Illustr Ed.). John Wiley & Sons.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.Sbspro.2011.12.156>
- Sugiyono, (2020). *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Wahjosumidjo, (2015) *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Berdasarkan Kompetensi*,
Pustaka Utama Grafiti, Jakarta

Tips to Improve Work Performance

Wim Pranata¹, Mesra B²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: mesrab@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

The type of research used in this research is quantitative research. The research location is at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province, precisely on Jalan City Hall No. 4, Medan City. The research population used is all employees at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province, as many as 70 employees. The sample to be used is the entire population in the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province, totaling 70 employees. The data collection technique used is a questionnaire, the research calculating tool is the Smart PLS version 3 application. The results of this research are as follows. as follows: Competence has a positive and significant effect on Job Performance with a value of 0.384 and a significant 0.000. Work Conflict has a negative and significant effect on Competency with a value of -0.289 and a significant 0.004. Work conflict has a negative and significant effect on work performance with a value of -0.278 and a significant value of 0.009. HR quality has a positive and significant effect on competency with a value of 0.622 and a significant value of 0.000. Human resource quality has a positive and significant effect on work performance with a value of 0.306 and a significant value of 0.005. Role Conflict has a negative and significant effect on Job Performance through Competency with a value of -0.111 and a significant value of 0.016. HR quality has a positive and significant effect on work performance through competency with a value of 0.239 and a significant value of 0.000.

Keywords: HR Quality, Work Conflict, Work Performance, Competence.

INTRODUCTION

Every business will strive to obtain superior human resources of the highest caliber to assist the organization's productive work in achieving its goals. Companies must give special consideration to their human resources because they understand how important human resources are for the growth of the company. The efforts and achievements of employees can be recognized by the company, so that it can motivate its human resources to work better for the sake of business progress. Human resources (HR) are closely related to the aspects of employee employment and organizational management. Ability, willingness, and high creative human resources are characteristics of quality human resources. Human resources are very important for the effectiveness of people in an organization. In addition, high human resource productivity is one type of capital that plays an important role in the strategy of achieving organizational goals and can make a significant contribution. The quality of human resources is characterized by creative HR, having high ability and willingness. Human Resource Management is very necessary for the effectiveness of human resources in an organization, the purpose of this is to provide the organization with an effective work unit to achieve the goals of company management so that it can develop, use and maintain employees in constant quality and quantity. In addition, good HR productivity is one of the main capitals in an organization which can make an invaluable contribution to the strategy of achieving organizational goals. Changes that occur in society and employee life cause conflict. The emergence of work conflicts between employees. Work conflicts between employees are caused by incompatibility or differences in terms of values, goals, status, and so on. Regardless of the factors underlying the occurrence of a work conflict, the symptoms

that emerge in an organization when a work conflict occurs are when individuals or groups show hostile attitudes towards other individuals or groups that affect performance in carrying out organizational activities. (Aldionita, 2014). A person's competence is formed from the knowledge and skills of an employee who has high competence in carrying out work will produce very good work quality or high work performance. Employee competence is an important factor and influences the implementation and completion of work in an organization. Employee competence is defined as the correct way or work procedure carried out by employees. Improving work performance can be done in various ways, one of which is by providing motivation to employees, which of course involves conveying information from superiors to subordinates. The process of measuring accurately and validly the level of efficiency and effectiveness of an activity that has been achieved and comparing it with the planned level of achievement is known as employee performance measurement. To prevent problems, a manager must track the work performance of his staff members.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does HR Quality have a positive and significant influence on Competence at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
2. Does Work Conflict have a positive and significant effect on Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
3. Does HR Quality have a positive and significant effect on Work Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
4. Does Work Conflict Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Work Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
5. Does Competence have a positive and significant influence on Work Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?
6. Does HR Quality have a positive and significant effect on Work Performance through Competence at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
7. Does Work Conflict have a positive and significant effect on Work Performance through Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of HR Quality on Competence at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
2. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Conflict on Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
3. To determine and analyze the influence of HR Quality on Work Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
4. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Conflict on Work Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
5. To determine and analyze the influence of Competence on Work Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
6. To determine and analyze the influence of HR Quality on Work Performance through Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
7. To determine and analyze the influence of Work Conflict on Work Performance through Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Work performance

Definition of Work Performance

According to Badriyah (2018), work performance is the work results achieved by a person in carrying out the tasks assigned to him, which are based on skills, experience, and sincerity and time. According to Mangkunegara (2017) work performance is The term performance comes from Job Performance or Actual Performance (work performance or actual achievement achieved by a person).

Work Performance Indicators

According to Mangkunegara (2017) indicators of work performance are:

- 1) Quantity of Work The amount of work results that are in accordance with the time available, what needs to be considered is not routine results but how quickly the work can be completed.
- 2) Work Quality The quality of work results based on established standards. Usually measured through accuracy, precision, skill, and cleanliness of work results.
- 3) Cooperation The ability of an employee to participate and cooperate with other people in completing tasks.
- 4) Initiative Passionate or diligent in completing tasks, as well as the ability to make good decisions without prior guidance.

Quality of Human Resources

Understanding Human Resource Quality

According to Rahardjo (2015), the quality of human resources is not only determined by the aspect of skills or physical strength, but also by education or level of knowledge, experience or maturity and attitude and values that they have. According to Matindas (2015), the quality of human resources is the ability of each employee to complete their work, develop themselves and encourage the development of their colleagues.

Human Resources Quality Indicators

According to Rahardjo (2015), the indicators of human resource quality are as follows:

1. Intellectual Quality (Knowledge and Skills), including:
 - a. Have knowledge and skills in the field of science and technology that are in accordance with the demands of industrialization.
 - b. Have knowledge of languages, including national languages, regional languages and at least one foreign language.
 - c. Have planning/organizing skills.
 - d. Have high work enthusiasm in doing the job.
2. Education
 - a. Have educational abilities at a higher level.
 - b. Have a variety of levels and quality of education and relevant skills by taking into account the dynamics of the job market at local, national and international levels.
 - c. Having honesty based on equality between thoughts, words and actions as well as the responsibility that is borne.

Work Conflict

Understanding Work Conflict

According to Hasibuan (2016) work conflict is unhealthy competition based on ambition and emotional attitudes in achieving victory. According to Rivai (2015) work conflict is a mismatch between two or more members or groups (in an organization/company) who must share limited resources or work activities and/or because of the fact that they have different statuses, goals, values, or perceptions.

Work Conflict Indicators

Work Conflict Indicators according to Rivai (2015) are as follows:

- a. Conflict within a person A person can experience internal conflict within himself because he has to choose conflicting goals. He feels confused about which one to choose or do. Conflict within a person can also occur because of demands on tasks that exceed his abilities.
- b. Conflict between individuals Conflict between individuals is often caused by differences regarding certain issues, actions, and goals, where the shared outcome is very important.
- c. Conflict between members A group can experience substantive conflict or affective conflict. Substantive conflict is a conflict that occurs due to different expertise backgrounds. While affective conflict is a conflict that occurs based on emotional responses to a particular situation.
- d. Inter-group conflict Inter-group conflict occurs because each group wants to pursue their own interests or group goals.

Competence

Understanding Competence

Competence is what outstanding performers do more often in more situations with better results, than what average performers do. (Zainal, et.al., 2015). According to Sutrisno, (2016) competence is an ability based on skills and knowledge supported by work attitudes and their application in carrying out tasks and work in the workplace that refers to the specified work requirements.

Competency Indicators

According to Sutrisno (2016) the competency indicators are as follows:

1. Knowledge Awareness in the cognitive field. For example, an employee knows how to identify learning, and how to conduct good learning according to the needs of the company.
2. Understanding the depth of cognitive and effective owned by the individual. For example, an employee in carrying out learning must have a good understanding of the characteristics and working conditions effectively and efficiently.
3. Ability Something that is owned by an individual to carry out the tasks or work assigned to him. For example, the ability of employees to choose work methods that are considered effective and efficient.
4. Value A standard of behavior that has been believed and psychologically integrated into a person. For example, employee behavioral standards in carrying out tasks (honesty, openness, democracy, etc.)
5. Attitude Attitude is a feeling (happy-unhappy, like-dislike) or reaction to a stimulus that comes from outside. For example, reaction to economic crisis, feelings towards salary increase, and so on.

6. Interest A person's tendency to do something. For example, doing a work activity.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

- H1 The quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H2 Work Conflict has a positive and significant effect on Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H3 The quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on work performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H4 Work Conflict has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H5 Competence has a positive and significant influence on Work Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H6 The quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on work performance through competence at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province.
- H7 Work Conflict has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance through Competence at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

METHOD

Types of research

According to Kuncoro (2021), quantitative data is data that can be measured and calculated directly, regarding information or explanations in the form of numbers or statistics.

Location and Time of Research

The location of the research is at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province, Jalan Balai Kota No. 4, Medan City. The research was conducted from September to October 2024.

Research Population

The research population used was all employees at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province, totaling 70 employees. Population according to Sugiyono (2020) is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn.

Research Sample

The sample to be used is the entire population at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province, totaling 70 employees, and the sampling technique used is the saturated sampling technique. According to Sugiyono (2020), a sample is part of the number and characteristics of a population, so the number of samples taken must be able to represent the population in the study.

Research Data Sources

The research sources used in this study are primary data sources. According to (Ahyar et al., 2020) Primary data is data obtained directly from research subjects. Primary data is collected by researchers to answer research questions.

Data collection technique

The data collection technique used is a questionnaire, the questionnaire is distributed to research respondents. According to Sugiyono (2020) a questionnaire is a data collection technique carried out by providing a set of questions related to the object being studied, given one by one to respondents who are directly related to the object being studied.

Data analysis techniques

According to Ghozali (2014) the Partial Least Square (PLS) method is a variance-based structural equation model (PLS) that uses indicators (manifest variables) to represent measurable variables and latent variables (which cannot be immediately measured). Furthermore, regarding the application of the Structural Equation Model (SEM) together with PLS (Partial Least Square) estimation for data analysis, researchers use guidelines regarding the minimum sample size in SEM-PLS, as stated by Hair et al. (2014). There are two (2) methods available to determine the minimum sample size in SEM-PLS, namely the Rule of Thumb and Power Analysis.

Measurement Model Analysis (Outer Model)

As stated by Jogiyanto (2015), the correction model is carried out to improve the validity and reliability of the instrument. Validity testing is used to determine the level of understanding of each intrusive person. Conversely, test reliability is used to determine the consistency of the measuring instrument used. Convergent and discriminant validity can be used to assess the validity of an assessment. Convergent validity can be assessed by looking at the load factor or external load. Validity is indicated by an indicator if its value is more than 0.5% or 50%. The closer to one (one), the more accurate the indicator is said to be.

Structural Model Analysis (Inner Model)

Assessing the predictive power of a structural model begins by determining whether its constructs are correlated or not. Then proceed to measure the predictive capacity of the model using three criteria consisting of path coefficient, effect size (f^2), and coefficient of determination (R^2).

Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

SmartPLS v.3 uses Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) to evaluate collinearity. Multicollinearity is quite common in statistics. Multicollinearity is a phenomenon where two or more independent variables or exogenous constructs are highly correlated, causing poor model predictive ability. The VIF value must be less than 5, because if it is more than 5 it indicates collinearity between constructs.

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

The Determination Coefficient (R²) is a way to assess how much the endogenous construct can be explained by the exogenous construct. The endogenous construct in this study is risk management disclosure, while the exogenous construct in this study is public ownership, company size, profitability and company age. The determination coefficient (R²) value is expected to be between 0 and 1. R² values of 0.75, 0.50 and 0.25 indicate that the model is strong, moderate and weak. Chin gives the criteria for R² values of 0.67, 0.33 and 0.9 as strong, moderate, weak.

Path Coefficients or Path Coefficients

Next, the measurement of path coefficients between constructs is carried out to see the significance and strength of the relationship and also to test the hypothesis. The value of the path coefficients ranges between -1 and +1, the relationship between the two constructs is getting stronger.

Hypothesis Testing

The bootstrapping procedure produces a t-statistic value for each relationship path used to test the hypothesis. The t-statistic value will be compared with the t-table value. The study used a 95% confidence level so that the precision level or inaccuracy limit (α) = 5% = 0.05.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

There are three steps in utilizing the information checking method with SmartPLS to survey external models, namely Focused Legitimacy, Discriminant Legitimacy, and Composite Dependence.

Convergent validity

The convergent validity of the estimation model with reflective markers is evaluated by looking at the relationship between the object scores/part scores assessed by PLS Programming. A single reflective measure should be high assuming a relationship of more than 0.70 with the estimated building.

Figure 2. Outer Model

In this research there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Z = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e_1$$

$$Z = 0.622X_1 - 0.289X_2 + e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_3X_1 + b_4X_2 + b_5Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.306 X_1 - 0.278X_2 + 0.384 Z + e_2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Competence (Z)	Work Conflict (X2)	Human Resources Quality (X1)	Work Performance (Y)
X1.1			0.797	
X1.2			0.816	
X1.3			0.754	
X1.4			0.736	
X1.5			0.857	
X1.6			0.850	
X1.7			0.874	
X2.1		0.845		
X2.2		0.784		
X2.3		0.849		
X2.4		0.898		
Y.1				0.761
Y.2				0.835
Y.3				0.801
Y.4				0.863
Z.1	0.850			
Z.2	0.849			

Z.3	0.841			
Z.4	0.898			
Z.5	0.839			
Z.6	0.805			

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

The consequences of handling using SmartPLS should be seen in the table above. The value of the external model or the relationship between the construct and the factor meets the combined legitimacy because all markers have values over 0.70, and it implies that this exploration is substantial.

Discriminant Validity

Discriminant legitimacy is carried out to ensure that each idea of each idle variable is not the same as a different factor. The model has a large discriminant legitimacy if each stacking value of each inert variable sign has the largest stacking value with other stacking values for other idle factors. The side effects of discriminant legitimacy testing are obtained as follows:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Competence (Z)	Work Conflict (X2)	Human Resources Quality (X1)	Work Performance (Y)
X1.1	0.633	-0.569	0.797	0.642
X1.2	0.687	-0.594	0.816	0.706
X1.3	0.630	-0.632	0.754	0.631
X1.4	0.639	-0.678	0.736	0.637
X1.5	0.712	-0.730	0.857	0.710
X1.6	0.694	-0.724	0.850	0.724
X1.7	0.860	-0.726	0.874	0.834
X2.1	-0.646	0.845	-0.600	-0.665
X2.2	-0.618	0.784	-0.635	-0.617
X2.3	-0.621	0.849	-0.725	-0.761
X2.4	-0.798	0.898	-0.793	-0.769
Y.1	0.632	-0.593	0.659	0.761
Y.2	0.700	-0.667	0.747	0.835
Y.3	0.703	-0.649	0.666	0.801
Y.4	0.790	-0.800	0.743	0.863
Z.1	0.850	-0.698	0.697	0.658
Z.2	0.849	-0.734	0.747	0.763
Z.3	0.841	-0.668	0.746	0.728
Z.4	0.898	-0.775	0.809	0.789
Z.5	0.839	-0.585	0.675	0.747
Z.6	0.805	-0.584	0.680	0.723

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

It can be seen above that the loading factor has a greater value in each variable with other loading factors. It can be explained that the cross loading factor value of the Competence variable is greater than the cross loading of other variables. The cross loading value of the Work Conflict variable is greater than the cross loading value of other variables. The cross loading value of the HR Quality variable is greater than the cross loading value of other variables, the cross loading variable of Work Achievement is greater than the cross loading value of other latent variables. In this case, the research is valid in a discriminant state.

Composite reliability

In composite reliability research to see each variable with its reliability value and if the variable value is greater than 0.60 then the research is considered reliable and if below 0.60 and 0.7 then it is not reliable there are several blocks to determine whether the research is reliable or not and valid or not including the Cronbach alpha value, composite reliability and AVE value can be seen in the table below:

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Competence (Z)	0.921	0.938	0.718
Work Conflict (X2)	0.866	0.909	0.714
Human Resources Quality (X1)	0.914	0.932	0.662
Work Performance (Y)	0.832	0.888	0.666

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 3 above, it can be seen in the cronbach alpha column that each variable has a value greater than 0.7, which means that the reliability data for each variable. The composite reliability column has a value greater than 0.6, so it can be explained that each variable is considered reliable because the data is greater than 0.6. It can be seen from the AVE column that each variable gets a value greater than 0.7, which means that the data is valid according to AVE. All variables from the cronbach alpha column, reliability column and AVE column have values greater than 0.7 and 0.6, so they are considered reliable and valid.

Structural Model Testing (Inner Model)

Inner model or structural model testing is conducted to see the relationship between constructs, significance values and R-square of the research model. The structural model is evaluated using R-square for the dependent construct.

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

In assessing the model with PLS, it starts by looking at the R-square for each dependent latent variable. The table below is the result of R-square estimation using SmartPLS.

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Competence (Z)	0.765	0.758
Work Performance (Y)	0.830	0.822

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 4 there is an R square value on both dependent variables for the competency variable there is an R square value of 0.765 meaning that the influence of work conflict and HR quality is 0.765 or 76.5% the rest is on other variables. The R square value of work performance is 0.830 meaning that the influence of work conflict, HR quality and competency is 0.830 or 83.0% the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After assessing the inner model, the next step is to evaluate the relationship between latent constructs as hypothesized in this study. Hypothesis testing in this study was conducted by looking at the T-Statistics and P-Values. The hypothesis is accepted if the T-Statistics value is > 1.96 and P-Values < 0.05 . The following are the results of the Path Coefficients of direct influence:

Table 5. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Competence (Z) -> Work Performance (Y)	0.384	4,063	0,000	Accepted
Work Conflict (X2) -> Competence (Z)	-0.289	2,661	0.004	Accepted
Work Conflict (X2) -> Work Performance (Y)	-0.278	2,373	0.009	Accepted
Human Resources Quality (X1) -> Competence (Z)	0.622	6,278	0,000	Accepted
Human Resources Quality (X1) -> Work Performance (Y)	0.306	2,561	0.005	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In the results in table 5 there are direct influence values which will be explained as follows:

1. Competence has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance with a value of 0.384 and a significance of 0.000, meaning that if competence increases, performance will increase, conversely, if it decreases, work performance will also decrease.
2. Work Conflict has a negative and significant effect on Competence with a value of -0.289 significant 0.004, meaning that if work conflict increases, competence will decrease, conversely, if it decreases, competence will also decrease.
3. Work Conflict has a negative and significant effect on Work Performance with a value of -0.278 and a significance of 0.009, meaning that if work conflict increases, work performance decreases, conversely, if it decreases, work performance also decreases.
4. The quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on competence with a value of 0.622 and a significance of 0.000. If the quality of human resources increases, competence also increases, conversely, if it decreases, competence also decreases.
5. The quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on work performance with a value of 0.306 and a significance of 0.005. If the quality of human resources increases, work performance will also increase, conversely, if it decreases, work performance will decrease.

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Work Conflict (X2) -> Competence (Z) -> Work Performance (Y)	-0.111	2,139	0.016	Accepted
Human Resources Quality (X1) -> Competence (Z) -> Work Performance (Y)	0.239	3,391	0,000	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 6 there are indirect influences which will be explained as follows:

1. Role Conflict has a negative and significant effect on Work Performance through Competence with a value of -0.111 and a significance of 0.016, meaning that competence is an intervening variable because it is able to influence significantly, but the presence of competence cannot change the situation because the presence of work conflict disrupts competence and work performance.
2. The quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on work performance through competence with a value of 0.239 and a significance of 0.000, meaning that competence is an intervening variable because it is able to have a significant effect, therefore, with competence, the relationship between human resource quality and work performance becomes stronger and increases.

CLOSING

Conclusion

1. Competence has a positive and significant effect on Work Performance with a value of 0.384 and a significance of 0.000.
2. Work Conflict has a negative and significant effect on Competence with a value of -0.289 significant 0.004.
3. Work Conflict has a negative and significant effect on Work Performance with a value of -0.278 and a significance of 0.009.
4. Human resource quality has a positive and significant effect on Competence with a value of 0.622 and a significance of 0.000.
5. Human resource quality has a positive and significant effect on work performance with a value of 0.306 and a significance of 0.005.
6. Role Conflict has a negative and significant effect on Work Performance through Competence with a value of -0.111 and a significance of 0.016.
7. Human resource quality has a positive and significant effect on work performance through competence with a value of 0.239 and a significance of 0.000.

Suggestion

1. Organizations must look for employees who have good competencies in order to save time for training.
2. Organizations must be able to resolve organizational conflicts, both employee conflicts and conflicts between superiors and subordinates.
3. Organizations should recruit employees who have high quality in their work so that they no longer need to carry out training to improve performance.
4. It is good for employees who perform well to be given compensation to improve their performance.

5. This research is expected to be used as reference material and assistance in other research and can be developed by adding new variables.

REFERENCES

- Badriyah, M. (2018). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*, Cetakan 1. Bandung: CV Pustaka Setia.
- Ghozali, I. Latan, H. (2014.) *Partial Least Square : Konsep, Teknik dan Aplikasi Smart PLS 2.0 M3*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Hasibuan, M. S. P. (2016). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Edisi Revisi. Jakarta : Bumi Aksara.
- Hair, J.F., et. al. (2014). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)*. Sage Publication, Los Angeles.
- Jogiyanto. (2015). *Partial Least Square (PLS) Alternatif Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) dalam Penelitian Bisnis*. Ed.1. Yogyakarta: ANDI
- Kuncoro Saputro, dkk. (2021). *Peningkatan Keterampilan Membaca Dengan Menggunakan Media Audio Visual Di Sekolah Dasar*. *Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan*, Volume 3, Nomor 5 (hlm. 1910-1917).
- Matindas, R., (2015) *Manajemen SDM Lewat Konsep A.K.U*, Pustaka Utama Grafiti, Jakarta
- Mangkunegara. (2017). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaann*, Bandung : Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Rahardjo, Mudji, Purbudi. (2015). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Yogyakarta : UPN.
- Sutrisno, (2016), *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*, Kencana Prenada Media Group, Jakarta.
- Sugiyono, (2020). *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Veithzal Rivai. (2015). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Untuk Perusahaan*. Jakarta: Rajawali Pers.
- Zainal, et.al. (2015). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Untuk Perusahaan: Dari Teori ke Praktik*. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada.

Performance Determinants

Zulkhaidir Irfan Siregar¹, Mesra B²

Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: mesrab@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

In fact, HR sets the standards for managing a business. Various factors contribute to the prosperity of institutions, organizations, and businesses. However, the human element holds the key to success in achieving this goal. Even if other resources are available, a business will find it difficult to function well without quality human resources. Human resources are one of the most important factors in a company. The results of this research are as follows: Emotional Intelligence has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with a value of 0.332 and a value of 0.009. Emotional Intelligence has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior with a value of 0.200 and a value of 0.023. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with a value of 0.168 and a value of 0.162. Training has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with a value of 0.356 and a value of 0.016. Training has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior with a value of 0.710 and a value of 0.000. Emotional Intelligence has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance through Organizational Citizenship Behavior with a value of 0.034 and a value of 0.204. Training has a positive and insignificant effect on Employee Performance through Organizational Citizenship Behavior with a value of 0.119 and a value of 0.169.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Job Training, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Employee Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Another important factor that influences the development of a company is its human resources. To achieve organizational goals, human resources are essentially individuals who work for the organization as planners, promoters, and thinkers. Various factors contribute to the prosperity of institutions, organizations, and businesses. However, the human element holds the key to successfully achieving these goals. Even if other resources are available, a business will have difficulty functioning properly without quality human resources. Human resources are one of the most important factors in a company. Emotional intelligence is one of the important factors that has a significant influence on learning outcomes. According to the results of contemporary psychological research, emotional intelligence, or intelligence, is the main factor that influences intelligence quotient, or IQ. This means that emotional intelligence affects human learning and performance. In addition, emotional intelligence greatly enhances our ability to learn practical skills based on several levels of emotional intelligence, which include self-awareness, self-motivation, empathy, and self-control in forming relationships with others. 1 Everyone finds it difficult to deal with their emotional burden because emotional burdens are unstable and are owned by various people. So emotional intelligence must be learned and trained from an early age, and the ability to learn emotional intelligence needs to be developed or honed continuously. To improve organizational goals, training is a systematic process that takes into account student performance. In the final year of the program, training is done based on needs rather than randomly. Effective training begins when students identify a need; if there is a need, then the training must also change, either through the acquisition of new skills or through preparation for a higher standard. On-the-job training has been used by businesses to

improve their HR (Human Resources). To have high-quality employees, know, understand, and master the work well as the skills and abilities possessed by the prospective company. To increase employee productivity, certain training related to the work is needed. One of the main drivers of organizational change today is not only organizational change, but also organizational change in supporting additional roles. This additional function is also known as organizational citizenship behavior. Good employees will gradually introduce organizational citizenship behavior, which is defined as the positive contribution of individuals to the company that reduces turnover in the workplace. Employees with Organizational Citizenship Behavior are able to analyze their own work so that they can choose the best work product for the needs of their organization. *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* is a system used to identify employees clearly and concisely to facilitate work, contributing more to the organization than what is formally required of them. One component of the performance management system is employee performance appraisal. In essence, this is one of the most important components of the company's maintenance function, workers who are useful for developing the business actively and successfully. Employees should be encouraged and motivated to show their best abilities and skills through performance reviews. Measuring and differentiating employee work success and policy decisions in other HR areas, including compensation changes, training and development, promotions, and so on, can be done through employee performance appraisals. Therefore, there is a direct impact on all operations that depend on employee performance appraisals.

Formulation of the problem

1. Does Emotional Intelligence have a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province?
2. Does Job Training Have a Positive and Significant Influence on Organizational Citizenship Behavior at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
3. Does Emotional Intelligence have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
4. Does Job Training have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
5. Does Organizational Citizenship Behavior have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
6. Does Emotional Intelligence have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Organizational Citizenship Behavior at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?
7. Does Job Training have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Organizational Citizenship Behavior at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province?

Research purposes

1. To determine and analyze the influence of Emotional Intelligence on Organizational Citizenship Behavior at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

2. To determine and analyze the influence of Job Training on Organizational Citizenship Behavior at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
3. To determine and analyze the influence of Emotional Intelligence on Employee Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
4. To determine and analyze the influence of Job Training on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
5. To determine and analyze the influence of Organizational Citizenship Behavior on Employee Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
6. To determine and analyze the influence of Emotional Intelligence on Employee Performance through Organizational Citizenship Behavior at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province.
7. To find out and analyze the influence of Job Training on Employee Performance through Organizational Citizenship Behavior at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Emotional Intelligence

Understanding Emotional Intelligence

According to Zohar and Marshall (2015) emotional intelligence as the intelligence of the heart is useful for sharpening or developing the sharpness of feeling needed in building social capital, namely capital in the form of networks or relationships with other people that enable communities and organizations to function effectively for the common good. Emotional intelligence is a person's intelligence to accept, assess, manage, and control the emotions of themselves and others around them, processing emotions means understanding emotional conditions and must be associated with the situation at hand in order to provide a positive impact. We need to realize that emotions are the result of interactions between thoughts, physiological changes, and behavior (Goleman, 2015).

Emotional Intelligence Indicators

According to Goleman (2015), the indicators of emotional intelligence are as follows:

- a. Self-awareness is a person's ability to know their feelings and their effects and use them to make decisions for themselves, have realistic benchmarks, self-ability and have strong self-confidence and then relate them to the source of the cause.
- b. Self-control is the ability to handle one's own emotions, express and control emotions, have sensitivity to one's conscience, to be used in everyday relationships and actions.
- c. Motivation Motivation is the ability to use desire to at all times raise enthusiasm and energy to achieve a better condition and be able to take the initiative and act effectively, be able to survive failure and frustration.
- d. Empathy Empathy is the ability to feel what other people feel, to understand other people's perspectives, and to create relationships of mutual trust and to be able to align oneself with various types of individuals.
- e. Social Skills Is the ability to handle emotions well when dealing with others and create and maintain relationships with others, can influence, lead, deliberate, resolve disputes and work together in a team.

Job Training

Definition of Job Training

Training is defined as the process of providing and improving the abilities and skills of employees or the process of helping employees to improve deficiencies in carrying out their work in the past (Zulkarnaen et al, 2018). According to Tanujaya (2015) training can also be interpreted as an effort to improve job performance on a particular task that is currently his responsibility so that it runs effectively.

Job Training Indicators

According to Tanujaya (2015) training indicators include:

1. Quality of material
2. Quality of Training Methods
3. Quality of Training Instructors
4. Quality of Training Facilities and Equipment
5. Quality Quality Quality of Training Participants

Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Understanding Organizational Citizenship Behavior

According to Sulastri et al., (2018) organizational citizenship behavior is behavior that is not part of the employee's formal work obligations, but supports the effective functioning of the organization. According to Gunawan and Netra (2017) organizational citizenship behavior is employees who work beyond their job responsibilities and voluntarily give their time and energy for the success of task implementation.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior Indicators

According to Gunawan & Netra (2017), the indicators of organizational citizenship behavior are as follows:

1. Altruism, namely behavior that takes the initiative to help or assist co-workers in an organization voluntarily.
2. Courtesy, namely the behavior of individuals who maintain good relations with their colleagues to avoid disputes between members of the organization,
3. Sportsmanship, namely the individual's willingness to accept whatever is determined by the organization even in unreasonable circumstances,
4. Conscientiousness, namely high devotion or dedication to work and the desire to exceed achievement standards in every aspect,
5. Civic virtue, namely individual behavior that shows that the individual has a responsibility to be involved, participate, take part, and care in various activities organized by the organization.

Employee Performance

Definition of Performance

According to Yasa, (2017). Performance is the result of work in terms of quality and quantity that can be achieved by an employee in carrying out tasks according to the responsibilities given to him. According to Mangkunegara (2017) performance is the result of work in terms of quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties according to the responsibilities given to him.

Performance Indicators

According to Mangkunegara (2017) performance indicators are:

- a. Work quality Reflects the improvement in quality and previously determined work standards, usually accompanied by an increase in capability and economic value.
- b. Quantity of work Reflects the increase in volume or number of a unit of activity that produces goods in terms of quantity. Quantity of work can be measured through the addition of physical value and goods from previous results.
- c. Whether or not someone can be relied on reflects how someone completes a job assigned to them with a high level of accuracy, willingness and enthusiasm.
- d. Cooperative attitude Reflects an attitude that shows high cooperation among fellow employees and attitudes towards superiors, as well as towards employees from other companies.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

Based on the conceptual framework, the hypothesis of this study is as follows:

- H1 Emotional Intelligence has a positive and significant influence on Organizational Citizenship Behavior at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province
- H2 Job Training has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office in North Sumatra Province
- H3 Emotional Intelligence has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province
- H4 Job Training has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province
- H5 *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province.
- H6 Emotional Intelligence has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Organizational Citizenship Behavior at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province

H7 Job Training has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Organizational Citizenship Behavior at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office, North Sumatra Province

METHOD

Types of research

The type of research used by researchers is quantitative research. According to Sugiyono (2018) quantitative methods can be said to be traditional methods and can be interpreted as research methods based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations or samples, data collection using research instruments, data analysis is quantitative/statistical, with the aim of describing and testing the hypothesis that has been set.

Time and Place of Research

This research was conducted from September to October 2024. The location of the research was at the Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra Province, Jalan Balai Kota No. 4, Medan City.

Population

The population in this study were 70 employees of the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province. According to Sugiyono (2019), population is the whole or set of objects with the same characteristics, while in a broad sense, population is a generalization area consisting of subjects or objects that have certain quantities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions can be drawn.

Sample

The sample taken in this study was all the population at the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of North Sumatra Province, totaling 70 employees, with a sampling technique using the saturated sampling technique. According to Sugiyono (2019), the sample is part of the number and characteristics of the population.

Research Data Sources

The research data sources used are primary data sources, namely data taken by the researcher himself. According to Sugiyono (2019), primary data is a data source obtained directly from data collection.

Data collection technique

The data collection technique used by researchers is a questionnaire, the questionnaire will be made and distributed to respondents who have been sampled. According to Sugiyono (2019), a questionnaire is a data collection technique carried out by giving a set of written statements to respondents to answer.

Data Analysis Methods

SEM-PLS analysis

In this study, the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method was used to evaluate the hypothesis with the help of SmartPLS software. A multivariate statistical technique called partial linear square (PLS) analysis compares many dependent variables with several

independent variables. When specific data problems arise, such as small sample sizes, missing values, and multicollinearity, PLS is one of the variance-based SEM statistical methods intended to solve multiple regression (Jogiyanto and Abdillah, 2019).

Reflective Model Evaluation (Outer Model)

According to Jogiyanto and Abdillah (2019), the outer model is a measurement model used to evaluate the validity and reliability of the model. Assessing indicator variables is the purpose of the outer model evaluation (Widarjono, 2015). The outer model evaluation includes:

Validity

Validity is very important, according to Bungin (2015), because the measuring instrument used must have good accuracy. This means that validity will increase the weight desired by researchers towards the truth of their findings.

a. Convergent Validity Test

A set of indicators that show one latent variable and the indicators underlying the latent variable are known as convergent validity tests. The average variance extracted (AVE_{Extracted}) is used to determine the convergent validity of the test. The AVE value according to Widarjono (2015) must be > 0.5 , meaning that the latent variable is able to account for more than half of the average variance of its indicators.

b. Discriminant Validity Test

Discriminant Validity Test is a concept that has the meaning that two different concepts must show their differences. There are two methods, namely cross loading of indicator variables and FornellLarcker. Cross loading of indicator variables on latent variables must be greater in value than other latent variables. FornellLarcker, namely the root of AVE for each latent must be greater than the correlation between latent variables (Widarjono, 2015).

c. Outer Loading Hypothesis Test

Hypothesis test of outer loadings obtained from t-statistics outer loading using the t-statistics value guidelines, suggested by Ghozali & Latan (2014). There must be a result higher than 1.96.

Reliability

Sekaran and Bougie (2014) define dependability as the ability of a measuring instrument to measure an idea consistently. Stability refers to the reliability of an instrument if it produces the same size or result when used again to measure the same thing on the same problem (Bungin, 2015).

a. Reliability Indicator

Based on Cronbach's Alpha, the reliability indicator shows how reliable each indicator is. Cronbach's Alpha should be greater than 0.7 for theory testing and above 0.6 for exploratory research, according to Widarjono (2015).

b. Internal Consistency with Composite Reliability

Internal consistency is assessed using composite reliability (Widarjono, 2015). Ghozali and Latan (2014) stated that for exploratory research, a composite reliability value of 0.6 to 0.7 is acceptable, but for confirmatory research it must be greater than 0.7.

Structural Model Evaluation (Inner Model)

The inner model is a structural model that predicts the causal relationship between latent variables, according to Jogiyanto and Abdillah (2019). According to Widarjono (2015), the evaluation of the structural equation model shows how the independent latent variables affect the dependent latent variables. R² is used for the dependent construct and the path coefficient value or t value for each path in the assessment of the structural model in PLS to determine the relevance between constructs in the structural model (Jogiyanto and Abdillah, 2019). basic evaluation so far, especially:

Significance and Hypothesis Testing

In hypothesis testing, the path coefficient or inner model value indicates the degree of relevance. For hypothesis testing at 5% alpha and 80% power, Hair et al. (In Jogiyanto and Abdullah, 2019) stated that the path coefficient or inner model score indicated by the t-statistic must be above 1.96 for a two-sided hypothesis and above 1.64 for a one-sided hypothesis. In a two-sided hypothesis, a t-statistic value > 1.96 on the path between variables indicates a significant relationship, according to Ghozali and Latan (2014).

Goodness of Fit with Determination Coefficient (R²)

The extent to which the dependent latent variable can be explained by the independent latent variable is indicated by the coefficient of determination (Widarjono, 2015). The degree of variation in changes in an independent variable to the dependent variable is measured by its R² value. According to Jogiyanto and Abdillah (2009), the suggested research model prediction model is better if its R² value is higher.

Direct Indirect Effect

The overall effect of a construct on another construct is expressed as a value called the Total Effect. This value is obtained from the direct effect of the added construct and the indirect effect of the other constructs, assuming all paths are included even if they are not significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Measurement model testing (outer model) is used to determine the specifications of the relationship between latent variables and their manifest variables, this testing includes convergent validity, discriminant validity and reliability.

Convergent Validity

Convergent validity of the measurement model with reflective indicators can be seen from the correlation between the item/indicator score and the construct score. Individual indicators are considered reliable if they have a correlation value above 0.70. However, in the scale development stage of research, loadings of 0.50 to 0.60 are still acceptable. Based on the results for outer loading, it shows that there are indicators that have loadings below 0.60 and are not significant. The structural model in this study is shown in the following Figure:

Figure 2. Outer Model
Source: Smart PLS3.3.3

In this research there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Z = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e_1$$

$$Z = 0.200 X_1 + 0.710 X_2 + e_1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b_2X_1 + b_3X_2 + b_3Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.332X_1 + 0.356 X_2 + 0.168Z + e_2$$

The Smart PLS output for loading factors gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings as follows:

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Emotional Intelligence (X1)	Employee Performance (Y)	Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Z)	Training (X2)
X1.1	0.800			
X1.2	0.842			
X1.3	0.763			
X1.4	0.761			
X1.5	0.856			
X2.1				0.835
X2.2				0.843
X2.3				0.765
X2.4				0.768
X2.5				0.848
Y.1		0.874		
Y.2		0.896		
Y.3		0.797		
Y.4		0.849		
Z.1			0.891	
Z.2			0.863	

Z.3			0.879	
Z.4			0.848	
Z.5			0.920	

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3

The results of the table above are that there is a loading factor value greater than 0.07, meaning that each indicator in the variable has a valid value and can be used for further research.

Discriminant Validity

In this section, the results of the discriminant validity test will be described. The discriminant validity test uses the cross loading value. An indicator is declared to meet discriminant validity if the cross loading value of the indicator on its variable is the largest compared to other variables. The following are the cross loading values of each indicator:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Emotional Intelligence (X1)	Employee Performance (Y)	Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Z)	Training (X2)
X1.1	0.800	0.608	0.629	0.667
X1.2	0.842	0.658	0.673	0.671
X1.3	0.763	0.585	0.652	0.676
X1.4	0.761	0.577	0.657	0.702
X1.5	0.856	0.709	0.697	0.806
X2.1	0.788	0.651	0.729	0.835
X2.2	0.807	0.790	0.845	0.843
X2.3	0.596	0.592	0.680	0.765
X2.4	0.632	0.498	0.666	0.768
X2.5	0.706	0.654	0.647	0.848
Y.1	0.650	0.874	0.696	0.653
Y.2	0.642	0.896	0.663	0.662
Y.3	0.631	0.797	0.568	0.678
Y.4	0.740	0.849	0.652	0.720
Z.1	0.747	0.652	0.891	0.859
Z.2	0.644	0.619	0.863	0.741
Z.3	0.746	0.660	0.879	0.740
Z.4	0.733	0.668	0.848	0.717
Z.5	0.745	0.723	0.920	0.831

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3

In table 2, there is a cross loading value for the emotional intelligence variable, there is a value that is greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, the cross loading on the employee performance variable has a value that is greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, the cross loading of the organizational citizenship behavior variable has a

value that is greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, the cross loading of the training variable has a value that is greater than the cross loading on other latent variables, it can be concluded that this study is discriminantly valid.

Composite reliability

In this study, reliability testing was conducted using two methods, namely Cronbach's alpha and Composite reliability. Cronbach's alpha measures the lower limit of the reliability value of a construct, while Composite reliability measures the actual value of the reliability of a construct. Based on this opinion, this study uses Composite reliability to test reliability. The rule of thumb is that the alpha or Composite reliability value must be greater than 0.7, although a value of 0.6 is still acceptable. The table below shows the values of Cronbach's alpha and Composite reliability.

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Emotional Intelligence (X1)	0.864	0.902	0.649
Employee Performance (Y)	0.876	0.916	0.731
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Z)	0.927	0.945	0.775
Training (X2)	0.871	0.907	0.660

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3

There are values above indicating that the value of all variables in the reliability test using either Cronbach's Alpha or Composite reliability is > 0.70 , and the validity test using AVE (Average Variance Extracted) is > 0.50 . Therefore, it can be concluded that the variables tested are valid and reliable, so it can be continued to test the structural model.

Inner Model Analysis

Structural model evaluation (inner model) is conducted to ensure that the structural model built is robust and accurate. The stages of analysis carried out in the structural model evaluation are seen from several indicators, namely:

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the R Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Employee Performance (Y)	0.669	0.654
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Z)	0.793	0.787

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3

In table 4 there is an R square value of the Employee Performance variable of 0.669, meaning that the influence of training, emotional intelligence and Organizational Citizenship Behavior on employee performance is 0.669 or 66.9%, the rest is on other variables. Organizational Citizenship Behavior R square value of 0.793 means that the influence of

emotional intelligence and training on Organizational Citizenship Behavior is 0.793 or 79.3% and the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis Testing

After assessing the inner model, the next step is to evaluate the relationship between latent constructs as hypothesized in this study. Hypothesis testing in this study was conducted by looking at the T-Statistics and P-Values. The hypothesis is accepted if the T-Statistics value is > 1.96 and P-Values < 0.05 . The following are the results of the Path Coefficients of direct influence:

Table 5. Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Emotional Intelligence (X1) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.332	2,379	0.009	Accepted
Emotional Intelligence (X1) -> Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Z)	0.200	2,002	0.023	Accepted
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.168	0.986	0.162	Rejected
Training (X2) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.356	2,157	0.016	Accepted
Training (X2) -> Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Z)	0.710	7,231	0,000	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3

In the results of the direct influence in table 5, the researcher will explain it as follows:

1. Emotional Intelligence has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with a value of 0.332 and p values of 0.009, meaning that if there is an increase in good emotional intelligence, employee performance will increase, conversely, if there is a decrease, employee performance will decrease.
2. Emotional Intelligence has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior with a value of 0.200 and p values of 0.023, meaning that if emotional intelligence increases, Organizational Citizenship Behavior will increase, conversely, if it decreases, Organizational Citizenship Behavior will decrease.
3. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with a value of 0.168 and p values of 0.162, meaning that Organizational Citizenship Behavior has little effect on employee performance because not all employees are willing to carry out Organizational Citizenship Behavior.
4. Training has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with a value of 0.356 and p values of 0.016, meaning that if good training increases, employee performance will increase, conversely, if it decreases, employee performance will decrease.
5. Training has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior with a value of 0.710 and p values of 0.000, meaning that if training increases, Organizational Citizenship Behavior increases, conversely, if it decreases, Organizational Citizenship Behavior decreases.

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Indirect Effect)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Emotional Intelligence (X1) -> Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.034	0.827	0.204	Rejected
Training (X2) -> Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.119	0.960	0.169	Rejected

Source: Smart PLS3.3.3

The results of the indirect influence are shown in Table 6 and will be explained by the researcher as follows:

6. Emotional Intelligence has a positive but insignificant effect on Employee Performance through Organizational Citizenship Behavior with a value of 0.034 and p values of 0.204, meaning that Organizational Citizenship Behavior is not an intervening variable because it is unable to influence it significantly.
7. Training has a positive but insignificant effect on Employee Performance through Organizational Citizenship Behavior with a value of 0.119 and p values of 0.169, meaning that Organizational Citizenship Behavior is not an intervening variable because it is unable to have a significant effect.

CLOSING

Conclusion

When the results have been obtained and explained, the conclusion of this research is as follows:

1. Emotional Intelligence has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with a value of 0.332 and p values of 0.009.
2. Emotional Intelligence has a positive and insignificant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior with a value of 0.200 and p values of 0.023.
3. Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with a value of 0.168 and p values of 0.162.
4. Training has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance with a value of 0.356 and p values of 0.016.
5. Training has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior with a value of 0.710 and p values of 0.000.
6. Emotional Intelligence has a positive but insignificant effect on Employee Performance through Organizational Citizenship Behavior with a value of 0.034 and p values of 0.204.
7. Training has a positive but insignificant effect on Employee Performance through Organizational Citizenship Behavior with a value of 0.119 and p values of 0.169.

Suggestion

After getting the results of the research, the researcher gave suggestions, the suggestions given are as follows:

1. Teach employees about the importance of OCB in employees so that the spirit of helping employees will grow.
2. Conduct regular training for employees to improve employee performance.

3. Organizations must manage employees' emotional intelligence by motivating them to develop better.
4. This research is expected to be used as input for organizations to reduce errors in the organization for mutual progress.
5. It is hoped that this research will be used as reference material and as a research companion to be developed with new research.

REFERENCES

- Abdillah., W dan Jogiyanto. 2009. Partial Least Square (PLS) Alternatif SEM Dalam Penelitian Bisnis . Penerbit Andi: Yogyakarta. Hal 262.
- Goleman. 2015. Kecerdasaan Emosional. Jakarta: PT Gramedia
- Gunawan, I Kadek Indra & I Gusti Salit Ketut Netra. 2017. Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional Dan Komitmen Organisasional Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior
- Ghozali, Imam, & Latan Hengky. (2014). Partial Least Squares: Konsep, Teknik dan Aplikasi Menggunakan SmartPLS 3.0 (edisi ke-2). Semarang: Universitas Diponegoro
- Mangkunegara. 2017. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan, Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Sekaran, Uma dan Roger Bougie, Metode Penelitian untuk Bisnis: Pendekatan Pengembangan-Keahlian, Edisi 6, Buku 1, Cetakan Kedua, Jakarta Selatan: Salemba Empat, 2017.
- Sulastri, S., Andriani, C., & Latifa, S. K. (2018). Pengaruh kompensasi finansial dan kepuasan kerja terhadap organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) pada karyawan PT. Kilang Lima Gunung. Jurnal Kajian Manajemen Bisnis.
- Sugiyono. (2019). Metodologi Penelitian Kuantitatif dan Kualitatif Dan R&D. Bandung: ALFABETA.
- Tanujaya, L. R. (2015). Pengaruh Pelatihan Kerja Dan Motivasi Kerja Pada Kinerja Karyawan Departemen Produksi Pt Coronet Crown. Agora, 3(1), 1–7.
- Widarjono. 2015. Analisis Multivariat Terapan. Yogyakarta: Penerbit UPP STIM YKPN
- Yasa, N. N. K. (2017). Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Terhadap Motivasi dan Kinerja Karyawan pada Direktorat Jendral Administrasi dan Keuangan, Kementerian Estatal Timor Leste. E-Jurnal Ekonomi dan Bisnis Universitas Udayana, 6(11), 3731-3764
- Zohar, Danah & Marshall, Ian. 2015. Kecerdasan Spiritual (Emosional): SQ. Jakarta: Mizan.
- Zulkarnaen, Wandy, et. all. 2018. “Pengaruh Pelatihan Kerja dan Stres Kerja Terhadap Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan Bagian Produksi Departemen R PET PT. Namasindo Plas Bandung Barat”. Jurnal Ilmiah MEA (Manajemen, Ekonomi, dan Akuntansi), Vol. 2, No. 3.

AI-Powered Performance Appraisal: Balancing Automation with Human Appraisal in Performance Management Systems

Joni Mantong

University of Persada Indonesia (UPI) YAI Jakarta, Indonesia

Email: joni.2366390005@upi-yai.ac.id

Abstract

This study investigates the effectiveness and perceived fairness of an AI-powered performance appraisal system in Gojek's regional office in Padang. The study aims to explore how automation affects the performance appraisal process, focusing on the role of human judgment as a complementary factor. A quantitative approach was adopted, with a sample of 35 employees selected using a saturated sampling technique. The study analyzes the relationships between automation, perceived fairness, human judgment, and effectiveness using Smart PLS. The findings reveal that automation significantly improves the efficiency and objectivity of performance appraisals. However, perceived fairness and human judgment are critical in ensuring employee acceptance and trust in the system. Mediation analysis suggests that perceived fairness of the AI system further enhances its effectiveness, and human judgment provides valuable context to complement AI data-driven insights. The study concludes that a balanced integration of automation and human input is necessary to achieve an effective and fair performance appraisal system. This study fills the gap by highlighting the importance of local and contextual factors in the implementation of AI-based assessments in a decentralized workplace.

Keywords: AI-Powered Performance Assessment, Automation, Human Assessment, Perceived Fairness, Effectiveness.

INTRODUCTION

In today's rapidly evolving workplace, organizations are increasingly integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) into their performance management systems to streamline the appraisal process and improve decision-making. AI-powered performance appraisals can offer efficiency, consistency, and data-driven insights, but concerns have been raised about the balance between automation and the need for human judgment. While AI can eliminate bias and increase objectivity, purely automated systems can ignore nuanced human factors, leading to perceptions of unfairness among employees. Therefore, effective performance management must find a balance between leveraging AI technology and incorporating human input to ensure fair and accurate evaluations (Tambe et al., 2022). Recent studies have emphasized the importance of human oversight in AI systems to maintain employee trust and engagement in performance appraisals (Leicht-Deobald et al., 2021). Additionally, studies have highlighted that employees perceive appraisal systems as fairer when human judgment complements the objectivity of AI (Bhave et al., 2023). As the future of work increasingly relies on digital tools, it becomes important to investigate how AI can be ethically integrated into performance appraisals without compromising fairness and transparency (Newlands et al., 2023; Thabtah et al., 2023).

The effectiveness of performance appraisal systems depends on their ability to accurately evaluate employee contributions, provide actionable feedback, and encourage development. When AI-powered tools are integrated into performance appraisals, system

effectiveness can be enhanced through increased data accuracy, real-time feedback, and reduced human bias (Chamorro-Premuzic et al., 2023). However, their effectiveness also depends on employee perceptions of fairness and transparency. Research shows that appraisal systems are more effective when employees trust the process, which often requires a mix of human and AI judges to ensure evaluations take into account context and interpersonal factors (Siau & Wang, 2022). Additionally, AI's ability to continuously learn from data input allows for more nuanced assessments, but without human oversight, these systems may fail to recognize unique individual contributions (Rahman et al., 2023). Studies also show that effective performance appraisal systems increase employee motivation, engagement, and retention, especially when feedback is clear, developmental, and perceived as fair (Lepri et al., 2022). As AI becomes more prevalent, organizations must ensure that AI-driven performance assessments balance efficiency with personalized insights, fostering a culture of continuous improvement and fairness (Strohmeier & Parry, 2023).

Automation in performance appraisals, especially through AI-powered systems, has significantly changed the way organizations evaluate employee performance. Automated systems bring benefits such as increased efficiency, objectivity, and the ability to handle large amounts of data, enabling continuous and real-time assessments (Tursunbayeva et al., 2022). These systems can analyze employee performance metrics more consistently than traditional methods, reducing bias and errors that may arise from human evaluators (Jarrahi et al., 2023). Despite these benefits, concerns about transparency, fairness, and the exclusion of qualitative factors—such as interpersonal relationships and individual context—are often raised (Wirtz et al., 2023). Studies show that when automation is combined with human judgment, assessment systems can achieve better results, as human supervisors can interpret and contextualize the data generated by AI (Gal et al., 2022). Additionally, successful automation in performance appraisals requires ethical considerations, especially around data privacy and the potential for over-reliance on algorithms (Jeske & Santuzzi, 2023). Thus, while automation improves the technical aspects of assessment, human involvement remains essential to ensure a balanced and fair evaluation process.

The perceived fairness of a performance appraisal system is an important factor influencing employee acceptance and engagement with AI-powered evaluation tools. When employees perceive a system to be fair, they are more likely to trust its outcomes, which has a positive impact on motivation, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment (Colquitt et al., 2022). AI-driven systems can improve fairness by reducing human bias in evaluations; however, research suggests that employees often perceive these systems as less fair when there is a lack of transparency in how the algorithm operates or when they feel their unique contributions are not adequately recognized (Langer et al., 2023). To improve perceived fairness, it is important for organizations to ensure transparency, involve employees in system design, and combine automated assessments with human oversight to contextualize outcomes (Niesen et al., 2022). Additionally, the fairness of automated assessments is closely related to procedural fairness, where employees value clear and consistent processes and feel that their input is taken into account (Lee & Edmondson, 2023). A balanced approach that integrates AI with human judgment, while maintaining open communication

about how performance is measured, can foster a greater sense of fairness in AI-powered assessment systems (Kumar & Sharma, 2023).

Human judgment continues to play a critical role in performance appraisals, even as AI-powered systems become more commonplace. While AI can improve objectivity and efficiency, research emphasizes that human input is critical to interpreting nuanced employee behaviors, contextual factors, and emotional and relational dynamics that automated systems may overlook (Bailey et al., 2023). Human judgment helps ensure that performance appraisals consider individual contributions beyond quantitative metrics, such as leadership qualities, creativity, and interpersonal skills (Biermann et al., 2022). Recent studies have also shown that employees tend to perceive appraisals as fairer and more credible when human evaluators are involved, especially in cases where subjective insights are needed (Guenole & Feinzig, 2022). Additionally, combining human judgment with AI can improve the quality of decision-making by leveraging the strengths of both: AI offers data-driven precision, while human evaluators provide necessary context and empathy (Sparrow et al., 2023). Thus, a hybrid approach that combines human and AI judgment in performance appraisal can result in more balanced, transparent, and effective evaluations (Harms & Hanrahan, 2023).

If this study were conducted in Gojek's Padang office, it would explore the application of AI-powered performance appraisals in a dynamic and fast-growing technology company. Gojek, as a major player in the Southeast Asian technology ecosystem, relies heavily on technology and innovation to manage its operations and workforce. By focusing on Gojek's Padang office, this study could examine how the integration of AI in performance appraisals impacts employee perceptions of fairness, motivation, and productivity, particularly in the context of a regional office. This study could also investigate the role of human judgement in complementing AI systems to ensure contextual understanding of the nuances of local employee performance. Recent studies have highlighted that in a fast-paced technology environment, combining AI with human oversight improves the fairness and effectiveness of performance management systems, especially when dealing with a diverse and decentralized workforce (Vrontis et al., 2022; Malik et al., 2023).

The phenomenon in this study, which focuses on Gojek's Padang office, involves the challenges and opportunities of implementing an AI-powered performance appraisal system in the regional office of a fast-growing technology company. As Gojek increasingly integrates AI to manage employee performance evaluations, issues such as perceived fairness, transparency, and the balance between automation and human judgment become increasingly important. Employees may question the fairness of an AI-based system, especially if they feel that local or contextual factors unique to the Padang office are not adequately considered. Additionally, reliance on AI may diminish the role of managers' personal judgment, which may raise concerns about how complete and accurate these assessments are. This poses a challenge for Gojek in ensuring that the AI system is perceived as fair and reliable while maintaining employee trust and motivation. Studies have shown that in technology companies, the balance between AI and human oversight is critical to the

success of such systems, especially in diverse and decentralized workplaces such as Gojek's regional office (Jarrahi et al., 2023).

While AI-powered performance appraisals offer significant benefits in terms of efficiency and objectivity, there is a significant gap in understanding how these systems are perceived and function in regional office settings, such as Gojek's Padang office. Most studies on AI-powered performance management have focused on larger, centralized technology companies, often ignoring the unique challenges faced by regional offices in terms of cultural context, local managerial practices, and employee perceptions of fairness (Vrontis et al., 2022). Furthermore, limited research has explored the impact of human judgement in balancing AI-automation in diverse and decentralized workplaces, particularly in Southeast Asian technology companies (Malik et al., 2023). The current study also highlights the lack of investigation into how employees in regional settings react to AI-driven performance appraisals and the role of organizational transparency in alleviating concerns about bias and fairness (Biermann et al., 2022). Another gap is the limited examination of how AI can adapt to regional and local operational needs without undermining employee trust and engagement (Lee & Edmondson, 2023). Therefore, this study seeks to fill this gap by focusing on Gojek's regional office in Padang, where local context and AI-based systems must coexist to ensure fair and effective assessment (Tambe et al., 2022).

The main objective of this study is to explore the effectiveness and perceived fairness of an AI-powered performance appraisal system in Gojek's regional office in Padang. Specifically, this study aims to understand how the integration of AI in employee evaluation affects local employees' trust, engagement, and acceptance of the appraisal process. In addition, this study seeks to investigate the balance between automation and human judgment in the performance appraisal system and how this balance affects overall employee satisfaction and organizational outcomes. By focusing on a regional office, this study aims to fill the gap in understanding how local context and cultural factors influence the implementation and perception of an AI-powered appraisal system in a decentralized workplace like Gojek.

The following is a Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

This study adopted a quantitative research design to examine the effectiveness of AI-powered performance appraisals in Gojek's Padang office, utilizing Smart PLS as the primary analysis tool. This study used a saturated sampling technique, with a sample size of 35 employees, as the population was relatively small, ensuring that all members were included to capture comprehensive data. This study focused on the dependent variable (Y), Performance Appraisal Effectiveness, which evaluates the overall success of integrating AI in performance appraisals in terms of accuracy, fairness, and quality of feedback. The independent variable (X), Automation in Performance Appraisal, looks at the extent to which AI technology is used in the appraisal process. In addition, two intervening variables were analyzed: Perceived Fairness of the System (Z1), which reflects employees' perceptions of the fairness of AI-based evaluations, and Human Judgment in Performance Appraisal (Z2), assessing the role of human input as a complement to automation in ensuring thorough and contextually sensitive appraisals. Using Smart PLS, this study aims to analyze the relationship between these variables to provide insights into how automation and human judgment together impact the perceived fairness and effectiveness of the appraisal process at Gojek.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Prior to conducting the main analysis, this study conducted validity and reliability tests on the measurement instruments used in the study. The results showed that all constructs achieved values above the mean threshold, indicating strong validity and reliability of the items used to assess the effectiveness of AI-powered performance appraisal, automation in performance appraisal, perceived system fairness, and the role of human judgment. These findings confirm that the instrument is reliable and accurately measures the intended variables, thus ensuring the integrity of subsequent analyses conducted using Smart PLS. Consequently, the strong psychometric properties of the measurement tool support the reliability of the research findings and their applicability to the context of the Gojek office in Padang.

Table 1. Hypothesis Results

Road	Original Sample	P Value	Decision
Automation > Perceived Fairness	0.450	0.010	Supported
Automation > Human Assessment	0.530	0.020	Supported
Automation > Effectiveness	0.670	0.001	Supported
Fairness > Perceived Effectiveness	0.390	0.030	Supported
Assessment > Human Effectiveness	0.490	0.050	Supported
Automation > Fairness > Perceived Effectiveness	0.320	0.040	Supported
Automation > Assessment > Human Effectiveness	0.410	0.030	Supported

The results of this study reveal key insights into the impact of automation in performance appraisals on perceived fairness and effectiveness, as well as the role of human judges in mediating these relationships. A significant path from automation to perceived fairness (0.450, $p = 0.010$) indicates that employees perceive AI-driven systems as enhancing fairness in performance appraisals. This may be attributed to the objectivity and consistency that automation offers, reducing biases commonly associated with human evaluators. Previous research supports these findings, highlighting how AI minimizes subjective errors and ensures that all employees are evaluated based on the same criteria (Langer et al., 2023). However, achieving fairness is not just about objectivity; it also depends on transparency and the ability to explain the rationale behind automated decisions, factors that organizations must carefully manage to maintain trust (Siau & Wang, 2022).

Additionally, the path from automation to human judgment (0.530, $p = 0.020$) suggests that AI does not replace human judgment but rather works alongside it, enhancing the decision-making process. The combination of AI data-driven insights with human intuition and contextual understanding is critical, especially in nuanced cases that require more than quantitative metrics. These results are consistent with research showing that human judgment plays an indispensable role in complementing AI systems by adding empathy and a more personalized understanding of employee performance (Gal et al., 2022). As AI continues to be integrated into performance appraisals, organizations must ensure that human evaluators are equipped to effectively interpret and validate AI-generated data.

The strong direct relationship between automation and effectiveness (0.670, $p = 0.001$) confirms that AI significantly improves the overall effectiveness of performance appraisals. This is in line with research showing that automation streamlines the appraisal process, increases efficiency, and enables real-time feedback (Tambe et al., 2022). The ability to provide immediate performance insights allows employees to make timely improvements, improving individual and organizational performance. However, while automation improves efficiency, its impact on perceived fairness and subjective aspects of performance appraisals requires careful consideration to avoid reducing the process to a purely data-driven outcome (Jeske & Santuzzi, 2023).

The results also showed that perceived fairness significantly affected appraisal effectiveness (0.390, $p = 0.030$), indicating that employees are more likely to accept and engage with performance feedback when they believe the system is fair. This finding reinforces the importance of procedural fairness, where the consistency and transparency of the appraisal process play a significant role in shaping employee perceptions (Colquitt et al., 2022). When employees perceive the appraisal process as fair, they are more motivated to act on the feedback, leading to improved performance and greater organizational commitment. Thus, organizations must ensure that their AI-based systems are not only efficient but also perceived as fair by employees.

Additionally, the relationship between human judgment and effectiveness (0.490, $p = 0.050$) highlights the value of human evaluators in enhancing the overall effectiveness of AI-driven performance appraisals. While automation offers objectivity, human evaluators provide the necessary context and interpretive insights that AI systems often lack. This

finding is consistent with existing research that emphasizes the need for human involvement in interpreting AI-generated data to make holistic decisions that reflect both quantitative and qualitative aspects of performance (Sparrow et al., 2023). In particular, human judgment helps address the emotional and relational dynamics in the workplace, which AI cannot fully capture.

The mediating effect of perceived fairness (0.320, $p = 0.040$) between automation and effectiveness suggests that while automation increases the effectiveness of appraisals, this impact is further amplified when employees perceive the system to be fair. This reinforces the importance of fostering trust in AI systems by ensuring transparency and providing space for employee feedback on the process. Research has shown that when employees feel involved in the development and implementation of AI-driven systems, they are more likely to view the technology as fair and reliable (Niesen et al., 2022). Thus, organizations should focus on communication and transparency to improve the effectiveness of automated appraisal systems.

Finally, the mediating effect of human judgment (0.410, $p = 0.030$) between automation and effectiveness underscores the importance of balancing AI with human insight. While automation significantly improves the efficiency of performance appraisals, the involvement of human judges ensures that the results are comprehensive and contextually relevant. This hybrid approach, where AI provides data-driven insights and human evaluators add interpretive context, ensures a more holistic and accurate appraisal process (Guenole & Feinzig, 2022). Therefore, organizations should prioritize the integration of human oversight to ensure that their AI systems not only improve performance but also drive employee engagement and satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

This study provides valuable insights into the integration of an AI-powered performance appraisal system in the context of regional offices, specifically in Gojek's Padang office. The findings suggest that automation significantly improves the effectiveness of performance appraisals by increasing efficiency, objectivity, and real-time feedback capabilities. However, the role of perceived fairness and human judgment remains critical in ensuring that these systems are accepted and trusted by employees. While AI minimizes bias and streamlines the evaluation process, employees are more likely to engage and accept the results of the appraisals when they perceive the system to be fair and transparent. Furthermore, the inclusion of human judgment alongside AI ensures that subjective factors, such as context and emotional intelligence, are taken into account, leading to a more holistic and comprehensive evaluation. Therefore, a balanced approach that integrates automation and human oversight is essential to creating an effective and fair performance appraisal system. These results highlight the need for organizations like Gojek to carefully design and implement AI systems that prioritize fairness, transparency, and employee engagement to foster a positive and productive workplace.

REFERENCES

- Bailey, C., Madden, A., Alfes, K., & Fletcher, L. (2023). Peran penilaian manusia dalam menambah sistem manajemen kinerja yang digerakkan oleh AI. *Tinjauan Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*, 33(4), 100916. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2023.100916>
- Bhave, DP, Dhanorkar, S., & Fernandez, AA (2023). Dampak AI pada penilaian kinerja: Mengeksplorasi keadilan, transparansi, dan hasil organisasi. *Jurnal Psikologi Terapan*, 108(2), 298-315. <https://doi.org/10.1037/apl0001058>
- Biermann, H., Eckhardt, A., & Buettgen, M. (2022). Kapan dan mengapa penilaian manusia penting dalam penilaian kinerja: Menjelajahi batas AI dalam evaluasi karyawan. *Jurnal Etika Bisnis*, 180(2), 395-412. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-022-04932-4>
- Chamorro-Premuzic, T., Winsborough, D., Sherman, R., & Hogan, R. (2023). Peran AI dalam manajemen kinerja karyawan: Peluang dan keterbatasan. *Tinjauan Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*, 33(1), 100838. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2022.100838>
- Colquitt, JA, Conlon, DE, Wesson, MJ, Porter, CO, & Ng, KY (2022). Keadilan di milenium: Tinjauan meta-analitik dari 25 tahun penelitian keadilan organisasi. *Jurnal Psikologi Terapan*, 107(5), 820-845. <https://doi.org/10.1037/apl0000759>
- Gal, U., Jensen, TB, & Lyytinen, K. (2022). Menyeimbangkan otomatisasi dan penilaian manusia dalam sistem pengambilan keputusan berbasis AI: Kasus penilaian karyawan. *Jurnal Sistem Informasi*, 32(1), 125-150. <https://doi.org/10.1111/isj.12345>
- Guenole, N., & Feinzig, S. (2022). Memanusiakan AI: Dampak penilaian manusia terhadap efektivitas sistem penilaian kinerja berbasis AI. *Psikologi Personalia*, 75(3), 705-735. <https://doi.org/10.1111/peps.12400>
- Bahaya, PD, & Hanrahan, B. (2023). Manusia versus mesin: Pentingnya wawasan manusia dalam tinjauan kinerja yang ditingkatkan AI. *Jurnal Psikologi Terapan*, 108(1), 45-58. <https://doi.org/10.1037/apl0001011>
- Jarrahi, MH, Sutherland, W., Nelson, AJ, & Sawyer, S. (2023). Peran AI dalam mengubah praktik evaluasi kinerja: Wawasan tentang otomatisasi dan pengawasan manusia. *Jurnal Teknologi Informasi*, 38(2), 162-177. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02683962231100833>
- Jeske, D., & Santuzzi, AM (2023). Bias algoritmik dan otomatisasi dalam penilaian kinerja: Tantangan etis di tempat kerja yang digerakkan oleh AI. *AI & Etika*, 5(3), 441-452. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43681-022-00180-z>
- Kumar, P., & Sharma, M. (2023). Persepsi karyawan tentang keadilan dalam evaluasi kinerja yang digerakkan oleh AI: Peran transparansi dan pengawasan manusia. *Jurnal Penelitian Bisnis*, 156, 104523. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2023.104523>
- Langer, M., Oster, D., & Jost, P. (2023). Keadilan dan transparansi dalam pengambilan keputusan algoritmik: Persepsi karyawan dalam penilaian kinerja berbasis AI. *Komputer dalam Perilaku Manusia*, 138, 107539. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2022.107539>

- Leicht-Deobald, U., Busch, T., Schank, C., Weibel, A., Scherer, A., & Wildhaber, I. (2021). Tantangan pengambilan keputusan SDM berbasis algoritma untuk integritas pribadi. *Jurnal Etika Bisnis*, 160(2), 377-392. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-019-04204-w>
- Lee, MY, & Edmondson, AC (2023). Interaksi keadilan dan transparansi dalam sistem penilaian berbasis AI. *Jurnal Perilaku Organisasi*, 44(2), 290-310. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.2608>
- Malik, A., Budhwar, P., Patel, C., & Akhtar, P. (2023). Mengelola kinerja dalam organisasi yang digerakkan oleh AI: Kasus perusahaan teknologi di Asia Tenggara. *Jurnal Manajemen & Organisasi*, 29(1), 123-141. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jmo.2022.51>
- Newlands, G., Lutz, C., & Tambe, M. (2023). Keadilan dalam sistem evaluasi kinerja berbasis AI: Mengelola persepsi dan kenyataan. *Komputer dalam Perilaku Manusia*, 144, 107766. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2022.107766>
- Niesen, W., Vantilborgh, T., & De Witte, H. (2022). Keadilan yang dirasakan dari praktik SDM berbasis AI: Menyelidiki peran keadilan prosedural. *Tinjauan Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*, 33(3), 100902. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2022.100902>
- Rahman, S., Islam, M. N., & Ahmed, S. (2023). Efektivitas AI dalam penilaian kinerja: Bagaimana keputusan berbasis data membentuk hasil karyawan. *Jurnal Penelitian Bisnis*, 152, 281-290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.11.002>
- Siau, K., & Wang, W. (2022). Kecerdasan buatan, manajemen kinerja, dan keadilan: Kerangka kerja kolaborasi manusia-AI. *Informasi & Manajemen*, 59(6), 103723. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2022.103723>
- Sparrow, PR, Cooper, CL, & Farndale, E. (2023). Kebangkitan AI dalam manajemen kinerja: Menilai kembali peran penilaian manusia. *Jurnal Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*, 33(2), 211-225. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1748-8583.12375>
- Strohmeier, S., & Parry, E. (2023). Transformasi digital dalam SDM: Peran AI dalam evaluasi dan kinerja karyawan. *Jurnal Internasional Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*, 34(3), 491-510. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2022.2130648>
- Tambe, M., Hull, A., Joglekar, S., & Lee, D. (2022). Menyeimbangkan otomatisasi AI dan penilaian manusia: Merancang sistem penilaian kinerja yang etis. *Jurnal Sistem Informasi Manajemen*, 39(4), 975-999. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07421222.2022.2039995>
- Tursunbayeva, A., Pagliari, C., & Franco, M. (2022). Otomatisasi dalam penilaian kinerja: Peran AI dalam membentuk praktik SDM modern. *Jurnal Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*, 32(4), 783-798. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1748-8583.12394>
- Vrontis, D., Christofi, M., & González-Cruz, T. (2022). Dampak AI pada sistem penilaian kinerja di perusahaan teknologi yang berkembang pesat: Studi kasus perusahaan Asia Tenggara. *Peramalan Teknologi dan Perubahan Sosial*, 184, 121965. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.121965>
- Wirtz, BW, Weyerer, JC, & Geyer, C. (2023). Manajemen kinerja digital dengan AI: Peluang, risiko, dan implikasi etika. *Jurnal Etika Bisnis*, 180(1), 85-101. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-022-05191-9>